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SESSION A

The Development of a Digital Teaching Scenario on Climate Change for Blended Learning Environments

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Abstract

Climate change has become the most important environmental and planetary issue of the last decades. For that reason European Union highlights the need for incorporation of Climate Change in the STEM curricula so as to equip students with the necessary knowledge and skills in order to be able to make informed decisions and take informed sociopolitical actions. In the present study, we focus on the presentation of a digital teaching scenario designed to foster a. students' understanding of the basic scientific concepts involved in climate change, b. the development of students' informed decision-making skills and c. the development of students' digital skills. The digital Climate Change teaching scenario has been developed by the Science Teaching Laboratory of the Department of Primary Education of the University of Crete, in the context of the European Erasmus+ project "STEM DIGITALIS", which aims at developing blended and distance learning environments for teaching advanced STEM topics to prospective primary and secondary science teachers. The results of the data analysis will be announced during the conference and are expected to provide us with insights into the way a digital scenario about climate change should be structured for blended learning environments.

Keywords: Climate Change, STEM Education, Blended Learning, Distance Learning, Digital Tools

1. Introduction

During the recent years, the pandemic has influenced humanity and changed citizens' daily lives on different levels. The new conditions also formed new needs in the field of Education. These needs hastened the conversion of courses' format to an online one, a trend that had already begun in previous years. This new educational reality led to another necessity; the development of teachers' digital skills so that they can effectively form virtual learning environments in which students will be actively involved (Baincakova & Bernard, 2020). However, the digital conversion of traditional STEM courses seems to be quite demanding, as, up until now, they were mainly based on the conduction of hands-on and inquiry-based activities, which take place in a classroom or a lab and require specific equipment. Therefore, this shift towards the use of digital learning environments seems to be demanding for STEM teachers (Baincakova & Bernard, 2020).

One approach to form STEM lessons that can support the integration of digital environments is that of Blended Learning. Such courses can combine a variety of pedagogical approaches such as inquiry learning or problem-solving learning (Baeppler et al., 2014). However, research evidence on how to develop and evaluate Blended Learning digital STEM lessons is to the best of our knowledge quite limited (Ibáñez & Delgado-Kloos, 2018). These limitations extend to blended learning environments for STEM topics, such as Climate Change.

Climate change has become one of the most important environmental and planetary issues of the last decades with consequences for all ecosystems and by extension humanity. Counteracting this phenomenon demands the adoption of key policies, active action on behalf of the citizens, advances in science education are necessary, since it contributes to formation of people's personality and structure of society. Through targeted climate education, future citizens can acquire adaptation skills, redefine their lifestyles in order to reduce their ecological footprint, etc. (Leal Filho & Hemstock, 2019; Makrakis, Larios & Kaliantzi, 2012) and can ultimately redefine people's personality and structure of society (Dovros & Makrakis, 2012). That is why, European Union highlights the need for incorporation of Climate Change in the STEM curriculum so as to equip students with the necessary knowledge and skills in order to be able to make informed decisions and take informed sociopolitical actions.

Therefore, based on the above, the aim of this study is the development of blended and distance learning environments for teaching the advanced STEM topic of Climate Change, to prospective science teachers.

2. Climate Change

Climate Change is mainly caused by burning carbon-based fuels. Gases released from this process into the atmosphere cause pollution, which leads to the disruption of natural phenomena like greenhouse effect, which in turn disrupts the planet's ecosystems (Irwin, 2020). From

educational viewpoint the fundamental concepts of Climate Change are the following (Jacobson et al., 2017; Shepardson et al., 2011; McCaffrey et al., 2008):

1. Carbon Cycle & Greenhouse Effect,
2. Different types of radiation,
3. Interaction of gases with radiation,
4. Composition of atmosphere,
5. Climate & Weather,
6. Feedback and
7. Energy.

2.1 Carbon Cycle & Greenhouse Effect

Carbon Cycle & Greenhouse Effect constitute the main mechanisms for global warming that causes climate change. Human progress began to become more intense after the development of industrial production, which has been based exclusively on fossil fuel energy for over two hundred years (Irwin, 2020). According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, it appears that over the past century human activities, have contributed to intensifying greenhouse effect. This is due to the increased concentration of greenhouse gases (e.g., carbon dioxide, methane), which are produced by carbon-based energy economy, in the atmosphere. This increase also causes a rise in the overall temperature of the atmosphere, leading to global warming (Shepardson et al., 2011).

In addition to disrupting greenhouse effect, the ever-increasing concentrations of carbon-based greenhouse gases lead to the deregulation of the natural occurring carbon cycle (Friedlingstein, Dufresne, Cox, & Rayner, 2003). In regards to this cycle generally there is a predetermined amount of carbon on Earth. It alternates between atmosphere, biosphere, soils, oceans and rocks with both natural and anthropogenic sources and sinks of carbon compounds. Fossil fuels contain carbon that was part of living species millions of years ago. The burial process took that carbon out of the atmosphere-ocean-biosphere cycle. Burning fossil fuels for energy returns this carbon to the cycle (Jarrett et al., 2011).

3. STEM Education & New Technologies

The research related to new technologies reveals the potential, that have as tools to enhance teaching and learning in schools, especially in science education (Skinner & Preece 2003). New technologies (digital media, modelling tools, sensor software, etc.) can effectively support teachers' efforts to conduct inquiry-based learning in their classrooms. The appropriate integration of technology can lead students to a deeper conceptual understanding of scientific concepts, as well as encourage them to engage in STEM fields and become familiar with scientific processes necessary for inquiry (Maeng et al., 2013). Indicative digital tools that could be used in a STEM lesson:

Interactive Video. More specifically, the use of interactive video enables users to act on it and access content such as notes or questions (Zhang, et al., 2006; Klefodimos, Lappas & Evangelidis, 2020). Interactive features of a video can be some hotspots that students can click to show notes, quizzes, hyperlinks, etc. For example, quizzes are mainly open-ended

or multiple-choice questions that appear at specific points in time in the video (Klefodimos et al., 2020). Essentially, videos help in better understanding of the content by allowing users – learners to replay the video content whenever they need to. In addition, it enhances participation in the course, as it seems more accessible than the conventional classroom environment (Klefodimos et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2006).

Mobile Application (mobile learning). The learning process based on the use of mobile devices, such as modern mobile phones (smartphones), tablets, etc., is called “Mobile Learning” (Christensen & Knezek, 2017; Burden & Kearney, 2016). This type of learning is characterized by offering opportunity to students to learn from wherever they are, whenever they want, negating the limitations set by space and time (Christensen & Knezek, 2017). As a result, science teachers can design lessons, both inside and outside the school environment, while adopting inquiry approaches (Burden & Kearney, 2016). Using mobile devices, students can access the Internet, communicate, collaborate, collect, present and share information, as well as make audio-visual recording (Christensen & Knezek, 2017; Burden & Kearney, 2016). Essentially, students can imitate the scientists and conduct inquiry processes, such as collecting and analyzing data, observing, sharing results, etc. Mobile learning can support interaction, collaboration, communication and personalized learning (Burden & Kearney, 2016).

Infographics. Infographics are visual representations of complex data and provide the information through an innovative and desirable way. The main difference between Infographics and other visual media, such as photos, is the fact that they can combine in a practical way various elements, such as maps, symbols, videos, etc. to provide information in a clear and simple way. Infographics have been widely used in various fields, one of those fields is education. Students can access information through an alternative way, which differs from the traditional method. Providing information through visual media is one of the most important forms of information presentation (Alqudah, Bin Bidin, & Hussin, 2019). More specifically, as far as science education is concerned, the use of infographics provides motivational, cognitive and communicative benefits for students (Jarman & McClune, 2007).

Game (Gamification). Gamification is the process of incorporating game design elements, such as collecting points, meeting challenges, plotting, etc., into a completely different, non-game context (Bai et al., 2020; Huang & Hew, 2018). Essentially, the result of gamification is that it turns some learning processes into processes that students experience as a game and learn through it (Sailer & Homner, 2019). In this way, students are motivated, enhancing their interest and participation and problem-solving activities can be supported (Huang & Hew, 2018). The aforementioned tools could also be used in the design of Blended Learning (BL) courses.

4. Blended Learning (BL)

Blended Learning is a modern educational approach, which aims to improve learning beyond the traditional teaching environment (Nayar & Koul, 2020). According to

Margulieux et al. (2016), it combines two criteria. The first criterion is the "Delivery Medium", which defines the way that the instruction takes place and can be either "via the instructor", or "via technology". The second criterion is the "Instruction Type", in which students are "receiving content" or "applying content".

From the combination of these criteria, Margulieux et al. (2016) end up with three types of BL. The first type of BL is the "Flipped Blend", which consists of two parts. The first part is "Receiving Content via Technology". For example, an activity that could fit into this part could be studying a video lecture. In the second part of this type, "Applying Content via Instructor" takes place, in which students could conduct an experiment in the laboratory in the presence of the teacher.

The second type of BL is the "Supplemental Blend", which consists of two parts. In the first part, the "Receiving Content via Instructor" takes place, in which a discussion with the teacher about scientific concepts can be included. In the second part, "Applying Content via Technology" takes place. One form of activity could be the processing of a simulation of a phenomenon, where the student will receive feedback from the computer, without the presence of the teacher.

The third type of BL is called "Replacement Blend" and is more flexible than the previous ones. Depending on the needs of the students, it can combine in different way the following elements of instruction:

- "Receiving Content via Instructor",
- "Receiving Content via Technology",
- "Applying Content via Instructor" and
- "Applying Content via Technology".

(Margulieux et al., 2016)

Blended Learning courses can support both the combination of various pedagogical approaches in one course, such as inquiry-based learning and problem-solving learning (Baepler et al., 2014), as well as interdisciplinarity in the classroom, but also the utilization of new technologies (Nortvig et al., 2018). The element of technology utilization in BL courses leads to improved student performance, particularly when technology provides cognitive support (through visualizations, etc.) or facilitates student interaction with peers, content and teacher (Nortvig et al., 2018).

5. Methodology

5.1 Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework of this study is based on the Model of Educational Reconstruction (MER- Model of Educational Reconstruction) (Duit, 2007; Duit, Gropengießer, Kattmann, Komorek, & Parchmann, 2012). The present model has been developed as a theoretical framework for research, in order to examine whether it has any value and whether it is possible to teach specific scientific concepts and principles, as well as views on the nature of science (Stavrou & Duit, 2014).

Fig. 1. Model of Educational Reconstruction
(Duit et al., 2012)

This model consists of three main components, in which there is a close connection and interaction. These are:

1. Clarification and analysis of scientific content. This component includes the clarification of scientific content, scientific processes and views on the nature of science, as well as the analysis of educational significance.
2. Research on teaching and learning. Surveys of students' pre-existing knowledge, interest, attitudes, and behaviours, surveys of teaching and learning processes, and surveys of teachers' perceptions of science concepts, student learning, and their role in the learning process, are included in this component.
3. Design and Evaluation of Teaching and Learning Environments.

This element includes the design of teaching and learning sequences, activities and teaching materials (Duit, 2007; Duit et al., 2012; Stavrou & Duit, 2014).

Essentially, the basic principle of MER is the transformation of scientific content into suitable content for teaching. In the construction of the content to be taught, the students' perceptions, interests and needs should be taken into account. In addition, content should be embedded in a specific context to be meaningful to students (Duit, 2007; Duit et al., 2012).

5.2 Context of the study

The present study is part of the Erasmus plus project titled STEM DIGITALIS (<https://stemdigitalis-project.eu>). The main aim of the STEM DIGITALIS project is to develop blended learning environments for teaching advanced STEM topics (e.g., nanotechnology, climate change, renewable energy, etc.) to prospective primary and secondary science teachers. In order to achieve the aforementioned aim, the five European universities that participate in the consortium (a. University of Crete – Greece, b. Leibniz Universitaet Hannover - Germany, c. Tallinn University – Estonia, d. Dublin City University - Ireland and e. Rijksuniversiteit Groningen – the Netherlands) work on the following outputs:

1. Development of digital STEM teaching scenarios,
2. Development of strategies for teaching advanced STEM topics in blended learning environments,
3. Development of an open educational platform in order to support the teaching of advanced STEM topics in blended learning environments,

4. Development of guidelines and recommendations in order to promote the teaching of advanced STEM topics in blended learning environments.

In particular, the first year of the project, each of the partner universities has focused on a specific STEM topic in order to develop one digital teaching scenario by using a variety of digital tools and forms of digitalization. Specifically, the Science Teaching Laboratory of the Department of Primary Education of the University of Crete developed a digital teaching scenario on Climate Change. The following year, after the implementation of the digital teaching scenarios in the context of an international summer school and online seminars, strategies and guidelines for teaching advanced STEM topics in blended learning environments will be formed.

6. Results

The digital scenario on Climate Change focuses on the one hand on the negotiation of the relationship between temperature and carbon dioxide concentration rise through processing real data while on the other hand students are engaged with the man-made aspects of the phenomenon. In addition, core socio-scientific issues arising from the measures taken to mitigate Climate Change, were included in the scenario as well. Students explore the multiple perspectives of the issue such as European Union policies, non-governmental organizations initiatives etc. and are involved in informed decision-making and action-taking processes. For the digitalization of the aforementioned activities, a variety of tools was used such as a. h5p for interactive videos production, b. html tools for graphics design, c. unity 3D for the development of an adaptive game and d. Radio beacons.

The digital scenario consists of three sections which are briefly presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Structure of digital scenario

SECTION	TOPIC	DIGITAL TOOLS
1 st	To negotiate the relationship between temperature and carbon dioxide concentration rise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational game • Interactive video • Interactive graphs
2 nd	To realize how the anthropogenic activities contribute to Climate Change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobile Application
3 rd	To explore a socioscientific issue and to be involved in informed decision-making and action-taking processes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AR application

The first section aims at interpreting the correlation of temperature and carbon dioxide rise and the role of this correlation for climate change. In the context of this section, a game has been created with the UNITY 3D tool. The main character of the game travels through four different unknown decades, in order to discover the aforementioned correlation. From each decade, he collects data that will help him

complete his mission and form his own conclusions via interactive videos and graphs which are embedded in the game. The interactive video* presents the conducting of an experiment which was carried out in the lab and video-recorded. The video has integrated interactive elements such as questions and notes, which follow the principles of the inquiry approach. In particular, there are questions for predicting the outcome of the experiment, observing the experimental process, interpreting data, etc. The interactive graphs†, which are based on real data, refer to the temperature rise and to the carbon dioxide concentration rise. The graphs are supposed to support students in forming their conclusions regarding the correlation between the variables under examination. The aforementioned tools support students individual work and therefore, in a BL course, they could be part of the “Applying Content via Technology” section.

The second section is related to anthropogenic activities and how they contribute to Climate Change. For the purposes of this section an application was created for mobile devices (smartphones, tablets), which is called “CarbonDigitalis”. With the support of this application, users can calculate their carbon footprint, resulting from their daily transportation and from their household activities. Subsequently, students are also asked to calculate their footprint in case of using renewable energy sources for the aforementioned activities. The purpose is students to realize the difference in the amount of carbon dioxide that is released in atmosphere, in case of using fossil fuels and renewable energy sources, in order to cover their energy needs. In this section, the activities could be part of “Applying Content via Technology” or/and “Receiving Content via Instructor”.

The third section dealing with the socio-scientific issues related to Climate Change takes the form of a "treasure hunt". Students are asked to form an opinion on whether lignite plants should be closed and replaced with wind farms. In order to be able to form their own opinion, they are invited to study the role of various stakeholders that are involved in this issue, such as the European Union, local residents, Non-Governmental Organizations, companies etc. To support this activity, a mobile Augmented Reality (AR) application was used, in order to organize the “treasure hunt”. There are pictures and QR codes. Each picture corresponds to a particular stakeholder and is placed at a specific point in a predefined space. When the students approach this point, they scan the picture and the information regarding each stakeholder’s interests and views are appeared. Afterwards, students are called to form their own opinion on whether lignite plants should be closed and be replaced with wind farms. This section could be formed based on “Replacement Blend”, because the activities have the potential to be receiving or applying content via instructor and via technology.

5. Conclusions

The STEM DIGITALIS project aims at developing digital resources on advanced STEM topics to be used for

* <http://h5p.edthe.edc.uoc.gr/2022/05/27/co2-stemdigitalis/>

† <https://edthe.edc.uoc.gr/climateChange/co2.html>

blended learning. In particular, the features of the developed digital resources on climate change such as interactivity, the integration of inquiry – based learning and the opportunities they offer for personalized learning reveal their potentials for supporting blended learning in STEM education. The main beneficiaries of such digital resources are the prospective primary and secondary science teachers who are expected to improve both their digital competences as well as their understanding of how to integrate digital resources in STEM education. Finally, other beneficiaries of the results of the project are the teacher educators who will be able to use the digital teaching materials and the teaching strategies that are being developed in order to effectively integrate digital technologies and advanced STEM topics into their STEM courses.

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Integrating Citizen Science into Environmental Education for Sustainability. Design and Implementation of an Online Training Course to Foster Participation in Building Sustainable and Just Societies Through School Education

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Abstract

Citizen science aims to engage people with scientific research, empower them as citizens and facilitate their participation in democratic decision-making on local community issues. A large number of citizen science actions in Europe and internationally use Citizen Observatory infrastructures and technologies to engage people in the collection of scientific data and observations on the environment and various environmental problems, thus contributing to the achievement of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Environmental Education (EE), on the other hand, promotes learning processes aimed at fostering values and skills for the democratic participation of young people in shaping their living conditions for a more sustainable future.

This paper argues that developing synergies between citizen science and EE is both feasible and compatible not only because of their many common points of reference but also for the benefit of education and the collective efforts towards sustainability. We outline the framework of principles and practices formulated by the European project Cos4Cloud to support the integration of citizen science into school-based EE and describe the design and implementation of an online teacher training course entitled "Citizen Science and Environmental Education for Sustainability". This course was conceived of, organized, and delivered by the Environmental Education Lab of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, with the collaboration of the project coordinators and other partners within the framework of a strategy for integrating citizen science in school EE which was elaborated by Cos4Cloud. Targeting qualified and highly experienced Greek Environmental Education teachers and other educational stakeholders, this online course sought to introduce participants to citizen science practice and familiarize them with the implementation of innovative educational activities in their schools. More specifically, the participants attended four theoretical modules and then collaboratively designed educational scenarios, the main principle of which was to promote the environmental, scientific, political, and digital literacy of students through activities that make use of the digital platforms and applications of selected Citizen Observatories (COs) participating in the Cos4Cloud project. Finally, we briefly outline the methodological design employed and the different levels of evaluation applied; and we summarize findings from the evaluation data obtained and analyzed based on the experience of the trainees from their participation in the course.

Keywords: environmental education, citizen science, integration into school, online training course, teachers, evaluation, Cos4Cloud

1. Introduction

Citizen Science as a field encompasses a range of activities and practices, the common feature of which is the participation of citizens in scientific research processes. In one of the first attempts to define it, Lewenstein (2004) highlights that citizen science may involve: a) the participation of citizens in scientific processes of data collection, management and interpretation, b) the participation of citizens in decision-making on public issues of a technical or scientific nature, and/or c) the participation of researchers in corresponding democratic processes. All three dimensions pay particular attention to cooperation between amateur (citizen) scientists and professional scientists to jointly investigate issues and questions of a scientific nature. This is also highlighted by the definition provided by the Oxford English Dictionary (2014), according to which, citizen science refers to scientific work undertaken by individuals (citizens) from the general public, usually under the coordination of formal scientists and/or scientific institutions, often with the support of other community stakeholders. In any case, citizen science activities and initiatives serve a wide range of objectives,

often simultaneously, from promoting scientific activity and knowledge to enhancing scientific literacy and research skills, up to encouraging democratic engagement and participation and enabling citizens to participate in advocacy for environmentally more sustainable and just societies (European Commission, 2020).

Citizen science offers new means and opportunities to collect different kinds of data that contribute to science, monitor progress towards sustainability and inform environmental governance (Liu & Kobernus, 2017). This work can be facilitated or coordinated by research infrastructures called Citizen Observatories (COs), i.e. technological platforms that offer a range of tools (such as web portals, smartphone apps, and electronic devices) and support the development of citizen science projects, especially those whose main objective is large-scale citizen participation, or cover wide geographical areas and long periods of time. By digitally connecting citizen science practitioners, COs also enhance their observational and monitoring competencies 'in situ' and enable a bi-directional flow of data and information, by making use of the latest information and communication technologies (ICT) (Grainger, 2017).

Moreover, a large number of citizen science initiatives and projects in Europe and internationally making use of COs platforms engage people in the collection of scientific data and observations on the environment and various sustainability issues, thus actively contributing to both the achievement and assessment of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Woods et al, 2022). Supporting citizen science to increase the reach, quality and quantity of citizen-generated data and promote education, partnership and collective action is for the benefit of more sustainable and just societies. One of the ways this can be achieved is by creating and supporting a network of COs through the development of services and associated measures, which is the main objective of Cos4Cloud (Co-designed citizen observatories for the EOS-Cloud), a European Horizon 2020 project (Cos4Cloud).

Education and learning may not be among the first and explicit goals of citizen science, yet there are many intrinsic links between them (Daskolia et al, 2022). Both education and environmental protection are promoted by several citizen science projects as they are both considered public policy issues (Roche et al., 2020). However, citizen science engagement often involves a range of learning outcomes that go beyond the acquisition of mere content knowledge or skills related to citizen science per se, and they extend from the development of scientific and environmental literacy (Saunders et al., 2018) to the fostering of global citizenship, environmental stewardship and community empowerment.

Environmental Education (EE), on the other hand, promotes learning processes aimed at fostering values and skills for the democratic participation of young people in shaping their living conditions for a more sustainable future. As an educational process and practice that seeks to bring about changes in the environment and society, in individuals and in education itself at the same time (Sauvé, 1994, 2002; Daskolia, 2005), EE is based on and promotes a pedagogy that is not limited to a single renewal of the existing curriculum and its enrichment with sustainability concepts and issues but proposes a holistic reform of teaching and learning ways of thinking and doing, by introducing interactive and student-centered approaches that build on and promote inquiry-based learning and collaboration. Alongside awareness, a core aspect of EE is, therefore, engagement in individual and collective processes of inquiry and learning about global and local environmental and sustainability issues. This is attained not only through the development of key scientific concepts, content knowledge and skills to understand and address current environmental problems but also by prioritizing the nurturing of values and competencies as a prerequisite for democratic participation in more sustainable and just societies (Wals et al, 2014).

There are, therefore, several commonalities between citizen science and environmental education, with responsible and active citizen engagement and informed participation in achieving sustainability being at the core of both (Daskolia et al, 2022). However, synergies between them remain largely unexplored (Wals et al, 2014). Moreover, far fewer citizen science projects and initiatives, according to Dillon et al (2016), support in practice its

transformative potential through authentic citizen engagement with local sustainability issues. What we argue here is that by combining citizen science with EE, the former moves away from its instrumental nature to grow along with more emancipatory practice than its current footprint. Besides, through its incorporation into school curricula the emphasis is placed on teachers and students to build a more comprehensive and critical stance towards current social, economic and environmental reality, such as regarding issues of social inequality, poverty, overconsumption, violence, discrimination and pollution, with a view to revisiting their positions towards them (Vouzaxakis & Makrakis, 2017). The combination of citizen science and EE would eventually lead to a new paradigm of collective practice that actively promotes sustainability justice on the basis of the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy and culture (Makrakis, 2017a). As Makrakis (2017b) argues, environmental justice only occurs if there are effective policies to address these complex issues, and as the four pillars of sustainable development overlap, so do the respective dimensions.

In this paper we outline the framework of principles and practices formulated by the European project Cos4Cloud to support the integration of CS into school-based EE and describe the design and implementation of an online teacher training course entitled "Citizen Science and Environmental Education for Sustainability". This course was conceived of, organized, and delivered by the Environmental Education Lab of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, with the collaboration of the project coordinators and other partners within the framework of a strategy for integrating citizen science in school EE which was elaborated by Cos4Cloud. Targeting qualified and highly experienced Greek EE teachers and other educational stakeholders this course sought to introduce participants to citizen science practice and familiarize them with the implementation of innovative educational activities in their schools. Finally, we present the evaluation methodology and some results from different levels of evaluation we conducted in relation to the design, participation, and experience of teachers in the project.

2. Citizen science and Environmental Education within the Cos4Cloud project

2.1. The Cos4Cloud project: principles and practices

Cos4Cloud (Co-designed citizen observatories for the EOS-Cloud) is a European Horizon 2020 project which aims to enhance citizen science technologies by developing [12 technological services](#) to improve the COs' practice, focusing mainly on the quantity and quality of observations and on the platforms' their long-term sustainability. These are the core challenges of almost all modern COs. The services are being co-designed with key stakeholders and carefully tested with end-users to help improve interoperability, networking, data quality and secure management of data in user-friendly ways in a network of 9 COs and DIY initiatives focusing

on biodiversity and environmental monitoring. When ready, they will become available in the new [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#), a virtual space aimed at the European scientific community, so that anyone interested in creating or improving their CO can have access to them. A wide range of activities have been organized and being realized, thus creating a useful space for collaboration and co-development along the lines of open science, networking, innovation, sustainable practice, quality in research procedures and data, following the FAIR data principles (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) to make the most of the data available from citizen science.

Fifteen European and international partners and ten COs are participating in the project (see Figure 1), working together to create an MVE where COs, technological agencies, citizen science experts validating data and users will be able to establish synergies and build high-quality data in global repositories.

Fig. 1. Partners and citizen observatories participating in the Cos4Cloud project.

2.2. The Cos4Cloud strategy for integrating citizen science into school Environmental Education

Alongside the main objective of Cos4Cloud to promote the development of new technological services for the networking and sustainability of citizen observatories, the project supports the expansion of citizen science beyond traditional adult audiences, as in the context of school education. International experience from linking citizen science with school education indicates that most initiatives are one-off activities with no follow-up (DITOS Consortium, 2019). Instead, it is suggested that such integration should be designed and implemented in a systematic way, so that the possibilities to bring about deeper and more meaningful changes towards sustainability are increasing. To this end, a strategy was conceived and elaborated in Cos4Cloud project to support a better understanding and promotion of the integration between

citizen science and EE through collaborative research, technological innovation, and educational practice.

Following the suggestions by the DITOS consortium (2019) about the strategic actions to be promoted along these lines of thought, our approach focused, among others, on the deployment of innovative and challenging projects in schools, the training of teachers, the promotion of partnerships between local stakeholders and the school system, and the development of new concepts and tools to assess the competences and learning outcomes achieved. The strategy encourages the co-design and co-creation of learning situations and supports their enactment through the following three interrelated pathways (see Figure 2):

- (a) the establishment of an educational network of teachers, educators, educational stakeholders and schools eager to support the integration of citizen science through environmental education projects and activities;
- (b) the development of teacher training schemes and resources to empower teachers to incorporate citizen science into their teaching practices; and
- (c) the design and implementation of a range of educational projects and activities in schools and their evaluation in terms of their learning potential and educational impact.

Fig. 2. The Cos4Cloud strategy for integrating citizen science into school education.

Cos4Cloud plans to roll out this methodology to other citizen observatories to propose a model of integrating citizen science technologies in school EE across Europe. Through setting up networks of citizen observatories and supporting them with interoperable technology, the gains can be multiplied, and students can take advantage of a more holistic knowledge based on the improved quality and quantity of the data collected (Daskolia et al, 2022). Among the actions for expanding the scope of current citizen science practice and the use of citizen science observatories through integration into school EE was an online teacher training course. In this paper, we describe the design and implementation of the course entitled "Citizen Science and Environmental Education for Sustainability", and we present the methodology and some results from the evaluation conducted on the design and learning benefits of teachers from the course.

3. The online teacher training course: design and implementation

The course was conceived of, organized, and delivered by the Environmental Education Lab of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, with the collaboration of the Cos4Cloud coordinators, as one of the first and leading actions of the project's strategy for integrating citizen science in school EE. Targeting qualified and highly experienced Greek EE teachers and educational stakeholders the course sought to introduce participants to citizen science practice, the role and status of citizen observatories (CO), and the aims of the Cos4Cloud project, as well as to familiarize them with the implementation of innovative educational activities in their schools. It also aimed to train them in the collaborative design of educational projects and activities aimed to propose innovative pedagogical designs with multiple learning benefits for the students.

More specifically, the 100-hour online training course took place from July to December 2020 and was hosted on the CCE's Open eClass platform (<https://eclass.cce.uoa.gr/courses/CCEHUMAN121/>).

Twenty-three (23) participants were invited to enrol, of whom twenty-two (22) completed the course successfully and received a Training Certificate and a Europass Certificate Supplement (total ECVET points: 4). It comprised both asynchronous and synchronous learning activities. Trainees attended four theoretical modules and one practice-oriented module and participated in two dedicated webinars and one optional co-organized with other project partners. They then collaboratively designed six educational scenarios, the main principle of which was to promote the environmental, scientific, political, and digital literacy of students through activities by making use of the digital platforms and applications of selected COs.

Participants were divided into six groups of 3 to 4 and were invited to think and act as "educational designers" of citizen science projects and activities in schools (for a more detailed description of the co-design process, see: Daskolia et al, 2022). The idea was to get engaged in a co-design process of creating educational scenarios and activities for school use, building on their teaching experience and framing it with new knowledge and skills. They were encouraged to use at least two citizen observatories: PI@ntnet and OdourCollect, although they were free to choose among any other CO participating in Cos4Cloud. Natusfera was, for some groups, their third choice and was combined with the other two. Through a series of online meetings (e.g. via Zoom and Webex) each group collected, discussed and structured their initial ideas. To facilitate the co-design process and achieve a common working basis they were given detailed instructions on how to collaborate and work, along with two templates (the 'educational scenario' and the 'educational activity' templates) to assist them to reflect on every relevant information for describing and justify their ideas and suggestions in a comprehensive and codified way. Working with and on the two templates, each group drafted their scenarios via Google Docs and uploaded

the final versions of them to the eClass platform in January 2021.

The six scenarios co-created were the following:

1. In the suburban forest of Ymittos and the school garden with PI@ntnet
2. Sensorial walks in the school and the neighborhood with OdourCollect
3. In a former industrial area in Drapetsona with PI@ntNet and OdourCollect
4. In the school garden and the schoolyard with PI@ntNet and Natusfera
5. In the suburban streams and creeks of Athens with PI@ntNet
6. Mapping the history of the city's odours with OdourCollect

The evaluation was an internal part of the design and implementation of the online course, as a key tool for ensuring the quality of the training provided and the associated learning (Bray, 2008) and to enable a better understanding of educational practice taking place by matching it to the goals and intended outcomes (Zint, Dowd & Covit, 2011; Crohn & Birnbaum, 2010; Jenks, Vaughan & Butler, 2010). In the following section, we briefly outline the methodological design employed and the different levels of evaluation applied, and we summarize findings from the evaluation data obtained and analyzed based on the experience of the trainees from their participation in the course.

Fig. 3. The six educational scenarios.

4. Evaluation of the online training course

4.1. Methodological design

The online training course's evaluation was conceived and carried out at two interrelated levels:

1) As part of an ongoing internal process of reviewing and updating the online course's design and training materials. Here the data collected were extracted from the discussions and electronic messages exchanged within the trainers' team throughout the design phase, which formed a space of communication and reflection on the progress of the course.

2) During the implementation phase, to assess the progress of the course and whether and how it met the design criteria and the participants' expectations and development.

At this level, both qualitative and quantitative data were obtained and analysed from a set of questionnaires administered and completed by the trainees and based on their discussions on the eClass discussion forum. The evidence collected had to do with: the participants' professional background, their needs and expectations; and their reflections on the course's content, the Cos4Cloud technologies and other topics raised in the course. In addition, the trainees completed several assessment tasks and exercises designed by the trainers' team as feedback regarding their comprehension of new concepts and issues and their ease of transfer of the theoretical knowledge into practice-based intuition.

4.2. Participants

All twenty-two (22) trainees contributed with evaluation data. They were: 6 primary school teachers, 5 secondary school teachers, 3 coordinators of EE projects in primary and secondary education and 9 teachers and teacher trainers working in EE Centres. 18 were women and 5 were men. They were all experienced environmental educators or other long-term positions serving school environmental education. All had completed undergraduate, postgraduate and/or doctoral studies in various fields, including Education (7 trainees), Greek Language and Literature (3 trainees), English Language and Literature (2 trainees), Agricultural/ Geological/ Environmental Sciences (4 trainees), Architecture/ Engineering (2 trainees) and Mathematics/ Biology (4 trainees).

4.3. Analysis

A thematic analysis of all evaluation data collected from various sources was performed (Braun & Clarke 2006; Guest et al, 2018), looking for common and different themes. During the analysis we went beyond word and phrase counting and focused on identifying and describing explicit and implicit ideas, i.e., 'themes', in the data. We then developed codes to represent the identified themes and applied them to the raw data as summary indicators for later analysis. The analysis was based on several criteria, including the participants' personal assessments and comments of the course's effectiveness compared to their needs and expectations. The aim of the analysis was to summarize the actual data in a more condensed form and to describe the information collected in an accessible format.

An iterative process was used initially for familiarization with the data and data coding, with the third author carrying out the first round of organizing and reading the data, followed by the first author checking, revising and enriching the initial coding. Themes were identified by their significance as suggested by Braun & Clarke (2006), and then subjected to broader categories. All themes were primarily descriptive.

4.4. Results

The results briefly presented here are from the 2nd level of evaluation. As only a summary of the evaluation data analysis they are offered as insights to understand better the trainees' experience of participating in the online course.

Based on the analysis of the evaluation data, participants had the opportunity to get acquainted with the theory and practice of citizen science, the Cos4Cloud's COs and their technologies, and the project's goals and ambitions. Through their interactions with the training materials, their fellow trainees, the NKUA trainers and the other Cos4Cloud partners, they realized the common points of interest between citizen science and school-based EE, as well as the ways in which the former can be integrated into the latter. They also expressed their commitment to take action in their schools and areas of responsibility. Their commitment started with their involvement in the co-design of educational activities and projects, since the aim was for these scenarios to provide a 'roadmap' for educational practice, offering inspiration and guidance to the members of the upcoming thematic Educational Network.

According to the evaluation data analysis, all aspects and steps of the implementation of the online training course were designed and carried out in a way that served and fostered a culture of creativity, teamwork, collaboration, mutual support and recognition among participants, as well as a sense of being part of a community with defined goals, openness and ambition to remain in place well beyond the completion of the Cos4Cloud project.

Finally, some of the structural elements of success of this training course in terms of how it was designed and implemented based on the principles and practices of open science and citizen science promoted by the Cos4Cloud project, are the following:

- 1) the deliberate configuration of diverse groups of learners, from different disciplines, professional backgrounds, personal ambitions and stages of personal/professional development;
- 2) the provision of many opportunities to participate in online discussion forums, which encouraged reflection and exchange of ideas and opinions among trainees;
- 3) the organization of several collaboration and coaching sessions held in groups and/or plenary sessions;
- 4) the delivery of dedicated webinars to familiarise them with the use of CO platforms and tools and build their readiness to integrate them into school practice;
- 5) the promotion of collaborative practice-based learning through the co-design of educational scenarios and activities;
- 6) the co-design of educational scenarios aligned with the objectives of the online course and the Cos4Cloud project; and
- 7) the emphasis on the direct transfer and adaptation of the acquired knowledge to school practice.

5. Concluding remarks

In this paper we described the conceptual framework of principles and practices shaped by the European Cos4Cloud project to support the integration of citizen science in school

education and presented the design, implementation and part of the evaluation of an online teacher training course organised for this purpose. The analysis indicated a quite positive stance of the participants towards the online course and at the same time identified the strengths of the experience it offered them. An important aspect was the participants' satisfaction with the provided training and their sense of motivation to participate and support further actions in schools. Particularly encouraging was the sense of the majority of participants that their experience in the course was imbued with a culture of creativity, collaboration, and community building. Interdisciplinarity in synthesis, fostering communication and collaboration, hands-on experience in the use of technologies, and practice-based learning in relation to the school context were identified as important assets of the course.

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The Multidimensional Role of the Environmental Education Officers in Primary and Secondary Education. The Case of the Environmental Education Office of Athens B (North Athens) Directorate of Primary Education.

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Abstract

The role of the Environmental Education Officer is a complex role that touches on not only the organisation and administration of education but also the support of the teaching work of educators in the context of the implementation of innovative programmes and school actions in the field of education concerning the environment and its sustainability. In this paper, an analysis of the above-mentioned role is attempted focusing on the personal experience obtained from the exercise of the duties of the Environmental Education Officer of Athens B (North Athens) Directorate of Primary Education from September 2012 onwards, on the administrative, organisational, supportive and educational work of this role and especially on the precise characteristics of educational leadership and promotion of innovation that this position encompasses.

Keywords: Environmental Education Officer, innovation, educational leadership

1. Administrative and Organisational Work

As we refer to the administrative and organisational work, we consider it useful to first clarify and distinguish the terms "administration" and "organisation". Administration refers to the implementation of an organisational scheme, consisting of a purpose and many factors that have been defined and structured for this to be achieved (Bouris, 2008).

The Environmental Education Office of North Athens is responsible for coordinating Environmental Education programmes and promotional activities to highlight the importance of the environment and education for achieving sustainability. It has 195 school units of Pre-School Education and 159 school units of Primary Schools under its guidance. The educational policy of Environmental Education is based on the role of the Environmental Education Officer and other support structures such as the Environmental Education Centres (EE Centres).

The administrative and organisational policy philosophy under this context was based on forming a profile that requires the coordinated management of any given pedagogical and organisational role in and through the challenges of the modern digital era. In the performance of the officer's duties, the Everald et al. (2004) policy of understanding towards the teachers and their demands has been tried to be applied, giving thus a sense of moderation and dedication to our work in order to gain respect and appreciation of the teachers and their immediate supervisors and colleagues. At this point, we would like to express our agreement with Everald et al. (2004) regarding the notion that the focus of our management work is not only the organisation's results but a human relations issue (Everald et al., *ibid.*).

The development and implementation of innovative educational programmes can result in frustrations many teachers may not be willing to undergo. Lack of knowledge of the required teaching methodology and lack of teaching

time are two major sources of such frustrations. Of the individual factors mentioned by Vergidis (2008), regarding the implementation of Environmental Education programmes, we would focus on a) the lack of training in the collaborative teaching and learning method, the use of ICTs in educational practice, experiential teaching, the implementation of the project method, the use of teaching aids, as well as b) the lack of teaching time, especially in the upper grades of primary school, as only one teaching hour per week was available for the Flexible Zone of Creative and Interdisciplinary Activities, within which teachers have to dedicate many programmes in other areas (like Health Education and Culture).

In connection with the above-mentioned, the particularities of each school regarding its culture, the issues of homogeneity of the student population, the stability of the teaching staff, and the age and qualifications of the teachers (Lainas, 2000) were taken into account during our contact with each school unit for our research. We made sure to gather information on the above specifics through our cooperation with the Director of the Directorate of North Athens, the School Counsellors of the Directorate's Primary Education and Pre-school Education Districts and the Directors of the school units and to keep them informed when communicating with the teachers of the school units. The above-mentioned communications are carried out both in a synchronous and asynchronous way (e-mail, telephone, electronic contact forms, visits to schools, meetings at the Environmental Education Office).

Moreover, in the exercise of our tasks we tried to satisfy the following critical characteristics that theoretically form the ideal innovative leader (Flanagan & Jacobsen 2003, Theofilidis & Stylianidis 2000):

- Learning-focused envisioning: the leadership appropriates the use of ICTs in its vision for school education through continuous evaluation and feedback.

- **Equitable providing:** the leadership makes it a priority to actively seek ways of acquiring the necessary equipment and technical support for all teachers without discrimination. In the context of the above characteristic, our effort is formed to provide teachers with the proper educational material in printed, audiovisual and electronic form to support their programmes and to suggest other sources of finding similar material as well as technical support through the organisation of training seminars on the use of ICTs in Environmental Education.

- **Adventurous learning:** in this case, leadership invests substantially in the use of ICTs with an open and positive attitude to innovation. In the following text, we will try to highlight the importance we have given to the use of ICTs to promote innovation.

- **Patient teaching:** according to which the personal involvement of leadership in teacher training creates positive attitudes towards training without insisting on audit-type evaluations. In the context of our training role and especially in the experiential training workshops that we coordinated, we tried to have a collaborative and co-investigative role aiming at acquiring knowledge through the active participation of teachers and developing creative and critical skills.

- **Protective enabling:** leadership seeks the inclusion of educational community members and protects teachers' creative work in and out of school. During the training and/or the advisory meetings with teachers, we stressed the need for them to cooperate with the wider school community in implementing Environmental Education programmes and the importance of parental involvement.

- **Careful challenging:** Leadership challenges established perceptions by testing innovative pedagogical approaches. Of course, innovations must be introduced carefully so that they do not create problems for the school or its members. As mentioned above, we tried to take into account the individual peculiarities of each school unit in our effort to push their teaching staff to develop innovative actions through the implementation of Environmental Education programmes and teacher training based on the principles of the open school and the cooperation with the Environmental Education Centres, the Environmental NGOs, the Higher Education Institutions and other institutions.

In the above context, we take care of the timely circulation of information, its promotion through the World Wide Web and compliance with the deadlines for the submission of school Environmental Education programmes, expressions of interest for training seminars of our Directorate, Environmental Education Centres and other institutions, networking of schools in regional, national and international thematic networks of Environmental Education. Regarding the circulation of information through the World Wide Web, this is done through: a. the website of the Directorate of Primary Education of North Athens (<https://dipe-v-ath.att.sch.gr/>) b. the website of the Innovative Activities For Environmental Education (<http://perivallontikh.eu>) c. the website of the School Gardens of North Athens

(<http://northathensgardens.blogspot.gr/>) (a blog specialised in school garden management issues) d. the website of Environmental Educational Innovations (<http://kainotomoume.blogspot.gr>) (a blog that functions as a digital repository of material from the implemented Environmental Education projects).

2. Support and Training Work

According to Mintzberg (2004), three areas highlight the specific focus of educational leadership to promote innovation.

1. In the interpersonal field, the role of the mentor is to stimulate, encourage and support the whole project, to harmonise and synthesise individual needs, which is very important as change or innovation comes up against obstacles. At the same time, the role of liaison with external stakeholders will facilitate the unit's connection with local stakeholders. In the context of exercising our duties, we attempted to connect the teachers of the school units that implemented Environmental Education programmes with many external institutions such as:

a) The Environmental Education Centres throughout the country with which we cooperate in the framework of i) the implementation of training seminars for teachers ii) the participation of teachers in the Thematic Networks of Environmental Education iii) the visit of school classes to the Environmental Education Centres and the participation in their educational programmes.

b) local government organisations such as the Association for the Sustainable Development of Cities

c) Environmental NGOs such as the Hellenic Society for the Protection of Nature in the context of the coordination of the International Thematic Network for Environmental Education "Learning about Forests", Aeiforum NGO and the UNESCO Chair in Information and Communication Technologies in Education for Sustainable Development for the implementation of the Sustainable School Label project, the Earth Charter Hellas initiative for the introduction of the Earth Charter principles and values into the Environmental Education school programs, other environmental NGOs in the context of organising teacher training seminars and promoting their educational programmes.

2. In information management and utilisation, the innovative leader will collect and transfer information necessary for the action or initiative planned by the school units.

In the above context, we attempted to design, develop and manage the Environmental Educational Innovations blog (<http://kainotomoume.blogspot.gr>). The Environmental Educational Innovations blog was launched in January 2013. Its aim is to disseminate the actions and initiatives designed by the North Athens Directorate of Primary Education school units in the context of implementing Environmental Education programmes. The blog of Environmental Educational Innovations is not only a digital repository of the material produced in the framework of the Environmental Education programmes; it rather aims to be a guide for good practices and connecting teachers from

different school units, developing both cooperation and communication between them and giving the chance for the development of inter-school collaborations and the creation of an online community of teachers who are involved in environmental education. (Potamias et al., 2014).

3. The area of decision-making and implementation is perhaps the most important, as it is the core of administrative work. The Environmental Education Officer assumes the most important role of the innovator and reformer. Thus, it is important to identify opportunities, design, propose, promote and oversee changes. Equally important is managing the problems that arise, finding and allocating resources and negotiating with the external environment.

Unfortunately, the current institutional framework does not provide much compensation for the funding of Environmental Education Programmes.

We also made efforts to provide support for the Environmental Education programmes through:

a) The organisation and enrichment of the library of the Environmental Education Office, to which we refer in more detail below.

b) Encouraging teachers who implement Environmental Education programmes to join the Thematic Networks of Environmental Education, through which additional resources are provided to teachers in terms of specialised support in the thematic area of their programme in the form of educational material, training seminars (where accommodation and meals are covered) and educational visits of students.

At this point, it should be mentioned that the Environmental Education Office of North Athens Directorate of Primary Education was appointed the coordination for Greece of the International Thematic Environmental Education Network "Learning about Forests" in cooperation with the Hellenic Society for the Protection of Nature (HSPN). Within the framework of this network and through resources secured by HSPN and Greek and international sponsorships, educational material was developed and distributed, a nationwide award event for school units and experiential training seminars for teachers was organised.

An innovative stakeholder today cannot follow a simplistic model of a processor (Michopoulos, 1998). S/he must never forget that every educational structure is part of a wider system, which is interconnected with the society surrounding it. Thus, in order to be successful, s/he must make sure that s/he keeps in touch with the multiple developments and needs. This is achieved by disseminating news to the outside world but also by cultivating a positive mentality in school units, recognising that their role is to guide them by implementing and supporting educational innovations that come from within the educational community itself through collaborative processes and meetings (Everard & Morris, 1999).

In this way, the Environmental Education Officer, as a member of the educational system, can be the leader - main agent of innovations in the school units of their area of responsibility, as s/he contributes to the process of introducing innovations, supervises how changes are

introduced and bears the responsibility for the success or failure of educational innovations (Pasiardis 2004, Raptis & Vitsilaki, 2007).

The continuous training of teachers contribute to the modernisation of their pedagogical knowledge and strategies, the renewal of the teaching content and the provision of constant support for their challenging work (Chlapanis, et al., 2004).

In the above framework of guidance for the support and implementation of educational innovations and also after taking into account the training needs of teachers as they are presented in the self-evaluation forms of implemented programmes, completed by teachers at the end of each school year, as well as the type of submitted programmes (thematic areas quota, duration, content analysis of the submission plans), a series of optional afternoon training meetings of usually 3-4 teaching hours are planned and organised.

The following Education for Sustainable Development teaching principles are followed in the design and implementation of our training seminars and meetings (Biasuti et al, 2018, p.183)

- based on authentic learning;
- focused on experiential, constructivist and transformative learning;
- multi-methodological;
- participatory decision-making;
- locally relevant and culturally appropriate;
- interconnecting local to global and vice versa;
- interdisciplinary, cross-disciplinary and holistic approaches; and
- promoting core values and ethics.

The synergy and mutual information of all members of the school community, especially the School Counsellors of the Primary Education and Pre-school Education Districts, who are responsible for the pedagogical guidance and the whole operation of the school units, is considered essential.

Concerning the type and format of the training events we organised, we have the following categorisation.

- Workshops presenting good practices
- Introductory general methodology of Environmental Education programmes.
- Trainings in co-organisation with the Environmental Education Centres
- Specific thematic training (e.g. water, forest, climate change, school gardens).
- Multidisciplinary trainings based on Environmental Education.
- Trainings in the framework of the International Thematic Network of Environmental Education "Learning about Forests" coordinated by the Directorate of Environmental Education of North Athens.
- Training meetings on specific topics in collaboration with School Counsellors.
- Training meetings in cooperation with NGOs active in the field of the environment with targeted training and multi-level support: teacher training, distribution of

educational material and coordination of student groups by experts, as well as evaluative reflection meetings.

- Training meetings in collaboration with the Health Education and Cultural Affairs Officers, providing a holistic approach to several issues.
- Training seminars focusing on using ICTs in programme development and presentation.
- Supporting projects through art through training seminars for theatrical play, visual arts, audiovisual creations, etc.
- Promotion through the Innovative Activities for Environmental Education website of other training activities, conferences, educational programmes, or exhibitions that can contribute to the fuller implementation of the programmes. In addition, we take initiatives to introduce innovations. For instance, we could mention the adoption of the principles of the Earth Charter Initiative by teachers and school units in the framework of the implementation of Environmental Education programmes in cooperation with the Department of Primary Education of the University of Crete and the Earth Charter Hellas Initiative (<http://earthcharterhellas.edc.uoc.gr/>).

Concluding Remarks

Through our previous reports, we tried to highlight the multidimensional role of the Environmental Education Officer, who in difficult circumstances (very large number of supervised school units and implemented Environmental Education programmes, lack of secretarial support, lack of funding for the programmes) is called upon to carry out a complex task with administrative, organisational, training and support dimensions. Our reports were based on our personal reflection upon the experience and recording of how the Environmental Education Officer of the North Athens Directorate of Primary education performs his duties and in connection with contemporary literature and research.

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Teaching History and Philosophy of Early Childhood Education with Virtual Reality.

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Abstract

This study explored the design and implementation of Virtual Reality (VR) in an early childhood education course and in a theoretical subject, such as: history and philosophy of education. The primary aim of the study was to examine the potential of incorporating VR in Higher Education and whether students' engagement, motivation, learning and understanding would be enhanced. The implementation involved female preservice early childhood teachers (N = 49) completing one of their 13 tutorials using VR. Following ethics approval from the university, students in pairs completed a VR lesson on two major educational theories (Piaget and Vygotsky) and collaborated in solving a crossword at the end. They completed an online survey before and after the VR lesson and were video recorded during their VR experience. Descriptive statistics and thematic analysis were used and results are presented following Moore's (1989) theoretical framework around virtual learning environments. Findings consistent with previous studies are very encouraging as students provided very positive comments around their VR experience and felt that enhanced their pedagogical and theoretical understanding of the two eminent theories. This exploratory study provides initial positive evidence for the untapped potential of VR in supporting theoretical subjects, such as history and philosophy of education, in early childhood education. Implications for Higher Education, alignment with sustainability and social justice goals are discussed together with recommendations for future research.

Keywords: virtual reality, early childhood education, history and philosophy of education, learning environment.

1. Introduction

Virtual reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) are rapidly developing fields gaining popularity in higher education, with a plethora of studies emerging to support their incorporation in various university courses. According to an industry report on universities and colleges worldwide in 2019, more than 42 institutions utilize virtual reality tools to teach and offer VR courses (Lee & Kaufman, 2019). Cost reductions and increased computing power mean that VR industry is a profitable, steadily growing sector estimated to sell over 200m headsets by 2020 (Yamada-Rice et al., 2017) and can be experienced at home with a desktop computer or a mobile phone (Merchant et al., 2014; Schott & Marshall, 2018).

A variety of terms exists to describe VR technology and its related applications, such as virtual reality learning environments (VRLE), virtual worlds (e.g., second life), VR games and simulations and desktop VR. In this study we concentrated on desktop VR, using the Oculus Rift and HTC Vive headsets.

Although use of VR and Augmented Reality (AR) is growing fast in higher education (Gadelha, 2018) most studies refer to these tools in scientific, health and engineering courses e.g., Chemistry (Cai et al., 2014); Mathematics (Coimbra et al., 2015), Engineering (Martin-Gutierrez et al., 2015). Limited work has been attempted in more theoretical courses, such as history and philosophy of education and in programmes with prospective early childhood teachers who may not have a very strong technological background.

The most prominent theory underpinning the design and implementation of VR for learning purposes is constructivism (Huang et al., 2010; Jensen & Konradsen,

2018). Virtual reality facilitates constructivist learning by providing a highly interactive environment in which learners are active participants (Gadelha, 2018). Learners are allowed and encouraged to take control and ownership of their learning, building upon prior knowledge and creating new knowledge by synthesizing and revisiting their understandings (Huang et al., 2010; Mikropoulos & Natsis, 2011). Learning processes are more important than the products or end results (Huang et al., 2010; Iversen et al., 2015). In line with these views, the learning process facilitated by VR technology necessitates a careful examination of its design and how technological features support learning (Cooper et al., 2019; Lytras et al., 2015; Makrakis et al., 2019).

Considering the expansion of VR in higher education, alternative pedagogies which are in line with sustainable development and social justice issues (e.g., not excluding early childhood professionals who are mostly women from innovative digital practices) and further promote the engagement of students with the university community and their environment (Dovros & Makrakis, 2013) are encouraged. All four pillars of sustainable development: economy, environment, society and culture (Makrakis, 2017, p. 104) could be supported with the use of such technologies as they offer: a cost-effective approach which can be applied anywhere, anytime and repetitively (economy); an environmentally friendly tool with no paper/waste or dangerous emissions (environment); a social constructive pedagogy based on collaboration and teamwork will strengthen relationships between students, students and teachers and between students and the wider university community (society). Elimination of stereotypes and deepening of respect for cultural differences (culture) will also be supported.

1.1 Virtual reality and learning

Previous research suggests that the use of virtual reality could enhance students' learning in many fields (Bower et al., 2017; Lau & Lee, 2015). Studies on the development of didactic scenarios using VR or AR and collaborative learning report encouraging results for enhancing students' learning, performance and attitudes towards disciplines (Akçayır & Akçayır 2017; Fonseca et al., 2014).

Researchers have identified various reasons why VR can contribute to the achievement of learning outcomes. VR provides first-order experiences for learners and encourages active participation (Hewawalpita et al., 2018). VR is also an active experience, giving learners opportunities for active learning through movement and action on objects (Hartley et al., 2015). Students are able to build and interact with the 3D objects in the virtual reality environment and in this dynamic setting, they are supported to think critically about topics (Hew & Cheung., 2010). Students also reported that they were able to gain deeper understanding of the content as they were fully immersed in problem solving activities (Grenfell, 2013).

Virtual reality provides opportunities for learners to collaborate and communicate (Merchant et al., 2014). Learning is largely driven by exchange with peers, especially during the interpretation of complex and unclear knowledge (Alhalabi, 2016). The immediate exchanges between students can help them to consider multiple perspectives, and assist in reaching diverse interpretations. The ability to provide highly interactive learning experiences is one of the key features of virtual reality (Lau & Lee, 2015). In addition, the presence of users in the VR environment generated by the system contributes to a positive learning experience (Bower et al., 2017; Mikropoulos & Natsis, 2011). The virtual reality environment provides users with a common 3D space with various types of interactivity, where they can act on the objects in the environment, observe the outcomes of their actions, and learn by doing (Tsun-Ju & Yu-Ju, 2015). Learners are able to cooperate, exchange ideas and share experiences to construct knowledge during the learning process, particularly when working in groups (Huang et al., 2010).

Virtual reality can support immersive learning. This kind of learning offers greater potential for social scaffolding in cooperative and collaborative activities (Le et al., 2014). A collaborative virtual learning environment can be created as multiple users interact within the same virtual space or simulation, and this environment motivates them to learn in teams. This collaborative learning increases learners' interests and promotes critical thinking (Chen et al., 2018). Learners have the capacity to interact in real time, and share still or moving digital images, audio or any digital materials in the virtual environment (Grenfell, 2013). As a result, being present and working together supports groups of learners to solve problems collaboratively among themselves.

1.2 Virtual reality and motivation, engagement and satisfaction

Motivation is one of the major cognitive factors affecting learning, thus better-motivated students can learn more effectively (Zhang et al., 2014). Research results show that 3D fully immersive virtual learning environments can raise a learner's interest and motivation (Cheng et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2016). Features of interaction, imagination, and immersion are the main characteristics that attract and motivate students to learn in virtual learning environments (Webster, 2016).

Student engagement relates to the notion that learning is influenced by the levels of participation in learning activities (Yilmaz et al., 2015). Studies have provided substantial evidence that the use of virtual reality in education can be an effective way of increasing student participation, involvement and engagement (Sung & Hwang, 2013). Virtual reality can create a playful learning environment with less anxiety which improves learner confidence. It can enhance engagement with a topic more than in a 2D, text-based setting (Chen, 2016). Other researchers share similar ideas that virtual learning contexts reinforce learner engagement and participation, compared to students simply looking at pictures in a textbook or slide presentations in a traditional class setting. The studies indicate students invest significant time and effort when learning in a multimodal and multidimensional environment (Peterson, 2016).

As reported in the majority of studies, combination of high motivation and enhanced engagement in VR can also induce, positive feelings and satisfaction from users (Violante & Vezzetti, 2015). Studies in nursing education (Ulrich et al., 2014) and in science (Vrellis et al., 2016) reported high levels of satisfaction and described virtual reality experience as fun, unique, and interesting.

Overall, though motivation, engagement, fun and presence when engaging with VR are almost guaranteed, further empirical research comparing traditional and virtual tools is necessary around the impact on learning, retention and transferability of learning and on the novelty effect (Makransky et al., 2019; Merchant et al., 2014).

1.3 Issues and challenges with the use of VR in education

Cybersickness is a term that has been coined to describe the feelings of nausea, fatigue, dizziness, and bodily disorientation that users may experience following a VR session (Spiegel, 2018). Research suggests that with the increased input discrepancy between sensory organs, movement in the virtual environment is a strong contributor to VR-induced nausea and other cybersickness symptoms (Lindner et al., 2017; Rebenitsch & Owen, 2016).

Another challenge is that virtual reality learning environments are initially complex to use. Usability is an important technical factor that affects the educational success of technology innovations (Chang et al., 2014). Usability and technical issues may cause time loss for both students and instructors. Users can lose their motivation due

to technical and equipment-related problem (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2017; Coban et al., 2015; Gavish et al., 2015). It is also argued that using VR in teaching can be expensive and time consuming to set up. Sometimes the equipment needs to be operated in a specific space, and it cannot be moved easily. These concerns, however, are being mitigated by technological advancements.

Overall, previous studies, although mostly focused on VR use in scientific disciplines, report encouraging results and a high degree of motivation, engagement and satisfaction for tertiary students. Building on this literature, this study will explore whether similar findings can be reached after the implementation of VR in a theoretical subject with early childhood undergraduate students, who are not traditionally considered as technologically knowledgeable or confident (Hatzigianni & Kalaitzidis, 2018).

2 Methodology

In this study Moore's work on the affordances of distance education from 1989 was utilised as a theoretical framework. Moore's framework was based on constructivist principles (e.g., collaboration) and has been used by other similar studies (Huang, et al., 2010; Schoot & Marschall, 2018). Having a theoretical framework supported an in-depth examination of the VR implementation as will be discussed further in the results section. Questions Moore raised relevant to this study's research questions were for example: how is the design structured to facilitate learning; how can the design influence communication and dialogue between learners and between learners and instructors; and finally, how can learners' autonomy and self-regulation be promoted during their learning experience (Moore & Kearsley, 2011). Moore proposed three types of interactions in his framework for distance education but they are also critical today in a virtual learning environment. The interactions to consider were: learner-to-instructor, learner-to-learner, and learner-to-content. In a virtual reality learning environment, an instructor can trigger motivation, provide immediate feedback and support one to one or multiple interactions between learners. Learner-to-content interaction is a more autonomous process of gaining knowledge or information by interacting directly with the content resulting in learners' deeper understanding of the content. The VR environments provide learners with faster and diverse ways to interact with the learning content (Kinshuk et al., 2016). Finally, learner-to-learner interaction is the exchange of ideas, knowledge and interactions among learners. To collaborate in a VR learning environment, a shared space is established to help immerse participants in scenarios often requiring that they work together (Vrellis et al., 2016).

This project introduced a cohort of 49 first year students to the use of VR. Participating students were enrolled in the first semester of their university studies to complete a bachelor's degree in early childhood education in an Australian university. Selecting a core theoretical subject (History and Philosophy of Early Childhood Education) the

coordinator of the course with two other researchers, designed a VR lesson to explain two fundamental educational theories more efficiently (the theories of Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky). Students were informed about this VR intervention beforehand and they were asked to complete relevant readings in preparation. University ethics approval and informed consent forms were obtained prior to collection of any data. Students were encouraged to participate in the VR tutorial but were not in any way obliged to participate in the research component (online surveys and video recordings). The duration of this project was one semester (March 2018 – June 2018).

2.1 Research Questions

1) To what extent and in what ways can the integration of VR support first year university students' familiarisation and knowledge of two foundational educational theories?

2) How can the introduction and use of VR be consistent with contemporary theories on student-centred/led learning, motivation, engagement and active participation in higher education?

2.2 Participants

First year, first semester university students in the course of early childhood education (birth to five years old) completed this VR lesson as part of their weekly compulsory tutorials. Of these, 25 completed the pre-VR online survey and 16 the post-VR online survey. In addition, 36 gave permission to be video-recorded. The majority of students who participated in the research were female ($n = 45$ out of 49).

2.3 The VR lesson

The VR lesson was designed with the game engine, Unity 3D (Unity®Pro software, v. 5). The code library, Virtual Reality Toolkit (VRTK) was used, in order to be hardware agnostic. This allowed to run the simulation on both HTC Vive and Oculus Rift simultaneously. The hand controllers acted as laser pointers, which were the main interface mechanism for the students.

Before their planned VR lesson (similar to all their other lessons), students had to read two academic papers to prepare for the topic of the week. The VR lesson included ten multiple choice questions to answer relevant to each theory and based on assigned readings. After putting on the headsets and getting used to the laser pointer they had to choose one of the two theorists. The photos of the two theorists were presented to students in a calming blue-sky background (Figure 1). As soon as students selected one of the theorists, they could start answering the questions. There was no limit to the number of attempts to answer each question. When their answer was correct the theorists smiled, and when it was wrong they appeared sad. The unanswered question would appear repeatedly until the right answer was entered.

Fig. 1: The introductory scene and the laser pointers.

Fig. 2: The crossword and the pointer.

Fig. 3: Crossword, alphabet box and the timer in seconds.

The final part of the VR lesson was to complete a crossword (Figure 2 & 3) of 10 questions mostly focused on comparing the two theories. Students had to point to the right letter from the alphabet box to enter their crossword answer (figure 3). Additionally, they had to work out a plan on how to solve the crossword as they only had five minutes to complete it (a timer was on top right side of their screens, figure 3). Pairs had around 12 minutes to finish the VR activity due to timetable issues.

2.4 Instruments and process

Two anonymous online surveys were created using Qualtrics software (version: June, 2018). The pre-VR survey included eight closed and five open-ended questions, and was administered before the VR exercise. The aim of the pre-VR survey was to identify students' levels of familiarization with VR technology, previous VR experience, and general attitudes to, and expectations in relation to VR. The post-VR survey was administered after the completion of the VR experience and included nine closed and nine open-ended questions. The aim of the post-VR survey was to identify whether students benefited from their VR experience, the influence they considered it had on their learning, and was a chance to provide feedback for future iterations of the lesson. In post-survey, students were asked to choose any words from a list with 11 positive and five negative descriptions of their VR experience. They also had the choice to add their own words.

3. Analysis

Students' answers to the two online surveys (Pre-VR, Post-VR) were entered in SPSS v. 24 and descriptive statistics were produced. Answers to the open-ended questions were read carefully by the researchers and thematically analysed (Braun & Clark, 2012). Eighteen videos ($N = 36$, two students per video) of 12 minutes each, around 216 minutes were also thematically analysed by two researchers. Researchers watched the videos twice and recorded all comments. The comments were then categorised in main themes following Moore's framework.

As explained in Methodology section, Moore suggested a triadic framework: learner-to-instructor; learner-to-learner and learner-to-content. Findings from this study propose the extension of this framework and the addition of two more dimensions: learner-to-self for comments students were making about their own abilities and performance and learner-to-VR design for comments around their overall VR experience, the design of the lesson, the interface and the interactivity. The inclusion of two additional adjectives for learners and instructors could also be added to reflect the technological affordances of our time: "real" for the physically present learners and instructors and "virtual" for the ones who are online. The adapted framework is presented in figure 4.

Fig. 4: A proposed VR interaction framework based on Moore's (1989) framework.

4. Results

The presentation of the findings of this study will combine the two surveys and the videos in each of the framework's interaction category. As depicted in figure 4, starting from left to right and proceeding clockwise, we will start the presentation of findings from the category interactions with the "self".

4.1 Interactions with the self

Early childhood students were confident with the use of VR (mean: 3.59 out of 5, SD: 0.98) even though their familiarity was lower (mean: 2 out of 5, SD: 1.28) and 59% of students had no previous VR experience. Interestingly, out of the 59% of students with no prior experience only 17% were hesitant to give VR a try. In the post survey this percentage was even smaller. Only 7% of students reported that they were unsure if they would like to try VR again in the future.

The largest number of comments noted from the videos were associated with this interaction category. Two main themes were created. The first theme was around students' technical skills. Students were talking to themselves when they did not know or were unsure of something, for example:

- "I think I pressed, I don't know" (Oc.8 at 0.47min.).
- "Wait, do you point to the actual word?" (Vive 4, at 1.28 min.).

The second theme was around students' lack of theoretical knowledge and understanding, such as:

- "I don't know one down. No, I don't know what is it?" and soon after: "I don't know what 3 down is" (Oc.8 at 9.55 min.).
- "No, I don't know Vygotsky at all" (Oc.10 at 2.31min.).

4.2 Interactions with the VR design

In this category we included all the answers and comments around the general design of VR, technical issues, the interface and usability. Early childhood students were not familiar with VR technology but had a positive attitude, especially after they completed this VR lesson and students also expressed their desire to participate in more VR experiences in the future. The mean satisfaction level with the VR experience at the end was: 4.06 out of 5 (SD: 0.66). Their top choice from the positive list on rating their VR experience was: "hands on" ($n=13$), followed by: "engaging", "fun" ($n=12$) and "useful", "entertaining" ($n=11$). The majority of students (62.5%) reported that the VR experience fulfilled their expectations. A smaller percentage of students replied that their expectation was fulfilled to an extent (37.5%). One student commented: "it felt more like a game and wasn't as stressful as a normal test". Only two students gave negative connotations to their experience by describing it as "passive" or "difficult". Two students mentioned that they were expecting something more like a video game and also one of them had higher expectations in terms of "graphics and mechanics". The majority of students (62.5%) did not encounter any problems completing the VR experience but six replied they had some issues with the resolution of the screen; a heavy headset and learning to accurately use the laser pointers.

Students offered valuable advice on how to enhance the collaborative element of the VR design and make it even more immersive and playful. Their main recommendations were: to increase the duration of the activity; increase the number of students who can play together; add more time at the start for practice; include audio recordings of the questions (e.g., Piaget's voice asking the questions); more games and physical activities and to be able to experience all elements and affordances of the experience (e.g., answer the questions of both theorists and not just from one). Students also suggested for the lesson to be extended and continued in the real class after the VR completion. The use of laser pointers proved helpful and intuitive. One student enjoyed holding the laser pointers and commented: "It was nice looking down and seeing hands instead of two controllers". In addition, some consideration should be given around students who wear glasses as it was challenging for them to adjust the headset on their heads.

Comments in videos around the VR design were very rare and were about the use of the laser pointers. The aim was for students to finish their VR exercise in around 12 minutes as there were limitations with the availability of the VR space. All but one pair of students managed to finish on time. The students who needed extra two minutes struggled with answering the questions but also with accurately pointing the lasers to the right answer.

4.3 Interactions with the other learner

This is the second most frequent category of comments from the videos. Students referred to "others" in both their survey responses too. Collaboration and how much they enjoyed working with their classmates was the main theme in this category, as one student in the post survey commented: "*Being able to discuss with others while also engaging in the information and game*". A plethora of comments were made during their engagement with the VR crossword mostly trying to identify the right answer to the questions; devising a strategy around how to solve the crossword and encourage and supporting each other.

Comments from the videos centred around the right answers to the questions and how they could solve the crossword efficiently. Some quotes are provided below:

- "Can you guys see what I am doing?" (Vive4, at 3.11 min.).
- "Can you see it? Ok, cool. Oh". (Oc.9, at 5.35 min.). "Sorry, I am doing 5. Oh, it's the same. You are doing 4, okay?" (at 7.52 min.), "Okay, yes, can get it... You can do it" (at 10.43 min.).
- "Alright, you want me to do this one? ", "Is it cognitive? Is it cognitive and language? " (checking with partner, Vive7, at 2.01min.). "Is it only b and c? is it c? " (again, checking with partner about the right answer at 3.14 min.).
- "You are on fire. I am getting confused" (Vive15, at 6.35 min.). "Do you know what they are? I am stuck" (at 8.01 min.).

In this interaction category students' responses about the use of VR specifically with young children (future learners who will interact with each other) were included. The majority of students (60%) believed that VR would be useful for young children. Only one student gave a negative answer to this question. When elaborating on their answers, students also expressed concerns about the VR use concentrating on potential risks for their eyesight, body, brain and imagination development.

4.4 Interactions with the Instructor

Not much was reported about the instructor during the VR lesson, even though two instructors were present throughout the whole experience for all students assisting them when needed. Instructors introduced and explained the activity at the start of each session for each pair. Comments comparing the traditional class to the virtual are added under the "instructor" category as this would be useful feedback for future lecturers and tutors. The majority of students preferred the virtual class when compared with the physical class! Only two students reported that they liked more the physical class. One student commented on the efficiency of the VR activity: "*Firstly it was more efficient in terms of*

time. It was also useful in seeing what gaps I had in my knowledge and understanding of the concept. As it felt like a game the fear of saying the wrong thing was almost completely eliminated".

In the videos, students were asking questions mostly at the start (first two minutes) to better understand what they had to do and to practice the use of laser pointers. It was very evident in the videos which students came well-prepared and who were not. The ones who were well prepared and knew the answers to the questions needed no help and made almost no comments. Students who did not complete their readings before the VR activity were the ones who asked for more help from the instructor, asked a lot of questions and commented on things they did not know.

4.5 Interactions with the content

In this category the questions around whether VR can be used in education in general and in early childhood education and also the ones specifically around the content of the subject were included. The pre-survey students were asked questions about potential advantages and disadvantages of the implementation of VR in education. Half of the students were not sure whether VR would be useful for education. When asked to explain their answers, most students elaborated on the positive characteristics VR might have for education in general, such as promoting engagement, fun, interactivity, creativity, exploration, imagination and so on. One student specifically referred to history and how VR "*can give us more realistic idea of how things were back in the days...*".

Students provided very insightful answers when discussing the potential benefits from using VR. Not only they referred to common themes like engagement and innovation but they also raised equity considerations and empathy (e.g., "*...chance to have experiences and be in situations that may have not been possible previously due to reasons such as accessibility and affordability*"; "*...make a small classroom massive*") and added a range of new benefits such as: visualization of learning; making learning more relaxing and memorable; simulate real life; satisfaction; increasing children's curiosity in science and astronomy; and enriching the variety of educational methods.

Specifically, for the benefits of using VR for the history and philosophy subject, students predicted that it will enhance their understanding and offer them a more practical and exciting view to the heavy theoretical content of the subject. Two of the students also suggested on what might be helpful for them (e.g., "*walk around Froebel's kindergarten*"). Interestingly when directly asked about whether VR would enhance their understanding of the subject they were more cautious with 55% of them stating that they were not sure and 40% saying a definite yes. In their explanation about their answers most of them referred to their uncertainty of what to expect but also their inexperience. Two students referred to how VR might

provide them the opportunity to "travel" in time and develop a better understanding of life and beliefs of the past.

In the post survey, after the completion of the VR activity, students reported that they were actively-involved in the whole process, they took ownership of their learning and enjoyed leading their learning. Students explained how the VR design and content enhanced their theoretical and pedagogical understanding of the two educational theories. Some examples of students' comments around their knowledge and understanding are provided below: "*helped clarify knowledge*"; "*remember and retain more from it*"; "*helped outline the points of both theories...*"; "*required me to think more deeply about the subject*"; "*helped me compare the two theories*"; "*actively-involved and interactive*"; "*it was more physical...you actually had to move your hand forward as if you were physically grabbing the answer*". Similarly, in the videos, students' comments centred around whether they knew the answer or not. There were no comments about whether the questions were easy or difficult or anything else specifically around the content of the lesson.

5. Discussion

This exploratory study aimed at examining the learning potential of a VR experience within a first-year theoretical subject of early childhood education. Findings are clearly suggesting that first year, undergraduate, early childhood students enjoyed their VR experience immensely. Their answers revealed not only the value of interactivity and active participation (e.g., "hands on" was students' top attribute) but also an enhancement in their theoretical and pedagogical understandings of two major educational theories. Enriching their technological experiences but also advancing their theoretical understandings and promoting their motivation, agency and ownership of learning students were even able to make insightful suggestions on how to improve this VR experience to better facilitate future deliveries of theoretical courses. These findings are consistent with previous studies and constructivist theory which underlined active participation and a more salient role for the instructor (Bower et al., 2017; Grenfell, 2013; Hewawalpita et al., 2018; Kinshuk et al., 2016). The findings are also in line with sustainability and social justice issues when considering that these students were mostly female, early childhood preservice teachers with almost no previous experience with VR. There is a plethora of research arguing for the need to enhance women's role in science and technology and strengthen their confidence and participation (Beede et al., 2011; McGee Bentley, 2017; Ramsey et al., 2013).

It is evident from the findings of this study that VR applications are a very good fit with not only scientific or technical subjects in higher education but also with more theoretical ones, such as history and philosophy. Students even made specific suggestions on how VR could be used for a more solid understanding of historical development and significant events/theories. Significant attempts in this field already exist in relation to ancient history (Eggarxou &

Psycharis, 2007; Gutierrez et al., 2007) but more work could be recommended for history of education and social sciences (Mikropoulos & Natsis, 2011). Acknowledging that subjects such as the history and philosophy of education are very important in informing our future teachers and usually heavy in content due to all the important theories they must cover, VR experiences could provide a useful and interactive solution in engaging students more and further supporting their understanding.

Consistent with previous studies (Papanastasiou et al., 2018) findings revealed that communication and collaboration were promoted during students' VR experience, supported also by the fact that the VR experience was purposefully designed for students to work in pairs. Students felt more relaxed working with their classmates and even though they had to answer questions, "*it didn't feel like a test*", because they could talk to each other and ask questions. This is an important consideration when designing future VR experiences, consistent with Moore's (1989) suggestion that the design can influence communication and dialogue between learners. Collaboration and team work are also a vital part of establishing resilient societies and fight any kind of racism and stereotypes, aligning with the sustainability pillars of society and culture (Makrakis, 2017).

Implications for education in general were explored and revealed pre-service teachers' positive attitudes towards the integration of VR in education (Domingo & Bradley, 2018). However, as these were early childhood education students, they had legitimate concerns on whether young children (under 8 years of age) should engage with virtual reality, in line with the European guidelines (Yamanda-Rice et al., 2017), advice from the Australian e-safety commissioner (<https://esafety.gov.au/education-resources/iparent/resources/esafety-gift-guide/virtual-reality-gaming>) and the corporate guidelines, headsets and VR applications are to be used with children older than 12 years of age. However, more work might be helpful in this area as technology is advancing.

Finally, students made suggestions on design issues, proving their eagerness to participate more actively in the design of their own courses. New technologies, such as VR, can accommodate this desire and promote students' digital competences. Consistent not only with constructivist and pedagogical theories but also with sustainability and equity goals, empowering the future generation to lead significant changes and improvements in our educational systems is of primary importance.

6. Limitations

This study similar to many others (Papanastasiou et al., 2018) employed a small, convenient sample and had a short duration. Though innovative in its field one should treat the findings with careful consideration and no generalisations can be insinuated given the above-mentioned limitations. Additionally, the design of this VR experience did not fully capitalise on the playful elements and immersive approach that other VR applications encompass but this was more due

to the financial and administrative constraints the researchers had to overcome.

Finally, future studies would also need to carefully examine the novelty effect and whether knowledge is retained or transferred across contexts together with more complex statistical analysis (e.g., see for example study by Merchant et al., 2014) and/or neurobiological research (e.g., the use of electroencephalography, see paper from Anderson et al., 2019). Nevertheless, this small scale, exploratory study makes a significant contribution to the literature on implementing VR within theoretical courses, with less technologically savvy students and is useful to opening avenues for future research.

7. Implications and Conclusion

The rate at which VR technologies are being developed is extraordinary and it will soon be considered a standard digital technological tool in a lot of homes too, as Yamands-Rice et al. explained "virtual" reality can be our "everyday" reality soon (2017, p. 4). Higher Education is a natural place to experiment and try out ground-breaking practices and pedagogies. Being at the forefront of teaching and learning methodologies and investigating the implementation of innovative endeavours will enhance quality, sustainability, equity and bring a gust of new air in tertiary education.

More research with larger samples and longitudinal designs are imperative to reach conclusions and see whether a shift to "dynamic, flexible learning" is taking place steering away from "monolithic learning" (Lytras et al., 2015, p. 557). Education and professional development of teachers could be benefited by VR as realistic and interactive role-playing simulations are possible and cost-effective, promote collaboration and empower students (Reimbash-Kounatze, 2011). Future studies could also consider involving tertiary students in the design of their VR experiences, actively contributing to their VR narratives/content to enhance their critical engagement and digital competence skills (León-Pérez et al., 2020).

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Innovative Practices in Teaching and Learning Through the Exploitation of Educational Robotics, STEAM Education and the Openness of the Sustainable School to the Community

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Abstract

The present study focuses on the implementation of innovative practices in teaching and learning of a Sustainable Kindergarten in the context of its participation in the Unesco Associated Schools Network (ASPnet). The main research topic of this effort is to investigate the existence of a positive correlation between the expansion of the learning environment outside the classroom and the openness of the school, with the effortless approach of the Sustainable Development. Based on the Activity Theory and the belief that the natural, social and cultural environment is an important source of knowledge, the organized learning process includes formal, non-formal and informal types of education. The pedagogical innovation of the project is determined by the exploitation of Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM Education) and educational robotics as methodological tools, in order to approach the 17 goals of sustainable development. According to the framework for 21st century learning, the project pursues the enhancement of creativity and innovation, problem solving, effective communication and collaboration of the pupils. During the design and the implementation phase of the educational intervention, action research and field research are applied. This empirical research is completed with the process of the evaluation and dissemination of the learning outcomes to the community.

Keywords: (Sustainable development, STEAM education, Educational Robotics, 21st century skills)

1. Introduction

The application of innovative pedagogical methods in the learning process is seen as a crucial aspect of scientific research. This project uses as theoretical framework the principal element of Cultural Historical Activity Theory (CHAT) which is the belief that learning is the result of interaction. The specific concern of this effort is to investigate the existence of a positive correlation between the openness of the school and the expansion of the learning environment outside the classroom, with the experiential approach of the sustainable education.

Additionally, in order to prepare the students for a more complex life, the project focuses on the approachment of 21st century skills such as creativity and innovation, critical thinking, problem solving, technology skills, digital literacy, effective communication and collaboration, cross-cultural understanding, connectivity, constructing knowledge, co-responsibility.

The organized and emerging activities of the research are implemented to the students of the Sustainable Kindergarten of Klimatias, in Greece, in the context of its long-term participation in the Unesco Associated Schools Network (ASPnet), in international educational projects and the openness to the local and extended community.

During the implementation phase of this empirical research, field research and action research are applied (Cohen L. – Manion L., 1994), while the educational robotics and the socio-cultural approach of STEAM Education are utilized as methodological tools.

The progress of the study includes qualitative and quantitative collection data methods, such as semi-structured interviews and questionnaires, researchers' field notes, participatory and non-participatory observation. The research framework is completed with the evaluation and dissemination of the learning outcomes to the local and extended community.

The effectiveness of this pilot application is demonstrated by the active participation of students and the local community, the rich material produced, as well as by the international awards of the school.

2. Theoretical and Methodological Framework

Based on the Cultural Historical Activity Theory and the belief that the natural, social and cultural environment is an important source of knowledge, the organized learning process includes formal, non-formal and informal types of education (see Figure 1.). This learning expansion is considered as a process of acquiring and creating empirical knowledge and concepts and a process that leads to the formation of theoretical knowledge and concepts (Engeström, Y. – Sannino, An., 2010).

Fig. 1 Analysis of the activities based on the Cultural Historical Activity Theory.

In this context, the implemented project is based on the main parts of SCOPES: Systems of activities, Contradictions, Outcomes, Praxis, Expansive learning, Science education.

In order to approach the 21st century learning skills, the project pursues the enhancement of creativity and innovation, critical thinking, problem solving, technology skills and digital literacy, flexibility, effective communication and collaboration of the pupils.

During the planning and implementation phase are applied action research and field research (Cohen L. – Manion L., 1994). Simultaneously, the socio-cultural approach of Science teaching (Plakitsi 2012), technology, educational robotics, engineering, arts and mathematics are utilized as methodological tools. This action research organizes STEAM education as an activity aimed at the sustainable development (Plakitsi 2018).

More specifically, the children discover through play and exploration activities their environment, gather information and expand their knowledge. The “Little Creative Scientists” use the Nature as a classroom (Learn about Forests, 2021), connect learning activities with their daily lives and approach the Sustainable Development Goals experimentally (see Fig. 2).

Fig.2 Outdooring Activities

In the empirical part, proposed activities are submitted by the pedagogical team through brainstorming and democratic procedures (Topoliati 2015). At this point, a conceptual map is created with the use of an open source software, the Kidspiration, It is worth to be mentioned that parents are implicated in the action planning, materialization and evaluation of activities while the pedagogical role of teacher is facilitator, inspirational and participative.

The interaction between schools, educational institutions, international networks and the extended community has crucial importance while promotes the learning context.

Indicatively, we point out the collaboration with the Communication Officer for Greece and Cyprus, United Nations Regional Information Centre (UNRIC), who visits the school, after our invitation and brings the students into experiential contact with the goals of sustainable development (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Communication Officer for Greece and Cyprus, (UNRIC)

This activity motivates as stimulus the extended engagement of students with the learning area of the sustainable education through the exploitation of new technologies, educational robotics and STEAM education. Specifically, the children create a short narrative film approaching selective concepts-themes such as Human Rights, Poverty, Inequality, Environment/Climate changes, Peace and Human Health.

The leading actor of the “film” is the Active Citizen of the educational kit of the independent international organization, Action Aid, who narrates the experiences of his travels around the world (<https://youtu.be/jPUaqaNxQDI>).

Finally, the children cultivate their computational thinking by coding robotic systems (Bee-bot, LegoWeDo2.0, Thymio) on a floor track that is made of materials of their choice and depicts the 17 goals of sustainable development. In this context, the students create their first algorithm in order to move the floor robots between the goals of sustainable development, through playful coding activities and basic programming concepts.

3. Discussion and conclusions

Evaluating the learning outcomes of the project we confirm that the results are consistent with the corresponding research question. Particularly, the implementation of innovative practices in teaching and learning, such as the openness of the school to the community, the socio-cultural approach of STEAM education and educational robotics support preschool children to approach the sustainable development goals.

In our study we conduct observations, semi-structured interviews and questionnaires of students, parents and collaborating teachers. Conceptual mapping, photos and video recordings, personal and classroom portfolios are being investigated in order to demonstrate the effectiveness of this interdisciplinary teaching and learning method.

The analysis of the results reveal that the implementation of formal, informal and non formal type of education, the use

of STEAM education and the exploitation of educational robotics are introduced as effective learning tools that involve students in the learning area of sustainable development through authentic problem-solving activities, project-based learning, expansion of the learning environment and connection with their daily lives.

When the students were asked if they like the expansion of the learning environment outside the classroom, the entire percentage of the participants answered absolutely positively (see Graph 1.). Additionally, when they were asked to express their opinion about the presence of the educational robotics corner in their classroom, the majority of them identified that they strongly agree and only a small percentage of them (10%) gave neutral answer (Graph 2.).

The active participation of the students and the collaborative schools, the rich material produced, as well as the international awards of the school confirm the effectiveness of this pilot application. In particular, it is worth mentioning that the school is honored as a sustainable and ecological school during the last ten years, while the teacher is awarded for the educational contribution in border areas, by the National Commission of UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization).

4. Figures and graphs

Graph 1. Expansion of the classroom environment

Graph 2. Exploitation of educational robotics

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Διερεύνηση της Ιστορικής Ενσυναίσθησης Μαθητών/τριών μέσα από τον Έντυπο Τύπο ως Προαγωγή της Αειφορίας

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Περίληψη

Η εργασία στοχεύει να αναδείξει την επίδραση του έντυπου Τύπου στην ανάπτυξη και καλλιέργεια της ιστορικής ενσυναίσθησης προς τους μαθητές ως καλή πρακτική αλλά και ως μια προσπάθεια επικουρικής ενδυνάμωσής τους στη μελέτη της ιστορίας. Βασικό ζητούμενο είναι να διαφανεί αν ο Τύπος ως πηγή μπορεί να συμβάλει σε παραγωγική σκέψη μέσω διανοητικής αναβίωσης των γεγονότων ενεργοποιώντας την παραδοχή πώς οι αρχές της αειφορίας μπορούν να μετατραπούν σε διδάξιμη γνώση. Αναγνωρίζοντας την αξία της ενσωμάτωσης των αρχών της αειφορίας στην εκπαιδευτική πράξη, θεωρούμε ότι η έρευνα αυτή μπορεί να τροφοδοτήσει πρακτικές που προσδίδουν μαθητοκεντρικό και κοινωνικό προσανατολισμό στη διδασκαλία.

Λέξεις κλειδιά: αειφορία, ιστορική ενσυναίσθηση, Τύπος.

1. Εισαγωγή

Η έρευνα διεξήχθη σε μαθητές/τριες της Δευτεροβάθμιας εκπαίδευσης σε σχολείο του αστικού ιστού. Ως μεθοδολογικό εργαλείο χρησιμοποιήσαμε το ερωτηματολόγιο στο πλαίσιο ποιοτικής ανάλυσης έρευνας με ερωτήσεις ανοιχτού τύπου. Τα πρωτογενή δεδομένα που πρόεκυψαν από το ερωτηματολόγιο (περιγραφικές απαντήσεις), αποτέλεσαν αντικείμενο επεξεργασίας με το μεθοδολογικό εργαλείο της ανάλυσης περιεχομένου (ποιοτική ανάλυση), μέσω της οποίας πρόεκυψαν οι κατηγορίες δεδομένων και στοιχείων και οι μεταξύ τους συσχετισμοί (Cohen & Manion, 1994). Οι μαθητές/τριες κλήθηκαν μέσα από την ανάγνωση εφημερίδων εποχής σε συγκεκριμένο ιστορικό θέμα, ως άσκηση ενσυναισθητικού περιεχομένου και λογικής κατανόησης, να προσεγγίσουν τα ιστορικά γεγονότα, χωρίς απαραίτητα να τα αποδεχθούν, και να περιγράψουν τις προοπτικές τους. Η αξιολόγηση της ιστορικής ενσυναίσθησης με βάση την αρθρογραφία των εφημερίδων μέσω επιλογής συγκεκριμένων αποσπασμάτων είναι φυσικά ενδεικτική. Η ανάλυση των απαντήσεων των μαθητών/τριών επικεντρώθηκε σε πτυχές της ιστορικής ενσυναίσθησης: ιστορική διαμόρφωση, λογική κατανόηση, συναισθηματικά στοιχεία. Η πρωτοτυπία της παρούσας έρευνας έγκειται όχι απλώς στη χρήση έντυπου Τύπου ως ιστορικής πηγής, αλλά ειδικότερα στη χρήση εφημερίδων της χρονικής περιόδου κατά την οποία εκτυλίχθηκαν τα γεγονότα της Μικρασιατικής καταστροφής, δηλαδή το έτος 1922. Από τα αποτελέσματα του ερωτηματολογίου που τους δόθηκε, φάνηκε να βιώνουν νοερά συγκεκριμένες ιστορικές λεπτομέρειες του παρελθόντος αναπτύσσοντας συναισθήματα ως μια μορφή εξελιγμένης ιστορικής ενσυναίσθησης σε παράλληλη συν-αξιοποίηση με τις αρχές της αειφορίας. Επιπλέον, στις πράξεις των δρώντων προσώπων αναγνώρισαν υponοούμενους σκοπούς θέτοντας τους εαυτούς τους σε παρόμοιο ιστορικό γίνεσθαι.

2. Ιστορική Ενσυναίσθηση και αειφορία στο σχολικό περιβάλλον

Περί της ερμηνείας, της αξίας και συμβολής της ενσυναίσθησης στη διδασκαλία έχουν ήδη κατατεθεί για το θέμα αρκετές ελληνικές ερευνητικές μελέτες που συνεισέφεραν τα μέγιστα στις προοπτικές και προεκτάσεις

της στην εκπαίδευση (Κουργιαντάκης, 2005). Για τον λόγο αυτό και για τις ανάγκες της έρευνας θα αναφερθούμε αδρομερώς σε γενικές επισημάνσεις και σε δισταγμένες απόψεις.

Ήδη από τον 18ο αιώνα η έννοια της ενσυναίσθησης παρουσιάζεται σε συγγράμματα του φιλοσόφου κι ιστορικού Giambattista Vico (Pompa, 1971), ενώ πρωτεργάτης της γενικά στο χώρο της ιστορίας θεωρείται εξίσου ο Άγγλος ιστορικός και φιλόσοφος R. Collingwood, ο οποίος μέσα από το έργο του «The Idea of History» 1946/1994, ουσιαστικά καθιέρωσε την έννοια της «ιστορικής ενσυναίσθησης» ή «συμπαθητικής κατανόησης» (Pattiz, 2004). Σύμφωνα με τον Collingwood (όπ. αναφ. στο Foster, 2001, σ. 60-63 & Σμυρναίος, 2008 σ. 170-171,) το παρελθόν αποτελείται από πράξεις και όχι από συμβάντα. Η ιστορική γνώση είναι θεμελιωδώς διαφορετική από τη γνώση για τον φυσικό κόσμο, επειδή περιλαμβάνει τη γνώση τόσο του εξωτερικού / παρατηρήσιμου όσο και του εσωτερικού / μη παρατηρήσιμου. Με το «εσωτερικό» ο Collingwood εννοούσε τις σκέψεις των ανθρώπων που συμμετείχαν σε μια πράξη και ήταν αυτό που ουσιαστικά τους προκάλεσε ή τους ώθησε να ενεργήσουν (1946/1994). Επομένως, θα ήταν ευκατὰ να ανακατασκευάσουμε μέσω της ενσυναίσθησης αυτό το εσωτερικό κομμάτι, να συλλάβουμε νοερά μέσω των ιστορικών τεκμηρίων τις σκέψεις των ανθρώπων εκείνης της εποχής, για να την κατανοήσουμε με ενάργεια και να «ενσωματωθούμε» στο πνεύμα της.

Στο πλαίσιο αυτό η έννοια της ενσυναίσθησης εμφανίζεται όλο και συχνότερα στο λεξιλόγιο της ιστορικής σχολικής εκπαίδευσης, χωρίς βέβαια να λείπουν οι ενστάσεις και οι αμφισβητήσεις για το κατά πόσο μπορεί να συμβάλει αυτή η έννοια-κλειδί του Collingwood στην ιστορική κατανόηση και στη διδασκαλία της ιστορίας (Jenkins, 2006). Έτσι εδώ και δυο δεκαετίες η έννοια και η λειτουργία της ιστορικής ενσυναίσθησης στα σχολικά περιβάλλον φαίνεται να έχει αποκτήσει θιασώτες αλλά και σημαντικούς επικριτές.

Αρχικά η εμπειρική συνεισφορά των Lee και Ashby, μέσα από ένα ευρύ ερευνητικό πλαίσιο στην Αγγλία (πρόγραμμα CHATA, Concepts of History and Teaching

Approaches) άνοιξε πεδίο διαλόγου πάνω στο θέμα της λογικής κατανόησης ή της προοπτικής σύλληψης. Θεωρούν ότι η προσπάθεια του δασκάλου της Ιστορίας πρέπει να επικεντρώνεται στο να δοθούν στους μαθητές ιδέες πιο ισχυρές και αποτελεσματικές από εκείνες που είχαν ξεκινώντας τη μάθηση και ότι η διδασκαλία μέσω της ιστορικής ενσυναίσθησης είναι, ως ένα βαθμό, μια άσκηση στο να παρέχονται στους μαθητές πολλαπλές και διαφορετικές υποθέσεις και στρατηγικές, ώστε εκείνοι να προβληματίζονται και να δραστηριοποιούνται (Lee & Ashby, 2001, σ.25).

Ωστόσο, για τους Ashby-Lee οι μαθητές που αντιλαμβάνονται τι μετρά ως ενσυναίσθηση και έχουν μάθει τα βήματα που οδηγούν στην επίτευξη της, δεν έχουν κάνει μόνο ένα βήμα μπροστά στην ιστορία, αλλά είναι πολύ πιο ικανοί να αντιμετωπίσουν τον σύγχρονο κόσμο (Ashby - Lee, "Children's concepts", p. 64, οπ. αναφ. στο Κουργιαντάκης, 2005).

Για τον VanSledright, από την άλλη, οι μελέτες σε αμερικανικά σχολεία έδειξαν εξίσου ότι μέσω αυτής οι μαθητές αποκτούν τη δική τους ιστορική οπτική απέναντι στα γεγονότα (perspective) και εμμέσως αντιλαμβάνονται και νοηματοδοτούν μέσω πολλαπλών αναπαραστάσεων πρόσωπα και καταστάσεις στο σήμερα (VanSledright, 2010, σ.123). Στο ίδιο πλαίσιο και ο Foster που ισχυρίζεται ότι οι μαθητές πρέπει σαφώς να διαθέτουν μια σχετική γνώση του ιστορικού και του χρονολογικού πλαισίου, προτού αναδιφήσουν στο επιλεγμένο θέμα, ωστόσο θεωρεί ότι το να σκοτίζουμε τους μαθητές με ποσοτικά υπερβολικό πληροφοριακό υλικό, στο αρχικό τουλάχιστον στάδιο της αναζήτησης, μάλλον δεν είναι παραγωγικό. Ο εκπαιδευτικός που διδάσκει ιστορία στο σχολείο οφείλει να προσανατολίζει τους μαθητές του προς την κατεύθυνση του να αναρωτιούνται οι ίδιοι για τους λόγους ή τις προκαταλήψεις που ενδεχομένως τους επηρέασαν, ώστε να κατανοήσουν βαθύτερα μια ιστορική πηγή ή μια πράξη του παρελθόντος (Foster, 2001, σ.175-178). Σημαντικοί ερευνητές-θιασώτες της, όπως η Kitson, Husbands, Steward (2011), και Barton, Levstik (2004), υποστήριξαν με τις μελέτες τους ακριβώς αυτή την προοπτική.

Στον αντίποδα ο μεταμοντέρνος ιστορικός Jenkins, υποστηρίζει ότι η ανάπλαση του παρελθόντος δεν μπορεί να επιτευχθεί, αφού η φαντασία βοηθά στη ανάπλασή του μόνο μέσα από τις πηγές. Ειδικότερα υποστηρίζει ότι μελετάμε την ιστορία της σκέψης των ιστορικών και όχι αυτή των ανθρώπων του παρελθόντος και αυτό ενδέχεται να σημαίνει ότι το παρελθόν δείχνει να μην είναι ανακτήσιμο μέσω της ενσυναίσθησης, εμμένοντας έτσι στην αμφιλεγόμενη ιδεολογική λειτουργία της (Jenkins, 1991, σ.47). Στην ίδια ιδεολογική γραμμή κινούνται και ο Walsh, Stanford, Knight, και ο Brickley, αμφισβητώντας την αποτελεσματικότητά της, αφού η μέθοδος δειλά συνδέθηκε με προοδευτικές κινήσεις διδασκαλίας της ιστορίας στην Αγγλία, ενώ οι εμπειρικές έρευνες παραμένουν λιγιστές, ειδικότερα αν η εφαρμογή της είναι εφικτή αλλά και επιθυμητή στο σχολείο (Cooper, 2011, σ.87).

Σε αυτή την κατεύθυνση η ιστορική ενσυναίσθηση μπορεί να υποστηρίξει μια μαθητοκεντρική, ενεργητική, διερευνητική, ανακαλυπτική, συνεργατική μάθηση δημιουργώντας πλαίσιο διάδρασης μεταξύ των διδασκόντων και των διδασκομένων μέσω βιωματικών δραστηριοτήτων (Ράπτης, & Ράπτη, 1999).

Από την άλλη η εκπαίδευση για την αειφόρο ανάπτυξη μπορεί να ενεργοποιήσει νέες πρακτικές και μεθόδους που θα επιτρέπουν στον/ήν εκπαιδευτικό να παραγάγει και να διαχέει στην τάξη καινοτόμες και ευέλικτες διδακτικές δραστηριότητες για την επίτευξη των στόχων της αειφορίας, διασυνδέοντάς τες με όλες τις θεματικές περιοχές που διδάσκει, όπως η ιστορία, κ.λπ. Με γνώμονα το γεγονός ότι η εκπαίδευση για την αειφορία δεν περιορίζεται μόνο στην περιβαλλοντική διάσταση αλλά λαμβάνει υπόψη οικονομικές και κοινωνικές παραμέτρους, αποσκοπώντας στη διαμόρφωση νέων τρόπων σκέψης και δράσης για τη βελτίωση του επιπέδου της ποιότητας ζωής (Καλαϊτζίδης, 2016), η ιστορική ενσυναίσθηση θα μπορεί να λειτουργήσει συνεπικουρικά προς αυτή την κατεύθυνση.

Σε γενικές γραμμές, λοιπόν, είναι ενδιαφέρον να μελετηθεί περαιτέρω η εξακρίβωση της σύνδεσης της συμβολής του έντυπου Τύπου με την ιστορική ενσυναίσθηση ως συνδετική γέφυρα προσέγγισης ιστορικής γνώσης, κατανόησης και συνείδησης σε ένα πλαίσιο ενεργοποίησης των αρχών της αειφορίας, χωρίς αυτό να σημαίνει ότι απεμπολούνται συγχρόνως άλλες δεξιότητες, όπως πνευματικές, ψυχοκινητικές, κ.α. που σχετίζονται με τους γνωσιολογικούς στόχους της διδασκαλίας του μαθήματος.

3. Ο Τύπος ως πρωτογενή πηγή

Σύμφωνα με πολλούς ερευνητές ο Τύπος ως ιδεολογικός μηχανισμός, ως πολιτικός διαμορφωτής, ως φορέας πληροφόρησης (Καρυκόπουλος, 1984), καταγράφοντας γεγονότα, στάσεις, απόψεις και νοοτροπίες, γίνεται πηγή για την Ιστορία (Μπακουνάκης, 2016). Από την άλλη πλευρά, ως μέσο επικοινωνίας, έχει τη δύναμη να προκαλεί και ο ίδιος γεγονότα και να διαμορφώνει με τη σειρά του στάσεις, απόψεις και νοοτροπίες. Με λίγα λόγια, ο Τύπος διαδίδει γνώση και συγχρόνως επαναδιοργανώνει τις πρακτικές και τα πρότυπα που συνδέονται με αυτή, ενώ παράλληλα διαμορφώνει και συντηρεί τη συλλογική μνήμη.

4. Προετοιμασία μαθητών/τριών

Αρχικά η εκπαιδευτικός με βάση την παιδαγωγική αρχή της αφόρμησης παρουσίασε στο εργαστήριο πληροφορικής σε μια ολιγόλεπτη εισήγηση (10 λεπτά), με τη χρήση λογισμικού παρουσίασης και βιντεοπροβολέα, δομικά στοιχεία των ιστορικών γεγονότων της περιόδου, με επιλεγμένες φωτογραφίες και χάρτες από την εξέλιξη του μικρασιατικού πολέμου. Καθοριστικής σημασίας θεωρούμε το επετειακό έτος (2022) από τη Μικρασιατική καταστροφή, για την οποία κάποιοι μαθητές έχουν εικόνα από προσωπικά ακούσματα από το οικογενειακό τους περιβάλλον ή

διατηρούν ως κληρονομική παρακαταθήκη με αντικείμενα (κειμήλια) συγγενών τους (αξιοποίηση προηγούμενης γνώσης). Επιπρόσθετα οι καταθέσεις τους στην ολομέλεια της τάξης συνέβαλαν στην ανάπτυξη ενός διαλόγου. Παράλληλα παρουσιάστηκαν και συζητήθηκαν τα αίτια της εκστρατείας, τα γεγονότα και τα αποτελέσματά της, χωρίς αναλυτικές λεπτομέρειες, ώστε οι μαθητές να γνωρίσουν το ιστορικό πλαίσιο, πριν αρχίσουν, την αναζήτηση ειδικότερων πληροφοριών. Στον πίνακα η εκπαιδευτικός σημείωσε βασικούς ιστορικούς όρους, (δομικούς ή περιεχομένου) της ενότητας επεξηγώντας και αναλύοντας παράλληλα τη σημασία τους (π.χ. καταστροφή). Ακολούθησε σχετική αναφορά και συζήτηση για τις αρχές της αειφορίας και τη διασύνδεσή της με την ενσυναίσθηση.

5. Η ερευνητική διαδικασία

5.1. Το δείγμα

Δείγμα για την παρούσα έρευνα αποτέλεσε το σύνολο των μαθητών/τριών της Γ' τάξης Γυμνασίου. Ο αριθμός των 51 μαθητών/τριών μπορεί να θεωρηθεί επαρκής μαθητικός πληθυσμός, ώστε να αποτελέσει αξιόπιστο δείγμα (Cohen & Manion, 1994; Wisniewska, 2011). Η έρευνα διεξήχθη κατά το Β' τετράμηνο του σχολικού έτους 2021-22, σε σχολείο του αστικού ιστού του Βόλου. Καθ' όλη τη διάρκεια της έρευνας δεν τηρήθηκε η ανωνυμία των συμμετεχόντων, καθώς το θέμα συζητήθηκε ανοιχτά στην ολομέλεια της τάξης.

5.2. Η μέθοδος

Σκοπός της έρευνας είναι να συλλεχθούν και να διερευνηθούν οι απόψεις μαθητών δευτεροβάθμιας εκπαίδευσης σχετικά με τον τρόπο πρόσληψης και κατανόησης των γεγονότων της Μικρασιατικής Καταστροφής και των συνεπειών της μέσα από αποσπάσματα εφημερίδων του Τύπου της εποχής εκείνης. Για τις ανάγκες της κατασκευάστηκε ερωτηματολόγιο με περιεχόμενο σχετικό με το ερευνητικό μας ερώτημα. Ως μεθοδολογικό εργαλείο χρησιμοποιήσαμε το ερωτηματολόγιο στο πλαίσιο ποιοτικής ανάλυσης έρευνας με ερωτήσεις ανοιχτού τύπου. Οι ανοικτές ερωτήσεις επιτρέπουν να συλλέγονται οι απαντήσεις στη “φυσική” γλώσσα των ερωτώμενων. Τα ερωτηματολόγια αυτά σύμφωνα με τους Cohen and Manion χρησιμοποιούνται σε συνδυασμό με άλλες μεθόδους για τη διεξαγωγή μιας έρευνας (Cohen & Manion, 1994). Πρόκειται για το πιο διαδεδομένο μεθοδολογικό εργαλείο της εκπαιδευτικής και κοινωνικής έρευνας το οποίο παρουσιάζεται ως ένα έντυπο στο οποίο σημειώνονται οι απαντήσεις ή οι αντιδράσεις ενός ατόμου (Bell, 1997, 121-139). Στόχος του εν λόγω μεθοδολογικού εργαλείου είναι η μέτρηση στάσεων, γνώμων και αντιλήψεων. Τα πρωτογενή δεδομένα που πρόεκυψαν από το ερωτηματολόγιο (περιγραφικές απαντήσεις), αποτέλεσαν αντικείμενο επεξεργασίας με το μεθοδολογικό εργαλείο της ανάλυσης περιεχομένου (ποιοτική ανάλυση), μέσω της οποίας πρόεκυψαν οι κατηγορίες δεδομένων και στοιχείων και οι μεταξύ τους

συσχετισμοί (Cohen & Manion, 1994). Άλλωστε, στην έρευνα η ανάλυση περιεχομένου κατέχει τη μεγαλύτερη βαρύτητα, καθώς βασικός σκοπός της είναι να πάρει ένα λεκτικό, συμβολικό μη ποσοτικό ντοκουμέντο μιας κοινωνίας ή μιας κουλτούρας και να το μετασχηματίσει σε ποιοτικά και ποσοτικά δεδομένα. Ο τρόπος διεξαγωγής τους έδωσε στα παιδιά τη δυνατότητα να απαντήσουν όσο πιο ελεύθερα γινόταν. Αφόρμηση υπήρξε η δημιουργία σχετικού σεναρίου για τις ανάγκες της επιμόρφωσης στα Νέα Πιλοτικά Προγράμματα του ΙΕΠ, σύμφωνα με την οποία οι επιμορφούμενοι καλούνται να υλοποιήσουν διδακτικό σενάριο του μαθήματος που διδάσκουν. Συνδυαστικά αξιοποιήθηκε και η έρευνα-δράσης, με τη μορφή της αναστοχαστικής διερεύνησης, ως μέθοδο «βελτίωσης καθημερινής πρακτικής, που ασκεί ευεργετική επίδραση στα εμπλεκόμενα με την εκπαιδευτική πράξη πρόσωπα» (Kemmis, 1985, 38). Η εν λόγω πρακτική μπορεί να επιφέρει βελτίωση, τόσο στην ίδια την πρακτική όσο και στην κατανόησή της αλλά και στην κατάσταση μέσα στην οποία ασκείται (Carr & Kemmis, 1986). Στο πλαίσιο της έρευνας δράσης, ο εκπαιδευτικός και οι μαθητές συμμετέχουν ως ισότιμοι συνεργάτες και συν-ερευνητές, στοχάζονται και αναστοχάζονται σχετικά με τις στρατηγικές μάθησης -εν προκειμένω- προχωρούν σε κριτικές αναλύσεις, διαλέγονται, ενισχύουν τις συνεργατικές τους δεξιότητες (Somekh, 1994).

5.3. Τα ερευνητικά εργαλεία και η μέθοδος συλλογής δεδομένων

Στους/στις μαθητές/τριες δόθηκαν αρχικά στοχευμένα αποσπάσματα και τίτλοι από συγκεκριμένες εφημερίδες της εποχής, οι οποίες κάλυπταν τα γεγονότα της καταστροφής. Δόθηκε ο απαιτούμενος χρόνος για να μελετηθούν, ενώ η εκπαιδευτικός εξομάλυνε γλωσσικές δυσκολίες λόγω της ιδιαιτερότητας τους και έδινε επεξηγήσεις. Στη συνέχεια οι μαθητές/τριες συμπλήρωσαν τα ερωτηματολόγια στην ώρα του μαθήματος της ιστορίας. Με τα ερωτηματολόγια αυτά, διερευνήθηκε η αρχική στάση (συναισθήματα) των μαθητών/τριών απέναντι στα γεγονότα, και οι δεξιότητες που καλλιεργήθηκαν με την εκπαιδευτική πρακτική της ενσυναίσθησης. Είναι σαφές ότι, καθώς οι ιστορικές δεξιότητες διερευνούνται αποτελεσματικότερα με δοκιμασίες που συμπεριλαμβάνουν ανοιχτές ερωτήσεις και ελεύθερες απαντήσεις (Dickinson & Lee, 1978; Ashby & Lee, 1987; Sanson, 1987), δομήθηκαν ερωτήσεις διερεύνησης των ιστορικών γεγονότων μέσω των ιστορικών πηγών, (ενδεικτικά, μπορείτε να εντοπίσετε τα κίνητρα του δράντος προσώπου ή τι οδήγησε στη συγκεκριμένη ενέργεια, πώς αξιολογείτε τις πράξεις ... κ.λπ.). Ειδικότερα μελετήθηκε και η θυμική λειτουργία της ενσυναίσθησης, δηλαδή, κατά πόσον βοήθησε στην ανάπτυξη κινήτρων και στην ενεργοποίηση του ενδιαφέροντος των συμμετεχόντων μαθητών/τριών (Barton & Levstik, 2004; Κωστή, 2016) (ενδεικτικά, βρήκες ενδιαφέρουσα τη συγκεκριμένη μέθοδο; σε διευκόλυνε/σε βοήθησε στη μελέτη και στην κατανόηση της Ιστορίας;).

5.4. Το ερωτηματολόγιο

Τα ερωτήματα στα οποία κλήθηκαν οι μαθητές να απαντήσουν είναι τα εξής:

α. «Ποιά συναισθήματα σου προκαλεί ο τίτλος των ρεπορτάζ;»

β. «Φαντάσου ότι είσαι στη θέση των προσφύγων της Σμύρνης, όπως την περιγράφει ο συντάκτης του άρθρου. Πώς αυτό σε κάνει να νιώθεις;

γ. Στο υλικό που σας δόθηκε αναφέρεται ότι οι Κεμαλικοί προέβησαν σε φρικώδεις ωμότητες. Για ποιους λόγους πιστεύετε ότι το έκαναν αυτό;

δ. Σας προβληματίζει κάτι στις αναφορές των εφημερίδων για τη στάση των ξένων απέναντι στα γεγονότα; Τεκμηριώστε την απάντησή σας.

ε. Πιστεύεις ότι ο τρόπος που προσεγγίσαμε το θέμα αυτό σε βοήθησε να το μελετήσεις και να το κατανοήσεις καλύτερα; Αιτιολόγησε την απάντησή σου

5.5. Τα αποτελέσματα

Οι απαντήσεις των μαθητών στο ερωτηματολόγιο, καταγράφηκαν, ώστε να αποδοθεί με ακρίβεια ό,τι είχαν πει οι ερωτηθέντες. Με τη μέθοδο της θεματικής ανάλυσης ακολούθησε η καταγραφή, καταμέτρηση και κωδικοποίηση των απαντήσεων. Στην ποιοτική αυτή προσέγγιση επιδιώκεται η σε βάθος διερεύνηση απόψεων και εμπειριών συγκεκριμένων ατόμων, αναφορικά με κάποιο φαινόμενο, με σκοπό το αποτέλεσμα που θα προκύψει να μπορούν οι ερευνητές να το επεξεργαστούν (Μαντζούκας, 2007). Για την επίτευξη αυτού του σκοπού, ο ερευνητής επιλέγει τη "σκόπιμη δειγματοληψία", επιλέγοντας άτομα και τοποθεσίες που θα τον βοηθήσουν να κατανοήσει το κεντρικό φαινόμενο (Creswell, 2011).

Οι πληροφορίες που αντλήθηκαν από την ανάλυση αυτών των απαντήσεων κατηγοριοποιήθηκαν σε συγκεκριμένους θεματικούς άξονες, έτσι ώστε να γίνει πιο εύκολα αντιληπτή η ιστορική και ταυτόχρονα συναισθηματική οπτική των μαθητών (ενδεικτικά, στο πώς θα ένιωθες αν ήσουν εσύ στη θέση των προσφύγων, απάντησαν, φόβο, τρόμο, απόγνωση, κ.ά.). Θεωρούμε ότι οι απαντήσεις τους ήταν και ειλικρινείς και στοχευμένες, καθώς επίσης ότι πέτυχε η προσπάθεια προσέγγισής τους και τους δόθηκε ένα βήμα ώστε να προκύψουν συμπεράσματα για την έρευνα μας. Όλες οι απαντήσεις που περιγράφουν τις απαντήσεις-αντιδράσεις των μαθητών-αναγνωστών σχετικά με τα συναισθήματα και τις σκέψεις τους κατηγοριοποιήθηκαν με βάση τις λέξεις που έδωσαν. Οι απαντήσεις των μαθητών/τριών ήταν σύντομες, με δυο τρεις λέξεις (ενδεικτικά, φόβο, απελπισία, φρίκη, μίσος, κ.ά.), καθώς οι ερωτήσεις είχαν προσανατολιστεί προς αυτή την κατεύθυνση, δηλαδή σαφείς και μονοσήμαντες (Babbie, 2011, 398). Σύμφωνα με τους Τζάνη και Κεχαγιά (2005) «μέσα στην ποιοτική ανάλυση, αυτό που είναι σημαντικό είναι αυτό που φαίνεται συχνά, δηλαδή ο αριθμός των φορών που εμφανίζεται η έννοια, φράση κλπ., αυτό είναι το κριτήριο σπουδαιότητας». Στο πλαίσιο αυτό, ο υπολογισμός της συχνότητας εμφάνισης κάποιων λέξεων ή και φράσεων στην ανάλυση περιεχομένου με κωδικούς in vivo, αποκτά

ιδιαίτερη σημασία, διότι μπορεί να αποκαλύψει τις βαθύτερες διαστάσεις ενός φαινομένου (Bryman, 2017, 329). Τα ποιοτικά δεδομένα ήταν πολύ διορατικά ως προς την αναγκαιότητα νέων μεθόδων προσέγγισης της ιστορικής γνώσης.

Ερώτημα 1. Ποιά συναισθήματα σου προκαλεί ο τίτλος των ρεπορτάζ?

Ερώτημα 2. Φαντάσου ότι είσαι στη θέση των προσφύγων της Σμύρνης, όπως την περιγράφουν οι συντάκτες των άρθρων. Πώς αυτό σε κάνει να νιώθεις?

Ερώτημα 3. Στο υλικό που σας δόθηκε αναφέρεται ότι οι Κεμαλικοί προέβησαν σε φρικώδεις ωμότητες. Σύμφωνα με τις εφημερίδες, για ποιους λόγους πιστεύετε ότι το έκαναν αυτό?

Ερώτημα 4. Σας προβληματίζει κάτι στις αναφορές των εφημερίδων για τη στάση των Δυνάμεων απέναντι στα γεγονότα?

Ερώτημα 5. Πιστεύεις ότι ο τρόπος που προσεγγίσαμε το θέμα αυτό σε βοήθησε να το μελετήσεις, να το κατανοήσεις καλύτερα αναφορικά με τις αρχές της αιεφορίας;

6. Συζήτηση επί των αποτελεσμάτων

Καθώς, η βιβλιογραφία υστερεί σε έρευνες που μελετούν το σχετικό θέμα, η έρευνα αυτή επιχειρεί μια πρωταρχική εξέταση. Αξιοποιώντας τον Τύπο, εφημερίδες του 20ου αι., ως ιστορική πηγή, για τη μελέτη μιας διδακτικής ενότητας στη Δευτεροβάθμια Εκπαίδευση, προσπαθήσαμε να διερευνήσουμε μέσω ποιοτικής ανάλυσης δεδομένων, την επίδρασή του στην ανάπτυξη και καλλιέργεια της ιστορικής ενσυναίσθησης. Να επισημάνουμε ότι η συγκεκριμένη δράση-έρευνα λειτούργησε και ως άσκηση ενσυναισθητικού περιεχομένου, προκειμένου να διαφανεί ή όχι η επίδραση του Τύπου ως πρόσθετη και συνεπικουρική ιστορική πηγή. Είναι γενικά αποδεκτό ότι η διδασκαλία και η εξέταση της ενσυναίσθησης βασίζονται σε περιορισμένη έρευνα και πρακτική εμπειρία και το να «ενσυναισθάνεται» κανείς, ενδεχομένως, να ισοδυναμεί με το να φαντάζεται προσπαθώντας να εισχωρήσει σε μια εμπειρία του παρελθόντος. Αναρωτιέται, λοιπόν, κανείς, αν το

περιβάλλον μια εφημερίδας μπορεί να ωφελήσει γνωστικά, παιδαγωγικά και συναισθητικά τους μαθητές και αν τους βοηθά να αποκτούν κρίση, στο πλαίσιο των αρχών της αιεφορίας ((αλληλεγγύη, ακεραιότητα, δικαιοσύνη, ανεκτικότητα, δημοκρατία, κ.α.) για το κοινωνικό περιβάλλον (Καλαϊτζίδης, 2016) .

Παρότι η μελέτη βασίστηκε σε ένα μικρό δείγμα μαθητών/τριών, οι απόψεις τους ελέγχθηκαν διεξοδικά μέσα από τη θεματική ανάλυση, η οποία και βοήθησε στη διατύπωση των ακόλουθων συμπερασμάτων. Μέσα από προσεκτική επεξεργασία των απαντήσεων τους αλλά και τη συζήτηση που ακολούθησε, μετά το ερωτηματολόγιο, διαπιστώθηκε ότι οι μαθητές έδειξαν ιδιαίτερο ενδιαφέρον για τη μελέτη των γεγονότων της μικρασιατικής καταστροφής όπως ακριβώς το αποτύπωναν οι εφημερίδες, κατανοώντας με συναισθηματική ταύτιση τη θέση των δρώντων προσώπων, είτε θετική για το δράμα των κατοίκων της Σμύρνης και τους πρόσφυγες είτε αρνητική για τους εισβολείς αλλά και τις άπραγες Δυνάμεις.

Έτσι, διαπιστώνουμε ότι:

α. Διαφάνηκε μια κλίση προς τη «συναισθηματική ταύτιση» των μαθητών/τριών με τα γεγονότα, και μια απόπειρα «κατανόησης των συναισθημάτων, σκέψεων και δράσεων» και ερμηνείας τους λαμβάνοντας υπόψη το ιστορικό συγκείμενο τους.

β. Η πλειονότητα των μαθητών/τριών εκφράστηκε με αρνητικά συναισθήματα απέναντι στις περιγραφές των εφημερίδων για τα τεκταινόμενα.

γ. Οι περισσότερες απαντήσεις ήταν μονολεκτικές (ενδεικτικά, θλίψη, λύπη, αγανάκτηση, κ.ά.)

δ. Η πλειονότητα των μαθητών/τριών αντιλήφθηκε βαθμιαία το δράμα των ανθρώπων του μικρασιατικού πολέμου, μέσω της διαδικασίας της λογικής κατανόησης. Ήρθαν κοντά στο παρελθόν, το άγγιξαν, το ερεύνησαν, το κατανόησαν και κυρίως το συσχέτισαν με τον σύγχρονο κόσμο.

ε. Υπήρξε, ωστόσο, μια προφανής δυσκολία στη γλωσσική εξομάλυνση των αποσπασμάτων λόγω της καθαρεύουσας των εφημερίδων της εποχής, η οποία επιβράδυνε τη διαδικασία.

στ. Η μελέτη του Τύπου, των εφημερίδων, ως ιστορικής πηγής, στη διδασκαλία της ιστορίας, φάνηκε να τους αποσπά το ενδιαφέρον, συγκεκριμένα στην ερώτηση 5 κάποιοι μαθητές ενδεικτικά απάντησαν, μαθητής 1: «οι πηγές αυτές, θεωρώ ότι παίζουν καταλυτικό ρόλο στην κατανόηση των γεγονότων, έξω από το πλαίσιο του σχολικού βιβλίου και με βοηθούν περισσότερο προκαλώντας έντονα συναισθήματα», μαθητής 2: «με βοήθησε περισσότερο γιατί είναι διαφορετικό να μελετάς πηγές που γράφτηκαν εκείνη την εποχή από εκείνους τους ανθρώπους, παρά το βιβλίο της ιστορίας που σίγουρα δεν θα

είναι ακριβώς τα γεγονότα όπως έγιναν», μαθητής 3: «δεν χρειάστηκε να τα μάθω παπαγαλία», μαθητής 4: «ήταν μαρτυρίες και εγώ ήταν σαν να ήμουν εκεί», μαθητής 5: «δυσκολεύτηκα με τη γλώσσα, δεν καταλάβαινα», μαθητής 6: «θα ήθελα να γίνεται μετά το μάθημα για να με βοηθήσει να το κατανοήσω καλύτερα», μαθητής 7: «κατανόησα καλύτερα τα γεγονότα, καθώς μπόρεσα να τα δω από αυθεντικές πηγές, όχι μόνο ημερομηνίες αλλά και συναισθήματα που έτσι με έκαναν να βιώσω τη φρίκη των γεγονότων».

ζ. Όσον αφορά στην ερώτηση 4, αν δηλαδή τους προβληματίζει κάτι στις αναφορές των εφημερίδων για τη στάση των Δυνάμεων, οι μαθητές ενδεικτικά απάντησαν, μαθητής 1: « οι «πολιτισμένες» δυνάμεις μάλλον δεν ήταν τόσο «πολιτισμένες», μαθητής 2: «πρέπει να αισθάνονται ντροπή», μαθητής 3: «αμέτοχοι, χωρίς αισθήματα για τους ανθρώπους που σφάζονταν».

η. Κάποιοι μαθητές δεν μπόρεσαν καθόλου να τοποθετηθούν απέναντι στις αναφορές των συντακτών για την απαθή συμπεριφορά των ξένων δυνάμεων και απάντησαν ουδέτερα.

θ. Ενδιαφέρον, επίσης, παρουσιάζουν οι απαντήσεις στην ερώτηση 3, αναφορικά με τα κίνητρα των κεμαλικών για τις σφαγές, οι οποίες καταδεικνύουν στην πλειονότητά τους μια στάση ηθελημένης αποχής των μαθητών απέναντι σε αυτό που διάβασαν. Η αμέσως επόμενη απάντηση, όμως, τις αποδίδει σε μίσος αλλά και φανατισμό.

Συμπερασματικά, σύμφωνα με το μοντέλο των σταδίων ενσυναίσθησης στο οποίο καταλήγουν με βάση τις έρευνές τους οι Dickinson, Lee και Ashby, καταλήγουμε στο ότι μέσα από τη μελέτη των εφημερίδων οι μαθητές ανέπτυξαν μια μορφή εξελιγμένης ιστορικής ενσυναίσθησης, καθώς οι απαντήσεις τους κατέδειξαν ότι θεμελιώνονται με ιστορικούς όρους σε σχέση με το ευρύτερο ιστορικό πλαίσιο. Διαπιστώθηκε μια ακολουθία με τις αρχές της αειφορίας στο πλαίσιο της κοινωνικής συνείδησης και της συν-υπευθυνότητας με τα γεγονότα, έτσι ώστε να σφυρηλατούνται νέες συμπεριφορές. Η ιστορική ενσυναίσθηση καλλιεργήθηκε μέσα από τον Τύπο ως εφόδιο για την μια βιώσιμη κοινωνική εξέλιξη. Στις πράξεις των δράντων προσώπων αναγνώρισαν υπονοούμενους σκοπούς θέτοντας τους εαυτούς τους σε παρόμοιο ιστορικό γίγνεσθαι (Ashby & Lee, 1987, 68). Αλλωστε, ζητούμενο δεν ήταν να διαφανεί η ποιοτική ή ποσοτική διάσταση των γνώσεων τους ή το επίπεδο νοημοσύνης τους αλλά η σταδιακή διερεύνηση της αντιληπτικής τους ικανότητας, η ενσυναίσθηση ως λογική κατανόηση των γεγονότων, μέσα από το επικοινωνιακό περιβάλλον του Τύπου.

Δείγμα από την Εφημερίδα *Ελεύθερος Τύπος*, 3.9.1922

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SESSION B

Addressing the Fundamentals of Nursing Science Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

The vision for Healthcare includes healthcare systems that are sustainable, fair, moral, adaptive and suitable for the future. Although nurses respond to the healthcare needs of people in all environments and throughout life and their roles are vital to achieving global demands, there is a lack of SDGs in Nursing program studies. The aim of the study was to present an example module of student-driven learning activities through the CARE methodology in Fundamental of Nursing Science course for the implementation of SDGs. Using the CARE methodology, learning activities were developed at each stage. The Conceptualisation based on Nursing sustainability justice which is asked to be correlated with “Nightingale’s Environmental Theory” and “The Voice of Florence Nightingale on Advocacy”. The Activation includes activities to support the characterization of nurses as “patient’s advocates” and describe their roles in daily clinical practise applying environmental, social, economic and cultural justice. After conceptualization and activation process, nursing students are asked to answer the “What” questions for Reflection. In the last step, Engagement, students are asked to connect the knowledge with the practise through Behavioural engagement, Socio-emotional engagement and Cognitive engagement. The SDGs should be integrated across curricula and assessed to maximize their value and perceived importance for undergraduate nurses. Future nursing research must incorporate the principles and recommendations for sustainability in the modern world within a sustainable and holistic healthcare model.

Keywords: CARE methodology, curricula, Nursing students, Sustainable Development Goals, sustainability

1. Introduction

The vision for Healthcare includes health systems that are sustainable, fair, moral, adaptive and suitable for the future. A human-centered approach for healthcare should also take into account vulnerable populations and reduce inequalities in health (Fields et al., 2021). The pandemic has increased inequalities and made us realize that optimal levels of health cannot be achieved without addressing other social issues, such as accommodation, education, employment, living standards, climate and nutrition (Butterfield et al, 2021; Chakraborty et al., 2021; ICN, 2020; Schwerdtle et al., 2020). The effort to eliminate inequalities related to gender, race, nationality, religion and socio-economic position will lead to better societies in general and a reduction in conflict and violence so that everyone can live more peaceful and fulfilling lives.

As the issue of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has already expanded in many human fields and activities, Good health and well-being holds a prominent role among the SDGs. The UN General Assembly adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN, 2015) and 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are at the core of the plan. The universal, transformational and inclusive SDGs describe major development challenges for humanity. The aim of the 17 SDGs is to secure a sustainable, peaceful, prosperous and equitable life on earth for everyone now and in the future. The SDGs cover global challenges that are crucial for the survival of humanity (UNESCO, 2017). The health goal (SDG 3) is broad and aims to a universal health coverage (UHC) ensuring health and quality of life at all ages. This makes SDG 3 a main contributor and beneficiary of sustainable development, with linkages to all the other SDGs. Achieving SDG 3 will depend on the progress of other SDGs (SDG 1: Poverty reduction; SDG 2: Nutrition; SDG 4: Education; SDG 5: Gender equality; SDG 6: Clean

water and sanitation, SDG 7: Sustainable energy, SDG 8: Decent work and economic growth, SDG 10: Reduce inequalities, SDG 11: safer cities SDG 12: Responsible consumption and production, SDG 13: Climate action, SDG 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions, SDG 17: Partnerships for the goals) (WHO, 2017).

Nursing is the largest professional entity in the field of Health and is also the basis of patients care globally. Nurses are specialized, experienced healthcare professionals with high education level, providing anthropocentric holistic care through whole life. Although nursing researchers have highlighted the issue of health sustainability, the scope and dimensions of sustainability in nursing are undefined and inadequate (Benton & Shaffer, 2016). Sustainability in nursing includes the concepts of ecology, environment, future, globalization, holism and conservation. Nursing in the context of sustainability must have knowledge of climate change and environmental impact, be aware and show responsibility, willingness to change the focus of nursing science on sustainability. However, according to literature, nurses have difficulty in appreciating the relevance of the SDGs to their nursing practice (Griggs, et al 2017; Richardson, et al 2019), particularly goals that may not have an obvious connection to health, such as those involving climate and environmental issues (Nicholas & Breakey, 2017). However, it is a “short sighted” point of view for nurses to focus only to SDG 3 (Rosa, et al., 2019).

Nurses should be considered by themselves as global citizens, since they are the people who recognize the growing interconnectedness among individuals, countries, and economies, and identify as belonging to a world community (Dossey et al., 2019). Nurses come into contact with the most vulnerable populations and witness social and economic inequalities but their experience is often ignored in the literature due to the lack of nursing research (Squires,

2019). Social determinants and their impact on health is not a new concept in Nursing. In fact, they are at the heart of the profession. Nursing has the mandate to be an ambassador and a leader in this field. It goes beyond health-related goals and includes all the determinants with an impact on health and well-being.

University Nursing programs should adopt evidence based clinical practice in order to participate in decisions related to global health and well-being and Nursing leadership will help build sustainable, climate-resistant health systems for the future. Therefore, many researchers emphasize the importance of increasing awareness through Nursing education on the SDGs (Sullivan et al, 2019). However, there is a lack of SDGs in Nursing program studies and courses outlines so the need for awareness and education of Nurses on the SDGs is now considered urgent (Sustainable Foundations, 2021).

2. Theoretical educational approaches

Adult education requires experiential learning through activities of participation in learning and consolidation of knowledge. Education today has been changed from knowledge transmission to knowledge construction. This shift is bringing about new ways in the teaching and learning process (Kostoulas-Makrakis & Makrakis, 2020).

A study in Slovenia found 'different areas of self-regulation could explain 34% of variance of school performance in the primary school, about 21% in the secondary school and nearly 14% in the university education' (Vukman & Licardo, 2010). This is one of the largest effects from a single variable, yet it is a variable that is mostly hidden in classrooms, but it has a significant effect. The authors suggest that it is because the data is based on learners' self-assessment - the older students have automatized more of self-regulative processes than younger, they may not be aware so much that they engage in these processes. Another possible explanation is that those who have self-selected to enter higher education are amongst the higher scorers on this variable, so the scale of variation is reduced. Other aspects of the self-regulated learner have been described as self-managing, self-monitoring, and self-modifying. Adults and young people learning process is better when they indicate the following elements (Costa & Kallick, 2004):

- A sort of Goal, more or less well-defined.
- Trying out an Approach/Strategy.
- Getting feedback, either directly from your own observation, or interpreting others.
- Adding variations to what you were doing.

The aim of Fundamental of Nursing Science (Basic Nursing Science) course is for students to understand the concept of nursing care and to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills related to the provision of care in accordance with the basic principles of Nursing. Moreover, another goal is to familiarize nursing students with the basic

principles of nursing care for the management of patients with pathological and surgical problems.

After the end of this course, students are usually able to:

- Assess the basic needs and problems of patients
- Plan and implement personalized nursing care, as well as to evaluate the results of care
- Apply therapeutic, supportive and preventive nursing interventions to the patient
- Describe the patient's treatment needs at all levels of Health care.
- Apply protective mechanisms of the body during the practice of nursing.

Through Basic Nursing Science course students are asked to search, analyse and synthesize data and information, using the necessary technologies, respect the diversity, uniqueness and multiculturalism of each individual, adapt to new situations and develop critical thinking, teamwork and decision making skills. If nurses aim to achieve the SCGs, they should leave the traditional nursing approach to healthcare and adopt a more holistic, precautionary model. Healthcare systems must be reoriented to play an important role in "health creation" and in addressing many of the factors of bad health. The SDGs should be integrated in the main objectives of Nursing courses but also in their learning outcomes.

The introduction and training of the SDGs should be done with the use of student-driven learning activities through the CARE methodology advanced by Kostoulas-Makrakis and Makrakis (2020). The CARE learning design methodology is an experiential learning process through four stages: the conceptualisation of a learning intervention through activating learning processes to critical reflection and student engagement. Below is an example of student-driven learning activities through the CARE methodology in Basic Nursing course for the implementation of SDGs in Nursing theory and clinical practise.

3. The CARE learning design methodology

3.1 Conceptualisation

Conceptualisation is the process of conceiving and clarifying what, why, who, when, and where. What refers to the process for setting-up the key drivers for learning, such as the transversal 10Cs skills, the six pillars for 21st learning and sustainability justice (Makrakis 2017a, 2017b; Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis 2017). Since the nursing profession has had a longstanding commitment to social justice as a core professional value and ideal, the concept of sustainability justice could make a good connection with the exploration of SDGs. The concept of sustainability justice reflects the four pillars of sustainable development from a justice perspective- environmental justice, social justice, economic justice and cultural justice. Nurses respond to the healthcare needs of people in all environments and throughout life and their roles are vital to achieving global demands such as universal health coverage and the SDGs

(why). The nursing process, as a holistic but also individualized to the needs of the patient process, is carried out at each stage with the care of sustainability development. Nurses have to perform key roles on their daily clinical practice with SDGs application to be very challenging. Concepts connected to the key drivers are contextualised in a learning issue or theme, such as the one used here as an example entitled “Nursing sustainability justice”.

Therefore, the issue of sustainability justice in the implementation of SDGs (what) in patient care settings should be undertaken from nurses (who), as soon as possible (when) wherever nursing is practiced at the primary level - in the community, at the secondary level - in hospitals and clinics and at the tertiary level - patient’s rehabilitation (where).

On the occasion of International Nursing Day, which is celebrated around the world every May 12th, the anniversary of the birth of Florence Nightingale, Nursing sustainability justice will be correlated with “Nightingale’s Environmental Theory” and “The Voice of Florence Nightingale on Advocacy”. Nightingale defined Nursing as “the act of utilizing the patient’s environment to assist him in his recovery.” It includes the nurse’s initiative to formulate appropriate environmental arrangements for the gradual restoration of the patient’s health and that external factors related to the patient’s environment affect life or biological and physiological processes and development. “What nursing has to do is to put the patient in the best condition for nature to act upon him” (Nightingale, 1859/1992). She identified 5 environmental factors: fresh air, pure water, efficient drainage, cleanliness or sanitation, and light or direct sunlight. She also used advocacy often in the development of modern nursing by reading her many letters and publications that have survived, it is possible to identify her professional goals and techniques. Specifically, Nightingale supported human rights and developed leadership principles and practices that provide useful advocacy techniques for nurses practicing in the 21st century (Selanders & Crane, 2012).

3.2 Activation

Activation refers to a process that shifts from learning planning to specific learning activities, providing opportunities for students for creative dialogue, reflection and participation to the learning intervention. Through questions that pose problems, activation attempts to make teachers and students co-construct knowledge (Kostoulas-Makrakis & Makrakis, 2020).

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that more than 13 million deaths worldwide each year are due to preventable environmental causes and argues that climate change will affect the health of the population, so that health care systems need to take the consequences of climate change seriously (WHO, 2011). It is obvious that today’s climate change is caused by humans and the consequences

weigh on him as health will be directly affected by increased air pollution, infectious diseases, deforestation, the spread of harmful waste and reduced biodiversity (Costello et al, 2009). These events are expected to pose a particular threat to vulnerable populations such as children, the elderly, people with chronic illnesses and the poor (Frumklin et al, 2008). In the modern city, serious problems in the field of health education are still the quality of drinking water and air, road accidents, home environment, waste, noise, lack of space for entertainment and greenery, overcrowding that increases violence and aggression, drug use, sexually transmitted diseases, isolation, insecurity and crime (Richardson et al, 2016). Still malnutrition, working conditions, health care and lack of exercise are determined by socioeconomic status and undoubtedly the world’s leading cause of morbidity and mortality is poverty (Kagawa & Selby, 2010).

Figure 1. World Health in Numbers, World Health Day 2022 - Our planet, our health

3.2.1 Activity 1.

Human health is inextricably linked to the pure natural and structured environment (Sharon & Krieger, 2019). After reading the evidence in **Figure 1**, nursing students divided in pairs are asked to:

Recognize the environmental diseases, which refer to any pathologic process having a characteristic set of signs and symptoms that are detrimental to the well-being of the individual and are the consequence of external factors, including exposure to physical or chemical agents, poor nutrition, and social or cultural behaviors (SDG 3 and SDG1, SDG 2, SDG 6, SDG 8, SDG 11, SDG 12, SDG 13).

Explore how the specific factors of the local environment such as air pollution, noise, hazardous chemicals and aquifer pollution are sources of stressors and have a negative impact

on human health (SDG 3 and SDG 2, SDG 6, SDG 7, SDG 11, SDG 12, SDG 13)

Examine how climate change in general affects human health by increasing its temperature, the greenhouse effect but also how there is a change in their distribution communicable diseases (SDG 3 and SDG 7, SDG 11, SDG 12, SDG 13).

Search the correlation of the above with communities' welfare and future risks at national and European level (SDG 3 and SDG 8, SDG 10, SDG 11, SDG 16, SDG 17).

3.2.2 Activity 2.

Students are given the **Pictures 1 and 2** and are asked to:

Picture 1. Florence Nightingale, Notes on Nursing

Conceptual Framework of Florence Nightingale's Environmental Theory

Picture 2. Conceptual Framework

Describe what they see in the pictures, what situations, inequalities, injustices have led to these results and how the photos make them feel.

Compare and contrast the first pictures with the Florence Nightingale Environmental theory for nursing care by giving a brief description of the theory and its implementation in today's settings.

Speculate about our health now and in the future and the feelings, thoughts, fears, hopes conveyed by these pictures.

React for what they are seeing and thinking, expressing their own feelings, thoughts, fears and hopes as well as thinking of what is their role as nurses.

3.2.3 Activity 3.

Nursing has a long history of leadership in advocacy. Advocacy began with Florence Nightingale, who changed the face of nursing from a domestic service to a professional career option for women (Nightingale 1859a./1978; Dossey, 2000; Bostridge, 2008). She advocated for:

- A formalized educational process to prepare women for the nursing profession (Bostridge, 2008; Nightingale, 1851).
- Egalitarian and competent care as a basic human right for all individuals (Selanders, Lake & Crane, 2010, Verney, 1970).
- Change in all levels of the British Health care system during the 1800s, (Burns, 2003). This leadership model has the assumption that all nurses are leaders and advocates by virtue of being a nurse (Selanders, 2005d).

Taking into consideration the above evidence, **support** the characterization of nurses as **"patient's advocates"** and **describe** their roles today in daily clinical practise applying environmental, social, economic and cultural justice. Also, discuss in classroom the following subjects:

1. How are poverty and health linked? What are strategies to intervene in Nursing? (SDG 3 and SDG 1)
2. How is health related to gender inequality? (SDG 3, SDG 5 and SDG 10)
3. What do the experiences of people who are discriminated against within the health care system say about the system in general? (SDG 3 and SDG 8, SDG 10, SDG 11, SDG 16, SDG 17)
4. What are some opportunities for holistic healing in the health and well-being of Indigenous communities? (SDG 3 and SDG 8, SDG 10, SDG 11, SDG 16, SDG 17)
5. How could education support Nursing to manage the new challenges in healthcare and prevention

programs aware communities to remain healthy and safe? (SDG 3 and SDG 4, SDG 8, SDG 11)

3.3 Reflection

Reflection is a process engage students in identifying, exploring and clarifying their own values, thoughts, feelings, habits and experiences (Makrakis, 2016; Kostoulas-Makrakis & Makrakis, 2020).

Nurses know that health involves more than the provision of health services and nurses need to address the social, economic and political causes of the problems they face. War and unrest, economic uncertainty, income inequalities, and the widening spectrum of rich and poor affect both health and well-being. Nurses in their clinical practice are in an advantageous position to witness these realities, but we need to realize the power we have to bring about change by talking about the human suffering we see. Advocacy can arise in patients' bedside when nurses bring to the attention of physicians, managers, and administrators the concerns of patients. Occurs when nurses navigate the "management chain" in health care systems and local, state, federal regulatory and agencies to transform health care concerns and issues into policy (Tomajan, 2012). Nursing leaders have experiences, knowledge, and information that are important to share with those leaders who have an impact on health regulatory and legislative policy (Maryland & Gonzalez, 2012).

Following the critical reflection cycle - What? So what? Do what? Now what? – and after conceptualization and activation process, nursing students are asked to answer the What questions below:

3.3.1 What? (Questions establish the context and provide a description of an event with facts)

What is the meaning of holistic nursing approach in Nursing?

What is life for a patient / child / community/ living in poverty and hunger?

What is it like to be a patient can't afford nursing care?

What kind of environmental problems and diseases will our children face in the future?

What are the main problems from environmental, social, economic and cultural injustice?

What are your feelings?

3.3.2 So what? (Analysis of the facts elicited)

Why do environmental, social, economic and cultural injustice exist?

Why nurses are the key for the implementation of environmental, social, economic and cultural justice?

Why do environmental, social, economic and cultural injustice concern the whole world?

Why should local/world leaders care about environmental, social, economic and cultural injustice?

Why now?

3.3.3 Do what? (The actions to do or should do). The actions should be taken merging knowledge (Learning to know) with action (Learning to do), enabling learners to deal with a variety of diversities (Learning to live together), expressing empathy not merely sympathy (Learning to be).

What needs to be done?

What can you do as a nurse to eliminate environmental, social, economic and cultural injustice in your daily clinical practise?

What can you do as a Leader nurse to eliminate environmental, social, economic and cultural injustice in your community/ institution?

What can you do as an Academic in Nursing to eliminate environmental, social, economic and cultural injustice in University students.

3.3.4 Now what? (Inviting learners to present the next steps/actions required to move forward)

How can you reclaim your knowledge and experience to make world a better place to live through nursing care?

How can you support, protect and defend your patients against environmental, social, economic and cultural injustice?

What other work should be done to eliminate environmental, social, economic and cultural injustice?

3.4 Engagement

This last step goes a step further and connects the knowledge with the practise. In the context of the CARE methodology, engagement as a process can be driven through (Kostoulas-Makrakis & Makrakis, 2020):

3.4.1 Behavioural engagement: learning to give and learning to do.

Nursing students are able to:

1. Include health promoting behaviours in their daily routines.
2. Plan, implement, evaluate and replicate strategies that promote health, including sexual and reproductive health, and well-being for themselves, their families and others.
3. Perceive when others need help and to seek help for themselves and others.
4. Publicly demand and support the development of policies promoting health and well-being.
5. Propose ways to address possible conflicts between the public interest in offering medicine at affordable prices and private interests within the pharmaceutical industry.

3.4.2 Socio-emotional engagement: learning to live together sustainably.

Nursing students are able to:

1. Interact with people suffering from illnesses, and feel empathy for their situation and feelings.
2. Communicate about issues of health, including sexual and reproductive health, and well-being, especially to argue in favour of prevention strategies to promote health and well-being.
3. Encourage others to decide and act in favour of promoting health and well-being for all.
4. Create a holistic understanding of a life of health and well-being, and to clarify related values, beliefs and attitudes.
5. Develop a personal commitment to promoting health and well-being for themselves, their family and others, including considering volunteer or professional work in health and social care.

3.4.3 Cognitive engagement: (learning to know and learning to be)

Nursing students:

1. Know conception of health, hygiene and well-being and can critically reflect on them, including an understanding of the importance of gender in health and well-being.

2. Provide facts and figures about the most severe communicable and non-communicable diseases, and the most vulnerable groups and regions concerning illness, disease and premature death.
3. Understand the socio-political-economic dimensions of health and wellbeing and knows about the effects of advertising and about strategies to promote health and well-being.
4. Understand the importance of mental health. The learner understands the negative impacts of behaviours like xenophobia, discrimination and bullying on mental health and emotional well-being and how addictions to alcohol, tobacco or other drugs cause harm to health and well-being.
5. Know relevant prevention strategies to foster positive physical and mental health and well-being, including sexual and reproductive health and information as well as early warning and risk reduction.

4. Discussion and conclusion

Individual nurses and the wider nursing profession have opportunities to more meaningfully contribute to the SDGs, beginning with an increased awareness through education and a commitment to research and participation in local and global decision making. The most current resolution of the strategic direction aligns to the SDGs and comprises several themes for growth, including education, leadership, evidence-based practice, policy, and workforce (WHO, 2017). The SDGs should be integrated across curricula and assessed to maximize their value and perceived importance for undergraduate nurses (Sensor, 2021; Schwerdtle et al., 2020). Sustainable development principles need to be scaffolded across nursing curricula to (a) establish awareness, (b) build critical thinking, and (c) promote action (Sensor, 2021).

Nursing students need to be enlightened on how they as individuals and the wider profession can impact the SDGs, especially outside of SDG 3, and begin to recognize themselves as global citizens who can impact society. Finally, nurses at all levels need to be educated on the importance of research and empowered to take action through collecting empirical evidence to push for a seat at the table, at both a local and global level where decisions are made regarding the SDGs.

Nursing can contribute to sustainable development, with the ultimate goal of maintaining an environment that does not impede the opportunities of present and future generations for an optimal level of health. Future nursing research must incorporate the principles and recommendations for sustainability in the modern world within a sustainable and holistic healthcare model.

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A Macro-ethical Point of View on Environmental Policies

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Abstract

The ongoing environmental crises brought about by climate change, resource depletion, and pollution demand a reevaluation of our ethical frameworks regarding environmental policies. A macro ethical perspective provides a comprehensive approach that considers the broader implications of human actions on the environment and future generations. The philosophy of Hans Jonas, particularly his principle of responsibility, offers valuable insights into how we should shape these environmental policies.

Keywords: eco-philosophy, ethics, environmental policies, Jonas, responsibility

It is beyond any doubt, that, having defined the human species as dominant we have been led to severe environmental disasters. Thus, the ethical attitude and the way it should be formed evolves as the supreme issue of philosophical research taken into account in decision-making, concerning irreversible human behaviors.

It should be also considered as undoubtable the fact that human moral sensitivity concerns all living creatures. It should be understood that the effects of our actions affect not only the human species but also all living creatures in general. It should also be noted that it is not just about living creatures of the present, but also of the future, since they will be influenced by current practices as well. To accept the ethical attitude of all living creatures, we need to adopt a bio-centric behavior, which requires a re-examination of the relationship between human and nature. Nature does not exist simply to be used or consumed by man. The human species is part of the many that have evolved in the ecosystem. Consequently, all species have intrinsic value (Benson, 2000, Kernohan, 2012).

Having said the above, one might wonder what the contribution of philosophy could be in this particular field. That would be a rather naïve thought, as environmental ethics is a constantly developing sector in science fields as well as in everyday life (Rose D., Van Dooren T., Chrulowshow M., O'Gorman E., 2013).

Defining the present human-centered era does not mean that we blame the entire humanity for the permanent interventions on Earth. All human have made intervenes on the planet, but not in the same way and certainly not at the same rate. The Capitalocene, as a new philosophical term, reinforces the notion that the richest people in richer societies are the main cause of rapid global climate change, thus highlighting the strong inequality resulting from socio-political and economic processes.

Jason W. Moore, who introduced the term Capitalocene, argues that capitalism, not industrialization, caused the transformation of the Earth by causing enormous social inequalities, which

supported strong strategies of world conquest, endless commercialization and relentless production.

In the book *The Shock of the Anthropocene*, historians Christophe Bonneuil and Jean-Baptiste Fressoz go further, emphasizing indifference to politics and arguing that the elites are responsible for damage to the environment, hiding from public opinion the consequences of their actions.

In 2014, philosopher Donna Haraway introduced the term Chthulucene. For Haraway and a host of

scholars at humanities and social sciences, the focus of the Anthropocene on man is a problem in itself. The definition of a period under human control does not allow the formation of more complex social and ecological processes in which non-human actors possess equal key roles.

By the term Chthulucene, Haraway refers to Chthulu, the mythical, cosmic, complex god, to symbolize the impenetrable involvement and interconnection of what appears to be individual beings.

For Haraway, individuality is just an illusion and if we want to achieve multilevel ecology, that means practicing the best care of interconnected species (not one species at a time). Finally, Haraway points out that, during the period of Chthulucene, on the one hand we discuss a biological cultural-political-technological recovery and reconstruction and on the other, we mourn the effects of irreversible losses, such as extinct species (Haraway, 2016 a).

"Mourning comes to assess losses, to understand how the world has changed and how we need to change and renew our relationships if we want to move on. In this context, genuine mourning must lead us to realize our dependence and relationships with the countless others that lead us to the limits of extinction ... The reality, however, is that it does not exist avoiding the necessity of his difficult cultural work reflection and mourning. This work is not opposed in practice, but is the foundation of a sustainable and up-to-date response" (Van Dooren & Rose, 2013).

Is the Anthropocene era human type an environmental disaster and the end of humanity? Alternatively, could there be a "good" Anthropocene, in which both man, as well as nature could grow together into one long-term form? From a scientific point of view, the term Anthropocene does not give neither a positive nor a negative sign. It is clearly approached as an "observational" reality. However, it should be made clear that the Anthropocene period is still in progress (Haraway, 2016 b). With positive or negative results, the Anthropocentrism remains an evolving reality, which is formed based on current and future actions of people. The results are judged based on how this era is experienced and interpreted. "Anthropokainos" is a new narrative that concerns our daily life compared to the environment and a bold new scientific example how to radically revise the way we think about what it means to be a person. Humankind may learn to thrive without destroying the planet. Anthropocene invites us to think beyond our individual lives, to imagine the functions of an entire planet and its changes in schedules, from beginning to end. It enables us to understand that people is a force of nature. Nevertheless, there is still time to shape a future in which humans and the environment thrive for millennia. There is still a chance for each of us to write a better future.

Joanna Zylińska in her book *Minimal Ethics for the Anthropocene* refers to the Anthropocene as a "critical crisis": "thinking is the most political thing we can do about the Anthropocene, before we do anything else".

According to the encyclopedia of University of Stanford, environmental ethics is that part of philosophy that studies people's ethical relationship, as well as its non-human content. The environmental ethics, not particularly well known in our country, has its beginnings as an autonomous field of philosophy in the decade of the '70s, when the first books dealing systematically with the moral view of the planet were published.

Robin Attfield, in his book *Environmental Ethics: A Very Short Introduction*, states, "among the philosophers Plato was one of the first to know about soil erosion and deforestation, but was superficial with these developments, as was his student Aristotle, who in *Meteorology*, depicted nature as permanent and essentially unchanged". In the whole of ancient Greek philosophical thought for nature, we encounter strong elements of anthropocentrism. Aristotle, based on his teleological view, believed that everything has a purpose or an end, and that is why they were initially formed, with the ultimate goal of all things being service to the human species.

In the 19th century, scholars such as George Perkins Marsh, in his book "Man and Nature" (1864), stood out nature as very vulnerable to human activity and at the same time human life vulnerable to nature and its changes. In 1973, the Norwegian philosopher Arne Naess, in "The Shallow and the Deep, Long-

Range Ecology Movement. A Summary", presents a new species of ecological movement.

The "shallow" species is concerned with the human interests of the next fifty years or so, with particular emphasis on those of the people of developed countries. On the other hand, the "deep" species (Deep Ecology), while dealing with the wellness of the people of developing countries, deepens the long-term future and interacts with non-human species, affirming their equal right to live and to bloom, the equal right of all species to live their own way of life: "biospheric equalization". For itself, the central value is the self-realization or the fulfillment of the possibilities of the organizations of any kind.

The philosophical view around Deep Ecology also includes some controversial claims, including personal identity. For Naess, the true self is not limited to the physical body, but extends to the whole spectrum of nature, since everything is interconnected. Mention that features such as the respect, admiration and desire of our successors to appreciate the same scenes as us, are necessary.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that it supported a significant reduction in the human population for continuous flowering of other species, which makes us respond carefully and selectively to the values developed in Deep Ecology.

An additional essay with a significant contribution to formulation of ethics regarding the environment was entitled as "There an Ecological Ethic?" of Holmes Rolston III. For Rolston, human life is especially precious and is highly dependent on recycling. Although the specific approach makes recycling a matter of defending human interests, a preferred solution promotes ecosystem integrity as an intrinsic value.

Attfield points out that " Rolston's special proposal is that ecological ethics can stand out from other approaches, finding what is fundamentally valuable not only in human fulfillment, but in the prosperity of the non-human beings, or perhaps their biological systems of which we are a part. If we accept that other living creatures have a moral attitude, then the flourishing of these creatures must be considered to have intrinsic value".

What should concern us is whether, and to what extent, future interests are taken into account. What is the future impact of our actions and whether we should consider these results. The effects of modern technology are often predictable and it would be irresponsible to use it ignoring the results it brings.

Hans Jonas, a leading theorist and lecturer on modern technological and ecological macro-ethics, in his essay "The Principle of Responsibility" argued that "the recently expanded impact scale of human behavior in future... requires reshaping of our perception of ethics itself".

Hans Jonas considers all the previous ethical approaches historically outdated, ontologically

unfounded and therefore practically inapplicable, and for this reason he had to propose a new ethical system, where the moral "Deon" and "Good" are based on "being", that is, the biological existence of humans.

In "The Principle of Responsibility" Hans Jonas argues that nowadays the gap between our inadequate ability to predict and our ability to do has narrowed, creating an unprecedented moral problem: does man have the right, through his powerful technology, to destroy the biosphere that enables him to exist as a human being?

Modern man has a very lack of understanding considering the changes brought about in his life and in his environment caused by the applications of new technologies, which he adopts both willingly and recklessly. This is an obvious visual impairment, a kind of "technological myopia", with very serious consequences for both himself and his environment. Like the myopic, people can recognize quite well only what is in front of their eyes, while they see in a vague and completely distorted way what is happening at some distance.

Although being a loan from medical pathology, the transfer of "technological myopia" as a peculiar, massive and timeless human mental phenomenon allows us to shed light on the absurd but stubborn refusal of so many people to recognize and even less to accept man-made causes, as the already visible ecological disasters and climate change.

When not deliberately misleading, this visual-perceptual blindness may be explained by our inherent ease of making many technological advances today, combined with our equal difficulty in predicting the future impact of these technical wonders.

Moreover, things have gotten worse than in the past, since economically and technically advanced western societies stubbornly refuse to consider the far-reaching consequences of their choices, which are targeted solely to the present or the immediate future. However, even the poorest countries in the South, mired in the problems of daily survival, can also not think about tomorrow: whoever is forced to survive day by day cannot afford to think about tomorrow or the catastrophic consequences of environmental degradation, for example, of the Amazon forests.

The paradox of today's planetary ecology is that, for different reasons and with completely different consequences for themselves, the rich and the poor live exclusively in the present, indifferent to the distant future of life on our planet. Unfortunately, the catastrophic consequences of this peculiar "myopia" have multiplied in our days due to the incomparably greater technological - and therefore invasive - capabilities of humans.

Of course, one could argue that in the distant past too, the interests and prospects of action of most people were limited to their families and a very narrow time horizon. However, the crucial difference about today is that, in the past, the actions of people

in their environment were very limited and the changes or disasters they caused were assimilated, to a large extent, by nature, without permanently disturbing the balances of the basic ecosystems of the planet.

The innovations of modern science and their -until recently- inconceivable planetary applications threaten and require us to reconsider the reassuring delusion we have been cultivating for centuries about the linear and supposedly "progressive" course of the human condition from a dark past to the present (and a brighter future?) (Bauman, 2007).

Given the recent historical course of humanity towards a globalized and therefore total technocratic power of our kind, what is the point of focusing on the "old-fashioned" ethical-political problems that arise from the new and extremely subversive applications of the almighty, as we believe our technology to be?

Again, we need to make a reference to Hans Jonas, who has been systematically investigating these troubling questions since 1950. It should be noted that at that time, these matters were considered nothing but regional observations with questionable social value, because the intoxicating post-war and the exaggerated technological optimism prevailed. Jonas captured the subversive answers and the extremely disturbing conclusions of his many years of research in 1979, in his pre-mentioned leading book "The principle of responsibility" which was almost immediately recognized internationally as the "classic" text of modern ethical philosophy: a leading intellectual achievement project that laid the foundations for the ethics of modern technological civilization.

Until the end of World War II, Hans Jonas was a far more famous philosopher, working as a historian and researcher on the philosophical and theological preconditions of Gnosticism, an early and very dark theological movement. Later on, he focused on formulating and establishing new ethical criteria that he considered necessary for the timely (and valid!) assessment of the consequences of human technology.

Considering historically outdated and philosophically unfounded the traditional ethics, Jonas was able to form a modern ethical system, which, without being based on ontologically arbitrary idealistic and / or transcendental theological principles of traditional ethics, allows us to exclusively and rationally evaluate pragmatic criteria - the current applications of modern technology and their future consequences for humans and the biosphere.

However, why does Jonas consider all previous ethical approaches historically outdated and practically inapplicable? Because, given the unprecedented destructive power of today's human technology, "The gap between our ability to predict and our ability to act creates an unprecedented moral problem ... No previous morality has been able to calculate the universal condition of human life. . . ",

as already pointed out in the first chapter of "The principle of responsibility".

No religion, no philosophy and no ethical theory of the past has ever been confronted with the visible prospect of a planetary ecological catastrophe or with the repeatedly confirmed threat of widespread and irreversible biosphere damage, not because of a major natural disaster, such as a satellite approaching or falling to Earth, or constant earthquakes, or unpredictable climate change, but due to ignorance or, even worse, the unforgiving negligence of people when using their technology (Minteer, 2011).

Both Aristotle's ancient Greek "wisdom" and Kant's moral "categorical command" referred to individual actions or collective human behaviors rather than to man's relation to the "inanimate" material objects of ecosystems or to other "inferior" living beings. For Jonas, on the other hand, the impressive developments of the last two centuries in technology and especially the unprecedented technical possibilities acquired by the human species - from the manipulation of atomic energy to biotechnology and from information technology and artificial intelligence to man-made ecological-climatic catastrophes - now require not only a radical overhaul but also an extension of the concept of "ethical responsibility" of human beings both to life and to terrestrial planetary systems that allow different life forms to exist and survive.

Indeed, based on the ethical principle of "responsibility", Jonas examines and evaluates the physical, anthropological and therefore ethical-political consequences of the purely anthropocentric and short-sighted utilitarian imperative of technological "progress for progress" (Morris, 2014). The dominant modern-capitalist principle has led to the complete deregulation of human societies and in addition seriously threatens our survival on a ruined planet.

A fact that forced Jonas to challenge the traditional, fundamental and, until then, commonly accepted principle of traditional ethics, which argues that all moral evaluations of our behavior should never arise from the temporary, ever-changing conditions of our lives (historical, social or even biological), but only from the abstract, timeless and eternal moral values. The innovation of Jonas's "principle of responsibility" argues the exact opposite: the "due" and "good" of our ethics must always be grounded and correspond to our human and biological "being": no moral precept must violate or, even worse, to endanger or threaten our special human "nature", which is inevitably biological since it arose and exists only thanks to the biological evolution of our species (Rolston, 1975).

Here is how Jonas himself formulates the ethical command of responsibility, as a variation of the Kantian categorical imperative (Kant, 1998): "Act so that the consequences of your actions are compatible with the constant preservation of authentic human

life". The same principle negatively stated: Act so that the consequences of your actions do not destroy or jeopardize the possibility of such a life in the future. However, how do we know if or when our actions endanger or threaten some form of life?

The method he advocates is the now famous "heuristic of fear". This methodological choice is based on the repeatedly confirmed fact that people pay much more attention to what seriously threatens them and therefore to what causes them fear. So they react much faster and more effectively to evil than if they were facing something less painful and less frightening.

The explanation for this behavior, according to Jonas, is that this is how we are made to react to our biological evolution: "We know the stakes only when we know that something is at stake." If Jonas is right, then our only hope for tackling planetary deregulation, which we ourselves have caused and is seriously threatening our future, is to feel in time and be quite afraid of the impending catastrophe.

The belief that today's people can change the future has prevailed only since the Enlightenment. It should be understood that human well-being in the present is directly related to our descendants well-being as well. "When we look at the extent of current people's responsibilities to their successors, the relevant future generations include all those who can be affected as this is expected from the actions of "today's people" (Attfield, 2018).

After all, what is it that shapes our actions for future generations? Our moral attitude is based on the task of doing and shaping the present in order to improve of our lives in the coming years and consequently in the lives of future people. It should be noted that shaping our practices for the future is not about specific individuals, but all those living in the near future. The ability to recognize or not individuals who are the future generations is not an obstacle to the ethical attitude towards them.

A key deterrent to our action for future generations is uncertainty in estimating current interests against those that will arise in the future. For many, the treatments for the diseases that have been discovered so far may not have the same effectiveness in those diseases that will arise - or flood defenses may cease to be just as effective in the wider future - bearing in mind sea level rise.

Therefore, "if the interests of future people are a function of preferences then, due to the inability to predict their preferences, behavior and taste, we cannot - as we would like - take into account their interests, due to our ignorance. Some philosophers consider this fact to be an obstacle to the tradition of anyone whether we are referring to wildlife or natural beauty sites or works of art such as paintings, statues and musical compositions. Because, if the preferences of future people turn out not to overlap with our own, then our best efforts to transmit of a remarkable heritage will be useless" (Attfield, 2018).

Therefore, it is very likely that future people will demand and be satisfied with the aforementioned needs, or at least that they will play a primary role in their immediate interests. Naturally, the way we will approach the future needs of people should be universal. We must take care of their general needs, shaping a framework in which those who can be considered necessary for humanity will be included, at any time and place.

Consequently, ethics is strongly integrated into every practice and every human artifact. "In fact, responsibility is established by deciding our contribution to the materiality and symbolism of any of our actions."

By understanding how we should act and manage destructive nature at the core of creation, we will be able to approach and evolve our critique look, which is not directly related to the rules of ethics. Rather, it has to do with the idea, the construction practices of the past and the present, their normalized operation services, systems, etc. which are part of the cultural life and the irresponsible actions that waste in general (Bauman, 1997).

By observing and acknowledging the positive or non-positive effects of what has been said, we are obliged to put aside any economic and political forces and to bring to light their potential.

Having in mind the dual character of creativity and taking into account the its' destructive aspects, we need to get a more informed, critical look and sustainable character purpose. We must keep in mind that our actions do not lead to an end in themselves, to paraphrase the Kantian notion again, but are an imperfect process in support of a sustainable daily life (Papanoutsos, 1971).

To rephrase what is so crucial to human futures, we cannot base on restoring what has already been destroyed. However, many forces can be removed to avoid further disaster. Likewise, it is also possible for them to recover, recreate and invent numerous promoters of material, intangible and cultural support.

To conclude, we have to restore universal ethics taking into ethical account the non-human world of nature that was until recently relatively marginalized in philosophical thought and morally neutral. The "ethics of closeness" adapted more easily to the established in the "here and now" moral agents (Thompson, 1995). The objective change of today's world lies precisely in the expansion of the range of space and time consequences of moral choices involving earth-changing acts. Technical development and technological advances have made the effects (and side effects) of individual actions noticeably long-term and certainly beyond the limit of immediate locality. The modern requirement of moral reform goes back to the expansion of the moral universe in order to include, except the close Other, the distant Other, whose space-time distance no longer assures him that he will not be influenced by

actions they are unable to control or by actions they have already taken place in the past.

Reductively, the scope of liability can no longer be defined in terms nor be limited to liability solely for the human world. The miscalculation of the consequences of human action on the non-human world, on Nature, bring man before another type of moral responsibility, which will define the living conditions of the human species on the planet. The world of nature has long since ceased to be its morally neutral background human behavior and interaction, or otherwise the setting that hosts them moral actions of people; The gap between "micro-" and "macro-" ethics emerged as natural consequence of the expansion of the possible human consequences acts. Even the most vivid human imagination finds it difficult to monitor the consequences of human action in distant lands and subsequent generations. The increase in the scope of operations, however, is not accompanied by a corresponding increase in the ethical "capacity" of people, although the people now possess both the means and the knowledge to create, in fact, the meaning and significance of taking responsibility for the other. The evolution of science and knowledge that has allowed humanity to practice control over forces, tools and weapons of uncontrollable power, instead of assisting field of ethical knowledge, also destroyed these existing bases on which moral rules could be structured - in essence, it destroyed itself the idea of the rule.

It would be a blessing if the abilities that made humanity a producer of incalculable technological miracles to be able to give people the wisdom and method in order to perform what they know their ethical duty really is. The insight of the mind does not always go hand in hand with the sufficiency of desire; the dedication to the near goal and the excitement offered by the creation of the theoretically impossible to create, are the disorientating forces that "heal" the wounded from the lack of moral action consciousness. The unpleasant conclusion, which results from all the above reports, is that knowledge cannot be used as the basis for ethics restart of inactive subjects. Sadly, knowledge is set in service of global forces, which do not recognize environmental ethics as critical important component for the continuation of the cultural edifice.

The ethical project is the creation of a completely new kind of ethics, adapted to the new data of infinitely long space and time potential impact of current ethical choices and actions. The mental tools proposed in this direction are the "principle of uncertainty" and the "heuristic of fear" as defined by Jonas. According to these principles, we mean to repeat the practical rule that might offer the philosophical solution, if there is at some point the correspondent social and political will to make this choice of life and sustainability: "Act so that your actions and their consequences are compatible with the preservation of genuine human life". The

command is simple and pure; the difficulty lies perhaps in the definition of the genuine human life, versus survival at all costs. Inner dignity and responsibility for the Other can make the difference between biological life and decent -ethically speaking- life, and can prepare the ground for the power of the new vision of humanity.

Possibly our ethical defense is enclosed in the macro-moral extension of responsibility for the Other. In any case, the common denominator of both is the treaty of justice as a source qualitative feature of human existence opposed to universal catastrophe, the avoidance of which does not provide any guarantee for the future. The concept of justice must permeate the way of thinking of the postmodern man, recognizing new ethical criteria in location of outdated spatial and temporal continuities. In addition, of course, the fair way of thinking should be based on the concept of responsibility towards significant others. The concept of responsibility, as mentioned earlier, is not about the ordinary notion of responsibility, in which we are accountable for our actions, but the essential meaning in which everyone is responsible for their own well-being and also the prosperity of the close and distant others, sharing a mutual fundamental obligation: to treat others with dignity and respect.

This type of liability extends beyond (and above) from the neighbor, the near Other with whom we share intimacy in everyday life. The responsibility, to be complete and to be occupied by modern spirit, must embrace the spectrum of the distant Other as well the spectrum of the non-human world (nature) as a significant Other. If we were to follow an ethical code, the modern philosophy's simple suggestion would not be a bad idea; since any other scientific idea so far did not succeed, maybe the time has come to give philosophy a chance.

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Efficiency Production of Goods in Free Competitive Market and Sustainability Issues Enabled Through the CARE learning Methodology

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Abstract

This article proposes a design of student – driven learning activities for the course “Economy ECON101” of KwaZulu-Natal University (UKZN). Activities have been built in the context of PUAT European project. The proposed student-driven learning activities make use of CARE Learning Design Methodology as a tool for infusing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into multiple university courses. The basic objective of these student – driven learning activities is to prompt learners to explore the issue of externalities resulting from the production and consumption of goods and services and to address climate change as a negative externality problem. Learners will meet the concept of efficiency production of goods theoretically through the Demand-Supply diagram. They will show externalities on that diagram and they will discuss about them. They will correlate externalities with SDG 12 for sustainable consumption and production as well as with the SDG 13 for climate change. They will discuss about current issues about sustainability, from an economic perspective, and they will recognize economic policies about fighting climate change all over the world. The flexibility and adaptability of student – driven learning activities was one of the main goals in their design and thus, it is not presented as a ready and non-negotiable product for reproduction, but as a starting point and a methodology basis for the educators and learners to use it in the classroom.

Keywords: (CARE methodology, Externality, SDGs, Climate change, Learning activities)

The PUAT project

This article describes the design of student – driven learning activities for the course PADMICO “Introduction to Public Administration” of KwaZulu-Natal University (UKZN), built in the context of the PUAT project. The content of the course is summarized as follows: The nature and scope of politics, state, government, constitutions, democracy, introduction to Public Administration, the theory of Public Administration, introduction to Provincial and Local Government service delivery; and the impact of globalization.

PUAT is a European Commission ERASMUS plus Capacity Building in Higher Education (CBHE) funded project entitled “Professionalisation of Undergraduate Academic Teaching in Multiple Disciplines to Address SDGs”. The PUAT project focuses on four Universities in South Africa (<https://puat.frederick.ac.cy/>).

Considering the strategic importance of quality teaching and curriculum design at the undergraduate level among university staff for infusing Sustainable Development Goals in course curricula, the project aims to create and provide capacity building workshops, resources and opportunities that foster innovative and effective pedagogical practices among academic staff in multiple academic disciplines in South Africa. More specifically, among others, PUAT project aims to embed the Sustainable Development Goals in multiple disciplines nationally prioritized in South Africa such as environment, agriculture, biology and related sciences, engineering, health sciences in line with Bologna process (<https://puat.frederick.ac.cy/>).

Infusing Sustainable Development Goals with CARE Learning Design Methodology

The Sustainable Development Goals, also known as the SDGs or the 2030 Agenda, cover a wide range of

sustainability issues; highlighting local, national and international issues.

Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis (2020) suggest the CARE Learning Design Methodology as a tool for infusing SDGs in student-driven learning activities. Student-driven learning activities refer to a process where learners are active partners of education procedure. Moreover, learners and educators act as constructors of knowledge and agents of change (Makrakis, 2016). The CARE learning design method includes four stages: a) Conceptualise b) Activate c) Reflect and d) Engage.

Conceptualise is the stage that learners enter the process of understanding and they are engaged with the subject of the course. As members of a local community, they perceive the interdependence and impact of their actions both locally and on the global society.

Activate is the stage that learners based on their personal experience and furthermore based on their active participation acquire new knowledge and skills related to SDGs. In this stage the student-driven learning activities are also based on the 21st learning pillars (Makrakis & Kostoula-Makrakis, 2014) and the 10Cs enabled by ICTs (Makrakis & Kostoula-Makrakis, 2017)

Reflect is the stage that learners and educators approach deeper the subject. Mezirow (1991) describes how critical reflection involves a critique of the presuppositions on which our beliefs and assumptions have been built. So, this stage can help the participants to step-back and examine their knowledge and attitudes.

Engage is the stage where learners put the theory in practice. It is the stage where learners put all the knowledge they acquired in previous stages into practice with the vision of a sustainable future. Engagement takes place behaviorally, emotionally, cognitively and transformationally.

The flexibility and adaptability of student – driven learning activities was one of the main goals in their design and thus, it is not presented as a ready and non-negotiable product for reproduction. In contrast these activities can be a starting point and a methodology basis for the educators and learners to use them in the classroom (Vouzaxakis & Makrakis, 2017).

Efficiency production of goods and sustainability issues

In free market, when the price of a good adjusts to make quantity demanded equal to quantity supplied, the equilibrium quantity reflects the optimal allocation of resources to the production of that good. This condition is achieved when Marginal Benefit equals Marginal Cost ($MB=MC$) or when social surplus is maximum and is known as allocative efficiency. Long-run equilibrium in perfectly competitive markets meets two important conditions: allocative efficiency and productive efficiency. These two conditions have important implications. First, resources are allocated to their best alternative use. Second, they provide the maximum satisfaction attainable by society. Social efficiency is the optimal distribution of resources in society. Social efficiency occurs at an output where Marginal Social Benefit (MSB) = Marginal Social Cost. When in the Demand of a good the Marginal Private Benefit is equal to the Marginal Social Benefit ($D = MPB = MSB$) as well as when in the supply of the good the Marginal Private Cost is equal to the Marginal Social Cost ($S = MPC = MSC$) then the market succeeds the optimal social allocation of resources (Tragakes, 2009; Mankiw, 2015).

Externalities occur when producing or consuming a good cause an impact on third parties not directly related to the transaction. Externalities can either be positive or negative. They can also occur from production or consumption. A negative externality is a cost that is suffered by a third party as a result of an economic transaction. Externalities are also referred to as spillover effects, and a negative externality is also referred to as an external cost. If a good has a negative externality – ignored by individuals, then in a free market, we tend to get over-consumption and social inefficiency. With a positive externality, we ignore the benefits to third parties. So, the free-market equilibrium is less than the socially efficient level (Tragakes, 2009; Mankiw, 2015).

Externalities are closely linked to sustainability issues. Learners will realize that free market under specific circumstances fail to achieve allocative efficiency and this is correlated to sustainability issues. In market failure too much or too little of goods or services are produced and consumed from the point of view of what is socially most desirable. An externality occurs when the actions of consumers or producers rise negative or positive side-effects on other people who are not part of these actions. Market failure is correlated with sustainability issues as overfishing, pollution and climate change. For example, the problem of environmental pollution, created as a side-effect of production activity, can be analysed as a negative production externality (Tragakes, 2009). Therefore, there is a strong link between these student-driven learning activities with the SDG 12 for responsible production and consumption. But

moreover, there are strong connections with SDG 13 for climate change.

Public solutions to deal with negative production externalities rely on the ‘command’ approach, where the government uses its authority to enact legislation and regulations in the public’s interest (Tragakes, 2009; Candela, Castellani & Dieci, 2008). Furthermore, government can implement market-based policies such as taxes and subsidies to incentivize private decision makers to change their own behaviour (Mankiw, 2015; Mankiw & Taylor, 2011).

Alternatively, consumers can act collectively (e.g., with environmental and consumer organizations) to solve external problems e.g., changing consumer habits by buying environmentally friendly products and reducing demand for goods produced in an environmentally harmful way.

Therefore, there is a strong links between this student-driven learning activities with the SDG 12 for responsible production and consumption and SDG 13 for climate change.

The student-driven learning activity

In this student driven learning activity learners discuss about externalities and they correlate externalities with issues as sustainable production, consumption and climate change.

Learners meet the concept of efficiency production of goods theoretically through the Demand-Supply diagram and they will show externalities on that diagram. But moreover, they will discuss current controversial issues, from an economic perspective, such as meat tax as a policy for fighting climate change.

It is necessary for learners, for this student driven learning activity, to already know the Demand-Supply diagram as the concepts of Marginal private cost (MPC), Marginal Social Cost (MSC), Marginal Private Benefit (MPB) and Marginal Social Benefit (MSB).

The learning activities constitutes of the following parts: Part 1 - Into, part 2 - We learn, negative externalities of consumption and SDG 12, part 3: We learn, negative externalities and SDG 13 and Part 4 – Action.

Learning objectives

The basic objective of this student-driven learning activity is to prompt learners to explore the issue of externalities resulting from the production and consumption of goods and services and to address climate change as a negative externality problem.

It is worth pointing out that learning objectives will be emerging and refined along with the development of the learning activities. The overriding learning objectives for these activities are the following:

1. Explore the issue of externalities resulting from the production and consumption of goods and services.
2. Correlate negative externalities with climate change
3. Design demand-supply diagram showing the negative externality of consumption
4. Design demand-supply diagram showing the negative externality of production causing climate change
5. Recognize public policies for correcting negative externalities
6. Raise awareness for climate change

7. Discover and suggest public and private solutions for externalities

Activities

Activity Part 1: Intro

The overriding learning objective for this activity is the following:

1. Gain the interest of the learners
2. Reflect on Sustainable Development Goals 12 and 13

Step 1:

Show the video “Causes and Effects of Climate Change | National Geographic”

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G4H1N_yXBIA

Step 2:

Show the following video “2030- SDG 12- Responsible Consumption and Production- Ted talks”:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dR0dzsFxjXc>

Step 3:

Ask learners in pairs or groups to make a presentation about Climate Change and the SDG 13 or for SDG12 for sustainable production and consumption. Ask them to include in the presentation answers to the following questions

- How does production of goods and services contribute to global climate change?
- How does the production of goods affect the environment?
- What products contribute to climate change?
- How does consumerism affect the environment?

Step 4:

Each group of learners present their work of the previous step.

Step 5:

Initiate a Fishbowl discussion, where learners seated inside the “fishbowl” actively participate in a discussion by asking questions and sharing their opinions, while learners standing outside listen carefully to the ideas presented. Learn to listen and listen to learn can also be supplemented through this discussion. The prompting questions for this discussion could be:

- Can the decisions and actions of businesses or consumers affect other businesses and other consumers in the economy?
- What are the benefits and costs of producing a product for society?
- Is there a difference between the private and social benefit / cost of an activity?
- Is there a difference between the quantity of market and the socially desirable quantity?

Activity Part 2: We learn, negative externalities of consumption and SDG 12

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Explore the issue of externalities resulting from the production and consumption of goods and services.
2. Understand how individual lifestyle choices influence economic and environmental development.
3. Design demand-supply diagram showing the negative externality of consumption
4. Recognize public policies for correcting negative externalities

Step 1:

Ask learners in pairs or groups to draw a demand-supply diagram and discuss about how free market achieves allocative efficiency. When there is no externality, the free market leads to an optimum quantity where $MPC=MSC=MPB=MSB$. You can use the following figure.

Fig. 1 Free market achieves allocative efficiency.

Step 2:

Ask learners in pairs or groups to answer the following questions

- 1) Discuss in your group the negative social consequences of increased consumption of meat and / or sugar or increased use of plastic bags.
- 2) Draw a market demand and supply diagram for the good you selected in the previous question.
- 3) Is the Marginal Private Benefit (MPB) identified with the Marginal Social Benefit (MSB)? Which of the above relation is correct?

- a) $MPB = MSB$ or
- b) $MPB > MSB$ or
- c) $MPB < MSB$?

Why;

In these cases, the Marginal Private Benefit of the consumer enjoying the good is higher than the others who accept the negative effects of this activity ($D = MPB > MSB$).

Step 3:

Learners can compare their answers between groups. Educator can use the figure 2 and initiate a discussion about the curves, about the welfare loss and about the external cost. Moreover, ask learners to compare the Price Market (P_m) and the Price Optimum (P_{opt}) as well as Quantity Market (Q_m) and Quantity Optimum (Q_o).

Fig. 2 Negative externality of consumption.

Step 5:

Ask learners in pair or groups to read the following articles.

- “Meat tax could help meet climate goals”

<https://www.foodservicefootprint.com/meat-tax-could-help-meet-climate-goals/>

- “EU urged to adopt meat tax to tackle climate emergency”

<https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2020/feb/04/eu-meat-tax-climate-emergency>

Step 6:

Initiate a discussion based on the above articles. The prompting questions for this discussion could be:

- How does eating meat affect sustainability?
- Is meat industry sustainable?
- Is the consumption of meat a negative externality?
- How does eating meat negatively impact on the environment?
- Why some countries discuss about taxing meat? Which are the pros and cons of taxing meat?

Activity Part 3: We learn, negative externalities and SDG 13

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Understand deeper the SDG 13
2. Raise awareness for climate change
3. Correlate SDG 13 with the issue of externalities
4. Design demand-supply diagram showing the negative externality of production causing climate change

Step 1:

Ask learners in pairs or groups to draw a demand-supply diagram and discuss about how free market achieves allocative efficiency. When there is no externality, the free market leads to an optimum quantity where $MPC=MSC=MPB=MSB$.

Step 2:

Ask learners in pairs or groups to answer the following questions

- 1) Discuss in your group the negative social consequences of industry-related greenhouse gas emissions

- 2) Draw a market demand and supply diagram for a good which emits greenhouse gases

- 3) Is the Marginal Social Cost (MSC) identified with the Marginal Private Cost (MPC)? Which of the above relation is correct?

- a) $MSC=MPC$
- b) $MSC>MPC$
- c) $MSC<MPC$

Step 4:

Ask learners to share their answers with the whole class. Initiate a discussion about negative externalities of production and SDG 13. The prompting questions will be the following:

- Is climate change a negative externality?
- Why climate change is an externality?
- Why are carbon emissions a negative externality?

Step 4:

Ask learners in pairs or groups to use the previous demand-supply diagram with negative externality of production and to show how sustainable consumption can affect it.

Consumers can act collectively (e.g. with environmental and consumer organizations) to solve external problems e.g. changing consumer habits by buying environmentally friendly products and reducing demand for goods produced in an environmentally harmful way.

In this case the reduction in demand could therefore shift the demand curve to the left from D_1 to D_2 and achieve the socially optimal quantity.

Step 5:

Ask learners to present their diagrams in class and initiate a discussion about diagram. Educator can use the Figure 3.

Fig. 3 Sustainable consumption and negative externalities

Activity Part 4: Action

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Raise awareness for climate change
2. Investigate about existing solutions for externalities in production/consumption and climate change
3. Search for solutions for the above externalities in local, national and global policy strategies
4. Present their research and support their opinion

Step 1:

Show the following video: “How Africa is affected by climate change | DW News”

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8P1WG43VvgU>

Step 2:

Ask learners to read the article “Externalities of climate change and how to tackle them”

<https://www.grin.com/document/386156>

Step 3:

Ask learners in pairs or groups to investigate and make suggestions on how negative externalities could be reduced with the help of public administration or with private solutions if possible.

Step 4:

Students will create a presentation to share their research and ideas. Indicative issues of the presentation and discussion.

- What are the environmental effects of this practice?
- Does the government need to intervene in externalities?

- What role does government play in managing externalities?

- What can governments do to help reduce the negative externalities associated with the production and consumption of goods and services?

- Where does this practice occur? Does it happen in South Africa?

Step 5:

Give the learners the opportunity to reflect on the following questions taking into consideration all previous activities:

What did you finally learn from all these activities?

Did you find your personal experience about the subject useful for the educational process?

Did anything change your own ideas about SDG 12?

Explain what caused your ideas to change or why you think your ideas did not change.

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Ethical Entrepreneurship, Student–driven Learning Activities Infused with Sustainable Development Goals with the CARE Learning Methodology

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Abstract

This article proposes a design of student – driven learning activities for the course “Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development” of KwaZulu-Natal University (UKZN). Activities have been built in the context of the PUAT European project. The proposed student-driven learning activities make use of CARE Learning Design Methodology as a tool for infusing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into multiple university courses. The basic objective of these student – driven learning activities is to prompt learners to identify a problem that is important to them or to their local community and it is correlated with at least one SDG and propose an ethical business solution to the problem. Learners will discover that there is a clear conceptual relation between ethics and SDGs and between ethics and sustainability. They will analyse the ethical attitudes of South African business managers with regard to ethical business decision-making and they will undertake a limited range research in order to find a local ethical entrepreneur or business. The flexibility and adaptability of student – driven learning activities was one of the main goals in its design and thus, it is not presented as a ready and non-negotiable product for reproduction, but as a starting point and a methodology basis for the educators and learners to use it in the classroom.

Keywords: (CARE methodology, Ethical entrepreneurship, SDGs, ethics)

1. The PUAT project

This article describes the design of student – driven learning activities for the course ENTR7CO “Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development” of KwaZulu-Natal University (UKZN), built in the context of the PUAT project. The course covers the following topics: Understanding small business development; Entrepreneurial Leader and the Team; Resource Requirements; Managing the family business; Ethical decision Making and the Entrepreneur; Managing growth; Crises and recovery; Harvesting and beyond; Franchising; Business Management functions (general management, financial function, marketing, PR and sales function, operations and supply chain, purchasing function, information management, legal issues).

PUAT is a European Commission ERASMUS plus Capacity Building in Higher Education (CBHE) funded project entitled “Professionalisation of Undergraduate Academic Teaching in Multiple Disciplines to Address SDGs”. The PUAT project focuses on four Universities in South Africa (<https://puat.frederick.ac.cy/>).

Considering the strategic importance of the quality of teaching and curriculum design at the undergraduate level among university staff for infusing (SDGs) in course curricula, the project aims to create and provide capacity building workshops, resources and opportunities that foster innovative and effective pedagogical practices among academic staff

in multiple academic disciplines in South Africa. More specifically, among others, the PUAT project aims to embed the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in multiple disciplines nationally prioritized in South Africa such as environment, agriculture, biology and related sciences, engineering, health sciences in line with Bologna process (<https://puat.frederick.ac.cy/>).

2. Infusing Sustainable Development Goals with CARE Learning Design Methodology

The Sustainable Development Goals, also known as the SDGs or the 2030 Agenda, cover a wide range of sustainability issues; highlighting local, national and international issues.

Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis (2020) suggest the CARE Learning Design Methodology as a tool for infusing SDGs in student-driven learning activities. Student-driven learning activities refer to a process where learners are active partners of education procedure. Moreover, learners and educators act as constructors of knowledge and agents of change (Makrakis, 2016). The CARE learning design method includes four stages: a) Conceptualise b) Activate c) Reflect and d) Engage.

Conceptualise is the stage that learners enter the process of understanding and they are engaged with the subject of the course. As members of a local community, they perceive the interdependence and impact of their actions both locally and on the global society.

Activate is the stage that learners based on their personal experience and furthermore based on their active participation acquire new knowledge and skills related to SDGs. In this stage the student-driven learning activities are also based on the 21st learning pillars (Makrakis & Kostoula-

Makrakis, 2014) and the 10Cs enabled by ICTs (Makrakis & Kostoula-Makrakis, 2017)

Reflect is the stage that learners and educators approach deeper the subject. Mezirow (1991) describes how critical reflection involves a critique of the presuppositions on which our beliefs and assumptions have been built. So, this stage can help the participants to step-back and examine their knowledge and attitudes.

Engage is the stage where learners put the theory in practice. It is the stage where learners put all the knowledge they acquired in previous stages into practice with the vision of a sustainable future. Engagement takes place behaviorally, emotionally, cognitively and transformationally.

The flexibility and adaptability of student – driven learning activities was one of the main goals in its design and thus, it is not presented as a ready and non-negotiable product for reproduction. In contrast these activities can be a starting point and a methodology basis for the educators and learners to use them in the classroom (Vouzaxakis & Makrakis, 2017).

3. Ethical entrepreneurship and sustainability

According to the Markkula Center for Applied Ethics, *“ethics is based on standards of right and wrong that dictate what humans should do, usually in terms of rights, obligations, benefits to society, fairness, or specific virtues”*.

The relation between ethics and entrepreneurship is often concerned as a nexus between resources and targets of entrepreneurial activity (Wempe, 2005). For example, any small firms suffer from a relatively limited market presence and lack of support from suppliers and distributors. These characteristics often result in conditions that encourage or justify ethical compromises (Morris, Schindehutte, Walton et al, 2002). That’s why ethical entrepreneurship concerns all types and sizes of enterprises. One of the best-known ethical frameworks for business developed by Ken Blanchard and Norman Vincent Peale (1988), consists of three basic questions. These questions are: “It is legal?”, “Is it Fair?” and “How does it make me feel?” (Blanchard& Peale,1988).

The ethical entrepreneur concept involves businesses adopting innovative solutions to social problems while at the same time achieving the important business goal of profitability. Successful entrepreneurs often exhibit common behaviours and skills that they bring to their business, like establishing a shared vision; demonstrating initiative and innovation (Ardichvili, Mitchell & Jondle, 2009). Ethical entrepreneurs develop a deep understanding of the challenges faced by their communities and an ability to use innovation to create profitable enterprises that address these issues.

Using ethics in sustainability means that humans need to find an objective way to agree on what basic human needs are and whether these will be met for future generations (Levesque, 2019). This task is not simple by any means and has social, political and economic implications.

There is a clear conceptual relation between ethics and SDGs. Ethics are about “right things to be done for the

society even if not mandatory”, and SDGs are about “right goals for the society to be achieved even if not mandatory” (Balcerzak & Pelikánová, 2020). Moreover, there is a strong link between ethics and the concept of “sustainability justice”.

The concept of "sustainability justice" introduced by Makrakis (2016; 2017) reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy and culture. Sustainability justice is perceived as a process, which: 1) seeks fair (re)distribution of resources, opportunities, and responsibilities; 2) challenges the roots of oppression, exploitation and injustice; 3) empowers all people to raise their voice, needs and rights; and 4) constructs knowledge, empathy, compassion, social solidarity and action competences (Makrakis. 2018). Ethics can be applied within all four pillars of sustainability and should be present during the decision-making processes. and when analysing all possible perspectives of an issue. For example, economic justice and ethics considers issues like whether a product has been produced in an environment that provides fair wages and fair working conditions. It may also consider the resources that are used in producing a good and how they are used, and whether that resource may have been exploited in a way that is socially unjust (Levesque, 2019).

4. The student-driven learning activity

Learners are invited to search for information about an SDG and propose an ethical business solution to a problem of their local community.

Learners in these student-driven learning activities will watch videos with real cases of local eco-entrepreneurship, will discuss about what ethical decision mean and they will get familiar with the ethical framework by Ken Blanchard and Norman Vincent Peale. They will play with a free, non-profit web teaching tool designed to engage students to develop critical thinking and perspective-taking, practice empathy, and learn to make ethical decisions through fun and engaging gameplay. They will analyse the ethical attitudes of South African business managers with regard to ethical business decision-making and they will undertake a limited range research in order to find a local ethical entrepreneur or business. Finally in groups they will act as ethical entrepreneurs. They will identify a problem that is important to them or to their local community and it is correlated with at least one SDG. Then they will develop a business-based solution to that problem. The solution should involve the development of a business concept that addresses the problem while also meeting a range of business goals, including profitability. So, these student-driven learning activities can be correlated with all SDGs according to the socio-economic and environmental conditions of local community and of course according to the learners willing and needs.

The learning activities constitutes of the following parts: Part 1 – What we know, part 2 - We learn, part 3: We search, Part 4 – We act.

4.1 Learning objectives

The basic objective of this CARE scenario is to prompt learners to design an ethical business-based solution to a real problem and correlate ethical entrepreneurship with Sustainable Development Goals. Learners develop an understanding of how ethical entrepreneurs and businesses differ to other entrepreneurs and businesses.

It is worth pointing out that learning objectives will be emerging and refined along with the development of the learning activities. The overriding learning objectives for this scenario are the following:

1. Explore the issue of Ethical Entrepreneurship
2. Raise awareness for business ethical decisions
3. Correlate ethical entrepreneurship with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
4. Research for local ethical entrepreneurs
5. Develop a business-based solution to a real problem

4.2 Activities

Based on the brainstorming technique, participants using their mobile phones or a pc, are asked to fill in the words they think when they hear the concepts "Ethical Entrepreneurship ". The free WEB2 tool named answergarden (<https://answergarden.ch/>) creates a world cloud.

Ask learners in your class to fill in the following K.W.H.L. chart (Know; Want; How; Learned) about the subject of Ethical Entrepreneurship. Start with the "Know", "What" and "How" columns and save the "Learn" column for later. In pairs or groups, have students compare what they know and what they want to learn.

Activity Part 1: What we know

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Gain the interest of the learners
2. Recognize the previous knowledge of participants
3. Raise awareness for business ethical decisions

Step 1:

As a start in this part of activities invite learners to watch the following video "3 stories of local eco-entrepreneurship?" The video is from TEDx Midwest, where Majora Carter brings us the stories of three people who are saving their own communities while saving the planet.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jyYjI7zQlaA>

Ask learners to write words, phrases or questions that come to their mind while watching the video in their diaries / journals.

Step 2:

Initiate a Fishbowl discussion, where learners seated inside the "fishbowl" actively participate in a discussion by asking questions and sharing their opinions, while learners standing outside listen carefully to the ideas presented. Learning to listen and listen to learn can also be supplemented through this discussion. The prompting questions for this discussion would be: Who is an ethical entrepreneur? What does ethical decision mean? Why does our society need ethical Entrepreneurship?

Activity Part 2: We play - we learn

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Develop critical thinking and learn to make ethical decisions

2. Understand the ethical framework by Ken Blanchard and Norman Vincent Peale

3. Recognize the ethical attitudes of South African business managers

Step 1:

Invite learners to play Quandary. Quandary is a free, nonprofit web teaching tool designed to engage students to develop critical thinking and perspective-taking, practice empathy, and learn to make ethical decisions through fun and engaging gameplay.

<https://www.quandarygame.org/>

Step 2:

Based on the Quandary game, initiate a discussion about the ethical decisions of the entrepreneur/business. You can use the best-known ethical framework by Ken Blanchard and Norman Vincent Peale. It is also one of the simplest. The framework consists of three questions, as described below. The questions first appeared in their 1988 book, "The Power of Ethical Management."

Fig. 1: Ethical Decision Making
(<https://www.floridatechonline.com/blog/business/3-frameworks-for-ethical-decision-making/>)

Step 3:

Ask learners to read the following article: "An analysis of the ethical attitudes of South African business managers with regard to ethical business decision-making: Trends from 2007 to 2019"

<https://www.litnet.co.za/an-analysis-of-the-ethical-attitudes-of-south-african-business-managers-with-regard-to-ethical-business-decision-making-trends-from-2007-to-2019/>

Step 4:

Ask learners to complete the "L" column of their K-W-H-L chart. Finally, in pairs or groups, have students compare what they wanted to learn and what they have learned, identifying if there are remaining things to learn.

Activity Part 3: We search

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Research in order to find a local ethical entrepreneur or business

2. Correlate ethical entrepreneurship and Ethical decision Making with Sustainable Development Goals

Step 1:

Ask learners in small groups to undertake a limited range research in order to find a local ethical entrepreneur or business. If they can't find a local ethical entrepreneur or business, they can pick one of the three below:

- Who Gives a Crap (<https://au.whogivesacrap.org/>)
- Words with Heart (<https://wordswithheart.com/>)
- Pollinate Group (<https://pollinategroup.org/>).

(Source: <https://www.coolaustralia.org/activity/self-directed-billboard-for-an-ethical-business/>)

Moreover, they can choose to search one of the cases the article below presents (<https://www.greatworklife.com/ethical-decision-making-in-business-examples/>)

Step 2:

Ask each group to present the ethical entrepreneur or business they have chosen.

- What problem did they identify that they wanted to address? How did they/are they addressing this problem?
- What SDG does the project you have chosen serve?
- How does this entrepreneur/business/project make money?
- How does it help people and/or the environment?
- What do you find interesting about this entrepreneur/business/project?
- Is this a good example of ethical entrepreneurship?

Explain.

- Can we use SDG as a framework for ethical entrepreneurship?
- Why is their story interesting or inspiring?

Step 3:

Ask learners to complete again the “L” column of their K-W-H-L chart. They can compare what they wanted to learn and what they have learned.

Activity Part 4: We act

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Correlate ethical entrepreneurship with Sustainable Development Goals
2. Develop a business-based solution to a real problem
3. Reflect on what they have learned about Ethical Entrepreneurship

Step 1:

Ask learners in pairs or groups to select an SDG. As them to find information about their community correlated with the SDG they select. They can present to the whole class the information they found.

Step 2:

Ask learners, in pairs or groups, to imagine that they are ethical entrepreneurs. Ask them to identify a problem that is important to them and then develop a business-based solution to that problem. They can choose a social or environmental problem that personally interests them.

Step 3:

Ask learners to design a business solution to the problem they have chosen. The solution is not about applying aid or charity to the problem. Instead, it should involve the development of a business concept that addresses the problem while also meeting a range of business goals, including profitability.

Step 4:

Ask learners to present their business ideas and their ethical point of view. Use the following prompts to lead a brief dialogue with learners:

- Describe the problem you have chosen?
- What do you hope to achieve through your business idea?
- How will your idea solve the environmental or social problem you identified?
- What Sustainable Development Goal does your business idea serve?
- Does your business meet the following basic criteria for ethical entrepreneurship? Is it legal? Is it fair?
- How does it make you feel?

Step 5:

Give the learners the opportunity to reflect on the following questions taking into consideration all previous activities:

- What did you finally learn from all these activities?
- Did you find your personal experience about the subject useful for the educational process?
- What did you finally learn from all these activities?
- Did anything change your own ideas about SDGs and ethical entrepreneurship?
- Explain what caused your ideas to change or why you think your ideas did not change.

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Ethics in Management, SDGs and Greenwashing – driven Learning Activities Infused with Sustainable Development Goals with the CARE Learning Methodology

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Abstract

This article proposes a design of student – driven learning activities for the course “Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development” of KwaZulu-Natal University (UKZN). Activities have been built in the context of PUAT European project. The proposed student-driven learning activities make use of CARE Learning Design Methodology as a tool for infusing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into multiple university courses. The basic objective of these student – driven learning activities is to prompt learners to correlate Ethics in management with Sustainable Development Goals. Learners will discover that there is a clear conceptual relation between ethics and SDGs and between ethics and management. Learners are invited to search and discuss about ethics in management and to design a social campaign about anti-greenwashing and SDGs. The flexibility and adaptability of student – driven learning activities was one of the main goals in its design and thus, it is not presented as a ready and non-negotiable product for reproduction, but as a starting point and a methodology basis for the educators and learners to use them in the classroom.

Keywords: (CARE methodology, Ethical entrepreneurship, SDGs, ethics)

1. The PUAT project

This article describes the design of student – driven learning activities for the course ENTR7CO “Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development” of KwaZulu-Natal University (UKZN), built in the context of PUAT project. The course covers the following topics: Understanding small business development; Entrepreneurial Leader and the Team; Resource Requirements; Managing the family business; Ethical decision Making and the Entrepreneur; Managing growth; Crises and recovery; Harvesting and beyond; Franchising; Business Management functions (general management, financial function, marketing, PR and sales function, operations and supply chain, purchasing function, information management, legal issues).

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Considering the strategic importance of quality teaching and curriculum design at the undergraduate level among university staff for infusing (SDGs) in course curricula, the project aims to create and provide capacity building workshops, resources and opportunities that foster innovative and effective pedagogical practices among academic staff in multiple academic disciplines in South Africa. More specifically, among others, PUAT project aims to embed the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in multiple disciplines nationally prioritized in South Africa

such as environment, agriculture, biology and related sciences, engineering, health sciences in line with Bologna process (<https://puat.frederick.ac.cy/>).

2. Infusing Sustainable Development Goals with CARE Learning Design Methodology

The Sustainable Development Goals, also known as the SDGs or the 2030 Agenda, cover a wide range of sustainability issues; highlighting local, national and international issues.

Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis (2020) suggest the CARE Learning Design Methodology as a tool for infusing SDGs in student-driven learning activities. Student-driven learning activities refer to a process where learners are active partners of education procedure. Moreover, learners and educators act as constructors of knowledge and agents of change (Makrakis, 2016). The CARE learning design method includes four stages: a) Conceptualise b) Activate c) Reflect and d) Engage.

Conceptualise is the stage that learners enter the process of understanding and they are engaged with the subject of the course. As members of a local community, they perceive the interdependence and impact of their actions both locally and on the global society.

Activate is the stage that learners based on their personal experience and furthermore based on their active participation acquire new knowledge and skills related to SDGs. In this stage the student-driven learning activities are also based on the 21st learning pillars (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2014) and the 10Cs enabled by ICTs (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2017)

Reflect is the stage where learners and educators approach deeper the subject. Mezirow (1991) describes how critical reflection involves a critique of the presuppositions on which our beliefs and assumptions have been built. So, this stage can help the participants to step-back and examine their knowledge and attitudes.

Engage is the stage where learners put the theory in practice. It is the stage where learners put all the knowledge they acquired in previous stages into practice with the vision of a sustainable future. Engagement takes place behaviorally, emotionally, cognitively and transformationally.

The flexibility and adaptability of student – driven learning activities was one of the main goals in its design and thus, it is not presented as a ready and non-negotiable product for reproduction. In contrast these activities can be a starting point and a methodology basis for the educators and learners to use them in the classroom (Vouzaxakis & Makrakis, 2017).

3. Ethics in management, SDGs and greenwashing

According to the Markkula Center for Applied Ethics, “*ethics is based on standards of right and wrong that dictate what humans should do, usually in terms of rights, obligations, benefits to society, fairness, or specific virtues*”.

Ethics in management is related to Corporate Social Responsiveness (CSR) of a firm. CSR is usually defined as the “*type of international private business self-regulation*” (Sheehy, 2015) and covers organizational policies and practices but also ethical strategies (Torelli, 2021). For example, if a company adopts in its CSR policies a commitment to reduce direct impacts on the fauna and flora of the external environment in which it operates, it will have adopted a behavior that is truly sustainable but also ethical (Torelli, 2021). In contrast if there is a lack of respect for basic ethics in management behavior, then CSR practices and processes will be inappropriate and ineffective and it will not be possible to make discernible progress towards meeting sustainability objectives (Fassin et al., 2011; Pedersen, 2010; Rushton, 2002).

Using ethics in sustainability means that humans need to find an objective way to agree on what basic human needs are and whether these will be met for future generations (Levesque, 2019). This task is not simple and has social, political and economic implications. But SDGs poses managers with an already defined framework of action and strategy. In the past voluntariness was the basic feature of ethical and sustainability actions but now SDGs represent an important basic analysis of the areas (economic-social-environmental) where managers and companies can ethically act. Ethics has been proposed and placed at the forefront of the path towards sustainability and responsibility (Torelli, 2021).

The concept of greenwashing is linked to ethics is. It is a term that can be approached from different views and so there are many studies that attempt to define greenwashing (Berrone et al., 2017; Blome et al., 2017; Delmas & Burbano, 2011; Wolniak, 2016). The Oxford English Dictionary defines it as: “*Disinformation disseminated by an*

organization so as to present an environmentally responsible public image; a public image of environmental responsibility promulgated by or for an organization, etc., but perceived as being unfounded or intentionally misleading” (<https://www.oed.com/>). Greenwashing is an unethical practice used by companies to make more money, and solicit trust (Delmas & Burbano, 2011). Greenwashing prevents achieving SDGs because when companies greenwash, there is less transparency and accuracy on sustainability metrics. In contrast companies with ethics codes are less likely to greenwash (Delmas & Burbano, 2011).

4. The student-driven learning activity

Learners are invited to search and discuss about ethics in management and to design a social campaign about anti-greenwashing and SDGs.

Learners in these student-driven learning activities will discuss about what ethical decision mean and they will be familiar with the ethical framework by Ken Blanchard and Norman Vincent Peale. They will play with a free, non-profit web teaching tool designed to engage students to develop critical thinking and perspective-taking, practice empathy, and learn to make ethical decisions through fun and engaging gameplay. They will correlate ethics in management with Sustainable Development Goals and they will be familiar with real ethics cases studies. Moreover, they discuss about greenwashing and ethics and they will meet real cases of greenwashing in South Africa and all over the world. Learners are prompt to design a social campaign about anti-greenwashing and SDGs for their local community.

The learning activities constitutes of the following parts: Part 1 – What we know, part 2 – We play, we learn, part 3: Ethics and SDGs 2, Part 4 - Greenwashing and ethics, we act.

4.3 Learning objectives

It is worth pointing out that learning objectives will be emerging and refined along with the development of the learning activities. The overriding learning objectives for this scenario are the following:

1. Explore the issue of Ethics in management
2. Raise awareness for business ethical decisions
3. Correlate ethics with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
4. Develop critical thinking and learn to make ethical decisions
5. Understand the ethical framework by Ken Blanchard and Norman Vincent Peale
6. Recognize the normative, individualism, and justice approaches for management ethics
7. Recognize the ethical attitudes of South African business managers
8. Explore the issue of greenwashing
9. Raise awareness for the problem of greenwashing
10. Correlate greenwashing with ethics and sustainability
11. Meet real cases of greenwashing

12. Design an anti-greenwashing campaign correlated with SDGs

4.4 Activities

Activity Part 1: What we know

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Gain the interest of the learners
2. Recognize the previous knowledge of the participants
3. Raise awareness for ethics in management

Step 1:

Based on the brainstorming technique, participants using their mobile phones or a pc, are asked to fill in the words they think when they hear the concepts "Management Ethics - Sustainable Development". Ask learners to do the same when they hear the concept "Green Washing". The free WEB2 tool named answergarden (<https://answergarden.ch/>) creates a word cloud. Initiate a short discuss about the word clouds that have been created.

Step 2:

Ask learners in your class to fill in the following K.W.H.L. chart (Know; Want; How; Learned) about the subject of Ethical Entrepreneurship. Start with the "Know", "What" and "How" columns and save the "Learn" column for later. In pairs or groups, have students compare what they know and what they want to learn.

Step 3:

After watching the video initiate a Fishbowl discussion, where learners seated inside the "fishbowl" actively participate in a discussion by asking questions and sharing their opinions, while learners standing outside listen carefully to the ideas presented. Learning to listen and listen to learn can also be supplemented through this discussion. The prompting questions for this discussion would be: Why are ethics important in management? What does ethical decision mean?

Activity Part 2: we play - we learn

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Develop critical thinking and learn to make ethical decisions
2. Understand the ethical framework by Ken Blanchard and Norman Vincent Peale
3. Recognize the normative, individualism, and justice approaches for management ethics
4. Recognize the ethical attitudes of South African business managers

Step 1:

Invite learners to watch the following video: "Ethics in Management" by GreggU.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0vScvaAw56g>

Normative, individualism, and justice approaches are briefly analyzed. Initiate a short discussion about the above approaches.

Step 2:

Invite learners to play Quandary. Quandary is a free, nonprofit web teaching tool designed to engage students to develop critical thinking and perspective-taking, practice

empathy, and learn to make ethical decisions through fun and engaging gameplay.

<https://www.quandarygame.org/>

Step 3:

Based on the Quandary game, initiate a discussion about the ethical decisions. You can use the best-known ethical framework by Ken Blanchard and Norman Vincent Peale. It is also one of the simplest. The framework consists of three questions, as described below. The questions first appeared in their book, "The Power of Ethical Management."

Fig.1: Ethical Decision Making
(<https://www.floridatechonline.com/blog/business/3-frameworks-for-ethical-decision-making/>)

Step 4:

Ask learners to read the following article: "An analysis of the ethical attitudes of South African business managers with regard to ethical business decision-making: Trends from 2007 to 2019".

<https://www.litnet.co.za/an-analysis-of-the-ethical-attitudes-of-south-african-business-managers-with-regard-to-ethical-business-decision-making-trends-from-2007-to-2019/>

Step 5:

Ask learners to complete the "L" column of their K-W-H-L chart. Finally, in pairs or groups, have students compare what they wanted to learn and what they have learned, identifying if there are remaining things to learn.

Activity Part 3: Ethics and SDGs

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Correlate ethics in management with Sustainable Development Goals
2. Be familiar with ethics cases studies

Step 1:

Invite learners to watch the video: "Business Ethics – Sustainability" by the Supply Chain Sustainability School.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Sx4laIJKCVY>

This video connects Business Ethics with Sustainability and helps learners recognize the correlation.

Step 2:

Invite learners to watch the video: "Understanding Ethics in Management" by the GreggU

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MUSNKjx9zt0>

This course defines ethics in management and explain how ethical behaviour plays an important role in the life of manager's today.

Step 3:

Invite learners in pairs or groups to study the UN Global Compact–Accenture CEO Study on Sustainability 2019. This study deals with the business contribution to the Sustainable Development Goals conducted by the United Nations Global Compact and Accenture Strategy. More than 1,000 top executives across 21 industries and 99 countries candidly reflect on the opportunities and challenges to sustainability since the launch of the Global Goals. While CEOs acknowledge the opportunity for competitive advantage through sustainability efforts and report pockets of progress, they recognize that the business community could—and should—be making a far greater contribution to achieving a sustainable global economy by 2030. <https://www.accenture.com/us/en/insights/strategy/ungccoesstudy>

Alternatively invite learners to watch the webinar on Key Findings from the 2019 CEO Study on Sustainability: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C3x5Q3BfacY>

Presented by Lise Kingo, CEO & Executive Director of the UN Global Compact and Peter Lacy, Senior Managing Director of Accenture Strategy, discover insights drawn from 1,000 CEOs across 21 industries and 99 countries, reflecting over 100 in-depth interviews and 1,500-plus senior business leaders.

Step 4:

Invite learners to watch the video “Ethics Case Study: It was Just a Careless Mistake” of the Institute of Singapore Chartered Accountants.

About the case: “David, the Finance Director of a company was alerted to the fact that major customer, Super Pte Ltd, had returned most of the goods shipped to them near the end of the last year. While David is proposing adjustments to the financial statements in order to reflect the return, his proposal is faced with stiff opposition from within his company. Would he be able to handle the situation ethically?”

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZwFyASop8nc&list=RDLVZwFyASop8nc&start_radio=1&rv=ZwFyASop8nc&t=2

Step 5:

Invite learners to watch the video “Ethics Case Study: Do Not Let Your Friends Suffer” of Institute of Singapore Chartered Accountants.

About the case: “John, a newly promoted audit partner in a mid-sized audit firm is having a meeting with Mr Tan, the Chairman of KS Pte Ltd, one of his major clients. During the meeting, a disagreement over the accounting treatment of KS Pte Ltd’s accounts arose, invariably posing an ethical dilemma for John. How would he be able to handle the situation ethically? Watch the video to find out.” <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KWz7ekIL9cI&list=RDLVZwFyASop8nc&index=2>

Step 6:

Ask learners in pairs or groups to make a presentation about ethics and SDGs making use of the above cases and the study of step 3. They have to select one of the following SDG: 8,10,12 and correlate it with ethics. Each group can make a presentation to the whole class. Coordinate a discussion about the conclusions of the presentations.

Step 7:

Ask learners to complete again the “L” column of their K-W-H-L chart. They can compare what they wanted to learn and what they have learned.

Activity Part 4: Greenwashing and ethics, we act

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Explore the issue of greenwashing
2. Raise awareness for the problem of greenwashing
3. Correlate greenwashing with ethics and sustainability
4. Meet real cases of greenwashing
5. Design an anti-greenwashing campaign correlated with SDGs

Step 1:

Invite learners to read the following article in euronews: “What is greenwashing and why is it a problem?” <https://www.euronews.com/green/2020/09/09/what-is-greenwashing-and-why-is-it-a-problem>

Step 2:

Invite learners to read the following article “Greenwashing a reality in South Africa” <https://www.environment.co.za/environmental-issues-news/greenwashing-a-reality-in-south-africa.html>

Step 3:

Initiate a Fishbowl discussion, where learners seated inside the “fishbowl” actively participate in a discussion by asking questions and sharing their opinions, while learners standing outside listen carefully to the ideas presented. Learning to listen and listen to learn can also be supplemented through this discussion. The prompting questions for this discussion would be:

- How do you identify greenwashing?
- What is greenwashing in business ethics?
- Is greenwashing an ethical issue?
- Why is greenwashing important?
- Why is greenwashing harmful?
- Why is greenwashing unethical?
- Why greenwashing might be unethical and a problem for a business?
- What is the problem with greenwashing?

Step 4:

Ask learners to write a short persuasive text (about 400 words) that either supports or opposes the statement “Ethics in Management can be supported by SDGs”. The text should include an introduction that states their position clearly, at least one piece of evidence to support their stance, and a conclusion that restates the topic and summarizes their main points.

Step 5:

Have learners pair up and ask them to exchange with each other their texts and comment on them. Then each learner keeps his own text with the comments of his/her classmate.

Step 6:

Ask learners in pairs or groups to design a social campaign about anti-greenwashing and SDGs. The outcomes of the campaign should be: Objectives of the campaign:

- The name of the campaign
- A hashtag
- A logo and colour scheme
- A slogan

- Images to use in online resources and printed materials

Step 7:

Initiate a discussion so that order learners will reflect about all the previous activities. Ask learners to fill the 'L' column of their K.W.H.L. chart (Know; Want; How; Learned).

Step 8:

Give the learners the opportunity to reflect on the following questions taking into consideration all previous activities:

- What did you finally learn from all these activities?
- Did you find your personal experience about the subject useful for the educational process?
- What did you finally learn from all these activities?
- Did anything change your own ideas about SDGs and ethics in management?
- Explain what caused your ideas to change or why you think your ideas did not change.

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Externalities and Public Solutions, Student – driven Learning Activities Infused with Sustainable Development Goals with the CARE Learning Methodology

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Abstract

This article proposes a design of student – driven learning activities for the course “Introduction to Public Administration” of KwaZulu-Natal University (UKZN). Activities have been built in the context of PUAT European project. The proposed student-driven learning activities make use of CARE Learning Design Methodology as a tool for infusing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into multiple university courses. The basic objective of these student – driven learning activities is to prompt learners to explore the issue of externalities and to approach experimentally the impact of business on the physical, economic and social environment. Learners will discover the concept of externalities and the “tragedy of commons” through an experiential game. They will correlate externalities with SDG 12 for sustainable consumption and production as well with the SDG 13 for climate change. They will search and be aware for real externalities cases in South Africa. They will also search for and suggest public solutions for the issue of externalities and finally they will reflect about their previous knowledge and attitudes about sustainability issues of their local community. The flexibility and adaptability of student – driven learning activities was one of the main goals in their design and thus, it is not presented as a ready and non-negotiable product for reproduction, but as a starting point and a methodology basis for the educators and learners to use them in the classroom.

Keywords: (CARE methodology, Externality, SDGs, Learning activities)

1. The PUAT project

This article describes the design of student – driven learning activities for the course PADMICO “Introduction to Public Administration” of KwaZulu-Natal University (UKZN), built in the context of PUAT project. The content of the course is summarized as follows: The nature and scope of politics, state, government, constitutions, democracy, introduction to Public Administration, the theory of Public Administration, introduction to Provincial and Local Government service delivery; and the impact of globalization.

PUAT is a European Commission ERASMUS plus Capacity Building in Higher Education (CBHE) funded project entitled “Professionalisation of Undergraduate Academic Teaching in Multiple Disciplines to Address SDGs”. The PUAT project focuses on four Universities in South Africa (<https://puat.frederick.ac.cy/>).

Considering the strategic importance of quality teaching and curriculum design at the undergraduate level among university staff for infusing Sustainable Development Goals in course curricula, the project aims to create and provide capacity building workshops, resources and opportunities that foster innovative and effective pedagogical practices among academic staff in multiple academic disciplines in South Africa. More specifically, among others, PUAT project aims to embed the Sustainable Development Goals in multiple disciplines nationally prioritized in South Africa such as environment, agriculture, biology and related sciences, engineering, health sciences in line with Bologna process (<https://puat.frederick.ac.cy/>).

2. Infusing Sustainable Development Goals with CARE Learning Design Methodology

The Sustainable Development Goals, also known as the SDGs or the 2030 Agenda, cover a wide range of sustainability issues; highlighting local, national and international issues.

Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis (2020) suggest the CARE Learning Design Methodology as a tool for infusing SDGs in student-driven learning activities. Student-driven learning activities refer to a process where learners are active partners of education procedure. Moreover, learners and educators act as constructors of knowledge and agents of change (Makrakis, 2016). The CARE learning design method includes four stages: a) Conceptualise b) Activate c) Reflect and d) Engage.

Conceptualise is the stage that learners enter the process of understanding and they are engaged with the subject of the course. As members of a local community, they perceive the interdependence and impact of their actions both locally and on the global society.

Activate is the stage that learners based on their personal experience and furthermore based on their active participation acquire new knowledge and skills related to SDGs. In this stage the student-driven learning activities are also based on the 21st learning pillars (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2014) and the 10Cs enabled by ICTs (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2017)

Reflect is the stage that learners and educators approach deeper the subject. Mezirow (1991) describes how critical reflection involves a critique of the presuppositions on which our beliefs and assumptions have been built. So, this stage

can help the participants to step-back and examine their knowledge and attitudes.

Engage is the stage where learners put the theory in practice. It is the stage where learners put all the knowledge they acquired in previous stages into practice with the vision of a sustainable future. Engagement takes place behaviorally, emotionally, cognitively and transformationally.

The flexibility and adaptability of student – driven learning activities was one of the main goals in their design and thus, it is not presented as a ready and non-negotiable product for reproduction. In contrast these activities can be a starting point and a methodology basis for the educators and learners to use them in the classroom (Vouzaxakis & Makrakis, 2017).

3. Negative Externalities and sustainability issues

In this Student-Driven learning activities learners will meet the concept of externalities or external cost. Externalities are created when the actions of businesses have unintentional spillover effects (or costs) on third parties who are not directly involved in the production or consumption of their product. These externalities can be either positive or negative and they can result from either the production or consumption of a good or service. Negative externalities of production refer to external costs created by producers. For example, the problem of environmental pollution, created as a side-effect of production activity, can be analysed as a negative production externality (Tragakes, 2009). So, the significant problem of climate change, arising from the production of goods and the delivery of services, can be approached as negative external production.

Moreover, learners will discover the problem of “tragedy of commons”. Garrett Hardin (1968) published an article where through an example of a common-access sheep-grazing pasture he described the consequences when a finite resource is treated as common property and can be overused. In the example he described that the breeders are motivated to add cows to the common pasture but these exhausts the resources of the finite pasture. So, what is economically rational for each breeder is irrational all of them. Failure to manage shared resource markets can be seen in environmental issues such as pollution and overfishing.

Public solutions to deal with negative production externalities rely on the ‘command’ approach, where the government uses its authority to enact legislation and regulations in the public’s interest (Tragakes, 2009; Candela, Castellani & Dieci, 2008). Alternatively, government implements market-based policies such as taxes and subsidies to incentivize private decision makers to change their own behaviour (Mankiw, 2015; Mankiw & Taylor, 2011).

Learners will discover the “tragedy of the commons” through an experiential game that has been developed and tested with encouraging results in the formation of knowledge and skills but also in the formation of a positive attitudes towards sustainability issues. (Vouzaxakis & Makrakis, 2017). The proposed student-driven learning

activities use the tragedy of commons and negative externalities to bring learners in contact with the problem of over-exploitation and resource depletion. Therefore, there is a strong link between these student-driven learning activities with the SDG 12 for responsible production and consumption. But moreover, there are strong connections with SDG 13 for climate change.

4. The student-driven learning activity

The basic idea of this student-driven learning activity applying the CARE learning design is that in a society (groups of learners) some iron industries pollute a lake in which fish farms operate. Through an experiential game students will discover the concept of external cost because the cost of pollution is not integrated into the private costs of industries. Learners will also discover the "tragedy of commons" because fish farms can overfish.

Learners are divided into groups - societies (Society A, Society B, Society C) of six people (depending on the number of learners, a group may have more members so that everyone will participate in the game or we may create more societies of six). We assign the following roles per group - Society: 4 students undertake the management of four iron industrial units: industry a, industry b, industry c and industry d. Two students take on the role of 2 fish farming units: Fish farming a, Fish farming b.

Each community-group gathers at a point in the classroom to start the game. We will play a game in three rounds and then we will discuss the results. We need 12 pieces of iron and 12 pieces of fish (it can be anything we want, e.g., 12 and 12 pieces of different coloured paper, or 12 candies and 12 chocolates). In each round each student must produce at least one production unit otherwise he must leave the game.

The learning activities constitutes of the following parts: Part 1 - Into, part 2 - We play / We learn, part 3: SDG 12 and South Africa and Part 4 - We suggest.

4.5 Learning objectives

The basic objective of this CARE scenario is to prompt learners to explore the issue of externalities via an experiential game. Learners should correlate the issue of externalities and reflect on 12th Sustainable Development Goal.

It is worth pointing out that learning objectives will be emerging and refined along with the development of the learning activities. The overriding learning objectives for these activities are the following:

1. Discover the concept of externalities through an experiential game
2. Explore the issue of externalities resulting from the production and consumption of goods and services.
3. Recognize the problem of managing shared resources
4. Discover and suggest public solutions for externalities

4.6 Experiential game rules

Round A:

Phase 1: Industries

We give to the Industrial Units 12 pieces of iron (in a pile, in front of the 4 students) that represent the maximum possible production of all industries.

Each student can produce (take secretly) as many pieces as he wants from the pile of his team (at least 1) and keep them. In the next round the pile (the total production) will be renewed with as many pieces as the ones left in the middle. If they get all 12 pieces of iron they have run out of resources and cannot produce in the next round. For example, if students produce (take): industry "a" take 2 pieces

industry "b": 1 piece

industry "c": 3 pieces

industry "d": 2 pieces

Total pieces produced: $2 + 1 + 3 + 2 = 8$

Remaining: $12 - 8 = 4$ pieces in the pile. (In the next round they will be added to the 4 pieces but 4). Available for production in the next round: 8 pieces.

Phase B: Fish farms

There are 12 fish that represent the maximum possible production of all fish farms. However, the industrial iron units with their production pollute the lake where the fish farms are located. For every unit of iron production, 1 unit of fish is lost due to the pollution in the lake.

So, we give to the fish farms (in the pile, in front of the 2 students): 12 fish minus the pieces of iron produced.

In our example: $12 \text{ fish} - 8 \text{ (pieces of iron were produced so } 8 \text{ fish less in the lake)} = 4 \text{ fish available as total production.}$

Each student can produce (take secretly) as many pieces as he wants from the pile of his team (at least 1) and keep them. In the next round, however, the pile (the total production) will be renewed with as many pieces as the ones left in the middle. That is, if the students take all the fish, they exhaust the productive possibilities of the lake because they did not have time to renew the fish. For example, if students take from the pile:

Fish farming "a": 1 fish

Fish farming "b": 1 fish

Total pieces produced: $1 + 1 = 2$ fish

Remaining: $4 - 2 = 2$ fish in the pile.

In the next round, 2 pieces will be added but 2 and 4 fish will be available for production.

Round B:

Phase 1: Industries

Students have in their pile the pieces as formed in the previous round (e.g., 8 pieces). Each student can produce (take) as many pieces as he wants from the pile of his team (at least 1) and keep them. In the next round the pile (the total production) will be renewed with as many pieces as the ones left in the middle. In each round each student must produce at least one production unit otherwise he must leave the game.

Phase B: Fish farms

The students have the pieces in their pile as they were formed in the previous round (in our example 4) but before they produce due to the infection the fish must be removed from the lake. For every unit of iron production, 1 unit of

fish is lost due to the contamination in the lake. (There may be no fish available for production)

Round C: Repeats just like the second round of play.

Winners of the game per society: The industry that produced the most pieces of iron and the fish farming that produced the most fish!

Winning society: The society that did not exhaust its resources (e.g., fish or iron)

4.7 Activities

Activity Part 1: Intro

The overriding learning objectives for this activity is to gain the interest of the participants. Brief reference to the experiential game and its rules. Students are divided into groups as mentioned above and the game begins.

Activity Part 2: We play – We learn

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Discover the concept of externalities

2. Explore the issue of externalities and recognize the problem of managing shared resources

Step 1:

Educator's role is to coordinate so that all groups of students participate in the game according to the rules. Students through the experiential game realize the external cost of productive activity with the pollution of the lake. Each student tries to win (collecting the most goods) but taking into account the needs of his entire team (society). At the end of the 3rd round of the game you declare the end of the game.

Step 2:

Short presentation by each team. Which team/society has the most goods (resources)? which team member failed to complete all three rounds of play? You announce the winner.

Step 3:

Initiate a discussion about the results of the game. Indicative issues of the discussion:

- Are there groups that have run out of catches (or iron) and could not produce in a round? If yes; Why; Was There e.g., overfishing?
- What was the individual motivation of each fish farm? The common good;
- Does individual motivation conflict with the common interest?
- Was there communication between team members to conserve resources?
- Which team lost the most resources? Why; How did its members behave?
- Which team retained the most resources? Why; How did its members behave?
- What is the problem in the lake with the pollution? Who has the right to fish in the lake?
- Are there limits in fishing? Can anyone impose limits?
- Are the iron industries gaining at the expense of others from the pollution of the lake?
- Is there a loss (cost) in the cost of industries that the fish farms are subject to?

- What do you suggest as a solution to the pollution problem?
- What do you suggest as a solution to the problem of overfishing?

Activity Part 3: SDG 12 and South Africa

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Understand deeper the SDGs 12 and 13
2. Raise awareness for sustainable production and consumption
3. Correlate SDGs 12 and 13 with the issue of externalities
4. Be aware for externalities in real cases of South Africa

Step 1:

Lead a group discussion about Sustainable Development Goals with the following prompting questions:

- What do you know for the Sustainable Development Goal 12?
- Why do we need this goal?
- Why do we need this goal in South Africa?

Step 2:

Show the following video “Fostering Sustainable Economic Growth, Transformation and Promoting Sustainable Consumption and Production”:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=akG_50JwUJQ&t=2s

This video is from UN short film series "The Story You are Shaping" produced by HUMAN, which premiered at the UN Sustainable Development Summit 2015.

Step 3:

Show the following video “2030- SDG 12- Responsible Consumption and Production- Ted talks”:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dR0dzsFxjXc>

Step 4:

In groups learners can read the “South Africa’s implementation of the 2030 agenda for sustainable development” a voluntary national review report of 2019.

Learners can discuss about the implementation of SDG 12 in the South Africa

Step 5:

Show the video “Lake Victoria's massive pollution: Africa's largest lake is dying”:
<https://www.france24.com/en/tv-shows/focus/20211025-lake-victoria-s-massive-pollution-africa-s-largest-lake-is-dying>

Step 6:

Ask learners in pairs to read and discuss about the pollution of Lake Victoria in East Africa.
<https://www.newscientist.com/article/mg24632890-900-lake-victoria-is-at-risk-of-dying-from-pollution-and-climate-change/>

Step 7:

Ask learners in pairs to read and discuss about water pollution in South Africa: “Water pollution is a major threat to South Africa”.
<https://www.averda.com/rsa/news/water-pollution-major-threat-south-africa>

Step 8:

Initiate a discussion so that learners will reflect on the knowledge they gain with the following prompting questions

- what is a negative externality?
- Why is important to try to minimize the externality?
- Does the production procedures in South Africa cause negative externalities? Do you know any paradigms?

Activity Part 4:

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Investigate about public solutions for externalities
2. Search for public solutions for externalities in South Africa
3. Present their research and support their opinion

Step 1:

Students are asked to work in pairs or small groups to investigate and make suggestions as to how negative externalities could be reduced with the help of public administration while still meeting the economic needs of the companies involved.

Step 2:

Students will create a presentation to share their research and ideas. What type of manufacturing, production or service provision results in this negative externality? Indicative issues of the presentation and discussion.

- What are the environmental effects of this practice?
- Does the government need to intervene in externalities?
- What role does government play in managing externalities?
- What can governments do to help reduce the negative externalities associated with the production and consumption of goods and services?
- Where does this practice occur? Does it happen in South Africa?

Step 3:

Give the learners the opportunity to reflect on the following questions taking into consideration all previous activities:

- What did you finally learn from all these activities?
- Did you find your personal experience about the subject useful for the educational process?
- Did anything change your own ideas about SDG 12 and public solutions?
- Explain what caused your ideas to change or why you think your ideas did not change

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Poverty and Social Entrepreneurship, Student-driven Learning Activities Infused with Sustainable Development Goals with the CARE Learning Methodology

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Abstract

This article proposes a design of student-driven learning activities for the “Entrepreneurship and Economic Development” course at KwaZulu-Natal University (UKZN). Activities have been built in the context of PUAT European project. The proposed student-driven learning activities use CARE Learning Design Methodology as a tool for infusing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into multiple university courses. The fundamental objective of these student-driven learning activities is to prompt learners to explore the issue of poverty and to combine social entrepreneurship with the problems of poverty and hunger and SDG 1 and 2. Learners will meet and search for real social enterprises that operate globally and in South Africa and face the issues of poverty and hunger. Learners will think as social entrepreneurs to face the issue of poverty and hunger in their local community. The flexibility and adaptability of student-driven learning activities was one of the main goals in their design, and thus, it is not presented as a ready and non-negotiable product for reproduction but as a starting point and a methodology basis for the educators and learners to use them in the classroom.

Keywords: (CARE methodology, poverty, social entrepreneurship, SDGs)

1. The PUAT project

This article describes the design of student-driven learning activities for the course ENTR7AO “Entrepreneurship and Economic Development” of KwaZulu-Natal University (UKZN), built in the context of the PUAT project. The course covers the following topics: Introduction to Economic Development (poverty, inequality, unemployment, corruption), the link between entrepreneurship and economic development, the theoretical insights of entrepreneurship, youth entrepreneurship, and economic development; women entrepreneurship and economic development; public policy and macro policies towards small businesses and entrepreneurs; the role of Government in SMME development in South Africa; Social entrepreneurship; Corporate entrepreneurship; International entrepreneurship and other contemporary issues in entrepreneurship.

PUAT is a European Commission ERASMUS plus Capacity Building in Higher Education (CBHE) funded project entitled “Professionalisation of Undergraduate Academic Teaching in Multiple Disciplines to Address SDGs”. The PUAT project focuses on four Universities in South Africa (<https://puat.frederick.ac.cy/>).

Considering the strategic importance of quality teaching and curriculum design at the undergraduate level among university staff for infusing (SDGs) in course curricula, the project aims to create and provide capacity-building workshops, resources, and opportunities that foster innovative and effective pedagogical practices among academic staff in multiple academic disciplines in South Africa. More specifically, among others, the PUAT project aims to embed the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

in multiple disciplines nationally prioritized in South Africa, such as environment, agriculture, biology and related sciences, engineering, and health sciences in line with Bologna process (<https://puat.frederick.ac.cy/>).

2. Infusing Sustainable Development Goals with CARE Learning Design Methodology

The Sustainable Development Goals, also known as the SDGs or the 2030 Agenda, cover a wide range of sustainability issues, highlighting local, national, and international issues.

Makrakis & Kostoula-Makraki (2020) suggest the CARE Learning Design Methodology as a tool for infusing SDGs in student-driven learning activities. Student-driven learning activities refer to a process where learners are active partners of education procedure. Moreover, learners and educators act as constructors of knowledge and agents of change (Makrakis, 2016). The CARE learning design method includes four stages: a) Conceptualize, b) Activate, c) Reflect and d) Engage.

Conceptualise is the stage at which learners enter the process of understanding and are engaged with the subject of the course. As members of a local community, they perceive the interdependence and impact of their actions both locally and on global society.

Activate is the stage in which learners, based on their personal experience and, furthermore, based on their active participation, acquire new knowledge and skills related to SDGs. In this stage, the student-driven learning activities are also based on the 21st learning pillars (Makrakis & Kostoula-Makrakis, 2014) and the 10Cs enabled by ICTs (Makrakis & Kostoula-Makrakis, 2017)

Reflect is the stage at which learners and educators approach the subject more deeply. Mezirow (1991) describes

how critical reflection involves a critique of the presuppositions on which our beliefs and assumptions have been built. Thus, this stage can help the participants step back and examine their knowledge and attitudes.

Engage is the stage where learners put the theory into practice. It is the stage where learners put all the knowledge they acquired in previous stages into practice with the vision of a sustainable future. Engagement takes place behaviorally, emotionally, cognitively, and transformationally.

One of the main goals of its design was the flexibility and adaptability of student-driven learning activities. Thus, it is not presented as a ready and non-negotiable product for reproduction. In contrast, these activities can be a starting point and a methodology basis for educators and learners to use them in the classroom (Vouzaxakis & Makrakis, 2017).

3. SDG 1 and 2 and social entrepreneurship

Sustainable Development Goal 1 stands for ending poverty in all its forms everywhere. Globally, the number of people living in extreme poverty declined from 36 percent in 1990 to 10 percent in 2015. But the pace of change is decelerating and the COVID-19 crisis risks reversing decades of progress in the fight against poverty. The economic fallout from the global pandemic could increase global poverty by as much as half a billion people, or 8% of the total human population (Summer, Andy, Hoy & Ortiz-Juarez, 2020). The pandemic poses a real challenge to SDG 1 of ending poverty by 2030. Global poverty could face an increase that could represent a reversal of approximately a decade in the world's progress in reducing poverty (Summer, Andy, Hoy & Ortiz-Juarez, 2020). This would be the first time poverty has increased globally in the last thirty years, since 1990.

Sustainable Development Goal 2 stands for zero hunger. In 2020, according to the World Food Programme, 135 million suffered from acute hunger mainly due to man-made conflicts, climate change, and economic downturns (GNAFC & FSIN, 2020). Unfortunately, projections show that the world is not on track to achieve Zero Hunger by 2030, and despite some progress, most indicators are also not on track to meet global nutrition targets (FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP & WHO, 2020). An estimated 25.9 percent of the world population was affected by moderate or severe food insecurity in 2019, up from 22.4 percent in 2015. The fastest rise was recorded in Latin America and the Caribbean, although the highest levels were registered in sub-Saharan Africa (UN, 2021).

Social enterprises are traditionally seen as an intermediary point between regular businesses and non-profit organizations, such as charities and NGOs. There are multiple definitions for social entrepreneurship, which vary in their scope, depth, and among the entities and actors that they include. According to the European Commission (2018), a *“social enterprise is an operator in the social economy whose main objective is to have a social impact rather than make a profit for their owners or shareholders. It operates by providing goods and services for the market in an entrepreneurial and innovative fashion and uses its profits primarily to achieve social objectives”*.

According to United Nations Industrial Development Organisation social entrepreneurship represents an innovative and holistic business model, able to address global challenges (Vujasinovic, Lipenkova & Orlando, 2020). Social entrepreneurship plays a vital role in promoting sustainable development goals. For example, social enterprises, which include providing education technologies and e-health services for the most vulnerable and developing community tracing initiatives, have been even more critical during the COVID-19 pandemic, as they reach those missed by the market (UN, 2019). Moreover, we can find strong links between social enterprises and SDGs 1 and 2 as, for example, they can play a significant role in poverty reduction through job creation (Tanchangya, Yingjing & Chowdhury, 2020).

4. The student-driven learning activity

Learners in these student-driven learning activities will search and think about poverty and hunger. They will discuss SDG 1 and 2, and they will discover, by answering quizzes, the statistical data about these issues. With the help of interactive WEB2 tools they will discover the usual misconception most people have about statistical data (Rosling, Rosling & Ronnlund, 2018). Furthermore, they will “meet” families from all over the world and they will find out the real-life conditions of the poorest people as well as the extreme income inequalities.

Moreover, learners will research social entrepreneurship and meet and research real social enterprises that operate globally and in South Africa. These social enterprises are facing the issues of poverty and hunger. Finally, learners with the “Think, Pair, Share” strategy will be social entrepreneurs in their local community in order to serve SDG 1 and 2 as well as their personal and common needs.

The learning activities consist of the following parts: Part 1 – What we know, part 2 - We learn, part 3: SDG 1 and 2, and Part 4 - Engage.

4.1 Learning objectives

The basic objective of this CARE scenario is to prompt learners to explore poverty and to combine social entrepreneurship with the issues of poverty and hunger (SDGs 1 and 2).

It is worth pointing out that learning objectives will be emerging and refined along with developing the learning activities. The overriding learning objectives for this scenario are the following:

1. Explore the issue of poverty and inequality
2. Raise awareness for poverty and inequality and meet the SDGs 1 and 2
2. Adopt the use of valid and reliable statistical data
4. Combine social entrepreneurship with sustainability issues such as poverty and hunger

4.2 Activities

Based on the brainstorming technique, participants using their mobile phones or computers are asked to fill in the words they think when they hear the concepts "poverty and

inequality." The free WEB2 tool answergarden (<https://answergarden.ch/>) creates a world cloud.

Ask learners in your class to fill in the following K.W.H.L. chart (Know; Want; How; Learned) about the subject of Poverty and Inequality. Start with the "Know," "What," and "How" columns and save the "Learn" column for later. In pairs or groups, have students compare what they know and what they want to learn.

Based on the thoughts learners have written down in columns "Know" and "What", initiate a discussion with the following prompting questions. As educator participate in discussion without giving the "answers" to the queries.

- What do you want to learn about poverty and inequality?
- What is poverty?
- How poverty is measured;
- What is meant by absolute poverty;
- What is the difference between absolute poverty and relative poverty?

Activity Part 1: What We Know

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. gain the interest of the learners
2. Recognize the previous knowledge of participants

Step 1:

Participants using the free WEB2 Quizizz tool (<https://quizizz.com/>) answer anonymously from their mobile phones or PCs four multiple-choice questions on issues of poverty and access to basic goods. These questions are based on the Hans Rosling questionnaire, which was answered in 2017 by 12,000 people from 14 countries. Participants in his research answered correctly on average only 2 of the 12 questions it contains. This is due to the misconception we have about statistical data and the lack of valid and reliable sources of public information (Rosling, Rosling & Ronnlund, 2018).

Questions-answers

1. For the last twenty years, the percentage of the population living in extreme poverty has
 - a. Almost doubled
 - b. Reduced by half
 - c. No change
2. Where do most of the world's population live?
 - a. In low-income countries
 - b. In high-income countries
 - c. In middle-income countries
3. How much is life expectancy in the world today?
 - a. 50 years
 - b. 60 years
 - c. 70 years
4. What percentage of the world's population has some degree of access to electricity?
 - a. around 20%
 - b. around 50%
 - c. around 60%
 - d. around 80%

Correct Answers (1b, 2b, 3c, 4d)

The quiz with the above questions is public and ready to use (<https://quizizz.com/admin/quiz/61ab538cfcaab3001ea8671b>)

The participants will answer, but they will not see the correct answers immediately. However, this will increase their interest in continuing the learning process.

Step 2:

Show the correct answers and initiate a discussion with the following possible questions:

- What do we know about poverty in the world today?
- Why is there a misconception about statistical data?
- The last twenty years, absolute poverty may have been reduced, but is there an absolute need to reduce it further?
- Finally, what is poverty and extreme poverty? How is it to live in extreme poverty?

The above questions and answers will drive the learning process to the next activity.

Activity Part 2: We learn

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Understand deeper the issues of poverty and inequality
2. Develop emotional empathy for extreme poverty

Step 1:

As a start in this part of activities, invite learners to watch the following video: "What is poverty?" <https://www.worldvision.com.au/get-involved/school-resources/detail/1.-what-is-poverty>

Ask learners to write words, phrases or questions that come to their mind while watching the video in their diaries / journals.

Step 2:

Ask learners to discuss the problems that arise from the way we measure poverty. <https://www.worldvision.com.au/get-involved/school-resources/detail/3.-how-do-we-measure-poverty>

Step 3:

Meet families all over the world who live in poverty and extreme poverty. Compare this with high-income families. Use the free Gapminder Dollar Street tool. Dollar Street, a project created by Gapminder, sent teams of photographers around the world to take photos of over 264 homes in 50 different countries and upload them, allowing everybody to see how different people live across the world at different income points (<https://www.gapminder.org/dollar-street>).

Initiate a discussion about the conditions of life of poor and rich people. Ask the learners how they feel about people who live in extreme poverty.

Step 4:

Show the video of what causes poverty. <https://www.worldvision.com.au/get-involved/school-resources/detail/2.-what-causes-poverty>

Ask learners to write words, phrases, or questions that come to their mind while watching the video in their diaries or journals.

Step 5:

Give the learners time to share their ideas/questions and post them on the board as a mind map. Ask learners to fill in the column "Learn" of the K.W.H.L. chart.

Activity Part 3: SDGs 1 and 2

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Understand deeper the SDG1 and SDG2
2. Adopt the use of valid and reliable statistical data

Step 1:

Ask learners to fill in the column “Learn” of the K.W.H.L. chart. Lead a group discussion about Sustainable Development Goals with the following prompting questions:

- What do you know about Sustainable Development Goals 1 and 2?
- Why do we need these goals?

Step 2:

Show the following videos:

SDG 1: Explaining no poverty:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LVco1o01I6U>

SDG 2: Explaining zero hunger:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NCaRSKgnMV8>

Step 3:

Use the gapminder tool for animated data. In this tool anyone can choose a country in order to see the income distribution of the population in categories. You can show the income distribution from 1800 until today. Moreover, you can show an estimate for income distribution until 2050 ([https://www.gapminder.org/tools/#\\$chart-type=bubbles&url=v1](https://www.gapminder.org/tools/#$chart-type=bubbles&url=v1)).

Fig.1: Animated statistical graph for the distribution of the population in income categories (gapminder tools)

Activity Part 4: Engage

The overriding learning objectives for this activity are the following:

1. Focus on real social entrepreneurship about SDG1 and SDG2
2. Engage learners in entrepreneurship facing poverty in their society

Step 1:

Ask learners to watch two videos in groups.

Group A:

A business case about no poverty:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kfKOKbsowEw>

Group B:

A business case about zero hunger:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Jb12ZHy5V8Q>

Step 2:

Ask each group to present the basic ideas of business case they watched. They can discuss about the business ideas.

Step 3:

Give them to read the following article and watch the video: Four Notable Social Enterprises Fighting Poverty in Asia (<https://borgenproject.org/fighting-poverty-in-asia/>)

Step 4:

Use “Think, Pair, Share” strategy by asking learners to write and discuss a new business idea facing poverty in their society before sharing it with the whole class. More specifically, have learners reflect on the knowledge they

gain with the previous activities (Think). Have learners pair up and share their new business idea (Pair). Then, ask pairs to share their business idea to the whole class.

Step 5:

Give the learners the opportunity to reflect on the following questions taking into consideration all previous activities:

- What did you finally learn from all these activities?
- Did you find your personal experience about the subject useful for the educational process?
- Did anything change your own ideas about SDG 1 and 2 and social entrepreneurship?
- Explain what caused your ideas to change or why you think your ideas did not change

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SESSION C

Dissecting of The Conservation Biology Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

Conservation Biology is a course that offers a powerful idea. It is no longer an exclusive subject in university-based departments of biology. In many respects, ecology has turned into a worldview. As such, it presents a holistic challenge to the current modern worldview that reduces and fragments reality into distinct parts to understand. In short, conservation holds out the promise and hope of caring for the whole. From the sustainability perspective, this whole is the entire earth. The goal of deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing the Biology Conservation course was to infuse and highlight ESD and 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the utilization of ICT on learning. During the Implementation of the revised course, several challenges were faced. The first and foremost is the challenge to make class livelier. The students had been used to a classical class where active involvement was not required. There is a sense of fright among students to answer or raise questions in the wrong way. To ease the students, the teacher frequently invited their involvement by either answering questions or encouraging students to ask questions. The feedback for each student's activities seems to make students more confident that their active participation matters.

Keywords: Biology, Conservation, Global citizen, Tropical ecosystem, Sustainability

1 Introduction

The Conservation Biology course has been designed to give basic concepts of conservation biology, habitat degradation, and threats to biodiversity in relation to ecosystems and sustainable development, especially those of Indonesia. From this course, students are expected to have the ability to explain the issues on tropical ecosystem degradation in landscape ecology, the threats to biodiversity and global ecology, and the rule of conservation biology in achieving sustainable ecosystems in landscape ecology. In the end, students are expected to understand and be able to give simple alternative solutions to environmental problems (Odum et al., 1960).

Indonesia is a tropical archipelago with 13,466 verified islands out of 17,499 islands, with a land area of 2.01 million km² and a water area of about 5.8 million km² consisting of 3.25 million km² of Indonesian waters, 2.55 million km² of Exclusive Economic Zone, and an 80,791 km long coastline (CEA, 2018). Indonesia is also flanked by the Pacific Ocean and the Indian Ocean, making it rich in biodiversity and known as a megadiverse country. Indonesia's biodiversity includes the diversity of living things, including its variety of resources in terrestrial, marine, and aquatic ecosystems and its ecological complexity (LIPI, 2014). Broecker et al. (1991) stated that Indonesia's position between two oceans, namely the Pacific Ocean and Indian Ocean at 60°N – 110°S and 95°E – 141°E, is very important for the global thermohaline circulation. The species and genetic diversity are also believed to be very high if based on the ecosystem diversity ranging from Indonesia's area from the east to west, at sea and on land, and on each island. Indonesia is also

an archipelagic country with a complex topography that is believed to have the richest marine biodiversity in the world (Sasai et al., 2011). However, Indonesia's high biodiversity and strategic position needs to be balanced with its preservation and utilization to achieve UNCBD's goals for Indonesia.

Indonesian biodiversity has been utilized to support livelihoods, especially for food, health and energy, and basic industrial materials to meet human necessities. However, the number of biological diversities used to meet those needs is still very small compared to the number of biodiversity species that have not been studied yet. The limited number of researchers, resources, and institutional capacity are constraints faced in researching and utilizing the biodiversity of Indonesia. An ecosystem, which is one of the components of biodiversity, can serve as a provider of water, clean air, aesthetics, and culture. In line with a 50% world population growth and Indonesia's estimated population increase of 68% by 2050 (FAO, 2010), food availability needs to be increased two-fold, meaning conservation efforts and utilization of food sources must be continued to meet those needs. In principle, conservation, utilization, and preservation of biodiversity aim to maintain the integrity of the ecosystem and provide added value to the importance of biodiversity through the application of traditional and modern knowledge. In this approach, some new didactic methodologies were used, such as project-based learning. The research field demonstrates that using problem-based learning in science is one of the most effective ways of teaching science (Biasutti and EL-Deghaidy 2015). Also, using ICT could be effective in learning (Biasutti 2011). The course will discuss the response of conservation biology to

the biodiversity crisis and the impact human activities have on population, community, ecosystem, landscape ecology, and global pandemics. This course also studied the analysis of problems based on practical approaches such as avoiding the extinction of species and rehabilitating the degradation of tropical land, forest, swamp, and coastal ecosystems, as well as umbrella species in ecosystems, and the possibility of returning the threatened species to their functional ecosystem. The discussion includes conservation biology and biodiversity, resources belonging together, and the tragedy of the commons. The biodiversity threats. The change in conceptual approach to the conservation biology issues after the 1992 Earth Summit meeting at Rio De Janeiro, Brazil. The discussions include concepts on conservation at population and community levels, planning on protected areas, ecological restoration, ecosystem management, conservation and sustainable development, and the rule of practical ecologists.

With a heavy focus on biodiversity and conservation, this course is suitable as a vehicle to introduce SDGs and ESD. Thus, it was selected as one of the courses to be deconstructed and reconstructed to infuse ICT in the courses. As an elective course for the undergraduate program in the Faculty of Biology, roughly 50 students attend this course each year.

The main aim of this course is for the student to become aware of the principles and theories of the interaction between conservation biology and biodiversity after taking this course. The Biology Conservation course has been designed to make students able to: 1) have a comprehension of the basic principles of structure and threats to biodiversity; 2) distinguish between conservation at the individual, population, and community levels in the ecosystem; 3) Illustrate the connection between biodiversity conservation and sustainable ecosystem; 4) describes the ecosystem management and landscape ecology.

2 Methods

2.1. Teaching Method

The learning activities of Conservation Ecology integrate with problem-based learning (PBL) strategies. This is raised in a way that motivates and challenges learners to think and reflect, search and discover, build on prior knowledge, and promote the transfer of what they have learned in the ecosystem. For example, there has been discussion about global warming in the environment and how it is influenced and affected. Illegal logging is a social problem as it affects people's needs. Introducing issues that convey controversial meanings, such as illegal logging, is expected to raise learners' interest in studying the issue, developing various skills and competencies related to PBL, and raising awareness about the consequences of illegal logging on human life.

2.2. Methods of Assessing Students

The students' assessments in this course are done in various ways, from formative tests such as midterm and final tests to teacher reviews for fieldwork reports and final papers. In addition, this course also assesses student assertiveness during discussion. Students will also be given mini projects to do something meaningful toward conservation, such as habitat cleaning and rebuilding.

Students are assessed with formative and student-centered assessments that can give insight into their understanding, inform teaching practice, and be embedded in the classroom culture. In addition, students should develop practical projects to validate the academic side into deliverables, addressing fair environmental, social, and economic challenges. The Scoring components in this course are: Final Paper (20%), Midterm and Final test (25%), Quiz (15%), Homework (20%), and 20% of final project.

2.3. Improving Biology Conservation with DeCoRe and DREAM

DeCoRe Plus is an acronym for the Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction methodology. DeCoRe is complemented by three further steps: diagnostic assessment, implementation, and summative assessment (Makrakis, 2017). The goal of deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing the Biology Conservation course was to infuse and highlight 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The Biology Conservation course would undergo the DeCoRe+ six processes: **(1) Diagnose**. In this process, we reflect on who we are, what we have, where we want to go, and why we want to go there; **(2) Deconstructing**. This step is done to analyze the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules; **(3) Constructing-** the constructing process is conducted by gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives); **(4) Reconstructing**. This reconstructing process is when the integration of newly constructed knowledge is in line with the reconstructed frame of reference, **(5) Implementing**. Implementation starts initially with the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning. **(6) Finalizing**. The last step is to reflect on and evaluate what has been learned and changed.

The DREAM methodology developed by Makrakis (2023) was used to evaluate the Biology Conservation course based on the perspective of the students who took the course. Assessments are conducted before, during, and after the restructured general biology course delivery for undergraduates. This assessment method consists of several steps: Diagnosis, Review, explanation, assessment, and management, and enabling ICT employment in the course delivery (Makrakis, 2012; Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2014). The student diagnoses to know what is in the Biology Conservation course. Followed by a review and explanation, which usually occurs during the

implementation of the restructured course. Finally, evaluation and management are at the end of the implementation process. Evaluation is knowing if something has changed before and after the reconstruction. Finally, portfolios received from students are analyzed and used by instructors to obtain information for restructuring Biology Conservation courses.

3 Result and Discussion

3.1. New Competency to be developed and SDGs Highlight

The most notable revision is the division of instruction into activity modes, based on what students do rather than what teachers teach. Through student-centered learning, the delivery of learning materials becomes more comprehensive and provides a clear learning context (Biasutti & Frate, 2017; Biasutti et al. 2018). To meet the requirements of the Indonesian Quality Framework for Higher Education. This course focuses on problem-based learning methods that increase students' skills (Biasutti et al. 2018).

Course content is designed to ensure the achievement of the aim and objective of this course. This course discusses the response of conservation biology to the biodiversity crisis and the impact of human activities on population, community, ecosystem, and landscape ecology. These courses also analyze problems based on practical approaches such as avoiding the extinction of species and rehabilitating the degradation of tropical land, forest, swamp, and coastal ecosystems as umbrella species in an ecosystem. The possibility to return the threatened species to their functional ecosystem.

This course not only offers theoretical knowledge on biology conservation through class meetings but also brings students directly to the field to see for themselves habitat destruction, threats to diversity, conservation, and challenges. This design of study is chosen to ensure the student has a comprehensive knowledge of Indonesian conservation biology.

The balance between class activities and fieldwork in Conservation Biology will not only strengthen their basic knowledge about biodiversity from General Biology and Ecology courses but also give them an understanding of how Indonesian Regulation works on Biodiversity conservation.

The learning activity in the classroom, such as the discussion on the threat to biodiversity and human impact on the Ecosystem, as well as the fieldwork, is closely related to the objectives and outcome of this course. The learning activities are purposefully selected to encourage the student to have curiosity and sensitivity to environmental problems and appreciate and be sensitive to environmental issues relating to conservation biology and anthropogenic activities.

The course addresses the environmental pillar by discussing the possibility of returning threatened species to their functional ecosystem and analyzing the problems using a practical approach. It also addresses the social pillar by studying the response of conservation biology and the impact of human activities on the population and community. The cultural pillar uses the ICT tool to transfer scientific ideologies among different cultures toward sustainable communities.

The learning outcome of Biology Conservation courses is to prepare students to be able to: **1.** explain the concept of biodiversity concerning the external community changes and challenges; **2.** describe the importance of biodiversity to human welfare and economic development; **3.** list the causes of biodiversity depletion in Indonesia and global context; **4.** distinguish between extinct, endangered and threatened species; **5.** justify the conservation of biodiversity and how to deal and configure with it; **6.** describe various in-situ and ex-situ methods of conservation; **7.** describe the importance of national parks, sanctuaries and biosphere reserves; legal measures adopted by national and international bodies; **8.** plan and execute a simple campaign conservation project on social media and online digital platforms based on GEO network project. This course directly and indirectly will cover all of goals in SDGs with highlight on SDGs no 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17.

3.2. Developing Biology Conservation New Module

During deconstruction, there was a realization that a missed part is the effectiveness of the 10Cs towards conservation biology, especially through using the ICT tools to effectively interpret the experimental analysis. Moreover, the economic justice reflection through the course content, the course was mainly focusing on the environmental and sociocultural side than the economics pillar as it requires time to generate scientific real action into the economic formal scope, nevertheless, the ecological unity and the species interdependence can hugely affect the economic inequalities and injustice

The practical or the future implications for the students' initiatives that integrate conservation ecology and the problem-based learning methodologies, may the course aim to reflect to the constructed knowledge among course activities (Biasutti & EL-Deghaidy 2015) The practical solutions toward sustainable environment were not mentioned as it was mainly concerned about the theoretical pattern not the future coming steps, as such the below questions were not covered, while it is recommended to be added through the course development plan: 1. How to overcome threats of Biodiversity in relation to Sustainable Development? and 2. To what extent the ecosystem management and the ecological landscape could be easily monitored and tracked towards environmental lifelong wellbeing? All of those gaps were tried to be addressed in the new module of Biology Conservation.

The second revision of this course was done in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. Since the lockdown imposed by our government, there has been pressure to shift from in-person teaching-learning methods to long-distance learning. Moreover, there is also a need to change the approach of this course delivered. There is a need to encourage students to think and have insight on how the practical or the future implications for their initiatives that integrate conservation ecology and the problem-based learning methodologies may affect the conservation in the long run and how to construct knowledge among course activities not to deepen the scope of the external social initiatives.

3.3. Biology Conservation Learning Activities

The learning activities of Biology Conservation integrate with problem-based learning (PBL) strategies; this is raising in a way motivates and challenges learners to think and reflect, to search and discover, to build on prior knowledge, and promote the transfer of what they have learned in the ecosystem (Biasutti & EL-Deghaidy, 2015). For example, there has been a discussion about global warming in the environment and how these are influenced and affected. Illegal logging is a social problem as it affects people's needs. Introducing issues that convey controversial meanings, such as illegal logging, is expected to raise learners' interest in studying the issue and develop various skills and competencies related to PBL, besides raising awareness about the consequences of illegal logging to human life.

In the wake of the pandemic situation, the utilization of ICT in Conservation Biology courses has become a must. A creative way of learning by employing ICT is one requirement for the current course. For the recent course, students who participate in it should be really active in learning, self-motivated, and not depend on the teacher as the main source of information. The current version of the course designated more time for case studies and discussion. Moreover, this course had more interactive meetings than the previous ones.

As part of the reconstruction, there are designated 10C that are deemed suitable for learning this subject. The C's parts are: **Collaboration**; students will learn to cooperate and coordinate to use multiple modern communication tools to analyze the conservation problems through brainstorming groups, generating a pool of information to be scientifically validated. **Communication**: Students will capitalize on the offline/online digitalized modern communication means to transmit knowledge and thoughts to analyze and criticize the conservation's central notions, such as the threats to biodiversity through social media platforms and trends. Through critical thinking, students will learn how to conceptualize, synthesize, and evaluate their external surroundings by analyzing the problems of ecosystem degradation and conservation biology and thinking of the appropriate tools to solve these problems. **Cross-cultural**

understanding: Students will construct national and global practices by acknowledging the designs of reserved and protected areas and will think about how to integrate the significant techniques among their group initiatives. **Connectivity**: Students will eliminate the human/social complexities by having a full connection with their counterparts, discussing and reflecting on the academic content having holistic global critical implications of conservation biology. The activities such as discussions with peers and teacher assistants about lab reports is one of the examples. **Critical reflection**: Students will learn to reflect on the external social human activity in the environment. **Critical consciousness**: Students will learn how to promote critical awareness among the community to enhance praxis towards sustainability justice pillars addressing the environmental problems related to conservation concepts. **Constructing knowledge**, students will shift from the consuming and learning knowledge to the transformational change stage to create, innovate, and deliver to the community for the sustainability of human beings and other creatures and address these practical applications to the industry.

3.4. Analysis of Biology Conservation new concept implementation

During the Implementation of the revised course, several challenges were faced. The first and foremost is the challenge of making the class livelier. The students were used to a classical class where active involvement was not required. There is a sense of fright among students to answer or raise questions in the wrong way. To ease the student's situation, the teacher frequently invited their involvement by either answering questions or encouraging students to ask questions. The feedback for each student's activities seems to make the students more confident that their active involvement matters (Biasutti, 2011).

Fig. 1. Percentage of students exposed to course/work/issues that similar to the Biology Conservation.

Regarding the key diagnostic question in this part of Have you ever attended a course on this topic or skill area in the past? Most of the students of this course (55%) stated that they had participated in a similar course. In comparison, 45% said otherwise (Fig. 1). For Biology students, there are many courses with intersecting learning materials, such as

General Biology and Ecology. The course that has similar content to this course is Ecology. Both courses are compulsory for students in their early years. Although both courses also covered the subject of conservation, they were only superficial studies. In the need of deeper insight of conservation, students should take Biology Conservation.

The answers to the following questions, “Have you ever created a project or written work similar to this course?” and “Have you ever worked in work dealing with issues similar to the topic of this course?” show the students who took Biology Conservation class 67% had never created project or written work similar to the course and 90% said that they have worked dealing with the similar topics that are given in Biology Conservation courses (Fig. 1).

3.4. Student Expectation

The students’ expectations for joining this course were well stated: They hope to understand how conservation works and how they can contribute in the future. The students also expressed eagerness to grasp and gain insight into conservation, the environment, and how to find solutions to environmental problems that occur. Moreover, they see this course as an important preparation for their careers in the future.

The gathered results reflect the students' answers regarding their expectations from this course: About 72.7% of students focus on the basic concept of Biology Conservation, while 27.3% of them presume that the course will increase their practical knowledge of conservation (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Students’ expectation for Biology Conservation course

3.5. Student Reflection on the changing of course

The new reconstruction of the Biology conservation course heavily highlighted ESD and focused on some SDGs

while superficially covering almost all SDGs' goals. The course also incorporated ICT usage into learning activities. Most of the students expressed a positive outlook on the recent way of learning. They said the teachers were competent, the book was good, and the class was so enjoyable that it made them understand the topic in depth. They expressed that the class was very interactive, with various discussions and presentations. The material presented is fascinating. Lots of fascinating talks about climate change and other issues were presented. The students appreciated the connection between textbook knowledge and recent cases discussed in class. Moreover, they appreciated the skills they learned in the course, especially about data processing and research on conservation. However, it is of particular importance to take into consideration various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues on the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

4 Conclusion

The DeCoRe method was used to improve the delivery of this course. In the new concept of the Biology Conservation course, the emphasis on ESD and SDGs as part of a global idea is highlighted, and case studies of recent national issues are updated. The goal of deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing the Biology Conservation course was to infuse and highlight ESD and 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as well as the utilization of ICT in learning. During the implementation of the revised course, several challenges were faced. The first and foremost is the challenge of making the class livelier. The students were used to a classical class where their active involvement in class was not required. There is a sense of fright among students to answer or raise questions in the wrong way. To ease the students' situation, the teacher frequently invited their involvement by either answering questions or encouraging students to ask questions. The feedback for each student’s activities seems to make students more confident that their active involvement matters. With the new concept, students’ engagement was higher during the course, and they are confident that they can have a positive impact on society.

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Hydrometeorology Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing It through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

While education plays a critical role in disseminating the ideas and principles of sustainability, in addition to social, environmental, economic, and cultural sustainability, it was important to advance the education curriculum specifically in universities. This article explores a critical perspective on deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing the Hydrometeorology course through the lens of SDGs supported by ICTs and driven by six learning pillars and 10 Competencies (10 Cs). The DeCoRe Methodological Approach has been developed in this article to embed the ideas and principles of sustainability inside the course. The research process has been conducted through an assessment using a systematic questionnaire based on the DREAM Methodology to get the information before and after embedding the values into the course. It can be found out that there was an improvement in the course in scope of educational, professional, social, as well as personality of students.

Keywords: Hydrometeorology, Climate, DeCoRe plus Methodology, SDGs, Environment

1. Introduction

The Hydrometeorology course is a basic course introducing the relation of meteorological aspects, climatology, and hydrology. In this course, students learn about principles, concepts, measurement methods, and analyses related to hydrometeorological parameters related to the forestry sector, which can be used to conduct studies or research. The primary studies of this course are:

1. The basic concepts of hydrology, meteorology, and climatology; definition, development history, object, elements of meteorology and climatology, hydrological cycle and its application in forest resource conservation;
2. The role of forests in controlling water cycles, nutrient cycles, erosion, and landslides.
3. The Water balance components; characteristics of rain, interception, infiltration, runoff, and evapotranspiration;
4. The case studies, identification, and analysis of several hydrometeorological disaster events, and;
5. Utilizing hydrological and meteorological data, analyzing changes in the hydrological character of a forested area, and preparing engineering controls, mitigation, and adaptation.

Meanwhile, the course aims to make students:

1. understand the relation of meteorological aspects, climatology, and hydrology;
2. understand the environment problems caused by hydrometeorological disasters;

3. increase critical thinking in developing hydrometeorological disaster mitigation and adaptation strategies.

By attending hydrometeorology course, students are expected to understand the scope of study, various current problems, and formulate problems related to hydrometeorological disasters, create hypotheses, and develop hydrometeorological disaster mitigation and adaptation strategies.

Hydrometeorology was taught over 16 meetings, with lectures supported by multimedia (internet, visual learning videos, LCD), group discussion, demonstration, and practice being used as teaching methods. Hydrometeorology is the basis of forestry science. This course content promotes the basic knowledge of hydrometeorology, environmental factors, and water-related disasters. Several learning methods are used to increase the delivery method to students. Implementing new didactic methodologies, such as Project-based learning in science, affects students' learning effectively (Biasutti & EL-Deghaidy, 2015), especially when combining ICT (Biasutti, 2011). Bringing the field problems into the class becomes the primary method to accelerate the students' practical knowledge and analytical skills in identifying the problems and alternative solutions. Our world is now facing so many natural issues that are caused by human beings. By studying hydrometeorology, students are expected to understand various current problems, formulate those problems related to hydrometeorological disasters, create hypotheses, and

develop hydrometeorological disaster mitigation and adaptation strategies. Thus, every new case about hydrometeorology problems in the world that are most likely related to climate change gives the students new knowledge to develop disaster mitigation and adaptation strategies as a solution for the community. It is believed that students can understand the role of humans in protecting the Environment and know what to do in creating a safe and sustainable world in the future. What the course taught is in line with SDG 13, which says to *take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts*. It is increasingly being recognized that learning for sustainability is not simply an add-on or cross-curricula concept. It requires a significant shift in current curriculum practice. Learning for sustainability is not only about integrating new content into the curriculum but also about challenging teaching and learning approaches (Biasutti et al., 2018). It needs interdisciplinary and holistic discussion to deal with the complexity and interconnectedness of real-world problems. Since the Hydrometeorology course contains the concept of education for sustainability, there was a need to develop the course based on the concept of Deconstruction, Construction, and Reconstruction (DeCoRe process) that aims to help prospective and in-service teachers to embed sustainability justice in school curricula (Makrakis, 2017). The course was upgraded by integrating the Education for Sustainable Development concept and the SDGs values. Hydrometeorology was chosen as one of the ten courses because it is a common topic among UGM students, particularly those from the Department of Forestry. In addition, this course provides basic knowledge specifically in understanding the scope of meteorology, hydrology, and climatology in forest resources management. Furthermore, this course focuses on mitigating hydrometeorological disasters. This scope of learning is in line with the idea of SDG 13, which says to take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts; that is why it is important to integrate SDG principles and values into this course.

The DeCoRe Concept can adjust and identify the dimensions of sustainability justice from this hydrometeorology course, which are environmental justice, social justice, and economic justice, which have already been implemented during the course but have never been written in the Hydrometeorology lesson plan. Each of these learning activities was related to real life and dimensions of sustainability justice. From environmental justice, the students are expected to understand factors and processes in the environment cycles; students will be able to relate those concepts towards the practical actions in forest resources management based on sustainability as well as the SDGs ideas and values. From the site of social justice, students will be able to know that the potential forestry resources should be followed by a good understanding of fulfilling the needs of society, solving social life problems, and also improving social welfare. Society should play a critical role in environment management and its impact. From the economic justice,

students are expected to understand that forest is a great capital of Indonesia that makes Indonesia able to face economic challenges, fulfill social needs, achieve and improve prosperity, as well as ensure that this economic justice is driven by sustainable natural resources management. The students are expected to have a critical mindset for balancing economic development and the environment's carrying capacity. Meanwhile, from cultural justice, students are expected to understand the philosophy of local wisdom related to environmental conservation. For example, implementing environmental conservation must be carried out by strengthening the social wisdom that has been applied in conservation areas. Thus, sustainability should be maintained based on those values in a conservation area. This sustainable justice can be achieved by internalizing the ideas and principles of sustainability into the curriculum.

Methodologies: The How Question

2.1 Analysis Model Overview

The course revision was applied to embed the idea of sustainability, specifically the Sustainable Development Goals values, into the curricula. Makrakis (2017) advanced the DeCoRe Plus Methodology. DeCoRe Plus, an abbreviation for Deconstruction, Construction, is an approach used to identify and evaluate the course by embedding certain principles and values to develop the curriculum according to the added values.

Figure 1 : The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017)

DeCoRe Plus Methodology was formed by six processes as follows.

1. **Diagnosing:** Identify who we are, what we have (existing knowledge), where we want to go, and why we want to go there.
2. **Deconstructing:** Give a critical explanation including the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and units of chosen curriculum.
3. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new perspectives.
4. **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of

reference.

5. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module through the related course.
6. **Finalising:** Evaluating and reflecting on what has been learned and changed from the course.

Based on previous discussions, the objectives, and the need to construct a curriculum that aligns with the ideas and concepts of sustainability, the Hydrometeorology course curriculum is constructed. Students were assessed based on their direct experiences using a systematic Questionnaire. This assessment was carried out based on the DREAM stages of systematic learning evaluation, which are Diagnose, Review, Explain, Assess, and Manage (Makrakis, 2023). This DREAM Methodology process covers the course in five stages.

Figure 2 : DREAM Methodology Model (Makrakis, 2023)

The first stage, the diagnosis stage, focuses on identifying the profile of every student, such as personal identity, previous experiences related to the course, and the student's expectations of attending the course. From this stage, we could find out whether the students had ever created a project similar to the course. Furthermore, this stage aims to identify the students' work experiences with certain issues similar to those in the course. This previous information leads to the expectation of the student from the Hydrometeorology course.

Following the diagnosis is the review stage, which aims to understand challenges during the half-term of the course and the difference between expectations and results. By this stage, the students are expected to have a deep understanding of how to deal with the gap between previous expectations and the result of their course. The end of this stage was used to define the appropriate alternatives to improve the course based on the students' various suggestions.

The next stage, the Explain stage, focuses on describing how the course was not in the way the students expected and trying to explain how it might have happened. This stage helped to identify the possible causes that create the gap

between expectation and the learning process of the course. The result of this assessment was able to give a broader perspective related to the obstacles that are still encountered during the lesson process of the Hydrometeorology course.

The fourth stage is Assess, which aims to understand the impact of the course in multiple aspects, such as the impact on students' knowledge, professional development, sustainability of social community, and personality. Through this stage, the students were expected to critically reflect on how the course results affected self-capacity improvement. Thus, the result from this assessment could be the parameter of how this course improves the student's capacity through the learning process and methods.

Those stages were continued for the managed stage (last stage), where students were expected to apply the new learning from the course. This assessment was conducted to provide a comprehensive overview of constraints, expectations, and a strategic evaluation of the learning outcomes in a Hydrometeorology course. The results of the assessment are expected to provide an overview of the new learning process from Hydrometeorology courses in the future.

Assessment and Data Analysing Methods

This research method is descriptive qualitative research with primary data sources obtained directly from students as respondents by survey. The survey was done by providing an online survey form that was supposed to be filled out by students of the Hydrometeorology course. The form was constructed based on DREAM Methodology Models consisting of five stages: Diagnose, Review, Explain, Assess, and Manage. The identity of Hydrometeorology students was gathered through this form, which included their names, student numbers, and email addresses. All the answers given by the respondent were based on the student's consent. The answers will be reduced, displayed, and followed by a conclusion. The data analysis was based on the DeCoRe Plus Methodology advanced by Makrakis (2017).

Pre-Course Assessment Result

This stage aims to identify the students' previous experiences and knowledge. Based on the assessment result, 27% of respondents had attended a course on topics similar to hydrometeorology. Experiences in doing a project or writing work that is similar to the course show the same number, 27%. Some students have ever conducted an online discussion on a similar topic of Hydrometeorology. When it comes to work experience, the result of the assessment shows a lower percentage of 9%. The experience was about creating an educational video and raising the importance of the mangrove ecosystem.

Figure 3 : Percentage of previous knowledge and experience

The result shows a small number percentage of students' experiences. The content of hydrometeorology was considered a new topic for the student who was a respondent in this research. The capability and skills related to this course were also limited due to the low percentage of previous project experience. The topics that the students met were limited to one specific topic, and they had not integrated different dimensions. This result followed by various expectations of the student by attending the course.

Hydrometeorology was chosen as one of the ten courses because it is a common topic among UGM students, particularly those from the Department of Forestry. In addition, this course provides basic knowledge specifically in understanding the scope of meteorology, hydrology, and climatology in forest resources management. Furthermore, this course focuses on mitigating hydrometeorological disasters. These scopes of learning are in line with the idea of SDG 13, which says to take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts; that is why it is important to integrate SDG principles and values into this course. The hydrometeorology course has 200 undergraduate students. This course aims to introduce hydrological, meteorological, and forest climatological aspects. The scope of learning in this course includes principles, methods, measurements, and analysis related to hydrometeorological parameters from the forestry sector. Through this course, students are expected to understand the scope of the study and current issues, analyze meteorological disasters, and facilitate disaster mitigation strategies and adaptation to other problems in the forestry sector. In terms of the learning process, this course implements a

New Knowledge (45%)

Learning more (9%)

Attractive learning methods (9%)

Practical Knowledge (3)

Figure 4 : Student's expectation Diagram

The result showed that students had various expectations related to the Hydrometeorology course. The Hydrometeorology Students expected to gain new knowledge, advance their knowledge related to the course, and gain practical knowledge through attractive learning methods. This result shows that practical knowledge was expected as one of the results that the student can get through the Hydrometeorology learning processes.

Discussion

3. What, Why, and Where Questions for Revising (Hydrometeorology Course: Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing it through the Lens of SDGs)

The hydrometeorology course is supposed to be the basic course in the first semester. This course aims to give students basic knowledge related to hydrology, meteorology, and climatology.

Hydrometeorology was considered one of the Faculty Expertise Courses with mandatory status for students in the Faculty of Forestry. The competencies in this course are fundamental concepts of hydrology, meteorology, and climatology, the important role of forests in controlling hydrological cycles, water balance components, and case studies of disasters related to hydrometeorology. Those processes are used to analyze changes in hydrological character and mitigation of disasters. This course implements student-based learning through a group discussion inside the class. The assessment is carried out through the assessment of performance, participation, assignments, and report of student group discussion.

A student-based learning system. The learning process is carried out with several learning activities, including quizzes, individual assignments, group discussions, case studies, and group presentations.

This course focuses on providing a comprehensive understanding of the basic concepts of hydrology, meteorology, and climatology, as well as constructing the

mitigation of disaster in the scope of hydrometeorology. The Hydrometeorology learning process before revision was conducted theoretically through material explanation and group discussion supported by ICTs facilities. Prior to the revision, this course has supported undergraduate students in constructing and transforming knowledge (learning to know) by identifying the relation between the concept of hydrology, meteorology, and climatology with ecosystem balance as well as environment sustainability; developing concern of students about certain hydrometeorology phenomena that can affect human life (learning to be); Understanding that every human activity will affect to the environment and potentially disrupts sustainability as well as finding out the solution for specific Hydrometeorology problems (learning to live together and learning to do); Contributing to educating and protecting society as a part to achieve sustainability (learning to transform oneself and society); disseminating knowledge to community in order to improve the quality of knowledge and information. Based on the explanation above, it was known that six learning pillars for sustainable development were applied as the fundamental values of the Hydrometeorology learning process. However, the explicit introduction of SDGs has not supported the implementation of those pillars. This course is a strategic tool to internalize the value of SDGs, specifically in terms of the environment. However, the value of SDGs has not been introduced explicitly to the students. The main topic of this course is about the environment (forestry issues), which is represented by SDG 13, which says *take urgent. Action to combat climate change and its impacts*. Unfortunately, this Hydrometeorology course was only able to implement 8 Cs from the 10 Cs expected to be implemented through the course, including critical thinking, communication, collaboration, connectivity, critical consciousness, critical reflection, cross-cultural competencies, and constructing knowledge.

It is important to develop revisions in this course. The first revision must focus on explicitly infusing SDGs' ideas and values through the course content. Ten competencies are important to be integrated through the learning process in the Hydrometeorology course; those competencies can be a great collaborative way in terms of reflecting, conceptualizing, constructing, and assessing knowledge. The competencies that have not been included in this course before revision should be added, including co-responsibility, creativity, and innovation. Co-responsibility can be defined as a culture of sharing and shifting to less ego-centric practices and principles, while connectivity leads to the complexity of human-society-nature interaction that can be encouraged by ICT-driven supports (Makrakis, 2017). The content of the Hydrometeorology course needs to be integrated with SDGs value by giving more attention to the environmental, social, economic, and cultural aspects to combat climate change and manage forestry resources. According to those reflections, this course will pay more attention to the chosen theme of SDGs integrated with problem-based learning and the preparation of supporting media (visual videos) and other ICTs. The learning process should be integrated with SDG number 13, which says to

take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts. By understanding that this course provides knowledge that is entirely related to many natural phenomena and the possibility of disaster in the scope of Hydrometeorology, it is important to develop the content, curricula, and learning process. Advanced course, specifically the integration of the learning process with SDG ideas and principles, plays a critical role in achieving environmental sustainability. Through this integration, students are expected to understand critically the environmental changes that are able to affect human life. That is why it is important to increase the awareness of the appropriate mitigation towards disaster followed by a deeper understanding of managing natural resources in appropriate ways. Furthermore, this course should be supported by ICT as a modern education tool to increase the student's awareness of sustainability.

The How Question

The revision in the Hydrometeorology course used the DeCoRe Plus Model to identify the previous course as well as construct a new perspective for the advanced course. Based on previous discussions, the objectives, as well as the need to construct a curriculum that is in line with the ideas of sustainability, the reconstruction of the Hydrometeorology course curriculum is carried out. Students were assessed based on their direct experiences using a systematic questionnaire. This assessment was carried out based on the DREAM Methodology. This is descriptive qualitative research with primary data sources obtained directly from students as respondents conducting the survey. The survey was done by providing an online survey form that was supposed to be filled out by students of the Hydrometeorology course. The form was constructed based on DREAM Methodology Models consisting of five stages: Diagnose, Review, Explain, Assess, and Manage. The data analysis was based on the DeCoRe Plus Methodology advanced by Makrakis (2017).

Through the assessment process, this research conducted the review stage, which takes place when students have completed half of the total lectures of the Hydrometeorology course. This stage aims to identify both positive and negative incidents experienced by students. Through the result of the assessment, we were able to figure out the learning process, both the positive and negative sides. The positive side was dominated by the experience of understanding new knowledge related to Hydrometeorological topics as well as new skills that the students get through the course. Those skills were able to be built through the process of case discussion and assignment that encourage students to be more critical, collaborative, communicative, and critically conscious, as well as aware of cross-cultural issues and Hydrometeorological issues in general. Those skills can be improved during the learning process so the students become more aware of their surrounding issues (Biasutti et al., 2018; Biasutti & Frate, 2017). Meanwhile, the negative experience was dominated by the lack of technical or ICT support during the course. Students have to struggle more during the

learning process since the pandemic situation limited the chance to meet directly with other friends. This condition affected how students conduct group discussions, so they have to be adaptive by familiarizing ICT support communication during the course. From the description, it can be known that there was a gap between the student's expectations and what they got during a half period of the course. This condition can happen because the topic of Hydrometeorology is a new topic for almost all students, it became more complicated during the COVID-19 Pandemic era.

The Now What Question

Through the assessment, the students of the Hydrometeorology course found out that this course has been improved in terms of materials, learning methods, course learning outcomes, as well as tasks compared to other courses. From the assessment, we can see the impact of the course on academic development, professional development, surrounding society, as well as the personality of the students. Based on the responses from the assessment, there is improvement in terms of the academic development of Hydrometeorology students. From the feedback, it can be known that there is an improvement in the scope of academic development supported by an appropriate learning process of the Hydrometeorology course in one semester. It has clearly stated that this course is considered a basic course that is given to students in the first semester, so this course can be a basic foundation for the students to understand another course in the next semester. This improvement was followed by implementing ten competencies (10 Cs) in the daily learning process. From this course, the students can identify specific problems from environmental, social, economic, and cultural perspectives. The ability of critical thinking was able to lead the students to get a wider perspective and more profound understanding related to specific issues, specifically in Hydrometeorology. Recent cases that are given for group discussion were able to encourage students to be literate based on data and think critically to build an argument. Furthermore, these learning circumstances were able to push students to look for valid and credible data and resources supported by ICTs. This group discussion trained the students to have certain skills, as well as critical reflection. Those competencies are important to construct knowledge. Besides constructing knowledge, there is a need to disseminate the knowledge to society for the purpose of distributing broader knowledge and information. This process needs specific skills, including intercultural competencies, co-responsibility, and constructing knowledge. Each of the competencies was integrated with the ideas and principles of sustainability.

In terms of professional development, we found out that Hydrometeorological students also achieved an improvement. Through the responses, we know that this course encourages specific professional characteristics and skills of the student, including case analysis, time management, problem-solving, collective discussion, collaboration, and the capability for priority setting. This

result shows a difference from the previous course prior to the revision. From the side of social development, it can be known that this course has a significant impact, including improving social problem awareness and communication skills towards society, as well as integrating the values of sustainability. Those skills can be used for practical purposes, such as recommending specific social problems. This course transformed the content of the Hydrometeorology course by infusing

explicitly the importance of sustainability values in the scope of social life. Another aspect is personal development. Through this course, the student was able to improve the personal qualities needed in the learning process, including personal awareness of hydrometeorological issues, curiosity, adaptability, responsibility, and empathy for environmental issues in general. Furthermore, the course conducted online gave a particular challenge for students, specifically in achieving an effective learning process. Based on that condition, some inputs appeared to pay more attention to the learning media and teaching methods to achieve an effective learning process, especially in this pandemic era.

Furthermore, from the result of the assessment, in the management stage of the DREAM methodology that focuses on what should be done to achieve an ideal learning process in the future, we found that there must be a strategic integration through the course materials. This learning system encourages students to be more innovative both theoretically and practically (broader references and collective discussion), improves literacy towards ICT tools and supports, and increases awareness of certain social and environmental issues related to the course. All of the responses above were followed by the response about what kind of change should be applied to the course. Those responses showed that for the student, the Hydrometeorology course is an important course since this will be an essential foundation for another course ahead. Actual issues brought to the course could encourage the students' awareness and comprehensive understanding of hydrology, meteorology, and climatology. This learning circumstance optimized students' awareness to be supported by knowledge and skills to achieve sustainability ideas and principles.

Through the revision, implementing SDGs into the course gave the students a better understanding since the sustainability values were clearly stated. There were differences in how the students could understand the critical role of hydrometeorological science in mitigating the effects of climate change or environmental degradation. It can be said that the integration of SDG values plays a critical role in improving students' understanding of the content. Moreover, the implementation of 6 learning pillars and 10 competencies helps students apply knowledge in practical ways.

The 'So What' Question

Since the processes of deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing the Hydrometeorology course through

the lens of SDGs, there were challenges from the beginning of the processes. It was a great challenge since massive integration of specific values will need an appropriate adaptation. This commitment to the advanced course should be followed by the changes in content, various new assessments, and learning strategies, as well as

the use of ICT tools to support the learning activities. It was completely possible that we found obstacles through the process. The gap between students' expectations and what they got from the course was becoming a certain difficulty.

Undergraduate students in Hydrometeorology courses were still in a transition between students from high school and university. That explained that giving an integrative lesson can take a long time for them to understand it completely. Moreover, the topics of Hydrology, Meteorology, and Climatology were considered new for most students. That was the reason why this course needed to adjust to an ideal learning method: to ensure the students understood the basic knowledge as well as the relation towards ideas of sustainability. As the course focuses on environmental issues, the learning materials should be followed by contextual cases and issues. In this course, students were divided into many discussion groups. That is why it takes more time for discussion than theoretical learning.

The infusion of SDG values explicitly into the learning content combined with the confirmed cases surprisingly created a new point of view for the students. This was proved by the results of the assessment, which showed that students' awareness was improved. This answers the question that a real issue should support SDG values to create a deeper understanding among students. Based on the process of deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing through the lens of SDGs in the Hydrometeorology course, the students should have a comprehensive understanding of the course materials about hydrology, meteorology, and climatology based on real-world issues. SDG ideas and principles should play a critical role as catalysts for students to understand the concept of sustainability. This is in line with Pallant, E., Choate, B., & Haywood, B. (2020), which stated that the values as well as principles of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are designed to mobilize countries around the world to end all forms of poverty, inequalities, tackle climate change, as well as ensuring that there is no one left behind. Besides elaborate SDG values and real-world issues, applying appropriate learning methods to the course was important. It can be done by conducting problem-based learning as well as a discussion in groups to make students think critically as a first competency of 10 and able to implement the other 9 competencies through learning activities. However, it is of particular importance to take into consideration various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues on the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al., 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

This revised curriculum, learning, and teaching process of the Hydrometeorology course is supposed to impact both local and global society. By considering the student as an agent of change, having a sustainable-based mindset is important to define what will be done by the student, including educational aspect, social aspect, professional, as well as personality that can directly affect surrounding society. The ideas of sustainability that become the basic foundation of thinking are expected to enable the students to disseminate knowledge or information correctly to society. From all the revision processes that have been done, it can be known how hard knowledge is to stand without a real case of example, as well as the values that can be the frameworks to guide the learning process and goals. This leads us to another understanding that the values of SDGs must be seen as a framework for the student to learn inside the course that is still in line with the challenges outside as well as social, economic, environmental, and cultural problems. That is how we see this integration as an urgency to be implemented towards the course, specifically in the university. So, the implementation of SDGs' ideas and principles is needed to improve the hydrometeorology course and align it with the concept of sustainability.

Conclusion

This world recently is facing significant challenges in terms of social, environmental, economic, as well as cultural crises across the nations. Education plays a critical role as an agent of change in line with the values of sustainability. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) catalyze transformation in the education sector. The content of the course should be in line with the values of sustainability. In the case of the Hydrometeorology course, there is a missing link between the content in the forestry sector and the idea of a sustainable environment. That is why it becomes important to integrate the course with the ideas of SDG 13, which is *taking urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts*.

Implementing the DeCoRe Plus for embedding environment sustainability through the course curricula supported by ICTs and driven by six pillars of learning as well as 10 Competencies (10 Cs) is an appropriate alternative to improve education in university. Assessment using the DREAM Methodology has been conducted for the student to know their perspective before and after the revision. From the result, it can be known that at the beginning of the course, there was a gap between expectations and results that the students got along the course. Furthermore, the values of SDGs have not been stated clearly, so the students were not learning based on the concept of sustainability.

Through the revision, we found that there is an improvement in the form of a broader perspective and deeper understanding of sustainability related to hydrology, meteorology, and climatology issues. This improvement including aspects of educational, professional, social, as well as personality. The DeCoRe Plus led students into a practical transformation as it generated fundamental learning skills and competencies

for the students. Furthermore, embedding sustainable values into the course must be supported by unlocking ICTs to support learning activities. Technology is a crucial part of what is happening in the classroom (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2012). The support of technology through learning processes (internet, visual learning videos, LCD) helps students face difficulties and understand the knowledge they get inside the course.

Besides the improvement that can be achieved, we faced some challenges through the assessment and the learning process. Those challenges, including the understanding of students since this course, were new topics and were given during the transition period in the first semester. The pandemic era gives another challenge in terms of technology support and its efficiency during the online class. This condition leads to difficulties for students completely understanding the materials and the group discussion for specific issues. However, it is of particular importance to take into consideration various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues about the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al., 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

Through all the revision that has been done, it can be known how hard knowledge is to stand without real examples, as well as the values that can be the frameworks to guide the learning process and goals. That shows the importance of implementing the SDG ideas and principles to improve the Hydrometeorology course in line with the concept of sustainability.

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The General Biology Course: Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing the General Biology Course Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

Biology is a subject that directly relates to our living and environment. In addition, complex and comprehensive biological materials have the same value as several in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) agreement. Some SDGs' goals contain material from the biological sciences, including biotic and abiotic elements of ecosystems, pollution, and living things. In this course, students study Classical Biology in classes and explore Biology through field and laboratory work. This course aims to instill the basic knowledge and principles related to the structure and function within organisms and in their environment in connecting with sustainable justice, six key learning pillars, and 10 Critical Skills. ICT-based learning was used to facilitate theoretical understanding.

Keywords: General Biology, ICT, Sustainability Justice, SDGs,

1. Introduction

Living things and signs of life are discussed in General Biology. The fundamentals of living matter, the cell's structure and function, the cell's energy cycle, genetic information, mutation, and gene engineering are all topics covered in this course. In addition, this course covers the control, coordination, evolution, biodiversity, ecology, and behavior of organisms, as well as their structure, function, growth, and development. This course aims to transmit essential ideas and knowledge about organisms' structure, functional functioning, and environment.

Referring to the overall goals, the course's specific goals are for students to be able to: 1. express fundamental physics and chemistry principles related to the life process; 2. conceptualize biological phenomena within organisms and their environments; 3. classify organisms and demonstrate a basic understanding of taxonomy and systematics; 4. integrate the relationship between organisms and their environments; and 5. explain the value of maintaining biodiversity for the environment.

The biological sciences are referenced in some of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including the biotic and abiotic components of ecosystems, pollution, and living organisms. Biology has a crucial role in preserving ecosystems to promote environmental resilience. As a result, it was decided to deconstruct and reconstruct this course to incorporate information and communication technology (ICT).

In principle, biology is quite like living things, but not all learning activities incorporate the six pillars of sustainability, the 10Cs, or the four dimensions of justice. The topic of environmental justice in the course integrated

the interaction between living things and their surroundings. Students must understand their place as a person, a member of society, and most importantly, a biosphere member, even if this course merely covers ecology fundamentals. They are fully aware of the potential impact of their actions on the environment. Students take charge of implementing environmental justice through simple steps like minimizing paper usage by conducting writing assessments entirely online. From a sustainable world perspective, the course covers conceptualizing biological phenomena within organisms and the environment. An emphasis on social, economic, and cultural justice is necessary for this learning.

The content of biological material is very complex, starting from studying living things, the environment, and the use of living things for the welfare of the people. This course is very effective in realizing sustainability justice and realizing the SDGs. Higher education is important in disseminating SD principles (Biasutti & Frate, 2017; Biasutti et al., 2018). However, several academic goals are missing and must immediately be added and explained based on what is expected from education. Connecting the course to the six pillars of learning and the 10Cs should also be improved.

Furthermore, students must be able to integrate and relate their academic subjects to issues of social, economic, and cultural justice in addition to environmental justice. Additionally, by using ICT as a cutting-edge instructional tool to raise students' knowledge of the SDGs, teachers can help students comprehend how humans can be impacted by environmental change and biodiversity loss.

2. Methodology

2.1 DeCoRe Plus

The DeCoRe plus is an abbreviation for Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction methodology. The DeCoRe is supplemented by three other steps: Diagnostic Evaluation, Implementation, and Summative Evaluation (Makrakis, 2017). The aim of deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing the General Biology course was to merge the four dimensions of sustainability justice. Moreover, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the General Biology course.

Accordingly, the General Biology course would undergo six processes: **(1) Diagnose**. In this process, we reflect on who we are, what we have, want to do, and why we want to go there. **(2) Deconstructing**. This step analyzes the functioning of personal perspectives, habits of mind, and chosen curriculum units/modules. **(3) Constructing**. The constructing process is conducted by gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives), **(4) Reconstructing**. This reconstructing process is when integrating newly constructed knowledge aligns with the reconstructed frame of reference, **(5) Implementing**. Implementation starts initially with the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning. **(6) Finalizing**. The last was to reflect and evaluate what has been learned and changed.

Fig 1. The DeCoRe plus interaction (Makrakis, 2017)

2.2 DREAM Methodology

The dream methodology was used to evaluate the General Biology course based on the perspectives of the students who have joined the course. The assessment is done before, during, and after implementing the reconstructed General Biology course for undergraduate students. This evaluation method consists of several steps: Diagnose, Review, Explain, Asses, and Manage. The students do the diagnosis process to determine what exists in the General Biology course. This is followed by a Review and Explanation, which is usually conducted during the implementation of the reconstructed course. Lastly, the assessment and management are done at the end of the implementation process. Assessments are to know whether anything changes before and after reconstruction. In the end, the instructors analyze and use portfolios from the students to get input for the reconstruction of the General Biology course.

Fig 2. The Dream Methodology (Makrakis, 2019)

2.3 Data Collection

The data were collected using a survey method. We provide an online survey form (Google form) to students who took the general biology course. In the form, we also gather the student's identity, such as name, email address, and student number. We also provide a disclaimer and ask students for their consent. No alteration was made while transforming the questionnaire into an e-form. All the answers given by respondents were downloaded, grouped based on courses, and further analyzed.

3 Result and Discussion

3.1 Deconstruction of General Biology course

The General Biology course covers biology as a science and its future development, the underlying living material, the cell as a fundamental structural and functional unit, cell energy and cycle, genetic information, mutation, and gene engineering. This course also confers organisms' structure, function, growth, and development; regulation and coordination; evolution; biodiversity; ecology; and behavior. This course consists of 4 credits, divided into 3 class credits and one practicum credit in the laboratory and the field, depending on the subject matter. This course is compulsory for students in the first semester.

Biology is a subject that directly relates to our living and environment. In addition, complex and comprehensive biological materials have the same value as several in the SDGs agreement. Some of the SDG's goals contain material in which there is material from the biological sciences, including biotic and abiotic elements of ecosystems, pollution, and living things.

The contribution of biology is significant in protecting ecosystems to support environmental resilience. This is one of the basic concepts for achieving sustainable development goals (Khairina et al., 2020). Thus, this course was selected to be deconstructed and reconstructed to infuse Information and Communication Technology (ICT).

Although this course is a basic one, it will spark student interest. Students not only study classical biology in classes but also explore Biology through field and laboratory

work. This course introduces first-semester students to the most current issues in Biology and also introduces them to environmental problems that will impact the community. For example, students are shown biological-related movies/documentaries and must make and present a poster in a poster competition as a final project.

This course aims to instill the basic knowledge and principles related to the structure and function that occurs within organisms and in their environment. Referring to the general aims, the specific objective of this course is that students will be able to:

1. Encourage students' scientific, critical, reflective, and creative thinking.
2. instill the basic principles of physics and chemistry related to the life process and how to entail the effective environmental praxis
3. conceptualize biological phenomena within organisms and environment,
4. imbue to the student how humans can impact and get affected by environmental changes and biodiversity

loss and integrate ICT as a modern educational tool to heighten ESD awareness

The learning method was student-centered, with problem-based learning, group project work, and group presentation. Some research proves that using Problem-based learning, group project work, and group discussions could enhance effective learning in students (Biasutti & EL-Deghaidy, 2015; Biasutti & Frate 2018). Also, the integration of ICT could be effective for learning (Biasutti, 2011). Small group work, often used in this class, allows students to learn how to work in a team, in the process of which they identify and fill the gaps in their knowledge (Attard *et al.*, 2010)

Students were assessed based on key concepts by direct method. We infused three assessment components: sustainability justice, six learning pillars, and 10Cs (Makrakis & Kostoulas, 2020). Such as quizzes, formative tests, assignments, presentations, poster competitions, peer review, assistant teacher observation, pretest, posttest, laboratory research proposal, laboratory work report, and laboratory activity, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Methods of assessment

Key concept	Methods of Assessment											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
I. Sustainability justice												
a. Environmental justice	√	√	√									
II. Six learning pillars												
a. Learning to know		√								√	√	
b. Learning to be												√
c. Learning to live together				√								√
d. Learning to do												√
e. Learning to transform oneself	√	√										√
f. Learning to give and share				√			√				√	√
III. 10Cs												
a. Collaboration								√	√			√
b. Communication				√	√							
c. Critical thinking and problem solving	√	√	√			√				√	√	
d. Cross-cultural understanding					√							√
e. Connectivity							√		√			
f. Critical reflection		√							√			
g. Critical consciousness		√						√				

Key concept	Methods of Assessment											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
h. Constructing knowledge		√						√				

Note

1. Methods of assessment: Quiz
2. Formative test
3. Assignment
4. Presentation
5. Poster competition
6. Peer review
7. Teacher assistant observation
8. Pretest
9. Post test
10. Laboratory research proposal
11. Laboratory work report
12. Laboratory activity

Before the revision, the learning process was more on theoretical aspects than practice and problem-based learning activities. For example, in studying rare animals, previously, students tended to only study theoretically without their character, function, identity, conservation status, and role for living things and their environment. ICT-based learning was used to facilitate theoretical understanding. For instance, in this activity, the students were divided into groups, and each group got Rp50.000 as a biodiversity conservation fund. They have to select one of the endangered animals in Indonesia through the internet to collect information about this animal.

Biology is very close to living things, but not all learning activities apply the four dimensions of sustainability justice, six pillars, and 10Cs. The course has addressed environmental justice by integrating the relationship between organisms and their environment. Despite this course covering only introductory ecology, the students are expected to understand their position as individuals, part of the population, and foremost part of the biosphere. Hence, they fully understand that their actions could impact the environment. Students were led to implement environmental justice through simple activities such as reducing paper use by writing tests paperless through online platforms. The course addresses social justice by conceptualizing the biological phenomenon within organisms and their surroundings in relation to the sustainability world. Social, economic, and cultural justice must be emphasized and focused on this learning.

The content of biological material is very complex, starting from studying living things, the environment, and the use of living things for the welfare of the people. Thus, this course is very effective in realizing sustainability justice to realize the SDGs.

Although curriculum goals were mentioned in the curriculum handbook, some parts should be reconstructed to reflect the psychology, philosophy, and aim of Indonesia's national education system. Curriculum goals are itemized as Social and Civic, Personal, Vocational, and Historical and cultural goals. However, academic goals are missing and must be added immediately and explained based on what is

expected from education. In addition, connecting the course to the six pillars and 10Cs should be improved.

Students are expected to be able to integrate and connect learning materials not only with environmental justice but also with social, economic, and cultural justice. For instance, to end poverty (SDG No. 1), ensure inclusive and quality education (SDGs No. 2), achieve gender equality (SDG No 5), ensure access to energy (SDGs No. 6), promote economic growth (SDGs No. 8), build resilient infrastructure (SDGs No 9), promote peaceful (SDGs No 16) and strengthen the partnership (SDGs No 17) (United Nations, 2022).

In addition, students should understand how humans can be impacted by environmental change and the loss of biodiversity by integrating ICT as a modern educational tool to increase SDG awareness.

3.2. Reconstruction of General Biology course

The reconstruction of the General Biology course follows the DeCoRe+ methodology by Makrakis (2017). The reconstruction is to gather all the information regarding the deconstruction of the General Biology course in the previous section. The implementation process then follows the reconstruction. Implementation of the reconstructed General Biology course was addressed to the students. The students before, during, and after the course implementation have to fill in an online survey. The students' shared opinions may help in giving input about the reconstruction of the General Biology course.

Analysis based on the Dream Methodology was conducted. The first step is diagnosing the undergraduate students' previous knowledge. Twenty-five students completed the DREAM Methodology questionnaire for the General Biology course. For the question, "Have you ever attended a course on this topic or skill area in the past?" Thirty-seven-point-five percent (37.5%) of students said yes, and 62.5% said No. The students said they had similar courses mentioned in Biology courses in high school.

Biology is part of a natural science course mandatory for junior and senior high school. Thus, it should be natural that most students have had this similar course. However, *Have you ever created a project or written work similar to*

this course? Most students (83%) said no, and only 17% said yes, that they had created a project or written work similar to what we had given in this biology course. This means that our approach to delivering the course has made the students feel that they are studying something new in these courses. This conclusion was then strengthened by the fact that only 13% of the students agreed on whether they ever worked on similar topics in this course, and 88% of them said otherwise. The summary of the data is presented below in Table 2.

Table 2. Proportion of students exposed to course/work/issues that are similar to the General Biology course

Answers	Attended similar course		Created project similar to the course		Worked dealing with issues similar to the course	
	students	%	students	%	students	%
YES	9	36.00	4	16.00	3	12.00
NO	16	64.00	21	84.00	22	88.00
Total	25	100.00	25	100.00	25	100.00

The ones that said they have experience working on similar topics share their experience as below:

...a practitioner on a high school biology practice exam...
 ...laying out the main framework for the public park...

Based on the students' responses' expectations from the General Biology course is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 Student's expectation from the General Biology course diagram

The students' main expectations about the General Biology course were gaining more knowledge (39%), learning new knowledge (24%), and validating their comprehension of General Biology (15%). The top three percentages were followed by the students expecting to obtain practical knowledge to apply in real-life conditions (12%). To sum up, the students' main expectation of the course is to learn knowledge.

The second step of the Dream Methodology is to *Review or Reflect*. This occurs when the students have completed half of the total lectures in the General Biology course. When asked, 'What happened during a half period of

your course?', the responses from the students had similar experiences. The positive responses mainly explained that they were excited and enjoyed the group discussion. Thus, I gained a deeper comprehension of the lectures given in the General Biology course.

Meanwhile, most students responded that their negative experience is that the class felt boring, leading to sleepiness. Additionally, some felt burdened by the number of reports and homework given. The students also mentioned technical problems such as internet connection problems and inaccessible materials to download.

The third step is to *Explain*. This process is the follow-up of the previous question. The respondents were asked *In case some of your expectations from the first half of the course have not been how you expected, why is it so? How do you explain that?* Students tried to give their perspectives on why the General Biology course conducted had not yet met their expectations. Several factors were obtained from the responses. First, the lecturers had different teaching styles. Second, students have different capabilities in receiving new information—third, technical issues such as unstable connection problems and fewer teaching hours.

The fourth step is to *Assess*. The assessment process was held at the end of the course. The students were required to fill in the impacts of what they had learned. The impacts were divided into four categories: Academic development, Professional development, social development, and Personal development. The students responded that the general biology course gave them stronger fundamental knowledge, which helped them in other, more advanced courses. Responses regarding the knowledge the students obtain for their professional development are that they gain laboratory skills. However, several students feel the course did not contribute much to their employment or professional development. Next is the social development aspect. The students stated that the general biology course assisted them in explaining biological processes to other people and becoming more aware of current societal issues.

The fifth step is to *Manage*. Based on the student's responses to the question, *what can you change, or how can you apply the new knowledge learned from the course in the future?*

Adding to the assessments given by the students who filled in the online survey based on the DREAM methodology, the reconstructed General Biology course description was polished into explanations about living beings, signs of life, and a sustainable future for all humans and creatures. The objectives of the course were also reconstructed as follows:

1. encourage scientific, critical, reflective, and creative thinking in students.
2. instill the basic principles of physics and chemistry related to the life process and how to entail the effective environmental praxis
3. conceptualize biological phenomena within organisms and environment,
4. imbue to the student how humans can impact and get affected by environmental changes and biodiversity loss

5. integrate ICT as a modern educational tool to heighten ESD awareness

The reconstructed General Biology course's learning outcomes correlate to the course's objectives. The students are expected to be able to:

1. demonstrate and construct an understanding of principles and theories related to all living organisms' structure, function, and reproduction.
2. classify the living organism into biology systematics
3. apply the principle of scientific methods way of thinking to understand environmental change and the problem
4. analyze the human impact of environmental changes and biodiversity depletion and vice versa.
5. apply biological theories for developing humanity awareness in social media
6. propose a campaign for developing ESD awareness
- 7.

The course module contains four modules: (1) Introduction, Biology Today and Cells, (2) Genetics, (3) Plant and Animal Structure and Function, Evolution, and Diversity, and (4) Ecology.

Introduction, Biology Today and Cells is a module that will teach about the cell as the fundamental structural unit in living organisms. The module also includes experimental approaches that have been taken to investigate the biology of the cell. The module is equipped with a detailed explanation of the weekly activities that need to be done. The integrated SDGs were explicitly mentioned in the module. For instance, activity one and week 1 of the Introduction, Biology Today and Cell incorporate SDGs values focused on SDGs Number 1 (No poverty), 2 (Zero hunger), and 6 (Clean water and sanitation). Furthermore, in activity two, which is about essential chemistry for biology and the molecules of life, the SDGs that are raised include SDGs 2 (Zero Hunger) and 3 (Good Health and Well-Being) (Appendix 1).

The reconstructed course has also incorporated the use of ICTs throughout each module. Videos will help introduce students to the materials or current issues in General Biology. Problem-based learning is implemented in group discussions, where later, the students will have to present their findings regarding a recent topic or current issue.

3.3 Challenges in Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing the General Biology Course

In Indonesia, the basic concepts of biology, in general, have been conveyed since children were in elementary school. For instance, related to the composition of living things, metabolism, and the environment. Therefore, each individual has been exposed to Biology for approximately 12 years before entering college. The most formidable challenge is when they have a different mindset and understanding from deep theory in college. Therefore, what learning method will be used is essential in changing their perspective. For example, case-based learning and ICT facilitate the understanding of concepts. It has to be stressed that attention should be given to various drivers and barriers

at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues of the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

4 Conclusion

The General Biology course was deconstructed, constructed, and reconstructed using the DeCoRe+ approach. The modification of this course was done to implement sustainable development goals into the course. Incorporating the SDGs is important to improve the General Biology course, as the world is facing a sustainability crisis. The SDGs not expressed directly in the syllabus were identified in the deconstruction process. In addition, the four dimensions of sustainability justice, the six pillars of learning, and the 10Cs were also identified during the deconstruction of the course. Correspondingly, the missing aspects are noticed, and the revision process could focus on integrating the missing and existing aspects in the General Biology course. The reconstructed module also includes the use of ICTs to enhance the course.

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Appendix 1: The Activity Lecture of General Biology course

Week 1: Biology today and scientific methods (SDGS No: 1 – 17)

- The lecturer explains the course contract and plan in one semester.
- Every student read about Unsolved problems in biology-The state of current thinking at <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0079610715000115>. From this case, students can make an analytical paper about the following topics to be shared with their colleagues on the online platforms
 - Biological sciences discovery
 - Responses to the outstanding problems in biology
 - Personal Opinion
- Choose a topic about biological issues today from Science Daily (https://www.sciencedaily.com/news/plants_animals/biology/), for example:
 - Preventing Spread of SARS Coronavirus-2 in Humans

- The Brains of Shrimps and Insects are More Alike Than We Thought
 - The Microbes in Your Mouth
 - Unique Non-Oxygen Breathing Animal Discovered or, Watch this video about conventional and modern agriculture "Laptop Si Until: Pertanian di Bumi Pertiwi" through this <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yPa5LO-90Zc>
- Working in groups: apply and identify the scientific methodology to solve the biological problems in Activity number 2
 - Observation
 - Research question
 - Hypothesis
 - Prediction
 - Test of prediction (experimental design and methods)
 - Result
 - Conclusion
 - Discussion between groups
 - Lecture review
 - The lecturer gives a task to the students to read about essential chemistry for biology, for preparing the next meeting (week 2)
 - Each student makes a paper titled "Biology for Indonesia: The Role of Biology in Achieving the SDGs". This assignment is collected at the Final Test

Week 2: Essential Chemistry for Biology and The Molecules of Life (SDGS No: 2, 3)

- The lecturer asked to the students about the homework and online networking activities last week
- The lecturer discusses and leads an open brainstorming session about the basics of chemistry in biological science and molecules of life
- Watch a video about:
 - Our Chemical Lives at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J9SWBAUIA-vw>
 - Importance of Chemistry in Life, Everyday Uses at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L2Q2q20KaEk>
- Discuss the video: 3 – 4 students. In this activity, each group discussed this video in the following points of:
 - The definition of atoms and molecules
 - Macromolecules: Types and role in the body
- Group Presentations
- Lecture review

Week 3: A Tour of the Cell and The Working of the Cell

- Quiz: Please draw the schematic cell of bacteria, plant, and animal
- Lecturer and students discuss the quiz answer

3. Watch a video about the Inner Life of Cell at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=B_zD3NxSsD8
4. The lecturer gives a review of the video and an explanation about:
 - a. The difference between prokaryotic and eukaryotic cells
 - b. The structure and function of cell compartments
5. Discussion

Week 4: Cellular Respiration: Obtaining Energy from Food

1. The lecturer asks questions to all the students:
 - a. What is energy?
 - b. What is ATP?
 - c. How do cells obtain energy from food?
2. The lecturer clarifies "How Cells Obtain Energy from Food," including:
 - a. Food molecules are broken down in three stages to produce ATP
 - b. Glycolysis is a central ATP-producing pathway
 - c. Fermentation allows ATP to be produced in the absence of oxygen
 - d. Glycolysis illustrates how enzymes couple oxidation to energy storage
 - e. Sugars and fats both degraded to Acetyl CoA in Mitochondria
 - f. The Citric Acid Cycle generates NADH by oxidizing acetyl groups to CO₂
 - g. Electron transport drives the synthesis of most ATP in most cells
 - h. Organisms store food molecules in unique reservoirs
3. Students are asked to do the task: calculate ATP production in cellular respiration
4. Lecture clarification of the answer to activity number 3
5. The lecture gives information that students must read about energy production in cells at this link <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK26882/>

Week 5: Photosynthesis: Using Light to Make Food

1. Work in a group (3 – 4 students), about this video at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PSGKRd7Bbl0>
2. Group Presentations
3. Lecture review
4. The lecturer gives an explanation about the photosynthesis process in C₃, C₄, and CAM plant
5. Discussion

Week 6: Genetics

1. The lecturer gives a detailed explanation about the following topics among reflective feedback from the students to formulate a holistic view for all participants
 - a. Cellular reproduction: cells from cells
 - b. Patterns of Inheritance

- c. The Structure and Function of DNA
- d. How Genes are Controlled
- e. DNA Technology
2. Watch video:
 - a. Cell cycle: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U5vAO_f2LDQ
 - b. Nucleic acid: DNA and RNA structure: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0lZRAShqft0>
 - c. Recombinant DNA technology: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rB6B0qIrozE>
3. Work in a group (3 – 4 students) and discuss the case study in recombinant DNA Technology and Biosafety from <https://www.nature.com/scitable/forums/genetics-generation/case-study-in-recombinant-dna-technology-and-105751339/>
4. Students presentation: selected groups by lecturer (2 groups)
5. Open discussion
6. Lecture review

Week 7: Plant Structure and Function (1)

1. The lecturer gives a review and explanation about plant structure and function, followed by students' reflections formulating their understanding of the plant structure and different functions and importance in the environmental system
2. Watch the video entitled "Plant Structure and Function" at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J9fm9RbL_Sw
3. Open discussion
4. The lecturer gives a group assignment for activities 2 and 4. Each group consists of 3 – 4 students and must present a different topic. The first five groups will present about plant structure and function, and the rest will present about animal structure and function.
5. The lecturer provides the presentation topics, and the student can choose one of the topics below:
 - a. Tissue, organ, and organisms
 - b. Structure and function of root, stem, and leaf of dicotyledon
 - c. Structure and function of root, stem, and leaf of monocotyledon
 - d. Types of plant macro and micronutrients
6. Guttation, transpiration, and water secretion

Week 8: Plant Structure and Function (2)

1. Group presentation for each group
 2. Discussions
 3. Lecture review
- Mini quiz

Week 9: Animal Structure and Function (1)

1. The lecturer gives a review and explanation about animal structure and function, followed by students' reflections formulating their understanding of the

- animals' life and role and importance in the environmental system
2. Watch the video entitled "Animal Structure and Function" at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YeSXuSUaTRk>
 3. Discussion
 4. The lecturer reminds us that groups 6 - 10 will present about animal structure and function.
 5. The lecture gives the presentation topics to the students
 - a. Animal tissue and organ: motion system
 - b. Animal tissue and organ: coordination system
 - c. Animal tissue and organ: respiratory system
 - d. Animal tissue and organ: excretion system
 - e. Animal tissue and organ: digestion system

Week 10: Animal Structure and Function (2)

1. Group presentation for each group
2. Discussions
3. Lecture review
4. Mini quiz

Week 11: Reproduction and Development

1. Students are asked to observe plant and animal development in the campus yard for 10 minutes
2. Lecturer gives some basic questions:
 - a. How do living things reproduce and develop?
 - b. Why do they reproduce and develop?
 - c. How do environmental factors influence life cycles and development?
3. Lecturer explains and reviews in terms:
 - a. Life cycle and metagenesis
 - b. Growth factors
 - c. Development factors
 - d. Asexual and sexual reproduction
 - e. Stages of development
4. Discussion
5. The lecturer gives some homework for the next activity:
 - a. students must read and make a resume about "On the Theory of Evolution Versus the Concept of Evolution: Three Observations" at <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4778711/> and "Theory of the Origin, Evolution, and Nature of Life" at <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4187144/>
 - b. students should watch the video entitle "How Evolution Works" ["https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hOfRN0KihOU"](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hOfRN0KihOU)

Week 12: Evolution

1. Three student representatives share the results of reading and watching videos
2. Lecturer gives a review and some explanation about evolution theory
3. Discussion

4. Lecturer gives a homework for the next activity. Students must watch video "Biodiversity Loss – A Documentary" at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WKld7o6CISg> and search:
 - a. Endangered species in Indonesia
 - b. Location of endangered species in Indonesia
5. Government policy of endangered species in Indonesia

Week 13: Biodiversity

1. Lecturer gives a mini quiz as the feedback of student homework
2. Work in a group (3-4 students), to discuss:
 - a. Endangered species in Indonesia
 - b. Location of endangered species in Indonesia
 - c. Government policy on endangered species in Indonesia
3. The lecturer asks some basic questions:
 - a. Why biodiversity is important?
 - b. What is biodiversity loss?
 - c. What factors influence biodiversity loss?
 - d. What are the solutions to biodiversity loss?
 - e. What can people/communities do for biodiversity in Indonesia?
4. The lecturer confirms and explains the answer to number 3
5. The lecturer and students make a conclusion from this activity

Week 14: Ecology

1. The lecturer gives a detailed explanation about the following topics, followed by students' reflections formulating their understanding and thoughts
 - a. Introduction to Ecology and The Biosphere
 - b. Population Ecology
 - c. Communities and Ecosystems
2. Work in a group (3 – 4 students) and discuss Spatial point pattern analysis of the Sumatran tiger (*Panthera tigris sumatrae*) poaching cases in and around Kerinci Seblat National Park, Sumatra. This article can be downloaded at <https://biodiversitas.mipa.uns.ac.id/D/D1602/D160228.pdf>
3. Students presentation: selected groups by lecturer (2 groups)
4. Open discussion
5. Lecture review

Reviewing Pancasila Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

Pancasila, as Indonesian philosophy, has existed and developed not only through the affirmation of its national identity but also through the expansion of exchange with the world in order to acquire positive values from other nations. A course in Pancasila has a pivotal role in building and shaping a student's mind as an Indonesian citizen's way of thinking. This course is also a compulsory course at the university level; thus, all of UGM's undergraduate students take this course. This course consists of lectures in the scopes of Pancasila as philosophy and the ground of the Indonesian state, National identity, Politics and strategy, good and clean governance, The culture of democracy, civil society, Supreme of laws, and the declaration of Human Rights. This course will equip students to do creative and Innovative thinking. Students will learn to think and act in an innovative pattern through serving the external environment and heading social and societal prosperity; for example, this course requires students to design new solutions to a problem that is under the values of Pancasila while still considering the condition of the community so that no party is harmed. The DeCoRe method was used to improve the delivery of this course. In the new concept of the Pancasila course, the emphasis on ESD and SDGs as part of Global Idea is highlighted, as well as updated case studies into recent national issues. With the new concept, students' engagement was higher during the course, and they are confident that they can positively impact society.

Keywords: Pancasila, Indonesia, National Identity, Global citizen

1. Introduction

Pancasila, as Indonesian philosophy, has existed and developed not only through the affirmation of its national identity but also through the expansion of exchange with the world in order to acquire positive values from other nations. Only the recognition of diversity and respect for the specificity of various philosophies can help us to agree on the contribution made by philosophy to the life of humankind today (Tim Penyusun, 1990; Notonagoro, 1971).

Unfortunately, in recent decades, Pancasila has degenerated into a mere empty slogan for many. This is unacceptable, as Indonesians must move forward by prioritizing Pancasila in every move they make. The commitment to Pancasila as the Nation's basic philosophy certifies that the State is a living presence in maintaining the people's physical and political security and satisfying people's needs. As the Nation's founding ideology, Pancasila must be present in each heartbeat and breath of the Indonesian people's daily lives. Without consistent implementation, Pancasila's noble wording will become meaningless. Pancasila's daily behavior should be part of the curriculum from elementary school to college. Students of all ages should be required to correctly identify standard behavior exhibited by their family and friends that is compliant or conflicts with Pancasila and act as ambassadors for the active moves. Instead of mere memorization, taking practical examples from daily living is required (Kaelan, 2002), and the use of new methodologies and instruments

such our project-based learning, Inquiry-based learning, and ICT are more effective (Biasutti and El- EL-Deghaidy, 2015; Biasutti, 2011).

The course of Pancasila has a pivotal role in building and shaping students' minds as Indonesian citizens' way of thinking. This course is also a compulsory course at the university level. Thus, all UGM's undergraduate students take this course. Since the course is compulsory and has an important role in shaping the mindset of students as Indonesian citizens, this course was nominated as one to undergo revision. With the number of students that attend this course being around 5000 students/year, the success of this course will impact many students.

This course consists of a series of lectures on Pancasila as philosophy and the grounded of the Indonesian state, National identity, Politics and strategy, good and clean governance, the culture of democracy, civil society, the supremacy of laws, and the declaration of Human Rights (Hastangka et al., 2019; Kaelan, 2002).

Using the scope ranging from good governance to human right, this course is set to facilitate the student to be able to: 1) explain the definition of Pancasila and term in Pancasila; 2) have insight on Pancasila in national history context; 3) analyze Pancasila as a National principle; 4) analyze Pancasila as a National Ideological; 5) analyze and compare Pancasila with others; 6) analyze Pancasila as a Philosophy system; 7) analyze and establish Pancasila as an ethics

system in life, and 8) establish Pancasila as essential for scientific knowledge (Aipipidely & Ekawati, 2018; Jonathan, 2018).

Pancasila refers to civil education, nationality, rights, and obligations of the citizen. This course also discusses human rights, the archipelago, the rationale for their insight into the archipelago, national defense, and national security as a strategy. The philosophy of Pancasila can be classified as a practical philosophy. Pancasila, with its five tenets, is in harmony with the justice value of the world as a whole. The Key different between the current and before courses is the way of delivery. In the old model, the Teacher was teaching rather than becoming a learning facilitator, and the students were on the receiver end. The active involvement of students in learning/class was minimal. In contrast, the current version encourages students to be more active in learning Pancasila, and the teacher is a facilitator and not a single source of materials (Hastangka et al., 2019; Notonagoro, 1971).

2. Method

2.1. Deconstruct and Reconstruct Pancasila

DeCoRe plus is an acronym for the Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction methodology. DeCoRe is complemented by three further steps: diagnostic assessment, implementation, and summative assessment (Marakis, 2017). The goal of dismantling, building, and rebuilding the Pancasila course was to infuse and highlight 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The Pancasila course would undergo six processes: **(1) Diagnose.** In this process, we reflect on who we are, what we have, want to do, and why we want to go there. **(2) Deconstructing.** This step is done to analyze the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules; **(3) Constructing,** the constructing process is conducted by gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives); **(4) Reconstructing.** This reconstructing process is when the integration of newly constructed knowledge is in line with the reconstructed frame of reference, **(5) Implementing.** Implementation starts initially with the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning. **(6) Finalizing.** The last step is to reflect and evaluate what has been learned and changed.

The DREAM methodology was used to evaluate the Pancasila course based on the perspective of the students who took the course. Assessments are conducted before, during, and after the restructured general biology course delivery for undergraduates. This assessment method consists of several steps: Diagnosis, Review, Explain, Assess, and Manage, and enabling ICT employment in the course delivery (Makrakis, 2012; Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2014). The student makes the diagnosis to learn what is in the Pancasila course. Followed by a review and explanation, which usually occurs during the implementation of the restructured course. Finally,

evaluation and management are at the end of the implementation process. Evaluation is knowing if something has changed before and after the reconstruction. Finally, portfolios received from students are analyzed and used by instructors to obtain information for restructuring Pancasila courses.

2.2. Method of Delivery and Student Assessment

As UGM encouraged all courses to adopt student-centered learning with outcome-based education (OBE), the delivery method chosen for the Pancasila course is OBE integrated with PBL. The students were also given the task of developing an action plan on how to live in harmony in the community, have a high spirit of nationalism, prioritize deliberation for consensus, and maintain the integrity of the Indonesian state.

Students are assessed with formative assessment, student-centered assessment, embedded assessment, learner-centered assessment, and classroom assessment (the term we use hereafter) are all monikers that can be used to describe the type of assessment that gives insight into the understanding of the learner, informs teaching practice, and is embedded in the culture of the classroom. In addition, students should develop practical projects to validate the academic side into deliverables, addressing fair environmental, social and economic challenges. The Scoring components in this course are: Final Paper (25%), Midterm and Final test (40%), Quiz (15%), and Homework (20%).

The most notable revision was done by breaking up the class into activity mode based on what students will do rather than what the teacher will teach. By doing student-centered learning, the delivery of learning materials is more comprehensive and with a clear context of learning (Biasutti and EL-Deghaidy (2015). In order to satisfy the requirement of the Indonesian Quality Framework for Higher Education. The learning this course is made to focus on problem-based learning methods, which are effective methods even for science (Biasutti & EL-Deghaidy, 2015).

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. New Competency to be Developed and SDGs Highlight

One of the lesson goals of Pancasila is to increase student nationalism and understanding of the values of Pancasila. This could be assessed through the course work activities, the student's involvement and passion towards Pancasila, and how students are getting ambassadors for those values for the external community. The new paradigm of interfaith relationships brings unity and peaceful societies. The instructor focused on the values, ethics, and basics of the Pancasila philosophical context, not the indicators of improving the quality of life and intercultural harmony among Indonesians. Pancasila courses will cover broad

aspects of Indonesia's Ideology and Identity as a Nation. This course directly and indirectly will cover all of the goals in SDGs with a highlight on SDGs no 1 to 5, 7,10,11, 16, and 17.

In addition, we try to develop the course material based on demand. Thus, the teacher tries to accommodate the collected materials as much as possible. However, we omitted the essential role of citizens in making Pancasila's vision a reality since we needed to focus on Pancasila's foundational base and did not consider the external role of the citizen. We have now discussed the students' role as a first step for external moves.

Inquiry learning can be a recommended approach to preparing and equipping students with the required knowledge and skills. During inquiry-based learning, students might explore the natural or material world; they need to ask their own questions, make discoveries, and test their hypotheses when trying to understand the world around them.

Pancasila's encounter with globalization will produce local people who think globally and act locally. In addition, the marriage between the two will reconcile globality and locality. This learning is learned in social clusters, meaning they are dominant in contact with social life—the attitude of the initiative in responding to all social phenomena related to applying Pancasila values.

Students can assess policies, situations, and phenomena concretely that are in accordance with Pancasila's values so that they can make a real contribution in the form of criticism and suggestions. However, some values are intangible and cannot be measured, such as a sense of nationalism and concern for the surrounding environment.

As a democratic campus, UGM adopts this subject as a compulsory subject for university. In addition, Pancasila lessons are crucial for instilling an ideology that is believed to be unifying Indonesia. Pancasila values can be applied in every area of Indonesia and become a principle that unites the people of Indonesia. This process will produce students who are aware of the values and principles of Pancasila and have an awareness of initiative in solving various problems related to Pancasila values.

The content developer expects the student to understand that Pancasila is home to everyone. As the basis of a state that promotes universal values, Pancasila replaces freedom from barriers or cultural and national boundaries. Related, Pancasila does not only support the values of Indonesian society but also everyone.

3.2. The Updated version of the Pancasila Module

Pancasila is the foundation of knowledge in state citizenship and covers all aspects. Students will enhance

their collaboration, cooperation, and coordination talents by working in Groups and using all types of communication means to collaborate, aiming for the same ethical purpose. For example, in the discussion, each student will present several problems in each of their original regions, and then they collaborate to formulate a solution for those problems through brainstorming and group creativity techniques.

Students will capitalize on all offline and online digitalized communication tools to transmit and Present ideas about the implementation of Pancasila values in the life of the nation. Students are expected to bridge the communication of the central government, regional governments and the public to meet a consensus based on the values of Pancasila. In addition, students have an important role in reflecting on the effective application of Pancasila in social life practices, expressing Pancasila-societal and social awareness and accountability.

Students will learn to identify the problem of the nation-state of the various aspects of life-based on Pancasila and will dare to give criticism and be a fair judge of all existing problems, both to the government and to the community in a professional manner, will search for the powerful tools to combat those challenges and to transform actions towards a sustainable world. This course encourages students to have critical thinking and problem-solving on national problems. This will give students an appreciation of how democracy should work and how the government governs this country.

With this course, students will be equipped to think creatively and innovatively. They will learn to think and act innovatively by serving the external environment and leading social and societal prosperity. For example, this course requires students to design new solutions to a problem that are in accordance with the values of Pancasila while still considering the condition of the community so that no party is harmed.

Pancasila will also equip students with cross-cultural understanding. Since Indonesia is multicultural, all Indonesians must respect others and live together in harmony. Students will learn to analyze the issues of tolerance and diversity and the problems of democratic leadership and social justice, aiming to eliminate the human and social complexities among citizens.

Students will learn how to spread and represent the values of Pancasila in actions concerned with the external community. Connectivity can be achieved between fellow students and students and lecturers. And having online meetings and discussions with different background counterparts from different countries to express and spread those values worldwide through students' global forum; through these differences, the students will work on developing the current theme for a more sequential national environmental identity.

Pancasila course, in its current form, inspires students to analyze the ethical issues related to the development of science and technology. I can be wise and firm in dealing with all phenomena in the nation and state by reflecting on the external environment and aiming to support environmental justice and socio/cultural empowerment. Students are also expected to apply the values of Pancasila in life so that they are ethical in society, highly tolerant, leaders in spirit, democratic, and fair in determining a decision. This can be achieved by collecting relevant information, utilizing the reading materials and making a case of the issue concerned, and transforming the knowledge into deliverable to the external community. Explain Pancasila as the basic state ideology and system of philosophy and ethics., to all relevant parties who could be isolated from the current theme to expand the circle towards this philosophical context.

Planting the values of Pancasila is crucial and involves all elements of society. This requires attention that is no less important than other aspects of life so that the Indonesian nation is ready to face the disruptive era by sticking to the principles of Pancasila. Students will feel self-motivated to represent these notions as change makers in the environment.

In this course, we introduce the value of justice: Environmental justice. By understanding the importance of Pancasila as an Indonesian ideology, students will be co-responsible towards their external environment to maintain their philosophy regarding social and environmental calls. Social justice: Students are expected to understand the principles of the third point of Pancasila, which states: A unified Indonesia., whereby students will tackle the social and societal challenges as their main concern to combat all kinds of oppression and inequalities. Economic justice: Students are expected to understand the principles of fair play and the fair-trade system by constructing real national and international cases, reflecting on sustainable praxis, and developing economic awareness and richness. Cultural justice: Students should be able to understand that Indonesia is a very diverse country. Students are expected to understand the first point of Pancasila, which states: Belief in the Almighty God. Thus, they can respect other people with different beliefs and do good in society without looking at who they are, where they come from, etc., and learn how to accommodate others to develop the country towards lifelong welfare for the upcoming generations. In addition, this will also inspire the students to learn to identify the problem of the nation-state of the various aspects of life-based on Pancasila, and the unethical and injustice practices and work on initiatives that lead the coexistence with the natural sustainable world.

3.3. Similarity to another subject or courses

Regarding the key diagnostic question in this part, Have you ever attended a course on this topic or skill area? the majority of the students of this course (64%) stated that

they had attended a similar course. In comparison, 36% said otherwise (Fig. 1). The course that has similar content to this course is Civic Education (Pendidikan Kewarganegaraan/PKWN). PKWN is mandatory for all students since they are in middle school. Although both courses are covering the same topics, Pancasila discusses the topics in different depth compared to PKWN for high school students.

The answer to the next questions about “Have you ever created a project or written work similar to this course?” and “have you ever worked in a work dealing with issues similar to the topic of this course?” shows the students who took Pancasila class 84% never had created project or written work similar to the course and 88% said that they never work dealing with the similar topics that are given in Pancasila courses (Fig. 1). These answers are supporting proof that there is a PKWN course in high school.

Fig. 1. Percentage of students exposed to course/work/issues that are similar to the Pancasila

3.4. Student Expectation

The aggregated results reflect the students' answers to the question, "What do they expect from this course." About 60% of students focus on the basic concept of Pancasila, while 40% presume that the course will increase their understanding of how to implement Pancasila on a day-to-day basis (Fig. 2).

Here are some of the notable answers to this question:
 “To learn more about my responsibilities towards my country.”
 ” We can apply the values of Pancasila in everyday life to learn more about our country in general.”
 “Not only know about the material but also understand and practice, do the value of Pancasila in my daily activity.”

Fig. 2. Students' expectation for Pancasila course

3.5. Student Reflection on the course

The reflection questions that are being asked to the students on what happened during the half period of your course, either for positive and negative incidents, the answers showed that the students gain new knowledge (14.3%), have more insight about Pancasila (43%), have capability to analyses the problem (14,3%) and they said this course is easy to understand (30%). Meanwhile for the negative incident, 10% of the students reported negative incidents in this course such as there were too many assignments and language barrier for our international program students. Meanwhile the majority of the students (90%) reported to have no negative experience.

In the reflection on what students expect and whether the course meets or fails their expectation (What did you expect and what was different?). Forty percent of the students said that they have no expectations and 30% of them expect that the course will be the same as their high school's one, while the rest (10%) expect more on the knowledge and application sides of the topics. They think this course is already good on current condition and they have a positive outlook on how the course turns out and don't have any further suggestion for the improvement.

3.6. The Expectation of Reconstructing Pancasila

Some of the students (30%) thought that this course will be the same with PKWN which mostly made them memorize the tennet, decrees, and dates on history. However, when they realize that the learning process in high school and our university is vastly different. In university level, the professor already has an understanding that the students should be the one to experience the learning process in order for them to gain skills and knowledge. Thus, the learning process is students centred learning and facilitated with various methods to deliver the topics.

Even Though the student has nothing to suggest during the first half of the course, by the end of the course they have

something in mind to make it better such as adding more discussion time (12%), less assignment (24%), and add social project (3%), however most of the students (61%) said that nothing should be change in the course.

Forty one percent of students come into realization that they need to be a better citizen for Indonesia after they were taking Pancasila courses. This is in opposition to 27% that said they have no idea yet on how to apply their gained knowledge for their future. In addition, 19% of students are aware of the importance of implementing Pancasila values in their daily lives and 13% of students now realize the importance of study by context that helps them greatly to increase their understanding.

Fig. 3. New Pancasila Course impact to Students

Upon completed the Pancasila course, the students admit to increase understanding on current national issues (39%). There is an improvement on their fundamental knowledge of Pancasila. Moreover, they gain more appreciation and increase of their nationalism (17%) (Fig. 3).

4. Conclusion

DeCoRe method was used to improve this course delivery. In the new concept of Pancasila course, the emphasis of ESD and SDGs as part of Global idea is highlighted, as well as updated the case of studies into recent national issues. With the new concept, students' engagements were higher during the course and they are confident that they can have positive impact to society. However, it is of particular importance to take into consideration various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues pertaining to the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al. 2024).

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Basic Social Science Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing It through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

This world faces complex and intersectoral challenges that lead to various societal problems. Social Science is the foundation for a holistic perspective in identifying specific social issues. Since education plays a critical as well as strategic role in generating and disseminating the ideas and principles of sustainability, it is important to integrate the course curriculum, especially in universities. As the agent of change, students are expected to have a critical mindset in appraising their surrounding social problems. This article provides a deeper and more holistic explanation of deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing the Basic Social Course through the lens of SDGs supported by ICTs and driven by six learning pillars (6p) and ten competencies (10c). This article developed the DeCoRe Methodology approach that aims to embed the values of sustainability based on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The research process was conducted through an assessment using a systematic questionnaire based on the DREAM Methodology to get information before and after embedding the values of sustainability in the course. It can be found that there was an improvement in the course in the scope of education, professional, social, and personality of students. Besides that, many challenges were posed during the learning activities.

Keywords: Basic Social Science, Social, Sustainability, DeCoRe plus Methodology, SDGs

1. Introduction

The Basic Social Science (BSS) course is designed for students in the first semester, specifically in the faculty of social and politics. This course aims to introduce the foundation of sociological thinking. Through this course, students are expected to have a broader perspective on various social phenomena. In this course, students learn about the basic knowledge of sociology and its role in society and identify the link between that knowledge and social issues. The general aim of this course is to make the students understand the basic principle of thinking sociologically, while the practical objective of this course is to increase the awareness of students related to various social issues, so by attending the learning processes, they can create an appropriate solution to address social problems. The main objectives of this course are:

Define the object of study in sociological aspects.

Identify the existence and role of social structure through practical experiences.

Explain social phenomena based on the principles of sociological imagination.

Practicing critical thinking to address social problems

By attending the Basic Social Science course, students are expected to get a deeper understanding of the core knowledge of sociological concepts and principles to identify specific social phenomena based on their students.

Experiences. There is new knowledge that was tried to be achieved through this course, including direct social experiments, utilizing digital technologies to bring social phenomena, encouraging students to express their passion for ICTs through group work, and followed by the ability to

think out of the box in addressing a social problem. As previous research demonstrated, the use of ICT and the use of new didactic methodologies, such as Project-based

learning and inquiring-based learning, could be more effective in fostering students' critical thinking (Biasutti & El-Deghaidy, 2015; Biasutti, 2011)

The course content is in line with the objectives of the study, especially:

Understanding sociology as a distinct social science

Applying the concept of sociological imagination as well as social consciousness

Writing a well-structured paper that brings a logical argument as well as comprehensive contents

Presenting ideas clearly and persuasively driven by critical thoughts.

The Basic Social Science (BSS) course is conducted through 13 meeting sessions, where the learning activities were supported by using ICTs during the learning activities (including visual learning videos, internet supports, and LCD). This course implements problem-based learning where students. Learning methods used in this course include group discussion, social experiments, and individual assignments. Field problems were carried out in the course to help students identify real problems and find appropriate solutions.

Society is facing multisector problems that affect daily life. Through this course, students are supposed to bring these social problems into the course to be identified and then formulate those problems related to the basic theory of sociology. Those social problems encourage students to implement their knowledge by developing strategies to solve the problems for communities or society. The students are expected to understand their critical role as agents of change, specifically in solving social problems, including social gaps, sustainable cities, and communities, as well as realizing peace, justice, and strong institutions in society.

Based on the description above, the content of Basic Social Science is in line with the idea in SDG 10, which says to reduce inequalities within and among countries, SDG 11 in terms of achieving sustainable cities and communities, and

SDG 16 in realizing peace and justice, and strong institutions. Since this course carries out the idea of sustainability inside its content, it is important to adjust the curriculum based on the ideas and principles of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It has recently been recognized that embedding sustainability values is not as easy as adding new materials to the course content. It requires a holistic shift in terms of the curriculum practice. Embedding the idea of sustainability not only changes the content but must also follow an appropriate teaching and learning approach in this course (Biasutti et al., 2018). Teachers are expected to link the values of sustainability and ensure that each course material addresses sustainability principles. That is why it requires a holistic and interdisciplinary discussion that focuses on dealing with the complexity of social problems our society faces.

Since the Basic Social Science course contains the concept of education for sustainability, it is important to adjust and develop this course based on the concept of the DeCoRe Plus Process, which is the abbreviation of Deconstruction, Construction, and Reconstruction. This process can help in-service teachers realize that the course aligns with sustainability justice's values (Makrakis, 2017). The course is developed by integrating the curriculum with SDG values and the Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) concept. This course was chosen due to the content that gives a holistic view of real social problems in society, so it will be a strategic way to achieve sustainability values through this course. Moreover, this course is also in line with some values of SDGs, especially SDGs 10, SDGs 11, and SDGs 16, which aim to reduce inequalities, create sustainable cities and communities, and achieve peace, justice, and strong institutions across nations. That is why it is important to integrate the ideas and principles of SDGs into this course.

The DeCoRe Concept helps to adjust and identify the dimensions of sustainability justice from this Basic Social Science course, which are the social justice, environmental justice, economic justice, and cultural justice that have already been implemented during the course but have never been written in the Basic Social Science lesson plan. The course learning activities were related to real life and dimensions of sustainability justice.

From environmental justice, the students will learn to construct lively and questioning environmental challenges through the experiences of academic professionals carrying out research for and with local, national, and international sustainable communities. From the site of social justice, students will be able to learn how to construct the sociological theories and methods that can be used to affect social policies, communities, and lives, whereby students are expected to express their personal experiences towards public external issues. From economic justice, students will learn how to enhance the economic abilities of citizens to create opportunities for everyone to create an adequate material foundation for a dignified, productive, and creative

life. The students are expected to have a critical mindset for balancing economic development and society's capacity in general, especially those who live in periphery areas.

Meanwhile, from cultural justice, students are expected to understand how to capitalize on unrivaled opportunities to network with key public decision-makers, develop public engagement skills, and work at a grassroots level in partnership with various communities towards sustainability cultural orientation. In addition, sustainability should be maintained based on the values of justice. This sustainable justice can be achieved by internalizing the ideas and principles of sustainability into the course.

Methodologies: The How Question Analysis Model Overview

The course revision applied the DeCoRe Plus Methodology advanced by Makrakis (2017), which aims to embed the idea of sustainability, specifically the Sustainable Development Goals values, into the curricula. DeCoRe Plus, an abbreviation of Deconstruction, Construction, and Reconstruction, is an approach that was used to adjust the course by embedding certain values to develop the curriculum according to the values that were added.

Figure 1 : The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017)

Six processes can be found in DeCoRe Plus Methods. Experiences using a systematic questionnaire. This assessment was constructed based on the DREAM Methodology developed by Makrakis (2023). This DREAM Methodology process covers the course as a whole using five stages.

Diagnosing aims to obtain information related to who we are, what we have (existing knowledge), where we want to go, and why we want to go there.

Deconstructing provides a critical explanation, including the functioning of personal perspectives, habits of mind, and units of the chosen curriculum.

Constructing is a process for gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new perspectives.

Reconstructing and integrating newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.

Implementing and carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module through the related course.

Summative Evaluation, evaluating and reflecting on what has been learned and changed from the course.

Based on the previous explanation, it is important to construct a curriculum that is in line with the values of sustainability; this article carried out the reconstruction of the Basic Social Science course. Through this research, students were assessed based on their direct

Figure 2 : DREAM Methodology Model (Makrakis, 2023)

The diagnosis process focuses on identifying the profile of every student, such as personal identity, personal experiences both in knowledge and working experience, as well as the student's expectations by attending the course. From this stage, it can be known whether the students have ever created a project or worked with specific issues that align with the course's topics. This previous information leads to the student's expectations of the BSS course.

The second process is a review, which aims to know the challenges during the half period of the course, as well as the difference between expectations and the result. Through this process, the students are expected to have a broader perspective on dealing with gaps between previous expectations and actual learning activities. The end of this process is intended to explain the appropriate alternatives for students to improve the quality of the BSS course.

The explanation process is conducted to get a clear description of how the course was not in the way the students expected and to think critically about why it can be so. This process helped to identify the possible causes that create the gap between expectation and the learning process inside the BSS course. The result of this assessment was able to give a deeper understanding of many constraints that are still encountered during the learning process of the Basic Social Science course.

The fourth process is assessment, which aims to understand the impact of the course in multiple aspects, such as the impact on students' knowledge, professional development, sustainability of the social community, and personality. The students were expected to critically reflect on how the course results affected their self-capacity improvement. Through this assessment, it was able to be the parameter of how this learning process and methods of the BSS course improve the students' capacity.

The last process was managed. This assessment was conducted to provide a comprehensive overview of constraints, expectations, and a strategic evaluation of the learning outcomes in the BSS course. The results of the assessment are expected to provide a clear description of how to advance the Basic Social Science course in the future.

Assessment and Data Analysing Methods

This is descriptive qualitative research with primary data sources obtained directly from students of the Basic Social Science course as respondents conducting the survey. The survey was done by providing an online survey form that was supposed to be filled out by students of the BSS course. The form was constructed based on DREAM Methodology Models consisting of five stages: Diagnose, Review, Explain, Assess, and Manage. The answers will be reduced, displayed, and followed by the conclusion. The data analysis was based on the DeCoRe Plus Methodology advanced by Makrakis (2017).

Pre-Course Assessment Result

This part provides the students' previous experiences and knowledge. Through the assessment, 29% of students have ever attended a course similar to Basic Social Science (BSS). 21% of students have also done a project related to the course topics. Furthermore, the result of working experience shows only 14% of students had working experience before joining the course.

Figure 3: Percentage of previous knowledge and experience

Those results show a small percentage related to the student's experiences before joining the course. Even though the topic of society can be considered common knowledge, the percentage of students who attend similar course experiences is small. This can happen because, in previous degrees, students learned social topics theoretically without using problem-based learning methods. So, the content of the BSS course is still considered a new topic for most students. In addition, social topics have not been integrated with the real social issues in our society. The skills that can support the learning process were also limited based on the result of previous work and project experience. That is why it is important to integrate the basics of social knowledge with real social issues through this BSS course.

The data of various student expectations follow this result by attending the course.

4.1 What, Why, and Where Question for Revising (Hydrometeorology Course: Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing it through the Lens of SDGs)

Basic Social Science (BSS) courses are considered mandatory courses for students in the first semester. So, this course aims to give a basic understanding of social theory integrated with social issues. The competencies provided in this course include the central concept of social science, implementing the concept through problem-based learning supported by ICTs, and appraising the potentials and limitations of social science. This learning process is done so that the students can explore the core social science concepts that enable them to analyze social phenomena in our society. To lead students to a deeper understanding of analyzing social phenomena, some assessments are given in this course, including essay writing assignments, quizzes related to the learning topic, presentations, video assignments, participation in the class, and the result of mid-term and final exams. 80 students attend this course in a year.

Basic Social Science (BSS) was chosen as the revised course due to the content being related to common social topics so that a wider perspective can be obtained through this course. In addition, since this course focuses on implementing social science to solve social problems, it is in

line with the idea of SDG 10 and SDG 11 as well as SDG number 16 in terms of reduce inequalities,

Self Improvement
(9%)

Practical Knowledge achieve sustainable cities and communities, as well as create peace, justice, and strong institution. The main focus of this course is to create a wider perspective and deeper understanding of related to solve the social problems by identify the existence and role of social structure, explain certain social phenomena, as well as practicing a critical thinking on social phenomena. The BSS course before revision has been conducted theoretically through material explanation, presentation, as well as a group discussion to supported by ICTs facilities. Furthermore, the learning process focuses on how to solve social problems. Before the revision was conducted, this course supported the six learning pillars for sustainable development, including learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together sustainably, learning to do, (29%), New Knowledge (43%)

learning to transform oneself and society and learning to give and share. Prior to the revision, this BSS course

Figure 4 : Student's expectation Diagram

The result shows the percentage of student's expectations related to the BSS course, including new knowledge, impactful knowledge, practical knowledge, as well as the impact of self-improvement. From the result above, it can be known that besides the new knowledge that the students expect to get through the course, they also expect that the knowledge can be used to solve various social problems and impact society.

Discussion

supported students to construct the legitimacy of knowledge and understanding social phenomena through the lens of Basic Social Science (learning to know). Students were able to learn related to how to be an independent catalyst in the community, so students can apply specialized and advanced conceptual as well as methodological techniques to evaluate the existing knowledge (learning to be). Students are able to implement a critical social science approaches to live in a social diversity as well as multicultural society that aims to achieve the a sustainable and peaceful global orientation (learning to live together sustainably). By doing the previous pillars, students are expected to show a significant

initiative, independence, and personal sociological context commitment that focuses on public issues (learning to do). Related to the society, students are expected to

appraise the limitations and potentials of the social science and its theoretical proposition for analyzing social phenomena , enhancing a life- long learning skills, and personal development of reflective learning approaches. The last pillar related to learning to give and share, students are expected to do a participatory observation of social phenomena concerning issues of deprivation and exclusion related to economy, identity, culture, and race.

Based on the explanation above, it was known that 6 learning pillars of for sustainable development have been applied as the basic values in Basic Social Science course. But the implementation of those pillars has not been clearly supported by explicit introduction of SDGs. This course is a strategic tool for infusing the ideas and values of SDGs specifically in term of social aspects. However, the value of SDGs has not been introduced explicitly towards the students while the focus of this course is about social aspect and phenomena, which is represented by SDG 10, 11, as well as SDG 16. Unfortunately, this Basic Social Science course was able to implement 9 Cs from 10 Cs that is expected to be implemented through the course including critical thinking, communication, collaboration, creativity, connectivity, critical consciousness, critical reflection, cross-cultural competences, and constructing knowledge.

This course needs to be developed that is concerning in three aspects including what is the gaps that should be filled in the course, the SDGs theme to be infused, as well as the new competences to be developed. Related to the revision, there was a gap as well as the missing link between the content of social aspects with the main purpose that it is going to be achieved. There's not clearly stated what is the goals of each materials especially in order to achieve the values of sustainability. It shows that it is important to infuse the values of sustainability in terms of SDGs values and principles. The first revision has to be focused on infusing the ideas and values of SDGs explicitly towards the course curriculum. There are ten competencies that is important to be integrated through the learning process in BSS course, those competencies can be a great strategic way in terms of reflecting, conceptualizing, constructing and assessing knowledge. The content of BSS course has to be developed by integrating with the SDGs values and giving more concern towards real social problems as well as the sustainability justice aspects including social, environmental, economic, as well as cultural justice. According to the previous reflection, this course should pay more attention to in integrating the course with the appropriate values in SDGs. Those goals including SDGs number 10, 11 as well as 16 which focuses on reduce inequalities, achieve sustainable cities and communities, as well as create peace, justice, and strong institution. This integration will be supported by problem- based learning and ICTs.

Advanced course specifically the integration of learning process with SDGs values plays a critical role to achieve the ideas of sustainability. Through this integration, students are expected to understand critically the complexity of social aspects, so it needs a clear goal to be achieved. That is why it is important to increase the awareness of social problems followed by a deeper understanding to manage solve those problems in appropriate ways. Furthermore, this course should be supported by ICTs as a modern education tool that aims to increase the student's awareness of sustainability. The competencies should be added including co-responsibility that has not been included in this course prior

to the revision. Co-responsibility can be defined as a culture of sharing and shifting to less ego-centric practices and principles (Makrakis, 2017). These competencies help student to be able to develop a character that supports the goals especially of social aspect in SDGs.

4.2 The How Question

This article uses a DeCoRe Plus Model advanced by Makrakis (2017) to help in identifying the previous course as well as constructing the new perspective for advanced course. Based on the needs to develop a curriculum that is in line with the ideas of sustainability, the reconstruction of BSS course was carried out. This research conducted an assessment where students are expected to fill a systematic questionnaire. By doing a survey, this research is considered as a descriptive qualitative research with students of BSS course as the main data resources. The assessment was constructed based on the DREAM Methodology Model including Diagnose, Review, Explain, Assess, and Manage process.

Through this assessment using DREAM Methodology, it can be known related to the experiences of students during the BSS course. From the review process, we can get information about students' experiences after students have completed a half of total lectures in BSS course. This stage aims to identify both positive and negative experiences that experienced by students. Through the result of assessment, we were able to figure out the learning process both in positive and negative side. The positive side was dominated by the experience of understanding a new knowledge of social aspects in general as well as a new skills that the students get through the course. Those skills were able to be built through the learning process such as problem-based discussion and assignment that encourage students to be more critical, collaborative, communicative, being critical conscious, as well as being aware with cross-cultural issues and social issues in general. Those are skills that able to be improved during the learning process, this learning processes are able to help student in understanding their surrounding social issues. Meanwhile, the negative experience was dominated by the lack of technical or ICTs supports during the course. Students have to struggle more during the learning process since the pandemic situation limited the chance to meet directly with another friend. This condition affected how students conduct a group discussion, so they have to be adaptive by familiarize ICTs support to the communication during the course.

The Now What Question

Based on the result of assessment, it can be known that there is an improvement in this BSS course including the materials, learning methods, as well as course learning outcomes. The revision of this course was able to give impacts towards academic development, professional development, surrounding society, as well as the student's personality. Based on the assessment responses, there is improvement related to the academic aspect of BSS students. It can be known that through this learning process, students are able to get a new knowledge and understanding those materials. This is in line with the previous description that BSS course is considered as a basic course that's why it is given in the first semester for student. So, it is important to assure that students have a good and deeper understanding of what has been taught in this course. So, this revised course can help students to get a deeper understanding by integrating the values of sustainability

inside the content. The infusion of values of sustainability help students to identify what is the purpose as well as impacts from each materials in this BSS course. This improvement was followed by the implementation of ten competencies (10 Cs) towards the daily learning process. From this course, the students are able to identify certain social problems even from the perspective of environment, social, economic, and cultural.

Beside the improvement in academic aspect, this advanced course is able to stimulate the students to think critically related to the external issues that was brought into the class. This skill of critical thinking is able to lead students to get a logical and wider perspective in identifying problems in social aspects. Recent cases that are given towards students as a topics of group discussion was able to encourage students to collaborate one another. In addition, this learning activity can encourage students to literate based on data and think critically to build an argument. Furthermore, this learning circumstances was able to push students to look for a valid and credible data and resources supported by ICTs. This group discussion trained the students to have certain skills including skill in communication, collaboration, creativity, create networks and connectivity, critical consciousness, as well as critical reflection. Those competencies are important to construct a knowledge. Beside constructing knowledge, there is a need to disseminate the knowledge towards society that aims to distribute a broader knowledge and information. This process needs specific skills including inter-cultural Each of competencies was integrated with the ideas and principles of sustainability to generate a comprehensive knowledge that is impactful towards society in general.

In the professional development aspect, it can be known that there is also an improvement which achieved by students. Based on the result of assessment using DREAM Methodology, it can be known that BSD course encourages certain professional characteristic and skills that can support students in professional field. Those skills including case analysis skills, working management,

systematic discussion, problem solving, collaboration skills, as well as the capability for priority settings. This skills is supported by the appropriate learning methods for instance a group discussion and problem-based learning. This result shows that there is a differences from the previous course and the revised course in the aspect of professional skills.

From the side of social development, it can be known that this course is able to give impact including communication skills towards society, improvement of social problem awareness, as well as the integration of sustainability values in solving social problems. Since there were various social problems, those skills above are important to be used for practical purpose such as formulate a solution for certain social problems. Moreover, students become more aware and understand how to appraise a social issue in society. This course was able to transform the content of BSS course by infusing explicitly the importance of sustainability values in the scope of social life.

Another aspect is personal development. Through this course, student was able to improve their personal quality that is supported by an appropriate learning processes, this improvement including improvement of personal awareness toward social issues, adaptability, responsibility, curiosity, innovative mindset, as well as empathy to social issues in general. Furthermore, the course that was conducted online

gave a certain challenge for students specifically in keeping up with the materials taught by the teacher. Based on that condition, some inputs appeared to pay more attention to the learning media and teaching methods to achieve an effective learning process, especially in this pandemic era.

Furthermore, from the assessment result, in the management process that used the concept of DREAM Methodology, it can be known that there must be a strategic integration through the course materials. This learning system encourages students to be more innovative both theoretically and practically (supported by broader references and collective discussion); students were expected to improve their literacy towards ICT tools and supports, as well as increase awareness towards specific social issues related to the Basic Social Science (BSS) course. The last question in the management process is what kind of change should be applied to the course. The result shows that this course is considered as an important course that is considered as an important course since it gives the foundation for social knowledge in the first semester; a good understanding of this course will help students to understand another course ahead. The problem-based learning in this course by carrying out a real social problem into the class will increase student's awareness and understanding about the topic of this course. The learning process is able to optimize student's awareness to achieve the values in Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Through the revision, the implementation of SDGs into the course can help students to understand since in the revised curriculum, the sustainability values has been clearly stated. There were differences including in how the student can understand the critical role of basic social science in order to achieve equality and justice for society. It can be said that the integration of SDGs values plays a critical role in improving students understanding towards the course materials, it can be understood because the goals of learning are clearly stated inside the learning plans, moreover the implementation of 6 learning pillars and 10 competencies help student to applied knowledge in practical ways and improve their professional skills to solve problems in social sector.

The 'So What' Question

The whole process of revising the course of deconstruction, construction, and reconstruction of Basic Social Science through the lens of SDGs is considered as a strategic breakthrough to improve the quality of education. As this integration is new, we found challenges during the process. Those challenges appear since holistic integration by embedding specific values must be followed by appropriate adaptation and support throughout the process. This commitment to developing the course should be followed by changes in content, various new assessments, learning strategies, and the use of ICT tools to support the learning activities. We might have found out various constraints through the process. The gap between students' expectations and what they got from the course became a particular difficulty.

Undergraduate students in the Basic Social Science courses enter the transition phase between high school and university students. There must be differences in responsibility and learning environment, so most of the time, it will be used to adapt to new circumstances. This condition requires an ideal learning method to encourage students to participate actively in learning activities. An appropriate learning method will be able to help students

understand the basic knowledge of social science as well as its relation to ideas of sustainability. By carrying out a real case in society, it can help students to construct the problems that appear in the social aspect. Considering that the course focuses on environmental issues, contextual cases, and issues should follow the learning materials. In this course, students were divided into many group of discussion. That is why it takes more time for discussion than theoretical learning.

Embedding Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and values into the course curriculum gave a broader perspective and understanding. That condition was also supported by carrying out real social problems to be identified inside the course. This activity can help students think critically in individual or collective discussions. The infusion of SDG values explicitly into the learning content combined with the example of social issues surprisingly created a new point of view from the students. This was proved by the results of the assessment, which showed that students' awareness was improved. This answers that sustainable values from SDGs need to be supported by real social problems to encourage students to realize a deeper understanding through learning activities.

Based on the process of deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing through the lens of SDGs in the Basic Social Science (BSS) course, the students should have a holistic understanding related to the course materials that are complemented by real-world issues in the social aspect. The value of SDGs should play a critical role as a catalyst for students to understand the concept of sustainability. It is clearly stated that the values as well as principles of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are designed to mobilize countries around the world to end all forms of inequalities, tackle climate change, as well as ensure that there is no one left behind (Pallant, E., Choate, B., & Haywood, B., 2020). The sentence above shows that reducing inequalities is a goal that should be integrated with the course curriculum since education holds a critical role to infusing the idea of sustainability. Besides elaborating on the values of SDGs and real-world issues, it was important to apply appropriate learning methods to the course. It can be done by conducting problem-based learning as well as a discussion in the group to make the students think critically as a first competency of 10 and able to implement the other 9 competencies through learning activities.

Through this revised curriculum, the learning and teaching process of the BSS course is supposed to have a real impact on both local and global society. Having a sustainable-based mindset is important to define what the student should do, including the educational, social, professional, and personality aspects that can directly affect surrounding society. The ideas of sustainability that become the basic foundation of thinking are expected to make the students able to distribute knowledge or information correctly to society.

From all the revision processes that have been done, it can be known that it will not be easy for knowledge to be improved without carrying real cases of examples as well as the values that can be the appropriate frameworks to guide the learning process. This leads us to another understanding that the values of SDGs must be seen as a framework for the student to learn inside the course that is still in line with the challenges outside as well as social, economic, environmental, and cultural problems that exist. That is how we see this integration as an urgency to be implemented for

the course, specifically in the university as one of the leading educational institutions (Biasutti et al., 2018). This means that the university holds an important role in generating and disseminating the idea of sustainability. So, implementing the SDGs' values needs to be done by improving the Basic Social Science course to align with sustainability ideas and principles and realize Education for Sustainable Development (ESD).

Conclusion

Education is critical as the change agent to generate the ideal implementation of sustainable values. While this world is recently facing various problems in cross-sectoral sectors, including social, environmental, economic, as well as cultural issues, sustainable development goals (SDGs) need to be integrated into the course curriculum in universities. The course materials should align with the ideas and concepts of sustainability. In the scope of social science, it can be seen that there was a missing link between the content of social science and the values of sustainability. By understanding that social science is considered as the knowledge that focuses on social problems, it is important to develop the course to be in line with the values of SDGs number 10, 11, and 12, that is related to the idea of reducing inequalities, develop sustainable cities and citizens, as well as achieve peace, justice, as well as strong institutions.

Implementing the DeCoRe Plus for embedding social sustainability through the course curricula supported by ICTs and driven by six pillars of learning as well as 10 Competencies (10 Cs) is a strategic alternative to improve education in university. Assessment using the DREAM Methodology (Makrakis, 2023) has been conducted for the student to know their perspective before and after the revision. Based on the result, it can be known that at the beginning of the course, there was a gap between expectations and results that the students got along the course. In addition, the values of SDGs have not been stated clearly, so the students were not learning based on the concept of sustainability. However, it is of particular importance to take into consideration various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues about the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

Through the revision, it can be known that there is an improvement in the form of a wider perspective and deeper understanding of sustainability related to various social issues. This improvement including aspects of educational, professional, social, as well as personality. The DeCoRe Plus led students into a practical transformation as it generated the real learning skills and competencies towards the students. The embedding of sustainable values into the course needs to be supported by ICTs during the learning activities. Technology is a crucial part of what is happening in the classroom (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2012). Technology support through learning processes (internet, visual learning videos, LCD) helps students face difficulties and understand knowledge from the course.

Besides the improvement that can be achieved, we faced some challenges through the assessment and the learning process. Those challenges included students' understanding since this course was a new topic and was given in the transition period in the first semester. The pandemic era gives another challenge in terms of technology support and its efficiency during online learning. This condition leads to

difficulties for students to keep up with the materials, personal assignments, as well as group discussion for certain issues.

Through all the revision processes, it can be known how hard knowledge is to stand without real examples and values that can be the frameworks to guide the learning process. It shows the importance of implementing the SDG ideas and principles to improve the Basic Social Science (BSS) course in line with the concept of sustainability.

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Introduction to Game Theory Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing It through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

Game theory generally refers to the study of mathematical models that describe the behavior of logical decision-makers. The Introduction of Game Theory (IGT) is an elective course introducing game theory to undergraduate students. The general aims of IGT are that students can solve problems by figuring strategies out for the players with an objective function. IGT was chosen for the revision as this course relates to the concept of education for sustainability. The methods used in the course reconstruction were DeCoRe+ and DREAM methodology. The reconstructed course implemented the four dimensions of sustainability justice, the six pillars of learning, and the 10Cs. It was noticed that the course had not implemented student-centred and problem-based learning. The reconstruction helped in giving a clear structure and overview of the Introduction to Game Theory course through the lens of sustainable development goals (SDGs) and incorporating the utilization of ICTs to achieve sustainability justice and the six pillars for learning by the students

Keywords: Game Theory, ESD Course, SDGs, DeCoRe+, Dream methodology

1. Introduction

One of the most important roles of education is to infuse sustainable principles into the learning course to make students good citizens. (Biasutti et al 2018; Biasutti and Frate 2017). Game theory generally refers to the study of mathematical models that describe the behavior of logical decision-makers. It is widely used in many fields, such as economics, political science, politics, and computer science, and can model many real-world scenarios. Generally, a game refers to a situation involving a set of players who each have a set of possible choices, in which the outcome for any individual player depends partially on the choices made by other players. The course about game theory in Universitas Gadjah Mada (UGM) starts with an Introduction to Game Theory (IGT) course. It is an elective course for the second year of undergraduate students in the odd semester.

The key materials of IGT include motivating examples of games, non-cooperative games, strategic form or standard form of a game, two-player zero-sum game, maximin criteria, pure strategies, domination, Nash equilibrium, extensive form of a game, two-player non-zero-sum game, mix strategies, N-player game, cooperative game, Pareto optimal solution, transferable utility (TU) and non-transferable utility (NTU) game, game with coalitional form, imputation, core, Shapley value, and nucleolus. The total workload of IGT is 136 hours per semester, which consists of 150 minutes of lectures per week for 14 weeks, 180 minutes of structured activities per week, and 180 minutes of individual study per week, 16 weeks per semester, including mid and final exams.

The core concepts in the IGT course are assessed through learning activities such as:

Resolving non-cooperative game problems two players are given as an assessment through Homework and Quiz.

Solving cooperative game problems and players are given as an assessment through Homework and Quiz.

Linking non-cooperative game theory and simple applications is assessed through presentation and video assignments.

Linking cooperative game theory and simple applications is assessed through presentation and video assignments.

The general aim of IGT is that students can solve problems by figuring strategies out for players with an objective function. Players should consider that the strategies of other players influence the optimal solution for the objective function. In this course, non-cooperative and cooperative games are discussed. Meanwhile, the specific objectives of this course are:

to make students recognize optimization concepts in non-cooperative and cooperative games.

to make students capable of solving two-player game problems such as non-cooperative zero-sum games, non-cooperative non-zero-sum games, and cooperative games.

to make students capable of solving n-player game problems with the allocation method, namely Shapley value theory.

to help students relate between the theory and application of game problems and interpret the solutions in real-life situations.

IGT was chosen for the revision as this course relates to the concept of education for sustainability. After attending the IGT course, students are expected to experience the construct of knowledge through learning the basic principles of mathematical models that describe the behavior of logical decision-makers among different learning platforms heading toward lifelong well-being. From this, there was a need to identify the course's sustainability justice that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture.

Sustainability justice is viewed as a process, not a product, that seeks a just distribution of opportunities, resources, and responsibilities; challenges the causes of oppression and injustice; empowers all people to speak up for their needs and rights; and builds knowledge, empathy, compassion, social

solidarity, and action competences. Sustainability justice is a principle that ought to be incorporated into curriculum, teaching, and learning practices. (Makrakis, 2017).

2. Methodology

2.1 DeCoRe+

The DeCoRe+ is an abbreviation for Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction. DeCore+, a method advanced by Makrakis, was applied to incorporate the Introduction to Game Theory with the four dimensions of sustainability justice,

The DeCoRe+ consists of six steps that follow a linear order comprising (1) Diagnostic Evaluation, (2) Deconstruction, (3) Construction, (4) Reconstruction, (5) Implementation, and (6) Summative Evaluation. The diagnostic evaluation is where the instructors reflect on the existing knowledge and the future direction of the course. Deconstruction is the following process where the course is critically analyzed regarding the functioning of personal perspectives and curriculum units or modules. Subsequently, the construction process is settled by gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning. Reconstruction process is when new constructed knowledge is united and in line with the frame of reference. Implementation occurs when the reconstructed curriculum is based on the module supplements by the service learning. Lastly, evaluating is where reflection and evaluation of what has been learned and changed.

All six processes do not stand alone but interconnect, forming an undivided system, as seen in Figure 1.

Fig 1. The DeCoRe+ Interaction (Makrakis, 2017)

2.2 DREAM Methodology

Reconstruction of the Introduction to Game Theory course is then implemented in the implementation process mentioned before in DeCoRe+ methodology. The reconstructed course is assessed then revised using the DREAM methodology (Makrakis 2019). DREAM stands for Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage.

The process starts by diagnosing previous knowledge on the course. This process is done by distributing surveys for students who join the Introduction to Game Theory course. It asks whether the students have ever attended a similar course or not. The next step is to Review or Reflect then Explain. This process takes place when the students have completed half of the entire course for the Introduction to Game Theory. The last is to Assess and Manage. This takes place when all the students have finished their courses.

After going through all these processes, the instructors will gain information and input from the students' portfolios. The obtained information can be used to make changes and

enhance the Introduction to Game Theory course by reflecting and evaluating what has been learned and changed.

Fig 2. The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Deconstructing Introduction to Game Theory Course

It was chosen as one of the courses in Universitas Gadjah Mada to undergo the deconstruct, construct, and reconstruct process. Introduction to Game Theory was chosen for the revision as this course relates to the concept of education for sustainability.

The key content themes of Introduction to Game Theory are Non-cooperative game, Nash equilibrium Pareto optimal solution, TU and NTU game, Maximin criterion pure strategies, domination, mix strategies, Game with coalitional form, imputation, core, Shapley value, and nucleolus. After attending the Introduction to Game Theory course, students are expected to experience the construct of knowledge through learning the basic principles of mathematical models that describe the behavior of logical decision-makers among different learning platforms heading toward lifelong well-being. From this, there was a need to identify the course's sustainability justice that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture.

Teaching methods employed are normal lectures that last 150 minutes and structured activities that last 180 minutes every week. The assessments of the undergraduate students are based on the percentage of earned points. The final grades are determined based on the midterms and final exams. Undergraduate students from the Introduction of Game Theory are assessed through homework and presentation.

The content of the Introduction of Game Theory course prior to revision was yet to be classified and connected into the four dimensions of sustainability justice, six learning pillars, and 10Cs to enable ICTs. The deconstruction process of this course helped in identifying the content that suits the sustainability justice, the six learning pillars, and the 10Cs to enable ICTs. Furthermore, through deconstruction, the SDGs that are implicitly implied in the course of Introduction to Game Theory are able to be identified.

The Introduction of Game Theory studies about mathematical models that describe the behavior of logical decision-makers. Mathematical models can be used in many real-world scenarios. Research by Dolinsky (2015) has been conducted using game theory in making sustainable systems in order to preserve energy

resources. This indicates that game theory can play a crucial role in improving sustainability justice (Environmental, Social, Economical and Culture) in the future. Connecting to the SDGs, this act can be seen to fulfill SDG 12 about Responsible consumption and production which says ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns (United Nations, 2022)

Furthermore, the six pillars of learning (Learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together sustainably, learning to do, and learning to transform oneself and society) were all identified in the Introduction of Game Theory course as well as the 10Cs that enable ICTs. A second revision of the Introduction of Game theory to produce a structured module that explicitly implies the four dimensions of sustainability justice, six pillars of learning, and the 10Cs. Additionally, add SDGs into the reconstructed course.

The gaps found in the Introduction to Game Theory were aspects of the lecturing method, which the lecturer still dominates, and attempts to incorporate fundamental impacts in the natural and social sciences have not been made. New competencies to be developed are mentioned as follows:

To recognize optimization concepts in non-cooperative and cooperative games.

To solve two-player game problems such as a non-cooperative zero-sum game, non-cooperative non-zero-sum game, or cooperative game.

To solve the player game problem with an allocation method, namely Shapley value theory.

To relate the theory and application of game problems and to interpret the solutions and possible answers for open questions and challenges.

3.2 Reconstructing Introduction to Game Theory Course

In reconstructing the Introduction to Game Theory course, the method of assessment used during the implementation is the DREAM methodology. The five stages are Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Asses, and Manage. The assessment is done by sending online questionnaires to the students who had joined the Introduction to Game Theory. Responses from the students act as a portfolio for the instructors to analyze and use to improve the implemented course.

Online surveys were sent to obtain course assessments from students based on the DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023). Based on the survey, several students joined the introduction to game theory. Thirty percent of the students said they had attended a similar course to Hydrometeorology. The same percentage had created a project or written work similar to the Hydrometeorology course. However, when asked whether the students were asked if they had work dealing with issues related to similar topics, only five percent (5%) agreed. This shows that the Introduction of Game Theory course has not been applied yet in the work field. It is a relatively new topic that most undergraduates have not noticed. It is important to address this since this course contains sustainability justice, even though it is yet to be explicitly expressed in the module before revision.

Fig. 3 Overview of previous students knowledge and experience

Before joining the reconstructed course of the Introduction to Game theory, the students were questioned regarding their expectations from the course. There compilation of answers can be seen in Figure 4.

Fig. 4 Students' expectation of the Introduction to Game Theory course

Introduction to Game Theory course is an elective course. This is one of the reasons why most students expect to gain a comprehensive understanding of up to fifty percent (50 %) regarding the course, followed by gaining new knowledge (20 %) and solving current issues (20 %) that correlate to game theory.

The reconstructed course and module of Introduction to Game Theory was constructed. The course overview explains that game theory refers to the study of mathematical models that describe the behavior of logical decision-makers. However, it is of particular importance to take into consideration various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues about the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

The general objectives of the reconstructed Introduction to Game Theory course aim that undergraduate students may solve problems by figuring out the players who have an objective function and strategic moves to tackle. The four modules incorporated are cooperative and non-cooperative game theory, zero-sum games, Shapley value theory concepts, and game theory applications. The module provides more structure than the previous syllabus prior to revision. The reconstructed course has implemented the ICTs into the module.

3.3 Challenges in Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing Introduction to Game Theory Course

There were many challenges while deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing the Introduction to Game Theory. The Introduction to Game Theory is an elective course

in the Mathematics program, which affects the number of students enrolling in the course. However, through revision of the course, it is expected that the explicitly expressed SDGs and supported with the four dimensions of sustainability justice, the six pillars of learning, and the 10Cs will assist in delivering a more enhanced and enjoyable course for the undergraduate students who will take the Introduction to Game Theory course.

4. Conclusion

The DeCoRe technique aided in deconstructing, reconstructing, and constructing the Introduction to Game Theory course. Before the modification, the IGT course did not explicitly show sustainable development goals. The ecology course had to be rebuilt in order to do this. Not only to implement the SDGs, but also the six learning pillars, the 10Cs, and the four dimensions of sustainability justice. It was important to do all the changes to increase the awareness of students to current problems. Embedding ICT into the modules of IGT contributed to the improvement of the course. Numerous obstacles had to be overcome throughout the procedure, particularly when the rebuilt ecology course was put into use and assessments were conducted utilizing the DREAM approach.

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The Students Community Services Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing It through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

Student Community Service (SCS) course is a strategic alternative to embrace the values of sustainability. Since education play an important role to spread the ideas and principles of sustainability, it is important to improve the course curriculum so it can focuses on solving various community problems. Through this course, students are encouraged to think critically based on their role as an agent of change to solve problems in the community service areas. This article provides explanation related to deconstructing, constructing, as well as reconstructing the Student Community Service (SCS) through the lens of SDGs supported by ICTs and driven by six learning pillars (6p) as well as ten competencies (10c). This article developed the DeCoRe Methodology that aims to integrate the values of sustainability based on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The process of research has been conducted through an assessment based on DREAM Methodology to get the information from students related to the course revision. It can be known from the result that there is an improvement in the course including aspect of educational, professional, social, as well as personality of students. Beside that, there are still a lot of challenges that appear during the community service activities.

Keywords: Community Services, Students Community Service, ESD Course, SDGs

1. Introduction

Since the dissemination and infusion of the principles of sustainable development are key points, the university and higher education are called to carry out this task (Biasutti et al 2018; Biasutti and Frate 2017). Students Community Service (SCS) is a compulsory course for UGM's undergraduate students. It is covered with specific themes and designed to thematically address real issues faced by the community through multidisciplinary approaches and empowering local resources. Each theme is implemented by a group/unit consisting maximum of 30 students from various faculties in Universitas Gadjah Mada(UGM). One group will be led by one lecturer.

SCS aims to raise students' empathy and concern for the community's economic, social, and environmental issues. SCS is developed to shape students that are able to analyze problems and potentials in the community, design an empowerment program for the community, manage interdisciplinary cooperation network, implement empowerment programs based on the potency of the existing local wisdom, and formulate the performance accountability of the empowerment program based on accountability principle.

This course's guiding concepts are co-creation, co-finance, win-win solutions, sustainability, and flexibility. It is conducted by program-based research and using a multidisciplinary approach method. Thus, to achieve all the objectives of SCS, students must first comprehend a fundamental Tri Dharma principle of higher education about community services implementation. The implementation includes how to develop empathy for their surroundings, how to build a sustainable community, and how to help solve community issues.

SCS will always be a dynamic course as it has no certain knowledge patterns. Accordingly, it is expected that students

have fully comprehended the subject of their major before implementing it by developing an empowerment program for the community. They are supposed to create or build something that can be researched depending on their major during the process in order to come up with solutions or ideas for these numerous issues that have arisen in the community.

SCS was chosen as one of the revised courses as it is one of the key courses in UGM for undergraduate students. The SCS required UGM students' participation in the community to bridge the university with the local community in supporting Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), disseminate science and technology to improve the community's welfare, and empower the community to embody self-sustained society. Thus, the revision was needed as SCS has been addressing all SDGs but has not been written or stated in the curriculum.

The revision was expected to align the objectives of the course with the Sustainable Development Goals. The revision will help integrate the crucial points of SCS in addressing SDGs through the course. Overall, the revision made for SCS was around 20%. This was because most of the activities performed and programs created for the community by the students have been participating in promoting SDGs. However, there was no written instruction about how SDGs should be achieved during the student's work in the community. Thus, after the revision, UGM ensured that every program proposed by the students targeted certain SDGs indicators.

The average number of students enrolled in the SCS per year is around 8,000 students. They are divided into four implementation periods, while students are able to choose

which period they want as long as they have met the requirements to enroll in SCS. The SCS implementation periods are in January, February, July, and August, with July being the period chosen by most of the students. SCS is conducted in at least 288 effective working hours and stayed at the community service area for about 2 months. This course was supported by ICTs to help students in implementing their program. This course is given towards the students in the third year of their study, students are supposed to have completed lectures as well as laboratory works for at least 100 (one hundred) credits without an E score. The scoring component of this course including general test, activity plan report, student's performance during community service (discipline, team-work, self-reflection, and the effectiveness of the program), implementation report, as well as the response of students.

Our society is facing various problems including economic, social, environmental, as well as cultural aspect. Through this SCS, students are expected to implement multidisciplinary knowledge since a unit is consisted for about 30 members. What students learn through this course is that how to solve a multidisciplinary problems that appear in the society. Because the basic foundation of this course is a multidisciplinary knowledge from each cluster, this course is also supposed to address multidisciplinary challenges among society. So, the course is in line with almost all number of SDGs specially SDG 1 that says end poverty in all its forms in everywhere and also SDG 11 related to make cities and human settlement inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable. By understanding that the scope of SCS is consisted of various knowledge, it requires a significant change specifically through the course curriculum. This changes should be supported by integrating the revised curriculum with teaching as well as learning approaches. It needs interdisciplinary and comprehensive understanding through discussion to deal with the interconnectedness and complexity of current issues around the world. Since the SCS course is trying to infuse the idea of sustainability, it is necessary to develop the course through the concept of DeCoRe Plus concept (deconstruction, construction, and reconstruction). This concept can be used to help teachers in infusing ideas of sustainability justice into the course curriculum (Makrakis, 2017). DeCoRe Process aims to improve the course by integrating the concept of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) and the values of SDGs. The DeCoRe process is able to help in identifying the aspects of sustainability justice from SCS. Those aspects including economic justice, social justice, environmental justice, as well as the cultural justice that have been embedded into the learning process but has not been clearly stated through the learning plans or curriculum. From the aspect of economic justice, through this learning process, students are expected to have a critical thinking related how to develop and communicate a fair trade to combat economic exploitations. Furthermore, students were expected to implement knowledge in order to support local worker from various sector, for instance increasing agricultural product, fisheries, as well as forestry resources. From the social aspect, students are expected to develop a socio-cultural life

based on the local wisdom in community service area. Students should deliver the social wellbeing in terms of real community service initiatives against any kind of

social injustice. From the perspective of environment justice, student will face an environment problem through this course, they are expected to construct a scientific and applicable solutions such as helping local communities to manage domestic waste, developing natural resources, as well as disseminating knowledge towards the society. Meanwhile, from the side of cultural justice, this aspect is related with to the local wisdom of community service area. Students are expected to uphold values and norms that is applied by community as well as respect it. This sustainable justice is able to be achieved by internalizing the ideas and principles of sustainability into the curriculum of SCS course.

1. Methodologies : The How Question

1.1 Analysis Model Overview

The DeCoRe Plus Methodology advanced by Makrakis(2017) was used in this article that aims to integrate ideas and principles of sustainability from SDGs through the course curriculum. DeCoRe Plus comes from the abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction- Reconstruction as a core constructs supplemented by the process of diagnostic evaluation, implementation, and summative evaluation.

Figure 1 : The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017)

DeCoRe Plus Methodology was formed by six processes as follows.

1. Diagnostic Evaluation, aims to identify who we are, what we have from existing knowledge, where we want to go, and why we want to go there.
2. Deconstruction, gives a critical analysis of the functioning of personal perspectives and chosen curriculum units/modules.
3. Construction, gathering resources creating ideas, as well as constructing new perspectives.
4. Reconstructing, integration of a new knowledge with reconstructed frame of references.
5. Implementation, carrying out the reconstructed curriculum supported by service learning.
6. Summative Evaluation, Aims to reflect and evaluate on what has been changed and developed through the revision. It is necessary to carry out the reconstruction of SCS course by embedding the ideas and principles of sustainability. The research has been done by conducting an assessment for students using a systematic questionnaire. The questionnaire was constructed using DREAM Methodology. This methodology aims to identify the expectation, impact of the course, as well as understanding the appropriate improvement towards the course in the future. DREAM Methodology has five stages as follows.

Figure 2 : DREAM Methodology Model Makrakis

1. Diagnose

This stage aims to identify the individual profile of students including personal identity, previous experiences related to the course, as well as the student’s expectation by attending SCS course. Through this stage, we are able to know whether the issues that carried out in SCS course is a new things for them or not. The result was elaborated with the information of student’s working experience before joining this course. Those previous information were followed by the expectation of the student from Student Community Service (SCS) both theoretically and practically.

2. Review

This review stage focuses on identifying both positive and negative experience during the course. This stage provides information related to how much challenges that have been faced by students. Furthermore, this stage aims to know about how the student react towards the gap between expectation and what they got from the course. This stage was also questioning about the appropriate alternatives to improve based on the student’s experience along the course.

3. Explain

This stage is used to get a clear description related to gap that students got during the learning process in SCS course. This stage focuses on indentifying the possible reasons that can lead into the gap between expectation and result from the course. Furthermore, through this stage, we are able to know related to the constraints that are existed inside the course.

4. Assess

This stage focuses on identifying the impact of SCS learning process towards certain aspects from the students including knowledge, professional development, sustainability of social community, as well as the improvement of student’s personality. Through this assessment, students are expected to have a comprehensive reflection related to what kind of changes in those multiple aspects since the infusion of sustainability ideas and principle into the course. The result from the assessment was supposed to be a parameter of how effective this course in improving the student’s capacity.

5. Manage

The sixth stage, manage, aims to be a critical overview of how much obstacles, what kind of expectations, as well as the appropriate strategy to evaluate the learning outcomes in SCS course. The result leads us into an ideal learning process of SCS course in the future.

Assessment and Data Analysis Methods

This article uses a descriptive qualitative research with students of SCS course as the main resources in this research. This assessment has been conducted through a systematic questionnaire that supposed to be filled by students of SCS course. The assessment form was constructed based on DREAM Methodology Models which consisted of Diagnose, Review, Explain, Assess, as well as Manage process. The assessment was conducted by the consent from students, then the data will be reduced, displayed, and followed by a conclusion. The data analysing was based on DeCoRe Plus Methodology advanced by Makrakis (2017).

Pre-Course Overview of SCS

This chapter aims to identify the previous knowledge and experience of the students before attending SCS course.

Through the assessment, it can be known that there was 22% of the total respondent that had attended a similar course before joined SCS course. Furthermore, the number of students who have made a project similar to the course shows percentage of 18%. Some of those students have ever planned to conduct a project related to the course but it was cancelled during the pandemic era. From the result it can be known that the previous

knowledge is higher than the experience of conducting a project. Following the previous result, the number of students with working experience shows the lowest percentage of 16%. Those experiences stated by some students including became a project coordinator, administrative staff, school counselor, as well as social volunteer.

Through the result of pre-course assessment above, it shows a small number of percentage from three categories. We are able to know that the content related to SCS course as well as the working experience are considered a new things for students. In previous degree, students were not similar with the topics and practical skills related to empowerment program. This result was followed by the answers of student’s expectation by attending the SCS course.

This course aims to raise awareness, care, and empathy towards the poor and environmental problem, as well as economic and social issues through certain empowerment programs that was held during the community service. This

SCS course practically has organized to build student who are able to:

- Develop an empowerment program to address problem in society.
- Manage interdisciplinary and collective discussion.
- Implement empowerment program according to the

Knowledge Sharing
(4%)

Collaborative programme
(7%)

Impactful practical program
(27%)

Knowledge and skill improvement
(62%)

Figure 4 : Student's expectation Diagram

This article divided students' expectations into 4 categories, including achieving knowledge improvement, impactful practical programs, knowledge sharing, and conducting a collaborative program with society. Through this result, it can be known that student expect for a knowledge as well as skill improvement followed by impactful learning result for society, ability to conduct a collaborative program, an opportunity to share knowledge to society in community service areas.

4. Discussion

4.1 What, Why, and Where Question for Revising (SCS Course : Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing through the lens of SDGs)

Student Community Service (SCS) is considered as a compulsory course for UGM undergraduate students. This course is conducted in a particular theme that supposed to address real issues that faced by society in community service areas. SCS course is help multidisciplinary as well as interdisciplinatory approaches to improve the quality of life from people in community service areas. Students are divided into units which consisted of 27-30 students from various faculties 6 learning pillars for sustainable development. Prior to the revision, students are expected to learn about how to experience construction to explore the values and customs of

potency of region and local wisdom.

- Formulate the performance accountability based on the principles of accountability during the empowerment program.

This course is implementing a problem-based learning

since the empowerment program aims to address problems in community service area. The learning activities were done by planning and implementing a practical programs that is supposed to be impactful for society. This course is conducted based on the principles of co-creation, co-finance, win-win solution, sustainability, and flexibility. It can be known that the ideas of sustainability were tried to carry out through this SCS course.

Student Community Service (SCS) was chosen to be integrated as one of ten courses because this course is considered as a strategic way to implement knowledge from previous courses that has attended by the student. Furthermore, this course is conducted programs directly for society so this course is appropriate to raise the ideas of sustainability. Furthermore, this course focuses on addressing various social problems, it is in line with the

in every unit principles of SCS course which consisted of 27-30 students from various faculties. This circumstance is able to solve problems from many sectors in community service areas. SCS course has about 8000 students that joined in every year. The method of assessment in this course has been donethrough 6 stages including general test, activity plan report, student's performance during implementation, report of activities, response, and will be followed by a score coordination to decide the final score of the students. Through SCS, students are expected to have a critical understanding of how to solve problems that is in line with the values in SDGs.

This course aims to achieve an appropriate knowledge implementation by encourage students to have a deeper understanding about how solve a social problems. This goals are realized by create an impactful social program through Student Community Service (SCS) course. Through this course, students are expected to identify the social problems as well as its potentials as the basic foundation to make a community service program. The SCS course prior to the revision is conducted by running programs in purpose to address the local problems in community service areas. Because this course is considered as a practical course, the implementation focuses on how to develop and solve social problems at the same time. Before the revision, the learning activities in SCS course has been implemented based on the various Indonesian communities (learning to know), this process aims to know the main problems of communities and how to cope with that. This pillar can be developed when students are living among them and being the part of them. That is how the students

are expected to identify their role towards these problems reflecting on their academic content inside the course. Furthermore, the student will learn about how to be an active citizen and how to develop their sense of sympathy and empathy towards their society that supported by a critical thoughts (learning to be). Through the practical learning process, students are expected to be fully involved in community empowering activities, create certain empowerment program, as well as implement an effective program for the community (Learning to do). During the SCS course, students are expected to have both positive and effective initiative to transmit the peaceful and non-discriminatory human existence. As this course is held in field, students are expected to be engaged with the local communities (learning to live together). In scope of learning to transform oneself and society, students will learn how to drive others to transform values as well as unsustainable tradition to be in line with the values of sustainability. Through this course, students can make opportunities to share ideas, information, and experience toward society (learning to give and share)

Based on the explanation above, it was known that 6 learning pillars of for sustainable development have been implemented as the basic foundation in Student Community Service course. But the implementation of those pillars has not been clearly supported by explicit introduction of SDGs. This course is a strategic tool for infusing the ideas and values of SDGs by considering that through this course, students are able to address various and interdisciplinary social issues. However, the value of SDGs has not been introduced explicitly towards the students while the focus of this course is about social aspect and phenomena, which is represented by almost each points in SDGs especially number 11 that says *make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable*. This SCS course was able to implement 10 competencies (10 Cs) that is expected to be implemented through the course including critical thinking, communication, collaboration, creativity, connectivity, critical consciousness, critical reflection, cross-cultural competences, co-responsibility, and constructing knowledge.

By considering this course as a strategic way to develop cities and communities, it is important to develop this course that is focusing on three aspects including the gaps of this course that need to be filled, the SDGs theme to be infused, as well as the competencies that need to be strengthened. In this course, it requires infusing the values of sustainability as a strategic guidance for students to understand the goals for each content. The goals of this course are not clearly stated in the learning plans. This missing link between the program and its goals can prevent students from developing an effective solution to social problems in their communities. It

shows that it is important to explicitly state the SDGs values and principle inside the course curriculum. Basically, this course addresses almost each of SDGs values, but this course needs to focus on *make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable* (SDGs 11). Empowerment program that is constructed by students should be in line with the values of SDGs above. There are 10 competencies that need to be strengthened and explicitly stated into the learning plans. Those competencies can be a strategic way to encourage students in implementing their knowledge (instrumental,

practical, as well as emancipatory). The content of SCS course needs to be developed by infusing the SDGs values so students will be able to achieve sustainability through previous empowerment programs. This course should focus more on developing 10 competencies to address real community problems and achieve sustainable justice, encompassing the four aspects of social, environmental, economic, and cultural justice. This integration should be supported by problem-based learning and ICTs. The advanced learning process of the SCS course, specifically the integration of the learning process with SDGs values, plays a critical role in realizing education for sustainable development (ESD). Through this integration, students are expected to have a critical understanding about the complexity of local communities' issues so it requires a clear goals to be achieved.

The How Question

To identify the limitation of SCS before revision as well to construct an advanced course, this research uses the DecoRe Plus Models that is advanced by Makrakis (2017). The reconstruction of Student Community Service (SCS) is carried out that aims to develop the course curriculum by integrating the course curriculum with sustainability values. This research conducted an assessment where students are expected to fill a systematic questionnaire. This research is considered as a descriptive qualitative research with students of SCS course as the data resources. The assessment was constructed based on the DREAM Methodology Model that consisted of five stages including Diagnose, Review, Explain, Assess, and Manage process.

Through the assessment with DREAM Methodology, the experiences of students during the Student Community Service (SCS) course can be known. The second process in this model is a review process. It can be observed that students' experiences are evident after they have completed half of the total lectures in the SCS course. Through this process, we can gain insight into the students' experiences, both positive and negative. The results show that the positive experiences were dominated by the opportunity to learn something new, as well as to communicate with the local community in community service areas. Additionally, through the program in the SCS course, students can develop their soft skills, including critical thinking, collective discussion, negotiation, and prioritization. The response indicates that the positive aspect of their course is when they can create an impactful program for the local society. From the results, it can be seen that the SCS course has a positive impact both theoretically and practically.

Meanwhile, the negative experiences were primarily attributed to the lack of technical or ICT support during the course.

Students have to struggle more during the learning process since the pandemic situation has limited the chance to meet directly with friends. This condition affected how students conduct a group discussion, so they have to be adaptive by familiarize ICTs support to the communication during the course.

The Now What Question

Through the assessment, we found out that the integration of course curriculum with the values of sustainability is able to

lead into improvement in scope of course content, learning methods, and the impact of the learning process. This revised course is able to provide an appropriate learning activities, so it can give a good impact towards academic development, professional development, surrounding society, as well as the improvement of personality of students. According to the assessment result, there is an improvement in terms of the academic aspect of SCS students. The majority of student's responses shows the answers stated the improvement in understanding a new knowledge. The embedding of sustainable values is able to give a deeper understanding about their goals. This is important since Student Community Service is conducted through thematic empowerment program, that's why it is important for students to be in line with the main sustainable goals as the main foundation of SCS course. That is why it is important to assure that students have a good and deeper understanding of what has been taught in the previous course to be implemented through this SCS course. So, this revised course can help students to get a deeper understanding by integrating the values of sustainability inside the course materials as well as the learning activities. The infusion of sustainable values helps students to identify what is the purpose as well as impacts from each materials in this SCS course. This improvement was followed by the implementation of ten competencies (10 Cs) to support students in running empowerment programs. From this course, the students are able to identify certain problems in society from the perspective of social, environmental, economical, and cultural justice. The embedding of sustainable values is able to encourage students to think critically. By adding value of sustainability, we adding the value of responsibilities as well towards the students. That why it requires students to have a critical thinking to solve the community problems. This skill of critical thinking is able to lead students to get a logical and wider perspective in identifying problems through the empowerment program. Recent cases that is given towards students as a topics of group discussion was able to encourage students to work in a team. Furthermore, this learning circumstances was able to push students to look for a valid and credible data and resources supported by ICTs. The unit that consist for 27-30 people trained the students to have certain skills including skill in communication, collaboration, creativity, create networks and connectivity, critical conciousness, as well as critical reflection. Those competencies are important to construct a knowledge. Beside constructing knowledge,

there is a need to disseminate the knowledge towards society that aims to distribute a broader knowledge and information.

This SCS course is a strategic way to distribute knowledge and information through a real empowerment programs. This process needs the ability of student including inter- cultural Each of competencies was integrated with the ideas and principles of sustainability to generate a comprehensive knowledge that is impactful towards local society in community service areas.

From the professional aspect, through the responses, it can be known that the revised curriculum is able to help students to improve their professional skills. From the DREAM Methodology assessment, we found out that, Student Community Service (SCS) course stimulate student's professional skills including the skill of

teamwork, public speaking skills, priority setting, time management, aswell as the ability to analyze a data. Those skills are supported by a collective as well as collaborative problem solving. Means that in making a program, a student should be able to work together inside a team or unit, then in running the program students are expected to collaborate with the local people in community service areas. Based on the previous discussion, it can be known that there are differences from the previous course and the revised course in the aspect of professional skills.

From the side of social development, it can be known that this SCS course is able to give a significant impact including improvement of social and community problem awareness, communication skills towards society, as well as the integration of sustainability values in solving social problems. Since there were various social problems, those skills above are important for practical purpose such as formulate a solution for community problem problems or develop an alternative solution to increase the productivity of local communities. Moreover, students become more aware and understand how to appraise a social issues community service areas. This course was able to revitalize the course materials to be in line the values of sustainability.

Another aspect is personal development. Through this course, student was able to improve their personal quality that is supported by a contextual empowerment program, this improvement including improvement of personal awareness toward social issues, innovative thoughts, co- responsibility, adaptability, as well as empathy to community problems in general. Furthermore, in this pandemic era, students face another challenge with ICTs issues such as electronic tools and internet support that is not good enough to support the empowerment activity.

Through the manage process that used the concept of DREAM Methodology, we found out that there must be a holistic integration through the course materials, a learning system which encourages students to be more innovative both theoretically and practically. In addition, students were expected to improve literacy towards ICT tools and supports, as well as increase awareness towards certain community issues related to this SCS course. The last question in manage process is about the changes that we need to improve the course. The result shows that this course

is considered an important course since it provides an alternative way to apply students' knowledge from the previous course in university. Infusing the SDGs values into the course will increase students' awareness and understanding of the real community problems in the local area. The learning process is able to optimize students' awareness to achieve the values in Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically SDGs number 11, to achieve an inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable cities and human settlement.

Through the revision, the implementation of SDGs into the course can help students to understand since in the revised curriculum, the sustainability values has been clearly stated. There was differences in terms of how the student can understand the critical role of students in order to achieve the sustainability and solve various community problems. It can be said that the integration of SDGs values play a critical role in improving students understanding towards the course materials, it can be understood because the goals of learning are clearly stated inside the learning plans, moreover the implementation

of 6 learning pillars and 10 competencies help student to applied create a program as a practical waysand to improve their knowledge as well as their soft skill in university.

The 'So What' Question

Deconstruction, construction, and reconstruction process of Student Community Service (SCS) course through the lens of SDGs is a strategic way to improve the quality of education. During the revision process, we encountered challenges that arose along the way. By considering this course as a completely practical course, students expected to develop an empowerment program that addresses the social problems in community service areas. Furthermore, these challenges arise because the holistic integration, which involves embedding specific values, must be followed by an appropriate adaptation and support throughout the process. This commitment requires changes of content, advanced individual as well as unit assignments, assessments, and the optimization of ICTs to support activities in the SCS course. Through the complex and interdisciplinary processes, we identified various constraints. The gap between students' expectations and what they received from the course was a significant difficulty in the first place.

The concept of community service is not a familiar topic among students, which means that conducting empowerment programs for the community is considered a novel approach for them. This condition puts students in a new phase that requires them to adapt in terms of a new responsibility, a new team, and a new environment. That is why most of the time will be used for adaptation in the new circumstances. This condition requires an ideal learning method to encourage students to be actively participating in the learning activities. The participatory learning that integrated with the ideas and principles of sustainability in every program is able to support students to understand with their goals through an empowerment program. Each unit consists

of around 30 students, so it requires collaborative skills for each student. This condition is considered as challenges for students. But, this case can be resolved by giving them a spare time to adapt and know each other before the programs started.

By infusing the values of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into the course curriculum is able to stimulate the students to have a deeper understanding and awareness towards social issues among communities specifically in the community service areas. The SCS course is conducted through a practical programs based on the real problem that faced by communities. This condition is able to habituate students in thinking critically both in individual or a collective teamwork. The infusion of SDGs values explicitly into the learning content and driven by ICTs tool supports was able to create a better understanding from the students. This was proved by the assessment result that shows students' awareness toward various social and community problems was improved. This is answering that sustainable values from SDGs need to be supported by a practical programs to generate an education for sustainable development (ESD).

Based on the process of deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing through the lens of SDGs in Student Community Service (SCS) course, the students are supposed to have a holistic understanding of their

empowerment programs based on the community issues that they are trying to resolve. The value of SDGs plays a critical role as catalyst for student to understand the concept of sustainability. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable is a goal that should be integrated with the course curriculum since education holds a critical role to embrace the idea of sustainability. Beside infusing the values of SDGs into a real programs, it was important to assure there is an appropriate assessment to assure that whether the program has been done effectively or not. That is why, the revised curriculum should be followed by a suitable learning strategy as well as the assessment system towards the result of each programs.

From all process of revision that has been done; it can be known that it will not be easy to infuse the idea of sustainability into a course. This leads us into another understanding that the values of SDGs must be seen as a framework for the student that is still in line with the social, environmental, economical, as well as cultural justice. That is why this integration should be seen as an urgency to be implemented towards the course as specifically in the university and its students as the agent of change. It means that, university play a critical role to generate and spread the idea of sustainability. So, the implementation of the SDGs values needs to be done by improving this Student Community Service (SCS) course that is in line with the ideas and principle of sustainability in order to realize Education for Sustainable Development (ESD). It is important to take into consideration various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues pertaining to the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al. 2024).

Conclusion

Education is considered as important actor that play a critical role as the agent of change to obtain the ideal implementation of sustainability values (Biasutti and Frate 2017; Biasutti and Frate 2018). While communities

Recently facing problems including social, environmental, economic, as well as cultural issues, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) need to be integrated into the course curriculum. It requires a systematic improvement towards the course materials that should be in line with the values of sustainability. Through the lens of SDGs, it can be seen that there is a missing link between the empowerment programs in SCS course and the values of sustainability, it is hard to understand what goals that the students need to achieve. Based on the description above, SCS course is considered as a course that aims to overcome various community problems, that is why it is important to develop the course to be in line with values of SDGs especially number 11 that is related to the idea of developing a sustainable cities and citizens.

The use of the DeCoRe Plus for embedding social sustainability through the course curricula supported by ICTs and driven by 6 pillars of learning as well as 10 Competencies (10 Cs) is a strategic way to improve the education in university. Assessment using DREAM Methodology has been conducted for the student to know their perspective about the course revision. We found out that at the beginning of the course there were a gap between expectations and result that the

students get along the course. In addition, the values of SDGs have not been clearly explained in the course curriculum. It can be known from the result that there is an improvement in form of a wider perspective and deeper understanding about the sustainability. The scope of improvement including aspects of educational, professional, social, as well as personality.

Besides the improvement that can be achieved, there were some challenges that we face through the assessment as well as learning process. Those challenges including the understanding of students since this course was a new topic for majority of students. Furthermore, students of SCS course needs to struggle more in running their programs with a collaborative teamwork. As a whole process shows the SCS course is needed to be improved by embedding and clearly stated the values of sustainability in course learning plans to achieve an education for social development (ESD).

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The Training of Successful Learners for New Students Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing It through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

The training of successful learners for new students courses of *pelatihan pembelajar sukses bagi mahasiswa baru* (PPSMB) is a compulsory course for new undergraduate students aimed to prepare them for adapting to university life. PPSMB was chosen as one of the revised modules since it is an essential module for students. The course aims to help students to be able to conduct their roles and responsibilities as students at Universitas Gadjah Mada. Furthermore, it will shape students' attitudes and develop UGM students' character. Sustainable development goals were acknowledged in the course in the last five years however inconsistently mentioned in the design of the course. The course was revised with two methodologies which are DeCoRe plus and DREAM methodology. Revision using the DeCoRe plus method resulted in a clearer guidance regarding objectives, assessments, and deciding more in depth topics. The DREAM methodology is an assessment done by students through surveys. In the revised course, utilization of ICT in the design of course implementation more broadly provides several advantages in the form of a wider scope of course implementation.

Keywords: PPSMB, DeCoRe+, DREAM Methodology, ESD Course, SDGs,

1. Introduction

1.1 Description of the course before revision

The training of successful learners for new students courses or *pelatihan pembelajar sukses bagi mahasiswa baru* (PPSMB) is a compulsory course for new undergraduate students aimed to prepare them for adapting to university life. The course was divided into three modules namely the University module, Faculty module, and soft skills module. Each module was conducted for two days. During the University and soft skills modules, students were a group in a heterogeneous mixture consisting of different backgrounds, sex, religion, hometown, and study program. This grouping aims to increase student awareness of cultural diversity so that in the end students are able to build social equity in the community. There were 200 classes of 40 - 50 students throughout the University. Meanwhile, the faculty module puts emphasis on the major they will learn and how they can use their expertise in society when they graduate.

PPSMB was chosen as one of the revised modules because it was an essential module for students. The course aims to help students to be able to conduct their roles and responsibilities as students at Universitas Gadjah Mada. Furthermore, it will shape students' attitudes and develop UGM students' character. The main character to be built was students who prioritize attitudes as intellectuals who rely on the intelligence of thinking, maturity in speaking and acting, anti-violence, cultured, dignified, inspiring, and upholding the values of Pancasila. Thus, this course had the potential to deliver the goal

of EfS and gave the students the insight to become change agents.

Each year, the number of students attending the course varies depending on the yearly intake in UGM. Around 7000+ students from the undergraduate courses and around 1000+ students from vocational courses entered University yearly. From batches 2018 and 2019 there were about 18.000 students who attended the course.

As the main content of the course will prepare students to be successful students and society members thus the course trains the students with essential skills needed in the 21st century. The other main contents delivered during the course are UGM values, nationalism, integrity, and communication. By learning and practising the contents delivered during the course, students will be competent in study skills, life skills, and social skills.

The teaching method adapted various learning activities based on experiential learning (Kolb & Kolb, 2017), active learning (Cattaneo, 2017), and student-centred learning (Wright, 2011; Biasutti et al. 2018) approaches. The course designers chose activities that stimulated students' active engagement such as case studies, small group discussions, poster presentations, and interactive quizzes. Meanwhile, interactive lectures given by the trainers aimed to give an introduction to specific topics and tips on achieving success in academic and social life. The lecture sessions are only given during the Faculty and soft skills module, and it comprised only a small percentage of the whole course.

Students were assessed based on their attendance during the sessions and the completeness of the assignment given. However, there was no grade or concrete rule on how to assess the assignments. The uncertainty of the assessment system hindered the determination of pass and fail decisions. Students who passed

all of the qualifications will receive a certificate that became a prerequisite for various activities such as scholarship application, student exchange applications, and judicium at the end of study time. Meanwhile, students who failed have to follow remedial training by following “Dharma Bakti Kampus”.

1.2 Comparison of content of the course before and after

Sustainable development goals were acknowledged in the course in the last five years however inconsistently mentioned in the design of the course. Sometimes the SDGs were explicitly mentioned in the course and part of the assignments but sometimes did not. Most of the time it was only implicitly mentioned during the discussion with the co-facilitator as the one who will directly face the students. Each year, the 17 SDGs issues were discussed at different levels. SDGs issues were delivered through real action such as zero plastic waste and some were delivered through the class activities such as a case study on gender equality.

In terms of the six pillars, the philosophy of the six learning pillars (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2017) for sustainable development is already in the course. PPSMB is a special course that is designated to help new students to adapt and blend into campus life. To achieve that final aim, the course designers carefully inserted the six learning pillars whether in the content or in the learning activities. For example, in the soft skills topics, students learnt to know, to be, to do, and also learned to transform themselves. Whereas learning to give and share, learning to live together, and learning to transform oneself and society were more embodied in the learning activities such as discussion, sharing sessions, and community service. However, according to the deconstruction process, we still found some gaps in SDGs issues to be delivered, 6 pillars of learning, and 10 Cs in terms of the course design and implementation. From the course design aspects, SDGs were taught but were not explicitly described in the course. The six learning pillars were implicitly covered, however, they were not consciously referred to. Based on the finding, it was suggested that there was a need for revision to make the course more suitable for the philosophy of EfS.

The soft skills that are taught during PPSMB are intended to be owned by students in a long-term orientation. All soft skills could be measured and tracked along the coursework activities and practical projects, where the students foster their personal competencies through critical discourse with the surrounding environment. The course designer did not set any omission in this learning process, since the PPSMB is a wholesome soft skill building for preparing a freshman for university life, we are setting learning activities that will build their skills in every aspect possible. The student has learned to develop a great character as a new student of Universitas Gadjah Mada. After joining PPSMB for about a week, students are expected to understand the history, philosophy, values, visions-missions, tridharma activities, achievements, contributions, academic system, and best practices of Universitas Gadjah Mada, upholding the values of Pancasila

1.3 Gaps to fill in the course

In terms of SDGs issues, the new course design was trying to infuse all of the 13 issues in the SDGs. The SDGs issues are mostly infused into the action plan module of the course. In the previous course, the SDGs issues had been

infused at a certain level but had not been well written. In the new course, the SDGs issues had been included in the learning resources as the basis for students planning their action plans.

The robust utilization of ICT in the teaching and learning process, especially due to the pandemic, changed the way students learn strategy. They were forced to increase their digital literacies which resulted in the development of competencies related to ICT (Gastelú et al., 2015; Biasutti 2011). Changes in society by increasing the use of ICT in daily life added the importance of improving students’ digital literacy levels through this course (Pineida, 2011; Biasutti 2011). In terms of sustainability, ICT acquisition helps the achievement of SDGs due to the characteristics embedded in the technology itself. ICT enabled information to be shared to wider audiences with minimum cost, and replaced materials that cause environmental damage and are more costly.

2. Methodology

2.1 Course revision using DeCoRe Plus methodology

Curriculum transformation by infusing SDG issues and using ICT is carried out by the task force team using the DeCoRe plus model (Makrakis, 2016). The DeCoRe plus curriculum transformation model consists of deconstruction, construction, and reconstruction processes, and is strengthened by the diagnostic evaluation, implementation and summative evaluation processes (Makrakis, 2016). This model has been used in various curricula especially to infuse education for sustainable development and the use of technology to deliver the course (Lorente-Echeverria, 2022, Hayes & Jandrić, 2017).

The transformation process started by conducting the diagnostic evaluation while trying to reflect on the guiding question of who we are, what we have, where we want to go, and why we want to go there (Makrakis, 2016). By having all of the answers from this reflection process, the team gains insight into the objectives of the course that has been developed, a general description of the course as well as baseline data on the available resources to run the course. The deconstruction process was conducted following the diagnostic evaluation process. The essential concept of the deconstruction process is critically analyzing the chosen course components in terms of the content, assessment methodology, gaps and omissions, power and interest, projected image and reality, and author’s reality (Makrakis, 2016). During the deconstruction process, the course developer critically described the argumentation and reasoning of the course components. A critical description of the course components was made based on the previous course curriculum. Each component was critically analyzed whether there was constructed alignment between the course objective, assessment method, course content, and learning activities chosen. In addition, a critical evaluation of whether the course already served principles of sustainable development was also conducted during the deconstruction process.

The biggest part of the curriculum transformation process is the construction process. The main concept of the construction process is creating new ideas and perspectives for the course by gathering all the resources available (Makrakis, 2016). During this process, the course director designs teaching and learning activities that promote interactiveness and student engagement enabled by ICT. Various learning activities with active learning (Camacho & Legare, 2015) and cooperative learning methods (Johnson & Johnson, 2009) are chosen so that students can achieve maximum results through increased engagement (Wolff et al., 2015), excitement, interest and self-efficacy (Hendrickson,

2021). The course chooses activities such as independent small group discussion, case study, role play, presentation, and games. In addition, the use of ICT in the teaching process, especially the use of audio-video-based teaching resources, LMS, ARs (e.g. Quizziz), collaborative tools (e.g. Google workspace) and online conferencing platforms, was also designed. ICT provided powerful tools for the implementation of active learning techniques (Camacho & Legare, 2015). Further, in the construction phase, the course directors also tried to integrate 21st-century learning pillars and 10 Cs into the course (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2017). These two frameworks were used as guidance in developing the objectives of the course, content and learning activities in the course. The next step in transforming the course was the reconstruction process. The key concept of this process is to integrate the new course design with the reconstructed frameworks (Makrakis, 2016). During this stage, the course director planned the course implementation.

The implementation stage in the DeCoRe Plus method occurs when the course that has gone through the stages of deconstruction - construction - and reconstruction is implemented on students. The PPSMB course is carried out for all new students in full online due to the pandemic. Learning activities are carried out synchronously and asynchronously. Synchronous sessions are conducted for 6 days with a duration of 4 hours a day using the GMeet virtual conferencing platform. Meanwhile, asynchronous sessions are conducted through eLOK (University's learning management system) and social media (Instagram, Youtube, Line group). Near-peer students facilitated the most learning process, especially on topics related to the adaptation to campus life and the learning experience at UGM. The selection of near-peer students as facilitators aims to increase student engagement because of the closeness of age and emotion as well as connection to students' level of understanding (Stigmar, 2016). The final stage of the DeCoRe Plus methodology is a summative evaluation which aims to measure the output of the course. The information exported at this stage is the changes that occur to students after taking the course and how much students are able to construct new knowledge and skills (Makrakis, 2016). The summative evaluation process on the PPSMB course used the DREAM methodology developed by Makrakis.

2.2 Course Evaluation using DREAM methodology

The course director conducts an evaluation of the PPSMB course which has been transformed into a course that infuses the SDGs issue and utilizes ICTs using the DREAM methodology. Makrakis developed the DREAM methodology as a tool to evaluate courses that support education for sustainable development. DREAM methodology consists of a series of processes consisting of diagnosis, review, explain, assess, and manage, with several open-ended and reflective questions in each category. The dream methodology was chosen as a course evaluation tool because the evaluation framework built is similar to the Gibbs reflection cycle (Gibbs, 1988) which supports experiential learning (Kolb, 2014) which is an educational approach to the PPSMB course. In the category of diagnosis, information about the condition you already have is explored. The next process is followed by exploring issues that occur during the course, in the middle of the course duration, which is included in the review category. Extracting information about positive and negative things, conformity with students' expectations of the course, and also

identifying gaps between what is expected and what is happening are detailed information that is explored in the explain stage. Further explanation was conducted in the explain category to obtain information about the reasons for conditions that were not as expected in the middle of the course and what effect they had on the student learning process. The next category is an assessment that explores the impact of a course on student development in terms of academic, professional, personal, and social aspects. In addition, this category also collected information on how students will change the course into a course that is more in line with student needs. The last category in this evaluation is managing which tries to explore students' plans for the abilities gained during the course in their future lives and how to apply these new abilities in different conditions.

The evaluation of the PPSMB course using the DREAM methodology was carried out using a survey method for students who took the PPSMB course in 2020. The DREAM questionnaire was distributed to students in the form of an e-questionnaire sent to students via WhatsApp. The information collected from the questionnaire consists of quantitative and qualitative data. The data obtained in the form of quantitative descriptive analysis was carried out to determine the frequency of the participant's background. While the data in the form of qualitative analysis is carried out qualitatively by means of open coding to then get a theme. Thematic analysis was carried out on each category in the DREAM methodology.

3. Key Results

3.1 Number of students administered the course

The number of students administered the Training of Successful Learner for New Student course in the academic year of 2020 and 2021 for each year were 8000 students.

3.2 Changes made in the course

University through the curriculum team for PPSMB made some revisions in some aspects of learning outcomes, contents, and delivery mode. The changes made resulted from the evaluation conducted and the demand from the progression of the world. Graduates must have skills to fulfil the industry and community demands. Nevertheless, students need certain knowledge and skills to be able to tackle learning tasks during University life. Completing the task is certainly not enough for students, they also need to be able to adapt to the University norms and cultures. The student's ability to blend in with the University will foster student's personal development which in turn will help students to reach their utmost potential. To make sure that objectives are achieved, the curriculum team designed a new learning instruction for the new batch of students.

In order to give clearer guidance than before, the task force reformulated the learning objectives into more measurable ones. The learning objectives were written following Bloom's taxonomy levels for knowledge and attitude (Bloom & Anderson, xxxx). This action made the course clearer. From the assessment point of view, the team could design how to assess students. Most of the assessments are designed to capture the knowledge and skills students achieve during the course. At the end of the course, students will get grades based on their achievement and conformity with the assessment rubric of each assignment. The course designers knew what kind of topics should be delivered during the sessions. Further, it also helped in deciding the breadth and depth of the topics given. Clear learning objectives also gave guidance in developing the learning activities that should be employed during the course. Thus, the course alignments could be maintained by all of the team teaching.

3.3 DREAM methodology results

The DREAM methodology developed by Makrakis (2023) has been used for carrying out the assessment. The diagnosis part of the assessment of the course showed that most of the students had attended similar courses in form of the high school induction program, basic leadership training, nationalism training, motivation training, also gender and sex education during their high school. However, only a few of them had worked on similar topics. The students expected that the course will help them to better know the University, improve their self-capacity and widen their network. These three students' expectations were met with the course aim and design.

Students reflected on their positive and negative experiences during the course, in addition, they also reflected on the gap between what they expected with their experience. The positive incidents were that the course was delivered in a fun and enjoyable manner, and they got an opportunity to meet new friends from various regions in Indonesia and different majors which helped them to adapt to the new learning environment. The new students also put emphasis on the involvement of their near-peer students as their facilitators during the course as the positive part. The near-peer facilitators made students feel more comfortable to fulfill their curiosity about university life and any issues they wanted to know related to the course. The ability to speak the same language as the new students and experience of the same status as students make the condition possible. In addition, students also appreciated the content of the course that added new knowledge and skills especially related to soft skills, health awareness and social awareness. The design of the learning course also get positive reactions from students, however, they also found some uncomfortable incidents related to the online nature of the course. Technical problems such as the unstable signal, high cost of the internet data, and servers being down due to overload happened during the course as the most challenging in conducting online courses in developing countries. Further, the duration of the course from morning until afternoon even being structured as synchronous and asynchronous activities still gave the symptoms of screen fatigue. Students also complained that there were so many learning tasks and assignments they had to finish. Even though they also thought that happened due to the shock they got due to the long school break due to the pandemic. Nevertheless, the course that was conducted online was also beyond what the new students expected. They felt disappointed, less excited and less interested in their interaction with new friends and the University itself. Suggestions were made by students especially related to the incidents that were perceived as not as they expected and negative.

4. Implication

The revised course uses the DeCoRe Plus method and is guided by the six pillars of 21st-century learning and 10 Cs so that it can incorporate elements of SDGs issues and use ICTs in the teaching and learning process, which is expected to have a positive impact on the teaching and learning process, curriculum and society. Course development based on the six pillars of 21-century learning is expected to have an influence on student learning outcomes so that students' character is formed according to the expectations of the University. This can happen because the six pillars not only prioritize learning processes that are knowledge and skills but also about transforming society towards a sustainable and self-aware

society. All of this is very much in line with the learning outcomes of the PPSMB course, including mastery of 21st-century skills in the form of soft skills, learning skills, and social skills. In addition, the ability to transform society and become a person who encourages sustainable development is also one of the learning achievements of the PPSMB course which is boosted because of the use of the 6 pillars of the learning foundation. Further, the course instructional design employed more active learning and collaborative learning methods in their learning activities. The use of this method increases student engagement, motivation and interest which ultimately leads to a higher level of material mastery in students (Hendrickson, 2021; Camaco & Legare, 2015).

After carrying out the course revision process by increasing the portion of the use of ICT and instructional design that is more directed at education for sustainable development, the course developer can draw some lessons learned. Course development by referring to an existing framework, in this case, the six-pillar of 21st-century learning and 10 Cs, can help course developers to provide a framework for what issues need to be considered during course development or revision (Makrakis, 2017). Evaluation and reflection on what the previous course has had with the chosen framework help course developers find out the gaps that need to be developed in order to meet the needs and demands of the community. This action is in accordance with the stages required when developing a curriculum (Kern, 2016). In the end, the revised course can have an indirect impact on society through students who study the course because the content taught is in accordance with the needs of the community. In addition, the content and teaching process in the course can also shape students' attitudes and behavior when performing their roles in society.

Utilization of ICT in the design of course implementation more broadly provides several advantages in the form of a wider scope of course implementation. The use of technology in the educational process was previously limited to making learning resources in the form of audiovisuals and using web-based technology as a place to store learning resources. In the revised course, ICT is used more broadly, web-based technology in the form of a learning management system not only functions as a repository but is also used in the interaction process with students. Online discussion using the LMS platform gives students the opportunity to exchange arguments and learn from each other there. LMS is also used in the assessment process as well as facilitating the assessment documentation process, a more open assessment and providing direct feedback on the assignments given. This provides benefits to students because the feedback provided strengthens the student learning process. In addition, other students can also learn from their peers through peer feedback and discussions that show a diverse point of view. Indirectly, this condition provides an opportunity for students to practice appreciating the differences that will be encountered in society. This is reinforced by Makrakis (2017) who states that ICTs have the potential to enable the implementation of education for social justice because of their nature that can break through geographical, time and social strata. However, attention should be based on the various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues pertaining to the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al. 2024).

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The Ecology Course: Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing the Ecology Course Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

The ecology course was designed to give students basic knowledge of Ecology which this course contains principles and basic concepts of individual characters, population, community, and ecosystem characters. As time passes, it has become an urgent matter to incorporate sustainable development goals and sustainability justice into the course. This article aims to deconstruct, construct, and reconstruct the Ecology course through the lens of SDGs. Implementation of ICTs was also conducted in the course, supported by the six learning pillars and 10Cs. The DeCoRe+ method was used to embed the ideas and principles of sustainability. Throughout the process, the DREAM methodology was an approach for the students to gain input regarding the reconstruction of the course.

Keywords: Ecology, ESD Course, DeCoRe+, DREAM methodology, ICT, SDGs

1. Introduction

The ecology course has been designed to give students basic knowledge of Ecology where this course contains principles and basic concepts of individual characters, population, community and ecosystem characters. The course describes how ecological concepts and processes are applied at various scales to conserve and manage renewable natural resources (e.g., plants, animals, water, soil) in terrestrial and aquatic systems—it explains how ecological science is applied to help solve real-world problems. This will be disseminated through the sustainability justice concept, respecting all the environmental, social, cultural and economic aspects as a rounded figure.

Since most of these concerns result from human activity, the course strongly emphasizes potential conservation and management techniques to lessen anthropogenic problems such as habitat fragmentation, invasive species, disease, and climate change. The course focuses on how animals interact with one another and with their abiotic environment. It examines various biological concepts, including population growth, symbioses, biodiversity, and nutrient and water cycles, and emphasizes how these concepts are used to manage natural resources efficiently (Johnson, 2020).

The course emphasizes how human behavior affects ecological phenomena in land and marine systems while also providing a wide foundation of significant ecological principles. Examples from natural resource management are used to highlight major ideas and concepts (Johnson, 2020). In addition, this course uses case studies to demonstrate the application of ecological principles to conserve and manage natural resources for current usage and future demand. As

stated in some researches the Use of new didactic methodologies such as project based learning or case studies could enhance the effectiveness of the students' learning (Biasutti and El-Deighady 2015) so it is important to revise the curriculum according to that (Biasutti et al. 2018).

Several references and databases can use to improve the student's understanding, including recorded lectures, web-based learning activities, problem sets, nature documentaries, and textbook readings. There is also group practical projects and several online discussions based on nature documentaries students must watch.

The basics of comprehending the intricate connections that exist throughout our world and serve as a framework for understanding our current global challenges will typically be taught to students. While recorded lectures focus and explain the global application of environmental principles to conservation and management of natural resources, text readings offer a comprehensive foundation of general ecological ideas (Moles, 2010).

Ecology studies the interactions between living organisms, including humans, and their physical environment; it seeks to understand the vital connections between plants and animals and the world around them (Smith and Smith, 2009). Therefore, this course becomes very effective in the delivery of sustainability justice for the existence of living organisms.

Curriculum goals are itemized as Social and Civic Goals, Personal Goals, Vocational Goals, and Historical and Cultural Goals. However, Academic goals are missing and immediately must be added and explained based on what is expected from education. Ecology is very close to living

things, but not all learning activities apply the four dimensions of sustainability justice, 6 pillars and 10Cs. Therefore, connecting the course to 6 pillar and 10Cs should be improved.

2. Methodology

2.1 DeCoRe Plus

The DeCoRe Plus methodology is a contraction of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction processes. The three steps are supplemented by those of Diagnostic Evaluation, Implementation and Summative Evaluation. The theoretical foundation of the DeCoRe plus approach originates from critical social theory, critical pedagogy and postmodern conceptions of teaching, learning and curriculum. This method was developed by Makrakis (2019).

The DeCoRe plus processes comprises six processes where this linear process is interconnected to each other in forming a whole system as shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1. The DeCoRe plus interaction (Makrakis, 2017)

The six processes contain key concepts which explain what is done throughout each step of the DeCoRe Plus method. **(1) Diagnostic evaluation** reflects on our identity, what we currently possess regarding the knowledge, where we are heading, and why do we head there, **(2) Deconstruction** is where critical analyses are conducted upon the functioning of personal perspectives of mind and chosen curriculum units/ modules, **(3) Construction** is a process in assembling resources, generate ideas, and constructing new perspectives, **(4) Reconstruction** process integrates newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference, **(5) Implementation** process is where the reconstructed curriculum unit or module is carried out by service learning, and **(6) Summative Evaluation** process helps to reflect and evaluate about what has been learned and changed (Makrakis, 2017)

2.2 DREAM Methodology

The DREAM methodology (Fig. 2) was used to evaluate the revised Ecology course during the implementation process based on the students' perspectives that have joined the course. This evaluation method was started from *Diagnosing*, where students give their opinions before the implementation of the courses, followed by *Reviewing/reflecting*, and *explaining* which was done during the course. *Assessing* and *managing* were done by the end of the implemented course. The goal of DREAM

methodology is to assess and improve the course where the improvements result from the instructor's analysis of the students' portfolio. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios obtained from undergraduate students will provide important information regarding course improvement in the future.

Fig 2. The Dream Methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

2.3 Data Collection

The data was collected using an online survey approach. The survey was run through Google Forms. The survey was distributed to former Ecology course participants to acquire the data. Google Forms was used to conduct the survey online. Students who had previously taken the Ecology course received the survey. Names, email addresses, and student numbers were among the details about students' identities that were gathered. Before completing the questionnaire, the students were asked for their permission. When it was converted to an e-Form, none of the questions were changed. The responses were downloaded, organized into courses, and then further examined.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Deconstructing the Ecology course

Ecology course provides information about the relation between organism and their environments; distribution and abundance of organisms and some affected factors; the relation between evolution and ecology; ecosystem and its metabolism; principles, structure, and population dynamic, regulation and interaction between populations; community and its structure, ecological succession and biomes; ecological applications, conservations, biodiversity and global ecological issues.

Students who are interested in taking ecology as their final undergraduate thesis may take some elective courses that required this course, such as: advanced courses of ecology, limnology, wetland ecology, marine ecology, biology conservation, pollution and toxicology.

The learning goals or competencies of the ecology course before had not yet been identified and explicitly imply the four dimensions of sustainability justice, six learning pillars

for sustainable development, and the 10Cs. The learning goals were focused on five main points which are (1) Knowledge and understanding, (2) Ability or intellectual skill, (3) Practical skill, (4) Managerial and transferable skill, and (5) Attitude.

Content of the ecology course before revision encompass several topics, including: relation between organism and their environments; distribution and abundance of organisms and some affected factors; relation between evolution and ecology; ecosystem and its metabolism; principles, structure and population dynamic, regulation and interaction between populations; community and its structure, ecological succession and biomes; ecological applications, conservations, biodiversity and global ecological issues. The students were assessed theoretically through final examination, presentation and attendance. Meanwhile practical assessments were conducted through laboratory work.

Based on the earlier syllabus of the ecology course, it can be seen that the ecology course has potency to be added with the four dimensions of sustainability justice, six learning pillars for sustainable development, and the 10Cs. At the Faculty of Biology, every year about 200 students take the Ecology course. However, the number of students may vary depending on the student intake per year. Furthermore, ecology plays a crucial part for human well-being and prosperity. In order to recognize what is already implicitly implemented in the ecology course and/or needed to be added, the deconstruction of the ecology course was conducted based on the DeCoRe methodology.

Through the deconstruction process, the learning activities related to real life and the four dimensions of sustainability justice (environmental justice, social justice, economic justice, & cultural justice) were identified in the ecology course. The environmental justice mentioned in the ecology course expects students to learn how to integrate the ecological concepts and approaches for the major ecosystems and to build an interdisciplinary approach on observing environmental dynamics. The social justice implemented in the ecology course is that the students will learn the core theme in ecology and diversity of leading elements among the wildlife conversion and habitat and species, addressing sustainable societal lifelong well-being. The economic justice values in the ecology course are correlated to how students learn about ecological awareness and consciousness which will improve the economic and fair human evolution. The cultural justice value was identified in the ecology course prior to revision. This value is seen when students learn the basic principles of structure and ecosystem diversity, and how to develop minds and directions towards sustainable global world, addressing ecological integrity

Simultaneously, the deconstruction process connected the ecology course's learning activities to all the six learning pillars for sustainable development. Learning to know is where students learn to build knowledge of the principles of ecology and current threats to transmit lifelong awareness

and sustainable modes that will help to convert structure and ecosystem diversity, nutrient cycles and energy flow in the ecosystem. The second pillar, learning to be, is implied when students learn how to generate solutions to problems of applied interest, e.g. the concepts of ecology phenomena that interact in real life and definition of terms in the field of environment.

The third pillar is about learning to live together sustainably. This pillar is shown when students learn how to lead the peaceful community theme and to develop a natural relationship between the dimension of space and time with the natural change and change on the body at a time in the environment. Learning to do it is the fourth pillar. In the ecology course prior to revision, the activity that shows the fourth is when students learn how to transform the ecological knowledge into real acts and social initiatives reflecting their academic course, explain character, structure, population dynamic, and population regulation among practical course activity.

The fifth pillar is about learning to transform oneself and society. Students will learn to spread out and generalize ecological concepts related to environment and human activity that may change habitat, ecosystem, and environment among their surroundings as a driving wheel towards sustainability justice orientation. The last pillar is learning to give and share. The ecology course from the sixth pillar of sustainable development will ensure students learn to explore the principles and theories related to the interaction between the structure, function, and reproduction that occurs in plants, animals, and humans and how humans and the environment impact animals.

The learning activities inside the ecology course prior to revision have shown that the course holds 8Cs from the total of 10Cs. The 8Cs identified in the ecology course are Collaboration, Communication, Critical thinking, Cross-cultural understanding, Connectivity, Critical reflection, Critical consciousness, and Constructing knowledge. The two missing Cs were creativity and innovation and co-responsibility.

In the ecology course, the method used for learning was the student-centered learning method combined with problem-based learning, group project work, and groups presentation approach. Small group work often used in this class and laboratory practices, allows students to learn how to work in a team, in the process of identifying and filling the gaps in their knowledge (Attard et al., 2010).

The students who enroll in the ecology course are assessed based on key concepts, by direct method. We infused three components of assessment including sustainability justice, six learning pillars, and 10Cs (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). Such as, quiz, formative test, assignment, presentation, poster competition, peer review, assistant teacher observation, pretest, posttest, laboratory research proposal, laboratory work report, and laboratory activity as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Methods of assessment

Key concept	Methods of Assessment											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
I. Sustainability justice												
a. Environmental justice	√	√	√									
b. Economic justice		√	√									
c. Cultural justice												√
II. Six learning pillars												
a. Learning to know		√								√	√	
b. Learning to be												√
c. Learning to live together				√								√
d. Learning to do												√
e. Learning to transform oneself	√	√										√
f. Learning to give and share				√			√				√	√
III. 10Cs												
a. Collaboration								√	√			√
b. Communication				√	√							
c. Critical thinking and problem solving	√	√	√			√				√	√	
d. Cross-cultural understanding					√							√
e. Connectivity							√		√			
f. Critical reflection		√							√			
g. Critical consciousness		√						√				
h. Constructing knowledge		√						√				

Note

1. Methods of assessment: Quiz
2. Formative test
3. Assignment
4. Presentation
5. Poster competition

6. Peer review
7. Teacher assistant observation
8. Pre test
9. Post test
10. Laboratory research proposal
11. Laboratory work report
12. Laboratory activity

The gaps in the ecology course prior to revision was that the course only addresses the theoretical part of ecology and lacks a practical approach for day to day life. The ecology course also has not included the creativity and innovation pillar since the instructor relied on scientific facts and social moves. But this pillar should be addressed as the course encourages students to have an innovative, creative and enterprising attitude in solving problems, to work with and appreciate difficulties and change. The question that was not raised in the ecology course was regarding methods of ecological investigation and control of social and economic issues. The course mainly focused on current status and problem tracking rather than how to solve the problem which would enhance the students ability to act and think of a sustainable future.

It is important to understand that there are several competencies to be developed in the reconstructed Ecology course. The course aims to know the principles and theories of interaction between the structure, function, and reproduction that occurs to plants, animals and humans in our environment. The aims are specified into objectives mentioned below:

1. Understand the basic principles of structure and ecosystem diversity,
2. Understand how to classify nutrient cycles and energy flow in ecosystem,
3. Able to associate between the dimension of character, structure, population dynamic, and population regulation;
4. Describe the ecological concepts which relate to the environment and human activity that may change habitat and ecosystem and environment

3.3 Reconstructing the Ecology course

The reconstruction of the Ecology course was aimed to integrate the new constructed knowledge obtained from the deconstruction process explained previously. This process is aimed to achieve an enhanced ecology course that implements four dimensions of sustainability justice (environmental justice, social justice, economic justice & cultural justice), six learning pillars for sustainable development (learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to transform oneself and society, & learning to give and share), and the 10 Cs (constructing knowledge, critical thinking and problem solving, communication, collaboration, creativity and innovation, connectivity and networking, critical consciousness, critical reflection, cross/intercultural competence, and co-responsibility).

The reconstructed ecology course undergoes implementation to be assessed by the undergraduate

students. The ecology course was assessed by distributing questionnaires to previous students who joined the ecology course. The questions proposed in the questionnaire are constructed based on the DREAM methodology. The questions were divided into the five processes mentioned previously in subsection 2.2.

The first step is to *Diagnose*. There were 36 students who responded to the given questionnaire. When asked *have you attended a similar course*, seventy-five percent (75%) of the students who attended the ecology course answered Yes while the other twenty-five percent (25%) said No. Fifty percent (50%) of the students had worked in dealing similar issues to the topic of the course. The respondents who answered Yes, mainly worked as an assistant researcher. Based on this, ecology is seen as an important course for the students, providing them the knowledge to implement in scientific and daily settings. Thus, it is important to reconstruct for the students to learn sustainability justice and SDGs.

The students were asked regarding their expectation of the ecology course. The responses of the students are visualized in figure 1. Forty-one point seven percent (41.7%) of the respondents expected to obtain a more in depth knowledge concerning ecology. The second highest percentage is acquiring practical knowledge (25%). The practical knowledge that the students expect are the ones that can be applied at work or to solve current environmental problems.

Fig 1. Students' Expectation of the Ecology course

The second step is to *Review* or *Reflect*. In this part, the respondents were asked to describe their experience regardless positive or negative and what was different between the course and their expectations. The students had similar positive responses regarding the ecology course. The ecology course helps the undergraduate students broaden their knowledge regarding ecology. At the same time, the

respondents also had negative experiences during the ecology course that they took even though some responded that they did not experience negative incidents during the course. Mostly, the students were overwhelmed with the number of tasks such as laboratory reports and term papers that must be completed. Furthermore, several students stated that the materials were complex which affected their capabilities in understanding the course.

In the third step, the students were asked to further explain their previous responses concerning their different expectations after midway joining the course. The implementation of ICTs in the ecology course were used as platforms for online learning such as Google meeting and Zoom. Several students preferred in-person classes but could not experience it as the pandemic occurred. The student's comprehension can be improved by using a variety of resources and databases, such as recorded lectures, web-based learning activities, problem sets, nature films, and textbook readings through the LMS.

In assessing the course, four impacts were questioned: academic, professional, social, and personal development. The students stated in their survey that the course helped them in their academic development where their score improved and was able to publish a scientific article in the ecology field. On the other hand, some felt that the course had no significant impact on their academic development. In the professional development aspect, the knowledge of the ecology course assisted them with skills to work in the biodiversity sector. Soft skills such as time management, persistence, and perseverance were developed through the course. As for social development, the students stated that they became more aware of their environmental problems and would try to help maintain a sustainable life. Last, the impacts of the knowledge on their personality.

The fifth step is to *Manage*. The students were asked about what they can change or how they apply new learning of the course in the future. The responses showed very different answers from one another. Taking two responses, they suggested that the course include local language translation and increase more practical knowledge or practice sessions to enhance skills.

The responses given by the students through the survey based on DREAM methodology of the revised ecology course gave the instructors insight of what can be improved. Based on the responses given by the students and analyzed, the final reconstructed ecology learning objectives were able to be created. The objectives include:

1. encourage scientific, critical and creative thinking in students in the ecology field.
2. instill the basic principles of fundamental ecology in environment and biodiversity preservations
3. conceptualize ecological phenomenon within organisms and environment,
4. integrate ICT to heighten ESD awareness and the socio-cultural awareness among the current and future praxis

The aims presented in the reconstructed ecology course are more complete than the objectives prior to the revision of the course. Furthermore, the ecology course outcomes were enhanced for the students. The reconstructed outcomes

are shown, as follows:

1. Explain how different modern ecological principles are applied to solve specific problems affecting the conservation and management of natural resources at different spatial and temporal scales
2. Construct and explore the concept of biodiversity, describe ecological and socioeconomic values of biodiversity, and make science-based arguments as to why biodiversity should be conserved
3. Explain how biotic and abiotic factors affect the abundance and distribution of plants and animals and understand how organisms adapt and evolve in response to changing environments; analyze the role of climate change in this context and discuss strategies for mitigating negative effects of climate change on renewable resources
4. Understand and define basic interactions within and among species (e.g., competition, predation, symbioses), and explain how these interactions can be manipulated to manage populations of plants and animals to meet specific objectives
5. Explain energy flow through food webs, and nutrient (e.g., carbon) and water cycles at global and local scales and how the flow of energy is affected by the actions of humans

The course module of the reconstructed ecology course consisted of 4 modules: (1) Course Introduction, Organisms and their Environment, (2) Ecosystems, Communities and Populations, (3) Habitat and Interactions Among Organisms, and (4) Applied Ecology. Each new reconstructed module incorporates comprehensive information of the materials that will be taught. Students will know what unit they will learn each week inside the module, the references they need to read, and what activities will be held during class. The added activities connected with the four dimensions of sustainability justice, six learning pillars of sustainable development and 10Cs.

One example module (Appendix 1) in the Ecology course is the Applied Ecology module. The key concepts are population, community and ecosystem. In this module, students will gain current top environmental issues that should be concerned. The topics include: Public Health, Land Management & Urban Sprawl, Waste Disposal, Overpopulation, Loss of Biodiversity, Water Scarcity & Water Pollution, Pollution, Deforestation, Ecosystems & Endangered Species, and Climate Change. Students will be divided and present based on the topic they acquire. The topics given above include several SDGs such as Sustainable development goals 6 (Clean water and sanitation), 7 (Affordable and clean energy), 13 (Climate action), 14 (Life below water), and 15 (Life on land) (United Nations, 2022). These efforts in teaching will increase the students' awareness of recent ecological problems found in real-life situations. However, attention should be based on the various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues pertaining to the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al. 2024).

3.4 Challenges in Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing the Ecology course

Ecology and Environment materials for students in Indonesia have been introduced since elementary school. Ecology is one of the topics in Biology Lessons. This is a challenge in itself when Biology students re-learn Ecology. More in-depth knowledge of Ecology is needed so that students have sustainability justice behavior. For example, studying ecosystems and communities is not just a definition. However, more comprehensively how the biotic and abiotic components interact according to their respective roles. There needs to be material updates in accordance with the latest ecological developments and the use of ICT as a learning resource. For example, web-based reference and use of LMS for asynchronous enrichment. The case-based learning method is expected to be able to change the mindset of students to be wise about the survival of organisms on this earth.

4. Conclusion

The DeCoRe methodology helped deconstruct, reconstruct, and construct the ecology course. Prior to revision, the ecology course had not explicitly shown the sustainable development goals. To do so, the ecology course had to be reconstructed. Not only to implement the SDGs but also the four dimensions of sustainability justice, six learning pillars, and 10Cs. Throughout the process, several challenges were faced, especially during the implementation of the reconstructed ecology course accompanied by assessments using the DREAM methodology.

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Appendix 1. The Module of Ecology Course

Week 1: Course contract and introduction and the principal of ecology

1. Lecturer explains about the course contract and plan in one semester
2. Students read the article entitle “Historical ecology: past, present and future” at <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5424069/>
3. Lecturer gives an explanation the principal of ecology and reviews the article above
4. Discussion
5. Lecturer divided students into 10 groups (3 – 4 students for each group) for student presentation in the end of this semester (module 5: Applied Ecology, week 12 – 14). The topic can be listed below:
 - Group 1: Migration
 - Group 2: Over population
 - Group 3: Biodiversity
 - Group 4: Ecosystems and endangered species
 - Group 5: Land management and urban sprawl
 - Group 6: Deforestation

- Group 7: Climate change
- Group 8: Water scarcity and water pollution
- Group 9: Pollution
- Group 10: Public health

Week 2: Biotic factors

1. Lecturer explains the kind of biotic factors and how biotic factors affect ecosystem
2. Case study learning by watching a video documentary: “Wildest Islands of Indonesia – Series 1 at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u5di4kilYLO>
3. Discussion among the class participants for free open reflection
4. Lecture review and conclusion
5. Homework for next week: students read an article “How you can help conserve Indonesia’s endangered species” at <https://www.thejakartapost.com/life/2018/12/01/how-you-can-help-conserve-indonesias-endangered-species.html>.

Week 3: Abiotic factors

1. Lecturer explains the kind of abiotic factors and how abiotic factors affect ecosystem
2. Case study learning by watching a video documentary: “Wildest Islands of Indonesia – Series 1 – Episode 3 at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=30edfCD2Vhw>
3. Discussion the homework and the video reflection and applying the case on common case surrounding the students
4. Lecture review and conclusion
5. Homework : reading a scientific article related to species richness for preparing next week lesson at <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/species-richness>

Week 4: Community structure

1. Lecturer ask some basic question to students:
 - a. What is community structure?
 - b. How do we measure community structure?
 - c. What factor shapes community structure?
2. Lecturer gives a detail explanation about:
 - a. A community's structure can be described by its **species richness**, which is the number of species present, and **species diversity**, which is a measure of both species richness and species evenness (relative numbers).
 - b. Some important factors that influence community structure: climate patterns, geography, heterogeneity, frequency of disturbances or disruptive events.
3. Discuss the community-based case in Indonesia from this article: “Effects of habitat change and geographical variation on the bird communities of two Indonesian islands”
4. Lecture conclusion
5. Homework: student watch video:
 - a. Ecology-community dynamics at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hCdSJSJHNX-8>

- b. Orangutans fall victim as forest fires burn in Indonesia at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sak0oYoUrJo>

Week 5: Community dynamics

1. Lecturer ask student representatives to tell the content (homework) of:
 - a. Video 1: Ecology-community dynamics
 - b. Video 2: Orangutans fall victim as forest fires burn in Indonesia
2. Lecturer leads the discussion the content of the video and gives an explanation the description of community dynamics, giving the students the floor to express their ideas and thoughts exploring the subject matter
3. Discuss the community dynamics-based case in Indonesia from this scientific article “Post fire succession in Tegal Panjang Grassland, Mount Papandayan, West Java, Indonesia” at <https://biodiversitas.mipa.uns.ac.id/D/D1803/D180347.pdf>
4. Lecturer concludes the material and gives a review
5. Homework: each student reads an scientific article “Food Web: Concept and Applications” at <https://www.nature.com/scitable/knowledge/library/food-web-concept-and-applications-84077181/>

Week 6: Energy flow

1. Online Learning Activities: Videos and simulations emphasize the complex relationships among species in trophic cascades: Ecosystem Ecology: Links in the Chain - Crash Course Ecology at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v6ubvEJ3KGM>
2. Individual task: draw and describe a food web
3. Collect the individual task via online classroom
4. Lecturer explanations: food chains, food webs and energy pyramid
5. Discussion

Week 7: Biogeochemical cycle: (Carbon and Nitrogen cycle)

1. Working in groups (3 – 4 students)
2. Lecturer gives carbon and nitrogen cycle puzzle for each group to be arranged as a cycle
3. After each group finish doing number 2, they must discuss and present in front of the class
4. Lecturer appoints representative groups to present
5. Watch video:
 - a. The Global Carbon Cycle: Crash Course Chemistry at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aLuSi_6O18M
 - b. What is Nitroge Cycle: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-nrIYhKSyvk>
6. Discussion and lecture review

Week 8: Biogeochemical cycle: (Phosphorus and Sulfur cycle)

1. Working in groups (3 – 4 students)

2. Lecturer gives phosphorus and sulfur cycle puzzle for each group to be arranged as a cycle
3. After each group finish doing number 2, they must discuss and present in front of the class
4. Lecturer appoints representative groups to present
5. Watch video:
 - a. The Phosphorus Cycle:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c5KqwhX1dvk>
 - b. Sulfur Cycle:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5AZZwBNCYOo>
6. Discussion and lecture review

Week 9: Habitat

1. Lecturer gives some question listed below:
 - a. What is habitat?
 - b. What is a niche? What factors define a niche? How is it different from a habitat?
 - c. Please describe the different habitats in your ecosystem!
2. Lecture explanation: habitat and niche
3. Student discussion: case-based study in Indonesia: a global biodiversity hotspot in Indonesia related to their habitat at www.arcgis.com
4. Lecture review
5. Announcement and explanation: the role of group presentation for student activities in week 12 - 14

Week 10: Interaction among organisms

1. Lecture explanation:
 - a. Competition
 - b. Predation
 - c. Herbivory
 - d. Symbiosis
 - e. The correlation between species interaction and evolution
2. Student discussion: research-based study
 - a. **Dominance of the suppressed: Power-law size structure in tropical forests.**
 - b. The interaction between predation and competition: A review and synthesis
3. Lecture explanation and confirmation
4. Mini quiz
5. Students who will bring presentations next week, collect their cited articles and presentation file to be reviewed by lecturer

Week 12: Student presentations (Group 1 – 4)

1. Students presentation:
 - Group 1: Migration
 - Group 2: Over population
 - Group 3: Biodiversity
 - Group 4: Ecosystems and endangered species
2. Lecturer leads the discussion, giving the students the floor to express their ideas and thoughts exploring the subject matter
3. Lecture review and conclusion
4. Mini quiz

Students who will bring presentations next week, collect their cited articles and presentation file to be reviewed by lecturer

Week 13: Student presentations (Group 5 – 8)

1. Students presentation:
 - Group 5: Land management and urban sprawl
 - Group 6: Deforestation
 - Group 7: Climate change
 - Group 8: Water scarcity and water pollution
2. Lecturer leads the discussion, giving the students the floor to express their ideas and thoughts exploring the subject matter
3. Lecture review and conclusion
4. Mini quiz

Students who will bring presentations next week, collect their cited articles and presentation file to be reviewed by lecturer

Week 14: Student presentations (Group 9 – 10)

1. Students presentation:
 - Group 9: Waste Disposal and Pollution
 - Group 10: Public health
2. Lecturer leads the discussion, giving the students the floor to express their ideas and thoughts exploring the subject matter
3. Lecture review and conclusion
4. Mini quiz

Lecturer delivers the general topics in week 1 – 14 to prepare the student final evaluation

Supporting SDGs learning through Participatory Video in Yogyakarta's Primary and Secondary Schools: Best Practices from ICTeEFS In-service Teacher Training

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Abstract

Spreading global idea on suitability and achieving SDGs is better suited to be introduced into education, especially on level of primary and secondary school. Online video is one of tools for distance learning for underserved students. The access to online education has steadily increased in recent years especially during COVID-19 pandemic. The process of creating participatory videos included a number of procedures, start with planning, production, and then utilization/dissemination. The participants of UGM's ICTeEFS in-service teacher training were assigned to develop two types of participatory video: one of which is a learning video demonstrating how they incorporated ESD and SDGs into their respective fields of study participatory video (PV-1) and the other one is video "Gethok Tular" as part of peer-to-peer dissemination (PV-2). Determination the quality of PV-1 can be done based on the types of the videos, which are: Videos that only an slide show of participants learning material slides without any context or story given; the other one is a narrated the slides, with addition of context/ story given. Some participants also submitted a video of their class, hence we included those to this group; and the last one is the best videos which are more insightful, the material are infused with ESD/SDGs and the videos were well planned and executed. Participatory video is a useful tool for promoting global concepts like the SDGs and ESD. ICTeEFS in-service teacher training at UGM taught us that investing in future classes by making video participatory is a good idea. The PV materials could be used more than once by teachers in their classes. Uploading PV to school or teacher social media accounts is a good method to get the message out to a wider audience.

Keywords: Participatory Video, Learning material, ICTeEFS, SDGs, ESD

1. Introduction

Educational for Sustainable Development (ESD) is a way to spread the global sustainable idea through education (Little and Green, 2009; Biasutti and Frate 2017; Biasutti et al 2018; UNESCO, 2007). These ideas should be a normative idea of all human generations in order to achieve sustainable live on earth. The concept of sustainable development has evolved from traditional agendas including social inclusion, economic growth and environmental protection to centered around five key elements: people, planet, prosperity, peace and partnership (Brown and Rasmussen, 2019; United Nations, 2015; Nassar, 2017). Seventeen UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in line with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development are "urgent calls for action by all countries, both developing and developed, in the global partnership". This call to action is peace and prosperity for all peoples and the planet, now and in the future. The goals focus on improving inequalities in health, education and the economy, with a primary focus on tackling climate change and protecting the oceans.

Spreading global idea on suitability and achieving SDGs is better suited to be introduced into education, especially on level of primary and secondary school. Hence, our approach to encouraged the participants of in-service teacher training

is in line method to spread of sustainability awareness and SDGs

A rich and effective medium utilized in online learning is video. It has the ability to provide information in an engaging and consistent manner. A potent learning system with an educational video component has been created as a result of recent advancements in multimedia technology and communication. Students can now engage with instructional videos thanks to the development of non-linear interactive digital video technologies. As a result, learning effectiveness may rise due to increased learner engagement. Random access to video footage serves as the primary interactive video's "media characteristic".

Online video is one of tools for distance learning for underserved students. The access to online education has steadily increased in recent years as well as the enrolments in online courses has steadily increased since 2016 (Seaman, Allen, & Seaman, 2018). The rapid growth of online education has resulted in increasing interest in research on learning with instructional video (Poquet, Lim, Mirriahi, & Dawson, 2018). In online courses, especially massive open online courses (MOOCs), video is often the primary method for delivering instruction (Ou et al., 2019; Hansch et al., 2015; Hollands & Tirthali, 2014; Means, et al., 2009).

Therefore, instructional video plays a significant role in online learning experiences and also enrich offline learning.

2. Method

The process of creating participatory videos included a number of procedures, start with planning, production, and then utilization. The ICTeEFS in service teacher training program at UGM includes the PV development developed by Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis (2023). It was agreed that each participant can create their own participation video due to the diverse range of courses the participants had in mind as well as the variances in school levels. This choice was made to ensure that each video would be appropriate for each participant's course.

Two hundreds and ten teachers, 72% of whom are women and 28% of whom are men, were enrolled in UGM's ICTeEFS service teacher training program that took place from November 2021 to January 2022. Special Region of Yogyakarta, is province with area of 3,186 km², has 3.689 million population with 3042 schools from primary to secondary level (BAPEDA DIY, 2020). Even though not all schools in Special Region of Yogyakarta sent representatives for the in-service teacher training program, these participants were a representative from schools in this province. Some of the schools that sent their delegations are located in urban area, while many of them are in remote area and far from the city (Fig.1).

Fig 1. The approximate location of schools which sent the delegates for 2021 ICTeEFS in-service teacher training program in UGM

There are 149 completed participatory videos that have been submitted out of the total number of participants. The PV, which covers the elementary, junior high, and high school (either regular high school or vocational high school) levels, was submitted by participants from 104 schools (Fig. 2). The ICTeEFS in service teacher training participants are instructing 33 notable courses (Fig. 3).

The participants of UGM's ICTeEFS in-service teacher training were asked to develop two types of participatory video, one of which is course related participatory video (PV-1) and the other one is video "Gethok Tular" as part of training dissemination (PV-2). The words "Gethok Tular" is

originated from Javanese, which mean "dissemination" or "spread the words". PV-1 should prioritize the use of ICT and be a video delivery/instructional of educational materials infused with ESD and SDGs. PV-2, on the other hand, is a video for sharing information with colleagues regarding training on "Integrating the Concept of Sustainable Development Education in Learning in Schools Using Information and Communication Technology (ICT)".

The maximum video duration that was required for PV-1 was 20 minutes, whereas the maximum video length for PV-2 was 5 minutes. Participants might upload a video link or a video file (around 700MB/video) for this assignment. Additionally, participants were required to submit screenshots or photographs as proof that their recordings had been shared with classes or co-workers either directly (during in-person meetings) or indirectly through group chats or YouTube.

Fig. 2. Number of PV from UGM's ICTeEFS in service teacher training participant and their respective school of origin.

Although each ICTeEFS participants has develop their respective PV on their own style, there are a pattern of their PV development. The following were the development of course-related PV (PV-1). The participants will first determine which course and which particular chapter their video would cover. Afterwards, participant developed the participatory video and lastly, they need to post these videos in their own social media platform of their choice as well as utilized it for their class. Each participant developed a PV demonstrating how they incorporated ESD and SDGs into their respective fields of study.

Fig. 3. Courses that being taught by the participants of UGM's ICTeEFS in service teacher training and the percentages of number of the participant that taught the courses.

The second video is "Gethok tular" (PV-2). This video is more straight forward in the making. The participants were asked to be a trainer for the colleague and spread the idea of infusion SDGs and ESD as well as the use of ICT in education. The video could be a video of the teachers meeting, where the participants conveyed about the training program or a video where they spread the idea of SDGs and ESD and the usage of ICT in learning.

The development of PV-1 and PV-2 were begun with briefing during the training, then the participant was given 30 days to develop their ideas. Afterward, the participants were invited to focus discussion and given times for consultation. The final videos were submitted on the 3rd month after the briefing and become ones of requirements for obtaining the training certificates of completion.

3. Result

There are 3 different level of schools that sent their delegates to participate in UGM's ICTeEFS in-service teacher training 2021 (Fig. 2). Since the mandatory schooling in Indonesia is 9 years, the primary school consist of elementary (6 years of studies) and junior high school (3 years of studies). Meanwhile, the secondary school consist of senior high schools. There are two different types of high school, which are regular high school and vocational ones. These two types of school have quite distinct learning environments. While the vocational ones will prepare students to enter the workforce immediately, the regular high schools will focus more on preparing students for the next level of education (college).

A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Asal Sekolah	Video -1	Tautan Video -1	Bukti berupa Screenshot Video -2			
SMA Perak-Yogyakarta	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://youtu.be/725K733Qo	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SMA Negeri 7 Yogyakarta	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://www.powtoon.com/ba2z9P4t4b1	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SMA Negeri 11 Yogyakarta	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SMK Mar'eer Semarang	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://youtu.be/3P9W9X0G45	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SMA Stella Duce 2 Yogyakarta	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://youtu.be/Fl_KuF_C0a3eE	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SMA Negeri 1 Bambanglipuro	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://youtu.be/25b2C7789d92	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SMAN 1 Bambanglipuro	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://youtu.be/25b2C7789d92	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SMAN 1 Dingo	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SD Negeri Trusmi	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://youtu.be/CVW9a3C7yC8	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SMKN 6 Yogyakarta	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SMP NEGERI 9 YOGYAKARTA	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SMAN' Abu Bakar Boarding School Kudu	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
SMP PERAK YOGYAKARTA	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk	https://youtu.be/311FNUK0sp	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			
		https://youtu.be/311FNUK0sp	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GZaB0R_u4fuQw_7usp/drivesdk			

Fig. 4. eForm for VPs submission from the participant of UGM's ICTeEFS in-service teacher training 2021

UGM's ICTeEFS in-service teacher training 2021 were designed to have 87 hours of training. PV is one of the outcomes that were required for the completion of the training. About 121 out of the 210 participants were able to submit their VP assignments completely. The remaining of the participant were either submit low quality of PV, or only submit one of PV or did not submit at all. The submissions of PVs were done through e-form that was posted in training

google classroom. There were 159 entries of submission (Fig 4.). This means that 51 participants were failed to submit their PVs. All the PV submission must be accompanied with proof of disseminations, either through class group chat, online meeting or any social media platforms (Fig 5.).

Fig. 5. Sample of PV-1 proof of dissemination, either through class group chat, online meeting or any social media platforms.

The length of PV-1s were varies from short ones (less than 5 minutes) into very long videos (> 30 minutes) (Fig. 6). In term of number of SDGs that being infused in PV-1, we can confidently report that all seventeen goals were covers by all PV-1s (Fig. 7). Top three issues that were covered by PV-1 are: SDG #4 Quality Education (11%), SDG #3 Good Health and Well-Being (10%), SDG #5 Gender Equality (9%) and SDG #8 Decent Work and Economic Growth (9%). One PVs would support more than one goal of SDGs.

Fig. 6. The percentage of PV-1s based on the duration of the videos. The VP-1 are grouped into very short videos (less than 5 min), short (5-10 min), medium (11-20 min), long (20-30 min) and a very long one (>30 min).

The type of videos in VP-1 were varies. This depends on the style that each participant comfortable to develop (Fig. 8). We can determine the quality of PV-1 based on the types of the videos, which are: Group 1. The video only an slide show of participants slides without any context or story

given (9%); Group2. (12%) Narrated the slides, with addition of context/ story given. Some participants also submitted a video of their class, hence we included those to this group; and the last one is Group 3 (79%) which are more insightful, the material are infused with ESD/SDGs and the videos were well planned and executed.

Fig. 7. The percentage of each of SDGs covered by PV-1s.

Fig. 8. Photograph of PV-1.sample. There many styles of learning videos that being submitted for UGM's ICTeEFS in-service teacher training 2021

"Sharing is caring" is the spirit of UGM's ICTeEFS in-service teacher training 2021. Participants were encouraged to share what they had learned to their colleague. The participants might reach to his/her peers through several way, i.e.: meeting in person or online which either school teachers' meeting or lesson-based teachers' association meeting, and through social media platform (WhatsApp Group, YouTube). The development PV-2 is part of dissemination the idea of infusing ESD and SDGs and employment of ICT into learning.

Seventy five percent of PV-2 consisted of videos showing a meeting with a colleague, with the remaining videos serving to disseminate the ICTeEFS concept. A total of 2305 people were reached by the PV-2 "Gethok Tular" distribution (Fig. 9). Only PV-2 that provided convincing evidence of dissemination meeting and obtained in May 2022 was used to determine this value.

Fig. 9. Number of people outreach for dissemination phase of UGM's ICTeEFS in-service teacher training 2021. All participants in this graph already gave their permission that their names to be published.

4. Discussion

The of UGM's ICTeEFS in-service teacher training 2021 were carried out in the height of pandemic COVID-19. The training itself were designed to incorporated online and offline meeting as well as synchronous and asynchronous methods. This was done to ensure that every participant will embody the idea of infusing ESD and SDGs into their teaching materials and employ ICT as part of learning tools. The training on employment of ICT for learning can not be more in right time, since the pandemic changes the way of face-to-face learning to distance learning.

As of now, the learning in Yogyakarta is return to full offline in the wake of COVID-19 subside. However, PV as learning tools surely can still be utilize as supplement of offline learning. The most suitable learning video that could be used in offline learning were the ones that have short to medium length of times (5-30 minutes). Video with short-medium lengths were more suitable to the Indonesia's study timeframe study unit which are 35 minutes for elementary school, 40 minutes for junior high school, and 45 minutes for senior high school and vocational high school. The allocated amount of time/learning unit in Indonesia is regulated by Decree from Minister Educations, Culture, Research, and Technology no 16 about Standardized Process of Education for Kindergarten, Pre-School, Elementary School, Junior High School, Regular High School, Vocational High School,

and Equivalent level of schooling (MENDIKBUDRISTEK, 2022).

The length of video also affects the effectiveness of learning material comprehension by students. Our students lived in environment with a lot of distractions, hence they have less attention time span. Short video is more interesting for the students rather the longer ones.

The type of videos that more appealing to the audience is the one which has context or story that relate and engage to their day-to-day life. Thus, it is advisable for the teacher to build ones that has story to it and clearly highlight the SDGs that they support. That kind of improvement will surely make the PV more attractive for the students, relevant to the learning material, and can be used in learning repeatedly.

Most of the PV-1 that submitted highlight more than one SDGs in it. The SDGs that infused were vary, depend on the learning material and learning outcome that were intended for that material. Overall, all SDGs were covered in all participant videos. SDG number 4 Quality Education and number 3 Good Health and Well-Being have the highest coverage. This was caused by the influence of current pandemic situation.

The participants were enthusiastic to submit dissemination video (PV-2). This is an opportunity for them to introduce the core idea of ICTeEFS to their fellow teachers who haven't had the opportunity to join training program themselves. The impact of PV-2 can be determined by the number of teachers outreached. Based on data that we gathered on May 2022, the UGM's ICTeEFS in-service teacher training 2021 participants has reached a very astounding number (2305) of people. This number was only calculated from 41 participants out of 121 participants who submitted PV-2. From this data we can confidently claim that the core idea of infusion of ESD and SDGs as well as utilization of ICT on learning has spread widely in Yogyakarta Province.

5. Conclusion

Participatory video is a useful tool for promoting global concepts like the SDGs and ESD. ICTeEFS in-service teacher training at UGM taught us that investing in future classes by making video participatory is a good idea. The PV materials could be used more than once by teachers in their classes. Uploading PV to school or teacher social media accounts is a good method to get the message out to a wider audience. However, direct (person to person) dissemination is deemed more successful at spreading ICT use and integrating ESD and SDGs into education.

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SESSION D

Reviewing Biology Teaching Methods Syllabus Using DeCoRe+ Methodology: Embedding SDGs via ICT as Enabler

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to review course syllabus for Biology Teaching Methods to integrate SDGs concepts via ICT. In addition, four Biology Teaching Methods modules have been developed. The methodology was divided into two phases: Phase I, by using Capacity Building Model, all teacher educators have been trained for 4 weeks to review the syllabus. At the beginning, they did the curriculum mapping since USM already embedded sustainability concepts in its courses. In phase II, teacher educators developed the modules using DeCoRe+ methodology by infusing 10Cs, six learning pillars and four dimensions of sustainable justice. A total of 54 pre-service teachers involved in this study. All of them were compulsory to take this course since they were prospective biology teacher. We implemented these four modules for 14 weeks (one semester). By using DREAM methodology, they need to develop concept maps about SDGs and its description and answer questionnaire. The results showed that majority of our students have a very good, and good understanding of SDGs. Their concept maps have knowledge representation, interconnectivity, meaningfulness, complexity, contextuality and transformational characteristics. For the questionnaire, most pre-service teachers have positive feelings about SDGs, good knowledge on SDGs, likely to use ICT and positive actions on sustainability and have control on their action. These findings will be a good indicator that our students could disseminate the knowledge and skills about SDGs and could be the agent of change in the future in forming sustainable society.

Keywords: (Biology Teaching Methods, sustainable concepts, pre-service teacher, DeCoRe+, concept map)

1. Introduction

Earth's population and resources move in opposite directions. The population is expected to reach 8.7 billion in 2030 compared to 7.7 billion currently (United Nation [UN] World Population Data, 2019). Population growth and unsustainable use of resources cause an increase in carbon dioxide and result in global warming. Carbon dioxide gas release statistics for 2019 showed that Malaysia was in the ranks of 39th, with an increasing pattern since 2009 (Friedlingstein, O'Sullivan, & Jones, 2020). Even after 5 years Malaysia declared efforts to lower carbon emissions and sustainable development. This movement has not yet taken place comprehensively and aggressively (Wan Izatul Asma, 2020; Siti Diana, Afzan, Nadia, Abdul Wafi, & Nurfadilah, 2020). The sources of these problems are human activities because their awareness and commitment towards environment are low. Therefore, the best solution to educate people and young generations is through education.

With education, schools will provide students with the information they need for the future. The knowledge and skills that they get from the educational programs helps them to make proper decisions about their lives and societies in the future because the students of today are the leaders of the future. They need to be empowered as a leader in Sustainable Development Goals. Thus, teachers play an important role as agent of change in disseminating knowledge and skills about SDGs to students for creating a future sustainable society. For that reason, it is necessary for the higher education institution such as school of education to review their courses in producing a new generation of teachers that are more aware and understand about SDG.

The ICTeEfs project is a project that would help teacher educators to review their courses on how to integrate ICT and ESD concepts, 10Cs, six learning pillars for sustainable development and four dimensions of sustainable justice (Makrakis, 2017). This project was funded by EU. Thus, by involving in this project will give a lot of benefits for these preservice teachers in experiencing and exploring on how sustainability can be embedded in their teaching. This situation will lead them to be sustainable teacher leaders in their future schools.

One of the courses that is closely related to sustainability is biology education. Jeronen, et.al. (2019), stated that biology education is related to sustainable education. As mentioned by Yudha and Ali (2019), instructor should teach and discuss about biology in students' daily life especially social issue that can highlight the sustainable development goals. For example, when we discuss about nutrition, it can be related to SDG 3, healthy lifestyle. Thus, to ensure preservice teachers know and master about SDGs concepts, Biology Teaching Methods is the best choice.

1.2 Biology Teaching Methods

Biology Teaching Methods (PGT 315E) is the core course for students who want to be biology teachers. This course aims at building the students' inner qualities for the role of responsible and effective teacher. Priority is on the mastery of 'content-pedagogy' and effective teaching plan based on the current teaching and learning theory. Proficiency of ICT usage is upgraded and this course further stresses on the importance of teaching for understanding.

Focus is put on practical work in small groups as to train scientific skills, appreciate and practice positive attitudes and good values which will be evident through various products such as digital teaching materials, portfolios and team-teaching experiences. Critical and creative thinking as well as sustainability of our local flora and fauna is embedded through the biodiversity project appropriate for the secondary school level. Issues and real classroom challenges will be discussed beside professional development.

With this course, students will be exposed up-to-date biology teaching theories and strategies to enable students to implement biology teaching based on lesson plans provided and collaborate in producing ideas/products using concepts and knowledge of sustainable development in biology. The learning outcome for this course are:

- Elaborate the theory and strategy of teaching biology (CO1)
- Implement biology teaching based on the proposed innovative lesson plans (CO2)
- Integrate appropriate SDG goals in preparing a project on biodiversity with emphasis on SDG 13 (Climate Action) and SDG 15 (Life on Land) (CO3)

To register this course, students need to pass at least grade 'C' in General Science Teaching Methods (PPG 210E).

The reason for choosing this course is it is a core or compulsory course for preservice biology teacher. Thus, every preservice biology teacher in School of Education Studies, USM need to take this course. In this course, they will learn how to design biology instruction, Teaching strategies & integration of ICT in biology Part 1 and 2: Digital Game Based Learning in biology, Biology in Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) / Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Teaching biology through experiential learning and Environmental based teaching and learning, etc. There were about 54 students registered in this course for semester 2 2020/2021 and 2021/2022. The number of students taking this course was quite low compared to General Science Teaching Methods since they need to choose their major and minor. For example, one student may choose Biology as a major and Chemistry as a minor, so s/he need to register Biology Teaching Methods and Chemistry Teaching Methods.

1.3 The assessment of the course

For the assessment, it consisted of two parts:

- a. Final examination - 50% (essay questions)
- b. Coursework - 50%.

The 50% consisted of:

- i. Simulated teachings (ST – 30%) are microteachings where students will apply teaching theories and skills into short

teaching demonstrations. These ST will be carried out during other face to face class as scheduled. Students will need to choose a biology topic from the list given and plan lessons and build teaching aids to perform an instruction that should illustrate effective teaching practices. During the other face to face class, the appointed student shall play the role of a teacher while the rest of the class cooperate as students in a normal classroom. The use of ICT/digital tools is compulsory to aid in teaching. In groups of three students from the same tutorial group: Each week, students are to 'hold a class' and they are expected to furnish the lecturer with a complete set of lesson plan for double period, intended exercises and a concept map of the day's lesson at least a day before the class commences.

After each simulated teaching session, each student needs to write the reflection of the about the teaching and submit it. Discussion on these reflections should be completed two days before the next simulated teaching session. The purpose of this assignment is to help students evaluate the teaching effectiveness of themselves and their peers. With this, it is a hope that students will develop their teaching skills. The weightage of this assignment as follows:

- Lesson plan – 10%
- Teaching - 10%
- Reflection – 10 %

Project 2 (20%)

In groups of three/ four students, they need to:

1. Identify two STEM activities that is suitable for any topic in KSSM Biology (curriculum) and relate it with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). They also need to do a concept map on selected SDG.
2. Collect information on that activity (Use concept map to summarize the info)
3. Write a lesson plan on how to teach students about that STEM activities.
4. Present your project through e-book/ e-module Information on that SDG 13 and SDG 15.

1.4 What has been change

During the re-evaluating the course, we realize that the course contents need to be updated since in 2018, Malaysian education system has implemented a new syllabus for secondary schools. In this new curriculum, there is a Cross Curricular Elements as a set of value-added elements. The purpose of this element is to strengthen the human capital skills and competency besides preparing students for the challenges of the present and the future. The two elements that related to sustainability are Environmental Sustainability Awareness which developing awareness, nurturing the love and care for the environment through teaching and learning, promoting knowledge and awareness on the importance of the environmental ethics and sustainability for students to appreciate. While Global Sustainability will develop sustainable thinking (responsive towards the environment, being responsible, creative and

resourceful) with the concept of living within global resources without damaging its present or future environment and prepare students to face challenges on complex interconnected global issues. Thus, every teacher needs to be able to teach this element directly and indirectly in related subjects (CDC, 2018).

Because of this, we changed our Course Learning Outcomes (CLOs). With new CLOs, the focus not only on students' final exam results (Cognitive Domain), but also on other learning outcomes (Psychomotor & Affective Domains). We also added several new topics to update our course content such as Biology in Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) / Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and Teaching biology through experiential learning and Environmental based teaching and learning. With these new topics, it is a hope that our pre-service teachers will have more knowledge and skills in sustainability. In this course the content of SDGs were more detail compared to General Science Teaching Methods, PPG 210E.

We also make changes on the assignments in which it more focused on the project. In addition, we included one ICT topic in this course: Part I: Teaching strategies & integration of ICT in biology and Part 2: Digital Learning in biology. It referred to ICT as enabler. Thus, our students will be exposed to variety types of apps/ or software and know how to apply these apps in their teaching.

We were also be able to implement 21st century learning framework. Our students will be active learners since the purpose of 21st century is transition from the industrial age to knowledge age (Erdem, et.al. 2019). Thus, our pre-service teachers have been trained with the 21st century skills.

We make certain changes to make sure that the content and approach of this course are up-to-date and relevant for our prospective biology teachers. However, the percentage of the changes was only 25% since in USM, we are not allowed to change the course syllabus more than 30%. If there is more than 30%, it would need more time for approval because it required approval from the school board and university senate. The approval process will take at least one year.

2. Methodology

In this project consisted of two phases. Phase I: we trained selected teacher educators (course coordinator) on ICTeEfS concepts while for phase II: developing the ICTeEfS module using DeCoRe+ methodology developed by Makrakis (2017).

In phase I, a Capacity Building Model (2006) proposed by Makrakis has been used. This model is a six-stages capacity building model for training academic staff to embed

sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006). Refer to Figure 1.

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model (Makrakis, 2006)

We followed all the six stages and the process of reviewing the course syllabus as follows. At the beginning, we need to do the curriculum mapping since this course already integrated sustainability concept. The purpose of doing this was to make sure no overlapping sustainability concepts. We have four workshops on how to infuse ESD enabled by ICT in the university's existing curriculum, research, and community engagement. The training also focused on disseminating knowledge about CARE learning design. Besides, SDGs, 10Cs, six learning pillars, four dimensions of sustainable justice and variety types of apps also have been introduced. Because of covid-19 pandemic, we conducted our training via online. The online training was interactive training, we have a lot of discussion on how to integrate 10Cs, six learning pillars, four dimensions of sustainable justice. They raised a lot of questions since these concepts were quite new to them. We also distributed questionnaire to assess teacher educators' understanding about the training's content. After attending four workshops, the result showed that our teacher educators have a good understanding on how to develop ICTeEfS curriculum and ready as trainers in their faculty. They have enough knowledge and skills on ICTeEfS.

In phase II, for course revision, we used DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) to review the course syllabus. This methodology was proposed by Makrakis (2017). According to him, the DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. DeCoRe+ consisted the following processes.

1. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
2. **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
3. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
4. **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.

5. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. **Finalising:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

By using all steps in the DeCoRe+, new elements such as 10Cs, six learning pillars for sustainable development and four dimensions of sustainable justice were added in this course syllabus. For the quality assurance, we evaluated the reviewed course syllabus internally by using our own rubric. Each members of the project need to evaluate the course syllabus. It is a peer-reviewed evaluation. After getting feedback, we did certain amendments. Then, we have external evaluator from other university in Malaysia and for USM, we chose UTM team as our external evaluator to review our course syllabus since USM and UTM has the same characteristic which producing prospective teachers. Finally, we have another external evaluator that was from Frederick University. With the feedbacks, we did all the amendments in order to have the final draft of DeCoRe+ document. Thus, our new course syllabus for this course has three modules:

- Module 1: Elaborate the theory and strategy of teaching biology
- Module 2: Implement biology teaching based on the proposed innovative lesson plans
- Module 3: Integrate appropriate SDGs in preparing a project on biodiversity with emphasis on SDG 13 (Climate Change) and SDG 15 (Life on Land)

Then, we implemented these modules to our students using DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2023;2022) for 14 weeks (one semester). These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process which aims not only assess a course but more importantly to make whatever changes to improve it (Makrakis, 2023). Through the parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student guided by the course instructor creates a portfolio that he/she has to give back to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. Refer to figure 2.

Figure 2. The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

For the DREAM methodology, a total of 54 pre-service teachers involved in this study. They were divided into 22 groups voluntarily. We used purposive sampling since these students were compulsory to take this course. The reason was, they were the prospective biology teacher. At the beginning, they need to familiarize with the concept map especially on using words to link the ideas, individually. Then in a group of 4/5 students, they need to develop the concept map on selected SDGs.

Concept Mapping (CM) has been well-known as teaching and learning strategy in the classroom. The nature of CM could be observed as a graphic organizer which illustrated itself using labelled nodes representing ideas with propositions signifying contacts between concepts (Nesbit, & Adesope, 2006). Chiou (2008) indicated that a CM usually as a network structure, to aid learning and understanding. Concept Map enables students to gain a higher level of thinking skills (Novak & Canas, 2006; 2007, makes learning more meaningful and understandable (Novak, 2006; 2013; Simper, Reeve & Kirby, 2016). The use of CM can aid students to advance their abstract thinking skills. Concept Map helps students to understand propositions and concepts more visibly, make formation amid old and new knowledge, and change a cognitive structure in their ideas (Wushishi, Danjuma, & Usman, 2013). It was regarded as a network structure to support the development of knowledge and understanding (Chiou, 2008). Thus, concept map of SDGs will help the instructor evaluate whether students understand about SDGs and its connectedness.

We evaluated their concept maps by using rubrics which has five categories (excellent, very good, good, fair, and failing) and six criteria that has been developed by Makrakis (n.d). The criteria as follows:

- For knowledge representation – refer to the relationships and concepts that are logical and related to the key theme
- Inter-connectivity – refer to the level of understanding and meaning in terms of inter/cross-disciplinarity, connection to the curriculum, and connection with the real-world context.
- Meaningfulness of links – refer to words and the links make are sense and help develop dialogue, deep learning, critical thinking and reflection and inference-making
- Complexity – refer to the concept map allow a shared meaning to emerge; generates many complex patterns and results; provides high-level representations of evolving thinking; makes sense of complex problems requiring connecting ideas and eliciting relations between ideas
- Contextuality – refer to the concept map elicits relations between ideas within and across contexts; provides opportunities to contextualize ICTs with Efs and knowledge construction transferable to other contexts.
- Transformational – refer to the concept map encourages learners to raise awareness about the key theme, critical consciousness, generate critical reflection, and empower action.

They also need to answer the questionnaire as part of their assessment. There were 75 items in this questionnaire. It measured about students' feelings about SDGs elements, knowledge about SDGs elements, action on as a future teacher using ICT as tools, SD action of as a citizen, and true statement about their self-action.

3. Finding and Discussion

The findings for this study divided into 2 parts: Part A for concept mapping and Part B for the questionnaire.

3.1 Part A: Concept Mapping

A total of 22 groups consisted 54 students submitted the SDGs concept map. For SDGs choice, the findings showed that two groups chose SDG 1 and SDG 3, four groups chose SDG 4, and one group chose SDG 2, 5 up to SDG 17. It can be concluded that majority of the students in this course like to choose SDG 4 – Quality Education since these students were prospective teachers who majoring in science education.

Based on DREAM, students need to do a concept map of SDGs since each of SDGs are connected to each other. Thus, the understanding of the SDGs concepts and its interconnectivity is important especially for young future teachers since they will disseminate the SDGs concepts for future generation. There were 5 types of SDGs understanding such as Knowledge Representation, interconnectivity, meaningfulness of links, complexity, contextuality and transformational.

The overall findings showed that majority of the groups have good understanding on SDGs. Refer to table 1:

Table 1 Overall result for concept mapping

Level	Frequency
Fail	2
Fair	3
Good	10
Very Good	7
Total	22

As shown in table 1, seven groups had very good, ten groups had good understanding of SDGs, three groups had fair understanding and two groups were failed.

For knowledge representation of SDG, we observed the relationships and concepts that are logical and related to the key theme. The theme that they highlighted as follows: how to solve the global issue to related SDGs, during covid-19 pandemic, how to achieve the targets on related SDGs and the importance of the selected SDGs.

Table 2 Knowledge representation

Level	Frequency
Fair	3
Good	2
Very Good	9
Excellent	8
Total	22

As refer to table 2, the findings showed that eight groups were in excellent level in which the relationships and concepts in the map are logical and clearly relate to the key theme on multiple levels and nine groups were in very good level in which almost all relationships and concepts in the map are logical and clearly relate to the key theme on multiple levels. Two groups were in good level in which most of the relationships and concepts in the map are logical and clearly relate to the key theme on multiple levels and three groups were in fail level in which very few relationships and concepts are logical and clearly relate to the key theme.

For the interconnectivity, it is referred to the level of understanding and meaning in terms of inter/cross-disciplinarity, connection to the curriculum, and connection with the real-world context. In this criterion, most of our students mentioned the connection on the curriculum such as about how education related to SDGs and how they could implement in the classroom. They also mentioned about real-world context when they showed the global data on related SDGs. For the inter/cross-disciplinary, our students were able to relate it with the policy – the nation needs.

Table 3 Interconnectivity

Level	Frequency
Fair	2
Good	7
Very Good	9
Excellent	4
Total	22

From table 3, findings showed that four groups were in excellent level in which the connections show high level of understanding and meaning, especially in terms of inter/cross-disciplinarity, connection to the curriculum; and connection with the real-world context while nine groups were in very good level in which the connections show very good level of understanding and meaning, especially in terms of inter/cross-disciplinarity, connection to the curriculum; and connection with the real-world context. While seven groups were in good level of understanding and meaning, especially in terms of inter/cross-disciplinarity, connection to the curriculum; and connection with the real-world context and two were in fair level of understanding and meaning, especially in terms of inter/cross-disciplinarity, connection to the curriculum; and connection with the real-world context.

For meaningfulness of links, it referred to words and the links make are sense and help develop dialogue, deep learning, critical thinking and reflection and inference-making. In here, our students showed they mastered on how to use appropriate words in making the relationships between themes.

Table 4 Meaningfulness

Level	Frequency
Fail	2
Fair	1
Good	6
Very Good	9
Excellent	4
Total	22

As shown in table 4, the findings showed that four groups in excellent level when all words and links make sense and help develop dialogue, deep learning, critical thinking and reflection and inference-making. A total of nine groups in very good level when almost all words and links make sense and help develop dialogue, deep learning, critical thinking and reflection and inference-making. Six groups in good level when most words and links make sense and help develop dialogue, deep learning, critical thinking and reflection and inference-making. However, one group in fair level when a number of misconceptions are evident with surface learning and less opportunity for developing dialogue and other skills and two groups in fail level when very few linking words, mostly without meaning and opportunities for developing dialogue and other skills.

For complexity, it referred to the concept map allow a shared meaning to emerge; generates many complex patterns and results; provides high-level representations of evolving thinking; makes sense of complex problems requiring connecting ideas and eliciting relations between ideas. The result showed that our students in this course able to generate complex pattern when they able to relate one concepts to another concepts. It showed that these students understand about SDGs, and the themes that they highlighted.

Table 5 Complexity

Level	Frequency
Fail	2
Fair	1
Good	10
Very Good	3
Excellent	6
Total	22

From table 5, the findings showed that six groups in excellent level in which the concept map allows very high shared meaning to emerge; generates complex patterns and results; provides a very high-level representations of evolving thinking; makes sense of complex problems requiring connecting ideas and eliciting relations between ideas, while three groups in very good level in which the concept map allows a high shared meaning to emerge; generates many complex patterns and results; provides high-level representations of evolving thinking; makes sense of complex problems requiring connecting ideas and eliciting relations between ideas and ten groups in good level in which the concept map allows a good shared meaning to emerge; enough complex patterns and results; provides good-level representations of evolving thinking; makes sense of complex problems requiring connecting ideas and eliciting relations between ideas. However, one group in fair level in which the concept map allows a fair shared meaning to emerge; some complex patterns and results with low level representations of evolving thinking; makes some sense of complex problems requiring connecting ideas and eliciting relations between ideas and two groups in fail level in which the concept map allows limited shared meaning to emerge with very few complex patterns and results; provides low-level representations of evolving thinking and does not makes sense of complexity.

For contextuality, it referred to the concept map that elicits relations between ideas within and across contexts and provides opportunities to contextualize ICTs with EfS and knowledge construction transferable to other contexts. In this course, our students able to show the contextuality. Their concepts map showed that they were able to generate new themes/ ideas in different context such as root problem address, target, policy etc.

Table 6 Contextuality

Level	Frequency
Fail	2
Fair	8
Good	5
Very Good	5
Excellent	2
Total	22

As shown in table 6, findings showed that two groups in excellent level in which their concept map elicits relations between ideas within and across contexts; provides very high opportunities to contextualize ICTs with EfS and knowledge construction transferable to other contexts, five groups in very good level in which their concept map elicits relations between ideas within and across contexts; provides many

opportunities to contextualize ICTs with EfS and knowledge construction transferable to other contexts and five groups in good level in which their concept map elicits good relations between ideas within and across contexts; provides good opportunities to contextualize ICTs with EfS and knowledge construction transferable to other contexts. Nevertheless, eight group in fair level in which their concept map elicits few relations between ideas within and across contexts; provides some opportunities to contextualize ICTs with EfS and knowledge construction transferable to other contexts and two groups in fail level in which their concept map elicits very few relations between ideas within and across contexts; provides very few opportunities to contextualize ICTs with EfS and transferability.

While for transformational, it referred to refer to the concept map encourages learners to raise awareness about the key theme, critical consciousness, generate critical reflection, and empower action. Only few groups showed the transformational criteria. They have knowledge about SDGs but not enough for them to transform the SDGs knowledge.

Table 7 Transformational

Level	Frequency
Fail	2
Fair	8
Good	5
Very Good	5
Excellent	2
Total	22

As table 7, findings showed that three groups in very good level in which their concept map helps to raise awareness about the key theme, critical consciousness, generate critical reflection, and empower action and 14 groups in good level in which their concept map contributes to raise awareness about the key theme, critical consciousness, generate critical reflection, and empower action. Nonetheless, three group in fair level in which their concept map provides a few opportunities to raise awareness about the key theme, critical consciousness, reflection, and empower action and two groups in fail level in which their concept map provides very limited opportunities to raise awareness about the key theme, critical consciousness, reflection and empower action.

As a conclusion, majority of the groups had a good criterion of SDG in terms of their knowledge representation, inter-connectivity, meaningfulness of links, complexity, contextuality and transformational except for two groups. Their concept maps were simple and their understanding about selected SDG were quite low.

3.2 Part B: Questionnaire

For the questionnaire, the result showed that on the item of feelings about element of SDGs, 59.3% students were agreed on the items and about 40.7% students were strongly agreed on the items. For the items on knowledge about element in SDGs, findings showed that 1.9% student had a little knowledge, 33.3% students had enough knowledge, 48.1% students had much knowledge and 16.7% students had very much knowledge about elements in SDGs. For the

items as a future teacher, you are going to teach your students by using ICT as tools, findings showed that 18.5% students were uncertain to use ICT, 51.9% students were likely to use ICT and 29.6% students were very likely to use ICT. While for items on as a citizen, findings showed that 14.8% students were did once, 46.3% students were done twice, 29.6% students sometimes did, and 9.3% students often did the actions. For the items true about self-action in which they have controlled in their action, the finding showed that 1.9% students never did by their own, 3.7% students rarely did, 53.7% students sometimes did, 35.2% students often did, and 5.6% students very often did their own.

4. Conclusion

As a conclusion, after attending this course, most of students showed positive changes on the acquisition of SDGs concepts at different scales and levels. These findings showed that the modules in this course gave them benefit on the understanding of SDGs. They were able to relate SDGs with global issues and know how to solve it. They were able to demonstrate their critical thinking skills when they can relate the selected SDGs with policy and infrastructure. It showed that CM promotes meaningful learning and that has demonstrated potential effects in the learning process (Machado and Carvalho, 2020).

These findings could be a good indicator that our students could disseminate the knowledge and skills about SDGs to students. With the experience that they have in this course, they are ready to be future biology teachers that could affect students on the SDGs knowledge, skills, and practice. It also could benefit them in terms of their daily life practice. Now, our prospective biology teachers could be agents of change not in the classroom and school but also in the society.

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Infusing Sustainability Concepts in the Foundation Course for Preservice Teachers

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Abstract

Education systems, especially Higher Education bear their own responsibility for the sustainability crisis since they are medium whereby, future leaders were nurtured and developed. On this matter, initiative needs to be taken to embed the sustainability concepts in most of the courses offered in the higher education institutions. The focus of this paper is to present the processes, practices, and outcomes for revising one of the foundation courses that need to be registered by all first year, first degree education students in a leading public university in Malaysia. This course is an introductory course whereby students were introduced to important concepts in the educational field. Approximately, 200 students register for this course each semester. For course revision to embed sustainability and 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2017) was applied. The result shows that elements of sustainability are stated clearly in the objective of the course but not the case with elements of 21st century skills. However, the application and the implementation of the 21st century skills are integrated in the teachings of the course indirectly through the usage of ICT and coursework. An element that could be highlighted is globalization and internationalization of education. Measures taken in this course are examples of how the concept of SDGs could be integrated in the syllabus of higher education institutions by means of ICT. Integrating the concepts of SDG on students of higher education institution is hoped to accelerate the spread of awareness on SDGs, which will later turn into practical actions and transformation.

Keywords: Higher education institutions, preservice teachers, 21st century skills, ICT, sustainable development goals.

1. Introduction

Over the last decades, humanity has been facing the impacts of an unsustainable economic development growth driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014). Despite the current initiatives aimed at reversing this unsustainable development process, there is still much to be done. Education systems at all levels, and significantly higher education, bear a significant responsibility for the sustainability crisis we are facing globally. This is mainly because consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions who drive society and the economy, as well as shape an unsustainable consumer culture. Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that “[t]he scopes and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented” (p. 3).

Education should play a critical role for a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is closely aligned with Aristotle’s eudaimonic well-being, as contrasted with the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The quest for “sustainable justice”, a concept developed by Makrakis (2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable

development —environment, society, economy, and culture —is of paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth pointing out that while much has been invested in environmental education in the last decades, it has more reflected in raising positive environmental attitudes, but less concern on environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability have shown that lecturing, as expected, is the most prevalent teaching method. At the same time, role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, are used at much lower rates (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015).

A project entitled Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013; 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of, and capable of acting in transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts for teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary

school levels. Teaching staff are key agents for change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016), as well as in transforming schools into sustainable institutions (Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

As early as 2008, the previous Vice chancellor of USM has highlighted the role of higher education institutions in

promoting SDGs. A sustainable world, humanity, and the future of humankind are among the issues focused on by Universiti Sains Malaysia, as presented by Prof Dzulkifli Abdul Razak (2009). Based on these over-arching principles, USM has been chosen by the Malaysian Ministry of Higher Education to implement the Accelerated Programme for Excellence (APEX) under its auspices. APEX is a fast-track development programme to enable institutions of higher education to be recognised as world-class entities. The programme aims to facilitate the university in being selected for an international level and to motivate and help raise the level of excellence in higher education. Emphasis is given "... to integrate sustainable development into the educational system so that future generations can be nurtured and imbued with the need to embrace ecological protection, conservation of resources and human development based on the virtues of equity, accessibility availability, affordability, appropriateness and in articulating a wholesome meaning of quality."

In line with this, USM has executed a rebranding-cum-advocacy programme that would allow it to deepen and translate its main mission as "a pioneering university, transdisciplinary and research-intensive that empowers future talents and enables the bottom billions to transform their socioeconomic well-being." USM, therefore, incorporated the concept of sustainability to achieve its vision as an APEX university through the theme, "Transforming Higher Education for a Sustainable Tomorrow." As an extension of the steps taken by the university, the School of Educational Studies (SES) then took the initiative to embed sustainability concepts in most of the courses offered in the school, particularly at the undergraduate level.

The ICTeEfS Project

One of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental degradation. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian policymakers must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby securing sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While Asian leaders have committed EfS, alongside their concern for implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS), and on the other hand, they must capitalize on

the potential of such technologies in advancing Education for Sustainability to all in-service subject teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. However,

integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

1. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.
2. Build the capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education to enable them to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers' training program on education for sustainability.
3. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program, enabled by blended learning, that focuses on integrating education for sustainability across school curricula.
4. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
5. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices, and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the School of Educational Studies, USM entitled Teacher, School, and Society. This course, Teacher, School, and Society (PGA103), is one of the foundation courses that all first-year, first-degree students in the School of Educational Studies at Universiti Sains Malaysia are required to register for. This course develops students' understanding of the fundamental and main concepts in the development and sustainability of the Malaysian education system from the perspectives of philosophy, sociology, history, and governmental policies. This course also nurtures students' concern and awareness of living in a plural society, racial integration, innovation in education, and the importance of collaboration with stakeholders, with a particular emphasis on the bottom billion group. Therefore, students are expected to understand the concepts of schooling, the teacher's role, and related issues in education.

The overarching goals of this course are: a) to provide students with knowledge on the foundation of education,

particularly in Malaysia; b) to develop students' critical thinking over educational theories and issues in Malaysia in

Collaborating, communicating, and innovating in preparing charismatic future teachers using ICTs, participatory video, and social networking technologies as tools to help the community by highlighting elements of SDG 4 (Quality Education). Given these goals, a few learning outcomes of this course have been outlined. Those outcomes are as follows:

- i. Discuss the development of the Malaysian Educational System, highlighting SDG 4 (Quality Education).
- ii. Discuss educational reports, strategies, and roles of the Ministry of Education, related agencies, teachers, and various educational institutions highlighting SDG 4 (Quality Education).
- iii. Be able to critically discuss educational theories related to sociology, philosophy, and history regarding education within the Malaysian context, highlighting SDG 4 (Quality Education)
- iv. Be able to critically discuss educational issues relating to sociology, philosophy, and history regarding education within the Malaysian context, highlighting SDG 4 (Quality Education)
- v. Able to plan, design, and implement community engagement projects addressing issues in the students' locality.
- vi. Able to propose innovations to the bottom billion community with advocacy in mind, utilizing participatory YouTube videos on social media.

It is essential to note that this course is an introductory one, where students are introduced to key concepts in the educational field. The aspect of sustainability is explicitly mentioned in the course objective. Approximately 200 students register for this course each semester.

This course is assessed in two parts: Coursework and Examination. Coursework consists of short tests, a presentation on the issue of school and society, and a Project (Community Service). The assessment is authentic because it incorporates various modes of evaluation, including online quizzes and presentations (quantitative criteria) and community project reports (qualitative criteria). Coursework is a formative assessment, not a paper-and-pencil test. The assessment methods primarily relate to real-life situations through the community project report.

Throughout this course, assignments were submitted electronically, whereas lecture notes were accessible through the e-learning medium set up by USM. All learning materials are distributed through eLearn@USM and are accessible to registered students. Active involvement in class discussions and activities is necessary in this course. Thus, students were expected to be actively involved and participate in all activities carried out during lectures and tutorials. "

The review of this course is done due to some reasons, as follows:

1. To explicitly highlight the concepts of sustainable development in the content and outline of the course.
2. To re-align the course learning outcomes so that they are in line with the program learning outcome and institutional objectives as conditioned by the Outcome

Based Education approach adopted by the Ministry of Higher Education. OBE is a student-centered learning system

specific and the world as a whole; and c) to instill relevant skills.

that focuses not only on students' final exam results (Cognitive Domain), but also on other learning outcomes (Psychomotor & Affective Domains) that could be added-value to students (Spady & Marshall, 1991).

3. Implementing the 21st-century learning skills framework in education. This framework focuses on students' skills, knowledge, and wisdom, which leads to a paradigm shift in the teacher's role in the 21st century. Thus, preservice teachers need to be equipped with all the skills relevant to the 21st century.
4. As part of the ICTeEfs Project – in ensuring elements of SDGs and ICT were integrated in the courses.

Methodology

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrakis (2017), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ are as follows.

1. Diagnosing: Reflecting on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
2. Deconstructing: Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
3. Constructing: Gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
4. Reconstructing: Integration of newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
5. Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. Finalizing: Reflecting on and evaluating what has been learned and changed.

Figure 1: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017)

For the evaluation of revised courses during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess, and Manage) methodology, advanced by Makrakis (2023), has been employed. These processes encompass the entire course, covering what students bring to class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (reviewing, reflecting, and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but more importantly to make whatever changes to improve it. Through the various parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students' DREAM portfolios must be analysed by the instructor, and a report must be prepared for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide essential information that the instructor and students can discuss and use to find ways to improve the course.

Figure 2: The DREAM Methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

Result

Following the review of the PGA103 course, which was conducted using both the DeCoRe+ and the DREAM Methodology approaches proposed by the ICTeEFs project, some improvements have been made to the course. However, these changes were still made within the scope and limits suggested by the Ministry of Education (MoE) and USM. Among the elements that have been updated are the course content, skills, ICT integrations, and sustainability concepts. In the aspect of ICT integrations, this aspect has become more important, particularly due to the online teaching and learning process that happened during the pandemic.

About the adjustments done, the course learning outcomes (CLOs) were reviewed. Nevertheless, the newly stated CLOs were carefully stated to ensure they are still in alignment with the program learning outcome (PLO) and the program educational objectives (PEO) as consistencies between CLOs, PLOs and PEOs is an important requirement set by the MQA. Alignment to the assessment method of this course is also taken into consideration.

The elements of sustainability are clearly stated in the course's objective. Nevertheless, the elements of 21st

century skills are not stated explicitly. However, the need to clearly state the aspect of 21st-century skills in the learning outcome is not urgent because the application and implementation of these skills are integrated into the course through the use of ICT and coursework. An element that could be highlighted in the course is the globalization and internationalization of education. The element was not highlighted in the course because, during the time of its development, the importance of this aspect was not yet prevalent.

As suggested by DREAM methodology approach, students' feedback was also being reviewed. The figure below illustrates the findings extracted from the students' feedback:

Figure 3: Mind Mapping of Students' Feedback on the Course

Most of the students who attended this course said that they had never created a project or written work close to this course. Similarly, the same figures also contended that they have never been involved in a work dealing with issues comparable to the topic presented in this course. For those with experience in handling projects similar to those offered in this course, the experience was gained through their position as contract teachers or as volunteers in university programs, often through cocurricular activities such as informal community service. Thus, to most students who took this course, it succeeded in offering them new experiences in community services and providing new knowledge about the policies, philosophy, history, and education system in Malaysia.

In general, at the beginning of the semester, prior to taking this course, students perceived the teaching profession as an unchallenging career, based on their

previous outlook as school students. Nonetheless, at the end of the semester, students stated that this course successfully broadened their perspectives and horizons on the role and responsibilities of a teacher, particularly in providing a quality education to students. Among the expressions of the students:

“My feeling is that I feel grateful to have studied this course before becoming a real teacher and I have learned that being a good teacher is not easy. For example, the dropout topic in this course allowed me to know the problem of a student in the dropout issue and the teacher does play an important role in dealing with this issue. Through this course, I have been inspired to be a person who is loving and well-liked by students, and I will always care for them, especially those with problems. Student A

Specifically, one major theme that can be drawn from the findings is the aspect of a teacher's professional development. In terms of the impact of this course on their knowledge enhancement, which contributes to their academic development, students noted some beneficial points worth noting. Students highlighted some increase in their understanding of a teacher's role, their knowledge about 21st-century learning skills, particularly by using the approach of problem-solving and game-based learning, their knowledge about issues in the education system, their knowledge of the history of the Malaysian education system, and their knowledge about the philosophy of education. Below are some vignettes from students related to the increase of knowledge on the professional development of a teacher.

“I was able to know the issues in the country, the characteristics that a teacher should have, I was also able to know the origin of the development of education in Malaysia and so on. The sciences are instrumental to know because they are vital to learn for every Malaysian.”

Student B: “The course not only emphasizes teaching ethics but also touches on the education of students, especially those focused on the bottom billion group.”

Student C

In the aspect of social development, the impact of this course on students is primarily in the planning, restructuring, implementation, and dissemination of projects related to community service. Indirectly, such a designed project helped students build their teamwork spirit, communication skills, and problem-solving skills. “The result of learning has made me a confident person to deal with other people. I feel satisfied.”

Student C: “The result of this learning has made me a more dedicated and consistent person in doing things. I feel happy and satisfied with the results of the study because it was worthwhile and built me a lot to achieve my ambitions as a teacher.”

Student F: “Learning about this subject taught me to listen actively in order to be able to understand and solve a problem with excellence.”

Student G

“Social skills increase.”

Student H “I was able to increase and develop my knowledge in communicating as a student to become a teacher, communicating in the school environment and with the community.”

Student A

Another important skill that students gained from this course, particularly due to the online teaching approaches adopted during the COVID-19 pandemic, is the use of ICT in teaching and learning. Students were introduced to a range of digital tools and applications while learning this course. The responses of the students are stated below:

“Through the use of various learning platforms.”

Student D “I think this course is indeed excellent and far away from my previous expectations. The doctor always conducts activities to answer various questions, such as forums and videos. I also got to know the app to make a mind map through this course.” Student E

Discussion

During the reevaluation of the course, we realized that the content needs to be updated. The elements of sustainability are clearly stated in the course's objective. Nevertheless, the elements of 21st-century skills are not stated explicitly.

However, the need to clearly state the aspect of 21st-century skills in the learning outcome is not urgent because the application and implementation of these skills are integrated into the course through the use of ICT and coursework activities. An element that could be highlighted in the course is the globalization and internationalization of education, mainly through the interdisciplinary aspect. The element was not highlighted in the course because, during the time of its development, the importance of this aspect was not yet prevalent.

Furthermore, a few questions were also asked in reconstructing this course, such as: How could students be the agent of change? How could students inspire changes in the schools they are assigned to? It was not previously considered because it was not the primary aim of the course. Thus, to address these questions, approaches that integrate more elements of ICT were employed, including the use of social media for disseminating information.

Future teachers need to know the policies, system, philosophical and sociological aspect of education (Shulman, 1987). The ability to understand the educational foundation and critically evaluate policies requires students to have a basic knowledge of the field of education. Nevertheless, students should also be prepared to explore new changes and developments in the field of education.

21st-century learning is a student-centred learning process based on elements of communication, collaboration, critical and creative thinking, as well as the application of moral values and ethics (KPM, 2018). Theories regarding 21st century learning aim to revolutionize education in response to the changes in 21st century society (BC-MoE, 2019). This is based on the belief that students nowadays can no longer be taught using 20th century approaches but should be given the opportunity to learn about 21st century skills (BC-MoE, 2019). The MoE has released the 21st century Basic Learning Standard (PAK 21) comprising of communications, creativity, collaborative, critical thinking and ethics and values, adopting the student-centred learning as the approach. The standard issued by MoE is in line with the P21 framework as well as a study conducted by Friday Institute (2015) which states that 21st century learning focuses a lot on communication, collaboration, and self-learning (Hess et al., 2017).

The teacher's job in the 21st century is unlike before and indeed very different. Teachers are no longer considered the main source of information providers, but are facilitators of knowledge (BC-MoE, 2019). To ensure that 21st century learning is successfully implemented, several things need to be paid attention to by teachers. From this course, students apply the aspect of learning to know, by learning the theories and foundation of education and simultaneously analyze and apply the knowledge to the existing development of the field. At the same time, students learn to realize and actualize themselves terms of strength and weakness, skills and talents and ability to contribute to the society which is in line with the learning pillars of sustainable development. The elements of communications; that is by interacting effectively with a broader audience during presentation in tutorial groups in which the students will justify, discuss, share, articulate their arguments is very much needed for students undertaking foundations courses. It is also obvious that elements of critical thinking, is very important in students learning. Critical thinking, which is one of the important 10c's is shared as an important aspect in the 21st century learning skills.

Target 4.8 in the 4th sustainable development goal; Quality Education mentioned about "building and upgrading education facilities that are child, disability and gender sensitive and provide safe, non-violent, inclusive and effective learning environments for all" (UNESCO, 2016). Such target could be achieved by adopting the 21st century learning and teaching skills, driven by the constructivist theory of learning. The development of the professionalism of teachers based on the 21st century can improve their teaching effectiveness when they can identify different ways of learning, intelligence, strengths, and weaknesses of students. The 21st century learning environment also requires access to quality teaching and learning materials, technology, and resources. This is closely related to the importance of using technology in the 21st century. Pre-service science teachers need to have continuous professional development and need a suitable

learning environment at their respective institutes of study before carrying out actual teaching at school.

Apart from gaining and constructing new knowledge, students should also be prepared to explore latest changes and development in the field of education. Teachers, schools, and society have their own roles and influences in determining the aspiration and the shape of the society. Despite the diverse Malaysia population of Malaysia, the element of living together harmoniously is important to be stressed explicitly rather than implicitly. Respect the rules and regulation of the country, realize, and respect the unique identity of the country which populate by diverse population of race, religion, and culture. Students are to be treated equally regardless of their background or gender. Teachers are to be respected.

Grant and Gomez (2001) contended that preservice teachers need to be prepared with the realities of the community context that they will face throughout their teaching career. Wade, 2000 suggested that though community services activities, preservice teachers were able to grow personally, socially, and emotionally, consequently develops their skills of reflection and ability to question their assumptions, beliefs, and prejudices as well as their understanding of their roles as teachers in the community. The design and implementation of the community projects in this course provides students the chance to make transformation, towards themselves and the society. It is through this means, students need to pull together their knowledge and skills for the success of the project. They learn to build up their positive attitude and personality, and at the same time give positive impact and influence on others. However, more elements of interdisciplinary connections could be integrated and highlighted in the projects proposed in this course. Experts from other fields, could be invited to give talks and guidelines in helping students with their community projects. Technical persons could also be involved in the designation and innovation of certain tools for the project.

It is also important to note that the process of revising and reconstructing this course using the DeCoRe+ and DREAM Methodology, as proposed in the ICTeEFs project, does not come quickly. Amid the process, the world was struck by the COVID-19 pandemic, which forced the educational system in most countries, including Malaysia, to transition online. Such a sudden scenario hit our students and our lecturer particularly in the aspect of readiness and acceptance of online distance learning. Allam et al (2020) reported that CIL among undergraduate students is at a high level, while SDL and MOL reported at a low level during the early stage of the outbreak. Other studies have also reported various challenges in the implementation of ODL (Shahariah Harun Najdah Abd Aziz, 2021). Implementation of community project were also suspended due to the movement restriction order during the pandemic. Instead, only the aspect of planning, designing and simulation of the project could be done. At time when the movement control order (MCO) was

loosened, projects involving minimum participants were done by the students.

Conclusion

As a conclusion, integrating sustainable development goals in the syllabus of higher education institutions need to be perceived as an important measure in promoting the concepts of SDGs to the next generation. Higher education institutions are medium whereby, future leaders were nurtured and developed. Integrating the concepts of SDG on students of higher education institution is hoped to accelerate the spread of awareness on SDGs, which will later turn into practical actions and transformation. ICTs on the other hand, is another tool that is equally important in disseminating the Concepts of the SDGs to the target population. The role of ICT in today's world needs to be utilized and maximized accordingly to ensure the broader dissemination of information and knowledge on the SDGs. The measures taken in this course serve as an example of how the concept of SDGs can be integrated into the syllabus of higher education institutions through the use of ICT. Simultaneously, important learning pillars of the SDGs and the elements of the 10Cs of the SDGs were also adopted to maximize impact in the course implementation.

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Infusing SDG in the Mathematics Teaching Methods Course through The ICTeEfs Project: A Case Study.

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Abstract

Over the last decades, humanity has faced the impacts of an unsustainable economic development growth driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014; 2021). Despite the current initiatives for reversing such an unsustainable development process, there is much to be done.

Education systems, at all levels, especially Higher Education, bear responsibility for the sustainability crisis we face globally. Universities play a crucial role in moving towards sustainability in education. The institutions should lead the sustainability movement by providing appropriate content to students and developing knowledge. Therefore, it is necessary to establish initiatives in curricula that infuse SDGs and sustainability. It is hoped such initiatives will transform knowledge in education for sustainable development into critical systemic thinking and action.

Efforts to infuse SDGs in mathematics showed some challenges. Mathematics is very abstract; many students struggle to understand and make sense of mathematics. Mathematics educators propose that teaching mathematics should promote critical thinking, reasoning, making sense of mathematics, and connecting it to the real world.

This paper describes a research project to infuse SDG in the mathematics teaching method courses, a compulsory course for students teachers opting to major in Mathematics. This paper will discuss the infusion of SDG into mathematics teaching methods courses through DeCore methodology for curriculum review and the implementation of the SDG infusion through the DREAM methodology.

This first part of this paper will discuss the applied Decore methodology for curriculum review of the Teaching Mathematics course 1. Therefore, the Decore methodology applied to the course focuses on making meaning and mathematics 'visible' to the students so that the students can see mathematics as problem-solving and focus on reasoning.

The second part of this paper will discuss the application of the Dream methodology to the mathematics teaching 1 course.

The findings from this project show that it is possible to design an approach to infuse SDG into the mathematics curriculum.

Students' reported increase in their understanding of mathematics and how mathematics could be related to the real world such as increase in the student's knowledge of teaching methods, 21st century learning and skills. Furthermore, students reported increase understanding of actual teaching elements such as preparing mathematics lesson plan, pedagogy as well as the arts of being a good mathematics teacher. Another exciting aspect is that the students reported an increase in their knowledge of ICT and the use of ICT in their mathematics teaching. Furthermore, the students reported acquiring communication skills as a teacher, for example, they report they improved their self-development, especially in their interpersonal skills and social development. Students too reported increase understanding and awareness in SDG issues especially related to environmental issues.

Keywords: (Mathematics Teaching Methods, sustainable concepts, pre-service teacher, DeCoRe+, concept map)

1. Introduction

Education should play a critical role in a radical transformation through an alternative development model emphasizing sustainable wellbeing. In our understanding, sustainable wellbeing is close to Aristotle's eudaimonic wellbeing as contrasted to the general hedonic wellbeing driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015; 2020; Makrakis, 2012-14). The quest for "sustainability justice," a concept developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture, is paramount in learning to transform oneself and society.

One of the challenges of infusing SDG in mathematics is that mathematics itself is an abstract subject with inherent challenges. For example, The UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) raised concern that 617 million children and adolescents worldwide – six out of ten – are not reaching minimum proficiency levels in reading and mathematics. Millions of youths and adults cannot play their part in the social and economic life of their communities and nations because they lack the skills to read or write a simple sentence or make a simple calculation. Quality education should acquire fundamental skills, such as literacy, numeracy, and higher-level skills. The end of lower secondary school often coincides with the end of compulsory education. By this stage, students should be able to master subject-related knowledge and skills, possess personal and social skills, and

have a solid foundation for further learning throughout life (Montoya, 2018). Mathematics is an essential part of education, which empowers people and opens new job opportunities. Mathematics is used to model global changes and their consequences on biodiversity.

Some works document the introduction of sustainability in subjects such as science or language teaching. However, little research investigates the fundamental role of mathematical education for students to achieve sustainable development.

Zehetmeier and Krainer (2011) present ways to promote sustainability in the curriculum among mathematics teachers. Cardeño, Azácate, and Oliva (2013) use a sample of students who were studying for the Master's Degree in Teacher Training in Secondary Schools, in the specialties of mathematics, physics and chemistry, and biology and geology to find out about their understanding of and approach to sustainability. The authors conclude that students in the specialty of mathematics (future teachers of this area) are less aware of sustainability than those in biology and geology, who are more predisposed to this subject.

Sometimes students do not understand mathematics's usefulness; some even consider it a complicated subject, which already predisposes them to it. On the other hand, many students perceive mathematics positively because they think it is used in everyday life but consider it problematic. Furthermore, some see mathematics as an isolated set of procedures with no real-life applications, discouraging them from learning. Innovative practices that provide them with a positive experience could help improve their performance in mathematics and the perception of its usefulness.

Suppose students considered mathematics as a valuable means of solving everyday problems. This approach could solve broader concerns, such as those involving the planet. However, how could sustainability skills be introduced into this subject alongside learning new mathematical techniques in higher education?

To answer this question, this paper aims to relate mathematical teaching to real problem solving focused on SDGs and to assess whether teaching this subject stimulates students. This teaching innovation makes it possible to attract students' attention to mathematical techniques when solving current problems that affect their more or less immediate environment.

The ICTeEfS project

One of Asia's most visible side-effects of rapid growth has been environmental damage. Recent climate-related disasters in the region show that Asian policymakers must act now to protect their citizens and mitigate and reverse climate change's impacts to secure future sustainable growth. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While there is the commitment of Asian leaders for EfS along with their concern for implementing Sustainable Development Goals

(SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS). On the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in the PCs make the integration of ICT in the curriculum of teacher education programs and in-service training inevitable. However, ICT integration does not merely mean adding ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims at developing an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators and turn them able to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies orienting to education for sustainability (EfS) through DeCore and DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for 2019-2023. In light of the above-discussed features, needs, and objectives, a six-stage capacity-building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006) was used (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on the diagnosis of the didactic profile of every trainee. Based on the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and is structured in thematic units, or modules that can be further enriched, considering the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will compare to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The exact process of evaluation is continued for the final recipients, the learners, through transferring their acquired

skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all settings to help sustain the proper functioning and possibly upgrade the training process (sixth stage).

The DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction advanced by Makrakis (2017), was also applied for course revision to embed sustainability and, most specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. Similarly, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2023) has been applied for the revised course evaluation during the implementation process.

The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes.

Diagnosing: Reflecting on a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017).

Methodology: Application of DECORE into The Mathematics Teaching Methods I: PGT 212E

This course is the first of the two compulsory teaching method courses offered to prospective mathematics teachers for the bachelor's degree in Mathematics Education at Universiti Sains Malaysia USM. Both mathematics teaching methods 1 and 11 are the core courses for students who wish to major in mathematics education and become teachers in Malaysian secondary schools. Both selected courses had the potential to be infused with ICTeEfS based on the relevant topics presented in its instructional plan.

This mathematics teaching method course aims to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes to become effective and competent mathematics teachers. The course will introduce students to the aims, fundamentals, and theories of mathematics education, curriculum, and planning of mathematics teaching and learning in secondary schools that emphasize higher order thinking skills and employ the appropriate pedagogy to teach the contents.

Among the main topics are to familiarize students with the aim and objectives of the Mathematics KSSM; to train students and future teachers in planning and to prepare suitable mathematics teaching units/lessons for various learning environments that promote higher order thinking skills; to enhance students' understanding of different teaching strategies and techniques employed in classroom mathematics teaching (problem-based learning, contextualize learning cooperative learning); to provide opportunities for students to practice simulated teaching with their peers through tutorial sessions, and to develop student's confidence and skills in teaching mathematics in secondary schools.

Deconstructing

Deconstructing in the DeCore methodology refers to critically analyzing the functioning of personal perspectives, habits of mind, and chosen curriculum units/modules.

We observed that the application of the element of sustainability or any other element as a novelty needs to be carefully planned. It requires sufficient knowledge among lecturers before adjusting the existing curriculum. Not all lecturers are proficient in the aspects of sustainability, especially SDGs. So, the first task in revising the curriculum is to have specific workshops related to the SDGs and their relevance to the courses involved. Thus, teachers can easily integrate SDGs into the existing curriculum rather than new things or subjects taught to the preservice teacher.

Teaching and learning become more challenging in adapting to the existing curriculum. Lecturers also need to delve into the 'content' about the elements of sustainability before presenting it to the student teacher. Lecturers also need to be proficient in the curriculum in school to make it easier for them to show examples that they can do in school later. Students should also be exposed to specific teaching examples incorporating sustainability elements with ICT as an enabler.

Constructing

In implementing this project, we organized a workshop that was not during the official class hour. The reason was students needed more time to understand all the SDGs concepts and to answer the questionnaire.

In some of the courses, the researcher was not the course coordinator. Thus, it was hard for us to implement all planned activities. To overcome this issue, we need to arrange the slot, i.e., 2 or 3 slots, for the researcher as an invited lecturer to lecture on specific topics related to SDGs. Each slot was about 2 hours/slot. In the tutorial time, we did the activities.

Each pair will choose a topic from the secondary school mathematics curriculum to prepare a lesson plan for teaching. Each group is required to present the project in a simulated teaching presentation. Each pair's students must teach the assigned topic according to the lesson plan as scheduled. The simulated teaching presentation will also encourage discussions, comments, and defending ideas with the whole class. Evaluation of the individual teaching will be based on: content knowledge, competencies in teaching, and professional dispositions demonstrated through verbal and non-verbal behaviors. During each teaching, students must participate actively by observing and evaluating the lesson. After instruction, every student has to give comments and suggestions on the lesson followed to improve the lesson further. Students must study the topic before the tutorial to actively participate in each discussion. Evaluation of individual participation in all discussions will be based on critical comments and suggestions to improve the lessons further. Students who embark on their journey to be mathematics teachers do not have prior learning of mathematics teaching methods. However, as former mathematics students in schools, they now need that experience to reference the issues and content covered in this course.

The learning activities consist of a weekly lecture for two hours and a one-hour tutorial for students. While all students attend the class simultaneously, students can choose their best tutorial slots. Tutorials are designed for a small group to further teacher and student engagement. Both lectures and tutorials discuss relevant topics related to the course objectives.

Furthermore, the tutorial consists of three different activities aimed at achieving the learning objectives:

- i. Review journal articles where students are required to read and review selected journal articles related to mathematics education.
- ii. Project (lesson plan) where students work in pairs, choose a topic from the secondary school mathematics curriculum, and prepare a complete 40-minute mathematics lesson plan for teaching.
- iii. Tutorial presentation (simulated teaching) where every pair of students is required to teach the assigned topic according to the lesson plan as scheduled.

ICTeEfs Project – by involving this course with this project, we need to review the relevant topics and assignments for the students. Thus, ESD will focus on ICT as a tool for the students to integrate ESD into their teaching.

Thus, by reviewing this course, we need to make certain amendments to make sure that the content and approach of this course are up-to-date and relevant for our future teachers. However, the percentage of the amendments was only 25% since, in USM, we are not allowed to change the course content by more than 30%. If there is more than 30%, it would need more time for approval because it requires permission from the school board and university senate. The approval process will take at least one year.

The content of the course is aligned with the goals and objectives of the course. Five main areas of learning mathematics are addressed: Numbers and operation, measurement and geometry, relationship and algebra, statistics and probability, and discrete mathematics.

Planning for mathematics instruction will require incorporating appropriate and relevant pedagogical approaches and tools for teaching mathematical concepts and skills. Issues and topics discussed include:

- Problem-solving in mathematics.
- Misconceptions in mathematics.
- Theories of learning mathematics and issues and challenges in mathematics teaching and learning.

Assessment of and for learning in mathematics is also explored to improve students' learning and teachers' teaching. Integration of ICT in mathematics teaching and learning is also given special attention. The course also discusses resource development for the teaching and learning of mathematics. This course would actively engage students with the course material through discussions, problem-solving, case studies, simulated teaching, role play, and other methods. Opportunities are provided for students to work individually, in pairs, and in groups.

Reconstructing

Reconstruction of the DeCore methodology refers to integrating newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.

After the course revision, we feel the content of the courses has added value in terms of the SDGs concept and the application of ICT as teaching tools.

For the local society, even though the students did the project using project-based learning, they couldn't implement it due to the covid-19 pandemic. Our university policy and Malaysia policy (during the Movement Control Order phase) did not allow us to do any field work activity. The infrastructure, especially internet access, was the barrier to online workshops or seminars.

Amendments and adjustments to the existing curriculum educate lecturers and students on the changes that need to be made. At least that element of sustainability needs to be highlighted and emerge in the curriculum.

However, for the curriculum change, we couldn't do it since it is a top to bottom process. It must go through a few layers of approval to change the curriculum. It took a long process and was time-consuming.

The process was as follows:

The changed need to be approved by the school board which will be forwarded to the university senate.

The University senate will approve the changes and must be officially endorsed by the Ministry of Higher Education (MHE).

Then, back to the university and school for the implementation.

Applying sustainability elements in teaching and learning requires few amendments to the existing curriculum. At the university level, any change in the curriculum there is limitations. If it exceeds the set percentage, it must go through a long process, from the approval at the faculty level to the ministry of higher education. Therefore, we can only amend the existing curriculum to a small extent.

Small changes in the existing curriculum - will hopefully provide student teachers with adequate information and understanding of how to deliver the SDGs concepts – knowledge and skills in school. The Covid 19 pandemic further boosted the use of ICT and made the process easier for student teachers. With this ability, they can convey this element of sustainability to students, and these students will be agents in sharing the message of sustainability to society.

Implementation in the mathematics education programs whereby students had to enroll in mathematics and science classes which are members of the ICTeEFS project enhances and supports mathematics students' understanding of SDGs.

The DREAM Methodology

For the revised course evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2023) has been applied.

For the revised course evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2023) has been applied. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims to assess a course and, more importantly, make whatever changes to improve it. Through the parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student guided by the course instructor creates a portfolio they have to give back to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students' DREAM portfolios must be analyzed by the instructor and prepared into a report for the whole class. Analyzing the DREAM portfolios will provide important information that the instructor and students could discuss and find ways to improve the course.

Figure 3. The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

Diagnose

All courses that were selected had the potential to be infused with ICTeEFS based on the relevant topics presented in its instructional plan.

This project applied participatory curriculum design (PCD) methodology in infusing ICTeEFS. Participation curriculum design (PCD) is proposed as an essential factor for the success of the curriculum development process (World Agroforestry Center, 2003). Stakeholder participation through meetings and workshops engaged different stakeholders in involvement workshops and meetings.

In this methodology, we have holistic participation, which involves several stakeholders such as students, teachers, lecturers from several faculties, and administrators. PCD involves a wide range of stakeholders in a meaningful way, drawing upon their experiences and insights in a structured approach to curriculum planning, implementation, and evaluation (Taylor, 2000). The stakeholders in this project were engaged in providing information on the nature of the curriculum, which lecturers should carry out in their teaching and learning of their courses.

All stakeholders have active discussion to 1) identify topics / segments in the course syllabus to implement ICTeEFS, 2) on how to infuse ICTeEFS in that selected topics/segments including the selection of relevant ICT and relevant ESD concepts without interrupting the course content in USM official documents. In infusing ICTeEFS, the following points are emphasized: - 1) the six learning pillars for sustainable development; 2) the 10Cs, 3) the four dimensions of sustainability justice; and 4) the learning activities that are integrated with problem-based learning (PBL) strategies. All ideas presented in the discussion are considered.

Based on the DREAM methodology, we also reviewed the students' feedback. From the findings, most of our students never attended a course on this topic and skills area in the

past. They also never created a project or written work like this course and never dealt with the same issues as the topic of this course. This course gave them first experience with the knowledge and skills about this course and how to create and deal with issues. The demography data shows that the students' ages range from 21 to 23 years old, and the majority, 66.6%, is 21. 83.3 % of the students are from urban areas, and 16.7% are from rural areas. However, 61.1 % of the students reported they have access to fast internet. Most students use laptops (66.7%), 27.7% use mobile phones, while only 5.6% use desktop computers.

77.8% of the students reported that they always or often find information on the web, e-book, e-journal, and e database. Almost 50% frequently or sometimes use communication channels such as blogs, forums or discussion groups. All 100 % of the students reported they are comfortable using PowerPoint and e-learning platforms. 44% of the students are satisfied learning new things, while 38.9% said they welcome challenges. Student interview data showed that the students look forward to learning mathematics and express their passion for learning to be good mathematics teachers. At this stage, there was no mention of learning about SDG in this course.

Review and Reflect

At the beginning of the semester, most students said the course they took is easy to score since they perceived that being a teacher is easy. They also perceive that the teacher's role and responsibility only focus on the teaching process. Findings also revealed that their perception of the pedagogical knowledge, especially on the teaching method, the curriculum, and syllabus, were easy to learn. They learned a lot of teaching techniques and strategies, holistic approaches, and SDGs. For them, SDGs are a new topic. Relate making sense of mathematics to SDG 4 and UNESCO mathematics day here

Data Review and reflection show that the students understand the pedagogical aspects of teaching mathematics, especially connecting mathematics to critical thinking, problem-solving, and inquiry learning. Analysis of their interview responses yield statements such as 'teaching methods', 'write a good lesson plan', 'blended learning, 'game-based learning, 'student centered' and 'inquiry-based learning. All of these are elements necessary to make mathematics relate to the real world and understanding mathematics. Interestingly, the ICT team has begun to emerge here too. Students responded that they see the use of ICT in teaching mathematics. Students to begin to identify teaching mathematics with critical thinking and 'learning how to teach mathematics.

However, the students had a different expectations about the course at the end of the semester. They said they had learned a lot in these courses. They never expected that there were

too many things to know on how to be a good quality teacher, such as integrating ICT in their teaching, assessment, teaching approaches, etc. Being a teacher is not as easy as they think, especially in the 21st century.

Need to have more challenging activities that suit students' interests and time to complete the task

The students also proposed to implement the ESD projects (students developed their ESD module) in the community to see the impact of that module.

They also feel satisfied with the course since they have learned so many things, such as different approaches, a variety of IT software/apps since most of the lectures and simulated teaching were conducted online. For them, it is a new experience that their seniors didn't have it. In conclusion, the different expectation brings benefits to students.

Explain, Assess & Manage

The number of students who reported that they always or often find information on the web, e-book, e-journal and e data base increased from 77.8% to 94.6%. While early in the semester, almost 50% frequently or sometimes use communication channels such as blogs, forums or discussion groups now increases to 74%. All 100 % of the students reported they are comfortable using powerpoint and e-learning platforms. 44% of the students are satisfied with learning new things at the beginning of the semester and now has increased to 75%. The number of students who welcome challenges risen from 38.9% to 75% at the end of the semester.

As we can observe, in this course, they learned a lot of concepts under pedagogical knowledge, current issues in mathematics education, teachers' role, etc. There are mentions of learning about SDG, However, their understanding of mathematics and how mathematics could be related to the real world is evident for example, in the student's knowledge of teaching methods, 21st century learning and skills as well as the actual teaching elements such as preparing mathematics lesson plan, pedagogy as well as the arts of being a good mathematics teacher. Another exciting aspect is that the students reported an increase in their knowledge of ICT and the use of ICT in their mathematics teaching. Furthermore, the students reported acquiring communication skills as a teacher, for example, they report they improved their self-development, especially in their interpersonal skills and social development. For example, data from the students' interviews stated that the students learned how to manage a task, make decision, problem-solving, Teamwork and Technical skills (ICT) and Ability to accept other people's idea – listening and considering all ideas.

Conclusion

Data from the interview revealed three main themes. Firstly, the students reported they are being presented with a model teaching of mathematics which they would like to emulate, for example, in modelling the lecturer's activities during class, the application of new knowledge, and the many hands-on activities.

Under the knowledge theme, they mentioned that they learned how to be a good and effective teacher by taking this course. They learned how to write a good lesson plan, be creative in teaching, and manage the classroom. They also expected to learn more about sustainability since they had already learned in the previous semester. It means that they need to know more about sustainability.

For future thinking on teacher's role and responsibility theme, they mentioned that by taking this course, they want to be a good teacher and committed to a teaching career with total commitment. Thus, it can be concluded that they would get the knowledge and skills to become a teacher. Then, they would know their role and responsibilities as a teacher.

On the self-development, there was one emerging theme, self-development. The students expected their confidence level to increase since they knew they needed to do the simulated teaching. With this assignment, they would be able to enhance their teaching and communications skills. They also expected that they could have a good grade in this course since most of their seniors said this course was fun and easy to score. It can be concluded that this course helps them maximize their potential to be a good preservice teacher and an effective teacher for the future.

All students mentioned that they get knowledge of the syllabus and curriculum of the subject they will teach in schools, the education history in Malaysia, and lots of learning theories. All these aspects were essential for them to be excellent and effective teachers. They also understand the sustainable development goals and education for sustainable development better. This is because USM has always been the first in terms of sustainability.

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ICTeEfs: Curriculum Revisions and Geography Pre-service Teachers Preparation

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Abstract

Action is needed now to create a sustainable future due to various global issues related to sustainability. Formal education at all levels, play a major role in delivering education for sustainability, along with their concern for the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). There is a need to revise curriculum in higher education to ensure that prospective teachers are competent in infusing SDGs with ICT as enabler. At USM, one of the courses involved in this review is Geography Teaching Method 1. In reviewing this course, a Capacity Building Model and the DeCoRe+ methodology (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) and DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology proposed by Makrakis was applied. For DREAM methodology this study employed the qualitative research approach and the data is collected through semi-structured focus group interview about students' feedback. After thoroughly review, and going through challenges and difficulties, some amendments to the course content had been done. A topic Geography and SDGs in the existing course outline and emphasized the 10°C, the six learning pillars and four dimension of sustainable justice in teaching and learning activities including assessment for this course and be one of the criteria in the assessment (wherever possible) were added. Based on the DREAM methodology, findings show that the students learned lots of thing such as curriculum and syllabus of geography, pedagogical content knowledge including SDGs, creativity, productivity, and ICT as an enabler for teaching about sustainability.

Keywords: (Curriculum Revision, Geography Pre-service teachers, Sustainable Development Goals, ICT)

5. Introduction

Global issues including climate change, biodiversity loss, growth in population, poverty, competition for finite resources need to be understood and dealt with wisely. Rapidly changing technology should be used to the maximum to deal with these issues. Action is needed now to create a sustainable future, protect our way of life and preserve nature as best it can to ensure its sustainability for now and into the future. In this regard, the importance of education in general to the well-being and prosperity of any society is well recognised (Australian Government, 2009). Thus, formal education at all levels, play a major role in delivering education for sustainability, along with their concern for the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Teachers play a crucial role in achieving the SDGs. There is a need to revise curriculum in higher education in the need of preparing competent teachers with knowledge on sustainability especially SDGs and skills on modern teaching methods, especially digital pedagogies.

A project entitled Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013; 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of, and capable of acting in transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts to teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are the agents for change in

promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016;2018; Blake et al., 2013) and for turning schools sustainable (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

At USM, efforts have been made to adapt the existing curriculum to the desire for sustainability and meet the goals of the Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability project, particularly at the School of Educational Studies which provides professional training to prospective teachers. This adaptation is also in line with the ICT-enabled In-service Training of Teachers to Address Education for Sustainability [ICTeEfs] project. In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the School of Educational Studies, USM entitled Geography Teaching Methods 1

6. Geography Teaching Method 1

This course, Geography Teaching Methods 1 (PGT 223) is the core course for every student who want to be geography teachers (major and minor in Geography). The purpose of this course is to expose students to the knowledge of appropriate and up-to-date geography teaching theories and strategies to enable them to implement geography teaching based on the lesson plans provided and work together to produce ideas or products using concepts and knowledge related to sustainable development.

In ensuring the goals of geography education in Malaysia are achieved, pre-service geography teacher need to be equipped with the knowledge and skills to teach geography using variety of teaching and learning strategies such as inquiry-based learning, project work based learning, cooperative learning, role play, PBL, discussion and study project (Curriculum Development Division, 2015). In addition, micro and macro teaching (simulated teaching) will be used as a part of the procedure to train these pre-service geography teachers on how to conduct the teaching and learning process using prepared lesson plan. They also learned on how to use questioning techniques, teaching aids, inculcation of moral values into the lesson, evaluation of lesson, response to questions and sustainability concepts. The learning outcome for this course are:

- i. Demonstrate knowledge of appropriate and up-to-date geography teaching theories and strategies
- ii. Implement geography teaching (simulated) based on the teaching lesson provided
- iii. Summarize geography simulation teaching

Thus, every pre-service geography teacher in USM, they need to take this course. Each week in this course, they will be exposed to several basic concepts of geography education especially teaching and learning geography. There were 110 students registered in this course for semester 1 2020/2021 and 2021/2022. The numbers of students depended on the projections of Ministry of Education.

Based on the original lesson plan, slight amendments have been made to include all elements related to sustainability and ICT. Through the new topic, the assignment and learning activities, the idea six learning pillars of 21st century, the 10'C (instead of well-known 4'Cs - critical thinking & problem solving, communication, collaboration and team building, creativity and innovation) as suggested by Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis (2014), and four pillars of sustainable justice were imposed.

There are several reasons that we need to review this course. In 2017, there is a curriculum change in Malaysia Education System known as Standard Based Curriculum for Secondary Schools (KSSM). KSSM explicitly include 21st Century Skills and Higher Order Thinking Skills and emphasizes the use of ICT in teaching and learning as well as environmental sustainability (Curriculum Development Division, 2015). In this new curriculum, there is a Cross Curricular Elements as a set of value-added elements. The purpose of this element is to strengthen the human capital skills and competency besides preparing students for the challenges of the present and the future. The two elements that related to sustainability are Environmental Sustainability Awareness which developing awareness, nurturing the love and care for the environment through teaching and learning, promoting knowledge and awareness on the importance of the environmental ethics and sustainability for students to

appreciate. While Global Sustainability will develop sustainable thinking (responsive towards the environment, being responsible, creative and resourceful) with the concept of living within global resources without damaging its present or future environment and prepare students to face challenges on complex interconnected global issues. Thus, every teacher need to be able to teach this element directly and indirectly in related subjects by maximizing the use of ICT.

Because of this, we add several new topics to update our course content such as Geography and Education for Sustainable Development (EfSD) and emphasized the idea of 10'C, 21st century learning pillars and four sustainable justice in the assessment and learning activities with ICT (variety of relevant IT apps/software) as an enabler. With these new topics and ideas, it is a hope that our preservice teachers will have basic knowledge and skill in sustainability and know to convey to the students at school later.

Another reason why need to review this course was the requirement from Malaysian Qualification Agency (MQA) for public universities in which Outcome-based Education need to be implemented. Compared to traditional learning systems that only conduct quantitative assessment, OBE improves the existing system by adding elements of qualitative assessment (Aravind, et. al, 2008). Outcome-Based Education focuses on the planning and outcomes that will be achieved by students at the end of the program. OBE emphasizes student learning by:

- i. Using clear learning outcomes statements to make it easier for students to know and understand the expected outcomes they need to achieve.
- ii. Provide specific learning activities with the aim of enabling students to achieve all planned learning outcomes.
- iii. Evaluate the level of student achievement against the evaluation criteria that have been set clearly and effectively

OBE is a student-centered learning system that focuses not only on students' final exam results (Cognitive Domain), but also on other learning outcomes (Psychomotor & Affective Domains) that could be added-value to students (Spady & Marshall, 1991). OBE adopted the concept of Student Centered Learning (SCL) are highly dependent on appropriate teaching and learning methods to achieve all the Learning Outcomes (LO) that have been set (Norhayati Zakaria et.al, 2013) for the course, program and university.

7. Methodology

In reviewing this course, we used a Capacity Building Model (2006) proposed by Makrakis. This model is a six-stages capacity building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model (Makrakis, 2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on the diagnosis of the didactic profile of every trainee. In this stage, only one lecturer selected since she was co-coordinator of this course. She has experience skills in ICT. She has 5 years' experience in teaching geography in school and two years' experience as co-coordinator for this course. For the second stage, creating an action plan. There were 4 workshops for teacher educators which focused on how to infuse ESD enabled by ICT in the university's existing curriculum, research and community engagement. The workshop also focused on disseminating knowledge about CARE learning design. Thus, in this stage, SDGs, 10Cs, 21st century six learning pillars, four pillars of sustainable justice and variety types of IT apps have been introduced. In the third stage, we conducted our training via online since face-to-face training was not allowed due to Movement Control Order (MCO) during Covid-19 pandemic. At the beginning of the training, it is one-way interaction in which the selected trainer learned all the important concepts such as SDGs, 10Cs, six learning pillars and four pillars of sustainable justice. Since most of these concepts were new to them, we have question and answer at the end of session. We also distributed questionnaire to assess their understanding about the training's content. After attending 4 workshops, the teacher educator have a good understanding on developing ICTeEfS curriculum and ready to be a trainer on ICTeEfS in their institution. They had enough knowledge and skills on ICTeEfS. In the 5th stage, the same process of evaluation is continued for the final recipients, the learners through transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom. Finally, a system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages that help to sustain the proper functioning and possible upgrading of the training process (sixth stage).

While for the revision of PGT 223 course, the DeCoRe+ methodology (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) by Makrakis (2017) was applied. According to him, the DeCoRe+ is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes (Figure 2).

7. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
8. **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
9. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
10. **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
11. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
12. **Finalising:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017).

We answer all the questions given in the template. The syllabus was reviewed by external evaluator for two times. Finally, we have the final draft of DeCoRe+ document. We add new elements in our course, 10Cs, six learning pillars for 21st century learning and four dimensions of sustainable justice were included.

The element of 10Cs that integrated in this course were:

- Constructing knowledge

Students learned not only about teaching theories, approaches, and issues in geography education but also about the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and how to utilize Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching and learning. Students are prepared for constructing knowledge through the inquiry approach.

- **Collaboration**
Students worked together in a group assignment, completing their teaching simulation and related activities, as well as a forum presentation that emphasized sustainability.
- **Communication**
Students need to communicate to each other prior to their presentation (assignments). During the lecture, the lecturer also provided them with an 'issue to ponder' for discussion.
- **Critical thinking**
Students need to think critically and analyze before making decisions and addressing the issues related to SDGs in their assignments.
- **Creativity**
Students need to be creative in teaching simulations, forum presentations, and their Facebook statuses.
- **Cross-cultural understanding**
Students need to have a partner who is from a different race, religion, and culture to complete their assignment. In Malaysia we have three different races, Malay, Indian and Cina. They worked as a single group, the Malaysians.
- **Co-responsibility**
Students should be able to recognize the importance of playing an active role in disseminating knowledge about SDGs to schools and the public.
- **Connectivity**
Students need to conduct simple investigations into issues related to the SDGs and provide solutions to them.
- **Critical consciousness**
Students' critical consciousness about the importance of SDGs and the health of our earth were developed while they discussed issues regarding SDGs
- **Critical reflection**
Students need to do the critical reflection on their simulated teaching and forum presentation.

The six learning pillars for sustainable development were:

- **Learning to know**
Students learned about various related learning theories and teaching methods, as well as the SDGs, among

other topics. They were able to analyse and apply the knowledge to the real world situation

- **Learning to Do**
Students were able to design and conduct interactive learning activities in their presentations and simulated teaching by using ICT, provided they had understood all the important concepts in geography teaching methods.
- **Learning to Be**
Students were able to make a positive contribution to society through their projects. Thus, they knew how to develop their self-potential.
- **Learning to Live Together**
Students learned to respect the university's and faculty's rules and regulations. They also realized how to be a good citizen in a plural society with different backgrounds and cultures.
- **Learning to transform oneself and society**
Students learned how to cultivate their positive attitude and personality, and in doing so, have a positive impact and influence on others.
- **Learning to give and share**
Students were able to share their views and opinions on specific issues, particularly during presentations and simulated teaching sessions. They respect others' opinions to find the best solutions to solve real-life problems related to their task.

Additionally, this course incorporates four dimensions of sustainable justice. There were:

- **Environmental justice**
environmental racism, especially in the case of disproportionate and unequal exposure to environmental hazards.
- **Social justice**
Ethics of fair and equitable allocation of resources, rights, and obligations in society.
- **Economy Justice**
unfair trade, economic exploitation, socio-economic polarization, and income distribution
- **Cultural Justice**
violation of human rights, gender, diversity, and heritage.

(Makrakis, 2017)

Then, we developed ICTeEfS course syllabus for this course. It consists of 5 modules, each based on a specific course learning outcome. The modules as follows:

Module 1: Geography and its Contribution

Module 2: School Geography Curriculum and Planning for Teaching

Module 3: Methods and Techniques of Teaching

Module 4: Resources and Assessment

Module 5: Issues Related to Geography

With all the requirements from the School of Educational Studies, USM, and ICTEefs projects, as course developers, we update the course content, skills, and sustainability concepts. Additionally, with the COVID-19 pandemic, the use of ICT as teaching tools has become essential. Schools, as well as higher education institutions, had to rapidly adapt their learning processes to operate in an online environment.

As a result, we added a topic on Geography and SDGs in the existing course outline. We emphasized the 10th C, the six learning pillars and four dimensions of sustainable justice in teaching and learning activities and the assessment for this course and be one of the criteria in the assessment (wherever possible) which consists of two parts:

c. The final examination is 50% - there is a question related to sustainability and the SDGs.

d. Coursework - 50%. In the coursework. It consisted of:

iii. Assignment 1 (10%) – Individual

Each student is required to post two statuses on their Facebook that contain elements educating Facebook readers on the importance of environmental sustainability. Students need to prepare a brief report (between 4-6 pages in length) in response to the submission. The report should contain status submissions that have been made, likes earned, comments obtained, and their reflections on the comments.

iv. Assignment 2 (10%) – Group Work

Presentations (Forums) & Comments based on one of the following topics:

Various ways of student learning, 21st Century Skills and Teaching & Learning Geography, Inquiry in Teaching & Learning Geography, Higher Order Thinking Skill in Teaching & Learning Geography, and Geography and Sustainable Development. Students were encouraged to maximize the use of ICT.

v. Simulated teaching (30%) – Group Work

Students need to prepare notes for related topics, teaching aids (with an emphasis on ICT), a half-hour lesson plan for the given topics in lower secondary geography (Form 1 and 2), and a teaching simulation video that has been conducted. Students should implement elements of the SDGs wherever and however possible. The lesson plan will be presented by the group

in tutorial class following the tutorial schedule. The lesson plan should incorporate a didactic analysis of the geography content, subject content knowledge, students' prerequisite learning and/or experiences, learning goals, media, references, procedures, and student and teacher assessment and evaluation.

During the implementation of the syllabus, we reviewed the course using the DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) methodology proposed by Makrakis (2023). The processes cover the entire spectrum of the course, encompassing what students bring to class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing, reflecting, and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but, more importantly, to make changes in order to improve it (Figure 3).

Figure 3 The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

At the end of the semester, students must submit a concept map outlining what they have learned in this course.

For the DREAM methodology, this study employed a qualitative research approach, and data were collected through semi-structured focus group interviews. In qualitative methods, there are no specific rules regarding the sample size (Gay, 1996; Patton, 2002; Polit & Beck, 2008). The sample size depends on the point to be addressed, the research purpose, the available resources, and the allocated time. However, according to Smith (2004), in qualitative research, the sample size must be small to allow for a detailed investigation. We used focus group interviews to explore participants' experiences and perceptions, employing group processes to stimulate

responses and gain insights through participants exchanging views, questioning, and challenging each other (Scheelbeek, P.F.D., Hamza, Y.A., Schellenberg, J., et al., 2020). For this research, we conducted interviews with five geography student teachers.

8. Findings and Discussion

Based on the DREAM methodology, we reviewed the students' feedback. According to the diagnosis findings, most of our students (4 out of 5) have never attended a course on this topic or in this skills area in the past. They also never created a project or written work (4 out of 5) like this course and never dealt with the same issues as the topic of this course. It means that this course provided them with their first experience in acquiring knowledge and skills related to the course, as well as how to create and address issues. They hope to learn a great deal about teaching methods that will enable them to be effective geography teachers.

Findings from the interview session in the review and reflection stage reveal that they share the same opinions. For them, the taken course provided a wealth of knowledge regarding the syllabus and curriculum. At the beginning of the course, they were unfamiliar with the syllabus and curriculum.

"I don't know much about the curriculum and syllabus..." (*saya tidak begitu tahu tentang kurikulum dan silibus ...*) S2

"Yes....I don't even know much about the curriculum and syllabus of this course..." (*Ya....saya pun tidak begitu tahu tentang kurikulum dan silibus kursus ini...*) S4

Thus, in the middle of the semester, the syllabus and curriculum served as a guideline on how to teach the subjects in schools.

....when I have attend this course...., I can feel that this course will guide me toto teach at school later... (*...apabila saya telah menghadiri kursus ini...., saya dapat merasakan bahawa kursus ini akan panduan saya untukmengajar di sekolah nanti....*) S1

"I noticed that.... this course give me..... a guide to teach in the school later...especially pedagogi aspect...." (*"Saya dapati.... kursus ini memberi saya panduan untuk mengajar di sekolah nanti...terutamanya aspek pedagogi..."*) S5

In addition, they also improved their ICT skills. Because of the covid-19 pandemic, they learned a lot about the software and apps that can be used in their simulated teaching. They feel very happy since they mastered on how to integrate those apps in their teaching.

"I learned more about ICT....about some app...before I don't know about it...but now I...I can used it...in teaching." (*Saya belajar lebih banyak tentang ICT....tentang beberapa aplikasi...sebelum ini saya tidak tahu mengenainya...tetapi sekarang saya....saya boleh menggunakannya...dalam pengajaran"*) S2

"I'm happy because now.... I know a lot....the new app" (*"Saya gembira kerana sekarang....saya tahu banyak....aplikasi baharu"*) S1

They also claimed that they are improved in terms of teamwork. They also improved in critical thinking skills and know how to do reflections.

"...it can improve teamwork...we learn to agree...learn to discuss....to reach one decision..." (*"ia dapat meningkatkan kerjasama berpasukan...kami belajar untuk sepakat...belajar untuk berbincang....untuk capai satu-satu keputusan..."*) S3

"I also learned how to think.think critically...and also learned to reflect....specifically....reflection on the teaching I do." (*"saya juga belajar bagaimana berfikir....berfikir secara kritikal...dan juga belajar membuat refleksi....khususnya....refleksi terhadap pengajaran yang saya jalankan."*) S4

They need to think deeply in order to have a good lesson plan based on the instructor's feedback. After doing all the needed amendments, they will submit the revised lesson plan. They also mentioned while doing this, they learned how to reflect. For them, thinking and reflection were two important elements in producing creative activities and lesson plan.

"I learned to reflect....look back at the RPH....then submit again...." (*"Saya belajar untuk buat refleksi....tengok balik RPH....kemudian hantar semula..."*) S2

From these findings, it can be concluded that most of the students are very concern about their professional development and self-development as future geography teacher. As stated by Darling-Hammond & McLaughlin, (1995), teacher training and professional development are seen as central mechanisms for the improvement of teachers' content knowledge and their teaching skills and practices in order to meet high educational standards.

However, findings revealed that they had a different expectation about the course at the end of semester. The data showed that all their expectation was not in line with reality. The results showed that, after finishing the course teacher's role and responsibility were too many and it was not easy to be a teacher as they think. They also mentioned that that they

learned a lot such as teaching techniques and strategies, and also about SDGs. For them, SDGs is a new topic.

“Through this course..., I was able to learn....how to teach geography...learn techniques and strategies...and...aaa....about the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)....” (“Melalui kursus ini..., saya dapat belajar....cara mengajar geografi...belajar teknik dan strategi...dan...aaa....tentang Matlamat Pembangunan Mampan (SDG)....”) S1

They also learned on how to a lesson plan and how to integrate ICT in their teaching since it is 21st century. They also mentioned that to be a teacher in the 21st century was not easy as they think

“I was able... to use the... knowledge given to be used....in preparing the lesson plan... of the Geography subject.” (“Saya dapat... menggunakan... pengetahuan yang diberikan untuk digunakan....dalam menyediakan rancangan pengajaran... mata pelajaran Geografi.”) S4

“...indirectly...I learned to use ICT in teaching...use technology to teach....it's the 21st century...especially during Covid 19.” (“...secara tidak langsung...saya belajar menggunakan ICT dalam pengajaran...guna teknologi untuk mengajar....sekarang kan abad ke 21...lebih-lebih semasa Covid 19.”) S5

From the finding above, they built a strong self-resilience. Resilience can be developed through experience. With resilience, students could have a better grade in this course. According to Waxman et.al. (2003), students with resilience will succeed in the school and always display courage, motivation and maintain a positive mindset. (Education Hub, n.d).

They also feel satisfied with the course since they have learned so many things in the course such as different approaches, variety of IT software/apps since most of the lectures and simulated teaching were conducted online. For them, it is a new experience. As a conclusion, the difference expectation brings benefits to students: self-resilience and self-satisfaction.

In assess stage, every student did a concept map about what they have learned in this course. From their concept map, we summarized as below (Figure 4).

Figure 4 PGT 223 students’ understanding about the course

As observed, in this course, students learned a lot of concepts such as curriculum and syllabus of geography, pedagogical content knowledge, creativity and productivity. Thus, it can be concluded that students learned lots of concepts in this course for their self-development as future geography teacher. They also learnt ESD and SDGs. As Potter-Nelson and O’Neil (2019) states that in order to be a change agent, teachers need to become sustainability literate which can be accomplished through formal and informal professional development offered by tertiary institutions and nonprofit organizations.

After attending the course, the findings showed that the impact on their knowledge that contributes to their academic development such as increase their knowledge on teaching methods, 21st century learning skills, SDG, on how to do the lesson plan properly, pedagogy and how to a good teacher. They also mentioned that their ICT skills also improved. The course helped them to improved their self-development especially on their interpersonal skills as future geography teacher. They know a lot about Malaysian Education System. They know a lot about the IT and their IT skills is improved.

In manage stage, they feel they were ready mentally and physically to be a teacher. They were ready to go to schools and take on the challenge as a beginner teacher. They were able to apply all the knowledge to make the teaching and learning process meaningful. They were also able to plan a lesson plan that is more suitable in the 21st century and know how to use ICT effectively.

After I revised and made certain changes to the courses, it appeared that they had had an impact on our students. Before the revision, we did not focus on students’ potential. We focused more on academic performance. Because of this, the teaching and learning process should provide students with a meaningful experience. Thus, we need to review our learning outcomes, as Roa (2019) mentioned that the outcome serves as the basis for effective interaction

among concerned stakeholders and is a product of learning, a so-called learning product. In addition, the integration of 10Cs, six learning pillars for sustainable development, and four dimensions of sustainable justice make the students more aware of sustainable issues in their daily lives.

Regarding the content revision, we focused not only on cognitive development but also on affective and psychomotor development. Roa (2019) stated that non-cognitive factors, including the 10Cs, six learning pillars, and four dimensions of sustainable justice, are also important for students' development. With these two factors, the learning process would be more meaningful. Students would be more appreciative and practice what they have learned in their daily lives. Thus, transformative learning occurred, as it involved an ontological process where students can experience a change in their being (Ilisko, 2007) and enact their sense of social responsibility (Cranton, 1994). With this type of learning, preservice teachers will become agents of change, transforming knowledge and skills to benefit students in creating a sustainable society for the future.

9. Challenges and Difficulties

There were numerous challenges that we faced from the project's beginning to its end. The challenge as follows:

1. Due to covid-19 pandemic, all classes were online classes and we were not sure about students' readiness and acceptance of online distance learning (ODL). Even though, all of these students were generation Z, but they were not ready with online learning. Data form interview revealed that they were mentally exhausted with this type of learning because their internet access were not so good.
2. In implementing this project, we need to have a workshop which was not an official class hour. The reason was students need more time to understand all the SDGs concepts and to answer the questionnaire.
3. We need to carefully look into the existing course guideline because the percentage of the amendments was only 25% since in USM, we are not allowed to change the course content more than 30%. If there is more than 30%, it would need to go through a few layers of approval. It took a long process and time consuming. It is not a curriculum change but curriculum revised with a few amendments. The process was as follows:
 - The changed need to be approved by the school board which will be forwarded to the university senate.
 - The university senate will approve the changes, and they need to be officially endorsed by the Ministry of Higher Education (MHE).

- Then, return to the university and school for implementation.
4. We need to consider other elements that need to be incorporated related to geography and geography teaching, as this is a geography teaching method course.
 5. I also need more time to explain to the co-coordinator of this course the idea of applying ICTeFS in this course. She was not proficient in the elements of sustainability, particularly the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It is not a 'new' thing or a new subject to be taught or an addition to the existing course. It is a part of geography and teaching the subject of geography.

After the course revision, we believe that the content of the courses has added value in terms of the SDGs concept and the application of ICT as teaching tools. The Covid-19 pandemic further boosted the use of ICT and made the process easier for student teachers. With this ability, they can convey this element of sustainability to students and these students will be agents in conveying the message of sustainability to society.

6. Conclusion

After thoroughly review, through a step by step process by using Capacity Building Model (Makrakis, 2006), the DeCoRe+ methodology (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) by Makrakis (2017) and DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology proposed by Makrakis (2019; 2022), we managed to do some amendments to the course content. We added a topic Geography and SDGs in the existing course outline and emphasized the 10'C, the six learning pillars and four dimension of sustainable justice in teaching and learning activities including assessment for this course and be one of the criteria in the assessment (wherever possible). By integrating SDGs in the Geography Teaching Method 1, it gave lots of knowledge and experience to students on how to be agents of change in sustainability moved. It is a hope that this course be able to provide student teachers with adequate information and understanding on how to deliver the SDGs concepts – knowledge and skills in school. With this ability, they can convey this element of sustainability to students and these students will be agents in conveying the message of sustainability to society. Based on the DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023), we found that the students learned lots of thing such as curriculum and syllabus of geography, pedagogical content knowledge, creativity, productivity, and ICT as an enabler for teaching about sustainability.

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DeCoRe+ Methodology: A Model to Revise Pre-Service Teachers Course Syllabus in Integrating SDGs Using ICT: A Case Study for General Science Teaching Methods

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Abstract

This report describes our process in reviewing the pre-service course syllabus for General Science Teaching Methods to infuse the Education for Sustainability (EfS) concepts using information and communication technology (ICT) in teaching and learning process. The Capacity Building model is used to train and equip the teacher's educators on EfS and ICT while the DeCoRe+ (abbreviated from Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) model is used for the course revision which focuses on the transformative education development. A total of 106 pre-service teachers participated in this study. This course is a compulsory course to those who want to be a science teacher. Based on the course revision we developed four modules which integrate the fundamental concepts such as CARE learning design, 10Cs, six learning pillar and four dimensions on sustainable justice. We implemented the modules for one semester (14 weeks). During the implementation, we also evaluated the students' feedback on the revised course using the DREAM (Diagnose-Review-Explain-Asses-Manage) methodology to cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). Based on the DREAM evaluation, the findings showed that there are several themes on the impact to the pre-service teachers' development such as professional development, self-development, and social development. For them, this course helped them not only on the knowledge but also the skills to infuse EfS in science subject using ICT.

Keywords: Science teaching methods, DeCoRe+, DREAM methodology, pre-service teacher, sustainability

10. Introduction

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is a current trend now. Every country including Malaysia are not left behind in integrating SDGs in education curriculum as it is one of the nation's directions. Thus, to achieve this, teachers played an important role to disseminate knowledge, skills and practice of SDGs. Teachers will be the "changing agent". As one of the top universities in Malaysia, Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM) has its own agenda on sustainability. Tan Sri Dzul as a former vice chancellor has disclosed the sustainability concept through several actions. Thus, in 2000 USM has started the education for sustainable development and "University as a Living Lab" through the concept of Kampus Sejahtera and University in a Garden (USM 2019).

The journey is continued when USM integrating 17 SDGs within USM's ecosphere. This agenda is never ending in USM, when School of Educational Studies (SES) took the initiative to embed the sustainability concepts in several related courses in preparing preservice teachers as transforming agents for sustainability. To ensure the pre-service teachers equip with sustainable knowledge, they need to be trained. Thus, General Science Teaching Methods is suitable since this course is related to science subject. As mentioned by Birdsall (2013), education for sustainability's foundations were in science education, since the 1990s and science knowledge able to bring enormous transformations to Earth's natural systems in an unprecedented way (Colucci-Gray, et.al., 2006).

1.1 General Science Teaching Methods

General Science Teaching Methods (PPG 210E) is a compulsory course for every pre-service teacher who wants to be a science teacher. This course is offered in the first semester in every academic calendar for the second-year students from science education program, and they need to pass this course at least with grade "C". If they fail this course, they would not be able to register for the course of general teaching methods II for the next semester. The purpose of this course is to expose students to the knowledge of appropriate and up-to-date science teaching theories and strategies to enable them to implement science teaching based on the lesson plans provided and work together to produce ideas or products using concepts and knowledge related to the SDGs.

In ensuring the goals of science education in Malaysia are achieved, pre-service science teachers need to be equipped with the knowledge and skills to teach science using variety of teaching methods such as inquiry, discovery, cooperative learning, role play, problem-based learning, discussion and study project. In addition, microteaching (simulated teaching) will be used as a part of the procedure to train these pre-service science teachers on how to conduct the teaching and learning process using prepared lesson plan. They also learned on how to use questioning techniques, teaching aids, inculcation of moral values into the lesson, lesson evaluation and on how to response the questions. Besides, they also learned about sustainability concepts since USM are very actively promoting sustainability to the whole university.

Most of the courses in USM already infused with the sustainability concepts. In addition, the management of science laboratories is also given emphasis in this course.

Thus, the learning outcomes for this course are as below:

- Explain the theory and strategy of teaching science
- Implement science teaching based on the teaching plan (in line with the National Science Education Philosophy) in a group
- Demonstrate appropriate science process skills and thinking skills in science teaching.
- Integrate appropriate SDG goals in preparing Education for Sustainability (EfS) modules with emphasis on SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG 13 (Climate Change) and SDG 15 (Life on Land)

In this course, they will learn several basic concepts of science education such as Nature of Science, Scientific Literacy, Sustainable Developments Goals, assessment in science, etc. There were about 106 students registered in this course for semester 1 2020/2021 and 2021/2022.

The assessment for this course consisted of two parts:

a. Final examination is 50%.

It consisted of 4 essay questions. All questions are higher order thinking skills questions. The duration of examination is two hours. In this part, it will assess the cognitive aspect of students related to the course.

b. Coursework is 50%.

It measured the affective part which consisted of:

i. Project 1 (20%): Writing a lesson plan and simulated teaching

Students need to prepare one-hour lesson plan for any topics in science secondary levels (they need to choose from syllabus: - Form 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5). The lesson plan can be in Malay or English language since Malaysia implemented Dual Language Programme (DLP) in teaching Science and Mathematics.

In the lesson plan, students need to prepare a lesson consisted of science practical activities (science experiments) or activities that are suitable with the Malaysian curriculum syllabus which *Dokumen Standard Kurikulum dan Pentaksiran (DSKP)*. They are also able to relate the topics from DSKP with everyday life experience. For the simulated teaching, the lesson plan will be presented by a group consisted of two students in tutorial class following the tutorial schedule. The lesson plan should incorporate a didactical analysis of the science content; subject content knowledge; students' pre-requisite learning and/or experiences; learning goals; media; references; procedure; and student and teacher assessment/evaluation.

ii. Project 2 (30%)

Students need to design an EfS module. In this module, they need to highlight any EfS issues in a community. In this project, students need to use project-based learning integrating with any Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Students need to identify the issue in a community or globally. They need to present the module at the end of semester.

One of the reasons to review this course is the curriculum change in Malaysia science curriculum in 2018 in which need to be aligned with 2030 agenda for sustainable development goals (SDG 2030). Thus, sustainability concept needs to be introduced. It was introduced as Cross Curricular Elements as a set of value-added elements. These elements are applied to strengthen the skills and competency of the intended human capital, capable of dealing with the current and future challenges (MOE, 2017). Under Cross Curricular Elements, there were two elements related to sustainability known as Environmental Sustainability (ES) and Global Sustainability (GS).

i. The aims for ES are:

- Develop awareness and love for the environment need to be nurtured through the teaching and learning process in all subjects.
- Knowledge and awareness on the importance of the environment would shape pupils' ethics in appreciating nature.

ii. The aims for GS are:

- Develop pupils with sustainable thinking highly responsive attitude to the environment in their daily lives with the application of knowledge, skills, and values acquired through the elements of the Sustainable Consumption and Production, Global Citizenship and Solidarity.
- Prepare students to face challenges and current issues at the local, national and global levels.

(Curriculum Development Centre, 2018)

Thus, every teacher needs to be able to teach these elements directly and indirectly in any related subjects. However, for science subject, it is compulsory since there are certain topics related to sustainability such as climate change, ecosystem etc.

Because of this, we need to review this course and make several amendments to ensure the content and approach of this course are up-to-date and relevant for our future teachers. Thus, we added several new topics to update our course content such as Science and EfS, Current Issues in Science Education, etc. It is a hope that our pre-service teachers will have basic knowledge and skills in sustainability. This situation is further strengthening when this course is selected for revision under the project - ICT-enabled In-service Training of Teachers to address Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS). In this project, the

ICT elements will be the focused and students need to use variety of relevant ICT application or software in promoting EfS. ICT will be one of the tools in teaching and learning process.

With all these elements, this course, General Science Teaching Methods were ready to be implemented as a stepping stone in preparing future science teachers for sustainable development.

11. Methodology

In reviewing the course, a Capacity Building Model (2006) proposed by Makrakis has been used. This model is a six-stages capacity building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their teaching and learning process. Refer to Fig 1.

Fig. 1. A Capacity Building Model by Makrakis (2006).

In the first stage, training focuses on the diagnosis of the didactic profile of every trainee. In this stage, only one lecturer selected since she was the course coordinator of this course. She has experience in SDGs and skills in ICT. She has 15 years' of experience in teaching science. For the second stage, creating an action plan. There were four workshops for teacher educators which focused on how to infuse EfS enabled by ICT in the university's existing curriculum, research and community engagement. The training also focused on disseminating knowledge about CARE learning design as proposed by Kostoulas and Makrakis (2020). Thus, in this stage, SDGs, 10Cs, six learning pillars, four pillars of sustainable justice and various types of ICT application for teaching and learning have been introduced. In the third stage, we conducted our training via online since face-to-face training was not allowed due to Covid-19 pandemic. At the beginning of the training, it was a one-way interaction in which the selected trainers learned about all the important concepts such as SDGs, 10Cs, six learning pillars and four pillars of sustainable justice. Since most of these concepts were new to them, we have discussion at the end of session. We also distributed questionnaire to assess their understanding about the training's content. After attending four workshops, majority of the teacher educator have a good understanding on

developing ICTeEfS curriculum and they were ready to be a trainer on ICTeEfS in their institution. They had enough knowledge and skills on ICTeEfS. In the 5th stage, the same process of evaluation is continued for the final recipients, the learners through transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom. Finally, a system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages that help to sustain the proper functioning and possible upgrading of the training process (sixth stage).

While for course revision, the DeCoRe+ methodology (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) by Makrakis (2017) was applied. According to him, the DeCoRe+ is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes.

- i. **Diagnosing:**
In this step, we need to reflect on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
- ii. **Deconstructing:**
Need to analyse critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
- iii. **Constructing:**
Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
- iv. **Reconstructing:**
Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
- v. **Implementing:**
Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
- vi. **Finalising:**
Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Fig. 2. The DeCoRe+ interaction (Makrakis, 2017).

By using DeCoRe+, we reviewed General Science Teaching Methods. We answer all the questions given in the template. The syllabus was reviewed by external evaluator for two times. Finally, we have the final draft of DeCoRe+ document. We add new elements in our course which are, 10Cs, six learning pillars for sustainable development and four dimensions of sustainable justice.

The element of 10Cs that integrated in this course were:

- i. Constructing knowledge**
In this course, students learned not only the teaching theories, teaching approach, issues in science learning, but also learned about science education and SDGs, lab management, nature of science, etc. With these topics, students will get knowledge and experience and be ready for next teaching methods in second semester.
- ii. Collaboration**
In this course all students worked together in a group. They worked for group assignment in doing their project which focused on designing ESD module. In this project, they need to find a solution for the selected issues. They also worked in pair for their simulated teaching. In this assignment, they need to teach based on their lesson plan.
- iii. Communication**
In doing the assignment, students need to present their project. During lecture, lecturer also gave an 'issue to ponder' for them to discuss.
- iv. Critical thinking**
In doing project, they need to analyse the issues related to SDGs in order to develop the e-module.
- v. Creativity**
In designing the e-module, they need to be creative to make sure the module is interesting and doable
- vi. Cross-cultural understanding**
Since the project and simulated teaching were group assignment, their partner need to be different race, religion and culture. In Malaysia we have 3 different races, Malay, Indian and Cina. They worked as one group, Malaysian.
- vii. Co-responsibility**
In doing the project, they be able to notice how important they are to play an active role in disseminating knowledge about SDGs to school and public.
- viii. Connectivity**
In this part, they need to do simple investigation about issues in SDGs and provide solution on it.
- ix. Critical consciousness**
By having the project, they analysed the data, and the finding would raise students' critical consciousness about the importance of SDGs and the health of our earth.
- x. Critical reflection**
At the end simulated teaching, they need to do the reflection.

The six learning pillars for sustainable development were:

- i. Learning to know**
Students learn about the related learning theories and teaching methods, SDGs, etc. They were able to analyse and apply the knowledge to the real-world situation
- ii. Learning to do**
After understanding all the important concepts in general science teaching methods, they were able to

design and conduct interactive learning activities in their presentations and projects including by using ICTs.

- iii. Learning to be**
In here, they were able to contribute to the society by having a project. Thus, they knew how to develop their self-potential.
- iv. Learning to live together**
In doing the assignments, they respect the rules and regulation of the university and faculty. They also realized how to be a good citizen in diversity backgrounds.
- v. Learning to transform oneself and society**
Students also learn on how to build up their positive attitude and personality, and at the same time give positive impact and influence on others.
- vi. Learning to give and share**
They were able to share views and opinions about certain issues especially in doing project and simulated teaching. They respect others opinion to find the best solutions to solve real-life problems related to their project.

Then, four dimensions of sustainable justice also integrated in this course. There were:

- i. Environmental justice**
In this course, all assignments have been submitted through e-learning@usm.
- ii. Social justice**
All learning materials distributed through eLearning@USM and accessible to registered students.
- iii. Economy Justice**
Students are equipped with stable internet infrastructure - Wi-Fi connection. Once they registered as USM students, they will be given a username and password that will be used throughout their study at USM.
- iv. Cultural Justice**
Active involvement in class discussion and activities is necessary - students are expected to be involved and participated in all activities that will be carried out during lectures and tutorials.

Even though, all of these were new elements to us, but we did not have difficulties in integrated them since USM was already has the sustainable elements in most of the courses.

After understanding all the fundamental concepts, we developed modules based on the course syllabus for General Science Teaching Methods by infusing the concepts mentioned above. It has four modules based on the course learning outcomes. The modules as below:

- i. Module 1: Explain the theory and strategy of teaching science**

- ii. Module 2: Implement science teaching based on the teaching plan (in line with the National Science Education Philosophy) in a group
- iii. Module 3: Demonstrate appropriate science process skills and thinking skills in science teaching.
- iv. Module 4: Integrate appropriate SDG goals in preparing ESD modules with emphasis on SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG 13 (Climate Change) and SDG 15 (Life on Land)

With all the requirements from School of Educational Studies, USM, and ICTeEfS projects, as a course developer, we update the course contents, skills and also the sustainability concepts. In addition, with the Covid-19 pandemic, the use of ICT as teaching tools become necessary.

During the implementation of the syllabus, we reviewed the course by using the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology proposed by Makrakis (2023). The processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process which aims not only assess a course but more importantly to make whatever changes in order to improve it. Refer to Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. The DREAM methodology by Makrakis (2023)

12. Findings and Discussion

Based on the DREAM methodology, we reviewed the students' feedback according to the stages above. From the diagnose findings, most of our students never attended a course on this topic and skills area in the past. They also

never created a project or written work like this course and never dealing with the same issues as the topic of this course. It means that this course gave them first experience on the knowledge and skills about this course and know how to create and dealing issues. They hope they will learn a lot about teaching methods in which they can be a good and effective science teacher.

In review/reflect stage, majority of the students said the course that they took is easy to score since they have a perception that to be a teacher is easy. They also have a perception that teacher's role and responsibility was only focusing on teaching process. Findings also revealed that their perception on the pedagogical knowledge especially on the teaching method, the curriculum and syllabus were easy to learn. Most them had positive incidents since they learned a lot about the science teaching technique. Their confidence level improved. They were able to write a good lesson plan. Their negative incident was attending the online class (Covid-19 era).

After attending the course, they mentioned that in this course, they need to learn and understand about learning theories and approaches to be an effective science teacher. They learnt about how to write a good lesson plan, how to be creative in teaching, and how to manage the classroom. They learned a lot of teaching techniques and strategies, holistic approaches and about SDGs. For them, SDGs is a new topic. This course gave them experience on how to be a teacher since they need to do the teaching simulation. With simulated teaching, they could enhance their teaching skills and communication skills.

From these findings, it can be concluded that most of the students are very concern about their professional development and self-development as future science teacher. They want to be a good science teacher where they can handle everything in class (class management) and prepare good activities for their student. In addition, they also want to have a good grade for this course. Thus, as a course coordinator, I believed that this course helps them in maximizing their potential as a science teacher for the future. However, findings revealed that they had a different expectation about the course at the end of semester. They never expected that there were too many concepts to learn on how to be a good quality science teacher such as learned on how to integrate ICT in their teaching, assessment, teaching approaches, etc. For them, being a teacher was not as easy as they think especially in the 21st century.

Since their expectation was difference, they built a strong self-resilience. Resilience can be developed through experience. With resilience, students could have a better grade in this course. According to Waxman et.al. (2003), students with resilience will succeed in the school and always display courage, motivation and maintain a positive mindset. (Education Hub, n.d). In addition, they also have a

better physiological well-being. With these characteristics, it is a hope that preservice teachers from USM could be the best teacher.

They also feel satisfied with the course since they have learned so many things in the course such as different approaches, variety of IT software/apps since most of the lectures and simulated teaching were conducted online. For them, it is a new experience. As a conclusion, the difference expectation brings benefits to students: self-resilience and self-satisfaction.

In assess stage, every student did a concept map about what they have learned in this course. From their concept map, I summarized as below in figure 4.

As observed, in this course, students learned various concepts, including pedagogical content knowledge, learning theories, informal science learning, current issues in science education, and the role of teachers, among others. Thus, it can be concluded that students learned numerous concepts in this course to enhance their self-development as future science teachers. They also learned about ESD, including air, water, quality education, and health, in this course (refer to Figure 4). It means that this course reflected the current curriculum in the Malaysian system of Education.

At the end of the semester, all students submitted their e-module as their final product in groups. However, they were more interested in SDG 2, 12, and 13 instead of SDG 6 and 15. From the module, they have a good understanding of those SDGs. They were able to explain the three SDGs in detail and relate them to their real-life experiences.

After attending the course, the findings showed that the impact on their knowledge contributes to their academic development, such as increasing their knowledge on teaching methods, 21st-century learning skills, SDG, how to do the lesson plan properly, pedagogy, psychology, and how to be a good teacher. They also mentioned that their ICT skills also improved. For them, this course helped them improve their self-development as future science teacher.

In terms of professional development, the findings showed that the impact on their professional development that makes them more competent in terms of problem-solving skills since they need to think critically on how to solve issues (about their project assignment). They also learnt on how to be an effective communicator since for them teacher need to have a good communication skill. They also improved their teamwork skills. They also mentioned that after taking the course, they know teachers' role and responsibility was challenging. They need to be as a risk-taker and multi-tasking.

While for social development, the impact towards them, they were more aware on environmental issues and be proactive in sharing those issues to the society. For students' personality, the impact on them were, they were able to enhance their confidence level, more creative, positive attitudes and perseverant.

In manage stage, they feel they were ready mentally and physically to be a teacher. They were ready to go to school and take on the challenge as beginner teachers. They were able to apply all the knowledge to make the teaching and learning process meaningful. They were also able to plan a lesson plan that is more suitable in the 21st century and know how to use ICT effectively.

However, they have suggestions as they would like to have simulated teaching in school, not in the classroom. They also proposed conducting a fieldwork visit to implement the SDG activity, as it would be a place where they could gain experience by applying what they have learned. This situation reflects to "learning by doing". Learning by doing will make the class atmosphere lively, and students will actively engage in their learning process (Fitzsimons, 2014; Abuzandah, 2020). However, this could not happen since all classes were online classes due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

After I revised and made certain changes to the courses, it became apparent that they had had a positive impact on our students. Before the revision, we did not focus on students' potential. Most of us focus on academic performance. Because of this, the teaching and learning process should provide students with a meaningful experience. Thus, we need to review our learning outcomes, as Roa (2019) mentioned that the outcome serves as the basis for effective interaction among concerned stakeholders and is a product of learning, a so-called learning product. In addition, the integration of 10Cs, which encompasses six learning pillars for sustainable development and four dimensions of social justice, makes students more aware of sustainable issues in their daily lives.

Regarding the content revision, we focused not only on cognitive development but also on affective and psychomotor development. Roa (2019) stated that non-

cognitive factors are also important for students' development. With these two factors, the learning process would be more meaningful. Students would be more appreciative and practice what they have learned in their daily life. Thus, transformative learning occurred, as it involved an ontological process where students can experience a change in their being (Ilisko, 2007) and enact their sense of social responsibility (Cranton, 1994). With this type of learning, preservice teachers will be agents of change where they could transform knowledge and skills to students in creating a sustainable society for the future.

4. Conclusion

As Universiti Sains Malaysia is the University in a Garden and always a leader in sustainability, the application of sustainability elements in teaching and learning process is a need. Integrating SDGs in the General Science Teaching Methods gave students a lot of knowledge and experience on how to be agents of change in sustainability. It is a hope that this course be able to provide student teachers with adequate information and understanding on how to deliver the SDGs concepts – knowledge and skills in school. With this ability, they can convey this element of sustainability to students and these students will be agents in conveying the message of sustainability to society.

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The Development of Participatory Videos (PVs) as Reflective Approach in Infusing SDGs in Curriculum Using ICT as Enablers

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Abstract

The production of a Participatory Video (PV) is a method that was adapted from the Participatory Learning and Action (PLA) Approach. The reflection activity in PLA should be based on the participants' experiences and should be conducted as a cycle of activities. In the context of this project, PVs are prepared by teachers to share their experiences in infusing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the subjects that they teach, through the medium of ICT. Before coming up with the individual PVs, teachers were asked to develop the lesson plan for topics that would be recorded as PVs. Then, when the lesson plans were ready, the teachers were required to develop a storyboard based on the lesson plan that they had designed. A total submission of 100 lesson plans, 100 storyboards and 100 participatory videos were submitted by the teachers. Throughout the development of PV, both researchers and teachers were directly exposed to the opportunity to reflect on their own practices in infusing SDGs in classroom and act towards that reflection. Since development of PVs involves analytical and reflective exercises about the project in which the teachers as the community are involved in, the group can convey what and how they have done on SDGs, from their perspectives. Indirectly, the production of the PVs encourages teachers to work together and help each other on how to implement sustainability by using ICT. Simultaneously, PVs help both teachers to widely disseminate those strategies to their colleagues through the in-house training.

Keywords: Participatory Video, Sustainable Development Goals, reflection activity

Introduction

Participatory Video (PV) is a method that was adapted from the Participatory Learning and Action (PLA) Approach through production of filmmaking or video. PLA encourages the participants to reflect upon and analyze the project in which they are involved via filmmaking (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Ludwin & Capstick, 2015). The basis of PLA is organisational learning theory, which elaborates on the process of learning within an organisation and how this process can enhance the organisation's performance. Thus, evaluation and reflection play an important role in PLA (Gustav et al., 2007). The reflection activity in PLA should be based on the participants' experiences and should be done as a cycle of activities. Collaboration is another aspect that is important in PLA (Sitter, 2015). The objective of PLA is to initiate changes to oneself, team members, organisational members, and the social system.

In the context of this project, PVs are prepared by teachers to share their experiences in infusing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the subjects that they teach through the medium of ICT. Throughout the process, teachers reflected on their teaching techniques, skills, and activities. In using the PVs, the messages, reflections, and experiences displayed by teachers became more visible and could be used as evidence to the authorities of their efforts in integrating SDGs.

Methodology

To ensure that PVs from the teachers can be produced with minimal difficulties, several methods for addressing bureaucratic and technical issues will be highlighted. To start with the project involving service teachers, several discussions

were held with respective officers from the Kedah State Education Department (JPN). Among others, content of the discussions looked into seeking the approval and consent from the JPN on the involvement of the teachers in the project and strategies to acquire teachers' commitment in the project. Other important reasons to hold such a discussion are:

1. To overcome the aspect of bureaucracy at the school administrative level – top-down instruction from the JPN
2. To ensure commitment from the teachers
3. To enable the training to be done in schools as part of in-house training (dissemination of knowledge)

Agreements were then reached to some degree, whereby teachers involved in the project would attend several training sessions and later produce the PV individually. By participating in the PVs, teachers will receive a certification of attendance, along with points for their LADAP (Teacher's Continuous Professional Development Programme), and will also serve as trainers in the in-house training that will be conducted in their respective schools.

During the training, six topics have been identified for introduction to the teachers. In Topic 1, teachers will be introduced to concepts of Sustainable Development, Education for Sustainable Development, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and sustainable thinking. Topic 2 integrates the concept of ICT in teaching and learning for sustainability education, focusing on theories such as the 10Cs, learning pillars, and Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) across curricula, among others. Next, in topic 3, the focus was on the ICT as an enabler for ESD. Topic 3 requires teachers to participate in hands-on activities. In topic 4, they did the curriculum mapping to ensure that the content of the PV is aligned with the school curriculum.

The teachers who are involved in the trainings will produce the PVs, while their students will be indirect

participants in the PVs. The research team members from Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM) played the role as facilitators and advisors for the teachers in the planning and production of their PVs, whereby the JPN officers will monitor the progress of the teachers in ensuring the PVs will be submitted as prescribed.

There were specific characteristics of the PVs that the teachers need to develop. These characteristics were outlined for the teachers to ensure that the PVs produced would reach certain standards. These characteristics were also important as guidelines for teachers in managing their in-house training later in schools. The characteristics were:

- i. Linking the SDGs with specific topic in their syllabus, in any subject matter that they are teaching
- ii. Highlighting specific SDGs that they would like to integrate into their teaching
- iii. Highlighting specific UNESCO International Days relating to the topic of their teaching
- iv. Highlighting the elements of 6Cs (6 learning pillars - Delors, 1996) that appeared in their teaching
- v. Highlighting the elements of 10Cs (10 learning skills - Makrakis (2014), Kostoulas-Makrakis & Makrakis (2020), that appeared in their teaching
- vi. Teacher's reflection on the training and the development of the PV

Several strategies were applied to ensure that all the abovementioned characteristics would materialise in the PV. Before developing the individual PVs, teachers were asked to create a lesson plan for topics that would be recorded as PVs. A Google Classroom platform was set up for teachers to upload their lesson plans, which the facilitating team (USM researchers) would then revise and provide input on. Then, when the lesson plans were ready, the teachers were required to develop a storyboard based on the lesson plan that they had designed. Similarly, another Google Classroom platform was developed for teachers to upload their storyboards. Facilitators provided comments and input to the respective teachers to improve the designed storyboards.

Though some teachers are familiar with producing videos, and preparing teaching materials using videos, producing a PV might be different and can be confusing. Moreover, the PVs in this project should be able to highlight the integration of SDGs in the teachings. Thus, teachers need to fulfil what is needed in each specific stage in the preparation of their PVs. Those stages are the Pre-Planning Stage, Planning Stage, Production Stage and Dissemination Stage.

1.1 Pre-planning Stage

For the pre-planning stage of the PVs, four steps were involved, which are:

1. Searching and looking into good examples
2. Identifying and analysing local problems
3. Looking for suitable participants
4. Building participatory communication

For step 1, teachers need to choose and decide on the topic that they would showcase in their PVs. Thus, to do this,

teachers need to explore the DSKP (Standardised Document on Curriculum and Assessment) to look for content and do some literature review in the aspect of SDGs. Then in step 2, where identifying and analysing local problems are concerned, teachers tried to relate the topic that they have chosen in the DSKP with relevant sustainability issues associated with the problems faced by the local community. In this aspect, the issues regarding sustainability chosen might be different from one community to another, mainly due to the differences in the location and background of the community. Producers tasked for the PVs are the participants of the training i.e., the teachers that have been identified by the JPN. The teachers were identified based on their subject area, namely the science subjects, mathematics, language, and social science subjects such as moral education and geography.

Furthermore, to ensure that there is two-way communication happening between the facilitators (cum researchers) and the teachers (participants of the training), a Telegram group was established to facilitate the process.

1.2 Planning Stage

The planning stage is perhaps the most critical step to produce a meaningful PV. Teachers began to develop their lesson plans according to the topics that the teachers have identified from the DSKP, and the learning outcomes of the lesson. At this stage, teachers would also design their teaching and learning activities, highlighting the elements of 6Cs and 10 Cs skills that they were exposed to earlier.

Teachers were given between two weeks to almost two months to produce their PVs, starting from the process of planning the lesson plan, designing the storyboard to implementing the teaching in their schools and finally, producing a PV. Teachers were given the flexibility in their work schedule. Nevertheless, monitoring strategies were done with the help of the JPN (State Education Department) officers. Thus, the activities in preparing the lesson plan were an important strategy taken to ensure a smooth and systematic development of the storyboard. The teachers were then required to extend the content of the lesson plan into a storyboard. As the development of the storyboard is important as part of the production process of the PV, the submission of a storyboard is made compulsory to the teachers.

1.3 Production Stage

Regarding the production aspect, the process would involve doing editing, giving accreditation and an assessment. The main issue with the editing is time. Teachers need to hurry to record their videos, as they need to do so within the period of the school term. During the implementation of this project, the

covid19 was at its peak. Thus, the school environment was facing constant change, shifting frequently from F2F to virtual mode, depending on number of Covid-19 cases in their schools and localities. In terms of the technicalities, not many problems have arisen since most of the teachers involved are young teachers, part of the ‘Guru Pewaris Negara’ group of teachers with potential, whom have been very much exposed to the ICT and digital tools in developing and editing the PVs.

A standard introductory page format was prepared for the PVs. Specific SDG goals were mentioned in the title of the PV, together with the topic chosen to ensure that the SDGs were given special note. In this section, accreditation was given to the developer of the PV, the Erasmus team, JPN, and the teachers’ respective schools. Copyright was not yet applied. The footage was also not yet captured. In testing the validity and the functionality of the PV, specific rubrics were used to map the data gained from formative assessment and data generated through participant observation, focus groups, semi-structured interviews, informal conversations, and participatory learning activities.

1.4 Dissemination Stage

Dissemination of knowledge happens when the different layers of trainings were executed, from the researchers to the teachers, and from the teachers to their colleagues in their respective schools through the in-house training. The dissemination of knowledge also happens through the content of the PVs produced by the teachers. At the level of JPN, teachers who produced best PVs were given acknowledgement and special appreciation. Their PV were also displayed within the circle of teachers to be learnt and exemplified.

Result

A total submission of 100 lesson plans, 100 storyboards and 100 participatory videos were submitted by the teachers. The length of each video differs from one to another, ranging from as short as five minutes to 25 minutes. From these participatory videos, the breakup of the SDGs integrated into the videos are as indicated in the table below:

	SDGs	No of Participatory Video
1.	GOAL 1: No Poverty	7
2.	GOAL 2: Zero Hunger	3
3.	GOAL 3: Good Health and Well-being	23
4.	GOAL 4: Quality Education	16
5.	GOAL 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth	3
6.	GOAL 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure	6
7.	GOAL 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities	9
8.	GOAL 12: Responsible Consumption and Production	2
9.	GOAL 13: Climate Change	5
10.	GOAL 14: Life below Water	1
11.	GOAL 15: Life on Land	11
12.	GOAL 16: Peace and Justice Strong Institutions	7
13.	GOAL 17: Partnership to Achieve the Goals	4

Table 1: Breakup of SDGs in teachers PV

1.5 Reflection from teachers and facilitators

Most teachers have given positive feedbacks on the trainings given to them. Almost half of the teachers found that the trainings had given them the chance to explore new strategies in infusing sustainability in their teachings effectively, which consequently opened the minds of their students regarding sustainability issues happening around them. Such response could be extracted from the reflections given by the teachers at the final part of their PVs. Some excerpts of their reflections are as follows:

“The implementation of SDGs in teaching and learning has opened the minds of students about the role and responsibility as an individual in taking care of daily nutrition”

“The implementation of the SDGs in teaching and learning has opened the minds of students about the role and responsibility as an individual in protecting animals that are threatened with extinction.”

Furthermore, students have become more active and their focus on learning has improved with the use of ICT in the classroom.

“I can also see that students are more fun and active during in the classroom,”

“I found that the use of ICT can improve the students' skills and abilities in using ICT. Next, the use of ICT in T&L can attract students' interest and focus on class. Finally, the use of ICT can help teachers become more creative in planning the lesson.”

Most teachers also agree that integrating elements of sustainability in the curriculum is very suitable for students because students can relate the SDGs to their daily lives at home and in school.

“Pupils can make connections with their daily lives such as personal hygiene care and foster an attitude of personal hygiene care as a teenager”

“Finally, students can relate the SDGs to current issues and their daily lives.”

However, one of the language teachers found that the application of SDG in his curriculum was not suitable because he thought that language subjects should focus more on the fundamental skills of listening, reading, writing, and speaking. He added that the language subject focuses more on aspects of grammar, morphology, and vocabulary.

“In addition, the application of SDG in the subject of Arabic is not suitable because learning Arabic revolves around four basic skills, namely listening, speaking, reading, and writing for words, phrases, sentences, and texts. Learning Arabic is also limited to aspects of grammar, morphology, and vocabulary. Even so, the application of ICT in

teaching is very important in accordance with the development of science and technology”

There are also a few teachers expressing their opinion that planning learning and teaching that involves elements of sustainability and the use of ICT has made them feel burdened with time and workload.

“SDG learning is felt to be important, but the addition of things that need to be included in the construction of RPH (lesson plan) causes the teacher's workload to increase. With hours that exceed 30 hours a week, teachers are not able to include those elements during the construction of lesson plan”

Teacher also mentioned that the benefit from the workshop were empowerment, self-learning, and self-confidence.

“For me, some of the benefit will be empowerment...teachers’ empowerment in T&L process using ICT with SDGs an element to be integrate in our current curriculum...it will help especially the slow learners. Their interest will increase.”

“The benefits are self-encouragement, self- learning where the teacher makes their own participatory video, it empowers their self- confidence.”

The teacher stated that the trainings help them to enhance their professional development that be used in their classroom.

“I think that I can include in our classroom. We work together in this workshop and understand what had been learnt here and will implement it in our practice.”

“Yes, I think I can use it. What I get from this workshop I can use it in my classroom.”

Overall, the teachers really hope that such trainings could be developed further to improve the professionalism of teachers and produce more teachers who are ready to implement the latest pedagogy that is in line with today's educational technology.

1.6 Time of trainings for PVs

In developing the PVs, teachers should first be exposed to the philosophy of PVs development, the importance of PVs and the strategies and techniques in developing the PVs. The preparation of the storyboard, and lesson plan were among aspects that need to be exposed to teachers as the community that would later develop the PVs.

Equally important are main concepts of SDGs, its important elements and strategies on how they could be infused in the teachers’ teaching activities. Relevant ICT tools were also introduced to teachers in assisting them in infusing SDGs in their classroom. Thus, significant number of hours has been allocated to train the teachers on these aspects of training and PVs development. Table 2 below indicated the specific hours dedicated for the trainings that covered both, from researchers to the teachers, and teachers to their colleagues.

Table 2: Tabulation Information of Trainings on SDGs and PVs

Cohort	Day, Date	Mode of Delivery		
		face to face (F2F)	Sync hr onous	Async hr onous
1 (40 teachers)	Sunday 07 November 2021	7H and 15 min		28 H
	Monday 08 November 2021	4 hours		16
	Sunday 14 November 2021	7H		68
	Monday 15 November 2021	3.5H		16 H
Total Hours				153 TH and 45 minutes.
2 (210 teachers)	Sunday 10th April 2022		4 H	28 H
	Tuesday 12th April 2022		4 H	16 H
	Sunday, 17th April 2022		4 H	68 H
	Tuesday, 19th April 2022		4 H	16 H
	Total Hours			153 TH and 45 minutes.

1.7 Coaching and mentoring

Related to the aspect of coaching and mentoring, online coaching and mentoring approaches were adopted in ensuring the best result of the training. Al Hilal, et.al. (2020) mentioned that coaching and mentoring has proven to be critical methods of development and learning used to bring about change, develop efficiency, raise awareness, and change attitudes and behaviors in organizations.

The researchers played the role of coaches and mentors to the teachers in integrating SDGs via ICT in their teaching and learning activities. It was also the role of the researchers to guide teachers in developing lesson plans and PV. Platforms like WhatsApp, Telegram, and Google Classroom (GC) were used as mediums of communication between the researchers and the teachers, as well as the community that develops the PVs. Thus, a two-way interaction occurs, as any queries or questions asked by teachers are answered directly by the researchers through these mediums of communication. our teams' members. Such strategy could be considered as a successful one since all teachers able to produce lesson plans and PVs.

1.8 Skills developed through this process

The involvement of teachers in the trainings on SDGs and PVs development has helped them to further develop their skills in moving towards 21st-century learning. The main skills developed, as highlighted in their reflection, are critical thinking skills. Teachers not only convey the knowledge found in textbooks, but they also need to be aware of issues that occur in the country and globally, so that they can be discussed with students in class to spread awareness. Next, another skill that the teachers highlighted is the collaboration skills.

“Competencies such as critical thinking, envisioning future scenarios and making collaborative decisions among students can also be empowered”

“We collaborate among us - the participants today, to make videos together, starting with story board, we discuss and communicate about an issue.”

The involvement of teachers from various levels and school areas has built a new network and fostered a spirit of cooperation among teachers throughout the workshop. Finally, teachers contended that through the trainings and the exercise of the PVs, they can improve their digital learning skills.

“The use of ICT in the T&L process helps teachers to attract students' interest so that the learning session can take place effectively. This organized program provides a lot of useful input to new teachers in facing today's digital world.” The teachers who are involved in the trainings could explore more deeply the knowledge of ICT to be practiced in schools. These skills are very important for today's teachers to make the right decisions in dealing with all the possibilities that may occur, such as the Covid-19 pandemic

which has brought about limitations in physical learning.

Discussion

PVs help both researchers and teachers to widely disseminate the strategy in infusing SDGs in classrooms using ICT as enablers. Additionally, throughout the development of PV, both researchers and teachers had the opportunity to reflect on their own practices in integrating the SDGs into the classroom and take action based on that reflection. Since the development of PVs involves analytical and reflective exercises about the project in which the teachers, as the

community, are involved, the group can convey what they have done on SDGs and how from their perspectives.

On the other hand, in producing the PVs, teachers need to discuss with their colleagues on the content and presentation of the video. Indirectly, the production of PVs encourages teachers to work together and help each other with implementing sustainability using ICT. Together, the teachers then, create effective strategies to infuse SDGs in the classroom. This aligns with Kindon's (2003) assertion that PV enables participants to create new narratives within their life context.

PV offers teachers to express themselves on what they did in their classroom or in schools and encourage them to be more confident in integrating SDGs within their subjects. By giving them a chance to express themselves through PV, they will strive to integrate SDGs into the classroom and demonstrate this through their presentations in PV, utilizing a process of mediated self-representation. Such exercises could encourage teachers to be an active teachers compared to before. Through PV teachers gained an understanding of their situation (curriculum and classroom), confidence and an ability to integrate and to improve their teaching (Sarvaes, 1996)

At the end of training on SDGs integration in curriculum ad PV development, teachers showed confidence in putting more effort in integrating SDGs by using ICT; strengthened their relationship with school community; applied lessons; and expressed their insights in on SDGs. They managed to plan the design (storyboard), implement their lesson plan that incorporated SDGs in the classroom, and conduct a reflection on their efforts.

The exercise of sharing videos with the rest of their colleagues and other school community also helped others to enhance awareness and capacity to integrate SDGs and related issues in school. Thus, indirectly, the professional development of the teachers was improved, as well as their quality of teaching. They were also able to synergise their students and local communities in tackling sustainability problems. It could be seen that when teachers became more knowledgeable on SDGs and pedagogical aspect in integrating SDGs in the classroom, the teachers' quality of teaching would be enhanced. On the other hand, from the side of the students, they became more active and their focus on learning has improved with the use of ICT in the classroom. Thus, both sides, teachers and students, gained benefits from the production of the PVs.

Another important note that could be highlighted is the two-way communication that happened throughout the process of producing the PVs. During the different layers of trainings (one organized by researchers and others in their schools) there is two-way communication, which demands the teachers' willingness to hear and learn from other participants, and finally produce a decision on which topic from each subject, what SDGs will be focused, how to integrate and how to perform in participatory video. In trainings organized by the researchers, the relationship between the researcher and the participants (teachers) is altered (Chambers, 1995), where the researcher is part of this knowledge construction, not independent of it (Kane, 1995).

Through an interactive and integrative approach, participants are encouraged to share their feelings (connectedness), evaluate their actions for their social and environmental impact, and fulfill the objectives of PV

(integrative thinking), while also helping others through their comments or suggestions (cooperative enactment).

Conclusion

Developing PVs is a new experience to researchers and teachers; as the community that participated directly in the project of infusing SDGs in curriculum using ICT as enablers. PVs could be an effective medium in conveying messages about SDGs, strategies in teaching the concepts of SDGs in classroom, also in presenting meaningful messages about SDGs to relevant authorities in the sphere of educational field and relevant stakeholders for the betterment of the future generation. From the PVs, it is also evidence that students have become more active and their focus on learning has improved with the usage of ICT by teachers in the classroom.

Acknowledgments

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SESSION E

Art Education: Deconstruction, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDG

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Abstract

Sustainable development at the local level should engage several groups, rather than being a one-way street. The Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013–2025 has transformed how and where students are taught. Education can help students develop durable behaviours (EfS). Much work remains to curtail unsustainable development. Education should impact the deep shift caused by the sustainable development paradigm. Higher education institutions will have a significant challenge in the 21st century: teaching professionals who are critical of their frames of reference and can adapt them to achieve sustainable development goals. Teachers in the classroom are the actual change agents in Asia, not EfS or the SDGs. Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam must train teachers on ICTs, climate change, and other environmental challenges. This study observes SDG in Art Education online learning. It examines the level of ICT competency among online learners and evaluates the efficiency of the learning framework based on DeCoRe+ on the 21st-century learning pillars: Learning to know, Learning to be, Learning to do, Learning to live sustainably and Learning to give and share. The survey gathers data from in-service teachers after their training. The survey is based on the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess, and Manage) method purported by Makrakis (2023). This study will show how art education content affects in-service teachers' students' ICT use during learning. This study will examine how art education course themes affected participants' careers, jobs, and academic preferences. The study will also address SDG components learnt through art education.

Keywords: SDG, Art Education, DeCoRe+, Teachers Training, ICT

1. Introduction

In recent decades, humanity has faced the impacts of unsustainable economic development driven by profit maximization, resulting in the excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite efforts to reverse unsustainable development, much remains to be done. All levels of education, but especially higher education, contribute to the global sustainability crisis. Consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are products of educational institutions, which drive society and the economy and shape an unsustainable consumer culture (Makrakis 2011). Corcoran and Wals (2004) note that the negative impacts of college graduates on Earth's natural systems are unprecedented. Education should play a key role in a radical transformation through a sustainable development model. Sustainable well-being is similar to Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being, as opposed to hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). Makrakis (2006; 2017) developed the concept of "sustainability justice" to reflect the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture.

In recent decades, much has been invested in environmental education, but it has focused more on positive

attitudes than environmental action. Environmental action requires a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. Higher education does not necessarily lead to more sustainable thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). Mismatched environmental attitudes and actions reflect education practises and other factors. Recent curriculum development studies on sustainability have shown that lecturing is the most common teaching method, while role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning are less common (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021). Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013; 2014) revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for higher education institutions is to train professionals who are critical of and capable of acting to transform their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. Teacher educators and primary and secondary classroom teachers face a similar challenge. Teaching staff are change agents in promoting an EfS approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016; 2018; Blake et al., 2013) and turning schools sustainable (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

1.1 Background of Study: The ICTeEfS project in the Context of Art Education in Open University Malaysia

HBEF 1403 Seni Dalam Pendidikan (Art in Education) is the undergraduate core course in the Bachelor of Teaching Primary Education (BTPE) programme. This three-credit-hour course can be completed entirely online in 8 to 15 weeks. The course focuses on the concepts of art education, visual art, music, and the fundamentals of movement, all of which require imagination, expression, inquiry, and multiple intelligences to optimize and enjoy learning. The course also provides opportunities for teachers to participate in activities that explore, experience, and express the sensitivity of children's senses.

Figure 1: The Community of Inquiry (CoI) Model of Engagement by Garrison, Anderson & Archer (2000).

The teaching and learning approach (see Figure 1) includes synchronous, totally online face-to-face tutorials performed via Google Meet to enable interactions between learners and instructors (Teaching Presence), as well as an asynchronous online forum to facilitate interactions between learners and peers (Social Presence). The forum uses OUM's MyInspire LMS. Cognitive Presence is achieved through online modules and e-lessons.

OUM's module has a "self-check" and "activities" component. Both sections urged participants to test/check their knowledge after completing the module and undertake the specified activities in groups or individually. E-lessons are based on each topic of the module. Included within each E-lesson are OERs, videos, reading materials, references, discussion questions, pre and posttests.

1.2 Problem Statement

Efforts have been made to reverse unsustainable development, but much work still needs to be done. Education should play a pivotal role in the profound transformation that will occur as a result of the sustainable development model. The application of the SDGs in the visual arts must be clearly stated in any planning document for teaching and learning. A paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and the curriculum is required for effective environmental action. Training professionals who are critical of the frames of reference they use and capable of acting to modify such frames to attain sustainable development goals and objectives is one of the most significant challenges that higher education institutions will face in the 21st century. Integration of SDG in visual arts needs to be relooked at in terms of its formulation of

instructional strategy in online learning due to its tangible learning outcomes. Promoting sustainable development should not be a one-way street on the local level; instead, it should involve several parties. Both teaching and learning in schools have been altered due to the Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025, which outlines the system's five goals. Education in sustainable practices can help overcome these challenges (EfS). Teachers in the classroom are the true agents of change, even though governments in Asia are committed to EfS and concerned about the SDGs. Educators in Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam must receive training on ICTs, climate change, and other environmental risks.

1.3 Research Objectives and Research Questions

In line with the study's aim, this research seeks to answer the following questions.

Table 1 Coherency table Research Objectives and Research Questions

Research Objectives	Research Questions
1. Observe the integration of SDG in Art Education course in an online learning	RQ4: What is the elements of SDG gained from the learner's experience in undergoing the art education course RQ2: Do the learners take the course in line with their ability in making decisions?
2. Examine the level of ICT competency amongst the online learners	RQ1: What is the level of frequency amongst the learners on accessing online materials and social media?
3. Evaluate the effectiveness of the learning structure designed based on DeCoRe+ on the 21st-century learning pillars (Learning to know, Learning to be, Learning to do, Learning to live together sustainably and Learning to give and share)	RQ5: What is the greatest impact of the topics in the course on the learners? RQ6: What are learners' reactions to the differences from their expectations? RQ7: What is the impact of the course on the academic development of the learners RQ3: Does the course enrolled related to the learner's job?

2.0 Literature Review: Education & SDG

In a local context, efforts to promote sustainable development should not be one-sided; all communities should be exposed to the concept. Education for Sustainable Development was first officially recognized at the Earth Summit Conference in Rio de Janeiro in 1992, which led to the formation of Agenda 21. Each chapter of Agenda 21 emphasises education, but Chapter 36 focuses specifically on improving basic education, adapting existing education to sustainable development, improving community understanding and awareness, and training. (2017). In 2001, Malaysia's Ministry of Housing and Local Government launched Local Agenda 21, a follow-up to the 1992 UN Rio Conference (GDRC.org, 2022). Malaysia's plan requires all levels of society to participate in education for sustainable development.

The Malaysian Ministry of Education (MoE) developed the Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 in 2013. This Blueprint has changed school teaching and learning. New preschool, primary, and secondary curricula were developed to align with the Blueprint's educational objectives. The Blueprint is comprehensive to ensure the holistic development and full potential of students. The blueprint outlines five system aspirations, six student aspirations, and 11 reform shifts. The 5 Systems Aspirations are the MoE's goals for the education system. These include 1) ACCESS: to ensure 100 percent enrolment across all levels from preschools to upper secondary; 2) QUALITY: focusing on achievement in reading, math, and science; 3) EQUITY: equal opportunities for all (urban-rural, socio-economic, gender, indigenous communities, special needs children); 4) UNITY: promotes shared values and experiences by encouraging students to embrace diversity; and 5) EFFICIENCY: maximises student outcome within the current nation's resources.

Malaysia's education system is based on the Philosophy of National Education (FPK), enacted in 1996. FPK emphasises that education is a continuous effort to develop individuals' intellectual, spiritual, emotional, and physical potential. Thus, FPK's perspective and view of nature align with the SDGs, especially UNESCO's four pillars of learning agenda for the 21st century, announced in 1996, and the global SDG agenda, 2016-2030. (Widad et. al., 2022)

2.0 Literature Review

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2.1 SDG in Teaching & Learning

2.2.1 SDG in Art Education

Lack of logic, natural geographic roots, and common knowledge are all essential variables that should be considered when discussing culture. The human capacity for inventiveness was the driving force behind the development of a peculiar cultural phenomenon. The cultural manifestation referred to as art encompasses various fields, including writing, performing arts, visual arts, theatre, and film.

Art is an inseparable part of culture and has the unique role in the development of human civilization. As mentioned above, along with crafts, we also consider art as a mean of implementing sustainable development. In particular, we will rely on aesthetics and modern trends of one of the directions of "visual art" (Edisher Beradze, 2020) In developing a relationship with sustainable development, we must emphasise on implementation that involves any form of innovation for change in the social-economic.

Within the arts, we will feel these changes as well, but we will also have unique, active responsibilities. Our cultural facilities will evolve into sustainable machines and contribute to environmental health. The art and culture that we preserve and carry with us will ease migration and transition and preserve memory (Garrett, 2015 p. 121)

2.2.2 The ICTeEfS project

Environmental deterioration is one of the most evident results of Asia's fast growth. Recent climate-related disasters in Asia demonstrate that politicians must act now to safeguard residents and mitigate and reverse climate change, ensuring long-term growth. Sustainability education can help meet these difficulties (EfS). While Asian policymakers

are committed to EfS and concerned about the SDGs, classroom teachers are the primary drivers of change.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam must train teachers on ICTs, climate change, and other environmental hazards. On the one hand, education faculties must incorporate ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS) into their study programmes. Conversely, they must use these technologies to advance EfS to all in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the increasing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs necessitate the integration of ICT in teacher education programs and in-service training. ICT integration isn't only adding ICT as a subject or instrument. It requires reforms in teaching and learning and extensive ICT-enabled EfS planning in teacher education.

The proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to adopt innovative teaching techniques and pedagogies focused on Education for Sustainability (EfS). ICTeEfS is financed by the European Commission's Erasmus+ programme for 2019–2023. Specific targets include:

1. Develop education faculties at partner universities to connect curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with ES. Increase the capability of education faculty to plan, implement, and evaluate a substantial ICT-enabled in-service teacher training programme on sustainability.
2. Develop a blended learning-enabled in-service teacher professional development programme that is efficient, cost-effective, decentralised, multiplicative, and innovative, focusing on integrating education for sustainability across school curricula.
3. Create a multilingual e-Toolkit of innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials addressing sustainability education. Create a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to increase collaboration and replicability.

ICTeEfS is funded by the European Commission's Erasmus+ Higher Education Capacity Building Program for 2019-2023. Specific goals include:

1. Assist partner universities' education faculties in aligning curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with education for sustainability.
2. Develop academic staff at education faculties so they can contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of an ICT-enabled in-service teacher training program on education for sustainability.
3. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralised, multiplier, and innovative in-service teacher professional development programme enabled by blended learning, focusing on integrating education for sustainability across school curricula.
4. Create a multilingual e-Toolkit of innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials addressing education for sustainability.

5. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field and the replicability of outputs and outcomes.

3.0 Methodology

In light of the above discussed features, needs and objectives, a six-stages capacity building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006) was used.

DeCore Plus is divided into three phases. The first phase includes two concurrent tasks, Step 1: diagnostic evaluation and Step 2: deconstructing. The diagnostic review is concerned with determining what learners require, whereas deconstruction is concerned with analysing the assessment's input. Both processes result in the learner's profile.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017).

Course Development

Figure 3: The 10Cs (Makrakis, 2017)

The visual arts course covers all 10 Cs components. These components correspond to the course content. Myinspire students synthesize and transmit ideas in written, oral, and virtual modes. Students must think critically in order to respond to the challenge in the online E-Lesson. To make informed decisions and take effective action, individuals must think critically, apply relevant knowledge, analyze data, synthesize insights, and evaluate outcomes. The incorporation of 10Cs elements in the Art Education course

entails the development of instructional strategies for engaging learning activities.

The development of the content are divided into 4 main stages as synthesized from DeCoRe+ methodological approach to curriculum (Makrakis, 2017). First, trainees' didactic profiles are diagnosed. Based on trainee profiles, a training session action plan is formulated (second stage). The training content follows the action plan and combines theory and practice in thematic units or modules that can be enriched based on trainee needs (third stage). The trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and action plan aims and objectives (fourth stage). The final recipients, the learners, are evaluated by transferring their new skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A monitoring and upgrading system is integrated across all stages to maintain proper training process functioning and possible upgrading (sixth stage).

Makrakis (2017) used DeCoRe+, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, to embed sustainability and the 17 SDGs. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. DeCoRe+ has eight (8) processes.

1. Diagnosing: Reflecting on who we are, what we know, where we want to go, and why.
2. **Deconstructing:** critically analysing personal perspectives, habits of mind, and chosen curriculum units/modules.
3. Gathering resources, creating ideas, and building meaning (perspectives).
4. **Reconstructing:** Integrating newly constructed knowledge with the reconstructed frame of reference.
5. Implementing the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. Finalizing: Reflecting and evaluating what has been learned and changed.
7. Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
8. Finalizing: Reflecting on and evaluating what has been learned and changed.

3.1 DeCore+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) process in learning design

The four stages of DeCore+ are synthesized into four outputs of the process: 1) User requirement 2) Product Specification 3) Usability Testing and 4) Product Review

Table 4: Template Organizer for applying the DeCoRe+ methodological approach to curriculum (Makrakis, 2016 p. 156)

DECONSTRUCTION PROCESS	CONSTRUCTION PROCESS	CRITICAL REFLECTION	RECONSTRUCTION PROCESS
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User Requirement	Product specification	Usability Testing	Product review
1. Unit/Module 2. Method of Assessment 3. Gaps, purposeful omission and underlying assumption 4. Power and interest 5. Projected image and reality	Based on the detailed and critical answers to the deconstruction process, start the construction process by recording the main points that need changes and describing your proposals which will be used in the reconstruction process.	Reflect on what is needed to support the following four domains 1. Interactive Teaching/Learning 2. Teaching/Learning approaches 3. Learning pillars and 10Cs 4. Authenticity	Write the general goals of the unit/module: Describe what kind of previous knowledge you will use in teaching the reconstructed unit/module: Describe the characteristics of learners (e.g. skills, values, knowledge, attitudes, action competences) that will contribute to the learning outcomes

3.1.1 Deconstruction

The first stage of the course development is to determine the level of Table of Content (TOC) and category of content which will be chunked into Module, Unit and Topics. The chosen topics are then designed according to the DREAM framework (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess, and Manage). DREAM is considered as part of the strategies in the instructional design process. Makrakis (2023) proposed the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess, and Manage) method for evaluating revised courses during implementation. These processes encompass the entire course, from what students bring in before (Diagnosing), during (Reviewing, Reflecting, and Explaining), and after the course (Assessing and Managing). The DREAM method represents a critical action research process designed to assess and improve a course. Through the DREAM Methodology, the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio to give back to the instructor at the end of the course. DREAM is a course requirement. Instructors must analyse DREAM portfolios and prepare a report for the class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide important information that the instructor and students can use to improve the course.

Figure 5: The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

In Online Class Participation, students develop innovative applications and solutions based on course topics. Regarding cross-cultural competence, students explore how art is relevant to their daily lives in a multicultural and global context. This course has a final exam and course work. The course work consists of written assignments, online class participation, and online quizzes. The Online Final Exam essay accounts for 40% of the grade.

3.1.2 Construction

All course content is designed based on Malaysian Qualification Agency (MQA) standards and matches three skills: Thinking and Scientific skills, Practical skills, and Managerial and entrepreneurial skills. The learning activities use a blended-learning approach (face-to-face and Online Learning). Students must complete an Online Task and Activity, Case Study, and Visual Research.

3.1.3 Critical Reflection & Reconstruction

The elements in the Construction stage is use as an indicator to formulate and organize the course objectives, key content themes and teaching approaches. Content knowledge that is promoted in the learning unit focuses on Issues in Art Education, Child development through arts, Sensory and Arts, Basic knowledge in Visual Arts and Exploration of ideas, Experience and Expression. The course objectives are aligned with the key content themes and suggested teaching approaches as described in the table below:

Table 2 Course Objective, Key Content themes and Teaching approaches related to the theme in Visual Art course

Course Objectives	Key Content Themes	Teaching approaches
1. Apply the knowledge related to visual arts, with other related economics	Cross-cultural, environment, mutual understanding, human relationship, values and aesthetics	Art educators work with students and colleagues to appreciate their own personal and cultural identities.
2. Explain in detail on the relationship and integration of visual arts, music and movement from the rhythmic theme approach	This course shows the image of the world through the cross-cultural environment, mutual understanding, human relationships, values, and aesthetics.	Share ideas for identity exploration and creation of artworks among students and teachers.
3. Apply and use the knowledge the instructional concepts via arts for planning, design in teaching and learning activities to be integrated to other subjects	This will empower the learners to demonstrate their creativity and innovation through the creative process, through their strong ideas, expression and critical thinking ability.	Creative and critical method of inquiring through art and technology that involved creative ideas for further exploration

The teaching approaches lead to the formulation of the instructional strategy as below:

Figure 6: Task Analysis for Learning Activities in Fully Online mode for Visual Arts

expectations (Reflect: Item 4) **gained from the course.** The learners' reaction is coded into eight categories as below:

Category: reaction to the difference in expectations

1. Open-hearted
2. Open-hearted, Excited
3. Open-hearted, Enthusiastic, Excited
4. Excited
5. Fun, Open-hearted
6. Fun, Open-hearted, Enthusiastic
7. Fun, Open-hearted, Enthusiastic, excited
8. Fun, Excited

The findings on elements of SDG gained from the learner's experience in undergoing the art education course are also generated in a contingency table 2 X 2 table. The data are coded and organized into seven traits of (Item 1: Reflect) learning experiences (Lx). The seven Lx traits are then matrix with the learners' preferences based on their listed (Item 8: Diagnosis) keywords on topics they remembered while taking the course.

Category: The learner's experience in undergoing the art education course

1. This course has increased my knowledge.
2. This course is quite difficult for a student who is working.
3. Through this course assignment,
4. I found this course very interesting.
5. I enjoy doing activities
6. Not much I learned in this course.
7. Some concepts in this course are less clear.

Descriptive analysis is used to determine how often learners access online materials and social media, how well the courses they take to match up with their ability to make decisions, and how closely the courses they take relate to their jobs.

4.0 Findings and Discussion

4.1 Technology Competence

RQ1: What the level of frequency amongst the learners on accessing online materials and social media?

In terms of their technological competence, only one student (7.14%) regularly uses online materials like ebooks, e-journals, and edata bases for their studies, six (42.86%) do so frequently, and four (28.57%) do so occasionally. (N=11, 78.57%) more females than males access e-books, e-journals, and databases. Only one student (7.14%) was reported to use social media frequently, nine (64.29%) were reported to use social media occasionally, and four (28.57%) were claimed to have never used social media. One student (N=1, 7.14%) utilised Microsoft Excel, IBM SPSS, and Matlab often, whereas three students (N=3, 21.4%) had never used any of these statistical software applications. The remainder (N = 10, or 71.42%) utilise these statistical programmes occasionally. Throughout their learning path, students are required to give presentations. Consequently,

3.1.4 Construct in DeCore+ and DREAM

Table 3 Construct in DeCore+ and DREAM, Data types and it Output

Construct in DeCore+	Construct DREAM	in Data	Output
		The learners' expectation related to the reaction to the difference on their expectation	CMap
Deconstructing	Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage	Contingency table 2 X 2 between Item 3 and 4	
		The elements of SDG gained from the learner's experience in undergoing the art education course	CMap
		Contingency table 2 X 2 table	

This study uses a mixed-method dynamic research design that simultaneously blends qualitative and quantitative data within one research study. The data comprises nominal data, quantified by the 3 and 4 Likert scale and ordinal data from an open-ended question. For an open-ended question, a contingency table 2 X 2 table is used to determine the learner's expectations from the course. *A contingency table is a powerful tool in data analysis for comparing two categorical variables. Although it is designed for analysing categorical variables* (Yen-Chi Chen, 2018), The data are generated in the statistical open source software JASP to matrix the **learners' reaction to the difference in their expectations with the learners' expectations gained from the course.** A contingency table is used to determine the learner's course expectations. The data are generated in the statistical open source software JASP to matrix the (Reflect: Item 3) **learners' reaction to the difference in their**

they utilise presenting software such as Microsoft Powerpoint, Google slides, and Prezi, among others. Six students (N=6, 42.86%) used them regularly, seven students (N=7, 50%) used them rarely, and one student (N=1, 7.14%) never used them.

RQ 2: Does the course taken by the learners in line with their ability in making decision?

The majority of male learners (n=12, 85.71%) and two female learners (14.29%) pursuing this course agreed that they enjoy learning and doing new things in accordance with their decision-making ability. In fact, they will all deliberate carefully before making any decision. They can also work well in groups, remaining calm and composed during discussions. They can effectively communicate with others. They also enjoyed doing hands-on activities and challenges.

RQ 3: Does the courses enrolled related to the learner's job?

On the whole, nine (64.29%) of the learners agreed that their job is related to the course, and five (35.71%) of the learners stated that their job is unrelated to the course. Three (21.43%) of students enrolled stated that their job is irrelevant to the course, while two (14.29%) agreed that their job is related to the course.

Three (21.43%) students who took four courses stated that their job was unrelated, while two (14.29%) agreed that their job was related to the course.

Table 4 The Course Related to the Learners job

Numbers of courses enrolled	2. What course are you taking now?	5. Is your job related to this course? (D)				Total	
		No		Yes			
1	HBEF1403 Seni dalam Pendidikan (Art in Education)	3	21.43	2	14.29	5	35.71
3	HBEF1403 Seni dalam Pendidikan (Art in Education) HBEF2303 Teknologi Maklumat dalam Pendidikan (IT in Education) HBEF3103 Prinsip Teknologi Pengajaran (Principle of Instructional Technology)	1	7.14	2	14.29	3	21.43
4	HBEF1403 Seni dalam Pendidikan (Art in Education) HBEF2303 Teknologi Maklumat dalam Pendidikan (IT in Education) HBEF3103 Prinsip Teknologi Pengajaran (Principle of Instructional Technology) MPU3412 Khidmat Masyarakat (Community Service)	0	0.00	1	7.14	1	7.14
3	HBEF1403 Seni dalam Pendidikan (Art in Education) HBEF2303 Teknologi Maklumat dalam Pendidikan (IT in Education)	0	0.00	1	7.14	1	7.14

	MPU3412 Khidmat Masyarakat (Community Service)						
2	HBEF1403 Seni dalam Pendidikan (Art in Education) OUMH1603 Kemahiran Belajar untuk Abad ke-21 (21st Century Learning Skill)	1	7.14	3	21.43	4	28.57
	Total	5	35.71	9	64.29	14	100.00

RQ 4 What is the elements of SDG gained from the learner's experience in undergoing the art education course

The map below shows the findings on learning experience (Lx) that is in line with the topics learned by the learners. Based on the contingency tables, the matrix table yield three primary learning experience (Lx) as the response by the learners, i.e. Lx1: not much is learned from the course, Lx2: course is very interesting and Lx 3: Increase knowledge. According to the keywords listed by the learners on the topics learned by the learners that they remembered, almost all learners (n=9, 81.81%) responded on Lx2 and Lx3 related to the keywords including the element of SDG, as shown in the map. Two (n=2, 18.18%) of the learner listed the keywords on Lx4 focusing on the content knowledge. Only one (n=1, 9.09%) learner responded on Lx1, Lx5 and Lx7 with related keywords, as shown in the map.

Figure 7 Cmap on elements of SDG gained from the learner's experience in undergoing the art education course

RQ 5: What is the greatest impact of the Topics in the course to the learners?

Based on the findings, almost all of the topics shown in the map above were identified by learners as having the greatest impact on them. Only three males (N=3, 21.43%) reported that the affected topics with N=1, 7.14% each are children and art, SDG, and Art in Education. While the majority of

females reported with N=11, 78.57% on the impact of the course topics, as shown in the map above

Figure 8: Topics that have greatest impact to the learners in Art Education course

RQ 6: To what extent does the learners' expectation related to the reaction to the difference on their expectation?

The learners' reflections identified some expectations were not as expected, but most of the expectations are widely covered in most of the eight categories of the expectation. The reaction of the learner's expectation is found in most categories of their expectations gained from the course. The learner is open-hearted due to the friendliness of the tutor. They also feel excited with the flexible assessment supported by the user-friendly e-tutor. The learner feels fun and enthusiastic while undergoing the visual learning resources supported by the user-friendly e-tutor and ample time to complete their assignment. The student with a User-friendly e-tutor, Flexible assessment is open-hearted and excited with their expectation of the course.

Table 5 Learners' Reflection on their expectation gained from the course versus their reaction to the difference in their expectations

2. What do you expect/ expect to gain in this course?	4. What is your reaction to the difference in expectations?							
	Category							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
User friendly e-tutor								(n =1, 0.1 1)
User friendly e-tutor, Flexible assessment		(n = 1, 0.1 1)						

Flexible assessment				(n= 1, 0.1 1)				
Visual learning resources, User friendly e-tutor						(n = 1, 0.1 1)		
Visual learning resources, User friendly e-tutor	(n = 1, 0.1 1)							
Visual learning resources., Flexible assessment				(n= 1, 0.1 1)				
Visual learning resources, Ample time to complete assignment, User friendly e-tutor						(n = 1, 0.1 1)	(n =1, 0.1 1)	
Visual learning resources, Ample time to complete assignment, Flexible assessment					(n= 2, 0.2 2%)			
Ample time to complete assignment, User friendly e-tutor, Flexible assessment				(n = 1, 0.1 1)				
Total	(n = 1, 0.1 1)	(n = 1, 0.1 1)	(n = 1, 0.1 1)	(n= 2, 0.2 2%)	(n= 2, 0.2 2%)	(n = 1, 0.1 1)	(n = 1, 0.1 1)	(n =2, 0.2 2%)

Category

- 1 - Open-hearted
- 2 - Open-hearted, Excited
- 3 - Open-hearted, Enthusiastic, Excited
- 4 - Excited
- 5 - Fun, Open-hearted
- 6- Fun, Open-hearted, Enthusiastic
- 7- Fun, Open-hearted, Enthusiastic, Excited
- 8 - Fun, Excited

RQ 7: What is the impact of the course on the academic development of the learners

Students were asked to suggest things they would like to be different if they were to retake this course; suggestions are provided in the table above. The responses gathered in Category 1 (N=2, 18.18%) indicate that, through knowledge of the SDGs and information and communication technology skills, students can become more sensitive and confident. While in

Category 2 (N=5, 45.45%) demonstrates three skills gained; the students hope to have different tutors provide different methods and the opportunity to attend seminars that require field studies abroad. Do the job more thoroughly and investigate further.

Category 3 (N=4, 36.36%) reveals that, with two sets of skills gained from the course attended, students will participate full-time, be more flexible, spend extended time, and be more active in the interaction between teachers and students to deepen their knowledge of these skills.

For the final stage, students are asked to suggest how they can apply the new knowledge they have learned from the course in the future. Various suggestions include sharing knowledge with others, creating a more positive social environment, applying knowledge in family life, and exploring new ways to seek knowledge.

Table 6 Impact of the course on the academic development of the learners

1. What is the impact of this course on you - in terms of "ACADEMIC DEVELOPMENT?" (A)	2. Gender			Total
	Male	Female		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I can improve my knowledge related to the SDGs. I can improve my information and communication technology skills. 	0	0.00	2	18.18
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I can improve my knowledge related to the SDGs. I can improve my information and communication technology skills. I was able to improve my skills in seeking information from trusted sources. 	2	18.18	3	45.45
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I can improve my information and communication technology skills. I was able to improve my skills in seeking information from trusted sources. 	1	9.09	3	36.36
Total	3	27.27	8	100.00

In the ASSESS stage, students are requested to assess the impact of what has been learned in terms of Academic Development. A majority of the learners expressed that they enriched their knowledge about SDG. As for Professional

Development, a majority of them can apply the acquired knowledge in their work. Based on the responses, a majority of the learners learned to work in team in Social Development. Finally, the impact of what they learned in terms of personal development is that the students are more open-minded.

Table 7 Summary of the findings on ASSESS stage

Category	Impact of this course on you - in terms of "ACADEMIC DEVELOPMENT"	5. If you were allowed to retake this same course, how could you make it a different experience? (A)
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I can improve my knowledge related to the SDGs. I can improve my information and communication technology skills. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More sensitive and confident Give different ideas in the topics taught
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I can improve my knowledge related to the SDGs. I can improve my information and communication technology skills. I was able to improve my skills in seeking information from trusted sources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Different tutors give different methods Seminars that required me to do field studies abroad Do the job better Investigate something more thoroughly
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I can improve my information and communication technology skills. I was able to improve my skills in seeking information from trusted sources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attend full time More flexible and longer time Through active interaction between teachers and students Deepen the knowledge of skills.

5.0 Conclusion

5.1 Technology Competence

The findings on technology competence among art education students appear to be reasonable; they seem to spend more time online on social media and use presentation software such as Microsoft Powerpoint, Google Slides, and Prezi. Learners have less access to online study materials, such as e-books, e-journals, and e-databases. This is because the course was designed with 10Cs components in mind, which are covered in the visual arts course. These elements correspond to the course content. Students used Myinspire to synthesize and disseminate ideas in written, oral, and virtual forms. In this online E-Lesson, students are challenged to think critically. They must think critically, apply knowledge, analyze information, synthesize insights, and evaluate outcomes to make informed decisions and take effective action.

5.2 Ability of Decision Making and related Jobs

Most male students in this course stated that they enjoy learning and trying new things, which they attribute to their decision-making abilities. They will all deliberate carefully before making a decision. They work well in groups and remain composed during conversations. They communicate effectively. Hands-on exercises and challenges were popular, which is appropriate given the circumstances. Emphasize social-economic innovation when forming a partnership with sustainable development.

5.3 Elements of SDG and the learner's experience and impact of the topics in the course to the learners

The findings yield three primary learning experiences (Lx) as learners' responses, such as "not much is learned from the course," "the course is highly fascinating," and "the course can increase student knowledge." According to the keywords stated by the students on the themes they remembered, nearly all of them reacted to Lx2 and Lx3 related to the SDG aspect.

According to the findings, almost all of the topics depicted in the map above were identified as having the most significant impact on learners. According to the findings, the affected topics are children and art, SDGs, and Art in Education. However, it is of particular importance to take into consideration various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues pertaining to the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al., 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

5.4 Learner's expectation and the the impact of the course on the academic development of the learners

The tutor's friendliness makes the student open-hearted. They like the user-friendly e-flexible tutor's assessment. The learner enjoys the visual learning resources, user-friendly e-tutor, and ample time to complete their assignment. The student with a User-friendly e-tutor and Flexible assessment is excited about the course.

Students can become more sensitive and confident with knowledge of SDGs and ICT. The findings also show three skills gained; students hope to have different tutors give them opportunities to do field studies abroad. Improve and investigate something. It also shows that with two sets of skills from the course, students will participate full-time, be more flexible, extend their time, and be more active in teacher-student interactions to deepen their skill knowledge.

The majority of the findings are consistent with the Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025, which aims to ensure the full development and potential of students. There are five system goals, six student goals, and eleven reform shifts outlined. The 5 Systems Aspirations are the Ministry of Education's (MoE) education goals. 1) ACCESS: ensuring 100 percent enrollment across all levels from preschool to upper secondary; 2) QUALITY: emphasizing reading, math, and science; 3) EQUITY: equal opportunities for all (urban-rural, socioeconomic, gender, indigenous communities, special needs children); 4) UNITY:

encouraging students to embrace diversity; and 5) EFFICIENCY: maximizing student outcomes within the current nation's resources.

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Instructional Technology: Deconstruction, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDG

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Abstract

The Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 established a new approach to teaching and learning. ICT integration in teacher education and in-service training is crucial due to the increased availability of PC-based ICT infrastructure and the growing demand for ICT literacy. ICT integration entails more than just including ICT as a subject or tool. ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS) has the potential to promote Education for Sustainability (EfS) for all in-service teachers. Comprehensive, integrated ICT-enabled Environmental Sustainability (EfS) planning is required in teacher preparation. The proposed ICTeEfS project will develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators to utilize innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies focused on education for sustainability (EfS), taking into account all barriers and reasoning flaws. Due to the scenario, the instructional strategies should adhere to a proper instructional design process suitable for ICTeEfS. Models of instructional design (ID) improve understanding and guide ID performance. As the number and diversity of ID practices increase, implicit reservations about the reliability, validity, and usefulness of ID models imply the need for methodological guidance to produce ID models relevant to our ever-changing design issues. This study sought to provide a process model for ID model development by externalizing unique design experiences and synthesizing relevant knowledge through the DeCore+ framework and DREAM techniques in designing the entire instructional system to integrate SDG into the Principles of Instructional Technology course. To achieve the study's goal, the experience in the first content development cycle is documented to identify the critical ID model development dimensions to look for model traits, settings, and reasoning. The paper will report on the development process for the DeCore+ framework and DREAM techniques in lesson design to integrate SDGs into the course. The planning document's output is used as evidence to validate the process and conceptualize the new instructional design approach.

Keywords: SDG in Education, DeCore+, DREAM, ID process, SDG in Teachers Training

the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture.

1.0 Introduction

In recent decades, unsustainable profit-driven economic growth has drained natural resources (Makrakis, 2014; 2021). Significant work continues despite efforts to counteract unsustainable development. Higher education makes the most significant contribution to the global sustainability challenge. Educated consumers, leaders, and decision-makers affect society, the economy, and consumer culture (Makrakis, 2011). Corcoran and Wals (2004) note that college graduates harm the Earth's ecosystem. (p. 3).

Sustainable development should involve education in a fundamental change. Sustainable well-being is akin to Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being, as opposed to unsustainable production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). "Sustainability justice" reflects

In recent decades, environmental education has emphasized good attitudes over action. Teaching, learning, and the curriculum must change for environmental action. Higher education does not guarantee sustainable thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). Education and other factors contribute to a mismatch between environmental attitudes and actions. Recent curriculum development research on sustainability reveals that lecturing is the most popular teaching method, whereas role play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning are less common (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013; 2014) indicated that the great challenge of the 21st century for higher education is producing professionals who can alter their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives.

Primary and secondary instructors confront a similar challenge. Teaching staff promote an EfS approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016;2018; Blake et al., 2013) and make schools sustainable (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

Sustainable development should be introduced to all communities. Rio de Janeiro's 1992 Earth Summit established Agenda 21 and endorsed sustainable education. Chapter 36 of Agenda 21 focuses on increasing primary education, adapting existing education to sustainable development, and training. Malaysia's Ministry of Housing and Local Government launched Local Agenda 21 in 2001. (GDRC.org, 2022). Malaysia's plan calls for sustainable development education at all levels.

2.0 Background of the Study

The Malaysian Ministry of Education (MoE) created the Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 in 2013. This Blueprint has changed school teaching and learning. New preschool, primary, and secondary curricula were developed to align with the Blueprint's educational objectives.

The Blueprint is comprehensive to ensure the entire development and maximum potential of children. The strategy comprises five system objectives, six student aspirations, and 11 reform moves. The 5 Systems Aspirations are the MoE's goals for the education system. 1) ACCESS: to ensure 100% enrolment from preschool to upper secondary; 2) QUALITY: focusing on reading, math, and science; 3) EQUITY: equal opportunities for all (urban-rural, socio-economic, gender, indigenous communities, special needs children); 4) UNITY: promotes shared values and experiences by encouraging students to embrace diversity; and 5) EFFICIENCY: maximizes student outcome within the current national budget.

The Philosophy of National Education (FPK), implemented in 1996, guides Malaysia's education system. FPK emphasizes that education is a constant effort to enhance individuals' intellectual, spiritual, emotional, and physical potential. Thus, FPK's perspective and perception of nature align with the SDGs, particularly UNESCO's four pillars of learning plan for the 21st century, unveiled in 1996, and the global SDG agenda (2016-2030). (Widad, O et. Al, 2022)

2.1 The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible side effects of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental damage. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian policymakers must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby securing sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While there is commitment of Asian leaders for EfS along with their concern for the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS). On the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in the PCs make the integration of ICT in the curriculum of teacher education programs and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes about teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

1. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.
2. Build the capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education to enable them to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers' training program on education for sustainability.
3. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program, enabled by blended learning, that focuses on integrating education for sustainability across school curricula.
4. Develop innovative teaching, learning and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning and curriculum.
5. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

3.0 Problem Statement

The Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 was formed in 2013. This Blueprint completely transformed education. ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS) and its potential to promote Education for Sustainability (EfS) for all in-service teachers. ICT integration in teacher education and in-service training is crucial due to the increased PC ICT infrastructure and ICT literacy. ICT integration involves more than simply including ICT as a subject or tool. It

requires comprehensive, integrated planning of ICT-enabled EfS in teacher preparation. The proposed ICTeEfS project is to construct an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators to apply innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented to education for sustainability (EfS) while considering all barriers and reasoning flaws.

4.0 Research Objectives

The overall aim of this paper is to conduct a critical analysis of the process in the DeCore+ framework and DREAM techniques in designing the entire instructional system for the Principles of Instructional Technology course. To fulfil the aim above three steps of activity below are established:

1. Demonstrate the DeCore+ framework in the content development of the Principle of Instructional Technology course
2. Walk through the DREAM techniques in learning design activity for documentation of the processes
3. To observe the design phases of the DREAM technique in infusing SDG in the designing the lesson for the Principle of Instructional Technology course

Table 1 Coherency table between Issues and challenges, aim and research questions

Issues and Challenges	Aim of the study	RQ
Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 in 2013 has changed school teaching and learning.	To Demonstrate the DeCore+ framework in the content development of the Principle of Instructional Technology course	RQ1 To what extent does the DeCore+ plus framework enable to support the phases in the whole process of the content development in the Principle of Instructional Technology course
Capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers.	To Walkthrough the DREAM techniques in learning design activity for documentation of the processes	RQ 2 Does the design phases in DREAM sufficient enough to strengthen the instructional strategy in the Principle of Technology course?
The integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool.		
ICT-enabled capacity-building program to in-service teachers and teacher educators and turn them able to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies orienting to education for sustainability (EfS)	To observe the design phases of the DREAM technique in infusing SDG in the designing the lesson for the Principle of Instructional Technology course	RQ 3 What is the challenges in the design process in DREAM techniques in designing the lesson for the Principle of Instructional Technology course?

5.0 Methodology

The walkthrough of the development process through the DeCore+ framework and DREAM techniques advanced by Makrakis (2023) is set to identify a set of critical dimensions in the selected studies on ID model development. The development experience is documented to identify the specific features, development contexts, and logic of the development process, ensuring the quality of the output. The following task is set up to gain the development experience:

1. Review and study the DeCoRe plus interaction.
2. Synthesize the DeCoRe plus into a development task appropriate to the integration of SDG in the course
3. Embedding the task into the Community of Inquiry (COI) model as practice in OUM
4. Organize the task based on the DREAM combined with the DeCoRe plus and COI

5.1 Review and study the DeCoRe plus interaction.

5.1.1 Deconstruction Process

The DeCore+ and DREAM need to be blend into the Community of Inquiry (COI) model to align with the pedagogical aspect for online learning as practised in OUM. SAMR is used to support the formulation of the learning activity. The figure below shows the interface between DeCore+, DREAM, and COI. Each stage in the interface is unique in terms of its processes and output.

Figure 1. Analysis of the process of DeCoRe+ and DREAM with COI for learning design.

5.1.2 Introduction to DeCoRe+

A six-stage capacity-building strategy was presented by Makrakis (2006) for educating academic personnel on how to incorporate sustainability into their curricula (Figure 1). Three phases make up DeCore Plus. Diagnostic assessment

in step one; deconstruction in step two. Deconstruction of assessment input analyzes input, whereas diagnostic review identifies what learners require. Each one develops a learner profile. According to a summary of the DeCoRe methodological approach to curriculum development, the development of the material is divided into four major stages (Makrakis, 2017; 2016). The didactic profiles of the trainees are first diagnosed. A plan for the training session is created based on the profiles of the trainees (second stage). The training material aligns with the action plan and integrates theory and practice in thematic units or modules that can be tailored to meet the needs of the trainees (third stage). The learning outcomes of the trainees will be compared to their original profiles and the goals and objectives of their action plans (fourth stage). The learners, the intended recipients, are judged by how well they apply their newly acquired skills and information in the classroom (fifth stage). To maintain an optimal training process and ensure potential upgrades, a monitoring and upgrading system is implemented across all stages, including the sixth stage. DeCoRe+, an acronym for Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, was used by Makrakis (2017) to incorporate sustainability and the 17 SDGs. By utilizing a design method that focuses on transformative curriculum development, the DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents. There are eight processes in DeCoRe+.

1. Diagnosing: Reflecting on who we are, what we know, where we want to go, and why.
2. Deconstructing: critically analysing personal perspectives, habits of mind, and chosen curriculum units/modules.
3. Gathering resources, creating ideas, and building meaning (perspectives).
4. Reconstructing: Integrating new constructed knowledge with the reconstructed frame of reference.
5. Implementing the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. Finalizing: Reflecting and evaluating what has been learned and changed.
7. Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
8. Finalising: Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. (Makrakis, 2017).

5. 2. Synthesize the DeCoRe plus into development tasks appropriate to the integration of SDG in the course

This section discusses the curricular dimension that can be integrated into the courses and focuses on the course syllabus in the HBEF3103 Principles of Instructional Technology course. The HBEF3103 Principles of Instructional Technology is the undergraduate core course in the BTPE program. This three-credit hour course is conducted entirely online and delivered within 8 to 15 weeks. This course focuses on the concepts, fundamental principles, and practices of pedagogy and education. Among the main topics of the course is the relationship between teaching and learning and the learning models, instructional design, and the use of technology and media in teaching and learning.

By the end of the course, the students will be able to:

1. Explain the basic concepts and principles of teaching technology;
2. Applying the instructional design model in the context of systematic teaching and learning
3. Evaluate the instructional systems for revision and improvement

In order for the course to be more diverse in terms of integration elements of SDG in the learning objectives, it needs to be aligned to the Key Indicative Strategies is SDG 4 targets as

Table Example of Topic used to integrate with SDG

The majority of learning activities are closely related to another subject, such as languages, arts, and science. This, however, needs to be revised so that it can be linked to a wide range of subject areas. SDG concepts, which promote broad areas of sustainable development by requiring balanced progress in four interdependent dimensions, can be used to make the link. on social, economic, environmental, and cultural issues (Hawkes, 2001).

Table 2 Integration of SDG in Topic 1 Principle of Instructional Technology

Key Indicative Strategies is SDG 4	Topic 1: The domain of Instructional Technology (Example of the sub-topics)
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Target 4.4 ICT skills in curricula and training programs	1. Technology Concepts
Target 4.5 Enhanced distance learning in conflict and remote areas	2. Teaching Concepts
Target 4.6 Mobile technology for delivering programs	3. Concepts of Teaching Technology
Target 4.a Access to ICT resources in learning spaces and environments	1. Definition of teaching technology in the local context
Target 4.c Teachers with adequate technological skills to manage ICT (Gwang-Jo Kim, 2017 slide 8)	2. The latest trends in the concept of teaching technology.
	4. Teaching Technology Domain 1977
	1. The function of teaching development
	2. Function of learning resources
	3. Teaching management function
	5. Teaching Technology Domain 1994
	1. Definition and interpretation of teaching technology 1994
	2. The domain of teaching technology 1994.
	3. The Role of Teaching Technology
	Topic 2: Instructional Design
	Topic 3: Teaching Media
	Topic 4: Visual Design
	Topic 5: Effective Teaching
	Topic 6: Objectives, Strategies and Methods of Teaching Classroom Management
	Topic 7: Thinking skills
	Topic 8: Problem Solving and Decision Making Skills
	Topic 9: Thinking Tools (Source: Module HBEF 3103 Principles of Instructional Technology available in myINSPIRE (OUM LMS))

Example: SDG Integration Target 4. a Access to ICT resources in learning spaces and environments	Topics Concepts of Teaching Technology -Definition of teaching technology in the local context -The latest trends in the concept of teaching technology.
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Based on the standard in Malaysian Qualification Agency (MQA), the content of the course matched three skills, i.e. Ethics, professionalism and humanitarianism (A), Communication, leadership and team skills (A), methods, critical thinking and problem solving skills (C), Lifelong learning and information management (A), and Entrepreneurship and managerial skills (A) The learning activities are conducted through a blended-learning approach (Face to Face and Online Learning). The learners must complete the Online Task and Activity, as well as the Case study and Design and development.

The learning structure is built from easy to hard based on the instructional technique. PBL is utilized when students must identify problems, list solutions, assess options, make a decision, and monitor progress. The learning process follows PBL competencies (p. 8)

The course focuses on putting theory into practice by designing and developing instructional systems. Consider sustainability justice's four elements simultaneously. The dominant ideology and economic model of non-sustainable economic development aren't developed. This course intends to stimulate instructors' interest in instructional design and technology to improve instruction. system. Other learning courses delve further into skills and knowledge. Most content knowledge fits the aforementioned criteria.

Face-to-face and online learning (blended method) led to assignment writing and greater exam comprehension. So far, the assessment approach attempts to produce high learning engagement; some students are engaged, especially to online learning, while others are committed to face-to-face sessions.

The instructional strategy consider two dimensions as below:

Table 3 instructional strategy dimensions for teaching strategy on Instructional Technology course

Dimension 1: Communication, Collaboration, Connectivity, Critical reflection	Dimension 2: Critical consciousness, Constructing knowledge, Cross-cultural competence
Teaching strategy: Active learning for the design and development of the learning environment	Teaching strategy: Inductive (Eg-Rule) and Deductive (Rul-Eg) technique for case study

5.3. Embedding the task into the Community of Inquiry (COI) model as practice in OUM

The What, Why and Where Questions for Revising Open University Malaysia (OUM) offers 54 programmes comprising 28 at the undergraduate level and 26 at the post graduate level. The university academic calendar is divided into three equal semesters. During each semester, approximately 650 courses will be offered to about 27000 active learners. Typically, each learner registers for three courses per semester.

OUM employs a fully online blended pedagogy for teaching and learning, based on the Community of Inquiry (CoI) Model of Engagement by Garrison, Anderson, and Archer (2000).

Figure 3: The Community of Inquiry (CoI) Model of Engagement by Garrison, Anderson & Archer (2000).

This pedagogy comprises synchronous, entirely online, face-to-face tutorials conducted via Google Meet, which fulfill the need for interactions between learners and instructors (Teaching Presence). The asynchronous online forum, also known as Online Class Participation (OCP), is required to ensure interactions between learners and peers (Social Presence). The forum is conducted using OUM's learning management system, named MyInspire. The interactions between learners and learning materials (Cognitive Presence) is achieved through providing the online learning resources consisting of the modules and e-lessons.

In addition to the subject's essential content areas, the OUM module offers sections on "self check" and "activities." Both of these parts encouraged students to test their knowledge after completing the lesson and to do the prescribed activities in groups or individually. Moreover, e-lessons that are tailored to the topics of the modules supplement the learning process. This is a framework of each topic with connections to the topic's content in the module, relevant YouTube videos, and further references or reading materials. Additionally, the e-lessons offer discussion topics, associated problems, and self-assessments.

This course is intended to pique the instructors' interest in their roles to maximize the significance of instructional design and technology to ensure the efficacy of the instructional system.

The personal goal of the course creators in developing the course is based on the following factors:

- Applying the concepts and principles of teaching and learning to the planning and execution of teaching and learning. (Application of theory in practice. Translate the Constructivist method into an effective lesson plan as an example.
- In teaching and learning activities, demonstrate the principle of critical and creative thinking. (Capable of working in a group to provide unique ideas for building instructional systems that effectively convey content)
- Analyzing the principles of teaching technology, teaching design, and teaching media, as well as their application to the use of multimedia technology in the classroom.

(Capable of resolving issues to improve teaching and learning using multimedia technologies)

5.3.1 The How Question

In light of the aforementioned features, needs, and objectives, Makrakis (2006) developed a six-stage capacity-building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses (Figure 1).

Figure 4: A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

In the First stage, trainees' didactic profiles are diagnosed. Based on trainee characteristics, a training session action plan is generated (second stage). The training content follows the action plan and combines theory and practice in subject units or modules that can be tailored to meet the trainee's needs (third stage). Comparing trainees' learning outcomes to their initial profiles and action plan aims and objectives (fourth stage). The end receivers, the learners, are evaluated by transferring their skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A monitoring and upgrading system is integrated across all phases to maintain optimal training process functionality and facilitate possible updates (sixth stage).

Makrakis (2017) utilized DeCoRe+, an abbreviation for Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, to integrate sustainability and the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is a design technique that focuses on transformative curricular creation. DeCoRe+ has six processes.

1. Diagnosing: Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
2. Deconstructing: Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
3. Constructing: Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
4. Reconstructing: Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.

5. Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. Finalizing: Reflecting on and evaluating what has been learned and changed.

5.4. Organize the task based on the DREAM combined with the DeCoRe plus and COI

5.4.1 DREAM methodology

Makrakis (2019, 2022) proposed the DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) technique for evaluating redesigned courses during implementation (Makrakis, 2023). These procedures encompass what students bring to class before (Diagnosing), during (reviewing, reflecting, and Explaining), and after the course (evaluating and managing). DREAM approach is a critical action research procedure that tries to assess and enhance a course. The student, under the direction of the course instructor, builds a portfolio using the DREAM Methodology. DREAM is a course prerequisite. The instructor must examine students' DREAM portfolios and report to the class. The instructor and students can use the DREAM portfolio analysis to improve the course.

Figure 6: The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

Makrakis (2023) proposed the DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) technique for evaluating redesigned courses during implementation. These procedures encompass what students bring to class before (Diagnosing), during (Reviewing/Reflecting and Explaining), and after the course (Evaluating) (Assessing and managing) to promote the content knowledge as below

1) Fundamental principles and practices of instructional design. Example:
 Content: Instructional design concept (Module HBEF 3103-Topic 3)
 Design and develop: Apply the teaching model of teaching technology in a systematic and effective teaching and learning context.

2) the use of media in teaching and learning supported by pedagogy and education, teaching and learning and the learning models. Example
 Content: Design and development of instructional media (Module HBEF 3103 - Topic 2)
 Project-based: (Develop knowledge and skills in problem solving and evaluation of teaching technology programs).

Most of the processes in DREAM methodology are iterative. After successfully undergoing all processes in DREAM, the course designer has completed the process in Deconstruction. DREAM approach is a critical action research procedure that tries to assess and enhance a course. The student, directed by the course instructor, builds a portfolio using the DREAM Methodology.

More in-depth understanding of specific skills and knowledge is explored in other learning modules. Most of the content knowledge is likely to fit into the two criteria above. The instructor must examine students' DREAM portfolios and report to the class. The instructor and students can use the DREAM portfolio analysis to improve the course.

6.0 Findings and Discussion

RQ1 To what extent does the DeCore+ plus framework enable to support the phases in the whole process of the content development in the Principle of Instructional Technology course

During the process of enhancing the module based on DeCORE, several SDG elements, the 6 pillars of learning, and the 10 Cs were integrated into the course. The content of the unit/module and especially the learning activities relate to: 1) the six learning pillars for sustainable development (learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to transform oneself and society & learning to give and share), and 2) the 10Cs

Justification is made based on questions to reflect on the 10c's

- a. Communication, Collaboration, Connectivity, Critical reflection
 - How can learning theory benefit the area of instructional technology?
 - Why is instructional technology so crucial in strategizing the teaching and learning?
 - What is the instructional design in the development of instructional media?
- b. Critical consciousness, constructing knowledge, Cross-cultural competence
 - How can EFS be embedded in the planning and implementation of teaching and learning?

All 10C's elements can be linked to the content in this course. In summary, these elements can be mapped to the course content. In Myinspire, learners communicate with the

teacher and other learners to synthesize and transmit ideas in written, oral, and virtual formats.

Throughout the whole process in Deconstruction. The experience are as follows:

- Exploring and applying teaching and learning concepts and principles. (Applying theory. Example: Design a Constructivist lesson.
- Teach and learn with critical and creative thinking. (Can work in a group to develop unique concepts for content delivery)
- Analyzing teaching technology, teaching design, and teaching media, and using multimedia in education. (Multimedia-savvy problem-solver)

The learning design can meet the following criteria by implementing the DREAM and SAMR:

a. To solve the problem presented in the online E-Lesson, students must think critically. As a result, they must make decisions and take appropriate action while engaging in learning processes such as conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating information gathered.

b. In Online Class Participation, learners must also apply new ideas in developing innovative applications and solutions based on the Instructional Technology Principle. In terms of cross-cultural competence, students debate the application of instructional technology principles in daily life within a multicultural and global context. This course's evaluation consists of both course work and a final examination. The course work is worth 60% and consists of written assignments, online class participation, and online quizzes. The online Final Examination consists of an essay, which accounts for 40% of the total weightage.

c. The course focuses on the application of theory into practice, where the learner must understand the concept of Principle of Instructional Technology and apply it in a variety of activities.

To support the development process at this stage, SAMR need to be blend in to ensure an appropriate learning activity is appropriately formulated. Figure 7 shows the infusion of SAMR in DeCore+

Figure 7: Embedding SAMR in Template Organizer for applying the DeCoRe+ methodological approach to curriculum (Makrakis, 2016 p. 156)

DECONSTRUCTION PROCESS	CONSTRUCTION PROCESS	CRITICAL REFLECTION	RECONSTRUCTION PROCESS
User Requirement	Product specification	Usability Testing	
S A M R (Puentedura, 2006)			
Enhancement		Transformation	

	Augmentation	Modification	
1. Unit/Module 2. Method of Assessment 3. Gaps, purposeful omission, and underlying assumption 4. Power and interest 5. Projected image and reality	Based on the detailed and critical answers to the deconstruction process, start the construction process by recording the main points that need changes and describing your proposals, which will be used in the reconstruction process.	Reflect on what is needed to support the following four domains. 1. Interactive Teaching/Learning 2. Teaching/learning approaches 3. Learning pillars and 10Cs 4. Authenticity	Write the general goals of the unit/module: Describe what kind of previous knowledge you will use in teaching the reconstructed unit/module: Describe the characteristics of learners (e.g. skills, values, knowledge, attitudes, action competences) that will contribute to the learning outcomes
Examples of Learning Activities Based on SAMR			
A video that clarifies a particularly difficult concept is used to supplement teacher instruction.	Students do their own research on the Internet instead of relying on what their teachers say.	Students use a tech tool that makes an abstract idea more concrete and interactive.	Allowing students to submit their work online so that their peers and the larger community can see it

RQ 2 Does the design phases in DREAM sufficient enough to strengthen the instructional strategy in the Principle of Technology course?

Development Experience

Concepts are delivered through several learning tasks. The number of tasks depends on the complexity of the idea. Formative assessment is conducted through the tasks (such as Online Forum). Values are assessed according to the commitment of the learners on the task (for example, an online discussion, the learners are judged by the ethics). Assessment criteria are built in the Rubric. SDG is indirectly practice in most learning activities. It is not clearly stated in the syllabus or TOC.

The course is expected to achieve the learning outcomes as below:

- Explain the basic concepts and principles of instructional technology;
- Implementing a teaching model in the context of systematic teaching and learning

- Evaluate the design of instructional systems for teaching problem solving

The TOC, which is aligned to the learning outcomes, is in line with the Education for Sustainability (EfS), which appears to be a ‘hidden curriculum’.

The Learning Activity

Most of the learning activities are well connected with another subject, such as music. The connection can be made through the application of the concepts of SDG, which promotes the broad areas of sustainable development and requires balanced progress in four interdependent dimensions (Hawkes, 2001): social, economic, environmental, and cultural.

To fulfill the content specification above, the course designer must possess a set of skills and knowledge as outlined below to produce an effective learning activity.

Table 4. Skill and Knowledge for planning Learning Activity

Set of Skills and Knowledge	Learning activity
Pedagogical practice and education	Online Forum. Assessment: Formative assessment: Forum is rated) basic concepts and principles of pedagogical practice and education.
Fundamentals of Teaching and Learning	Workshop. Assessment: Peer assessment teaching and learning, teaching and learning models, preparation of teaching and learning objectives,
Instructional Strategy	Online Wiki - Design and Develop. Assessment: Summative (Written assignment) methods of achieving teaching and learning objectives, teaching strategies, classroom management, teaching media use and teaching design

In order to reinforce the process the DREAM techniques need to be supported by other model that is appropriate to the subject matter. In the case of the course Principle of Instructional Technology, the other model that can fit in the DREAM is SAMR with added set of skill for the course designer as in the figure below

Figure 8 Set of skill for the course designer embedded in revised DeCore+

DECONSTRUCTION PROCESS	CONSTRUCTION PROCESS	CRITICAL REFLECTION	RECONSTRUCTION PROCESSES
Product specification			
Set of skill for course designer			

Pedagogical practice and education	Fundamental of Teaching and Learning	Instructional Strategy	
S A M R (Puentedura, 2006)			
Enhancement		Transformation	
Substitution	Augmentation	Modification	Redefinition
Examples of Learning Activities based on SAMR			
A video that clarifies a complicated concept is used to supplement teacher instruction.	Students conduct their own research on the Internet instead of relying solely on their teachers' words.	Students use a tech tool that makes an abstract idea more concrete and interactive.	Allowing students to submit their work online so that their peers and the larger community can see it

The SAMR (Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, and Redefinition) Model can be used as a strategy in real-life learning activities, as shown below:

1. In a diverse and complex society, effectively communicates, demonstrates leadership skills, and adheres to the values of professionalism, attitude, and ethics.
2. Capable of problem-solving, self-reflection, and applying scientific and creative skills required in primary education.
3. Capable of instilling cutting-edge entrepreneurial skills in students while also instilling a positive attitude toward personal development and professionalism.

RQ 3 What is the challenges in the design process in DREAM techniques in designing the lessson for the Principle of Instructional Technology course?

The first challenge the design process in DREAM technique is to align the existing module content which is need to be updated to fit the purpose of SDG integration. OUM modules are written using a predefined template. Making changes to the content, therefore, necessitates critical analysis to identify where changes are needed, as well as creativity to rearrange so that the new materials can be embedded cohesively with the existing materials.

Time was a constraint while preparing modules for in-service teacher training, as was the current workload at the university. Furthermore, the language of reference materials created a barrier because most SDG reference materials are in English, necessitating translation into Bahasa Melayu. However, by cooperating, the group is able to overcome the language barrier.

The incorporation of SDGs into this course should raise learners' awareness and understanding of SDGs. As a result of this understanding, they should be more concerned about what is going on in their lives, society, country, and the

world. They must understand the significance of understanding the SDGs in order to ensure global prosperity and harmony.

Conclusion

SDG is already incorporated into the science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) curriculum in Malaysia (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2031). Therefore, many teachers are aware of the SDGs, but those not actively involved in STEM education may be unaware that the SDGs can be incorporated into any subject. With this awareness, teachers should be inspired to incorporate SDGs into their classes, hence increasing student awareness and knowledge of SDGs. In addition, exposure to SDGs can motivate teachers, students, and communities to incorporate SDGs into their daily lives.

This initiative has demonstrated that ESD is the most effective means of communicating the SDGs to the community, beginning with school-aged children and their trained instructors. Furthermore, it has been proved that the SDGs may be presented through any subject.

It is worth pointing out that particular importance has to be given various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues about the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

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The Community Service Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

Community service is any activity that a person performs unpaid for the benefit of the general public or a particular community. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals recognizes the significance of volunteers in attaining the 17 SDGs by 2030. This paper discusses the process, techniques, and results of revising MPU3412 Community Service course at Open University Malaysia (OUM) based on the six key questions. The first question, "What," asks about the course before revision. The second and third questions ask "Why" (explaining the need for review) and "Where," describing course deficiencies to be filled. Meanwhile, the fourth question details revision and course assessment during implementation. The fifth question, "Now What," describes how the course has changed from "What" it was earlier. The last question: "So what?" discusses the obstacles encountered from the beginning to the present and how they were resolved. Furthermore, this paper applies two methodologies which are DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) to embed sustainability and the 17 Goals of SDGs. Meanwhile, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess, and Manage) technique is used to evaluate redesigned courses during the implementation. Volunteering encourages more people to participate in social activities. Through volunteering, one feels like part of the community and gains positive ideals and latent skills.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); Community Service; volunteering, DREAM methodology; DeCoRe+ methodology

13. Introduction

Open University Malaysia (OUM) offers 54 programs, 28 at the undergraduate level and 26 at the graduate level. The academic year is divided into three semesters. Approximately 650 courses are provided each semester to 27,000 learners. Each semester, each learner takes three courses.

OUM utilizes a fully online blended pedagogy based on the Community of Inquiry Model of Engagement by Garrison, Anderson, and Archer (2000). (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Community of Inquiry (COI) Model of Engagement

This pedagogy comprises a synchronous fully online face-to-face tutorials delivered via Google Meet to ensure interactions between learners and instructors (Teaching Presence) and an asynchronous online forum to ensure interactions between learners/peers (Social Presence). The forum uses OUM's myINSPIRE learning management system (LMS). Online modules and e-lessons facilitate interactions between learners and learning materials (Cognitive Presence).

OUM's Study Guide consists of four components: learning outcomes, topic overview, content summary and study questions. Learning outcomes outline the specific tasks to be accomplished; the Topic overview explains briefly what the topic focuses on as a means to provide a general interpretative framework for understanding the topic content. Meanwhile, the content summary offers an interpretative framework for understanding the core content of the learners and study questions help our learners to focus on key subject areas. In addition, e-lessons based on six topics in the Study Guide will assist learning to our learners. This is a framework of each topic with links to the Study Guide's content, YouTube, and references or reading resources. E-lessons include discussions, case studies, and self-tests.

The ICTeEfS project

The fast growth of Asia has impacted the environment. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian authorities must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate and reverse climate change in order to ensure future development. Education for sustainability (EfS) can contribute in overcoming these obstacles. Leaders in Asia are devoted to EfS and concerned with implementing the SDGs, but classroom teachers are the true agents of change.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian nations in which instructors require training to address ICTs, climate change, and other environmental risks. On the one hand, education faculties must restructure their study programs to include ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS), while on the other, they must capitalize on the potential of these technologies to promote EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly expanding availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs necessitate the inclusion of ICT in teacher education curricula and in-service training. However, ICT integration does not merely entail adding ICT as a subject or instrument. It requires extensive and integrated planning of ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education and implies modifications to teaching and learning.

The proposed project aims to provide an ICT-enabled capacity-building programme for in-service teachers and teacher educators in order to prepare them to adopt cutting-edge teaching methodologies and pedagogies geared toward education for sustainability (EfS). The Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education of the European Commission has provided funding for the ICTeEfS project for the years 2019 to 2023. The more precise goals are to:

1. Encourage the growth of education faculties at partner universities so that curriculum, instruction, and research are in line with the field of education for sustainability.
2. Increase the academic staff's capability at the faculties of education so that they may contribute to the achievement, implementation, and assessment of a substantial in-service teacher training programme on sustainability education.
3. Develop a blended learning-enabled in-service teacher professional development programme that is effective, affordable, decentralised, scalable, and innovative, with a focus on integrating education for sustainability across school curricula.
4. Create cutting-edge teaching, learning, and curricular materials in the form of an e-Toolkit that is multilingual and addresses the incorporation of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
5. To improve collaboration in the area of ICTeEfS and replication of created outputs and outcomes, create a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability.

The objective of this paper is to discuss the process, strategies, and results of the revision of the course MPU3412 Community Service at Open University Malaysia (OUM), taking into account six key issues: The first question, "What," focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of learners enrolled in the course, important themes in the curriculum, competencies to be developed, the teaching strategies used, and the methods of evaluating learners. The second and third questions address "Why" (explaining the justifications for revision) and "Where," which describes the gaps in the course that will be filled during the revision process. The fourth question is a "How" inquiry that details the revision and course assessment procedures used during the implementation phase. The fifth question, "Now What," describes how the course has changed from "What" it was previously and illustrates how it has been updated or amended. The sixth and last question, "So What?" examines the difficulties encountered throughout the entire preceding process, from the beginning to the present, and how they were overcome. The discussion section specifically discusses the following sub-questions: What effects will the revised course have on local and global society, curriculum, teaching, and learning? How has knowledge of education, learning, and curriculum changed? What can be learned from this experience, and how will it impact society and the beneficiaries, such learners? What has to be done, why it has not been done, and what would be the next steps?

The What, Why and Where Questions for Revising MPU3412 Community Service)

Many universities around the world have introduced community service courses. The introduction of this course is to enable learners to engage with the community through various activities beyond the classroom or lecture hall. By participating and engaging in community service activities, various scholars agree about the benefits learners gain in their personal, social, ethical, and intellectual lives (Hooghe, 2003; Seider, Rabinowicz, & Gillmor 2011, Yoa, 2008).

MPU3412 Community Service course is introduced to all OUM learners to provide an understanding and appreciation of community engagement projects. It introduces learners to the concept of community service projects, the preparation of proposal papers, and practical projects' characteristics. Community service, often known as volunteerism, allows learners to gain life skills and knowledge while helping others in need. Engaging in community service will enable learners to be active citizens of their communities and has a long-term, significant impact on society. The relationship between community service and volunteerism has been significantly emphasized in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

“Volunteerism is a global phenomenon that transcends boundaries, religions and cultural divides. Volunteers embody the

fundamental values of commitment, inclusiveness, civic engagement and a sense of solidarity [...] The newly adopted Sustainable Development Goals offer another opportunity for individuals to show solidarity through volunteerism. All of us can contribute to realizing the 2030 Agenda's vision of ending poverty" (UN Secretary-General Ban Ki Moon, International Volunteer Day 5 December 2015)

There is no final examination for this course. The assessment is fully coursework. There are FOUR (4) activities to assess learners in this course comprising:

a) Activity 1: Report Writing

The learners are given guidelines to write a report which is from the planning stages to the implementation stages.

b) Activity 2: Video presentation

In this activity, the learners will be assessed through their communication, confidence, interviewing, involvement, creativity and many others.

c) Activity 3: Writing a reflective journal

The guideline for writing a reflective journal related to the community service activity conducted by the learners are based on the following criteria:

- Descriptive – What happened?
- Emotive – What did you feel at that time?
- Cognitive – What did you think at that time?
- Evaluative – Was the experience good or bad? Why?
- Analysis – What can you learn from this activity?
- Conclusion – What did you do, and what are the other options open to you?

OR

- What was your best experience while implementing the community service activity?
- What were the challenges you encountered while implementing the community service activity?
- What were the new skills that you have gained while implementing the community service activity?
- Describe any disappointments or successes of activities you have carried out. What did you learn from it?

- How will you share this experience and your learning with others?

d) Activity 4: Essay question (14%)

Learners to answer one essay question given to them which revolve around various topics related to volunteerism, leadership, ethics and many others

Finally, 6% of the marks is allocated for Overall Presentation focusing on the report format (Cover Page, Table of Content, page numbering) and Language and spellings

The key content themes of the community service projects are: environmental consciousness; educational responsibility; community development; healthcare and well-being of society; disaster management; information, communication and technology; social entrepreneurship; innovation, art and culture; and inclusivity and diversity.

Furthermore, the community service project guidelines also required learners to integrate and address through the projects the four sustainable dimensions; namely (i) environmental justice, (ii) social justice, (iii) economic justice and (iv) cultural justice. Also, included are the six learning pillars for sustainable development, that is; (i) learning to know, (ii) learning to be, (iii) learning to live together, (iv) learning to do, (v) learning to transform oneself and society and (vi) learning to give and share.*

Learners should be able to develop the following abilities: To master ODL while catering to the dynamic technological changes occurring within the e-learning environment; to lead in group discussions either physically or virtually; to collaborate in teams beyond the physical classroom; to think critically and creatively. Nevertheless, learners can practice the values and ethics, leadership and teamwork as well as social responsibility.

“Why” question

The process of enhancing this module is based on DeCoRe+, which Makrakis (2017) introduced. The DeCoRe+ is the abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction. Deconstruction, which is critically analysing the functioning of personal perspectives/habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules. Construction is the process of gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives). Meanwhile, Reconstruction is integrating newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference. The major goal of DeCoRe plus is to

* Vassilios Makrakis and Nelly Kostoulas-Makrakis. (2017). *An Instructional-Learning Model Applying Problem-Based Learning Enabled by ICTs*. In P. Anastasiades and N. Zaranis (eds.), *Research on e-Learning and ICT in Education*, DOI 10.1007/978-

assist pre-service teachers in thinking about teaching, learning, and curriculum through the perspectives of critical pedagogy and sustainable justice, as well as to develop numerous ways of knowing about these topics (Makrakis, 2017).

One of the missing parts before the revision of this course, the course content would be no emphasis on SDGs in any compulsory courses in OUM. The SDGs is only emphasized in one of the core courses for learners enrolling in the Bachelor of Political Science (BPS)*.

By adopting the 2030 Agenda, the 193 United Nations Member States have committed to leaving no one behind to achieve Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). For instance, if you are an educator, Goal 4 Quality Education of SDGs is a core goal that individuals can perform in their voluntary activities. As a volunteer, an individual can offer his or her service by providing free tutoring to the learners in his or her community who are not performing well academically. In addition, an individual and his or her colleagues also can raise awareness of the importance of SDGs voluntarily in his or her community. Notably, volunteering often causes ripple effects. It inspires people to transform other communities, either locally or internationally. This is significant in the SDGs as it echoes the "Leave No One Behind" slogan.

Therefore, after the revision, the emphasis on SDGs was embedded as a subtopic in the Study Guide of the 1.6 Volunteerism as a Driving Force to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); 1.6.1 Definition of Sustainable Development; 1.6.2 Relationship between Volunteerism and SDGs. Nevertheless, the SDGs have also been integrated assignments, particularly in Activity 3 of essay questions.

Generally, neither SDGs; the 6 pillars of learning nor the 10Cs are missing in this course after the first revision.

The justifications are as follows;

I. The SDGs

Many SDGs themes can be integrated into the community service project. One of the SDGs to be integrated for this course is Goal 13 Climate Action which the learners can raise awareness of the importance of global warming in their community. For instance, the learners can organize a campaign of the 3Rs of sustainability which is Reduce-Reuse-Recycle which, among others, highlights a few ways to reduce, reuse, and recycle the garbage in the home, as well as at work or school. At the same time, one can contribute to a healthier planet by refusing to buy products he and she does not need, reusing items multiple times, and properly

disposing of items that are no longer in use at appropriate recycling sites.

Besides, the government's role can be associated with Goal 16 Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions. The government also plays an important role in strengthening the role of its citizens by encouraging and promoting volunteerism in communities throughout the country.

One of the new competencies to be developed in this course would be emphasizing to the learners to have a positive mindset to serve a particular section of the society. In addition, the learners should have an interest, concern and a tendency to contribute physical energy and share interests and experiences with a target group or particular community groups. Furthermore, the learners need to be instilled in the mind that the community service project that they are implementing is not aimed at getting a financial reward or as a show-off to the public; rather than the activities must bring benefits to a community group.

II. The 6 pillars of learning

At the same time, there is also no missing of the 6 pillars of learning in this course. The content through the learning activities has embedded six learning pillars for sustainable development (learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to transform oneself and society and learning to give and share.

a) Learning to know

This course explains the concept of community service, the importance of community service, implications of community services to individuals. The discussion of the readiness of someone who wants to be a volunteer is also emphasized to the learners. Besides, this course also leads the learners on Volunteerism as a driving Force to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by introducing the concept of sustainable development.

b) Learning to be

Through this course, creativity in developing community service projects includes maintaining the sensitivity of the local community and the group members and respecting the group members' views to implement the community service project and others successfully. Developing community service projects related to the real-life problems and/or problems that they daily face

c) Learning to do

Community service projects to be carried out should bring high impact not just to learners themselves but also

* Under the subtopic 10.6 Searching for Sustainable Development of ABKK3203 Political Development and Third World Politics, the learners are introduced briefly on what is sustainable development, the three important aspects of sustainability:

environment, economy and society and finally on the 17 Goals of SDGs.

include the group members and communities involved in the project. Furthermore, values like accountability, cooperation, support, integrity, respect, and so on can be viewed in community service projects with a high impact. For instance, the learners can choose a community service from the list given by the instructor, such as Community service at school/kindergarten; Community service in the recreational area; Community service at the orphanage; Community service at home for old folks; Community service at the home of People with Disabilities (OKU); Community service with your colleagues at your workplace; Community service during the marriage feast/wedding ceremony; Community service after the occurrence of disasters like flood and others; Community service at the recycling centres; Community service at the animal shelters; Various community service projects at the village, city, and national level.

d) Learning to live together sustainably

Learning is not just about memorizing the facts, but also about appreciating and applying what we have learned. It is even more important to be concerned about your surrounding and your way of living in the environment. One of the goals of participating in community service activities is to foster a sense of love and togetherness among individuals towards their surrounding community.

e) Learning to transform oneself and society

The community service activities carried out together will create a sense of understanding and strengthen self-esteem in a group. At the same time, activities implemented jointly in a community made up of various ethnic groups will result in a stronger sense of tolerance and strengthen the unity among the ethnic groups.

f) Learning to give and share

Community service activities will produce positive input to the self-development of each individual. Well-planned activities will create a sense of consideration and love for other people, especially the disabled and elderly. Furthermore, community service activities also produce citizens of great heart who are patriotic and love the country. The course develops and expands skills in identifying communities for targeted, sustainable interventions.

III. ICTs as enabling tools for the 10Cs

Most of the 10C's elements can be linked to the content in this course. In summary, these elements can be mapped to the contents of this course, namely:

- i) Critical consciousness (Teachers' role in using various sources of knowledge). For instance, Tutors (Teachers) can use the case study to deliver to learners to enhance

their understanding of the relevant topics, such as the importance of volunteerism towards the selected marginalized groups. Besides, the tutors (teachers) also can use "World Day" to create critical consciousness when delivering tutorials. For instance, World Water Day (22 March). The tutors can develop discussion and communication skills with the learners to gather information and address water issues on a global level. Furthermore, the tutors should also encourage participation among the learners to create awareness on the importance of water saving.

- ii) Connectivity (group activities);
- iii) Critical reflection (reviewing through reflective journal);
- iv) Creativity & innovation (preparing a video recording of their community service project). For instance, learners need to be creative and innovative to ensure that the video recording fulfills the criteria: introduction, communication, confidence, audio and visual, interviewing, and involvement throughout the implementation of community service activities. Moreover, the learners also need to be creative to ensure the video is not dull. For example, at this juncture, learners will have to think creatively about selecting songs to be played in the video and many others.

IV. 4 pillars of sustainability justice

The concept of "sustainability justice" was introduced by Makrakis (2016, 2017) reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economics, and culture.

- a) Environmental justice: Discovering the environment, its benefits and the importance of conserving it.
- b) Social justice: Expanding our view from an individual perspective that is confined to us and our home to a collective perspective that concerns the global world as our surroundings.
- c) Economic justice: Reducing the economic exploitation, socio-economic polarisation.
- d) Cultural justice: Establishing the nature of volunteerism, the spirit of helping each other regardless of the race, religion and culture background, cooperation and communal works in learners as a practice of communal harmony.

In reality, this four-sustainability justice can incorporate into the themes of the community service projects. These themes are environmental consciousness; educational responsibility; community development; healthcare and well-being of society; disaster management; information, communication and technology; social entrepreneurship; innovation, art and culture; and inclusivity and diversity. Therefore, these four pillars of sustainability demonstrate how they are interdependent (Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2017) and the same time also emphasize social justice, nonviolence, and peace, which are frequently disregarded in sustainable development education (Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2012).

“Where” question

Since this course is offered to all learners undertaking any programme with OUM, so nothing has been purposefully omitted. Among the key concepts that are included in this course assessed through the learning activities and/or other forms of assessment are as follows:

i) Language Literacy; (Writing the assignment and discussion the e-forum and live forum)

ii) Numeracy; (Planning the budget when carrying out community service activities)

iii) Information, Communication and Technology (ICT) (Essay question in the assignment as well as video recording)

iv) Creative Thinking and Critical Thinking Skills (Essay question in the assignment)

v) Communication Skills;(Discussion during the face-to-face tutorial and video recording - Learners also need to carry out interview session with the target audiences)

vi) Collaborative Skills; (Preparing the assignment and carrying out the community service activities)

One of the SDGs infused for this course is Goal 17 Partnership for the Goals. It is because by mobilizing resources, exchanging knowledge, fostering the production and transfer of ecologically sound technology, and building capacity, stronger collaborations will contribute to environmental protection and sustainable development. Nevertheless, increased cooperation among the governments, civil societies, multilateral organizations, donors, and the private sector is required to provide developing countries and beneficiaries with technologies that increase efficiency in using natural resources, generate low waste, treat the pollution produced, and mitigate climate change. We have the potential to achieve all of our goals when we work together toward the same objectives. Sharing objectives entails sharing a vision. We all want to see poverty eradicated, inequality reduced, and global warming brought to a halt.

Creativity, critical thinking, communication, and collaboration are crucial 21st-century abilities, but we cannot limit our learners to these 4Cs. In a world where ICTs are driving rapid progress and extending human knowledge, education must go beyond the 4Cs to the 10Cs enabled by ICT (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2017). Learners will also study Connectivity and networking, Critical consciousness, Critical reflection, Cross/inter-cultural competency, Co-responsibility, and Knowledge construction.

Methodologies: The How Question

Makrakis (2006) proposed a six-stage capacity building strategy for training academic staff to include sustainability in their courses (Figure 2).

Figure 2. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

First, trainees' didactic profiles are diagnosed. Based on trainee characteristics, a training session action plan is generated (second stage). The training content follows the action plan and combines theory and practice in subject units or modules that can be enhanced based on the trainee's needs (third stage). Comparing trainees' learning outcomes to their initial profiles and action plan aims and objectives (fourth stage). The end receivers, the learners, are evaluated by transferring their skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A monitoring and upgrading system is integrated across all phases to maintain optimal training process functioning and possible updating (sixth stage).

Makrakis (2017) used DeCoRe+, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, to embed sustainability and the 17 SDGs. DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is a design technique that focuses on transformative curricular creation. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes.

1. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
2. **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
3. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
4. **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
5. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. **Finalising:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Makrakis (2023) proposed the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess, and Manage) technique for

evaluating redesigned courses during implementation. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what learners bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing) (Figure 3). DREAM approach is a critical action research procedure that tries to assess and enhance a course. The learner, directed by the course instructor, produces a portfolio using the DREAM Methodology. DREAM is a course prerequisite. The instructor must analyze the learners' DREAM portfolios and submit a class report. The instructor and learners can discuss the DREAM portfolios to improve the course.

Figure 3: The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

“How” question

The methodology used for the revision is DeCoRe which was introduced by Vassilios Makrakis (2017) as a consequence of experiences gained during the implementation, and the assessment using the DREAM methodology (Diagnose, Review/reflect, Explain, Assess and Manage) tool developed by Makrakis (2023) the project coordinator to be used as well as the new peer review by the Project Leader and the other team members. There are approximately 350 learners out of a total of 3,000 who have completed questionnaires based on the DREAM methodology.

On the other hand, the DeCoRe is the abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction. The table below shows that this approach includes six nonlinear processes: diagnostic evaluation, deconstruction, construction, reconstruction, implementation, and summative evaluation.

DeCoRe plus Processes

DeCoRe+ Processes	Key concepts in each process
Diagnostic Evaluation	Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
Deconstruction	Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives/habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
Construction	Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
Reconstruction	Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
Implementation	Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
Summative Evaluation	Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Makrakis (2017, p. 112).*

The links and internal inconsistencies of economic curricular courses with environmental challenges have been identified as a result of using this approach.

The MPU3412 Community Service was offered in the Fall 2021 semester. The learners comprise 34 males and 54 females. Most of OUM’s learners are working adults; thus, their ages range from a minimum of 21 years old to those above 60 years old also, since OUM’s teaching and learning are fully online, these learners are scattered throughout the country.

In terms of their technological competence, almost half of the learners never access online materials, such as e-books, e-journals, and e-databases. Meanwhile, only 4.5% of learners very often access online materials. At the same time, about 35 of 88 learners only sometimes access online materials such as e-books, e-journals, e-databases, etc. The survey confirmed that only 11.4% of learners often access online materials such as e-books, e-journals, e-databases, etc.

Of 88 learners that answered this survey, 31.8% often using statistical tools such as Microsoft Excel, IBM SPSS, MATLAB etc as compared to 35.2% learners sometimes this tool. In the meanwhile, 18 learners never use statistical tools such as Microsoft Excel, IBM SPSS, MATLAB etc and 11 learners very often use statistical tools such as Microsoft Excel, IBM SPSS, MATLAB etc.

More than 50% of our learners sometimes use social media platforms such as blogs, discussion forums, etc., followed by 29.4% never using social media platforms such as blogs, discussion forums, etc. Only 10 and 5 of our

* Makrakis V. (2017). Unlocking the potentiality and actuality of ICTs in developing sustainable – justice curricula and society. Knowledge Cultures 5(2), pp. 103-122, ISSN 2327-5731

learners often and very often use social media platforms such as blogs, discussion forums, etc.

Next, 34 and 29 of our learners never and sometimes use presentation tools such as Microsoft PowerPoint, Google slides, Prezi etc. - In contrast, only 10% and 18% of our learners often and very often use presentation tools such as Microsoft PowerPoint, Google slides, Prezi etc.

Next, only 6 of our learners often and very often use my Learning Platform such as myINSPIRE, respectively. More than 50% of our learners never use my Learning Platform, such as myINSPIRE. The remaining of our learners sometimes use my Learning Platform, such as myINSPIRE.

Of the 88 learners, 67 of them agree that they enjoy learning and doing new things, with the remaining 18 and 3 learners somehow agreeing or disagreeing on this matter. They are not hasty in making decisions. In fact, an overwhelming majority of our learners, which is 73 of them that are taking up this course, will think carefully before making any decision. Only 3 and 12 learners disagree and somehow agree and disagree that they will think carefully before making any decision.

Undeniably that 36 learners agree that they are able to work well in teams, being able to stay calm and composed during discussions. On the other hand, only a mere nine learners disagree that they are able to work well in teams; being able to stay calm and composed during discussions with the remaining learners somehow agree and disagree.

More than 60 per cent of our learners agree that they can communicate well with others, while 36 per cent somehow agree and disagree. The remaining 4 per cent disagree that they can communicate well with others.

Also, 50 of 88 learners agree that they loved doing hands-on activities and challenges as compared to 36 learners who somehow agree and disagree. Only two learners disagree that they loved doing hands-on activities and challenges.

This course was assessed using the DREAM Methodology. In the first stage, DIAGNOSE indicated that all of the learners are taking this course for the first time. Most of them are working as teachers and clerks. Their responsibility and tasks are teaching, managing documentation, controlling accounts and sales, administrating and others.

A majority of these learners admitted this course is related to their current jobs.

While mid-way studying this course, the learners were requested to reflect on the experiences they gained.

Discussion and findings

By learning this course, 74 of the learners expected to apply the knowledge or skills gained in their daily lives and another each of four learners expected to enrich their knowledge and increase their self-confidence. Besides, three learners are able to improve their skills by studying this course. Two learners believe that they can be better at decision making. Only one learner did not say anything.

There are five topics in this course such as:

- i. Topic 1: Introduction to Community Service Course
- ii. Topic 2: Community Service Project Implementation Process (I): Planning
- iii. Topic 3: Community Service Project Implementation Process (II): Implementation
- iv. Topic 4: Community Service Project Implementation Process (III): Reportage
- v. Topic 5: Community Service Project Implementation Process (IV): Reflective Journal

The participants identified various topics from the above-stated topics from this course as the most impactful to them are the concepts of fostering feelings of goodwill, independence, volunteerism, leadership, positively changing the personality of the individual, strengthening relationships, diligence, discipline, teamwork, sincerity, mutual-respect, concern and social responsibility in society (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Most Impactful Concepts from the Topics in the Study Guide Identified by the Participants Before the Course Revision

While mid-way studying this course, the learners were requested to reflect on the experiences they gained.

By learning this course, 56 of the learners find this course interesting. Meanwhile, 16 learners find this course enriching their knowledge. Two learners each enjoyed doing the activities in this course, and at the same time, they said the e-tutor provided a lot of assistance to enable them to understand the course. In addition, one each of the learners found this course made them more environmentally friendly, enjoyed attending the tutorial sessions and be more sensitive to the SDGs through doing their assignments. In contrast, four learners of this course found it is difficult for a part-time working learner like them, and one learner did not learn

much from this course. Unfortunately, four learners, or 4.6 percent, did not attempt to answer this question.

All of the learners found the course to be enjoyable and enriching, broadening their knowledge. The majority of them enjoy participating in the activities offered in this course. Through the assignment, they become more aware of the SDGs. Through this course, they learn to apply the SDGs in their daily lives. They also enjoy attending tutorial sessions. Those who cannot attend can refer to the e-tutorial session recordings. The learners also feel that the e-tutor provides significant assistance, enabling them to understand the course better. The nature of learning using myINSPIRE as a platform enables the learners to improve their ICT capabilities. As a result, this course made the learners more environmentally friendly.

The learners were also asked to reflect on what they expected from this course. Fifty-three learners expected more visual learning materials to be provided, and 16 more learners expected more time to be given to complete the assignment. Six learners expected an e-tutor who is more learner-friendly and four learners expected a more flexible assessment method and four learners also expected for a full coursework course. While the four learners did not attempt this question, and a learner said others which did not indicate the expectation

A reflection follows this as to what is different from the expected as well as something unexpected occurring. The most common difference is 38 responses to interesting visual learning resources, 19 responses to e-lessons supporting the learning process and nine responses to e-tutor who is creative and innovative in teaching. Furthermore, Seven of 88 learners say that they gain new knowledge about SDGs after taking this course. Eight respondents said e-tutorial sessions recordings available for future references. Four responses to thought-provoking and challenging assignment questions. Finally, four learners did not attempt to this question.

The learners' reflections identified some expectations are not as expected. They shared their reactions due to the differences in expectations. This includes mixture of feelings of surprise (4 responses), happiness (40 responses), acceptance (14 responses), excitement (10 responses), enthusiasm (13 responses), disappointment (3 responses). Four learners did not attempt to this question.

Among the suggestions to improve the course proposed by the learners are to increase the number of coursework (assignment), increase the time for e-tutorial and to, vary the activities to challenge their minds, participation of everyone during the tutorial session in the form of activity, e-tutor should be more knowledgeable and can explain better as well as a good command in English.

When learners were asked why this course did not meet their expectations, the responses indicated that the course

lacked activities, required learners to manage their time, and was quite challenging to complete during the Movement Control Order (MCO). Still, the majority of them found the course as they were expecting.

In the ASSESS stage, learners are asked to assess the impact of what they have learned in terms of Academic Development; the majority of learners enriched their knowledge about the SDGs. As for Professional Development, the majority of them can apply the acquired knowledge in their work. Based on the responses, the majority of the learners learned to work in a team in Social Development. Finally, the impact of what they learned in terms of personal development is that the learners are more open-minded.

Following the revision, participants identified concepts such as the relationship between SDGs and volunteerism, environmental awareness, and lifelong learning as having impacted them after enrolling in this course (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Most Impactful Concepts from the Topics in the Study Guide Identified by the Participants After the Course Revision

Learners were asked to suggest things they would like to be different if they were to take this course again. Some suggestions include increasing more knowledge, exploring new things, keeping learning virtually, adding more discussion, and solving problems creatively.

For the final stage, learners are requested to suggest how they can apply the new knowledge learned from the course in the future. Various suggestions were given, including; Sharing knowledge with others, creating a better social environment, applying the knowledge in family life and trying to explore a new way of seeking knowledge.

“Now What” question

Without a doubt, community service activities can produce positive self-development in each individual. Many benefits can be derived from the implementation of community service activities. For instance, the community service activities, which are carried out together, will create

a sense of understanding and strengthen the group's self-esteem. Besides, activities that are well-planned will have an impact on personal health in terms of physical and spiritual aspects. In fact, according to Lisman (1998), many learners think that what they acquire by volunteering is more valuable to their learning than what they study in the classroom. Furthermore, learners who have performed community service have been reported to have higher self-esteem and moral growth. On top of that, activities that are implemented jointly in a community consisting of various ethnic groups will result in stronger tolerance and strengthening of unity among the ethnic groups.

Community service is based on giving back and supporting others. As a result, it emphasizes the necessity of assisting others in need, especially those who are less privileged than ourselves. Community service is significant because it brings us closer to our community by strengthening it and contributing to the betterment of all of us to live.

Part for So What – sixth and last question:

All of OUM's course materials are crafted according to a uniform format. Because of this, modifying any kind of educational resource necessitates analytical rigor to pinpoint exactly where alterations are needed and innovative thinking to rearrange existing content to accommodate the addition of new information. The instructional guides provided by OUM adhere to a strict format. As a result, it takes analysis to reorganize the contents and incorporate the new information while making updates to any educational resources.

Time was a factor in developing the in-service teacher training modules because of the already heavy workload at the institution. Additionally, the language of reference materials was a challenge as most reference books pertaining to SDGs were written in English and so needed to be translated into the *Bahasa Melayu* (Malay Language). The group, however, is able to overcome their language barrier via cooperative effort.

One of the challenges I experienced was trying to convince people of the significance of the SDGs in our daily lives and its relationship to this course. As a result, I participated in the March 2021 OUM Lecture series, which aimed to increase awareness and comprehension of SDGs within the OUM community. My presentation's theme was "Peace Can Be Achieved Through C.E.S.S.," and I focused on SDG Goal 16 Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions.

Additionally, I have decided to enrol in the Coursera course "Driving business towards the Sustainable Development Goals" that Commonwealth of Learning and Coursera jointly organized. This course lasts seven weeks and is offered by Erasmus University Rotterdam. The reason this course is important and relevant to me is also because I am currently working on a research project for Erasmus +,

the European Union, called "ICT-enabled In-service Training of Teachers to Address Education for Sustainability [ICTeEfS]". My team and I had to create a program for pre-service and in-service teachers as well as train them to use ICT to address sustainability-related challenges in education as part of this research project.

The inclusion of SDGs in this course should motivate learners' knowledge of and understanding of SDGs. With this knowledge, individuals should be more concerned with what is going on in their own lives, in society, in their nation, and in the world. They ought to be aware of how crucial understanding of the SDGs is to maintaining peace and prosperity on the planet. Nevertheless, learners who are already familiar with the SDGs will be able to deepen their understanding and increase their commitment to the SDGs with the exposure provided by this course. After taking the course for one semester, learners should be able to educate their friends, family, and neighbours about the SDGs.

SDGs is already part of the Malaysian school curriculum (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2013). Volunteering offers a venue for individuals and entire communities to take part in their own development. To increase awareness of the significance of global warming in their community, learners can establish a team with their fellow learners and choose any one of the 17 SDGs, for example, Goal 13 Climate Action. Significantly, volunteering frequently has a cascading effect. It encourages individuals to influence other local or global communities. This is essential in terms of the SDGs since it refers to the phrase "Leave No One Behind."

Steve Jobs once said "If you define the problem correctly, you almost have the solution." Therefore, all these challenges were tackled and overcome successfully.

Conclusion

The success of implementing a community service activity depends on the cooperation and consensus between each member involved. Even though the planning was excellent and detailed, if it was not applied correctly, it would cause many problems. Therefore, each group member must ensure that the activity or the implementation of community service that will be carried out is a joint activity and must be conducted as a group.

Above all, community service activities should produce positive input to each individual's self-development. For instance, the community service activities inculcate the spirit of living together in a community, regardless of race, religion, beliefs and ideology. Besides, community service activities can nurture a sense of love and togetherness in individuals towards the surrounding community. For example, when learners carry out community service in nursing homes, they will learn to become friends with the residents and realize that kindness should be a daily activity and that everyone should be treated equally.

Moreover, this course is to cultivate respect for the world and each other and provide our citizens with the understanding of a diverse world to empathize, empower our learners to lead our societies, and enjoy the differences in this world. It is worth pointing out that particular importance has to be given various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues pertaining to the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al., 2024; Ghazali et al. 2024).

Finally, through the voluntary activities, one will feel like part of the community and subsequently, will gain various positive values and unleash hidden talents.

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Learning Skills for 21st Century Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

The 2030 Development Agenda was formally endorsed by 193 UN member states on September 25, 2015, combined with a set of bold new Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), also known as the Global Goals, comprising 17 Goals, 169 Targets, and 232 indicators. This paper aims to discuss the process, techniques, and results of revising OUMH1603 Learning Skills for the 21st Century at Open University Malaysia (OUM) based on the six key questions. The first question, "What," asks about the course before revision. The second and third questions ask "Why" (explaining the need for review) and "Where" describing course deficiencies to be filled. Meanwhile, the fourth question details revision and course assessment during implementation. The fifth question, "Now What," describes how the course has changed from "What" it was earlier. The last question, "So what?" discusses the obstacles encountered from the beginning to the present and how they were resolved. Furthermore, this paper employs two methodologies: DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) to embed sustainability and the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Meanwhile, the DREAM (Diagnose, review, reflect, explain, assess, and manage) technique is used to evaluate redesigned courses during implementation. The skills of creativity, critical thinking, communication, and collaboration have been built into this course, so the learner is better prepared and has a deeper understanding of the SDGs, the six pillars of learning skills, the 10Cs of learning tools, and the four pillars of sustainability and justice. Consequently, the learners will be independent, compassionate, and empathetic lifelong learners.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); Learning Skills; Global Citizenship Education; environment; DREAM methodology; DeCoRe+ methodology

14. Introduction

OUM offers 54 programmes, including 28 undergraduate and 26 graduate level. The academic year has three semesters. Each semester, approximately 650 courses are offered to 27,000 learners. Each learner takes three courses per semester.

OUM adopts an entirely online blended pedagogy based on Garrison, Anderson, and Archer's (2000) Community of Inquiry Model of Engagement (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Community of Inquiry (COI) Model of Engagement

This pedagogy comprises a synchronous, entirely online, face-to-face tutorial delivered via Google Meet to facilitate interactions between learners and instructors (Teaching Presence), and an asynchronous online forum to promote interactions between learners and peers (Social Presence). The forum uses OUM's myINSPIRE learning management system (LMS). Online modules and e-lessons facilitate interactions between learners and learning materials, promoting cognitive presence.

OUM's module has a "self-check" and "activities" component. Both sections prompted learners to test/check their knowledge after completing the module and undertake the specified activities in groups or individually. E-lessons based on topics in the module will assist learning. This framework outlines each topic, providing links to the module's content, relevant YouTube videos, and

supplementary reading resources. E-lessons include discussions, case studies, and self-tests.

Learners utilised to internalise teacher-presented material. In the digital age, such a practice is no longer viable. Technology has transformed how people learn, think, and connect. Learners must acquire, integrate, and apply new knowledge to solve problems and apply it in varied settings. Learners must be 21st-century ready. "21st-century skills" refers to the information, talents, work habits, and personality qualities considered essential to success in today's society, particularly in future professions and workplaces (Mishra & Mehta, 2017).

The ICTeEfS project

Asia's rapid economic expansion has had a detrimental impact on the environment. Recent climate-related disasters in the region underscore the need for Asian policymakers to act now to safeguard their citizens and mitigate and reverse climate change, ensuring future progress. Education for Sustainability (EfS) can help address these challenges. Asian leaders are committed to EfS and concerned about implementing the SDGs, but it is classroom teachers who are the actual change-makers.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries where teachers require training to address ICTs, climate change, and other environmental challenges. On the one hand, education faculties must reconstruct their study programmes by incorporating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS). At the same time, on the other, they must capitalise on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly increasing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs necessitate the incorporation of ICT into the curriculum of teacher education programmes and in-service training. However, ICT integration does not simply imply the addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It necessarily involves changes in teaching and learning and necessitates comprehensive and integrated planning of ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

The proposed project aims to provide an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, preparing them to adopt cutting-edge teaching methodologies and pedagogies geared toward education for sustainability (EfS). The Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education, funded by the European Commission, has provided support for the ICTeEfS project from 2019 to 2023. The more precise goals are to:

6. Encourage the growth of education faculties at partner universities to ensure that their curriculum, instruction, and research align with the field of education for sustainability.
7. Enhance the academic staff's capabilities at the faculties of education so that they can contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a

comprehensive in-service teacher training program on sustainability education.

8. Develop a blended learning-enabled in-service teacher professional development program that is effective, affordable, decentralized, scalable, and innovative, with a focus on integrating education for sustainability across school curricula.
9. Create cutting-edge teaching, learning, and curricular materials in the form of an e-Toolkit that is multilingual and addresses the incorporation of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
10. To improve collaboration in the area of ICTeEfS and the replication of created outputs and outcomes, create a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability.

The objective of this paper is to discuss the process, strategies, and results of the revision of the course OUMH1603 Learning Skills for the 21st Century at Open University Malaysia (OUM), taking into account six key issues: The first question, "What," focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of learners enrolled in the course, important themes in the curriculum, competencies to be developed, the teaching strategies used, and the methods of evaluating learners. The second and third questions address "Why" (explaining the justifications for revision) and "Where," which describes the gaps in the course that will be filled during the revision process. The fourth question is a "How" inquiry that details the revision and course assessment procedures used during the implementation phase. The fifth question, "Now What," describes how the course has changed from "What" it was previously and illustrates how it has been updated or amended. The sixth and last question, "So What?" examines the difficulties encountered throughout the entire preceding process, from the beginning to the present, and how they were overcome. The discussion section addresses the following sub-questions explicitly: What effects will the revised course have on local and global society, curriculum, teaching, and learning? How has knowledge of education, learning, and curriculum changed? What can be learned from this experience, and how will it impact society and the beneficiaries, such as learners? What has to be done, why it has not been done, and what would be the next steps?

The What, Why, and Where Questions for Revising (OUMH1603 Learning Skills for 21st Century)

The Learning Skills for 21st Century Skills course is introduced to all OUM learners, especially those in Semester 1, to meet the demands of the 21st Century. It introduces learners to workplace expectations in the 21st Century, basic learning skills including numeracy and digital literacy, and the important 21st-century skills known as the 4Cs (Creativity, Critical thinking, Communication, and Collaborative skills). Additionally, it fosters global citizenship, promoting a better understanding of diverse cultures and environmental awareness for a better future.

This is a university course compulsory for all undergraduate learners across various disciplines. Additionally, this course lays the foundation for Open and Distance Learning (ODL).

The number of learners registering will depend on the number of new learners enrolling. OUM's new enrolment every semester is approximately between 3000 and 4000 learners.

Learners should be able to develop the following abilities: to master Open and Distance Learning (ODL) while adapting to the dynamic technological changes occurring within the e-learning environment; to lead in group discussions, either physically or virtually; to collaborate in teams beyond the physical classroom; and to think critically and creatively. Nonetheless, the competencies to be developed in this course are to cultivate respect for the world and for one another and to provide our citizens with an understanding of a diverse world, enabling them to empathize, empower our learners to lead their societies, and appreciate the differences in our world. Besides, in this course, we not only want our learners to acquire 21st-century skills, but we also want them to take responsibility for acting sustainably on our planet.

OUM practices an entirely online blended pedagogy to deliver its courses. This pedagogy comprises fully online face-to-face tutorials conducted via Google Meet, an asynchronous online forum using OUM's learning management system, myINSPIRE, and online learning resources.

Besides, there is no final examination for this course. The assessment is 100% coursework, comprising 60% assignments and 40% online multiple-choice quizzes. The former assessment covers the elements of the 4Cs (Communication, Collaboration, Creativity, and Critical Thinking). At the same time, learners are given the freedom to select issues of their choice based on the themes presented in the questions. The coursework assessment, which includes an assignment, covers the elements of communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking. In addition, learners are given the freedom to select issues of their choice based on the themes presented in the questions.

On the other hand, the online multiple-choice quizzes will enable learners to develop the self-discipline to acquire knowledge relevant to the course's learning outcome. Twenty multiple-choice quizzes cover topics 1-10.

There are ten topics in this course:

Topic 1: Being a 21st Century Learner

Topic 2: Study Skills

Topic 3: Numeracy Skills

Topic 4: Digital Literacy

Topic 5: Creativity and Innovation

Topic 6: Critical Thinking and Reasoning Skills

Topic 7: Communication Skills

Topic 8: Collaborative Skills

Topic 9: Global Citizenship Education

Topic 10: The Environment and Us

“Why” question

The process of enhancing this module is based on DeCoRe plus, which Makrakis (2017) introduced. The DeCoRe is the abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction. Deconstruction, which involves critically analyzing the functioning of personal perspectives, habits of mind, and chosen curriculum units or modules. Construction is the process of gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives). Meanwhile, Reconstruction is integrating newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference. The primary goal of DeCoRe plus is to help pre-service teachers consider teaching, learning, and curriculum from the perspectives of critical pedagogy and sustainable justice while also developing various ways of knowing about these topics (Makrakis, 2017).

Before the revision of this module, there was no emphasis on marginalized people, referring to individuals and groups who are excluded from the benefits of economic, social, and political life in ways that vary over time and place.

By adopting the 2030 Agenda, the 193 United Nations Member States have committed to leaving no one behind, including marginalized people, to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Additionally, Goal 16 of the SDGs focuses on Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions. Goal 16 aims to develop strong and just institutions worldwide, supporting peaceful and inclusive societies.

Therefore, after the revision, the emphasis on marginalized people was embedded, as a subtopic in the module on a few topics of this module such as “Being a 21st Century Learner”; “Numeracy Skills”; “Creativity and Innovation”; “Global Citizenship Education” and “The Environment and Us”.

Generally, neither SDGs, the six pillars of learning, nor the 10Cs are missing in this course after the first revision.

The justifications are as follows;

I. The SDGs

In topic 9, “Global Citizenship Education,”; it covers specifically Goal 4 Quality Education in general and Target 4.7:

“By 2030, ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including, among others, through education for sustainable

development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship and appreciation of cultural diversity and culture's contribution to sustainable development”

Concurrently in topic nine, one of the subtopics discussed is gender equality, which is associated with Goal 5 Gender Equality. Men and women must be treated with respect and love to achieve equality. Human rights and inclusivity drive gender equality advocacy. Equal rights regardless of gender, whether male or female, in all spheres of life. How can a country develop when the society is discriminated against and marginalized economically, politically, and socially?

The importance of achieving gender equality within and outside the household has been reaffirmed in the recently adopted Goal 5 of SDGs.

Meanwhile, in Topic 10, “The Environment and Us,” the SDGs encompass Goal 13: Climate Action, Goal 14: Life Below Water, and Goal 15: Life on Land. These SDGs are covered under various subtopics such as “Global Environmental Issues”, “Changing Land Cover and Water Surfaces”, “Climate Change”, “Loss of Biodiversity”, “Population and Development”, “Pollution”, “Urbanisation”, “Green Technology and Environment”, “Ecological Footprint and You”.

II. The six pillars of learning

There are six pillars of learning:

- i. Learning to know
- ii. Learning to be
- iii. Learning to do
- iv. Learning to live together sustainably
- v. Learning to transform oneself and society
- vi. Learning to give and share

For instance, “Learning to transform oneself and society”. Literacy and numeracy are important, but we must also focus on issues such as change, interdependence, identity, diversity, rights and responsibilities, peacebuilding, poverty and wealth, sustainability, and global justice, which contribute to contemporary global issues at local, national, and international levels, for instance, in topic 9 Global Citizenship Education (GCED). This topic provides our citizens with an understanding of a diverse world, enabling them to respond to the unfamiliar with empathy, empowering young people to lead our societies, embracing peace, promoting civic participation, and celebrating our differences. Through Topic 9, learners will develop greater empathy, compassion, adaptability, and tolerance towards local and global events.

Besides, “Learning to live together sustainably.” For example, education for sustainable development should not be taught in isolation, but rather on how people should react

and practice in their daily lives. We were taught about the environment's 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle) a long time ago. It is now 5Rs (Refuse, Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, and Repurpose) or even 6Rs (Reduce, Rethink, Refuse, Recycle, Reuse, and Repair). Regardless of whether it is the fundamental 3Rs, 5Rs, or 6Rs, the “Rs” of sustainability should not only be comprehended by learners, but more importantly, they need to act so that everyone can live together sustainably. Confucius once said, "I hear and I forget. I see, and I remember. I do, and I understand."

III. ICTs as enabling tools for the 10Cs

ICTs as enabling tools for the 10Cs include: critical thinking and problem-solving, communication, collaboration, creativity and innovation, connectivity and networking, critical consciousness or conscientization, critical reflection, cross-cultural competence, co-responsibility, and knowledge construction. However, some 10Cs can be mapped to the contents of this course as follows;

- i. Communication (Attending e-tutorial)
- ii. Creativity & innovation (preparing assignment)
- iii. Critical thinking (preparing assignment)
- iv. Connectivity (Online Class participation)
- v. Critical reflection (reviewing through reflective journal)
- vi. Critical consciousness (preparing assignment)

V. 4 pillars of sustainability justice

The concept of "sustainability justice" was introduced by Makrakis (2016, 2017) and reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economics, and culture.

Environmental justice, for instance, is discussed in sections 10.1, "Why Should We Care about the Environment?", 10.3, "Green Technology and the Environment," and 10.5, "Ecological Footprint and You." It is hoped that through the discussion, learners will act and become advocates for change. Meanwhile, society, economics, and culture are well-explained in Topic 9 of Global Citizenship Education from the perspectives of gender equality, globalization, and conflicts. Society, economics, and culture are also implicitly discussed in Topic 10 of this course and vice versa. Therefore, these four pillars of sustainability demonstrate how they are interdependent (Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2017) and the same time also emphasize social justice, nonviolence, and peace, which are frequently disregarded in sustainable development education (Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2012).

“Where” question

Since this course is offered to all learners undertaking any programme with OUM, nothing has been purposefully omitted. In addition, the nature of this course is to lay the basic foundation for our learners in the Open Distance Learning (ODL) learning experience over the next 4-5 years.

Therefore, some individuals and items are purposefully omitted from this course.

One of the SDGs addressed in this course is Goal 17: Partnership for the Goals. This is because mobilizing resources, exchanging knowledge, fostering the production and transfer of ecologically sound technology, and building capacity will lead to stronger collaborations, which in turn contribute to environmental protection and sustainable development. Nevertheless, increased cooperation among governments, civil society, multilateral organizations, donors, and the private sector is necessary to provide developing countries and their beneficiaries with technologies that enhance the efficient use of natural resources, minimize waste, effectively treat pollution, and mitigate climate change. We can achieve all our goals when we work together toward a common objective. Sharing objectives entails sharing a vision. We all want to see poverty eradicated, inequality reduced, and global warming brought to a halt.

Creativity, critical thinking, communication, and collaboration are crucial 21st-century skills, but we cannot limit our learners to these four Cs. In a world where ICTs are driving rapid progress and extending human knowledge, education must go beyond the 4Cs to the 10Cs enabled by ICT (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2017). Learners will also study Connectivity and networking, Critical consciousness, Critical reflection, Cross/inter-cultural competency, Co-responsibility, and Knowledge construction.

Methodologies: The How Question

Makrakis (2006) proposed a six-stage capacity-building strategy for training academic staff to include sustainability in their courses (Figure 2).

Figure 2. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

First, trainees' didactic profiles are diagnosed. Based on trainee characteristics, a training session action plan is generated (second stage). The training content follows the action plan and combines theory and practice in subject units or modules that can be tailored to meet the trainee's needs (third stage). Comparing trainees' learning outcomes to their initial profiles and action plan aims and objectives (fourth

stage). The end receivers, the learners, are evaluated by transferring their skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A monitoring and upgrading system is integrated across all phases to maintain optimal training process functioning and possible updating (sixth stage).

Makrakis (2017) employed DeCoRe+, an abbreviation for Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, to integrate sustainability and the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is a design technique that focuses on transformative curricular creation. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ are as follows.

7. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.
8. **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
9. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
10. **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
11. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
12. **Finalizing: Reflecting on and evaluating** what has been learned and changed.

Makrakis (2023) proposed the DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) technique for evaluating redesigned courses during implementation. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what learners bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). DREAM approach is a critical action research procedure that tries to assess and enhance a course. The learner, directed by the course instructor, produces a portfolio using the DREAM Methodology. DREAM is a course prerequisite. The instructor must analyze the learners' DREAM portfolios and submit a class report. The instructor and learners can discuss the DREAM portfolios to improve the course.

Figure 3: The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

“How” question

The methodology used for the revision is DeCoRe, which was introduced by Makrakis (2017) as a consequence of experiences gained during the implementation. The assessment, using the DREAM methodology tool developed by the project coordinator, will be conducted during the pilot phase (Winter semester 2020) as well as through the new peer review by the Project Leader and other team members. Approximately 350 learners out of approximately 3000 have responded to surveys based on the DREAM technique.

On the other hand, DeCoRe is the abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction. The table below shows that this approach includes six nonlinear processes: diagnostic evaluation, deconstruction, construction, reconstruction, implementation, and summative evaluation.

DeCoRe plus Processes

DeCoRe+ Processes	Key concepts in each process
Diagnostic Evaluation	Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
Deconstruction	Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives/habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
Construction	Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
Reconstruction	Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.

Implementation	Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
Summative Evaluation	Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Makrakis (2017, p. 112).*

The links and internal inconsistencies of economic curricular courses with environmental challenges have been identified as a result of using this approach.

The OUMH1603 Learning Skills for the 21st Century was offered in the September 2021 semester. The learners comprise 68 males and 125 females. Most of OUM’s learners are working adults; thus, their ages range from a minimum of 21 years old to those above 60 years old. Also, since OUM’s teaching and learning are entirely online, these learners are scattered throughout the country.

In terms of their technological competence, 71 learners had never had access to online materials, such as e-books, e-journals, and e-databases. Meanwhile, only 4.7% of learners very often access online materials. At the same time, approximately 82 out of 193 learners have access to online materials, such as e-books, e-journals, and e-databases. The survey confirmed that only 1.1% of learners often access online materials, such as e-books, e-journals, and e-databases.

Of the 193 learners who answered this survey, 29.5% often used statistical tools such as Microsoft Excel, IBM SPSS, and MATLAB, compared to 38.9% of learners who sometimes used these tools. Meanwhile, 28 learners never use statistical tools such as Microsoft Excel, IBM SPSS, and MATLAB, while 33 learners use these tools very often.

More than 50% of our learners occasionally use social media platforms, such as blogs and discussion forums, while 31.1% never use these platforms. Only 24 of our learners use social media platforms such as blogs and discussion forums often or very often.

Next, 48 and 86 of our learners never and sometimes use presentation tools such as Microsoft PowerPoint, Google Slides, Prezi, etc. In contrast, only 19.7% and 10.9% of our learners often or very often use presentation tools such as Microsoft PowerPoint, Google Slides, and Prezi.

Only eight and seven of our learners use my Learning Platform, such as myINSPIRE, often and very often, respectively. More than 50% of our learners never use my Learning Platform, such as myINSPIRE. The remaining of our learners are sometimes use my Learning Platform such as myINSPIRE.

* Makrakis V. (2017). Unlocking the potentiality and actuality of ICTs in developing sustainable – justice curricula and society. Knowledge Cultures 5(2), pp. 103-122, ISSN 2327-5731

Of the 193 learners, 166 agree that they enjoy learning and doing new things, while the remaining 27 learners either agree or disagree with this statement. They are not hasty in making decisions. An overwhelmingly of our learners, which is 143 of them that are taking up this course, will think carefully before making any decision. Only three and 47 learners disagree and somehow agree and disagree that they will think carefully before making any decision.

Undeniably that 84 learners agree that they are able to work well in teams, being able to stay calm and composed during discussions. On the other hand, only a mere 15 learners disagree that they are able to work well in teams, staying calm and composed during discussions, with the remaining learners somehow agreeing and disagreeing.

Approximately 53.9 percent of our learners agree that they can communicate well with others, while 43 percent agree or disagree to some extent. The remaining 3 percent disagree that they can communicate well with others.

Additionally, 111 of 193 learners agreed that they enjoyed doing hands-on activities and challenges, compared to 77 learners who agreed or disagreed. Only five learners disagreed that they loved doing hands-on activities and challenges.

This course was assessed using the DREAM Methodology. In the first stage, DIAGNOSE indicated that all of the learners are taking this course for the first time. Most of them are working as teachers and clerks. Their responsibilities and tasks include teaching, managing documentation, controlling accounts and sales, administration, and others.

A majority of these learners admitted this course is related to their current jobs.

By learning this course, 170 learners are expected to apply the knowledge or skills gained in their daily lives. Another nine learners expected to enrich their knowledge, and four learners expected to Increase their self-confidence. Besides, eight learners are able to improve their skills by studying this course. Lastly, a mere two learners believe that they can be better in decision making.

The concepts of smart goals, ICT, gender equality, skills for the 21st century, numeracy, Global Citizenship Education (GCED), leadership, teamwork, as well as creativity and innovation were among the topics from this course that the participants said had the most impact on them. (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Most Impactful Concepts from the Topics in the Study Guide Identified by the Participants Before the Course Revision

Midway through this course, the learners were requested to reflect on the experiences they had gained.

Discussion and findings

By learning this course, 122 or 63 percent of the learners find this course interesting. Meanwhile, 32 or 17 percent of the learners find this course enriches their knowledge. Seven of the 193 learners who participated in this survey agreed that through the assignment, they have become more sensitive to the Sustainable Development Goals. Only two learners said that this course made them more environmentally friendly, and one learner enjoyed attending the tutorial sessions. On the same note, one learner reported being able to improve their ICT capabilities. Additionally, one learner noted that the e-tutor provides a significant amount of assistance, enabling them to better understand the course. Additionally, one learner reported that by completing this course, they learned to apply the SDGs in their daily life.

On the other hand, according to four learners, this course is challenging for part-time working learners, and one learner found some topics in the course difficult to understand. Meanwhile, four learners also found this course boring. Lastly, 16 or 8.2 percent of learners did not respond to this question.

All of the learners found that the course is interesting and enriching their knowledge. The majority of them enjoy doing the activities in this course. Through the assignment, they are more sensitive to the Sustainable Development Goals. Through learning this course, they are able to learn to apply SDGs in their daily life. They also enjoy attending tutorial sessions. Those who cannot attend, they can refer to the e-tutorial session recordings. The learners also feel that the e-tutor provides a lot of assistance to enable them to understand the course. The nature of learning using myINSPIRE as a platform enables the learners to improve their ICT capabilities. As a result, this course made the learners more environmentally friendly.

The learners were also asked to reflect on what they expected from this course. 104 of 193 learners expected

more visual learning materials to be provided, and 28 more learners expected more time to be given to complete the assignment. Eight learners expected an e-tutor who is more learner-friendly, 15 learners expected a more flexible assessment method, and nine learners also expected a fully coursework course. Seven learners expected more collaborative learning activities in this course. While the sixteen learners did not attempt this question, and six learners said others, which did not indicate the expectation.

This is followed by a reflection on what is different from the expected, as well as on an unexpected occurrence that took place. The most notable differences are eight responses to interesting visual learning resources, three responses to e-lessons that support the learning process, and two responses to an e-tutor who is creative and innovative in teaching.

A reflection follows, detailing what is different from the expected, as well as any unexpected events that occurred. The most common responses are 81 learners, or 42 percent, who are interested in visual learning resources, 37 learners, or 19.2 percent, who are interested in e-lessons that support the learning process, and 16 learners, or 8.3 percent, who are interested in an e-tutor who is creative and innovative in teaching. Furthermore, fourteen learners, or 7.3%, reported gaining new knowledge about the SDGs after taking this course. Fifteen learners, or 8 percent of respondents, stated that e-tutorial session recordings are available for future reference. Eight learners, or 4.1 percent, responded to thought-provoking and challenging assignment questions. Finally, 17 or 9 percent did not attempt to answer this question.

The learners' reflections identified some expectations that were not as expected. They shared their reactions due to the differences in expectations. This includes a mixture of feelings of surprise (18 responses), happiness (71 responses), acceptance (44 responses), excitement (11 responses), enthusiasm (29 responses), and disappointment (3 responses). Sixteen learners did not attempt to answer this question.

Among the suggestions to improve the course proposed by the learners are more interactive learning in Google Meet, tutors being more creative in their approach to learning during tutoring to engage learners, the e-tutorial session requiring additional time, and adding more quizzes and questions that can test learners' understanding, among others.

When learners were asked why this course did not meet their expectations, the responses included numerous subtopics, such as the need for more comprehensive coverage, a lack of relevance to their work, and the requirement for an examination to test their understanding, as the quizzes were deemed insufficient. Still, the majority of them found the course as they were expecting.

In the ASSESS stage, learners are asked to assess the impact of what they have learned in terms of Academic Development; the majority of learners enriched their knowledge about the SDGs. As for Professional Development, the majority of them can apply the acquired knowledge in their work. Based on the responses, the majority of the learners learned to work in a team in Social Development. Finally, the impact of what they learned in terms of personal development is that the learners are more open-minded.

The participants recognized concepts such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), unity is strength, pollution, global warming, and sustainable development that impacted them after registering for this course (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Most Impactful Concepts from the Topics in the Study Guide Identified by the Participants After the Course Revision

Learners were asked to suggest things they would like to be different if they were to retake this course. Some suggestions include increasing knowledge, exploring new things, continuing virtual learning, adding more discussion, and solving problems creatively.

For the final stage, learners are asked to suggest how they can apply the new knowledge they have learned from the course in the future. Various suggestions were offered, including sharing knowledge with others, fostering a more positive social environment, applying knowledge in family life, and exploring new methods of seeking knowledge.

“Now What” question

The learner will be better equipped with knowledge from the 4C's: Creativity, Critical thinking, Communication, and Collaborative skills, which have been embedded in this course and will subsequently become an autonomous lifelong learner. Nevertheless, the last two topics of this course, “Global Citizenship Education” and “Environment and Us,” will undoubtedly create greater awareness and foster the development of responsible learners.

It is hoped that through this course, learners will be able to practice the 4Cs (Creativity, Critical Thinking, Communication, and Collaborative Skills) in their daily lives. Furthermore, the developers of the course content also

proposed to re-evaluate learners' position in the environment, in the hope that learners can appreciate the intricate interrelations among various components within the environment.

Moreover, the other ideas espoused by the course writers aim to empower learners to think, share, and act toward a more just, peaceful, inclusive, and sustainable world. For instance, in module 9, each of us may contribute to policy reforms to ensure that no one is left behind, including marginalised communities such as 'orang asli' (the native/indigenous or aboriginal people) and people with special needs or disabilities. Undeniably, persistent discrimination, especially gender discrimination, is a primary cause of people being left behind, leaving individuals, families, and entire communities marginalised and excluded.

Part for So What – sixth and last question:

All of OUM's course materials are crafted according to a uniform format. Because of this, modifying any educational resource necessitates analytical rigor to pinpoint precisely where alterations are needed and innovative thinking to rearrange existing content to accommodate the addition of new information. The instructional guides provided by OUM adhere to a strict format. As a result, it takes analysis to reorganize the contents and incorporate the new information while making updates to any educational resources.

Time was a crucial factor in developing the in-service teacher training modules, given the institution's already heavy workload. Additionally, the language of reference materials was a challenge as most reference books pertaining to SDGs were written in English and so needed to be translated into *Bahasa Melayu* (Malay Language). The group, however, can overcome their language barrier via cooperative effort.

One of the challenges I faced was convincing people of the importance of the SDGs in their daily lives, particularly about this course. Consequently, I participated in the OUM Lecture series held in March 2021 to raise awareness and understanding of the SDGs within the OUM community. The title of my presentation was "Peace Can Be Achieved by C.E.S.S.," in which I focused on SDG 16: Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions.

Additionally, I have selected "Driving Business Towards the Sustainable Development Goals" as a Coursera course co-organized by the Commonwealth of Learning and Coursera. Erasmus University Rotterdam offers this course over a period of seven weeks. The importance and relevance of choosing this course also lie in the fact that I am currently involved in a research project entitled "ICT-enabled In-service Training of Teachers to Address Education for Sustainability [ICTeEfS]," funded by Erasmus +, a European Union initiative. This research project required my

team and I to write a module for pre-service teachers and in-service teachers and train the teachers to integrate the ICT to address the issues of sustainability related to education.

The integration of the SDGs within this course should create awareness and understanding of the SDGs among learners. From this understanding, they should be more concerned with happenings around them: in their lives, society, country, and the world. They should understand the importance of knowledge about SDGs to ensure prosperity and harmony can be maintained throughout the world. Furthermore, through this course, learners who are already familiar with the SDGs will be able to deepen their understanding and become more committed to achieving the SDGs. After completing the 1-semester course, learners should be able to share knowledge about the SDGs and create awareness among family members and their communities.

SDGs are already part of the Malaysian school curriculum (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2013). Indeed, Global Citizenship Education, as stated under Target 4.7, is taught across multiple subjects in primary schools through multidisciplinary topics that aim to improve students' knowledge, skills, and behavior related to sustainability (Sharifah Zarina Syed Zakaria et al., 2021). With this awareness, teachers should be motivated to integrate the SDGs into their lessons, thereby creating awareness and enriching their learners' knowledge of the SDGs. Additionally, exposure to the SDGs can catalyze teachers, learners, and ultimately, communities to integrate the SDGs into their daily lives.

Steve Jobs once said, "If you define the problem correctly, you almost have the solution." Therefore, all these challenges were successfully tackled and overcome.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this course introduces learners to the workplace expectations in the 21st Century, basic learning skills including numeracy and digital literacy, and the increasingly important 21st-century skills known as 4C (creativity, critical thinking, communication, and collaborative skills). These skills are designed to help learners keep pace with the 21st-century world. Each skill is unique in how it helps the learner, but they all are essential in the Internet age. The learner will utilize most of these skills while participating in learning activities in their academic courses and will eventually apply them directly or indirectly in their workplace. Additionally, this course aims to cultivate respect for the world and for one another, providing our citizens with an understanding of a diverse world that fosters empathy and empowers learners to lead their societies and appreciate the differences that exist in our world. It is also critical to say that particular importance has to be given various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues about the participatory curriculum development process enabled

by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

Finally, this course also depicts the importance of the planet. It demonstrates that the planet we inhabit is complex and challenging. The only planet we inhabit has become increasingly interdependent and interconnected. Any actions that happen locally will affect our community, our city, and all of us. Therefore, we must understand one another, live as one global citizen, and prepare our younger generation to find solutions to the challenges in this interconnected world. In this course, we do not only want our learners to acquire 21st-century skills but equally important is they have the responsibility to act sustainably for our planet.

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The ABSY1103 Introduction to Shariah Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens Of SDG

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Abstract

Environmental education aims to produce an environmentally literate individual who understands the relationship between natural and social systems, believes in the unity of humans and nature, and is aware of the effects of technological developments on the environment. This paper aimed to present the processes, practises, and outcomes of revising ABSY1103 Introduction to Shariah at OUM to integrate education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum through course revision. The DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Makrakis's (2017) Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction approach, was employed to integrate sustainability, specifically the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The course has been revised to reflect the main content, objectives, approach, and course assessment. The DREAM methodology, developed by Kostoulas-Makrakis (2016), was used to evaluate revised courses during the implementation process. During the process of improving the DeCoRe-based module, several SDG elements, the 6 pillars of learning, and the 10Cs were incorporated into the course. This project has demonstrated that DeCoRe and the DREAM Methodology are effective ways to revise a curriculum, integrating education for sustainability into teaching, learning, and curriculum for participants. After all, ESD is the most effective way for the community to receive the SDGs. It has also been shown that SDGs can be communicated through any discipline that promotes the same goal, most notably Islamic Studies.

Keywords: DREAM methodology, DeCoRe+ methodology, Shariah, Sustainability, Pillar of learning

1. Introduction

Humanity has been grappling with the consequences of unsustainable economic development driven by profit maximization, resulting in the excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources over the past few decades (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite current efforts to halt this unsustainable development process, much work remains to be done. The sustainability dilemma that the world is currently facing is directly attributable to education systems at all levels, but notably higher education. This is primarily because decision-makers, leaders, and consumers are the end products of educational institutions, which contribute to an unsustainable consumer culture and drive societal and economic development (Makrakis, 2011).

A fundamental change through an alternative development model that gives proper weight to sustainable well-being should depend heavily on education. In contrast to the prevalent hedonic well-being fueled by unsustainable behaviours and forms of production and consumption, sustainable well-being, in our understanding, is similar to Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). To learn how to improve oneself and society, it is crucial to pursue "sustainability justice," a concept coined by Makrakis (2006, 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economics, and culture.

It is worth noting that while significant investments have been made in environmental education over the past few decades, they have primarily focused on fostering positive environmental attitudes rather than increasing concern for environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning and curriculum.

However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability have shown that lecturing, as expected, is the most prevalent teaching method, while role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, are used at much lower rates (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

A project entitled Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (RUCAS) (Makrakis, 2013; 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of, and capable of acting in transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts to teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are the agents for change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016;2018; Blake et al., 2013) and for turning schools sustainable (Kadji-Beltran, C., Zachariou, A., & Stevenson, R. B. (2013).

To put the issue in a local context, efforts to raise awareness of sustainable development should be made in collaboration with all communities and not just one group. The 1992 Rio de Janeiro Earth Summit Conference, which led to the creation of Agenda 21, marked the first time that the component of education for sustainable development was formally acknowledged. Every chapter of Agenda 21 places a strong emphasis on education, but Chapter 36 identifies explicitly four areas where it should do so: (i) improving

basic education; (ii) adapting current education to promote sustainable development; (iii) raising community understanding and awareness; and (iv) training (Mahat & Idrus, 2016). The Ministry of Housing and Local Government Malaysia, which is a government agency, introduced Local Agenda 21 in Malaysia in 2001.

In the year 2013, the Ministry of Education (MoE) Malaysia developed the Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 for Preschool and Post-Secondary Education. This Blueprint has chartered a new pathway to teaching and learning in schools. Consequently, new curricula for preschool, primary, and post-secondary education were designed to achieve the educational objectives stipulated in the Blueprint.

The Blueprint is comprehensive, ensuring the ultimate goal of education: to develop students holistically and enable them to fulfill their full potential. The blueprint outlines five system aspirations, six student aspirations, and eleven shifts of transformation to support the education reform. The 5 Systems Aspirations are the key outcomes that the MoE aspires for the entire education system to achieve. These include 1) ACCESS: to ensure 100% enrolment across all levels from preschools to upper secondary; 2) QUALITY: focusing on achievement in reading, mathematics and science; 3) EQUITY: equal opportunities for all (urban-rural, socio-economic, gender, indigenous communities, special needs children); 4) UNITY: promotes shared values and experiences by encouraging students to embrace diversity; and 5) EFFICIENCY: maximizes student outcome within the current national budget.

The Philosophy of National Education (FPK), which was adopted in 1996, serves as the fundamental tenet and cornerstone of Malaysia's national educational system. FPK emphasizes that education is a continuous effort to develop people's potential in a holistic and integrated manner, producing individuals who are intellectually, spiritually, emotionally, and physically balanced and harmonious. Due to its alignment with the global SDG agenda for 2016-2030 and UNESCO's four pillars of learning agenda for the 21st century, which was also announced in 1996, FPK has a perspective and view of nature that is consistent with the SDGs (Widad et al., 2022).

As an Open and Distance Learning (ODL) provider, Open University Malaysia (OUM) is well-positioned to promote environmental education through its Lifelong Learning framework. Environmental education is defined as the process of educating individuals to acquire the necessary information and skills and to enhance their motivation and attitudes towards proposing solutions to environmental problems and adopting environmentally friendly behaviors (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 1978). Environmental education is aimed to produce an environmentally literate individual who can comprehend the relationship between natural and social systems, beliefs in the unity of human beings and nature, and is aware of the effects of technological

developments on the environment (SRS Abd Latif, W Kamarulzaman, OC Keat, CC Chea, NA Abd Jalil, H Mat & Siti, 2020).

2. The ICTeEfS project

Environmental destruction has been one of the most notable consequences of Asia's rapid growth. Recent climate-related disasters in the region underscore the need for immediate action by Asian policymakers to protect their citizens and mitigate the effects of climate change, thereby ensuring sustainable growth for the future. Education for Sustainability (EfS) is one strategy for overcoming these obstacles. While Asian leaders have expressed support to EfS and concern for the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the classroom teachers are the ones who bring about change.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS), and on the other hand, they must capitalize on the potential of such technologies to advance Education for Sustainability for all in-service subject teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Considering all the challenges and shortages outlined in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to utilize innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards EfS. The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

- I. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.
- II. Build the capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education to enable them to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers' training program on education for sustainability.
- III. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by

blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.

- IV. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
- V. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEFS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at Open University Malaysia (OUM) entitled ABSY1103 Introduction to Shariah considering six main questions: The first question is the “What” question, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The second and third questions refer to “Why” (justifying the reasons for revision) and “Where” describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The fourth question is the “how” question, describing the methodologies used for revision and course assessment during the implementation process. The fifth question is the “Now What” question, which shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course appears and how it has changed from its previous iteration. Lastly, the sixth question is the “So What?” question, which focuses on discussing the challenges encountered while navigating all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it affect the beneficiaries such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why and what would be the next actions?

3. Background of the course (ABSY 1103 Introduction of Shariah)

ABSY1103 Introduction to Shariah is a core course for the Bachelor in Islamic Studies Program. Usually, about 20 students register for this course each semester. This course is introduced to students to spread the knowledge of Shariah including the concept, special features and its application in daily life.

This course is a fundamental course for the programme, as the course is the basic course for other shariah courses. After taking the course students will be able to understand the principles of Shariah and apply these principles in daily life.

The course aims to:

- I. explain the meaning of shariah and its importance in the life of human beings;
- II. discuss the sources of shariah, including the main source and branch sources; and
- III. Summarize certain characteristics of Islamic law, making it a unique form of legislation.

Regarding course delivery and assessment, OUM employs an entirely online blended pedagogy for teaching and learning, based on the Community of Inquiry (CoI) Model of Engagement by Garrison, Anderson, and Archer (2000).

Figure 1: The Community of Inquiry (CoI) Model of Engagement by Garrison, Anderson & Archer (2000).

This pedagogy comprises synchronous, fully online face-to-face tutorials conducted via Google Meet, which fulfill the need for interactions between participants and instructors (Teaching Presence). The asynchronous online forum, also known as Online Class Participation (OCP), is required to ensure interactions between participants and peers (Social Presence). The forum is conducted using OUM’s own learning management system, named MyInspire. The interactions between participants and learning materials (Cognitive Presence) is achieved through providing the online learning resources consisting of the modules and e-lessons.

Besides the core content areas of the subject, OUM’s module includes a section on “self-check” and “activities”. Both sections encouraged participants to attempt to test or check their knowledge after completing the module and to complete the suggested activities, either in groups or individually. Learning is further supported by e-lessons, which are prepared according to the topics of each module. This framework outlines each topic, providing links to the topic's content within the module, relevant videos, and additional references or reading materials. The e-lessons also include discussion topics, related problems, and self-tests.

The main focus of ABSY1103 is on the ideas of Shariah, as well as its distinctive characteristics and practical applications. This course was chosen since it is a

requirement for all students taking the programme. The subjects and exercises in this course touch on social, cultural, and environmental issues that are relevant to everyday life. Examples of how SDG and Shariah are related include the following:

a) environmental justice – SDG13 Climate Action (Topic 9: al-Ijabiyah) This is consistent with Bakar, S. A., Sarkawi, A. A., and Abdullah, A. (2017), who emphasised the importance of environmental planning under the five essential aspects of Maqasid al-Shari'ah (syariah objectives), which is to protect and maintain human life.

b) Social Justice SDG10: Reduced Inequalities (Topic 10: Syariah Application in Daily Life) The Islamic approach to reducing income inequalities and alleviating poverty emphasizes the mechanisms that have historically been successful in reducing inequalities. For example, both obligatory (zakāh) and voluntary (ṣadaqāt) mechanisms are used to motivate the rich to spend generously on poverty reduction programs (Bashir, A. H. M. (2018).

c) economic justice – SDG 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth (Topic 10: Syariah application in daily life). Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are in consonance With Islamic ethos and philosophy. Maqasid al-Shariah emphasizes human well-being from spiritual, physiological, intellectual, and economic perspectives (Ismail, A. G., & Shaikh, S. A., 2017).

d) cultural justice - SDG 11 Sustainable Cities and Communities (Topic 10: Syariah application in daily life) This is align with the acceptance of urf (custom and culture) as a basis for rulings and judgements, provided it does not contravene or contradict Islamic values and principles (TO, H. I. R. (2008).

Consistent with the rapid changes in the world, the skills required for learning have also expanded. Along with the current sustainability crisis that threatens the very existence of humankind, education must go beyond the focus on the 4Cs (critical thinking & problem solving, communication, collaboration and teambuilding, creativity and innovation) to the new sets of skills known as the 10Cs. Although there is some overlap among the 10Cs, each one plays a distinct role in teaching and learning for problem-solving. For example, critical thinking and problem-solving refer to the ability to make decisions, solve problems, and take appropriate action, using learning processes such as conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or evaluating information gathered through multiple means. Communication refers to the ability to synthesize and transmit ideas in written, oral, and virtual formats. Collaboration refers to the ability to work effectively with others using multiple forms of communication. Creativity and innovation refer to the ability to apply new ideas in developing innovative applications and solutions (Makrakis, V., & Kostoulas-Makrakis, N., 2017).

The course aimed to develop competencies among participants with a solid foundation in the principles of Shariah, encompassing problem-solving skills, leadership

skills, communication skills, collaborative skills, and critical and creative thinking skills.

Thus, all 10C's elements can be linked to the content in this course. In summary, these elements can be mapped to the course content. In Myinspire, participants communicate with the teacher and other participants to synthesize and transmit ideas in written, oral, and virtual formats.

In the online E-Lesson, participants need to think critically to solve the given problem. Hence, they need to make decisions and take appropriate action, using learning processes such as conceptualizing, applying, analysing, synthesizing, and evaluating information gathered.

In Online Class Participation, participants also need to apply new ideas in developing innovative applications and solutions from a Shariah perspective. As for cross-cultural competence, the participants discuss the application of Shariah principles in daily life within a multicultural and global context.

The assessment for this course consists of both course work and a final examination. The coursework carries a score of 60%, comprising written assignments, Online Class Participation, and online quizzes. The online Final Examination comprises of essay with a weightage of 40%.

4. Methodology

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrakis (2017), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ are as follows.

13. Diagnosing: Reflecting on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.
14. Deconstructing: Analyzing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
15. Constructing: Gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
16. Reconstructing: Integration of newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
17. Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.

18. Finalising: Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

DeCoRe plus is the abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction that forms the core constructs supplemented by the processes of Diagnostic Evaluation, Implementation and Summative Evaluation. The theoretical underpinning of the DeCoRe plus methodological approach derives from critical social theory, critical pedagogy and postmodern conceptions of teaching, learning and curriculum. Although the six processes follow a linear order, in practice each process is closely interconnected with the other, forming a whole (Figure 2).

In this revision, the course has been diagnosed to reflect on the main content, objectives, approach and course assessment. The course is then critically examined to determine why it was selected. The analysis found that the topics and activities in this course are related to real life, as the main content of the course focuses on the characteristics of the Shariah and discussions on daily life issues from a Shariah perspective. Daily life issues also encompass social, cultural, and environmental concerns, which align with the SDG elements. The process then continues with construction, gathering resources, creating ideas, and developing new perspectives on the course. The reconstructing process occurs by integrating newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference. This course module promotes various types of knowledge, including technical knowledge/instrumental knowledge (the transmission of information), focusing on the concept of syariah, fundamental principles in syariah, and its unique features. Practical knowledge (focusing on a deep understanding of Shariah in various aspects of life) can also be promoted through this course. In addition, emancipatory knowledge (creating conditions for empowerment and change towards sustainable societies) can be promoted by incorporating sustainable values into the discussions students are formed to have, thereby fostering greater awareness and development of responsible participants. To complete the circle of revision, the course has been implemented by carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning. Finally, the reflection takes place to evaluate what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017)

For the revised courses evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2023) has been applied. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process which aims not only assess a course but more importantly to make whatever changes in order to improve it. Through the parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student guided by the course instructor creates a portfolio that he/she has to give back to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students' DREAM portfolios must be analyzed by the instructor, and a report must be prepared for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide essential information that the instructor and the students could discuss and find ways for improving the course.

Figure 3: The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

In this project, a set of questionnaires comprising two parts (open-ended and multiple-choice) was distributed among participants at the end of the semester. The questionnaires focus on seeking participants' views on the course and their skills in learning.

5. Findings and Discussion

During the process of enhancing the module based on DeCORE, several SDG elements, the 6 pillars of learning, and the 10Cs were integrated into the course. The emphasis on SDG 3, which is “to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages,” was embedded as activities related to topic 10, Shariah application in life. SDG 4 also has been included in this course, as seen in topic 9 in the discussion on the objectives of the Islamic rulings, including maintaining good, welfare, advantage, benefits, and warding off evil, injury, and loss of the living and non-living creatures. The emphasis on SDG 8, which is "Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all," is embedded as part of the assessment in the final examination. For example, the participants were asked to justify the responsibility to fulfil jobs without harming the environment.

The course also embedded SDG 6 which is to ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation. For example, in the teaching for topic 6, participants need to discuss how they can play a role as khalifah (vicegerent) of Allah in managing the natural resources including clean water.

The content and learning activities of the course are found to be interconnected with the six learning pillars, which are the core of the sustainability of development. The participants learn to know the concept of Syariah, its features and application. They are learning to be knowledgeable about the syariah, Self-actualization; Self-regulation; Respect the syariah. They are encouraged to apply syariah correctly. They also learn to determine and propose solution for social problems based on syariah teaching. At the end of the course, students learn to live together sustainably by respecting the syariah and understanding global issues in real life, which in turn leads to respecting others’ rights.

Additionally, this course encouraged students to learn how to transform themselves and society. They can formulate good values, create a better attitude, and have opportunities to influence others positively. The knowledge and skills acquired through this course can be applied to transform oneself and the surrounding communities. The principles of justice learned through activities in this course can also educate them to transform themselves and society based on Shariah teaching. In addition, students learn to share their ideas and work together to find the best solutions to real-life problems based on Syariah teachings.

This course was assessed using the DREAM Methodology. The results showed that all students are taking this course for the first time during the January 2021 semester. Only 16 students answered the questionnaires out of 20. Most of them are working as teachers, mosque administrator, government servants and entrepreneurs; indicating their work is related to teaching and learning; as well as managing activities at the mosque. However, a few of them are retirees. Their ages ranges from minimum 21 years old to those above

60 years old. Also, since OUM’s teaching and learning is fully online, these participants are scattered throughout the country.

Regarding their technological competence, five participants accessed online materials, such as e-books, e-journals, and databases, regularly (very often). At the same time, nine of them did so frequently, and two did so occasionally for their studies. Regarding statistical programs such as Microsoft Excel, IBM SPSS, and Matlab, four students used them frequently, while another four never used them. The remaining statistical programmes are used occasionally.

Almost half of the students use social media platforms such as blogs and discussion forums, while the rest occasionally use these platforms. Myinspire is a learning platform for students. Most of the students use the platform frequently. Most students need to make presentation throughout their learning journey. Hence, they use presentation tools such as Microsoft Powerpoint, Google slides, Prezi etc. Ten students used them frequently, three students used them occasionally, and three of them never use any of these tools.

Based on the responses, majority of the participants pursuing this course agreed that they enjoy learning and doing new things. They are not hasty in making decisions. In fact, all of them will think carefully before making any decision. Also, they are able to work well in teams, being able to stay calm and composed during discussions. They can communicate well with others. Furthermore, they loved doing hands-on activities and challenges.

A majority of these students admitted this course is related to their current jobs. By learning this course, 14 of the participants expected to apply the knowledge or skills gained in their daily lives and another two participants expected to enrich their knowledge.

Various topics from this course were identified by participants as the most impactful to them are the concept of shariah, tauhid, shariah sources, importance of shariah, communication and 21st Century learning skills.

Figure 4: Most Impactful Topics Identified by the Participants before the Course

While mid-way studying this course, the students were requested to reflect on the experiences they gained. All of the participants found that the course is interesting and

enriching their knowledge. A majority of them enjoy doing the activities in this course. Through the assignment they are more sensitive to the Sustainable Development Goals. Furthermore, they learn to apply the SDGs in their daily lives. Also, they enjoy attending the tutorial sessions. Those who cannot attend can refer to the e-tutorial session recordings. The participants also feel that the e-tutor provides a lot of assistance to enable them to understand the course. The nature of learning using Myinspire as platform enable the students to improve their ICT capabilities. As a result, this course made the students more environmentally friendly.

The students were also asked to reflect on what they expected from this course. A learner expected for more visual learning materials to be provided, two more participants expected more time given to complete the assignment. One learner hoped for an e-tutor who was more student-friendly, and another learner expected a more flexible assessment method. One learner also expected for the assessment of the course to have no finals. A majority of the participants expected to have more collaborative learning activities while the rest two of the participants did not mention their expectations.

This is followed with a reflection as to what is different from the expected as well as something unexpected occurring. Eight of the students were surprised by the availability of interesting visual learning resources, while three of them enjoyed the e-lessons, which support the learning process. Two students are happy to have e-tutors who are creative and innovative in teaching.

The students' reflections identified some expectations are not as expected. They shared their reactions due to the differences in expectations. This encompasses a range of emotions, including surprise, happiness, acceptance, excitement, and enthusiasm. Among of the suggestions to improve the course proposed by the participants are to increase the number of coursework (assignment), to increase the time for e-tutorial and to vary the activities to challenge their minds. When asked why this course is not as expected, among the responses are insufficient activities, affecting participants' time management, however majority of them found the course as expected.

Figure 5: Most Impactful Topics Identified by the Participants after the Course

In the ASSESS stage, students are requested to assess the impact of what have been learned in terms of Academic Development. A majority of the participants expressed they enriched their knowledge about SDG. As for Professional Development, a majority of them can apply the acquired knowledge in their work. Based on the responses, a majority of the participants learned to work in a team in Social Development. Finally, the impact of what they learned in terms of personal development is that the students are more open-minded.

Students were asked to suggest things they would like to be different if they are to retake this course. Some suggestions provided include increasing knowledge, exploring new things, maintaining virtual learning, incorporating more discussions, and engaging in creative problem-solving.

For the final stage, students are asked to suggest how they can apply the new knowledge they have learned from the course in the future. Various suggestions were offered, including sharing knowledge with others, fostering a better social environment, applying knowledge in family life, and exploring new ways to seek knowledge.

6. Conclusion

One of the challenges faced in the revision process is enhancing the module, as OUM's modules are written based on a specified template. Therefore, making changes to the content requires critical analysis to identify where changes are needed and creativity to rearrange the materials so that the new content can be integrated cohesively with the existing materials. The integration of the SDGs within this course should create awareness and understanding of the SDGs among participants. From this understanding, they should be more concerned with happenings around them: in their lives, society, country, and the world. They should understand the importance of knowledge about SDG to ensure prosperity and harmony can be maintained throughout the world. Furthermore, with the exposure through this course, participants who are already aware about SDG will be able to enhance their understanding and be more dedicated to SDG. After completion the course, participants should be able to share the knowledge about SDG as well as create awareness among family members and their communities. It is also critical to say that particular importance has to be given various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues pertaining to the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

Through this project, it has been proven that Decore+ and DREAM Methodology are the success way to revise a curriculum to integrate the education for sustainability in teaching, learning and curriculum for participants. After all, ESD is the most effective way to deliver the SDGs to the community. It has also been demonstrated that SDGs can be

communicated through any discipline that promotes the same goal, particularly Islamic Studies.

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The HBIS 1103 Pedagogy In Islamic Education Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing It Through The Lens Of SDG

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Abstract

The goal of environmental education is to produce an environmentally literate individual who understands the relationship between natural and social systems, believes in the unity of humans and nature, and is aware of the environmental consequences of technological advancements. The purpose of this paper was to present the processes, practises, and outcomes of revising HBIS1103 Pedagogy in Islamic Education at Open University Malaysia (OUM) to integrate education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum through course revision. DeCoRe+, an abbreviation of Makrakis's (2017) Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction methodology, was used to embed sustainability, specifically the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This revision of the course has been diagnosed to reflect on the main content, objectives, approach, and course assessment. Some of the SDG elements, the 6 pillars of learning, and the 10Cs were incorporated into the course during its improvement. This project demonstrated that Decore is a successful method for revising a curriculum in order to integrate education for sustainability in participants' teaching, learning, and curriculum. After all, Education for Sustainability (EFS) is the most efficient means of delivering the SDGs to the community. SDGs can also be communicated through any discipline that promotes the same goal, pedagogy in Islamic Studies, in particular.

Keywords: Decore+ methodology, Pedagogy, Islamic Education, Sustainability

1. Introduction

Humanity has been grappling with the consequences of unsustainable economic development driven by profit maximization, resulting in the excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources over the past few decades (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite current efforts to halt this unsustainable development process, much work remains to be done. The sustainability dilemma that the world is currently facing is directly attributable to education systems at all levels, but notably higher education. This is mainly because decision-makers, leaders, and consumers are the end products of educational institutions, which influence an unsustainable consumer culture and drive society and the economy (Makrakis 2011).

A fundamental change through an alternative development model that gives proper weight to sustainable well-being should depend heavily on education. In contrast to the prevalent hedonic well-being fueled by unsustainable behaviours and forms of production and consumption, sustainable well-being, in our understanding, is similar to Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). To learn how to improve oneself and society, it is crucial to pursue "sustainability justice," a concept coined by Makrakis (2006, 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economics, and culture.

It is worth noting that while significant investments have been made in environmental education over the past few decades, they have primarily focused on fostering positive environmental attitudes rather than increasing concern for environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a

paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability have shown that lecturing, as expected, is the most prevalent teaching method, while role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, are used at much lower rates (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

A project entitled Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (RUCAS) (Makrakis, 2013; 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of, and capable of acting in transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts to teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are the agents of change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EFS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016, 2018; Blake et al., 2013), as well as in transforming schools into sustainable institutions (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

To put the issue in a local context, efforts to raise awareness of sustainable development should be made in collaboration with all communities and not just one group. The 1992 Rio de Janeiro Earth Summit Conference, which led to the creation of Agenda 21, marked the first time that the component of education for sustainable development was formally acknowledged. Every chapter of Agenda 21 places

a strong emphasis on education, but Chapter 36 identifies explicitly four areas where it should do so: (i) improving basic education; (ii) adapting current education to promote sustainable development; (iii) raising community understanding and awareness; and (iv) training (Mahat & Idrus, 2016). The Ministry of Housing and Local Government Malaysia, which is a government agency, introduced Local Agenda 21 in Malaysia in 2001.

In the year 2013, the Ministry of Education (MoE) Malaysia developed the Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 for Preschool and Post-Secondary Education. This Blueprint has chartered a new pathway to teaching and learning in schools. Consequently, new curricula for preschool, primary, and post-secondary education were designed to achieve the educational objectives as stipulated in the Blueprint.

The Blueprint is comprehensive, ensuring the ultimate goal of education: to develop students holistically and enable them to fulfill their full potential. The blueprint outlines five system aspirations, six student aspirations, and eleven shifts of transformation to support the education reform. The 5 Systems Aspirations are the key outcomes that the MoE aspires for the entire education system to achieve. These include 1) ACCESS: to ensure 100% enrolment across all levels from preschools to upper secondary; 2) QUALITY: focusing on achievement in reading, mathematics and science; 3) EQUITY: equal opportunities for all (urban-rural, socio-economic, gender, indigenous communities, special needs children); 4) UNITY: promotes shared values and experiences by encouraging students to embrace diversity; and 5) EFFICIENCY: maximizes student outcome within the current national budget.

The Philosophy of National Education (FPK), which was adopted in 1996, serves as the fundamental tenet and cornerstone of Malaysia's national educational system. FPK emphasizes that education is a continuous effort to develop people's potential in a holistic and integrated manner, producing a human being who is intellectually, spiritually, emotionally, and physically balanced and harmonious. Due to its alignment with the global SDG agenda, 2016–2030, and UNESCO's four pillars of learning agenda for the 21st century, which was also announced in 1996, FPK has a perspective and view of nature that is consistent with the SDGs (Widad, et.al, 2022)

As an Open and Distance Learning (ODL) provider, Open University Malaysia (OUM) is well-positioned to promote environmental education through its Lifelong Learning framework. Environmental education is defined as the process of educating individuals to acquire the necessary information and skills and to enhance their motivation and attitudes towards proposing solutions to environmental problems and adopting environmentally friendly behaviors (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 1978). Environmental education aims to produce an environmentally literate individual who can comprehend the relationship between natural and social

systems, believe in the unity of human beings and nature, and be aware of the effects of technological developments on the environment (SRS et al., 2020).

2. The ICTeEfS project

Environmental destruction has been one of the most notable consequences of Asia's rapid growth. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate the need for immediate action on the part of Asian policymakers to safeguard their citizens and mitigate the effects of climate change, thereby ensuring future sustainable growth. Education for sustainability (EfS) is one strategy for overcoming these obstacles. While Asian leaders have expressed support to EfS and concern for the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the classroom teachers are the ones who bring about change.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS). On the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

- VI. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning and research with the area of education for sustainability.
- VII. Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.
- VIII. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by

blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.

- IX. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
- X. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEFS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at Open University Malaysia (OUM) entitled **HBIS 1103 Pedagogy in Islamic Education** considering six main questions: The first question is the “What” question, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The second and third questions refer to “Why” (justifying the reasons for revision) and “Where” describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The fourth question is the “how” question, describing the methodologies used for revision and course assessment during the implementation process. The fifth question is the “Now What” question, which shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course looks and how it has changed from what it was before. Lastly, the sixth question is the “So What?” question that focuses on discussing the challenges met to go through all the preceding processes from the beginning up to now and how has been tackled. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the following actions?

3. Background of the course (HBIS 1103 Pedagogy in Islamic Education)

The HBIS1103 **Pedagogy in Islamic Education** is a core course for the Bachelor of Teaching (Primary Education). This course is designed to enable students to define the strategies, approaches, methods, and techniques of teaching and learning Islamic Education subjects. Also, it will provide guidance to students to choose, plan and use appropriate strategies and materials in the effective teaching and learning process of Islamic Education.

Regarding course delivery and assessment, OUM employs an entirely online blended pedagogy for teaching and learning, based on the Community of Inquiry (CoI)

Model of Engagement by Garrison, Anderson, and Archer (2000).

Figure 1: The Community of Inquiry (CoI) Model of Engagement by Garrison, Anderson & Archer (2000).

This pedagogy comprises synchronous, fully online, face-to-face tutorials conducted via Google Meet, which fulfill the need for interactions between learners and instructors (Teaching Presence). The asynchronous online forum, also known as Online Class Participation (OCP), is required to ensure interactions between learners and peers (Social Presence). The forum is conducted using OUM’s learning management system, named MyInspire. The interactions between learners and learning materials (Cognitive Presence) is achieved through providing the online learning resources consisting of the modules and e-lessons.

Besides the core content areas of the subject, OUM’s module includes a section on “self-check” and “activities”. Both sections encouraged learners to make attempts to test or check their knowledge after completing the module and to complete the suggested activities, either in groups or individually. Learning is further supported by e-lessons, which are prepared according to the topics of each module. This framework outlines each topic, providing links to the topic's content within the module, relevant videos, and additional references or reading materials. The e-lessons also include discussion topics, related problems, and self-tests.

This course provides an opportunity to help students build a dominant ideology and a sustainable economic model. This can be seen through learning the concept of efficiency in making decisions (in planning teaching activities and developing assessment tools) and environmental sustainability (via infusion the elements in the content of Islamic Studies). Even though both of these concepts will be integrated through a micro perspective, but the knowledge and skills are beneficial to students towards building their own ideology and sustainable economic models upon completion of the program.

The key contents of this course align with the goals and objectives of teaching, where the concepts of strategies, approaches, methods, and techniques for teaching and learning Islamic Education subjects form the foundation of Islamic studies. This course is chosen because it is a

compulsory course for all learners enrolled in the Bachelor of Teaching Primary School Education. The topics and activities in this course are related to the pedagogy of teaching Islamic Studies as a subject. As an inclusive subject, the content of the course is related to real life issues including social, cultural and environmental issues. The following are examples of relation between SDG and the content of the course:

a) SDG 3: Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all people of all ages. Learners who plan to become teachers after graduation are introduced to activities and approaches that promote healthy living and well-being in this course. This is consistent with the findings of Barry, Clarke and Dowling (2017), who advocate for the importance of young people's social and emotional well-being in schools.

b) SDG4: Quality Education. The main focus of the course is to provide the whole idea of quality education in the Islamic Studies context. The content of the course is align with SDG4 which is to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong opportunities for all.

c) SDG 8: Economic justice, including decent work and economic growth. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) align with Islamic ethos and philosophy. According to Maqasid al-Shariah (Syariah objectives), human well-being from spiritual, physiological, intellectual, and economic perspectives is very important and should be emphasised in all its rulings that are taught in schools. (Ismail & Shaikh, 2017).

d) SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities. This SDG is about cultural justice, which is about protecting and preserving the world's cultural and natural heritage. This SDG has been emphasised in JAWI teaching topics as one of the ways of writing in Malay. This aligns with the acceptance of custom and culture as a basis for rulings and judgments, provided they do not contravene or contradict Islamic values and principles (TO, H. I. R., 2008).

Consistent with the rapid changes of the world, the skills needed in learning also expanded. Along with the current sustainability crisis that threatens the very existence of humankind, education must go beyond the focus on the 4Cs (critical thinking & problem solving, communication, collaboration and teambuilding, creativity and innovation) to the new sets of skills known as 10Cs. Although there is some overlap among the 10Cs, each one has its own role in teaching and learning for problem solving. For example, critical thinking and problem-solving refer to the ability to make decisions, solve problems, and take appropriate action, using learning processes such as conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or evaluating information gathered through multiple means. Communication refers to the ability to synthesize and transmit ideas in written, oral, and virtual formats. Collaboration refers to the ability to work effectively with others using multiple communication

means. Creativity and innovation refer to the ability to apply new ideas in developing innovative applications and solutions (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2017).

The course aimed to develop competencies among the participants with a solid foundation on the pedagogy of teaching Islamic Studies, which are:

- I. sharing/disseminating information using the various strategies and approaches in teaching Islamic education;
- II. the practical know-how with focus on deep understanding of the differences in approach for transferring knowledge and skills;
- III. Create conditions for empowerment and change towards sustainable societies through the integration of sustainable values.

Thus, all 10C's elements can be linked to the content in this course. In summary, these elements can be mapped to the course content. In Myinspire, participants communicate with the teacher and other participants to synthesize and transmit ideas in written, oral, and virtual formats.

In the online E-Lesson, the participants need to think critically to solve the problem given. Hence, they need to make decisions and take appropriate action, using learning processes such as conceptualizing, applying, analysing, synthesizing, and evaluating information gathered.

In Online Class Participation, the participants also need to apply new ideas in developing innovative applications and solutions based on pedagogy in teaching and learning. As for cross/inter-cultural competence, the participants discuss the different approaches in teaching Islamic Studies in multicultural and global backgrounds. The assessment for this course consists of both course work and a final examination. The coursework carries a score of 60%, comprising written assignments, Online Class Participation, and online quizzes. The online Final Examination comprises of essay with a weightage of 40%. The assessment for this course consists of both course work and a final examination. The course work carries a score of 60% comprising written assignment, Online Class Participation, and online quizzes. The online Final Examination comprises of essay with a weightage of 40%.

4. Methodology

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrakis (2017), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum

development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes.

- I. Diagnosing: Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
- II. Deconstructing: Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
- III. Constructing: Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
- IV. Reconstructing: Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
- V. Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
- VI. Finalizing: Reflecting on and evaluating what has been learned and changed.

DeCoRe plus is the abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction that forms the core constructs supplemented by the processes of Diagnostic Evaluation, Implementation and Summative Evaluation. The theoretical underpinning of the DeCoRe plus methodological approach derives from critical social theory, critical pedagogy and postmodern conceptions of teaching, learning and curriculum. Although the six processes follow a linear order, in practice, each process is closely interconnected with the other, forming a whole (Figure 2).

In this revision, the course has been diagnosed to reflect on the main content, objectives, approach and course assessment. The course is then critically examined to determine why it was selected. The analysis found that the topics and activities in this course are related to real life as the main content of the courses are the characteristics of the shariah and discussion on daily life issues in the perspective of shariah. The daily life issues also include social, cultural and environmental issues which are consistent with the SDG elements. The process then continues with constructing by gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new perspectives to the course. The reconstructing process take into place by integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference. There are various types of knowledge that can be promoted through this course module; Technical knowledge / instrumental knowledge (sending information) focusing on the pedagogy of teaching, approaches related to Islamic Studies as the content. Practical knowledge (focuses on deep understanding of shariah in various aspect of life also can be promoted through this course. In addition, emancipatory knowledge (create conditions for empowerment and change towards sustainable societies) can be promoted by inserting

the sustainable value in the discussions the students are formed to have greater awareness and development of responsible participants. To complete the circle of revision, the course has been implemented by carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning. Finally, the reflection take place to evaluate on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017)

5. Findings and Discussion

During the process of enhancing the course learning materials or the module, based on DeCORE, some SDG elements, the six pillars of learning, and the 10Cs were embedded. The first Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) to be embedded within this course is SDG 3, which emphasizes "ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages." SDG3 was embedded as activities related to topic 4 in teaching Fiqh in daily life especially focusing on cleanliness in Islam.

SDG4 is emphasized in this course. The teaching and learning of the course align with SDG 4, which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong opportunities for all. The learners are constantly reminded to include their discussion on education opportunities for all, including children with special needs as well as the marginalised population such as the aborigines.

The course also embedded SDG 6 which is to ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation. For example, in the teaching for topic 6, learners need to discuss how they can play the role as khalifah (vicegerent) of Allah in managing the natural resources including clean water. SDG 8, which is "Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all," is embedded as part of the assessment in the final examination. For example, the learners need to explain how to use resources from the nature without harming the environment in their teaching and learning for Islamic Studies subjects. The course also emphasises SDG 11, which is to strengthen efforts to protect and safeguard the world's cultural and natural heritage. In topic 5, the learners need to understand

the importance of Jawi (Arabic) writing and appreciate the skill in writing Jawi as the heritage of the Malay community in Malaysia.

The content and learning activities of the course are found to be interconnected with the six learning pillars, which are the core of the sustainability of development. The learners learn about strategies, approaches, methods, and techniques of teaching and learning of Islamic Education subjects. They also learn to choose, plan and use appropriate strategies and materials in the effective teaching and learning process of Islamic Education.

At the end of the course, learners will learn to live together sustainably by understanding strategies and approaches to teaching Islamic Studies, respecting, and being considerate of the diverse backgrounds of their peers. This will lead to respecting others' rights and needs. Additionally, this course encouraged students to learn how to transform themselves and society. They can determine values, develop better attitudes, and create opportunities to have a positive impact on others. The knowledge and skills acquired through this course can be applied to transform oneself and the surrounding communities.

In addition, the students learn to give and share their ideas and work together to find the best solutions to solve real-life problems related to teaching and learning of Islamic Studies. The course developed could motivate the learners to think independently; design situations for them to share their ideas; work together to find the best solutions to use their skills in teaching Islamic Studies.

All 10C's elements can be linked to the content in this course. In summary, these elements can be mapped to the contents of this course. In Myinspire, learners communicate with the teacher and other learners to synthesize and transmit ideas in written, oral, and virtual formats. In the online E-Lesson, learners need to think critically to solve the given problem, making decisions and taking appropriate action through learning processes such as conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating the gathered information.

In Online Class Participation, the learners also need to apply new ideas in developing innovative applications and solutions based on strategies, approaches, methods, and techniques of teaching and learning of Islamic Education subjects. As for cross/inter-cultural competence, the learners use different approaches in teaching the application of shariah principles in daily life in the multicultural and global background. Through this course, the learners critically reflect upon their reality, personal and social, and to transform it through actions and reflections in their daily lesson plan.

6. Conclusion

One of the challenges faced in the revision process is enhancing the module, as OUM's modules are written based on a specified template. Therefore, making changes to the content requires critical analysis to identify where changes are required and creativity to rearrange so that the new materials can be embedded cohesively with the existing materials.

The integration of the SDGs within this course should create awareness and understanding of the SDGs among participants. From this understanding, they should be more concern with happenings around them; in their lives, society, country and the world. They should understand the importance of knowledge about SDG to ensure prosperity and harmony can be maintained throughout the world. Furthermore, with the exposure through this course, participants who are already aware about SDG will be able to enhance their understanding and be more dedicated to SDG. After completion of the course, participants should be able to share their knowledge about SDG as well as create awareness among family members and their communities. It is also critical to say that particular importance has to be given to various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues pertaining to the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al. 2024).

Through this project, it has been proven that EfS is the best way to channel the SDGs to the community, starting with children in school through the trained teachers. It has also been demonstrated that SDGs may be communicated through any discipline, particularly Islamic Studies, which promotes the same purpose.

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The SDG's-focused IT Course for ODL: Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing

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Abstract

Environmental education aims to create environmentally literate individuals who recognize the interconnectedness of humans and nature, understand the impact of technological advancements on the environment, and comprehend the interrelationship between natural and social systems. To integrate Education for Sustainability (EfS) in teaching, learning, and curriculum through course revision, OUM revised HBEF2303 Information Technology (IT) in Education. This study aimed to explain the processes, practices, and results of this course revision. Makrakis's Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction technique (DeCoRe+) was utilized to integrate sustainability, particularly the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The fundamental objectives, approach, and instructional method have all been reviewed in this course version. While the course was being updated, some SDG components, the six pillars of learning, and the 10Cs were included. The efficacy of DeCoRe+ as a strategy for curriculum revision, successfully incorporating EfS into participants' teaching, learning, and the curriculum, was demonstrated by this study. The community can receive the SDGs the most effectively through EfS, after all. SDGs can also be spread through any academic field that supports the same objective, particularly in IT pedagogy.

Keywords: EfS, SDG, sustainability

1. Introduction

The effects of an unsustainable economic development fueled by profit maximization, which led to an excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources, have been felt by humanity during the past few decades (Makrakis, 2014; Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2021). Despite current efforts to halt this unsustainable development process, much work remains to be done. The sustainability dilemma we are currently experiencing worldwide is attributable to educational institutions at all levels, notably higher education. This is significant because educational institutions produce consumers, leaders, and decision-makers who influence an unsustainable consumer culture and drive society and the economy. Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that “the scope and range of the negative impacts of university-educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented” (p. 3).

Education should play a crucial role in driving a radical transformation through an alternative development model that emphasizes sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is close to Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being as contrasted to the overall hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Kostoulas-Makrakis & Makrakis, 2020). The quest for “sustainability justice” is a concept developed by Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis (2006; 2017) that well-being is the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture, is of paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is important to note that despite significant investment in environmental education over the past few decades, ecological action has received less attention than favorable environmental views. A paradigm shift in curriculum, teaching, and learning is necessary to translate ecological awareness and understanding into environmental action. However, educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living. (Makrakis, 2012). The discrepancy between environmental attitudes and activity is due to several other issues and educational techniques. Role-play, hands-on science, and problem-based learning, which are more effective approaches, were found to be used significantly less frequently than lecturing, according to recent curriculum development studies focused on sustainability. (Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2016; Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2021).

According to a project titled “Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability” (Kostoulas-Makrakis & Makrakis, 2012; Makrakis, 2014), the greatest challenge facing institutions of higher learning in the 21st century is to develop professionals who are capable of critically analyzing their terms of reference and acting to change them to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also applies to teachers at primary and secondary school levels. The teaching staff is the agent for change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti, 2016; Blake et al., 2013) and turning schools sustainable (Blake et al., 2013; Zachariou et al., 2013).

For instance, the Ministry of Housing and Local Government of Malaysia launched Local Agenda 21 in 2001

as a follow-up to the 1992 United Nations Rio Conference (GDRC.org, 2022). Through this program, Malaysia has discovered that the idea and practice of education for sustainable development demand involvement at all societal levels. Since the Third Malaysian Plan (1976-1980), when Malaysia was governed, the concept of universal sustainability has gained traction (Malaysian Prime Minister Department, 2022). Nevertheless, despite the rapid development of the industrial and infrastructure sectors at the time, the focus was more on protecting historical and cultural heritage (Izieadiana et al., 2016).

The Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 for Preschool and Post-Secondary Education was created in 2013 by the Malaysian Ministry of Education (MOE). This plan has outlined a new direction for classroom instruction and learner learning. As a result, a new curriculum was created for preschool through post-secondary education to achieve the learning goals outlined in the blueprint.

The plan is thorough to ensure that pupils are developed holistically and can reach their full potential through education. The blueprint for the education reform includes eleven transformation shifts, six learner aspirations, and five system goals. The MOE hopes that the entire educational system will achieve the five systems' aspirations. These include:

- (i) Access: to guarantee full enrollment from early childhood through upper secondary;
- (ii) Quality: emphasizing achievement in reading, mathematics, and science;
- (iii) Equity: providing equal opportunities for all (urban and rural, socioeconomic, gender, indigenous communities, and children with special needs);
- (iv) Unity: encouraging learners to embrace diversity while fostering shared values and experiences; and
- (v) Efficiency: maximizing learner outcomes within the current national curriculum.

The National Education Philosophy, also known as Falsafah Pendidikan Kebangsaan (FPK), was passed into law in 1996 and served as the fundamental principle and pillar of the national education system. It is the foundation upon which Malaysia bases its educational philosophy. FPK emphasizes that education is a continuous effort to develop people's potential in a holistic and integrated manner, producing a human being who is intellectually, spiritually, emotionally, and physically balanced and harmonious. Therefore, FPK has a viewpoint and understanding of nature consistent with the SDGs, especially in light of its agreement with the global SDG agenda, 2016-2030, and UNESCO's four pillars of a learning plan for the 21st century were proclaimed in 1996 (Widad et al., 2022).

2. The ICTeEfS project

Environmental destruction has been one of the most obvious adverse consequences of Asia's rapid growth.

Recent climate-related disasters in the area demonstrate that Asian politicians must take immediate action to safeguard their citizens and prevent and reverse climate change's effects to ensure future sustainable growth. Education for Sustainability (EfS) is a strategy to meet these difficulties. While Asian leaders have expressed a commitment to EfS and a concern for implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the educators who work in the classroom are the ones who bring about change.

One of the issues raised by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental risks is the need for teachers to be trained in certain Asian nations, such as Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam. On the one hand, educational institution must restructure their learning curricula by incorporating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS). To advance EfS to all subject in-service teachers, the institution must, however, take advantage of the possibilities of such technology. The inclusion of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training is a given due to the importance of ICT literacy and the rapidly expanding availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs. The incorporation of ICT as a topic or resource, however, is not all that ICT integration entails. It suggests modifications to teaching and learning, necessitating thorough and integrated planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher preparation.

Aiming to create an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators and train them to employ cutting-edge teaching methodologies and pedagogies focused on "education for sustainability (EfS)" in light of all the difficulties and shortages mentioned in the rationale. The European Commission's Erasmus+ Capacity Building Programme in the Field of Higher Education has provided funding for the ICTeEfS project from 2019 to 2023. The more precise goals are to:

- XI. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.
- XII. Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a comprehensive ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.
- XIII. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program, enabled by blended learning, focusing on integrating education for sustainability across school curricula.
- XIV. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
- XV. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

This paper focuses on presenting the processes, practices, and outcomes of revising one of the courses at the Open University Malaysia, entitled HBEF2303 Information Technology in Education, while considering six main questions.

The first question, “What” focuses on a description of the course as it was before revision, including the reasons for the revision's selection, the number of learners enrolled, the course's central themes, the competencies that need to be developed, the teaching strategies used, and the methods used to evaluate learners. The second and third questions address “Why” (explaining the justifications for revision) and “Where” describing the holes in the course that will be filled during the revision process. The “How” question, which relates to the revision and course assessment procedures utilized during the implementation phase, is the fourth one. The fifth question, “Now What” describes how the course has been updated and/or revised and how it differs from “What” came before. The sixth and final question, “So What?” explores the difficulties encountered throughout the preceding process, from the beginning to the present, and how they were overcome.

The discussion section explicitly discusses the following sub-questions: What effects will the altered course have on local and global society, curriculum, teaching, and learning? How did our knowledge of curriculum, teaching, and learning evolve? What can be gained from this experience, and how will it impact society and learners in particular? What has to be done, why has it not been done, and what would be the next steps?

3. The “What”, “Why”, and “Where” Questions for Revising (HBEF2303 Information Technology in Education)

OUM offers 54 programmes, comprising 28 undergraduate and 26 postgraduate programmes. Three equal semesters make up the university's academic year. A total of 27,000 active learners will access about 650 courses per semester. Typically, each learner enrolls in three courses each semester.

OUM uses a fully online blended pedagogy based on the Garrison et al. (2000) Community of Inquiry (COL) Model of Engagement for teaching and learning.

Figure 1 *Community of Inquiry (COL) Model of Engagement*

Notes. The model was suggested by (Garrison et al., 2000)

This pedagogy includes synchronous, fully online face-to-face tutorials conducted through Google Meet, which satisfies the need for interactions between learners and instructors (“Teaching Presence”); the asynchronous online forum, also known as the Online Class Participation (OCP), is necessary to ensure interactions between learners/peers (“Social Presence”). Using OUM's learning management system, called “myINSPIRE,” the forum is run. The interactions between learners and the learning materials (referred to as “Cognitive Presence”) are made possible through online learning tools, including modules and e-lessons.

In addition to the subject's primary content areas, the OUM module has a section on “Self-check” and “Activities”. After completing the module, each of these parts invited learners to test or confirm their knowledge by completing the specified tasks in groups or individually. E-lessons created under the module topics further aid in learning. This summarises each topic with links to the module's content; use your tubes and further reading resources or references. The e-lessons also offer associated problems, discussion points, and self-tests.

4. Why are this course chosen?

The HBEF2303 Information Technology in Education course is offered to learners enrolled in the Bachelor of Teaching (Primary Education). This course enables learners to understand information technology (IT) and apply it, especially in education. The main components of this course include an introduction to IT, use of standard application software, IT management in teaching and learning, internet, computer-assisted teaching and learning, courseware evaluation, and integration of IT in teaching and learning.

Competences to be developed

The various knowledge and skills acquired by learners through this course should be able to promote their development in several aspects, such as:

- (i) Outlines the basic principles of IT in education;
- (ii) Apply the principles of IT to teaching and learning activities in and outside the classroom;
- (iii) Integrating web applications with teaching strategies through software and hardware; and
- (iv) Develop knowledge and skills in using IT in teaching and learning success in and out of the classroom.

Since these are abilities needed in the modern world, having knowledge and comprehension of IT-related issues will educate these future teachers to be proficient in IT. Learners can use specific topics to incorporate sustainability principles into their classroom instruction and learning.

The content of this course is as follows, and it can be mapped to the SDG goals as shown in the following table:

Table 1
Course Content Mapping with SDGs

Course Content	SDG			
	4	9	12	17
Introduction to IT	X	X		
Word Processing			X	
Electronic Presentations			X	
Electronic Spreadsheets			X	
IT Management in T&L				X
Internet	X	X		
Computer-Aided Teaching and Learning (CATL)		X		
Course Software Evaluation		X		
Integration of ICT in T&L				X

The information listed above is significant because it serves as the foundation for creating graduates who are capable teachers. IT is the foundation of existing and future teaching and learning procedures (Zafar, 2019). Word processing abilities, computerized presentations, and spreadsheet knowledge are necessary for teaching activities within and outside the classroom. For usage in teaching and learning in the classroom, teachers also need knowledge of and proficiency with networks, the internet, and specialized software systems.

With a solid foundation in IT, it is hoped the learners will be able to develop (in-directly) the following skills, such as:

- (i) Problem-solving,
- (ii) Leadership,
- (iii) Communication,
- (iv) Collaboration, and
- (v) Critical-creative thinking.

All 10C's elements can be linked to the content in this course.

Figure 2

ICTs as Enabling Tools for the 10Cs

In myINSPIRE, learners communicate with the tutors and other learners to synthesize and transmit ideas in written, oral, and virtual formats. In the online E-lesson, the learners need to think critically to solve the problem given. Hence, they need to make decisions and take appropriate action, using learning processes such as conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating information gathered.

In Online Class Participation (OCP), the learners also need to apply new ideas in developing innovative applications and solutions based on IT from an educational point of view. As for cross/inter-cultural competencies, learners can use them through the topic, such as developing computer-assisted learning software. They can involve learners of all races, religions, and cultures – apart from focusing on the lesson's content alone.

The assessment for this course consists of both coursework and a final examination. The course work carries a score of 60% comprising Written Assignment, Online Class Participation (OCP), and Online Assessment-Activity. The Online Final Examination comprises a weightage of 40%.

5. Methodologies – The “How” Question

A six-stage capacity-building methodology proposed by Makrakis (2006) was utilized to teach academic staff to include sustainability in their courses in light of the abovementioned characteristics, needs, and goals (Figure 2).

Figure 3

A Capacity Building Model

Notes. Model adapted from Makrakis (2006).

In the first stage, training focuses on the diagnosis of the didactic profile of every trainee. An action plan for the training session is created based on the analysis of each trainee's profile (second stage). The training material, which combines theory and practice and is organized into theme units or modules that can be further developed while considering the trainee's needs, follows the action plan (third stage). The action plan's goals and objectives will be compared to the trainees' initial profiles and the evaluation of their learning results (fourth stage). Using their newly gained skills and information in the classroom, the end receivers, the learners, complete the same evaluation process (fifth stage). To maintain the proper operation of the training process and maybe improve it, a system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages (sixth stage).

The DeCoRe+ technique (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction), developed by (Vouzaxakis & Makrakis, 2017), was used to revise the course to incorporate sustainability, specifically the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The DeCoRe+ method adopts a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development and views curricula as living documents. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes.

- (i) Diagnosing: Reflecting on (a) who we are; (b) what we have (existing knowledge); (c) where we want to go, and (d) why we want to go there.
- (ii) Deconstructing: Critically analyzing the functioning of personal perspectives, habits of mind, and chosen curriculum units/modules.
- (iii) Constructing: Gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
- (iv) Reconstructing: Integration of newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.

- (v) Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
- (vi) Finalizing: Reflecting and evaluating what has been learned and changed.

Figure 4

The DeCoRe+ Interaction

Notes. Adapted from Makrakis (2017)

The course has been diagnosed in this iteration to reflect on the primary objectives, strategy, and course evaluation. The reason for choosing the course is next thoroughly analyzed. According to the analysis, the course's major content – IT characteristics and discussions of everyday situations from the viewpoint of learning – relates to themes and actions in real life. Social, cultural, and environmental challenges that align with the SDG components are also part of the day-to-day concerns. The next step in the process is construction, which involves acquiring information, coming up with ideas, and building new views on the subject. By integrating newly created knowledge under the rebuilt frame of reference, the reconstructing process is put into action. Technical knowledge and instrumental knowledge (sending information) focusing on the idea of IT, fundamental principles in IT for education, and its other features, are just a few of the types of knowledge that can be promoted through this course module. This course can promote practical knowledge (which emphasizes a thorough comprehension of applying IT to various aspects of education). By including the sustainable value in the discussions that learners are formed to participate in, it is also possible to promote emancipatory knowledge (create conditions for empowerment and change towards sustainable societies). This will help the learners become more aware and responsible participants. The reconstructed curriculum unit or module has been implemented along with service learning as part of the course's implementation, closing the revision circle. Reflection is conducted at the end to review what has been learned and altered.

For the revised course evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2022) has been applied. These

processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what learners bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims to assess a course and, more importantly, make whatever changes to improve it. Through the parts of the DREAM Methodology, the learner guided by the course instructor creates a portfolio they have to give back to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The learners' DREAM portfolios must be analyzed by the instructor and prepared into a report for the whole class. Analyzing the DREAM portfolios will provide important information that the instructor and learners could discuss and find ways to improve the course. The above processes can be summarized as shown in the diagram below.

Figure 5

DREAM Methodology

6. Finding and Discussion

6.1 Discussion on “Now What”

While enhancing the module based on DeCoRe+, some SDG elements, the six pillars of learning, and the 10Cs were embedded into the course.

Among the SDG Elements found is SDG 4 Quality Education. The learners are equipped with the knowledge and skills they deserve through learning this course. Courses with complete and up-to-date content can prepare learners to master various knowledge and skills – especially those related to 21st-century teaching-learning methods. With

such knowledge and skills, learners can support industry development (education) and innovation (in teaching and learning). The COVID19 outbreak has prompted new teaching and learning approaches to replace old methods – for example, face-to-face learning in the classroom. This situation supports the element of SDG 9 Industry, Innovation & Infrastructure. In addition, this course can also help the planning of the education system responsible for the bombardment of resources through SDG 12 Responsible Consumption & Production. It can be done through the efficiency of learners (a teacher later) who will optimize their knowledge and skills to carry out teaching tasks more effectively.

The content and learning activities of the course are found to be interconnected with the Six Learning Pillars, which are the core of the sustainability of development. Almost all topics aim to “learn to know” as all topics are new to every learner. This means that they learn the content of this course to learn something new to them and will be used in their duties as teachers later. With the latest knowledge and skills, learners need to seek to become effective teachers that are they are – “learn to be” by having such knowledge and skills. Learners can reasonably consider and support the principle of “learning to live together” with the knowledge learned. The topics in this course help them understand the problems in the teaching process (by teachers) and learning (by learners). In Online Class Participation (OCP), the learners must also apply new ideas to develop an understanding of ICT issues related to education matters. As for cross or intercultural competencies, the learners discuss the application of ICT knowledge and skills in their daily life. The knowledge and skills acquired can also provide them with “learning to do” something with concern about the environment. The knowledge and skills acquired through this course can be used to alter themselves and the communities around them. The principles of justice learned through activities in this course can also educate them to “learn to give and share”. Through this pillar, learners need to give and share ideas to find the best solution for using ICT that is most suitable for the existing learner environment – by using appropriate learning strategies such as collaborative learning. In OUM virtual learning environment – myINSPIRE, learners communicate with the teacher and other learners to synthesize and transmit written, oral, and virtual ideas.

Additionally, this course pushed learners to “learn to transform themselves and society” which means that they should be able to develop excellent attitudes, good values, and opportunities to affect others favourably. In online e-Lesson, the learners need to think critically to solve the problem given, so they need to make decisions and take appropriate action, using learning processes such as conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating information gathered. In summary, this course has provided learners with knowledge and skills that they may use to improve their lives and the communities in which they live.

All elements of 10C can be linked into the existing module. The “communication” element can be attributed to the discussion activity through the Live Forum through the learning portal. On the other hand, the “collaboration” element can be mastered by learners through group activities where they need to work together to complete the learning tasks set. The aspect of “creativity and innovation” is interjected through the evaluation process, where learners need to apply creativity and innovation to prepare graphs and tables through Electronic Presentation topics. The “thinking skills” elements are emphasized through an evaluation process where learners must think about planning to use e-Form in Word Processing topics. Learners will also master the aspect of “connectivity” by learning Network topics. The critical “reflection” element is emphasized through the topic Learning Software Assessment. While the “critical consciousness” element is obtained through the classroom learning process through various learning software – such as Word, Powerpoint, and Excel. Then, the aspect of “constructing knowledge” is mastered by learners through the topic of Choosing Software. Learners master the element of “cross-cultural competence” by applying the content of the lessons in this course to their daily lives. And finally, the “con-responsibility” element is obtained through the topic Computer and Laboratory Maintenance. In summary, these elements can be mapped to the contents of this course.

6.2 Challenges

The challenges faced during module deconstructing are in several areas: module content, content application, teaching and learning process, and assessment methods. All these concerns have to be considered to ensure that the SDG components can be well integrated within the module.

A module developer needs to carefully determine which topics are appropriate to integrate the SDG components. This is crucial because the contents have been prepared based on Course Learning Outcomes (CLO) as agreed upon by the authority for Malaysian higher institutions. The existing topics in the module need to be maintained, but with the addition of SDG components, the topic will change to some extent. The second challenge is how to connect the SDG components to the students' real life after they finish studying this module later or apply the knowledge from this module to their work needs later. Since SDG may be new and unfamiliar knowledge, they need to master the understanding of SDGs before they can apply them in real life. The third challenge is the methodology of teaching and learning. As a university with an ODL approach, the module undergoing deconstructing needs to take into account how the SDG components that have been integrated can be taught entirely online. This is because the lesson content in each module at OUM needs to be adapted to the existing online teaching methods. SDG components must be carefully incorporated into previous modules so that the content can be accurately measured through proper and causal measurement activities - examinations or continuous assessment. With appropriate assessment method, the SDG

components can be assessed at the end of the learning session, whether it was successfully achieved or otherwise.

6.3 Discussion “So What”

The HBEF2303 Information Technology In Education was offered in January 2021 Semester. The learners comprise eight males and two females. Most of OUM's learners are working adults; thus, their ages range from a minimum of 21 to those above 60 years old. Also, since OUM's teaching and learning are entirely online, these learners are scattered throughout the country. This course was assessed using the DREAM Methodology.

In the first stage, DIAGNOSE indicated that most learners are taking this course for the first time. All of the learners are answering the questionnaire. Their occupation is teaching, while other areas include services and technicians. The learners (participants) in this study were given a set of questionnaires with two parts (open-ended and multiple choice) at the beginning and end of the semester. The purpose of the questionnaires is to gather participants' opinions on the course and their learning capacity.

In terms of technological competencies, the data showed that more than half of learners are “often” or “very often” in the areas such as “Accessing to online materials (i.e., eBooks, journals, databases, etc.)”, “Using statistical tools (i.e., Microsoft Excel, IBM SPSS, MATLAB, etc.)”, “Using communication platforms (i.e., blogs, discussion forums, etc.)”, “Using presentation tools (i.e., Microsoft PowerPoint, Google Slides, Prezi, etc.)”, and “Using e-learning platform (i.e., myINSPIRE-OUM)”.

Besides having technological competencies, all learners pursuing this course agreed they enjoy learning and doing new things. They are not hasty in making decisions. All of them will think carefully before making any decision. They also can work well in teams, staying calm and composed during discussions. They can communicate well with others. Also, they loved doing hands-on activities and challenges.

Most of these learners admitted that this course is related to their current jobs – were they able to “improve their job skills”. By learning this course also, they can “apply the knowledge or skills gained in their daily lives” and “be better in the decision making”.

Learners identified various topics from this course as the most impactful, such as critical thinking, game-based learning, visual learning, internet, ICT, instructional objective, technology and design, induction set, learner analysis, and effective teacher.

Figure 6

DREAM Methodology

While mid-way studying this course, the learners are requested to reflect on the experiences they gained.

The positive aspects stated by the learners were that “this course attracted their attention” through “the addition of a variety of new knowledge and skills compared to the existing ones”. This makes them “feel fun to follow the planned learning activities in this course”. Then, it can also “expose and make them aware of the goals of the SDGs more significantly” so that they can be put into practice in the future.

However, one learner also gave negative feedback that “there is not much he can learn from this course” which may be isolated feedback compared to his other colleagues.

Furthermore, learners were also asked to reflect on what they expected from the course. Among the aspects they propose are “more visual learning materials must be provided while the learning process”, “more time must be given to learners to completing the assignment”, “e-tutor need to be more friendly to the learners”, and “the assessment method should be more flexibles”.

Next, the quantitative data are related to reflections on what is different from what the learners expected, as well as something they may never have expected to happen. The most common differences they make are “interesting visual learning resources was provided by this course”, “this course providing the e-lessons which are supporting their learning process”, “their e-tutor are creative and innovative in delivering the teaching process” and “the recorded e-tutorial sessions are available for the future references”, and “increasing the new knowledge about SDGs”.

The learners' reflections identified some expectations are not as expected. They shared their reactions due to the differences in expectations. This include “happy”, “accepting”, and “enthusiastic”.

Besides that, learners also suggest ideas to improve the course, such as “allocate more collaborative tasks

concerning SDGs”, “providing exercise questions with the format”, “give additional time for assignment submission”, and “encourage an active learner involvement in the learning process”, and “using the 21st-century education methods”.

The learners gave two reasons why this course was not as expected. The first reason is the availability of more “interactive sessions”. The students hope that more interactive sessions can be provided to open up opportunities for them to communicate more with lecturers and friends. They can use the opportunity to understand particular knowledge or skill better. The second reason is the “submission time” for the assignment should be extended. Most working students have significant time constraints. In addition, they also have to make commitments to their families, so the time to prepare the assignment answers becomes very critical. Therefore, they suggested that the assignment submission time be increased so that they could have more time to answer the required assignment questions. Based on the above discussion, it is found that there are aspects of improvement that have been successfully identified and mapped as in the following figure.

Figure 7
The Course Impact Factors After DREAM

In the ASSESS stage, learners are requested to assess the impact of what has been learned in terms of “academic development”. Data shows the learners agreed that they are “enriching their knowledge about SDGs” in addition to “ICT skills”, and also “upgrading their skills in searching authoritative learning resources”.

In the “professional development” aspect, learners stated that they are “able to apply the acquired knowledge in their work”, “able to enhance their competency in daily task dan work”, and also “improve their leadership skills”.

Meanwhile, in the aspect of “social development”, the learners have explained that “they have learned how to work in an effective group” while being able to “improve their interpersonal skills”, especially through communication that takes place, and eventually be able to make the topic of the SDGs as an exciting topic of discussion.

Compared to the aspect of “personal development”, they voiced their view that “they are now more open-minded” than before; in fact, they are “more confident in making a decision” based on arguments and new ideas that are more daring to be expressed among friends. Now they are

becoming "more sensitive to the environment related to aspects of the SDGs".

Learners were also asked to suggest things they would like to be different if they retake this course. Some suggestions include "prioritize behaviour and socio-emotional which should be included in this course". They were also looking forward to "learning the new knowledge", becoming "more sensitive and confidence in life", and also being able to accept the "different styles of tutor" while learning new things.

For the final stage, learners are requested to SUGGEST how they can apply the new knowledge learned from the course in the future. Various suggestions were given, including:

- more participation in SDG campaigns,
- use a blended approach in the teaching and learning process,
- relate to the daily life activities,
- integrate with an ICT application,
- helps others who needed, and
- apply knowledge in teaching jobs.

7. Conclusions

The SDG is already addressed in Malaysia's STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) curricula (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2031). Because of this, many teachers are aware of the SDGs, but those who do not teach STEM subjects might not be aware that SDGs can be integrated into any academic fields. With this understanding, teachers should be inspired to include the SDGs into their curriculum, raising student awareness and enhancing their knowledge of the goals. Additionally, exposing teachers, students, and communities to the SDGs might inspire them to adopt them as a way of life. Therefore, ESD is the most effective approach to spread the SDG to the community, starting with the students in the classroom through trained teachers.

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Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing the Science Course Using SDG's Perspectives

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Abstract

Environmental education aims to create a population that is aware of and concerned about the environment and the problems it causes, as well as one that has the knowledge, skills, attitudes, motivations, and commitment to work both individually and collectively to find solutions to the problems that are currently plaguing us and to prevent the emergence of new ones. Open University Malaysia (OUM) amended HBSC3303 School Science Curriculum in order to incorporate Education for Sustainability (EfS) into teaching, learning, and curriculum. The purpose of this study was to describe the procedures, methods, and outcomes of this course redesign. The Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction (DeCoRe+) method was used to incorporate sustainability, specifically the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In this course version, the core goals, strategy, and teaching methodology have all been addressed. Some SDG components, the Six Learning Pillars, and the 10Cs were added during the course revision. This study demonstrated the effectiveness of DeCoRe+ as a curriculum revision technique that successfully integrates EfS into participants' teaching, learning, and the curriculum. After all, EfS is the most effective way to spread awareness of the SDGs in society. Any academic discipline that promotes the same goal, including Science Curriculum pedagogy, can help propagate the SDGs.

Keywords: EfS, SDG, sustainability

1. Introduction

Humanity has had to contend with the effects of unsustainable economic development expansion driven by profit maximization, which has led to excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources over the past few decades (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). However, considerable work remains to be done to reverse this unsustainable development process, despite current measures. All levels of education systems, but notably higher education, are to blame for the global sustainability dilemma. This is due mainly to the fact that educational institutions produce consumers, leaders, and decision-makers who drive society and the economy and create an unsustainable consumer culture (Makrakis, 2011). "The magnitude and range of the negative repercussions of persons with university educations on the ecological systems that sustain Earth are unparalleled" Corcoran and Wals (2004). (p. 3).

A significant revolution based on an alternative development model that emphasizes sustained well-being should be driven through education. From our perspective, eudaimonic well-being, as opposed to the general hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and forms of production and consumption, is akin to Aristotle's concept of sustainable well-being (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020).

To learn how to improve oneself and society, it is crucial to pursue "sustainability justice", a concept coined by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economics, and culture.

It is essential to note that, despite significant funding for environmental education over the past few decades, environmental action has received less attention than favorable views on the environment. A paradigm shift in curriculum, teaching, and learning is necessary to translate environmental awareness and understanding into environmental action. However, better education degrees for citizens do not inevitably result in higher sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The discrepancy between environmental attitudes and activity is due to several other issues and educational techniques. Recent curriculum creation studies with an emphasis on sustainability reveal that lecturing, as anticipated, was the most common form of instruction, whereas more effective methods, including role-play, hands-on science, and problem-based learning, were assessed as being used far less frequently (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015; 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

According to a project called Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013, 2014), the great challenge facing institutions of higher learning in the 21st century is training professionals who are critical of and capable of changing their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. Teachers in primary and secondary schools face a similar problem. Therefore, teaching staff are the change agents in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum and making schools sustainable (Biasutti et al., 2016; Blake et al., 2013; Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

Education for sustainability is not a novel concept in Malaysia (Mahat & Idrus, 2016). For instance, the Ministry of Housing and Local Government of Malaysia introduced Local Agenda 21 in 2001 as a follow-up to the conclusions reached at the 1992 United Nations Rio Conference (GDRC.org, 2022). Malaysia learns through this strategy that participation at all societal levels is necessary for the theory and practice of education for sustainable development. Moreover, during the period of the Malaysian government following the Third Malaysian Plan (1976–1980), the concept of universal sustainability evolved (Malaysian Prime Minister Department, 2022). Nevertheless, despite the rapid development of the industrial and infrastructure sectors at the time, the focus was more on protecting historical and cultural heritage (Izicadiana et al., 2016).

The Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 for Preschool and Post-Secondary Education was created in 2013 by the Malaysian Ministry of Education (MoE). This blueprint outlines a brand-new course for classroom instruction. As a result, a new curriculum was created for preschool through post-secondary levels to achieve the educational goals outlined in the Blueprint.

The Blueprint ensures that pupils are developed holistically and can reach their full potential through education. The blueprint for the education reform includes eleven transformation shifts, six student aspirations, and five system goals. The Ministry of Education hopes that the entire educational system will achieve the aspirations of the five systems. These include;

- (i) ACCESS: to ensure 100% enrolment across all levels from preschools to upper secondary;
- (ii) QUALITY: focusing on achievement in reading, mathematics, and science;
- (iii) EQUITY: equal opportunities for all (urban-rural, socio-economic, gender, indigenous communities, special needs children);
- (iv) UNITY: promotes shared values and experiences by encouraging students to embrace diversity; and
- (v) EFFICIENCY: maximizes student outcomes within the current national budget.

The Philosophy of National Education (FPK), adopted in 1996, serves as the fundamental tenet and pillar of the country's educational system, providing the foundation for Malaysia's educational philosophy. FPK emphasizes that education is a continuous effort to develop people's potential in a holistic and integrated manner, producing a human being who is intellectually, spiritually, emotionally, and physically balanced and harmonious. Therefore, FPK has a viewpoint and understanding of nature consistent with the SDGs, especially in light of its agreement with the global SDG agenda, 2016-2030, and UNESCO's four pillars of a learning plan for the 21st century were proclaimed in 1996. (Widad et al., 2022).

2. The ICTeEfS project

Environmental harm has been one of the most significant adverse consequences in Asia's rapidly growing regions. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate the need for immediate action by Asian politicians to safeguard their citizens and mitigate the effects of climate change, ensuring future sustainable growth. Education for Sustainability (EfS) is one strategy for overcoming these obstacles. However, while Asian leaders are committed to EfS and concerned with achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), it is the classroom teachers who bring about change.

The educational workforce in Malaysia, Indonesia, Vietnam, and other Asian nations requires training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental risks. On the one hand, education faculties must redesign their course offerings by incorporating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS). On the other hand, they must take advantage of these technologies' ability to spread EfS to all in-service subject teachers. ICT will inevitably be incorporated into teacher education programs and in-service training curricula due to the increasing importance of ICT literacy and the rapid expansion of ICT infrastructure in PCs. However, ICT integration entails more than just including ICT as a topic or resource. It calls for thorough and integrated planning of ICTeEfS in teacher education, involving changes in both teaching and learning.

Given the difficulties and shortages mentioned in the rationale, the proposed project aims to create an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, encouraging them to adopt cutting-edge pedagogies and teaching strategies focused on education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has received funding from the Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for 2019–2023 by the European Commission. The following are the more precise goals:

XVI.

Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.

XVII.

Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a comprehensive ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.

XVIII.

Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program, enabled by blended learning, focusing on integrating education for sustainability across school curricula.

XIX.

Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.

- XX. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices, and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the Open University Malaysia entitled HBSC3303 School Science Curriculum, considering six main questions: The first question is the “What” question and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for modification, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The second question and third questions refer to “Why” (justifying the reasons for revision) and “Where” describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The fourth question is the “How” question relating to the methodologies used for the revision and the course assessment during the implementation process. The fifth question is the “Now What” question that shows what the course's revised and/or updated revision looks like and how it has changed from “What” was before. Lastly, the sixth question is the “So What?” question that discusses the challenges met through all the preceding processes from the beginning up to now and how has been tackled. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding of teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it affect the beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for not being done, why, and what would be the following actions?

3. The “What”, “Why”, and “Where” Questions for Revising (HBSC School Science Curriculum)

Course Background

Open University Malaysia (OUM) offers 54 programmes comprising 28 at the undergraduate level and 26 at the post-graduate level. Three equal semesters make up the academic year at the university. A total of 27,000 active students will access about 650 courses per semester. Each student typically enrolls in three courses each semester. OUM uses a community of inquiry (CoI) model of engagement-based, fully online blended pedagogy for teaching and learning (Garrison et al., 2000).

Notes. The model was suggested by (Garrison et al., 2000)

The asynchronous online forum, also known as the Online Class Participation (OCP), is necessary to ensure interactions between students/peers. This pedagogy consists of synchronous, fully online face-to-face tutorials conducted via Google Meet, satisfying the need for interactions between students and instructors (Teaching Presence) (Social Presence). The forum is run by MyInspire, a learning management system developed by OUM. In addition, online learning resources made up of modules and e-lessons are used to facilitate interactions between students and the learning materials (Cognitive Presence).

In addition to the subject’s primary topic areas, the OUM module has sections on “Self-Check” and “Activities”. Following completion of the lesson, each of these parts invited students to test or confirm their knowledge by completing the prescribed exercises independently or in groups. E-lessons that are created by the module topics further help to learn. This summarizes each case with links to the module's content; use your tubes and further reading resources or references. The e-lessons also offer associated problems, discussion points, and self-tests.

4. Why are this course chosen?

The HBSC3303 School Science Curriculum is a course offered to learners enrolled in the Bachelor of Teaching (Primary Education). The basic science curriculum, issues in science education, the history of the Malaysian primary science curriculum, primary science teaching, and learning methodologies, teaching science to all children, and teaching science to children with special needs are all covered in this course.

Figure 1

Community of Inquiry (COL) Model of Engagement

Aims

The primary goal of this module is to transmit the principles of how the primary school science curriculum was developed and what makes it unique. Teachers should be able to use this module as a solid basis to internalize the main science curriculum's guiding principles and design engaging science courses.

The learning outcomes for this course are:

- (v) To identify the objectives, learning outcomes, emphasis, content organization, and scope of the Malaysian Primary Science Curriculum;
- (vi) To state relevant issues in science education and their relation to primary science teaching;
- (vii) To describe the historical development of the primary science curriculum; and
- (viii) To apply strategies for adapting science instruction to meet the needs of learners from a culturally diverse population, gender differences, learner differences, and exceptional children.

All students enrolled in the Bachelor of Teaching degree with a Science major are eligible to take this course. The focus of this session is the principles of how the primary school science curriculum was developed and what makes it unique. This module ought to provide instructors with a solid basis upon which they may internalize the primary science curriculum's guiding principles and design engaging science courses. In addition, students can apply sustainability principles in the classroom by focusing on specific topics.

The content of this course consists of topics such as Formulation of the Curriculum (SDG 4 Quality Education, SDG 16 Peace, Justice and Strong Institution), Issues in Science Education (SDG5 Gender Equality), Historical Development of the Science Curriculum (SDG10 Reduced Inequalities), Integrated Curriculum for Primary Schools (KBSR) (SDG16 Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions), Primary School Standard Curriculum (KSSR) (SDG16 Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions), Teaching Science to All Children (SDG10 Reduced Inequalities), and Strategies for Diverse Learners (SDG10 Reduced Inequalities).

With a solid foundation in science, it is hoped the students will be able to develop the following:

- (vi) Problem-solving skills
- (vii) Leadership skills
- (viii) Communication skills
- (ix) Collaborative skills
- (x) Critical and creative thinking skills

The 10C learning skills elements can be explained as follows.

Table 1 10C Learning Skills Mapped within the Course.

10C's Learning Skills	Topics in Module
1. Critical thinking and problem solving	1, 4, 5

2. Communication	4, 6, 7
3. Collaboration	7, 8
4. Creativity and innovation	8
5. Connectivity and networking	3, 4, 5
6. Critical reflection	3, 6
7. Cross/ inter-cultural competence	7
8. Co-responsibility	8
9. Constructing knowledge	2
10. Critical consciousness/ conscientization	1, 8

All 10C's elements can be linked to the content in this course. Therefore, in summary, these elements can be mapped to the contents of this course.

Students interact with the teacher and other students in myINSPIRE to synthesize and transfer ideas in writing, oral, and virtual modes. To solve the problem presented in the online E-Lesson, students must apply critical thinking. They must therefore use learning processes including conceiving, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating information received to decide what to do and how to do it.

The students in "Online Class Participation (OCP)" must also use new concepts to create creative applications and solutions based on the science curriculum. When it comes to cross- and intercultural skills, students might use them by studying a subject like the creation of computer-assisted learning software. They don't just have to concentrate on the lesson's topic; they can also involve students of diverse races, religions, and cultures.

The assessment for this course consists of both coursework and a final examination. The course work carries a score of 60% comprising Written Assignment, Online Class Participation (OCP), and Online Assessment-Activity. The Online Final Examination comprises a weightage of 40%.

5. Methodologies – The “How” Question

A six-stage capacity-building methodology proposed by Makrakis (2006) was utilized to teach academic staff to include sustainability in their courses in light of the characteristics above, demands, and goals (Figure 1).

Figure 1

A Capacity Building Model

Notes. Model adapted from Makrakis (2006)

Training in the initial stage is concentrated on identifying each trainee's didactic profile.

An action plan for the particular training session is created based on the analysis of each trainee's profile (second stage). The training material, which combines theory and practice and is organized into theme units or modules that can be further developed while considering the trainee's needs, follows the action plan (third stage). The action plan's goals and objectives will be compared to the trainees' initial profiles and the evaluation of their learning results (fourth stage). Using the newly learned skills and information acquired in the classroom, the learners, as the end recipients, continue the evaluation process (fifth stage). All phases of the training process are supported by an integrated monitoring and improvement system that facilitates maintaining proper operation and identifying potential areas for improvement (sixth stage).

The "DeCoRe+ methodology," an acronym for "Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction" proposed by Makrakis (2017), was used for course modification to incorporate sustainability and, in particular, the "17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)". The "DeCoRe+ approach adopts a design methodology that focuses on transformative curriculum development and views curricula as living entities. The following processes are among the six that makeup DeCoRe+.

- (i) Diagnosing: Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.
- (ii) Deconstructing: Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
- (iii) Constructing: Gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
- (iv) Reconstructing: Integration of newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.

- (v) Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
- (vi) Finalizing: Reflecting and evaluating what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2

The DeCoRe+ Interaction

Notes. Makrakis (2017)

6. Finding and Discussion

6.4 Results – “Now What?”

This course emphasizes some elements of the SDGs. Among them are SDG 16 Peace, Justice, and Strong Institution through Topic 1 Formulation of the Curriculum. A Science teacher should consider the flexibility of the curriculum that can create peace, justice, and harmony for all students. This will make teaching and learning more enjoyable. In Topic 2: Issues in Science Education, students are introduced to the concept that teaching the content of this lesson is closely tied to the environmental scenario surrounding them. The challenge of presenting the lesson's content to the students may need to be considered as the differences in language, and environmental problems are different in the group of students. This will make the science curriculum in Malaysia better – in line with the goals of SDG 4 Quality Education. This goal was further strengthened when Topic 4 KBSR Science Curriculum I and Topic 5 KBSR Science Curriculum II further detailed the changes that have been made to the old curriculum to the new one. In this course, students study Topic 7, Teaching Science to All Children, and Topic 8, Strategies for Diverse Learners. Students learn how to implement science teaching and learn from a wide range of students. This indirectly teaches students about equal rights and opportunities among different students. This is in line with the goals of SDG 10 Reduced Inequalities.

The content and learning activities of the course are found to be interconnected with the six learning pillars, which are the core of the sustainability of development. Almost all topics are meant to “learn to know”, and the

students are trying to “learn to be” by having such knowledge. Students can reasonably consider and support the principle of “learning to live together” with the knowledge learned. The knowledge and skills acquired can also provide them with “learning to do” something with concern about the science curriculum. The knowledge and skills gained through this course can be used to alter themselves and the communities around them related to teaching and learning science. The principles of justice learned through activities in this course can also educate them to “learn to give and share”.

However, all elements of 10C can be linked into the existing module. The “communication” element can be attributed to the discussion activity through the Live Forum through the learning portal. On the other hand, the “collaboration” element can be mastered by students through group activities where they need to work together to complete the learning tasks set. The “Creativity and innovation” element is interjected through the evaluation process. Students must apply creativity and innovation to prepare a suggestion for new curriculum formula in Topic 1 Formulation of the Curriculum. The “thinking skills” elements are emphasized through an evaluation process where students must consider the Issues in Science Education (Topic 2). Students will also master the aspect of “connectivity” by reflecting on the reason and process of Malaysia's science curriculum development (Topic 3 Historical Development of the Science Curriculum). By comparing the content of Topic 4, KBSR Science Curriculum I, and Topic 4, KBSR Science Curriculum II, the student will have a critical “reflection” element that emphasizes why the changes need to be done in the Malaysian science curriculum. While the “critical consciousness” element is obtained through the classroom learning process through Topic 6 Primary School Standard Curriculum, where they have to understand how this new curriculum will be implemented deeply. Then, the “constructing knowledge” element is mastered by students through Topics 4, 5, and 6. Students master the concept of “cross-cultural competence” by applying the course content to their daily teaching tasks in school. And finally, the “con-responsibility” element is obtained through Topic 7, Teaching Science to All Children, and Topic 8, Strategies for Diverse Learners. In summary, all the 10C elements can be mapped into the contents of this course.

In addition, the science curriculum, particularly in teaching and learning activities, teaches the students to give and share their ideas and collaborate to find the best solutions to link to their real-life situations (in school). Learners collaborate with the teacher and other students in the OUM virtual learning environment, myINSPIRE, to synthesize and transfer written, oral, and virtual thoughts. For example, in an online e-Lesson, students must use critical thinking to solve the provided topic. To do this, they must decide what to do and how to do it by employing learning processes like conceptualizing, applying,

analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating the knowledge obtained.

At some point in Online Class Participation (OCP), students must also put new concepts into practice to grasp scientific curricular concerns based on past events. Regarding cross- or inter-cultural competencies, the students talk about how science curriculum information is applied to their later teaching and learning in the classroom.

6.5 Challenges

The difficulties encountered during module deconstruction can be broken down into four categories: assessment methods, teaching and learning processes, as well as module content and its application in the real world. The priority is to ensure embedding SDGs will further enhanced the quality of the module.

Selection of topics appropriate for integrating the SDGs components had to be carefully done; to ensure it is in tandem with the Course Learning Outcomes (CLO) which was already approved by the Malaysian Quality Agency (MQA). The current module topics must be maintained, although with the addition of SDGs components, the content have changed. The second challenge relate to the application of SDG knowledge gained from this module which students should do in their life; at work; at home as well as within the community. To do this, students need to master the acquired knowledge which may be new and challenging. The teaching and learning methodology is the third challenge. The curriculum being deconstructed must consider how the integrated SDG components can be taught effectively online based on the ODL approach. It is imperative all OUM's module content be constructed suited for the online teaching techniques. The final challenge is ensuring assessment of the newly integrated SDGs content is appropriately embedded within the evaluation method used. This include formative and summative assessment; through assignments and final examinations. However, it is of particular importance to take into consideration various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues pertaining to the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al. 2024).

7. Conclusions

SDG is already part of the Malaysian school curriculum in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2031). Therefore, many teachers are aware of SDGs, but those not involved in teaching STEM may not be aware that SDGs can be embedded across any discipline. With this awareness, teachers should be motivated to embed SDGs into their lessons, creating awareness and enriching knowledge on SDGs amongst their students. Also, exposure to SDGs can be a catalyst for teachers, students, and communities to make

SDGs part of living. Consequently, ESD is the best way to channel SDG to the community, start with the children in school through trained teacher.

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Teaching Preschool Mathematics: Implementing SDGs Through the DeCoRe Approach

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Abstract

There has been a significant shift in the global investment landscape toward early childhood education. A number of nations have increased their spending to support the provision of pre-school education at an adequate standard. The goal of environmental education is to instill in children a respect for the interdependence of the natural and social worlds, a faith in the intrinsic value of all living things, and an awareness that the advancement of technology can have unforeseen effects on the environment. The purpose of this research is to demonstrate the methodologies, approaches, and results of modifying the HBMT1203 Teaching of Preschool Mathematics course that is offered through Open University Malaysia (OUM). The DeCoRe approach was utilised in order to include the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into the content of this course. The core ideas of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, which are strengthened by the processes of diagnostic evaluation, implementation, and summative evaluation respectively. The DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2019;2022) has been applied for the revised courses evaluation during the implementation process. The application of DeCoRe and DREAM has been described, along with some of the difficulties that have arisen and areas that need more study.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); pre-school mathematics; DeCoRe+ approach, DREAM methodology; ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability

1. Introduction

Environmental destruction has been one of the most obvious adverse consequences of Asia's rapid growth. Asian policymakers must take immediate action to safeguard their citizens and mitigate the effects of climate change, ensuring sustainable growth for the future, as demonstrated by recent climate-related disasters in the region. Education for sustainability (EfS) is one method to meet these difficulties. The true change-makers are the teachers in the classroom, notwithstanding the commitment of Asian leaders to EfS and their concern for the execution of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Educators in Malaysia, Indonesia, Vietnam, and other Asian nations need to be trained to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. To advance Education for Sustainability (EfS) among all subject in-service teachers, colleges of education must, on the one hand, restructure their study programs to incorporate ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS). ICT will inevitably be incorporated into the curricula of teacher education programmes and in-service training due to rising ICT literacy rates and the availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs. ICT integration, however, entails more than just including ICT as a topic or resource. It calls for extensive and integrated planning of ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education, implying changes to how teaching and learning are conducted.

The purpose of this study is to show the procedures, techniques, and outcomes of reconstructing one of the Open University Malaysia (OUM) courses entitled HBMT1203 Teaching of Preschool Mathematics. It will consider six

primary questions: What was chosen for revision, why, where, when, and what obstacles were encountered. The HBMT1203 Teaching of Preschool Mathematics is one of the Major courses in mathematics for the Bachelor of Teaching (Primary Education). This course covers topics such as whole numbers up to 100, addition to the highest total of 18, subtraction within the range of 18, money up to RM10, introduction to time, shape, and space, as well as the teaching and learning methodologies used to deliver the various content areas.

2. Literature Review

Learning to improve oneself and one's community requires a deep commitment to the pursuit of "sustainability justice," a notion established by Makrakis (2006; 2017). When implementing a new model of development that priorities sustainable well-being, education should play a pivotal role in bringing about a sea change. A fundamental shift in how we educate and what we teach about the environment is necessary if we are to see that awareness and understanding translated into real, tangible change. The most common method of instruction, according to the studies, was the dreaded lecture. Although they are more effective, role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning were ranked far lower in utilization.

An Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016;2018; Blake et al., 2013) can make schools more sustainable, but it is the teachers themselves who must be the agents of change (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013). The Malaysian Ministry of Housing and Local

Government introduced Local Agenda 21 in 2001. Malaysia concludes from this strategy that all levels of society must be involved in implementing sustainable development education (GDRC.org, 2022).

The Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 was created by the country's Ministry of Education (MoE) for use in both primary and secondary schools. With the help of this Blueprint, we now have a fresh approach to education. To achieve the goals outlined in the Blueprint, a new curriculum has been developed that encompasses all levels of education, from early childhood through college.

OUM offers 54 programmes, comprising 28 undergraduate and 26 postgraduate programmes. The academic year at the university is divided into three semesters. Approximately 650 courses will be provided to approximately 27000 active learners per semester. Typically, each student will enroll in three courses per semester. OUM employs an entirely online blended methodology for teaching and learning, based on the Community of Inquiry (CoI) Model of Engagement developed by Garrison, Anderson, and Archer (2000).

This pedagogy consists of synchronous fully online face-to-face tutorials conducted via Google Meet, which fulfils the need for interactions between learners and instructors (Teaching Presence); and an asynchronous online forum, also known as the Online Class Participation (OCP), which is required to ensure interactions between learners/peers (Social Presence). The forum is run using OUM's proprietary learning management system, MyInspire. Interactions between learners and learning materials (Cognitive Presence) are achieved by providing online learning resources such as modules and e-lessons.

Aside from the subject's primary topic areas, OUM's module includes a section on "self-check" and "activities." Both sections encouraged learners to assess their knowledge after completing the module and to undertake the suggested activities either in groups or individually. E-lessons designed according to module topics supplement learning. This framework outlines each topic, including connections to the topic's content within the module, as well as relevant YouTube videos and additional references or reading materials. The e-lessons also feature discussion topics, associated problems, and a self-test.

3. Methodology

In light of the aforementioned traits, demands, and objectives, Makrakis (2006) developed a six-stage capacity-building model to educate academic staff on embedding sustainability in their courses (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

During the first stage of training, the primary emphasis is placed on conducting an individual assessment of each trainee's didactic profile. An action plan for the particular training session is developed based on an examination of the profiles of all of the trainees (second stage). After the action plan comes the training material, which combines theory and practice and is organised into themed units or modules that can be further developed, taking into consideration the demands and necessities of the learner (third stage). The evaluation of the trainees' learning results will include a comparison to their original profiles, as well as the goals and objectives outlined in the action plan (fourth stage). The same kind of evaluation is then carried out for the program's ultimate recipients, the students, by having them apply the skills and information they have gained in the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages, which helps to maintain the training process's proper functioning and allows for possible upgrades to be made (sixth stage).

The DeCoRe approach was used to incorporate the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into this course. DeCoRe + is an abbreviation for the primary constructs of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, which are complemented by the processes of Diagnostic Evaluation, Implementation, and Summative Evaluation. The DeCoRe+ methodological approach is founded on critical social theory, critical pedagogy, and transformative concepts of teaching, learning, and curriculum (Makrakis, 2017).

The following are the six steps that comprise DeCoRe+:

- i. Diagnosis: Considering a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.
- ii. Deconstructing: Critically analysing the operation of personal views and habits of thought, as well as selected curriculum units/modules.
- iii. Constructing entails gathering materials, developing ideas, and generating new meaning (perspectives).
- iv. Reconstruction: The incorporation of newly produced knowledge into the reconstructed frame of reference.

- v. Implementing: Putting the reconstructed curricular unit/module into action, enhanced by service learning.
- vi. Wrapping up: Reflecting on and assessing what has been learnt and changed.

Makrakis's (2023) DREAM (Diagnose, review, reflect, explain, assess, and manage) method has been used to evaluate the new courses during the implementation process. These steps encompass the entire course, from what students bring to class before it begins (Diagnosing) to what they do during the course (Reviewing, reflecting, and explaining) to what they do at the end of the course (Explaining, assessing, and managing). In a way, the DREAM method is akin to a critical action research process, which not only examines a course but also seeks to identify the necessary changes to improve it. With the teacher's help, the student applies the parts of the DREAM Methodology to create a portfolio that they will return to the teacher at the end of the course. The DREAM Methodology is one of the course requirements. The teacher must review the students' DREAM portfolios and write a report for the entire class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will give the teacher and the students very important information that they can talk about and use to find ways to make the course better.

Figure 2: The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

4. Result and Discussion

The concepts covered in this course do, in fact, have real-life applications; some examples include basic counting, money, time, and measurement. This also applies to the four aspects of sustainability, which are as follows: (i) Environmental Justice in relation to topics about basic counting and measurement; (ii) Social Justice is similarly related to topics about basic counting and measurement; (iii) Economic Justice in related to topics about money; and (iv) Cultural Justice is related to topics about time. The average

number of students enrolled in a course throughout a semester ranges from 15 to 25.

The key concepts that students need to master through this course are pedagogy, techniques, and approaches of teaching preschool mathematics. All of these three key concepts will involve appropriate learning activities. With a solid foundation in mathematics, it is hoped the students will be able to develop problem-solving skills, leadership skills, communication skills, collaborative skills, and critical and creative thinking skills.

The assessment for this course consists of both course work and a final examination. The achievement of this course is measured through continuous assessment methods, which include an online component (with a score of 60%) and a Final Examination (with a score of 40%).

Some aspects of the SDGs, the 6 pillars of learning, and the 10Cs were incorporated during the process of refining the course learning materials or modules based on DeCORE. SDG4 is the first SDG to be integrated in this course. SDG4 aims to ensure that everyone has equal access to high-quality, inclusive education and to promote lifelong learning. Understanding mathematical concepts and their links will serve as a bridge to sustainable development from the standpoint of teaching and learning (e.g., impact on lifelong learning).

The course's content and learning activities are discovered to be associated with the six learning pillars, which are at the heart of development sustainability. The students learn about the tactics, approaches, methods, and procedures used in the teaching and learning of mathematics. They also learn how to select, design, and implement successful teaching and learning strategies and materials.

At the completion of the course, they will be able to live together in a sustainable manner by learning tactics and approaches to teaching Mathematics, as well as respect and consideration for the learners' varied backgrounds. This will lead to respect for the rights and needs of others.

This course also encouraged students to explore ways to transform themselves and society. They can shape ideals, foster healthier attitudes, and create opportunities to positively impact others. This course's knowledge and abilities can be utilised to transform oneself and the communities around them.

All 10C aspects apply to the topics in this course. In general, these elements correspond to the course material. Learners use Myinspire to communicate with the teacher and other students in order to synthesise and convey ideas in writing, oral, and virtual formats. To answer the challenge test presented in the online E-Lesson, learners must think critically, making judgments and taking appropriate action while employing learning processes such as conceptualising,

applying, analysing, synthesising, and evaluating knowledge obtained.

5. Conclusion

There are numerous challenges in implementing the SDGs in this course, primarily because the course content cannot be altered by more than 25% due to the university's affiliation with the Malaysian Qualifications Agency (MQA). OUM's learning materials are created using a predefined template. Making modifications to any learning materials, then, necessitates critical analysis to identify where changes are needed, as well as creativity to reorganise so that the new materials may be incorporated cohesively with the current resources. However, it is of particular importance to take into consideration various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024) as well as issues on the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs to address sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al, 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

The incorporation of SDGs into this course should raise learners' awareness and understanding of SDGs. As a result of this understanding, people should be more concerned about what is going on in their life, society, country, and the world. They must understand the significance of the SDGs to ensure global wealth and harmony. Furthermore, by taking this course, learners who are already familiar with the SDGs will be able to enhance their understanding and deepen their commitment to the SDGs. After completing the one-semester course, students should be able to share their knowledge of the SDGs and raise awareness among family members and local communities.

SDGs are already taught in Malaysian schools in disciplines such as science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM). As a result, while many instructors are aware of the SDGs, those not involved in STEM education may be unaware that the SDGs can be integrated across any curriculum. With this awareness, teachers should be inspired to include SDGs into their courses, thereby raising awareness and enriching students' knowledge of the SDGs. Furthermore, exposure to SDGs can act as a spur for teachers, students, and communities to make SDGs a part of their daily lives.

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Teaching of Primary Mathematics: Implementing SDGs Through the DeCoRe Approach

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Abstract

Education should play a critical role for a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. This study will show the techniques, approaches, and results of altering the HBMT3103 Teaching of Elementary Mathematics Part III course offered by OUM. The process named as DeCoRe was applied in order to include the Sustainable Development Goals (also known as SDGs) into the material that is covered in this course. The fundamental concepts of deconstruction, construction, and reconstruction, each of which is bolstered in turn by the procedures of diagnostic evaluation, implementation, and summative evaluation. During the implementation of the redesigned courses, the methodology known as DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess, and Manage), developed by Makrakis (2023), was employed to evaluate these courses. The implementation of DeCoRe (Makrakis, 2017) and DREAM has been discussed, along with some of the challenges that have materialised and the domains that need additional research.

Keywords: *Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); primary school mathematics; DeCoRe+ approach, DREAM methodology; ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability*

1. Introduction

The excessive depletion and deterioration of natural resources have been a significant problem for humanity over the past few decades, resulting from unsustainable economic development driven by profit maximization (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite ongoing efforts aimed at reversing this type of unsustainable development, considerable work remains to be done. The global sustainability dilemma is primarily due to the shortcomings of the education system, particularly in higher education. In large part, this is because the people who drive society and the economy, and who construct an unsustainable consumer culture, are the products of our educational institutions (Makrakis, 2011). The detrimental effects of college-educated individuals on Earth's ecological systems are unprecedented, as noted by Corcoran and Wals (2004). (p. 3).

Transformation on a massive scale through a new paradigm of development that gives sustainable well-being its rightful importance should rely heavily on educational opportunities. When compared to the prevalent hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and ways of production and consumption, sustainable well-being, in our view, is quite similar to Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). It is crucial to learn how to improve oneself and society through the pursuit of "sustainable justice," a concept coined by Makrakis (2006, 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture.

It is essential to acknowledge that, despite considerable effort invested in environmental education over the past few

decades, the outcomes have primarily focused on enhancing people's awareness of environmental issues rather than motivating them to take tangible steps to address them. A paradigm shift in education and the curriculum is necessary to translate environmental awareness and learning into concrete environmental action. Higher degrees of education do not automatically result in more sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living among the populace (Makrakis, 2012). The gap between environmental beliefs and actions is due to several causes, not the least of which is the current state of environmental education. Even if role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning would be more appropriate teaching methods, they were ranked much lower in use in recent assessments of sustainability-focused curriculum creation (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

The purpose of this study is to describe the procedures, techniques, and consequences of redesigning one of the courses at OUM named HBMT3103 Teaching of Primary Mathematics Part III in consideration of six primary questions. The first question is the "What" question and focuses on a description of the course prior to revision, including why it was selected for review, the number of students enrolled, key content themes, competencies to be developed, teaching methods employed, and methods for assessing student progress.

The second and third questions refer to "Why" (justifying the grounds for revision) and "Where" (describing the course gaps to be filled through the revision process), respectively. The fourth question is the "How" question, which describes the revision and course evaluation procedures utilised during the implementation phase. The fifth question is the "Now

What" question, which demonstrates how the amended and/or updated revision of the course differs from the "What" question.

The sixth and final question is the "So What?" question, which focuses on explaining the obstacles encountered during the preceding procedures from the beginning to the present and how they were overcome. The discussion section discusses explicitly the following sub-questions: What are the anticipated effects of the altered course on instruction, learning, the curriculum, and local/global society? How did knowledge about teaching, learning, and curriculum evolve? What have been the lessons acquired from this event, and how will they impact the beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left undone and why, as well as what are the following steps?

2. Literature Review

According to the project Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013; 2014), the great challenge of the twenty-first century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of, and capable of acting to transform their frames of reference in order to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. Teacher educators and classroom teachers in primary and secondary schools face a similar difficulty. Teaching staff serve as change agents in promoting an Education for Sustainability (Efs) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016, 2018; Blake et al., 2013), and in transforming schools into sustainable environments (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

To put the issue in context, efforts to raise awareness about sustainable development should be multifaceted, with all populations receiving exposure to the notion. The element of education for sustainable development was first officially recognised in 1992 during the Rio de Janeiro Earth Summit Conference, which produced Agenda 21. Each chapter of Agenda 21 focuses on education, but Chapter 36 focuses on education specifically, notably I increasing basic education, (ii) adapting existing education towards sustainable development, (iii) improving community understanding and awareness, and (4) training. According to Mahat and Idrus (2016), Local Agenda 21 was introduced in Malaysia in 2001 by the Ministry of Housing and Local Government Malaysia as a follow-up to the findings agreed upon at the previous United Nations Conference on Environment and Development in 1992. (GDRC.org, 2022). Malaysia discovers via this strategy that the philosophy and practice of education for sustainable development necessitate engagement at all levels of society.

Malaysia's Ministry of Education (MoE) created the Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 for Preschool

and Post-Secondary Education in 2013. This Blueprint has blazed a new path for school-based teaching and learning. As a result, new curricula for preschool, primary, and secondary school were created to meet the educational goals outlined in the Blueprint.

The Blueprint is comprehensive in order to ensure that the ultimate purpose of education is to holistically develop pupils and enable them to reach their full potential. The blueprint outlines five system goals, six student goals, and eleven transformational objectives to facilitate education reform. The 5 Systems Aspirations are the key results that the MoE wishes for the entire education system. These are: 1) ACCESS: ensuring 100% enrolment across all levels from preschool to upper secondary; 2) QUALITY: focusing on achievement in reading, mathematics, and science; 3) EQUITY: equal opportunities for all (urban-rural, socioeconomic, gender, indigenous communities, special needs children); 4) UNITY: encouraging students to embrace diversity; and 5) EFFICIENCY: maximising student outcome within the current national budget.

Malaysia's education philosophy is based on the Philosophy of National Education (FPK), which was implemented in 1996 and serves as the primary guide and pillar of the country's educational system. According to FPK, education is a continuous effort to develop individuals' potential in a comprehensive and integrated manner, aiming to build a healthy and harmonious human being intellectually, spiritually, emotionally, and physically. Thus, FPK has a perspective and understanding of nature that is consistent with the SDGs, particularly its linkage with UNESCO's four pillars of learning plan for the twenty-first century, initially announced in 1996, and the global SDG agenda, 2016-2030.

3. Methodology

In light of the aforementioned traits, demands, and objectives, Makrakis (2006) developed a six-stage capacity-building model to educate academic staff on embedding sustainability in their courses (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on diagnosing the didactic profile of each trainee. Based on the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and is structured in thematic units, or modules that can be further enriched, considering the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The same process of evaluation is continued for the final recipients, the learners through transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages that help to sustain the proper functioning and possible upgrading of the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrakis (2017), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development

The following are the six steps that comprise DeCoRe+:

- i. Diagnosis: Considering a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
- ii. Deconstructing: Critically analysing the operation of personal views and habits of thought, as well as selected curriculum units/modules.
- iii. Constructing entails gathering materials, developing ideas, and generating new meaning (perspectives).
- iv. Reconstruction: The incorporation of newly produced knowledge into the reconstructed frame of reference.
- v. Implementing: Putting the reconstructed curricular unit/module into action, enhanced by service learning.
- vi. Wrapping up: Reflecting on and assessing what has been learnt and changed.

Makrakis's (2023) DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) method has been used to evaluate the new courses during the implementation process. These steps encompass the entire course, from what students bring to class before it begins (Diagnosing) to what they do during the course (Reviewing, reflecting, and explaining) to what they do at the end of the course (Explaining, Assessing, and managing). In a way, the DREAM method is akin to a critical action research process, which not only examines a course but also seeks to identify the necessary changes to improve it. With the teacher's help, the student applies the parts of the DREAM Methodology to create a portfolio that they will return to the teacher at the end of the course. The DREAM Methodology is one of the course requirements.

The teacher must review the students' DREAM portfolios and write a report for the entire class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide the teacher and students with critical information that they can discuss and use to identify ways to improve the course.

Figure 2: The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

4. Result and Discussion

The HBMT3103 Teaching of Elementary Mathematics Part III course is part of the Bachelor of Teaching (Primary Education) Major in Mathematics. The course's inclusion in the programme will help learners acquire foundational knowledge and skills in the learning and teaching of Year 4 mathematics (Malaysia Primary School). It prepares students to become more competent mathematics teachers.

The topics and activities in this course are related to real life such as basic counting, money, time and measurement. This also apply for the four dimensions of sustainability as follows: (i) Environmental Justice related to the topic Measurement Mass and Length, Shape and Space; (ii) Social Justice related to the topic Measurement Mass and Length, Shape and Space; (iii) Economic Justice related to topic Money; and (iv) Cultural Justice related to the topic Time. The key concepts that students need to master through this course are pedagogy, techniques, and approaches to teaching primary mathematics. All three key concepts will be incorporated into appropriate learning activities and subject to assessment.

Various types of knowledge can be promoted through this course module, as follows:

- i. Technical knowledge / instrumental knowledge (sending information): focusing on various strategies and approaches in teaching primary school mathematics.

- ii. Practical knowledge (focuses on a deep understanding of different approaches to transferring knowledge and skills.)
- iii. Emancipatory knowledge (create conditions for empowerment and change towards sustainable societies) by inserting the sustainable value in the teaching processes.

OUM practices an entirely online blended pedagogy to deliver its courses. This pedagogy comprises a fully online face-to-face tutorial conducted via Google Meet; an asynchronous online forum using OUM's own learning management system, MyInspire; and online learning resources. The assessment for this course consists of both course work and a final examination. The course work (60%) includes assignments and online participation. The final examination score is 40%.

During the process of enhancing the course learning materials or the module, based on DeCORE, some SDG elements, the six pillars of learning, and the 10Cs were embedded. The first Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) to be embedded within this course is SDG 4. The goal of SDG 4 is to ensure that everyone has access to high-quality, inclusive education and to promote lifelong learning. From the perspective of teaching and learning, comprehending mathematical concepts and their relationships will serve as a bridge to sustainable development, with a significant impact on lifelong learning.

The content and learning activities of the course are found to be interconnected with the six learning pillars, which are at the core of sustainable development. Learners learn about strategies, approaches, methods, and techniques for teaching and learning mathematics subjects. They also learn to choose, plan and use appropriate strategies and materials in the effective teaching and learning process.

At the end of the course, learners learn to live together sustainably by understanding strategies and approaches to teaching Mathematics, respecting, and being considerate of the diverse backgrounds of their peers. This will lead to respecting others' rights and needs. Additionally, this course encouraged students to learn how to transform themselves and society. They can determine values, develop better attitudes, and create opportunities to have a positive impact on others. The knowledge and skills acquired through this course can be applied to transform oneself and the surrounding communities.

All 10C's elements can be linked to the content in this course. In summary, these elements can be mapped to the course content. In Myinspire, learners communicate with the teacher and other learners to synthesize and transmit ideas in written, oral, and virtual formats. In the online E-Lesson, learners need to think critically to solve the given problem, making decisions and taking appropriate action through learning processes such as conceptualizing, applying,

analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating the gathered information.

5. Conclusion

There are numerous challenges in implementing the SDGs in this course, primarily because the course content cannot be altered by more than 25% due to the university's affiliation with the Malaysian Qualifications Agency (MQA). OUM's learning materials are created using a predefined template. Making modifications to any learning materials, then, necessitates critical analysis to identify where changes are needed, as well as creativity to reorganise so that the new materials may be incorporated cohesively with the current resources. It is of particular importance to acknowledge the various drivers and barriers at the teacher-school-system levels (Othman et al., 2024), as well as issues about the participatory curriculum development process enabled by ICTs, in order to address sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023; Makrakis et al., 2024; Ghazali et al., 2024).

The incorporation of SDGs into this course should raise learners' awareness and understanding of SDGs. As a result of this understanding, people should be more concerned about what is going on in their lives, society, country, and the world. They must understand the significance of the SDGs to ensure global wealth and harmony. Furthermore, by taking this course, learners who are already familiar with the SDGs will be able to improve their comprehension and become more committed to the SDGs. After completing the one-semester course, students should be able to share their knowledge of the SDGs and raise awareness among family members and local communities.

SDGs are already taught in Malaysian schools in disciplines such as science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM). As a result, while many instructors are aware of the SDGs, those not involved in STEM education may be unaware that the SDGs can be integrated across any curriculum. With this awareness, teachers should be motivated to incorporate the SDGs into their courses, thereby increasing awareness and enhancing students' understanding of the SDGs. Furthermore, exposure to the SDGs can catalyze teachers, students, and communities to integrate them into their daily lives.

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Training of Trainers on Sustainability and Development of Participatory Videos

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Abstract

The ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS) project offers training to in-service teachers, who serve as frontliners in implementing sustainability-related curricula in schools. A total of 10 training sessions were conducted, involving 103 in-service teachers trained to be master trainers for their schools later. Based on the module titled “Sustainable Development Goals: Across the Curriculum,” these teachers gained knowledge about sustainability and skills in integrating sustainability into the subjects they taught. Besides learning about sustainability, these teachers must produce a participatory video (PV) that records their teaching, incorporating one or more Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) within the lesson. Not all of these teachers are familiar with PV; therefore, throughout the development of PV, online support is provided through the myOUMeramus platform. According to the survey conducted after the training, it was revealed that most of these teachers are familiar with ICT, utilizing it to record marks and access resources. Even though they lack formal training in ICT, many are willing to use it in the classroom and allow their students to access the internet to search for information.

Keywords: participatory videos, training of trainers, sustainable, In-Set, curriculum

Introduction

The word “sustainable”, meaning “*kelestarian*” in Bahasa Melayu, is still alien to the populace even though Malaysia recognized the Rio Declaration established during the Earth Summit Conference in Rio de Janeiro in 1992, which formed Agenda 21 Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) was embedded within Agenda 21, with Chapter 36 emphasising on education, namely (i) improving primary education, (ii) adaptation of existing education towards sustainable development, (iii) improving the understanding and awareness of the community, and (4) training (Mahat & Idrus, 2016). Locally, the efforts to inculcate awareness of sustainable development are still limited. In 2001, the Ministry of Housing and Local Government Malaysia launched the Local Agenda 21, following the joint declaration agreed upon during the United Nations' Rio Conference in 1992 (GDRC.org, 2022). Consequently, from this effort, the Malaysian government realized that the successful implementation of sustainability requires participation at all levels of society, which calls for the involvement of the Ministry of Education. All learning institutions under this Ministry have to play a crucial role in the implementation of the ESD system via its two blueprints – Malaysia Education Blueprint 2013-2025 (Preschool to Post-secondary Education) (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2013); and Malaysia Education Blueprint 2015-2025 (Higher Education) (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2015). The Malaysia Education Blueprint shares similar

aspirations for learners from preschool, primary, secondary, and higher education systems: access, quality, equity, unity, and efficiency. The emphasis is on balancing knowledge and skills, as well as ethics and morality. The outcome is the holistic development of individual students, which is built around six primary attributes: ethics and spirituality, leadership skills, national identity, language proficiency, thinking skills, and knowledge. This is in tandem with SDG4, “ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.”

Teachers play a pivotal role as frontliners in successfully implementing the new education transformation. The newly transformed curriculum requires new knowledge and diverse teaching methods, which can be gained through In-service training (In-Set), known in the local language as *Latihan Dalam Perkhidmatan Guru (LADAP)*. As stipulated by Ganser (2000), teacher professional development can be formal, such as attending workshops, conferences, mentoring, or informal experiences gained through reading journal publications, watching documentaries related to any academic disciplines, etc. Glatthorn (1995) stated that teacher development is the growth that occurs as the teacher moves through the professional career cycle. LADAP aims to enhance teachers' knowledge, skills and competencies throughout their teaching journey. In-Set courses can be categorized into two types; qualification upgrading courses; and knowledge-skills upgrading courses.

More than a decade ago, teachers' training was under the jurisdiction of the Teacher Education Division (TED), an agency under the Ministry of Education. TED was then responsible for planning and implementing all training for in-service teachers. The State Education Department (SED) Office was responsible for disseminating the training-related information to all schools and selecting teachers to attend the training. Training can be conducted by TED officers themselves or by trainers appointed by TED, who may be from the private sector, depending on the type of training required. The emergence of the Malaysia Education Blueprint decentralized the authority and responsibility for in-service teachers' training. The baton has passed to the school management team led by the school Head or Principal. Organization details and training reports must be submitted to the SED Office for record-keeping purposes. Each year, it is mandatory for every in-service teacher to attend a minimum of 5 days or 30 hours of training. Depending on the needs of teachers, schools, or the availability of training, types of training include workshops, conferences, coaching, mentoring, field visits, research, publications, and professional discourse. However, a teacher may choose to complete a module on the public sector self-learning platform, *E-Pembelajaran Sektor Awam (EPSA)* or conduct a book or journal review. Very often, institutions of higher learning, public or private, will collaborate with schools to provide free training for teachers. Usually, there are two reasons for this win-win situation. First, these higher institutions can fulfil their corporate social responsibility by providing training. Secondly, the collaboration is related to research about teaching and learning at the school level.

The ICTeEfS project

OUM was involved in the ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS) project, which began in 2019. The ICTeEfS project is funded by the European Commission's Erasmus+ Capacity Building Programme in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. Including ICT in teacher education programs and in-service training does not mean ICT is used as a tool or subject within the curriculum. Still, ICT should be a catalyst for change in teaching and learning.

This project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program focusing on Education for Sustainability (EfS) for teachers, educators, trainers and in-service teachers. Consequently, those trained in this program should be able to inculcate EfS within their subjects using innovative teaching methods and pedagogies.

The more specific objectives are to:

- XXI. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning and research with the area of education for sustainability.

Build the capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will enable them to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a comprehensive ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.

Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program, enabled by blended learning, focusing on integrating EfS across school curricula.

Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of EfS in teaching, learning, and curriculum.

Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled EfS to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

As one of the partner universities, OUM is responsible for ensuring the project objectives. However, the primary purpose of this paper is to share OUM's experiences in training in-service teachers to become teacher-trainers at their respective schools, from the planning stage to the actual training, and to discuss the training results.

Training of Teacher-Trainers (ToTT)

Locally, the terminology EfS is not common among education professionals. The term is generally ESD, which connotes a similar meaning to EfS. In the Malaysian education system, ESD begins with students from the upper primary level, ranging from ages 9 to 12 years old, followed by another three years in the lower secondary level, where the subject of environmental education is embedded in geography. However, at the upper secondary level, students are streamed into three main areas: science or arts, vocational, and religious, where geography becomes an elective subject (Balakrishnan, 2021).

According to Mahat et al. (2015), ESD was informally implemented at the school level through the Sustainable School concept in 2005. To encourage the participation of schools, the Sustainable Schools Program Environmental Award (SLAAS) was implemented in the form of a competition to create a school environment that fosters the conservation and preservation of the environment in the aspects of management, curriculum, co-curriculum and continuous green activities to establish a life practice in line with the concept of sustainable development.

Quoting Balakrishnan's (2021) words, "without doubt, ESD in Malaysian schools is not fully optimized." He proposed empowering teachers to be champions of ESD in classrooms. Indeed, teachers' attitudes and knowledge are influential factors in driving ESD within the classroom (Mahat & Idrus, 2016). Thus, teachers need to be trained in sustainability and environmental education; only then can

they effectively teach students the skills, knowledge, values, attitudes, and behaviors related to sustainability (Kamis et al., 2017). Currently, there are few or no professional development courses for in-service teachers focusing specifically on ESD (Balakrishnan, 2021). Thus, the ToTT planned under the ICTeEfS project is timely and appropriate.

The primary purpose of ToTT is to equip teachers with knowledge of SDGs and the most appropriate pedagogical skills to teach sustainability, including hands-on, problem-based role play, although lecturing is the most prevalent teaching method (Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2016; Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2021).

The specific objectives are:

- (i) inculcate awareness and understanding of ESD and SDGs;
- (ii) use of ICT as a pedagogical tool to integrate SDGs within the curriculum;
- (iii) enhance knowledge of the 10Cs, and SDGs, specifically on Sustainable Justice;
- (iv) acquire skills on pedagogies and strategies in the integration of SDGs in teaching;
- (v) sharing case studies on the implementation of ESD and SDGs in Malaysia;
- (vi) the practical inclusion of SDGs across the school curriculum;
- (vii) develop the potential among participants to produce Participatory Videos about the integration of SDGs within the classroom

OUM began planning to train the in-service teachers in 2019. As a university located within the Central Zone of Peninsular Malaysia, OUM was responsible for training teachers from schools in the Federal Territory of Kuala Lumpur and Putra Jaya, as well as the state of Selangor. Meetings were held with the various SED adhering to the procedures of the Ministry of Education. The SED officers provided lists of ICT teachers and/or coordinators in schools as the main focus was to train them. However, any further actions related to training were halted due to the COVID-19 pandemic. At the end of 2021, under the new post-COVID-19 norms, OUM resumed meetings with the SED officers. This time, the officers requested that the training be offered to all in-service teachers regardless of their teaching options, i.e. subjects they teach in schools. With the SED office's approval, brochures describing the training were prepared and then disseminated through the SED official website and OUM's website to all primary and secondary school teachers throughout the states. The list of teachers who applied for this training was sent to the SED office for approval. These teachers are required to obtain a letter of consent from the SED office before attending training.

The face-to-face physical training was held between February and March 2022. The duration of each training session is 5 hours. A total of 10 training sessions at the Erasmus+ computer laboratory at OUM's main campus by all

the ICTeEfS project team members. In compliance with the new norm, training must adhere to the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) stipulated by the Ministry of Health and the Malaysian National Security Council. Recorded training sessions are also made available in *myErasmus—my* platform.

During the training, these teacher-trainers were informed of their roles in this project. They are aware that to receive the certificate as a trainer, they must complete and submit the required deliverables comprising (a) a Lesson Plan, (b) Microsoft PowerPoint, and (c) the Participatory Video (PV).

In tandem with the planning of training sessions, the ICTeEfS team developed the myVLE (my virtual learning environment) platform named *myErasmus.my*. This moodle-based platform contains several features to support online learning. One of the features is the group discussion forum, which is an important means of communication among the teacher-trainers and the training facilitators. Additionally, personal one-on-one communication is available through the chatroom. Also available is the resource-sharing section, where all learning materials, including the module, are uploaded and easily shared. Similarly, an assignment submission section is created to enable the teacher-trainees to submit assignments online. Finally, the project team can track the progress of the teacher-trainers through the progress-tracking button.

Besides *myErasmus* platform, the preparation of learning materials is equally important. The team wrote the teacher training module entitled “*Matlamat Pembangunan Lestari: Merentasi Kurikulum*” or “Sustainable Development Goals: Across the Curriculum”. The module comprises five chapters, each chapter written by a team member. The first chapter, entitled “Education for Sustainable Development”, focuses on introducing the 17 SDGs and ESD. The targeted learning objectives are to (a) explain the goals of SDG, (b) explain what ESD is, (c) differentiate the roles of SDG and ESD, and (d) discuss the opportunities to implement SDG and ESD. The second chapter, entitled “The Main Concepts in Learning SDG”, emphasizes the goals of 21st-century learning, identifying the six education thrusts; introduces the 10Cs and the utilization of ICT as a tool; and discusses the four dimensions of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The third chapter, titled “Pedagogies for ESD”, focuses on three significant aspects: (i) the need for transformative education, (ii) the five main action plans of ESD, and (iii) appropriate teaching strategies for SDG. The fourth chapter presents various case studies related to the SDGs and ESD within the Malaysian education environment. The specific learning outcomes include: (a) explaining the implementation of SDG in Malaysia; (b) explaining the challenges faced during the implementation of SDG in Malaysia; (c) discussing various case studies on the implementation of SDG in Malaysia; and finally (d) discuss case studies on the implementation of ESD in Malaysia. The fifth and final chapter, entitled “Subject-based SDG,” explains the relationships between SDGs and

teaching in schools. At the primary and secondary levels, it also focuses on integrating the SDGs into teaching and learning across various subjects, including science, language, arts, social sciences, humanities, and mathematics. This chapter ends with a discussion on the implications of SDGs on students.

Development of Participatory Video (PV)

To fulfil one of the requirements as a teacher-trainer, the teachers who attended the training must produce a “Participatory Video” (PV). What is a PV? According to Lunch and Lunch (2006), PV is a set of techniques to involve a group or community in shaping and creating their film. The idea behind this is that creating a video is easy and accessible, and it's an excellent way to bring people together to explore issues, voice concerns, or simply be creative and share stories. This process can be highly empowering, enabling a group or community to take action to address their problems and communicate their needs and ideas to decision-makers and/or other relevant groups and communities. As such, PV can be a highly effective tool for engaging and mobilizing marginalized people and helping them implement their forms of sustainable development based on local needs.

White (2003) describes PV as a powerful catalyst for development. PV has the potential to make changes personally, socially, politically and culturally, as it can stimulate critical awareness, which forms the foundation for creativity and communication. “That’s what video power is all about.” (White, 2003, p. 64).

Shaw and Robertson (1997) describe PV as an activity used predominately with disadvantaged or marginalized groups that “utilizes video as a social and community-based tool for individual and group development... to develop their confidence and self-esteem, to encourage them to express themselves creatively, to develop a critical awareness and to provide a means for them to communicate with others.” (p. 11).

The earliest recorded example of participatory video making is perhaps the 1967 work by the people of Fogo Island, Newfoundland, facilitated by Donald Snowden and Colin Low. The filmmakers set out to show that poverty could not simply be reduced to economic deprivation and that factors such as rural isolation and the inability to access information and communication media also needed to be addressed. The Fogo Process began by filming community members’ views and screening them with members of other isolated communities on the island. Thirty-five screenings, attended by a combined audience of 3,000 islanders (approximately 60% of the total population), were used to identify several critical common issues of concern (Roberts & Lunch, 2015).

However, the origins of PV can be traced back to the 1970s with the occurrence of the Community Arts movement, as well as the conscientization process advocated by Freire

(1970) in *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. Additionally, according to Shaw and Robertson (1997), the video’s potential as a tool for social action and development was recognized early in the 1970s by community workers, social workers, and community arts practitioners, leading to the development of a vibrant, independent video sector in the United Kingdom and other countries.

However, the term PV is very alien to the Malaysian populace. The term “video” is more recognizable and understood. For many, whether it is a recording of others or a recording involving themselves, it is still referred to as a “video”. Therefore, to avoid such misunderstandings, a brief explanation of what PV is was given to the teacher-trainees.

A guideline on how to develop the PV was shared with the teacher trainers (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2023). The PV Guideline divides the tasks into three sections. The first section focuses on tasks before or after preparing the Lesson Plan; the second section describes the Video Recording; the third section involves tasks after the PV is completed or the submission of deliverables. The Lesson Plan consists of (a) selecting a topic from one of the current teaching subjects associated with the appropriate SDG and (b) suggesting the appropriate teaching method/strategies and activities. The learning outcome is a Microsoft PowerPoint which should assist the teacher in video shooting. The characteristics of learning outcomes should include: (a) teaching and learning can be conducted asynchronous; (b) through the process of task analysis, and the presentation segment should clearly illustrate the method used; (c) the purpose of the lesson, i.e. SDG integration must be briefly stated; (d) SDGs can be integrated across the curriculum within the classroom and/or during co-curriculum activities; and (e) minimum use of soft wares and hard wares.

The second section outlines how to conduct the video recording using a smart mobile phone. The recording must focus on teaching, and learning activities with a focus on the SDGs implemented in the classroom. Besides, the video recording should illustrate the learning outcomes students have achieved.

The third section describes how the PV can be uploaded to YouTube. The Lesson Plan and Microsoft PowerPoint should be submitted to the *myEramus* platform, along with the link to YouTube. Every teacher-trainer must prepare a PV individually. However, they are also encouraged to work in a group with other teachers in their school.

In addition to the PV Development Guideline, assistance was provided through the online forum within the MyEramus platform. The project team members provide online support and monitoring daily, according to a set schedule.

The Outcome from ToTT

A total of 103 in-service teachers, comprising 31 males and 72 females, attended the training sessions. Most are Malays (89 teachers), followed by 19 Indian teachers and 5 Chinese teachers. Their age ranges from below 30 years old (9 teachers) to above 55 years old (5 teachers), with those between 31 and 45 years old being the largest group (64 teachers). Twenty-five (25) teachers are 46-55 years old. Their ages indicated that most of these teachers have more than five years of teaching experience, with 21 of them having more than 21 years of experience. Only 5 of them have less than five years of experience.

Sixty-one (61) teachers are from the primary school, while 52 teach at the secondary level. A total of 50 teachers teach subjects within the Mathematics and Science field, including General Science, Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics and Biology. In the language field, 39 teachers teach Arabic, Malay, English and Japanese, while 26 teachers teach Computer Science, ICT, Design and Technology, which falls under the field of Technology. Other subjects being taught include History, Geography, Music, Islamic Education, Moral Education, General Studies, early childhood, and Physical education (34 teachers).

Forty-seven (47) teachers admitted they have been using ICTs for 5-10 years, while 31 teachers have more than ten years of experience. However, 25 teachers with less than five years of experience are still new to ICT. Regardless of their experiences in ICT, only 14 teachers are officially appointed as their school ICT Coordinators. The majority, i.e. 80, are not ICT coordinators, with nine teachers as unofficial ICT coordinators.

Although 87 teachers are teaching subjects not related to ICT, about 80% of the teachers admitted they do integrate ICT into their subjects for two reasons: (a) ICT is embedded within the curriculum, and (b) they choose to do so. Also, ICT is taught as a separate subject in some schools. In fact, 22 schools have been using ICT for teaching and learning for more than 11 years, while 51 schools started between 5-10 years ago. The frequency teachers spend using computers in schools ranges from almost every day to once a month; the majority (70 teachers) do the former.

Twenty-one (21) teachers only use the computer a few days a week, with five teachers doing it monthly.

The purposes for using ICT are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Purposes for Teachers to use ICT

Purpose for Using ICT	Number of Teachers	
	No	Yes
1. Record marks using a spreadsheet	6	97
2. Typing examination papers	6	97
3. Finding information and resources on the internet	3	100
4. Accessing resources using online databases	3	100
5. Developing teaching resources	13	90

6. Developing digital content for learner use	9	94
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Although these teachers use ICT regularly, 14 of them have never had any formal ICT-related training. Only 18 teachers had more than 40 hours of training in the past, while 39 teachers had less than 15 hours. The rest had between 16-30 hours of training. However, more than 70% of these teachers never conduct workshops for other teachers in their schools.

All schools in Malaysia are equipped with the internet provided by the Ministry of Education. Consequently, more than 90% of students have access to the internet, although only about 50% have access to personal computers while in school. However, more than 70% of these students are allowed access to portable computers, laptops, netbooks or tablets. According to these teachers, the reasons students are permitted to use ICT in their lessons are depicted in Table 2.

Table 2 Reasons Students Use ICT in Lessons

Reasons for Using ICT	Number of Teachers	
	No	Yes
1. Use of subject-specific software	27	76
2. Prepare for examinations	21	82
3. Use of the internet to research information	2	101
4. Collaborating between classrooms	29	74
5. Using on projects	29	74
6. Solving problems, making decisions or forming opinions	19	84

Issues and Challenges

The most significant challenge was convincing officials from the Ministry of Education, as well as in-service teachers, to commit to this program. Discussions with officials from the Ministry started during the early stage of this project. The first meeting was with the Minister of Education, who gave his blessings. Discussions with Ministry officials follow this, and then further discussions at the SED level. However, the arrival of pandemic Covid19 puts a halt to further collaboration. After more than one year of hiatus, finally, the group had another round of discussions with the SED officers. All of them are new in the office due to the re-shuffling of personnel at the department. Another round of explaining and convincing was conducted before the new group of SED officers agreed to collaborate with the training of in-service teachers as planned.

The next challenge was to schedule the physical training for the in-service teachers. Scheduling must adhere to the conditions stipulated by the SED, such as no training should be conducted on the first and third Saturdays of the month and during school holidays. The schedule was endorsed by the SED officer before training could be conducted.

A total of 250 teacher-trainers were invited to attend the ten physical training sessions, but only 113 were able to attend.

The rest could not attend due to unforeseen circumstances, including infection of COVID-19. However, those unable to participate in the physical workshops are invited to attend the online sessions via Google Meet. News about the online sessions spread among the in-service teachers in other states not involved with the research project, including Kelantan, Kedah, Melaka, Negeri Sembilan, Pahang, Perak, Sabah and Sarawak. Thus, OUM received requests from teachers in these states to attend the online sessions, which they ultimately did. Recorded sessions of training are also made available on the myOUMErasmus platform.

Another issue pertains to the PVs developed by the teacher-trainers. Upon assessment, many PVs lack creativity, specifically in the flow of ideas and video shooting. Some of the ideas of SDGs integration are good but lack impact. This issue is no fault of the teacher-trainers; they are novices, and some even are ignorant of the process of video shooting. To assist these teacher-trainers to be better in PV development, OUM has a plan to conduct two workshops: (a) How to prepare a storyboard and (b) How to create a video using a mobile phone. All teachers trained with OUM will be invited to attend these workshops.

Conclusion

The ICTeEfS project is timely, as teachers have gained knowledge about ESD/SDGs and pedagogical skills for online learning. Consequently, this should facilitate the dissemination of SDG awareness among students, the school community, families, and the broader community. The exposure should raise concerns about making the world a safe and harmonious place. Furthermore, the support of SED officials, as well as the overwhelming interest of in-service teachers in learning more about the SDGs, becomes a catalyst for the ICTeEfS training to continue and become more inclusive.

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SESSION F

Integration of Education for Sustainability in Cereals and Tuber Processing Technology Course

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Abstract

Education must play a crucial role in driving radical transformation. The great challenge of the 21st century for higher education institutions is to train professionals to act in achieving sustainable development goals. Teaching staff are agents of change in promoting the Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum, as well as in transforming sustainable schools. Vocational teacher education plays a crucial role in preparing prospective graduates to become skilled workers who meet the demands of sustainable development needs. Technology for processing cereals and tubers is one of the subjects taught in vocational teacher education in food processing agriculture in Indonesia. After studying these courses, prospective teacher students are expected to have knowledge and skills in processing quality food products based on cereals and tubers. The integration of sustainability education in these courses is one of the efforts to change current food processing practices to be more sustainable by prioritizing the concept of sustainable food processing. Based on student feedback, we found that their academic development was supported by the learning activities they experienced during one semester. How they identify problems based on three dimensions (environmental, social, and economic) supports their literacy with existing data and encourages them to read more reliable and valid literature for the academic development of their knowledge about cereal and tuber processing technology, as well as its relation to SDG values.

Keywords: (Education for Sustainability; Cereals and Tuber Processing Technology)

1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, humanity has been facing the impacts of unsustainable economic development growth driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite the current initiatives for reversing such an unsustainable development process, there is much to be done yet. Education systems at all levels, and especially Higher Education, bear their own responsibility for the sustainability crisis we are facing globally. This is largely due to the fact that consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions who drive society and the economy, as well as shape an unsustainable consumer culture. Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that “the scope and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented,”

Education should play a critical role for a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is closely aligned with Aristotle’s eudaimonic well-being, as contrasted with the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The quest for “sustainability justice”, a concept developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy and culture, is of paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth pointing out that while much has been invested in environmental education in the last decades, it has more reflected in raising positive environmental attitudes, but less concern on environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action does not only reflect education practices but can also be attributed to several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability have shown that lecturing, as expected, is the most prevalent teaching method, while role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, are used at much lower rates (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

A project entitled “Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability” (Makrakis, 2013, 2014) has revealed that one of the great challenges of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of and capable of transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts for teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are the agents for change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016; 2018; Blake et al., 2013) and for turning schools sustainable (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

Vocational teacher education plays an important role in preparing prospective graduates for skilled workers to meet the demands of sustainable development needs (Diep & Harmann, 2016). UNESCO emphasizes that vocational teachers must be educated to be able to encourage behavior change in their future students, and contribute to a sustainable future. One of the competencies that vocational teachers need to have in education for sustainable development is to implement or actively contribute to changes that promote sustainable development within the scope of their own vocational/work field (Chinedu & Mohamed, 2017).

Cereals and tubers processing technology is one of the courses taught in vocational teacher education for agricultural vocational schools for food processing in Indonesia. After studying these courses, prospective teacher students are expected to have knowledge and skills in processing quality food products based on cereals and tubers. The development of food processing today, especially in developed countries, is oriented towards ready-to-eat foods that require high-level processing, require high energy consumption, large resources, and produce large amounts of waste and by-products which leave a huge impact on the environment (Ackar, 2021).

Integration of education for sustainability in cereals and tubers processing technology course is one of the efforts to change the current food processing practice to be more sustainable by promoting the concept of sustainable food processing. The concept is about finding new ways to meet today's food needs without compromising future survival, given changing economic and environmental conditions (Tiwari, Norton & Holden, 2013). There are four ways food processors to reduce their environmental footprint, namely: 1) using eco-friendly packaging; 2) reducing food waste; 3) improving energy and waste efficiency; 4) using sustainable ingredients (Bureau Veritas, 2020).

2. The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental degradation. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian policymakers must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby securing sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While Asian leaders have committed EfS, alongside their concern for implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS), and on the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all

subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in the PCs makes the integration of ICT in the curriculum of teacher education programs and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes about teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims at developing an ICT-enabled capacity-building program to in-service teachers and teacher educators and turn them able to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies orienting to education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

- XXVI. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning and research with the area of education for sustainability.
- XXVII. Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.
- XXVIII. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.
- XXIX. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
- XXX. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia entitled Cereals and Tubers Processing Technology considering six main questions: The **first question is the "What" question**, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The **second and third questions refer to "Why" (justifying the reasons for revision) and "Where" describing the gaps to be filled** in the course through the revision process. The **fourth question is the "how" question, describing the methodologies used for revision and course assessment** during the implementation process. The **fifth question is the "Now What" question, which shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course looks and how it has changed from what it was before**. Lastly, the **sixth**

question is the “So What?” question, which focuses on discussing the challenges encountered while navigating all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the following actions?

The What, Why and Where Questions for Revising (Deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing course through infusing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Case study in Cereals and tubers processing technology)

Cereal and tuber processing technology is one of the courses in the Agro-industrial Technology Education program at Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia. This study program prepares students to become teachers in agricultural vocational schools for food processing. This course aims to provide students with an understanding of cereals and tuber processing technology and to enable them to apply this technology in processing cereals and tuber-based food products, thereby preparing them to become professional product developers. The topics discussed in this module include the characteristics of cereals, tubers, and other raw materials; post-harvest handling of cereals and tubers; and the processing, diversification, and innovation of cereals and tuber-based food products.

This course was chosen as one of the revised courses in the context of the study of ICTeEFS because it aims to increase knowledge and foster student awareness and concern for various issues that arise and are currently faced in life. It is hoped that when students graduate and enter community life, they will possess the competence to anticipate and adapt to the various life roles that are rapidly changing due to advances in science and technology, especially in the development of cereals and tuber-based food processing. Therefore, this course is considered strategic to be one of the courses that need to be changed.

The number of students who took this course in the last year of this study was 35. The learning methods used are: (1) Lecturing, (2) demonstration and simulation, (3) Project Based Learning, and (4) Presentation. Learning evaluation is conducted through tests and project reports.

Initially, this cereals and tuber processing technology course was focused on developing quality cereals & tuber-based food products and profits without including SDG content in it. Then, it was revised by implementing sustainable food processing concepts to promote the achievement of SDGs, for example, goal no.3 (good health and wellbeing), goal no. 12 (responsible consumption), and goal no. 13 (climate action). After that, the learning method focused on handling cases related to SDG issues and product development, enabling students to master the 6 pillars of learning and the 10Cs.

This course is primarily a learning activity connected to the six pillars of learning for sustainable development,

namely: 1) Learning to know. Students are equipped with concepts, theories, principles, and procedures related to food processing technology as a scientific discipline; 2) Learning to be. Every student is seen as an individual with the potential to become a professional food product developer, so they are encouraged to develop their full potential; 3) Learning to do. Students' abilities can be seen from their capability to make innovative food products.; 4) Learning to Live Together. Learning activities are primarily conducted in groups, serving as real-life miniatures that require collaborative work.; 5) Learning to change yourself and the community. Learning activities foster discipline, cultivate a good work ethic, and promote safe and responsible production; 6) Learn to give and share. Practicing learning in groups to create food products trains students to share and exchange knowledge, as well as complete work assignments.

Course content especially in learning is directed so that students have several 21st Century skills, including: 1) Collaboration, for example collaboration in groups to work on assignments from lecturers in making innovative food product projects; 2) Communication, for example discussing with colleagues to complete the project and give a presentation the results of processed food products; 3) Critical thinking, for example evaluating processed food products and comparing with products on the market, providing proposals for improving product quality; 4) Creativity: for example designing the development of functional food products that have more healthy, designing food packaging for those products that are more environmentally friendly; 5) Cross-cultural understanding: for example food processing technology enables the creation of different food products, based on the distinctiveness of the local culture even though from the same raw materials; 6) Connectivity: for example, establishing cooperation with suppliers of raw materials, additives, distributors in processed food production; 7) Build knowledge: for example by creating scientific articles about developing innovative food products.

Prior to the revision, there were gaps, namely (1) the objectives of the courses which were more general not related to efforts to integrate the SDGs, (2) the content of the course material was also general and related to the national curriculum or subjects at school, (3) the initial learning method only developing products without considering the SDGs issue. Based on this gap, the actual SDGs themes were then infused into the course. The topics in this subject and its learning activities are related to real life and are also related to two of the four dimensions of sustainability justice (environmental justice, social justice, economic justice & cultural justice), namely as follows: (1) in the cereals and tuber processing technology, students were introduced to the concept of zero waste in food production to reduce waste so that it can support the environmental justice; (2) in the cereals and tuber processing technology, students were trained to process food products that have the potential to be developed into a business to improve welfare to encourage social justice. In this way, it is hoped that new competencies will be obtained, namely: 1) analyzing the characteristics of cereals and tuber as a potential food commodity and

environmentally friendly; 2) analyzing post-harvest handling of cereals and tuber; 3) analyze sustainable cereals and tuber-based food processing; 4) processing and evaluate food products that implement sustainable food processing concepts; 5) compiling scientific papers on innovation of sustainable cereals & tuber-based food processing technology development.

3. Methodologies

In light of the above-discussed features, needs, and objectives, a six-stage capacity-building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses, advanced by Makrakis (2006), was employed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on diagnosing the didactic profile of each trainee. Based on the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and is structured into thematic units or modules that can be further enriched to meet the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The same evaluation process is continued for the final recipients, the learners, by transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages, helping to sustain the proper functioning and facilitate possible upgrades to the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrakis (2017), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ are as follows.

19. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.
20. **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
21. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
22. **Reconstructing:** Integration of newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
23. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
24. **Finalizing: Reflecting on and evaluating** what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017).

During the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) methodology, as advanced by Makrakis (2019, 2022), has been employed to evaluate revised courses. These processes encompass the entire course, covering what students bring to class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (reviewing, reflecting, and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but, more importantly, to make changes in order to improve it. Through the various parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology (Makrakis, 2023) is part of the course requirements. The instructor must analyse the students' DREAM portfolios, and a report must be prepared for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide essential information that the instructor and students can discuss and use to find ways to improve the course.

Figure 3. The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

4. Results and Discussion

The first step in evaluating the cereal and tuber processing technology course, as applied by the Decore methodology to integrate education for sustainability, is to conduct a diagnosis. At this stage, the student's initial knowledge is diagnosed. These results indicate that our undergraduate students have never taken a course that explicitly integrates education for sustainability and the concept of SDGs. The concept of sustainable food processing is new knowledge for them. However, students are already familiar with the SDG issues in general. They aim to gain a deeper understanding of sustainable food processing and its connection to the implementation of SDG values in the processing of cereals and tubers, within the context of integrating education for sustainability.

The second step is Review/Reflection which takes place when students have completed half of the total courses on cereal and tuber processing technology. During this half period, students had both positive and negative experiences. The positive learning experiences they experienced included reviewing scientific articles from research journals related to the topic of sustainable food processing in cereal and tuber-based food processing and analyzing the latest news related to the development of a sustainable food processing industry (green industry). , collaborated with his friends to design an innovative project for the development of food products based on local cereals and tubers by implementing sustainable food processing. In addition, students realize the importance of using information and communication technology in learning, such as making information media for the socialization of innovative processed food products and also completing the task of reviewing articles based on research journals. They are also stimulated to have an awareness of sustainable issues, think critically, innovate, collaborate, and communicate with their fellow students while attending lectures. As for the negative experiences,

they felt related to the pandemic situation that prevented them from carrying out practicums in campus laboratories.

Third, explain. This condition was explained by students as sometimes experiencing demotivation when completing homework assignments. The difficulty of meeting classmates directly related to the pandemic situation reduces student enthusiasm for activities.

Four, judge. After one semester of lectures, we found that students realized the differences in the cereal and tuber processing technology courses that were implanted with SDG values. They understand the importance of implementing sustainable food processing in the development of quality processed food products that do not harm the environment or mankind's future.

Based on student feedback, we found that their academic development was supported by the learning activities they experienced during one semester. How they identify problems based on three dimensions (environmental, social, & economic) supports them to be literate with existing data and encourages them to read more reliable and valid literature. For the academic development of their knowledge about cereal and tuber processing technology, as well as its relation to SDGs values.

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Embedding Education for Sustainable Development in Higher Education: Case study in Current issues and Seminar on Educational Technology.

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Abstract

Sustainable development education has been evolving in Indonesia for a considerable time. This concept provides an understanding that there is a need for sustainability in caring, understanding, and behavior to protect the environment, society, and economy for survival in the future. However, public awareness is still found to be very low. A lack of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors characterizes it. The educational process is an alternative that can be used to introduce, explore, and implement these values by embedding ESD values, especially in higher education. In the Graphic Media course, at the beginning of the lecture meeting, students' comprehension of ESD was still very low. After being given an understanding through material exposure and video shows, students became more familiar with and explored these issues. To facilitate the learning process of instilling ESD values, the stages involve a diagnostic evaluation, deconstruction, construction, reconstruction, implementation, and a summative evaluation process. Through this process, it is hoped that its understanding will grow from an early age to implementing these ESD values in various activities. Not only in spoken theoretical concept mastery, but also students can apply into their behaviors that can reduce environmental, social, and economic problems.

Keywords: (Education for Sustainable Development; DeCoRe plus methodology; Curricula.)

1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, humanity has been facing the impacts of unsustainable economic development growth driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite the current initiatives aimed at reversing this unsustainable development process, there is still much to be done. Education systems at all levels, and especially Higher Education, bear their own responsibility for the sustainability crisis we are facing globally. This is largely due to the fact that consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions who drive society and the economy, as well as shape an unsustainable consumer culture (Makrakis, 2011). Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that "[t]he scope and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented" (p. 3).

Education should play a critical role for a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is close to Aristotle's eudaimonic wellbeing as contrasted to the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviours and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The quest for "sustainable justice", a concept developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development — environment, society, economy, and culture — is of

paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth pointing out that while much has been invested in environmental education in the last decades, it has more reflected in raising positive environmental attitudes, but less concern on environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability have shown that lecturing, as expected, is the most prevalent teaching method, while role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, are used at much lower rates (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

A project entitled Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013; 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of, and capable of acting in transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts to teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are the agents for change in

promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016;2018; Blake et al., 2013) and for turning schools sustainable (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

The course of Current issues and Seminar on Educational Technology is aimed at providing the students with, i.e., understanding, analyzing and evaluating current issues in the context of Educational Technology. It is considered essential because when they are graduated, at bachelor degree, from this program they will work in the field of the application of the most advanced digital technology to education (Direktorat Akademik UPI, 2021). In this case, every university graduate should be well-prepared to adjust with the rapid change in digital technology and the related-issues (Ali, 2021). In the preparation of the competencies, they should have a broad mind concerning the current issues in this field. Further, concerning the attempts of achieving SDGs 2030, the students also need to have awareness on the importance of every community and nation in the UN member countries to involve in the effort of achieving relevant goals of the SDGs (UNESCO, 2019).

The periodic implementation of ESD starts from DESD (2005-2014), followed by Global Action Program (GAP) of SDGs (2015-2020) and GAP of SDGs engagement (2020-2030). The expected main result of the program, every UN member country achieves the goals and each of their targets of SDGs by 2030 (UNESCO, 2014). Concerning the attempts to achieve the SDGs by 2030 every well-educated human resource should give significant contribution to this attempt (Miller, Hancock, Stricker & Wang, 2021), including those whose expertise are in the field of educational technology. Therefore, the student who is preparing themselves to become an expert should prepare in the importance of acquiring competencies concerning ESD and SDGs, and the course of Current Issues and Seminar on Educational Technology should include the related-issues in its course contents.

2. The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible side-effects of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental damage. Recent climate-related disasters in the region show that Asian policy makers must act now to protect their citizens and mitigate and reverse the impacts of climate change to secure sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While there is commitment of Asian leaders for EfS along with their concern for the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia and Vietnam are among the Asian countries, whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS), and on the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all

subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in the PCs makes the integration of ICT in the curriculum of teacher education programs and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes about teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims at developing an ICT-enabled capacity-building program to in-service teachers and teacher educators and turn them able to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies orienting to education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

1. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning and research with the area of education for sustainability.
2. Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.
3. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.
4. Develop innovative teaching, learning and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning and curriculum.
5. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia entitled the Graphic Media considering six main questions: The **first question is the "What" question**, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The **second question and third questions refer to "Why"** (justifying the reasons for revision) and **"Where"** describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The **fourth question is the "How" question describing the methodologies used for the revision and the course assessment during the implementation process**. The **fifth question is the "Now What" question that shows how the revised and/or updated revision of the course looks**

like, how it has changed from “What” was before. Lastly, the **sixth question is the “So What?” question that focuses on** discussing the challenges met to go through all the preceding processes from the beginning up to now and how has been tackled. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the following actions?

The What, Why and Where Questions for Revising Current issues and Seminar on Educational Technology. The course’s name is Current Issues and Seminar on Educational Technology or *Kapita Selektta dan Seminar Teknologi Pendidikan*. The general objectives of the course are the students, after completing the course, acquire competencies on analyzing current issues related to taking advantages of digital technology for enhancing the quality of education, particularly the quality of teaching-learning process, acquire competencies on finding solution of instructional issues and disseminating the solutions of the issues based on their academic analysis to the stakeholder. This course explores selected current issues in education and educational technology, analyzing and evaluating them to find reasonable alternative solutions. The results of the analysis and evaluation, along with the alternative solutions, should be documented in a paper and presented at a seminar. The alternative issues each group of students may select are: 1) The government policy on *Merdeka Belajar* (MBKM) or freedom of learning; 2) Digital technology trend and its impact on education; and 3) Competencies needed to anticipate challenges of rapid advance in digital technology.

This course was selected for revision as part of the ICTeEfS Revise project study. It is expected that students will develop competencies in anticipating and adapting to the rapid changes in science and technology, particularly in digital technology. Therefore, the course is considered important to be selected as one of those revised in this project.

The number of undergraduate students who undertake this course each year is approximately 76 persons. The teaching-learning engagement typically employs methods such as Problem-based Learning (PBL), Project-based Learning, and seminars. The assessment technique usually uses project report and their performance in the classroom activities and in seminar presentation.

As described above, the original course content does not include the subject matter related to the SDGs. The contents were focused on the themes of: 1) The government policy on *Merdeka Belajar* (MBKM) freedom of learning; 2) Digital technology trend and its impact on education; and 3) Competencies needed to anticipate challenges rapid advance in digital technology.

The contents are not related to the six learning pillars for sustainable development (learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to

transform oneself and society and learning to give and share). The learning activity of this course, to some extent, connected to 6 out of the 10 Cs, namely, communication, collaboration, critical consciousness, critical reflection, co-responsibility, and critical thinking & problem solving. Hence, the learning activity needs to strengthen its connection to the other 4 Cs, which are creativity and innovation, connectivity and networking, cross/intercultural competence, and constructing knowledge.

We recognize that the issues related to SDGs 2030 are crucial to be addressed in the current context of education and educational technology. These are the issues of which the UN and UNESCO encourage every member country to be concerned and engaged. Therefore, the issues were included through the revision of the course and the focus of the course becomes four themes, namely: 1) The government policy on *Merdeka Belajar* (MBKM) or freedom of learning; 2) Digital technology trend and its impact on education; 3) Competencies needed to anticipate challenges rapid advance in digital technology, and; 4) SDGs engagement in the education system.

The teaching-learning engagement relates to six pillars of learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to transform oneself and society and learning to give and share. This means, concerning the theme of ESD and SDGs, the students acquire knowledge on what and why they are. It should also be concerned with how they can participate in engagement with ESD and SDGs (learning to be). What should they do in living together with diverse global and community groups (learning to live together)? What competencies should they have to engage with ESD and SDGs (learning to do). What competencies should they have to transform the community into better living (learning to transform oneself and society)? What should they do to give and share knowledge and information with others (learning to give and share).

As aforementioned, to some extent, the teaching-learning process of the course is connected to 6 Cs through the use of PBL, project-based learning, and seminars. To consider the connection of the teaching-learning to the other four Cs, namely, creativity & innovation, connectivity & networking, cross/inter cultural competence, constructing knowledge, the course will add the project of creating YouTube and blog containing ESD, conducting network and collaboration with school teachers in the implementation of ESD, infusing example of cross/intercultural competence into the content of the YouTube and blog, and conceptualizing their analysis results of ESD and SDGs in their seminar paper (constructing knowledge).

The theme of sustainable development goals (SDGs) initially did not appear in the course contents or course’s themes because it was not considered as one of the essential current issues in educational technology. Actually, the course considered the issues related to government policy on MBKM, the challenges created by progress in digital technology, its impact on job markets, and the competencies

needed. These issues are the trending ones the students considered need to analyze and find their solutions.

The theme related to the SDGs is important for students to develop the relevant competencies, especially from the perspective of the sustainability concept. Therefore, it needs to include this theme into the course so it is one of the current issues the students have to learn, analyze and find the solution in the context of sustainability. It is because every student of all levels of the education systems, including those of the college and university, needs to have relevant competencies concerning sustainability.

There are some relevant issues related to SDGs. The students should possess the relevant competencies, such as SDG 4 quality education, SDG 5 gender equality, SDG 8 decent work and economic growth, and SDG 13 climate action. In line with the government's policy on Merdeka Belajar (MBKM) or freedom of learning and the digital technology trend and its impact on education, SDG number 4 on quality education can be incorporated. The theme of competencies needed to anticipate challenges in the rapid advance in digital technology, SDG number 5 on gender equality, and number 8 on decent work and economic growth can be included. All three SDGs, namely SDG number 4, number 5, number 8, and number 13 can be included in the theme of SDGs engagement in the education system. By infusing the SDGs in the contents or themes of this course the students are expected to acquire competencies connected to the ten Cs through engaging analysis of various issues related to the themes.

3. Methodologies: The How Question

In light of the above discussed features, needs and objectives, a six-stages capacity building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006) was used (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on the diagnosis of the didactic profile of every trainee. On the basis of the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which

merges theory and practice and is structured into thematic units or modules that can be further enriched to meet the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The exact process of evaluation is continued for the final recipients, the learners through transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages, helping to sustain the proper functioning and facilitate possible upgrades to the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrakis (2017), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes.

- 1) **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
- 2) **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
- 3) **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
- 4) **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
- 5) **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
- 6) **Finalising:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017, p.).

For the evaluation of revised courses during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess, and Manage) methodology, advanced by Makrakis (2019, 2022), has been employed. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but, more importantly, to make changes in order to improve it. Through the various parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students' DREAM portfolios must be analysed by the instructor, and a report must be prepared for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide very important information that the instructor and the students could discuss and find ways for improving the course.

Figure 3: The DREAM methodology

4. Results and Discussion

The process of revising the course were using DREAM Method starting from engaging diagnose (D), followed by engaging review (R), explain (E), assess (A), and manage (M). In the diagnose process, the students were asked: Have you ever attended a course on this topic or skill area in the past? Their response to the question are as follows: No. Is 28

and Yes is 55, so the total is 83. In general, the students' responsibilities include analyzing government policy issues related to MBKM, the impact of digital technology progress on education, the competencies required to anticipate the impact of digital technology progress, and finding solutions to the issues.

It is expected that this course will enable students to write an article or academic paper and publish it in a journal. The article or paper could be a solution to the aforementioned issues and capable of applying digital technology to address education-related problems.

During the review process, there are both positive and negative incidents during the first half of the course. Their positive description are as follows: Increase the students' understanding of the current issues related to the hems, understand more about the impact of progress in digital technology, have experience in finding solutions to problems (improve critical thinking, improve creative thinking, more literate in digital technology application, more informative, more responsible. Beside their negative description are as more work load during undertaking this course, the burden of assignment makes bored and stressful because at the same time have to do assignments in the other courses, need more time and working management, the issues formulated in the themes the students should analyses are complicated, and during the pandemic makes more fatigue.

In the explain process, students are completing their assignment it is possible what they are doing is not what is expected by their instructor it is probably due to miscommunication.

In the assess process:

1. Academic development
 - Improve knowledge
 - Capable of analyzing current issues
 - More literate in digital technology application to education
 - Understand more about how to write an academic article or paper
 - Aware more about the importance finding solutions to the current issues.
2. Professional development
 - Skillful in writing academic paper or article
 - More competent in managing learning resource
 - Well prepared in working professionally
 - Skillful of managing time
 - Understand more about the educational technology field.
3. Social development
 - Skillful in cooperative working
 - Having collaborative skill
 - Having more communication skill
 - Awareness of the importance of working together in problem solutions and problems
 - Become more sociable
4. Personal development

- The course encourages the need to improve competencies related to educational technology
- The students become more professional
- Motivate the students to become professional in digital technology application to education.

In the manage process, as it is the course discussing current issues on educational technology, it should be flexible in term of the co discussion on a wider scope of the content or learning material.

Since deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing current issues and seminars on educational technology course processes through the lens of SDGs was not easy, many obstacles were faced from the beginning. Students are confused about the SDGs as they do not yet understand the important meaning of the SDGs in their daily lives, especially since they are an essential element in promoting the achievement of the SDGs in society. Current issues and seminar on educational technology courses objectives are the students, after completing the course, acquire competencies on analyzing current issues related to taking advantages of digital technology for enhancing the quality of education, particularly the quality of teaching-learning process, acquire competencies on finding solution of instructional issues and disseminating the solutions of the issues based on their academic analysis to the stakeholder. Through this course, students are encouraged to understand the SDGs and implement them, enabling them to anticipate an uncertain future. Therefore, revision of courses through DeCoRe+ is inevitable.

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Integration of Education for Sustainability in Dairy Processing Technology Course

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Abstract

Education must play a crucial role in driving radical transformation. The great challenge of the 21st century for higher education institutions is to train professionals to act in achieving sustainable development goals. Teaching staff are agents of change in promoting the Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum, as well as in transforming sustainable schools. Vocational teacher education plays a crucial role in preparing prospective graduates to become skilled workers who meet the demands of sustainable development needs. Dairy processing technology is one of the courses taught in vocational teacher education programs for agricultural vocational schools specializing in food processing in Indonesia. After studying these courses, prospective teacher students are expected to have knowledge and skills in processing quality dairy food products. The integration of sustainability education in these courses is one of the efforts to change current food processing practices to be more sustainable by prioritizing the concept of sustainable food processing. Based on student feedback, we found that their academic development was supported by the learning activities they experienced during one semester. How they identify problems based on three dimensions (environmental, social, and economic) supports their literacy with existing data and encourages them to read more reliable and valid literature for the academic development of their knowledge about dairy processing technology, as well as its relation to SDG values.

Keywords: (Education for Sustainability; Dairy Processing Technology)

1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, humanity has been facing the impacts of unsustainable economic development growth driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite the current initiatives aimed at reversing this unsustainable development process, there is still much to be done. Education systems at all levels, and especially Higher Education, bear their own responsibility for the sustainability crisis we are facing globally. This is largely due to the fact that consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions who drive society and the economy, as well as shape an unsustainable consumer culture (Makrakis, 2011). Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that “the scope and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented”

Education should play a critical role for a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is akin to Aristotle’s eudaimonic well-being, as contrasted with the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The quest for “sustainable justice”, a concept developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development —

environment, society, economy, and culture —is of paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth noting that while significant investments have been made in environmental education over the past few decades, they have primarily focused on fostering positive environmental attitudes rather than increasing concern for environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability have shown that lecturing, as expected, is the most prevalent teaching method, while role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, are used at much lower rates (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

A project entitled Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013; 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of, and capable of acting in transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and

objectives. A similar challenge also accounts to teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are the agents for change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016;2018; Blake et al., 2013) and for turning schools sustainable (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

Vocational teacher education plays a crucial role in preparing prospective graduates for skilled work that meets the demands of sustainable development needs (Diep & Harmann, 2016). UNESCO emphasizes that vocational teachers must be educated to encourage behavior change in their future students and contribute to a sustainable future. One of the competencies that vocational teachers need to possess in education for sustainable development is the ability to implement or actively contribute to changes that promote sustainable development within the scope of their own vocational or work field (Chinedu & Mohamed, 2017).

Dairy processing technology is one of the courses taught in vocational teacher education for agricultural vocational schools for food processing in Indonesia. After studying these courses, prospective teacher students are expected to have knowledge and skills in processing quality dairy food products. The development of food processing today, especially in developed countries, is oriented toward ready-to-eat foods that require high-level processing, high energy consumption, and significant resources, producing large amounts of waste and by-products that have a significant impact on the environment (Ackar, 2021).

The integration of education for sustainability in the dairy processing technology course is one of the efforts to change the current food processing practice to be more sustainable by promoting the concept of sustainable food processing. The concept involves finding new ways to meet today's food needs without compromising future survival, given the changing economic and environmental conditions (Tiwari, Norton, & Holden, 2013). There are four ways food processors to reduce their environmental footprint, namely: 1) using eco-friendly packaging; 2) reducing food waste; 3) improving energy and waste efficiency; 4) using sustainable ingredients (Bureau Veritas, 2020).

2. The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental degradation. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian policymakers must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby securing sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While Asian leaders have made a commitment to EfS, alongside their concern for implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the

challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS) and, on the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.

Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.

Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.

Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.

Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia entitled Dairy Processing Technology considering six main questions: The **first question is the "What" question**, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The **second question and third questions refer to "Why"** (justifying the reasons for revision) and **"Where"** describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The **fourth question is**

the “How” question describing the methodologies used for the revision and the course assessment during the implementation process. The fifth question is the “Now What” question, which shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course looks and how it has changed from what it was before. Lastly, the sixth question is the “So What?” question, which focuses on discussing the challenges encountered while navigating all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the following actions?

The What, Why and Where Questions for Revising (Deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing course through infusing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Case study in Dairy processing technology)

Dairy processing technology is one of the courses in the Study Program of Agro-industrial Technology Education, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia. This study program prepares students to become teachers in agricultural vocational schools for food processing. This course aims to equip students with an understanding of dairy processing technology and to enable them to apply this knowledge in developing dairy food products, ultimately preparing them to become professional product developers. The topics discussed in this module include the characteristics of milk and other raw materials, post-harvest handling of milk as dairy food processing, and diversification and innovation of food products development.

This course was chosen as one of the revised courses in the context of the study of ICTeEFS because it is directed at increasing knowledge, building student awareness and concern for various issues that arise and are currently being faced in life. It is hoped that when students graduate and enter community life, they have the competence to anticipate and adapt to various life roles that are rapidly changing due to advances in science and technology, especially in the development of dairy products. Therefore, this course is considered strategic to be one of the courses that need to be changed.

The number of students who took this course in the last year of this study was 35. The learning methods used are: (1) Lecturing, (2) demonstration and simulation, (3) Project Based Learning, and (4) Presentation. Learning evaluation is conducted through tests and project reports.

Initially, this dairy processing technology course focused on developing high-quality dairy products and generating profits without incorporating Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) content. Then, it was revised by implementing sustainable food processing concepts to promote the achievement of the SDGs, for example, Goal 3 (good health and well-being), Goal 12 (responsible consumption), and Goal 13 (climate action). After that, the learning method was

directed at handling cases of SDGs issues and products development so that students master the 6 pillars of learning and the 10Cs.

This course is primarily a learning activity connected to the six pillars of learning for sustainable development, namely: 1) Learning to know. Students are equipped with concepts, theories, principles, and procedures related to food processing technology as a scientific discipline; 2) Learning to be. Every student is seen as an individual with the potential to become a professional food product developer, so they are encouraged to develop their full potential; 3) Learning to do. Students' abilities can be seen in their capacity to create innovative food products.; 4) Learning to Live Together. Learning activities are primarily conducted in groups, serving as real-life miniatures that require collaborative work.; 5) Learning to change yourself and the community. Learning activities train discipline, have a good work ethic and campaign for good and safe production; 6) Learn to give and share. Practicing learning in making food products in groups trains students to give and share knowledge as well as work assignments.

Course content especially in learning is directed so that students have several 21st Century skills, including: 1) Collaboration, for example collaboration in groups to work on assignments from lecturers in making innovative food product projects; 2) Communication, for example discussing with colleagues to complete the project and give a presentation the results of processed food products; 3) Critical thinking, for example evaluating processed food products and comparing with products on the market, providing proposals for improving product quality; 4) Creativity: for example designing the development of functional food products that have more healthy, designing food packaging for those products that are more environmentally friendly; 5) Cross-cultural understanding: for example food processing technology enables the creation of different food products, based on the distinctiveness of the local culture even though from the same raw materials; 6) Connectivity: for example, establishing cooperation with suppliers of raw materials, additives, distributors in processed food production; 7) Build knowledge: for example by creating scientific articles about developing innovative food products.

Prior to the revision, there were gaps, namely (1) the objectives of the courses which were more general not related to efforts to integrate the SDGs, (2) the content of the course material was also general and related to the national curriculum or subjects at school, (3) the initial learning method only developing products without considering the SDGs issue. Based on this gap, the actual SDGs themes were then infused into the course. The topics in this subject and its learning activities are related to real life and are also related to two of the four dimensions of sustainability justice (environmental justice, social justice, economic justice & cultural justice), namely as follows: (1) in the dairy processing technology, students were introduced to the concept of zero waste in food production to reduce waste so that it can support the environmental justice; (2) in the dairy processing technology, students were trained to process food

products that have the potential to be developed into a business to improve welfare to encourage social justice. In this way, it is hoped that new competencies will be obtained, namely: 1) analyzing the characteristics of milk as a potential food commodity and environmentally friendly; 2) analyzing post-harvest handling of milk; 3) analyze sustainable dairy processing; 4) processing and evaluate food products that implement sustainable food processing concepts; 5) compiling scientific papers on innovation of sustainable dairy processing technology development.

3. Methodologies

In light of the above-discussed features, needs, and objectives, a six-stage capacity building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006) was used (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on diagnosing the didactic profile of each trainee. Based on the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and is structured into thematic units or modules that can be further enriched to meet the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The evaluation process is continued for the final recipients, the learners, by transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages that help to sustain the proper functioning and possible upgrading of the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and most specifically the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction advanced by Makrakis (2017) was applied. The DeCoRe+

(Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ are as follows.

25. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.
26. **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
27. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
28. **Reconstructing:** Integration of newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
29. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
30. **Finalizing: Reflecting on and evaluating** what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017).

During the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess, and Manage) methodology, as advanced by Makrakis (2019, 2022), has been employed to evaluate revised courses. These processes encompass the entire course, covering what students bring to class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (reviewing, reflecting, and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but, more importantly, to make changes in order to improve it. Through the various parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The instructor must analyse the students' DREAM portfolios, and a report must be prepared for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios

will provide essential information that the instructor and students can discuss and use to find ways to improve the course.

Figure 3. The DREAM methodology

4. Results and Discussion

The first step in evaluating the dairy processing technology course, as applied by the Decore methodology, is to conduct a diagnosis. At this stage, the student's initial knowledge is diagnosed. These results indicate that our undergraduate students have never taken a course that explicitly integrates education for sustainability and the concept of SDGs. The concept of sustainable food processing is new knowledge for them. However, students are already familiar with the SDG issues in general. They aim to gain a deeper understanding of sustainable food processing and its connection to the implementation of SDG values in milk processing within the context of integrating education for sustainability.

The second step is Review/Reflection, which occurs when students have completed half of the total courses in dairy processing technology. During this half period, students had both positive and negative experiences. The positive learning experiences they experienced included reviewing scientific articles from research journals related to the topic of sustainable food processing in dairy, analyzing the latest news related to the development of a sustainable food processing industry (green industry), collaborated with his friends to design an innovative project for the development of dairy food products by implementing sustainable food processing. In addition, students recognize the importance of utilizing information and communication technology in learning, such as creating informational media for the socialization of innovative processed food products and completing tasks involving the review of articles from research journals. They are also stimulated to have awareness of sustainable issues, think critically, innovate, collaborate, and communicate with their fellow students while attending lectures. As for the negative experiences,

they felt related to the pandemic situation that prevented them from carrying out practicums in campus laboratories.

Third, explain. Students explained this condition as sometimes experiencing demotivation when completing homework assignments. The difficulty of meeting classmates directly related to the pandemic situation reduces student enthusiasm for activities.

Four, judge. After one semester of lectures, we found that students realized the differences in the dairy processing technology courses that were implanted with SDGs values. They understand the importance of implementing sustainable food processing in the development of quality processed food products that do not harm the environment and the future of mankind.

Based on student feedback, we found that their academic development was supported by the learning activities they experienced during one semester. How they identify problems based on three dimensions (environmental, social, & economic) supports them to be literate with existing data and encourages them to read more reliable and valid literature. For the academic development of their knowledge about dairy processing technology, as well as its relation to the values of the SDGs.

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Embedding Education for Sustainable Development in Higher Education: Case study in Graphic Media Course for Pre-Service Teachers.

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Abstract

Sustainable development education has been evolving in Indonesia for a considerable time. This concept provides an understanding that there is a need for sustainability in caring, understanding, and behavior to protect the environment, society, and economy for survival in the future. However, public awareness is still found to be very low. A lack of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors characterizes it. The educational process is an alternative that can be used to introduce, explore, and implement these values by embedding ESD values, especially in higher education. In the Graphic Media course, at the beginning of the lecture meeting, students' comprehension of ESD was still very low. After being given an understanding through material exposure and video shows, students became more familiar and explored how these issues were addressed. To facilitate the learning process of instilling ESD values, the stages involve a diagnostic evaluation, deconstruction, construction, reconstruction, implementation, and a summative evaluation process. Through this process, it is hoped that understanding of these ESD values will grow from an early age, enabling their implementation in various activities. Not only in spoken theoretical concept mastery, but also students can apply into their behaviors that can reduce environmental, social, and economic problems.

Keywords: (Education for Sustainable Development; DeCoRe plus methodology; Curricula.)

1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, humanity has been facing the impacts of unsustainable economic development growth driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite the current initiatives aimed at reversing this unsustainable development process, there is still much to be done. Education systems at all levels, and especially Higher Education, bear their own responsibility for the sustainability crisis we are facing globally. This is largely because consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions who drive society and economy as well as shape an unsustainable consumers' culture (Makrakis, 2011). Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that "[t]he scope and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented" (p. 3).

Education should play a critical role for a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is close to Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being as contrasted to the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviours and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The quest for "sustainable justice", a concept developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development — environment, society, economy, and culture — is of

paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth noting that, while significant investments have been made in environmental education over the past few decades, they have primarily focused on fostering positive environmental attitudes rather than promoting concern for environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability show that lecturing (as expected) was the most prevalent teaching method, while role play, hands-on-sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, were rated much lower in use (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015; 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

A project entitled Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013; 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of, and capable of acting in transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and

objectives. A similar challenge also accounts to teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are the agents of change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016, 2018; Blake et al., 2013), as well as in transforming schools into sustainable institutions (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

In Indonesia, with various environmental, social, and economic problems that occur, multiple efforts should be made to find different solutions to solve these problems. Government support is needed to handle issues effectively and efficiently (Lyn Parker, 2018). Policies have been carried out to support this. Still, the community's lack of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behavior towards these various problems have resulted in insufficient public attention and awareness of efforts to resolve these problems (Satrianawati, Wen Heng Fu, 2019).

One of the efforts that can be made in the educational process to help provide students with knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors is through the learning process. Given its ESD values cover various aspects of life, the ESD context can be integrated with multiple subjects. The goal is that these values can be appropriately integrated into the learning process. There needs to be a comprehensive analysis through a reorientation of curriculum design, implementation, and clear policies (Estévez & Chalmeta, 2021).

Instilling public awareness and understanding of continuing education is not limited to several courses in specific study programs, especially in the context of education. The importance of inculcating students' understanding of continuing education in various subjects needs to be considered (Chiba et al., 2021). Understanding and skillfully managing and improving global issues that occur in the surrounding environment is a shared concern. Educational technology is a study program that prepares graduates to possess knowledge and skills in the field of educational technology, including the ability to develop learning media. Learning media, as a medium of communication, have considerable potential in planning, developing, and disseminating information about continuing education through various channels of communication and learning (Burbules, Fan, & Repp, 2020). The learning media developed can be attempted to incorporate the values of continuing education (ESD).

Graphic media is one of the subjects that students acquire. This course includes forming basic skills in designing messages through graphics. Initially, this course did not align with ESD values in learning. However, after gathering information and input, this course attempted to make adjustments to the learning process. Changes are implemented through DeCore plus processes, which include diagnostic evaluation, deconstruction, construction, reconstruction, implementation, and summative evaluation (Makrakis, 2017). Through these graphic media design skills, students are expected to be able to promote ESD

values that are integrated with learning materials at both school and non-school levels. *Subsections*

Divide your paper/article into clearly defined and numbered sections numbered 1, 2, 3, etc. If subsections are needed, they should be numbered as 1.1, 1.2, etc. (the abstract, Acknowledgements, and References are not included in section numbering). Use this numbering also for internal cross-referencing: do not just refer to "the text". Any subsection may be given a brief heading. Each heading should appear on its own separate line.

2. The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible side-effects of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental damage. Recent climate-related disasters in the region show that Asian policy makers must act now to protect their citizens and mitigate and reverse the impacts of climate change to secure sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While there is commitment of Asian leaders for EfS along with their concern for the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS) and, on the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in the PCs makes the integration of ICT in the curriculum of teacher education programs and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes about teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims at developing an ICT-enabled capacity-building program to in-service teachers and teacher educators and turn them able to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies orienting to education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

6. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.
7. Build the capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education to enable them to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a

wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers' training program on education for sustainability.

8. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.
9. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
10. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia entitled the Graphic Media considering six main questions: The **first question is the “What” question**, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The **second and third questions refer to “Why” (justifying the reasons for revision) and “Where” describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process**. The **fourth question is the “how” question, describing the methodologies used for revision and course assessment during the implementation process**. The **fifth question is the “Now What” question, which shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course looks and how it has changed from what it was before**. Lastly, the **sixth question is the “So What?” question that focuses on discussing the challenges met to go through all the preceding processes from the beginning up to now and how has been tackled**. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the next actions?

The What, Why and Where Questions for Revising (Deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing course through infusing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Case study in Graphic Media Course)

The Graphic course is one of the core courses in the Educational Technology Study Program. The competency we aim to achieve in this course is for students to understand and create graphic media for educational purposes and beyond. Students collaborate to produce graphic media that can be used not only for the learning process in the class but also for a wide range of educational purposes. The learning content consists of the concept of graphic media, graphic as communication media, types of graphic media, principles of

graphic media, graphic media for instruction and education, designing of graphic media, produce graphic media manually and digitally. The learning process uses project-based learning. Students create graphic media tailored to their learning needs. The content of graphic media that students should develop is related to SDGs issues. The first step is that students analyze related articles to identify problems related to SDG issues. Students also need to interview teachers to find the real problems that occur in the learning process. For example, teachers need graphic media to explain how to decrease plastic trash and how to divide trash into different baskets. Using graphic media, the teacher can demonstrate how to sort trash into different bins. 26 males and 38 females followed the course during the even semester.

Initially, Graphic Media courses focused solely on teaching students how to develop graphic media content. The most important thing is that students know and are able to develop graphic media for any educational purpose without incorporating the SDGs as Graphic Media content. Then, it was revised by incorporating the SDGs as part of the content that will be integrated into various subjects in formal or non-formal education. All the goals of the SDGs can be incorporated into graphic media as long as they align with the instructional objectives of the subject matter in school. After that, the learning method focused on handling cases related to SDG issues and product development, enabling students to master the six pillars of learning and the 10Cs. Through media, we can share, motivate, and educate the audience widely on how to face a changing world wisely and also how to maintain the environment for a sustainable future. Students can incorporate values related to issues that arise in today's life with the SDGs.

This course is primarily a learning activity that is connected with six pillars of learning for sustainable development consists of: (1) **learn to know**: students are equipped with concepts, theories, principles, procedures about graphic media as a tools;(2) **learn to be**. Every student is seen as an individual who has the potential to become a professional graphic media developer, so students are motivated optimally to develop their potential; (3) **learning to do**. The ability of students in graphic media is evident in the capabilities and products they produce. So the media are not only theories but also produce creative works; (4) **learn to live together**. Produce the graphic media makes it easy for people to collaborate, through making of graphic media; It is easy to connect between students even though it is far from living and is blocked by long distances; Students also can share their idea to make a graphic media with sustainability theme; (5) **learning to change yourself and the community**, the indicators of the goals, and the vision of the media content presented, for example when making posters, the theme must teach the community to change, for example "Green Living/Environment" change the community to avoid drugs.; and (6) **learn to give and share**. The product of graphic media that students make will usually be shared with the school to be used by teachers in the learning process.

Course content especially in learning process is directed to 21st Century skills that are: 1) **collaboration**, for example collaboration in groups to work on assignments from teachers in making graphic media; 2) **communication**, for example individually student present an assignment in front of the class and they discuss to solve the problem; student do assignment in groups, while working they communicate each other, and also student collaborate in explaining how to make graphic media using software; 3) **critical thinking**: For example: Comment and answer the question from teacher, from other students. Analyze the article about graphic media; 4) **creativity**: Designing and developing of graphic media need creativity; 5) **cross-cultural understanding**. Students' graphic media that have made can be contain of cross-cultural understanding. The idea Concepts of different cultures in developing graphic media can be one of the creativity part of student. Examples of Sundanese people learning Batak culture from graphic media include **connectivity**. For example, instructing the task of creating media collaboratively using ICT cloud computing, utilizing the internet network for communication, and storing media products on the web to facilitate network access for users. 7) **critical reflection**. For example, the use of online assessment media makes it easy to evaluate and reflect on the success of learning, utilizing tools such as online quizzes, video conferencing, online reflection, and others, as well as fostering **critical consciousness**. **Evaluation** Case studies on graphic media in the community, making study reports, comparative studies of graphic media products, making reflective notes on the graphic media that have been made; 9) **constructing knowledge**. For example, students are asked to write a paper from many literatures. Their paper must contain an analysis, a comparison, an evaluation, and a new statement in their own words.

What is missing and needs to be developed in this course are: 1) combining aspects of Education for Sustainability (EfS) that are not yet explicitly written in the lesson plan also in learning process of graphic media; 2) the need to solve the challenges of the 21st century is more appropriate, and provides indicators that are consistent with 10C; 3) more detailed learning scenarios complemented by 21st and 10C Century Skills; 4) Education for Sustainability (EfS) has not been explicitly integrated into the lecture syllabus, so it is not able to measure learning outcomes; 5) there is still a shortage of graphic media products with the theme Education for Sustainability (EfS).

Prior to the revision, there were gaps focus on (1) the objectives of the courses which were more general not related to efforts to integrate the SDGs, (2) the content of the course material was also general and related to the national curriculum or subjects at school, (3) the initial learning method only developing products without considering the SDGs issue, (4) learning evaluation was used paper and pencil test then will be replaced to paperless test like using google form. Based on this gap, the actual SDGs themes were then infused into the course. The topics in this subject and its learning activities are related to real life and are also related to two of the four dimensions of sustainability justice

(environmental justice, social justice, economic justice & cultural justice).

3. Methodologies: The How Question

In light of the above discussed features, needs and objectives, a six-stages capacity building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006) was used (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on diagnosing the didactic profile of each trainee. Based on the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and is structured into thematic units or modules that can be further enriched to meet the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The evaluation process is continued for the final recipients, the learners, by transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages, helping to sustain the proper functioning and facilitate possible upgrades to the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrakis (2017), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ are as follows.

- 7) **Diagnosing**: Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.

- 8) **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
- 9) **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
- 10) **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
- 11) **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
- 12) **Finalising:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017, p.).

For the revised courses evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2019;2022) has been applied. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process which aims not only assess a course but more importantly to make whatever changes in order to improve it. Through the parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student guided by the course instructor creates a portfolio that he/she has to give back to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students' DREAM portfolios must be analysed from the instructor and prepare a report for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide very important information that the instructor and

the students could discuss and find ways for improving the course.

Figure 3: The DREAM methodology

4. Results and Discussion

First step is diagnosed. This phase is diagnosing previous knowledge on the course. From undergraduate students we find out that all undergraduate students never attended the course on similar topics that given in any courses. Other courses have never explicitly included SDGs values as learning content. So, course content itself is new for undergraduate students. SDGs issues was not familiar to undergraduate students and they were surprised they study this topic in Graphic Media Course. Student's expectation from this course is not just they able to develop graphic media but also they can insert the SDGs issues through media they made and spread out the media widely with SDGs issues.

Second step is Review/Reflect. This process takes place when undergraduate students have completed half of the total lectures of Graphic media courses. During the half period of their course, undergraduate students face positive and negative incidents. Positive incidents that presented by some undergraduate students focus on assignment they made. They learn how to analyze the articles which is related to the topic, the excited how to develop media manually and digitally specially how to integrate SDGs issues into Graphic Media. Various assessments that used in this course interesting and become challenges for some undergraduate students. They think that it is good for them. Skills become other positive impact that accepted by undergraduate students. How they used various technology when they prepare assignment, how they stimulate to aware, to critical, to innovate, to collaborate and to communicate are some thinking skills that was improved during attend to the course. They more aware about their surrounding problems related to topics course. Undergraduate students expected more improved their knowledge about SDGs. Negative Incidents is presented by they didn't expect the SDGs issues

in this course, because the course is not related with the SDGs issues. But finally, they can accept this new experience to improve knowledge and skill. Third, *explain*. This condition explained by undergraduate students that are students sometimes demotivation while do home works. Four, *assess*. After one semester we found that undergraduate students recognize that this course (graphic media) have different learning contents and assignment with other courses.

Figure 4. Concept map draw by undergraduate student on Graphic Media Course.

Based on undergraduate students' feedback, we found that their *academic development*, supported by the learning activities they experienced over one semester, was improved. How they identify problems based on three dimensions (environmental, social, and economic) supports them in literating with existing data and pushes them to read more reliable and valid literature. For academic development, they have knowledge about Graphic Media and SDGs issues.

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The Media Technology Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs.

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Abstract

Sustainable development education has been evolving in Indonesia for a considerable time. This concept provides an understanding that there is a need for sustainability in caring, understanding, and behavior to protect the environment, social and economy for survival in the future. The educational process is an alternative that can be used to introduce, explore, and implement these values by embedding ESD values, especially in higher education. In the Media Technology course, at the beginning of the lecture meeting, students' comprehension of ESD was still very low. After being given an understanding through material exposure and video shows, students became more familiar and explored how these issues were addressed. To facilitate the learning process of instilling ESD values, the stages involve a diagnostic evaluation, deconstruction, construction, reconstruction, implementation, and a summative evaluation process. Through this process, it is hoped that understanding of these ESD values will grow from an early age, enabling their implementation in various activities. Students can apply these concepts to their behaviors, which can help reduce environmental, social, and economic problems.

Keywords: (Education for Sustainable Development; DeCoRe plus methodology; Curricula.)

1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, humanity has faced the impacts of unsustainable economic development driven by profit maximization, resulting in the excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite the current initiatives aimed at reversing this unsustainable development process, there is still much to be done. Education systems at all levels, significantly higher education, bear their responsibility for the sustainability crisis we are facing globally. This is mainly because consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions that drive society and the economy and shape an unsustainable consumer culture (Makrakis 2011). Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that “[t]he scope and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented” (p. 3).

Education should play a crucial role in driving a radical transformation through an alternative development model that emphasizes sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is closely aligned with Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being, as contrasted with the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The quest for "sustainable justice", a concept developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development —environment, society, economy, and culture —is paramount in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth noting that while significant investments have been made in environmental education over the past few

decades, they have primarily focused on fostering positive environmental attitudes rather than increasing concern for ecological action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability have shown that lecturing, as expected, is the most prevalent teaching method, while role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, are used at much lower rates (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

A project entitled "Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability" (Makrakis, 2013, 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of and capable of transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts for teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are the agents of change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016, 2018; Blake et al., 2013), as well as in transforming schools into sustainable institutions (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible side effects of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental damage. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian policymakers must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby securing sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While Asian leaders have made a commitment to EfS, alongside their concern for implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS), and on the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in the PCs makes the integration of ICT in the curriculum of teacher education programs and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims at developing an ICT-enabled capacity-building program to in-service teachers and teacher educators and turn them able to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies orienting to education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning and research with the area of education for sustainability.

Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.

Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.

Develop innovative teaching, learning and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning and curriculum.

Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia entitled Media Technology considering six main questions: The first question is the "What" question, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of undergraduate students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing undergraduate students. The second question and third questions refer to "Why" (justifying the reasons for revision) and "Where" describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The fourth question is the "how" question, describing the methodologies used for revision and course assessment during the implementation process. The fifth question is the "Now What" question, which shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course looks and how it has changed from what it was before. Lastly, the sixth question is the "So What?" question that focuses on discussing the challenges met to go through all the preceding processes from the beginning up to now and how has been tackled. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience and how will it affect the beneficiaries such as undergraduate students and society? What is left for not being done and why and what would be the next actions?

The What, Why and Where Questions for Revising

At first the media technology course only focused on how students develop media that can be used by libraries in the context of providing information services. Prior to the revision, there were two major themes given, media literacy and media development. Each theme is presented to undergraduate students through problem-based learning and project-based learning. As a student of information and library science, mastery of ICT, especially technology-based information management is one of the demands in today's world of librarian professionalism (Wine, 2016), so it is very important to provide a learning experience for students about how to repackage information through the latest media that continues to develop. Then this course was revised by making explicit the value of the SDGs as part of the student learning experience. Meanwhile, the scope of the course has not changed, the content developed cannot be separated from the library area. Libraries as public institutions also have an important role related to the goals of the SDGs (Kosciejew, 2020), therefore the integration of SDGs values in libraries is actually not a new thing. Libraries also have a role in supporting the SDGs. For example, promoting the SDGs agenda, preserving information to ensure sustainable access are examples of real efforts from libraries around the world to contribute to realizing the SDGs agenda (sustainabledevelopment.un.org). Through the media we can convey more massive information related to the SDGs

agenda, preserve information, provide digital literacy services, and so on (Ali, 2021).

Learning methods are also designed to address cases of SDG issues and product development, enabling students to master the 6 pillars of learning and the 10Cs. This course is primarily a learning activity connected to the six pillars of learning for sustainable development, which consist of Learning to know, understanding multimedia technology in general, and being aware of current developments and multimedia trends. Learning to be has extensive knowledge of ICT integration in the field of Multimedia Technology, which is critical for developing multimedia products that are ready to master technology—learning to do so, thereby challenging the flowchart of the application of relevant technology in the development of multimedia products. Learning to live together sustainably fosters collaboration through discussion groups. For example, one group developed a multimedia products project at the library. The project is planned and executed together. Learning to transform oneself and society, providing recommendations to the public regarding the management and development of multimedia products. The media developed is persuasive. As an invitation to pay attention to forest destruction due to excessive use of paper. Learning to give and share, share knowledge and skills in developing multimedia products and for example, implementing a training program for people who need these skills. Unfortunately, the term SDGs was not explicitly introduced to undergraduate students. At first, this course only instilled 4C 21st-century skills, but after being revised, it was given reinforcement by instilling 21st-century skills. Including Critical thinking and problem-solving, for example, analyzing problems and finding the right solution through multimedia product planning in the library. Communication, for example, involves actively engaging with other parties involved in the planning of multimedia products in the library, both individually and institutionally, such as libraries and their librarians. Collaboration, for example, involves actively working with media experts and production houses, as well as museums and other information institutions within the library, which have been developed collaboratively. Creativity and Innovation, for example, being creative in determining ideas and thinking creatively to find something new and different about the project that has been planned. Connectivity and networking, for example, sharing information and media quality that made with practitioners, such as librarians. Critical Consciousness, for example, can be increased through the development of quality multimedia products. Therefore, we need knowledge and good skills in developing multimedia products in order to have a positive impact on human life. Critical Reflection, for example, is a reflection on the multimedia products that already exist in information institutions, as consideration in developing the following multimedia products. Cross/Intercultural competence, for example the media facilitates cross-cultural presence. Coresponsibility, for example the development of multimedia products in the library facilitate the existence of shared responsibilities between developers, media and users / users. Constructing Knowledge, for example, the planning

of multimedia products in the library is in the form of an application model to increase capacity capabilities about EfS.

According to our reflection, the revised media technology course focuses on determining the embedded SDGs theme, especially on goals 4, 16 and 17. This aligns with the target set by the International Federation of Library Associations (sustainabledevelopment.un.org). By incorporating SDGs into the content or theme of this course, students are expected to acquire competencies related to the 10s through interesting analyses of various issues related to these themes. This effort is part of the revision process that aims to support undergraduate students in becoming more familiar with the SDGs. New competencies are also tried to be stimulated in class when students discuss energy issues and goal actions on different scales. "Co-responsibility" is a new competency that is outlined in the learning outcomes of courses. This competency was previously considered unimportant but is now recognized as a crucial one that our undergraduate students must acknowledge. This becomes even more important because our undergraduate students will become future librarians. They will be responsible for our future generations by conserving and providing access to information, supporting the dissemination of information and research to help decision-makers achieve the SDGs, and ensuring access to health and environmental information. In other cases, the Education for Sustainability (EfS) aspect, prior to the revision, was not explicitly stated in the syllabus for the media technology course; the initial learning method only develops products without considering the SDGs. The evaluation of learning using paper-and-pencil tests will then be replaced with paperless media.

2. Methodologies: The How Question

In light of the above-discussed features, needs, and objectives, a six-stage capacity-building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses, advanced by Makrakis (2006), was employed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on the diagnosis of the didactic profile of every trainee. On the basis of the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and structured in thematic units, or modules that can be further enriched, considering the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The same process of evaluation is continued for the final recipients, the learners through transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages, helping to sustain the proper functioning and facilitate possible upgrades to the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrakis (2017), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes.

- 13) **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
- 14) **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
- 15) **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
- 16) **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
- 17) **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
- 18) **Finalising:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017).

For the revised courses evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2019;2022) has been applied. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process which aims not only assess a course but more importantly to make whatever changes in order to improve it. Through the various parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students' DREAM portfolios must be analysed from the instructor and prepare a report for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide very important information that the instructor and the students could discuss and find ways for improving the course.

Figure 3: The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023).

3. Results and Discussion

The DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) methodology, advanced by Makrakis (2023), has been applied to the evaluation of revised courses during the implementation process. These processes cover the entire spectrum of the course, encompassing what students bring to class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing, reflecting, and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but, more importantly, to make changes to improve it. Through the various parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The instructor must analyse the students' DREAM portfolios, and a report must be prepared for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide crucial information that the instructor and students can discuss to find ways to improve the course.

The first step is to diagnose. At this stage, I will review the previous knowledge covered in the course. Based on the diagnosis results, it is evident that our undergraduate students have not taken a course with a similar topic in any of their previous courses. They also lack experience in finding other courses that explicitly incorporate SDG values as learning content. So, the course content itself is new to students. The SDGs are not a foreign issue to undergraduate students. Students respond pretty critically and provide positive feedback. It is hoped that students from this course will not only be able to develop media but also incorporate SDG issues into the media they create and disseminate, thereby making media widely related to SDG issues.

Second, review/reflection. This process occurs when undergraduate students complete half of the total media technology courses. During half of their study period, undergraduate students face both positive and negative incidents. Positive events by some undergraduate students focus on the assignments they make. They learn how to analyze the digital reference sources they choose according to their needs, such as e-journal articles, e-books, YouTube videos, and so on, related to the topic. Students also showed high enthusiasm for how their media designs were linked to the SDGs agenda. The various assessments used in this course become a motivation and challenge for some undergraduate students. They think that this is a new thing, and they are motivated that the courses they take contribute to the SDGs agenda. Skills are another positive impact received by undergraduate students. They are wiser in using technology, starting to reduce paper materials in preparing their media designs, being critical, innovating, collaborating, and communicating are some of the skills that are improved during the course. They are more aware of the problems around them related to the topics that are their

focus. Undergraduate students are expected to expand their knowledge of the SDGs further.

Third, explain. Undergraduate students explained this condition as students sometimes experiencing demotivation when doing homework. Four, asses. After one semester, we found that undergraduate students realized this course (multimedia technology) had different content and learning tasks compared to other courses.

Figure 1. Concept map drawn by an undergraduate student in the Multimedia Technology Course.

Based on feedback from undergraduate students, we found that their academic development improved; this was supported by the learning activities they experienced during one semester. How they identify problems based on three dimensions (environmental, social, and economic) supports their study of the existing data and encourages them to find and research quality literature relevant to the course topic. Case and project investigation activities are a way for them to improve their competence. In addition, undergraduate students responded that collaboration is essential and necessary in this century, and they gained valuable professional development through the multimedia technology course. The dominant social development suggested by undergraduate students is sensitivity to social issues, networking, and effective communication with the community. Undergraduate students not only identify the problem but also try to design the required solution. Personal development suggested by undergraduate students to be developed through this course is motivation to learn, objectivity, curiosity, conscientiousness, flexibility, and adaptability. Suggestions from undergraduate students tend to focus on teaching materials that support independent learning.

Fifth, manage. Undergraduate student feedback on this question focused on efforts to be made to gain meaningful learning from the course, learning integrative content, literacy of technology tools, creativity that needs to be improved (find out more examples, read a book, or discussion) and sensitivity to problems -Social issues related to course content. The learning experience obtained by undergraduate students from this course is very valuable because it becomes their foundation after completing their studies. New things about world problems brought to the course indirectly open their mindset to achieve meaningful

learning. They know their position, pay attention to the problems around them, and try to find solutions creatively.

Discussion- “So What?”

Because the process of deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing the eyes of Media Technology based on the SDGs perspective is not easy, many obstacles were encountered from the start. Different expectations of course content received by undergraduate students during lectures, especially new insights about the SDGs related to their academic goals, are some obstacles that are trying to be seen as challenges for undergraduate students through Media Technology courses. Undergraduate students taking this revised course have recently been included in the final year. Their learning experience in semesters is used to being faced with integrative courses, but they have never found SDGs scores in other courses in previous semesters. Mathematics, science, technology and engineering materials are studied separately.

Through the process of deconstruction, construction and reconstruction of the eyes of Media Technology through the SDGs perspective, of course we want our undergraduate students to be able to use real-world issues related to the themes of education quality (goal 4), peace, justice and strong institutions (goal 16), and partnerships to achieve goals (goal 17). Universities should seek to refocus their mission to adapt to a more comprehensive and meaningful education policy, aligned with the SDGs policy (Ferguson and Roofe, 2020; Menon and Suresh, 2020). Understanding the SDGs allows students to broaden their ideas about issues in the world and how we can respond to the challenges of Mitchell et al., (2020).

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SESSION G

The Biological Processes for Environmental Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

This paper presents the process and results of revising one course at the International University, titled “Biological Processes for Environmental Engineering,” through the lens of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The main criteria used were the six learning pillars, the 10Cs, and sustainability justices. The DREAM methodology, with its six stages, was applied to the course revision. The results of the revision process are presented in this paper, addressing the six main questions: What, Why, Where, How, Now What, and So What. “What” question focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision. The “Why” justifies the reasons for revision, and the “Where” describes the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The “How” question describes the methodologies used for the revision. The “Now What” question illustrates the revised and/or updated version of the course, highlighting its changes from the previous iteration. Lastly, the “So What?” question addressed the challenges encountered in navigating all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. By identifying the remaining gaps in the course syllabus using the DREAM methodology, the course syllabus was revised to clarify the learning outcomes. The missing skills and learning requirements were added, and the assessment method has also been updated to reflect the revised learning outcomes. Through the course outline, which integrates 21st-century skills and training requirements, along with a focus on incorporating information and communication technology into learning activities, learners were equipped with a comprehensive understanding of integrated knowledge and skills. In addition to focusing on personal development, the course also develops skills to live responsibly as a member of the community and society.

Keywords: SDGs, DREAM methodology, 6 learning pillar, 10Cs, syllabus revision

1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, humanity has faced the impacts of unsustainable economic development driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014; Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis). Despite the current initiatives aimed at reversing this unsustainable development process, there is still much to be done. Education systems at all levels, and higher education in particular, bear a significant responsibility for the sustainability crisis we are facing globally. This is mainly because consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions who drive society and the economy, as well as shape an unsustainable consumer culture (Makrakis, 2011). Corcoran and Wals (Corcoran & Wals, 2004) observe that “[t]he scope and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented” (p. 3).

Education should play a critical role for a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is close to Aristotle’s eudaimonic wellbeing as contrasted to the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviours and modes of production and consumption (Kostoulas-Makrakis and Makrakis 2020). The quest for “sustainability justice”, a concept developed by Makrakis (Makrakis 2016, Makrakis 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy and culture, is of paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth noting that while significant investments have been made in environmental education over the past few decades, they have primarily focused on fostering positive environmental attitudes rather than increasing concern for environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability show that lecturing (as expected) was the most prevalent teaching method, while role play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, were rated much lower in use (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis 2015; Makrakis, 2016; Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2021).

A project entitled Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis 2013; Makrakis 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of, and capable of acting in transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts to teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are the agents for change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning and curriculum (Blake and Sterling 2011, Biasutti, De Baz et al.

2016, Biasutti, Makrakis et al. 2018) and for turning schools sustainable (Kadji-Beltran, Zachariou et al. 2013, Zachariou, Kadji-Beltran et al. 2013).

Research of (Kieu, Singer et al. 2016) reported that Vietnam is a country at high risk from the effects of climate change, in addition to the consequences of other environmental pollutions. Integrating sustainable development into education can support the sustainable development of the country. Nguyen (Nguyen 2018) emphasized on the application of the concept of Education for Sustainable Development depending on the specific situation of each developing country. Research with geography teachers in Vietnam on January and February 2016 found that the teachers' perception regarding ESD in Vietnam is different from ESD dimensions proposed by UNESCO when these dimensions do not entirely cover all ideas of the teachers. The results also show that the practical experiences of teachers, training programs for student teachers, the national curriculum, and social perceptions shape views on ESD (Nguyen, 2018).

2. The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental degradation. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian policymakers must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby securing sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While Asian leaders have committed EfS, alongside their concern for implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS). On the other hand, they must capitalize on the potential of such technologies to advance Education for Sustainability for all in-service subject teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Considering all the challenges and shortages outlined in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to utilize innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards Education for Sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education

for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

1. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning and research with the area of education for sustainability.
2. Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.
3. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.
4. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
5. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the International University Vietnam entitled Biological process for Environmental Engineering considering six main questions: The **first question is the "What" question**, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The second and third questions refer to "Why" (justifying the reasons for revision) and "Where" describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The fourth question is the "how" question, describing the methodologies used for revision and course assessment during the implementation process. The fifth question is the "Now What" question, which shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course appears and how it has changed from its previous iteration. Lastly, the sixth question is the "So What?" question, which focuses on discussing the challenges encountered while navigating all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the following actions?

3. The What, Why and Where Questions for Revising The Biological Processes for Environmental Engineering course

3.1 Addressing the “What” question

This course is a required course of the Environmental Engineering program. This was selected as one of two representative courses under this program to be revised for the integration of ICT and SDGs. The number of students attending this course is around 10-15 students per semester. The course was organized in three key contents. Chapter 1 gives general information on the roles of bioprocesses in environmental technology and its applications in practice. Content 2 provides fundamental knowledge on biological processes applied in wastewater treatment and reuse technologies. By going through this content, students will have an overview of why bioprocesses play an important role in biological wastewater reuse and treatment; differences among biological processes used to remove organic materials, to implement nitrification and denitrification, phosphorus conversion; deep understanding on modeling and microbial growth kinetics of suspended growth and attached growth treatment processes; gain knowledge about microbiology of different biological processes and environmental conditions of each. Content 3 provides fundamental knowledge on the reuse and treatment of biological solid waste. Applications of bioprocess in the conversion of biowastes into products such as compost, methane gas, and energy through aerobic and anaerobic digestion processes will be discussed in this chapter. By understanding the background of environmental biotechnology, students can apply their knowledge of biological technology to improve and enhance the efficiency of biological treatment in environmental applications. Laboratory work within this course introduces students to how to apply theoretical knowledge into practice.

Competences to be developed from the course include:

- Understand the fundamentals of biological process and process kinetics
- Understand the biological processes for wastewater and solid waste treatment
- Apply fundamentals and kinetics for design of environmental biological processes and units
- Obtain practical knowledge and skills via field trips and lab work.
- Enhance critical, communication, and problem-solving skills for students

The teaching method combined Classroom activities (Lectures, discussions, presentations) with Self-learning (Reading, homework) and Teamwork (Group assignment). Method of assessment of students: Combination of Assignment, Lab report, Mid-term exam, and Final exam

3.2 Addressing the “Why” question.

With the skill set requirements of the new age and the rapid development of technology, teachers and curriculum developers encounter criticism because the curriculum is outdated or can't meet industry requirements. Additionally, stakeholders involved in curriculum development hold diverse perspectives. Therefore, the challenges lie in teachers being able to impart the necessary skills and prepare students to be workforce-ready upon graduation while also

being responsible citizens of the development process. A systematic investigation of the curriculum gap will highlight the shortcomings in the curriculum, enabling faculty to refine their subject to meet stakeholder expectations. This course outline, prior to revision, has not addressed all six learning pillars, the 10Cs, and sustainability justice. The subject of the course is biological engineering applied to environmental remediation, so the course outline focuses on providing technical knowledge about microbiology and microbial processes in environmental remediation. Technical analytical skills were offered through 1 lab credit. Students were asked to complete a group project on a practical topic of their choice relevant to the local community, thereby enhancing their 10Cs skills, including collaboration, communication, critical thinking, knowledge construction, creativity, and Critical reflection. The subject has addressed learning to know, learning to be, and learning to do within the context of the six learning pillars through its content and teaching methods. Evaluation form and rubrics for assessing construction subject according to criteria related to technical knowledge and assessment of 6 skills through group exercises and classroom discussion. Regarding sustainability justice, the subject has addressed environmental justice by proposing solutions to address environmental pollution for each community-specific pollution problem. However, the course content did not address aspects of social justice, economic justice, and cultural justice. Three of the six learning pillars have not been addressed, including "Learning to Live Together Sustainably," "Learning to Transform Oneself and Society," and "Learning to Give and Share."

In addition, four of the 10Cs were also not addressed in the course outline prior to revision, including Cross-cultural understanding, Connectivity, Critical consciousness, and Co-responsibility. In the pre-revision outline, ICT tools were primarily used as calculation aids for addressing technical issues within the subject content. Therefore, it is necessary to revise the syllabus to meet the requirements of learners in the 21st century and to equip them with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for high-quality human resources in the country. and support the country's sustainable economic development.

3.4. Addressing the “Where” question

The issue of the skill set that students need to be equipped upon graduation is a requirement from employers (Gammie, Gammie et al. 2002). On that basis, all subjects in the training program need to focus on developing a comprehensive set of skills for students, enabling them to practice and develop their own skills during their studies. This course has been assessed for the gaps that still exist in the course outline, with a focus on equipping learners with 21st-century skills, including responsible learning and leveraging ICT tools.

Existing gaps in the course outline were identified, including those related to the six learning pillars, the 10Cs, and the SDGs. For the six learning pillars, gaps were identified in the areas of Learning to Live Together Sustainably, Learning to Transform Oneself and Society, and Learning to

Give and Share. Gaps about the 10Cs in the pre-revision course syllabus include Cross-cultural understanding, Connectivity, Critical consciousness, and Co-responsibility. The gaps in sustainability justice encompass social justice, as well as economic and cultural justice.

3.5. Addressing the “How” question

Methodologies: The How Question

In light of the above-discussed features, needs, and objectives, a six-stage capacity-building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses, advanced by Makrakis (2006), was employed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis ((2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on diagnosing the didactic profile of each trainee. Based on the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and is structured into thematic units, or modules that can be further enriched to meet the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The same evaluation process is continued for the final recipients, the learners, by transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages, helping to sustain the proper functioning and facilitate possible upgrades to the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrak2017) was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six

processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes (Figure 2):

1. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.
2. **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
3. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
4. **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
5. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. **Finalising:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (Makrakis 2017).

For the evaluation of revised courses during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess, and Manage) methodology advanced by Vouzaxakis and Makrakis (2019), Kostoulas-Makrakis and Makrakis (2020), and Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis (2021) has been applied. These processes encompass the entire course, covering what students bring to class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (reviewing, reflecting, and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but, more importantly, to make changes in order to improve it. Through the components of the DREAM Methodology (Figure 3), the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology developed by Makrakis (2023) is part of the course requirements. The

students' DREAM portfolios must be analysed from the instructor and prepare a report for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide very important information that the instructor and the students could discuss and find ways for improving the course.

Figure 3. The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

The syllabus of this course was revised using DeCoRe and DREAM methodology. DeCoRe was applied to analyze and assess the course syllabus and then reconstruct it according to the applied criteria, which include 10Cs, six learning goals, Sustainability justice, ICT, and EfS. DREAM methodology was applied in the reconstruction of the course syllabus.

Filling gaps in the syllabus

Existing gaps in the course outline were identified and filled in the revised course outline, including gaps related to the six learning pillars, 10Cs, and SDG:

6 learning pillars: filling three gaps related to Learning to Live Together Sustainably, Learning to Transform Oneself and Society, and Learning to Give and Share.

- Learning to live together sustainably: Students will learn how to appreciate the human coexistence among the community and how conceptualize the emotional intelligence among their external surroundings also through their in class, lab work and in project exercises and activities
- Learning to transform oneself and society: Transform the understanding and capability for environmental quality protection, suggesting solutions for environmental problems through introspection and visioning towards social actions.
- Learning to give and share: Create opportunities for sharing ideas and experiences for all the social levels and finding the best solutions via the course projects,

each group selecting its own topic aiming to create environmental commitment and ethical self-awareness

Gaps about the 10Cs in the pre-revision course syllabus include Cross-cultural understanding, Connectivity, Critical consciousness, and Co-responsibility. These gaps are addressed in the revised outline as follows:

- Cross-cultural understanding: students will learn how to communicate with different cultures, through interacting with different entities having the same to serve the environment seeking the best ways to apply on ground.
- Co-responsibility: Students will learn to take initiative towards others and towards lifelong environmental well-being addressing less-ego orientation.
- Connectivity: Students will explore the complexities of human and social interactions through various ICT tools, such as connecting the interaction between human activities, societal settings, and their impact on nature. Course project connects theory with practice
- Critical consciousness: Raising the consciousness of students for being active.

The gaps in sustainability justices, including social justice and economic and cultural justice, are addressed in the revised outline as follows:

- **Social justice:** the course will spread the idea of believing that change toward social justice is possible and raise awareness for the social and societal call through the adequate waste water and solid waste treatment systems
- **Economic justice:** Cost-effectiveness will be considered in the design that will affect the large-scale economic paradigm and the socio-economic polarization
- **Cultural justice:** diverting all the cultural norms and values towards sustainable environmental orientation.

4. Results- “Now What?”

The course outline has been revised to clarify the learning outcomes. Missing skills and learning requirements were added, and the assessment method has also been updated to reflect the revised learning outcomes. In the revised syllabus, course content is divided into six modules. The revised outline includes learning activities for each module, detailing the missing skills and learning requirements through these activities. The outline will be revised for the next iteration approximately 1-2 years from now to align with the requirements of the teaching and learning process. The syllabus prior to revision lacked detailed learning activities for each content. Therefore, it was not able to connect with the criteria in the 10Cs, six learning goals, and Sustainability justice. The revised syllabus provided a better connection between the course aim, objectives, and learning activities. The course's content was organized into modules with specific learning activities for each module, which was added into the revised syllabus. The connection of the

learning activities with the 10Cs and the 6 pillars were specified.

The revised syllabus was applied to teach the course at the International for 2 semesters (school years 2020-201 and 2021-2022). Subject assessment using DREAM methodology and e-concept mapping was performed 3 times per semester, at the beginning of the term, midterm, and end of the term. The pre-assessment showed that the student has preliminary knowledge related to the subject topic through related subjects in the previous semester and that the student has set expectations but is limited in their existing knowledge. In the midterm assessment, some students believe that this subject is too computationally intensive, making it difficult to grasp. Some students shared that they had not spent enough time reviewing the subject. Teaching in English also limits students' ability to understand thoroughly. Some said that the teacher communicated the subject matter. The end-of-term assessment, conducted through e-concept mapping, reveals the change in students' understanding compared to the beginning of the semester. The role of subject knowledge in contributing to understanding, employability, and contribution to the SDGs is also more clearly understood by some students. Some students said they have a clearer career orientation after completing the course. Subject assessment using DREAM methodology and E-concept mapping helps teachers understand how curriculum teaching and designed learning activities impact student performance, thereby enabling improvement. teaching process for the next semester.

In the revised syllabus, students will not only learn to know the knowledge on the principles and application of bioprocesses in environmental technology, but also learn to develop a personal, emotional and ethical relationship with the natural world and the cause of environmental pollution problems. Students also *learn to live together sustainably by actively collaborate between group member in lab work and in project exercise, learn to transform the understanding and capability for environmental quality protection, and learning to give and share by creating opportunities for sharing ideas and experiences and finding the best solutions via the course projects.* The linkage of the course content and learning activities with the 10Cs has provided students with the skills to collaborate with other members in groups via course projects and lab work, improving their communication skills by presenting the course project in class and discussing it with other class members. Critical thinking skills will be achieved by selecting a topic for the course project research, defining the problem, and finding a solution to the problem. Students will be assigned to work on designing and monitoring the wastewater treatment system, which will improve their creativity skills. Students also learn about the connections between human activities, societal settings, and their impact on nature. The solution proposed in the course project to address the problem reflects learners' reality and personal values. Students transition from consuming information to constructing knowledge on solutions to environmental pollution problems, utilizing principles of environmental biotechnology. Develop solutions to problems via course

projects and lab work. Students will learn advocating and solving problems for social, environmental, economic and cultural justice; Advancing quality of life and sustainability justice via environmental remediation solution. In addition, ICT tools have been integrated to enable students to learn about problems and find solutions to sustainability issues through websites and online resources.

The subject applying the new outline is taught at IU for 2 semesters (school years 2020-201 and 2021-2022). The DREAM methodology and e-concept mapping were applied to assess course performance three times per semester: at the beginning of the term (pre-assessment), at the midterm (review and reflection), and at the end of the term (assessment). The results of the pre-assessment showed that the student has some preliminary knowledge related to the course's topic and has set expectations but is limited in their existing knowledge. In the review and reflection assessment at the midterm, most students stated that this course provides appropriate knowledge and skills, and the teaching methods are also suitable and understandable for students. However, the content on quantitative calculations of microbial kinetics was relatively complex, requiring advanced calculation skills. End-of-term assessment results showed that students' understanding differed from that at the beginning of the semester. Students understood the application of this topic to their career and their responsibility as environmental engineers in designing a waste treatment system to effectively solve the environmental problem in the community. The role of subject knowledge in contributing to understanding, employability, and contribution to the SDGs is also more clearly understood by some students. The number of students has a clearer career orientation after completing the course. Subject assessment using DREAM methodology and E-concept mapping helps teachers understand how curriculum teaching and designed learning activities impact student performance, thereby enabling improvement. teaching process for the next semester.

5. Discussion- "So What?"

Evaluating and adjusting course outlines requires an understanding of the educational requirements of the 21st century, in which there are many new concepts, such as critical reflection, critical consciousness etc. Through the knowledge and tools acquired from the ICTsEfs project, I was able to better understand these new concepts. Training by experts from Europe has provided a more comprehensive approach, making the course outline revision better oriented. The evaluation using the DREAM method needs to be conducted three times per semester, which also brings pressure in terms of time and workload for both teachers and students. However, the results of the assessment and the students' opinions provide valuable information for adjusting the curriculum and improving the teaching quality of the subject.

Through the course outline, which integrates 21st-century skills and training requirements, along with a focus on incorporating information and communication technology into learning activities, learners were equipped with a comprehensive understanding of integrated knowledge and

skills. In addition to focusing on personal development, the course also develops skills to live responsibly as a member of the community and society.

The course revision process provided an opportunity for me to learn how to develop and revise course outlines, thereby strengthening my teaching skills to achieve the desired course learning outcomes. I have attended many training courses on pedagogy. However, the project's approach to revising the course outline, as described in the methods section, was new and effective for me in revising my course. Lessons I learned from participating in this project include how to generalize concepts and translate them into tools to apply at work. In addition, I find that the criteria in 21st-century education provide a good orientation to integrate into all subjects, not limited to the nature of the subject. When teachers focus on developing knowledge and skill sets for learners, learners will be more responsible for their study and be more responsible to their country and community. In addition, focusing on sustainability through a specific subject will contribute to training a responsible workforce for the future, leading to a more sustainable community development.

What is left out and why, and what would be the following actions?

Education in the 21st century is transitioning from classroom instruction to a project-based model where teachers act as coaches and mentors. Digital technology plays a fundamental role in this educational process. Although the Internet and other digital technologies offer many benefits, they also expose students to some dangers. Teachers should have a good knowledge of related issues such as Cyberbullying, IT security, and identity theft so that they can help students deal with these issues if they arise - and encourage students to become more responsible Web users.

Recognizing the need for computer skills, I see that my computer skills are still limited, although more attention has been paid to ICT integration, but the subject has not really explore the full power of ICT in both teaching and learning. My next actions will be focus on developing more skills in information technology, to be able to make teaching and learning more effective.

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Environmental Impact Assessment Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

This paper presents the process and results for the revision of one course at the International University, entitled “Environmental Impact Assessment,” through the lens of the SDGs. The main criteria used were the six learning pillars, the 10Cs, and sustainability justices. The DREAM methodology, with its six stages, was applied to the course revision. The results of the revision process are presented in this paper, addressing the six main questions: What, Why, Where, How, Now What, and So What. “What” question focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision. The “Why” justifies the reasons for revision, and the “Where” describes the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The “How” question describes the methodologies used for the revision. The “Now What” question shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course looks, highlighting how it has changed from what it was before. Lastly, the “So What?” question addressed the challenges encountered in navigating all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. By identifying the remaining gaps in the course syllabus using the DREAM methodology, the course syllabus was revised to clarify the learning outcomes. The missing skills and learning requirements were added, and the assessment method has also been updated to reflect the revised learning outcomes. Through the course outline, which integrates 21st-century skills and training requirements, along with a focus on incorporating information and communication technology into learning activities, learners were equipped with a comprehensive understanding of integrated knowledge and skills. In addition to focusing on personal development, the course also develops skills to live responsibly as a member of the community and society.

Keywords: SDGs, DREAM methodology, 6 learning pillar, 10Cs, syllabus revision

1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, humanity has been facing the impacts of unsustainable economic development driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite the current initiatives aimed at reversing this unsustainable development process, there is still much to be done. Education systems at all levels, and significantly higher education, bear a significant responsibility for the sustainability crisis we are facing globally. This is largely due to the fact that consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions who drive society and the economy, as well as shape an unsustainable consumer culture (V. Makrakis, 2011). Corcoran and Wals (Corcoran & Wals, 2004) observe that “[t]he scope and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented” (p. 3).

Education should play a critical role for a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is closely aligned with Aristotle’s eudaimonic well-being, as contrasted with the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Kostoulas-Makrakis & Makrakis, 2020). The quest for “sustainability justice”, a concept developed by Makrakis (Makrakis, 2016, 2017b) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture, is of paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth noting that while significant investments have been made in environmental education over the past few decades, they have primarily focused on fostering positive environmental attitudes rather than increasing concern for environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable thinking, being, and living. The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability have shown that lecturing, as expected, is the most prevalent teaching method, while role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, are used at much lower rates (Makrakis, 2016; Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015).

A project entitled Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2013; Makrakis, 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of, and capable of acting in transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts for teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are the agents for change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning and curriculum (Biasutti, De Baz, & Alshawa, 2016; Biasutti, Makrakis, Concina, & Frate, 2018; Blake & Sterling, 2011)

and for turning schools sustainable (Kadji-Beltran, Zachariou, & Stevenson, 2013; Zachariou, Kadji-Beltran, & Manoli, 2013).

Research by Kieu, Singer, and Gannon reported that Vietnam is a country at high risk from the effects of climate change, in addition to the consequences of other environmental pollutions. Integrating sustainable development into education can support the country's sustainable development. (Nguyen 2018) emphasized the application of the concept of Education for Sustainable Development depending on the specific situation of each developing country. Research with geography teachers in Vietnam in January and February 2016 found that the teachers' perception regarding ESD in Vietnam is different from ESD dimensions proposed by UNESCO when these dimensions do not entirely cover all ideas of the teachers. The results also show that practical experiences of the teachers, training programs for student teachers, national curriculum and social perception shape the' views on ESD (Nguyen, 2018).

2. The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible side effects of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental damage. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian policymakers must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby securing sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While Asian leaders have committed EfS, alongside their concern for implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS), and on the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS

project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

- XXXVI. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.
- XXXVII. Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.
- XXXVIII. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.
- XXXIX. Develop innovative teaching, learning and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning and curriculum.
- XL. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the International University Vietnam entitled Environmental Impact Assessment considering six main questions: The **first** question is the “**What**”, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The **second** question and third questions refer to “**Why**” (justifying the reasons for revision) and “**Where**” (describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process). The **fourth** question is the “**how**” question, describing the methodologies used for revision and course assessment during the implementation process. The **fifth** question is the “**Now What**” question, which shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course appears and how it has changed from its previous iteration. Lastly, the **sixth** question is the “**So What?**” question, which focuses on discussing the challenges encountered while navigating all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the following actions?

3. The What, Why and Where Questions for Revising Environmental Impact Assessment Course

3.1 Addressing the “What” question

This course is a required course of the Aquatic Resources Management program. These were selected as the representative courses under this program to be revised for the integration of ICT and SDGs. The number of students attending this course was around 10-15 students per semester. The course aims to equip students with knowledge for conducting environmental impact assessments of developing projects in the field of aquatic resources management so that students can conduct environmental impact assessments according to international regulations and domestic laws, helping society develop sustainably. The course was organized in 3 key content themes: (1) procedure and tools for conducting environmental impact assessment study; (2) law and regulations relevant to the environmental impact assessment study; (3) practical skills in collecting data for EIA and writing EIA report.

Competences to be developed from the course include:

- Understand the role of EIA in supporting sustainable development and minimizing environmental impacts
- Illustrate all steps in the environmental impact assessment process
- Obtain skills and tools to conduct environmental impact assessments
- Enhance students' communication skills, problem-solving and social responsibilities

The teaching method combined Classroom activities (Lectures, discussions, presentations) with Self-learning (Reading, homework) and Teamwork (Group assignment). The method of assessing students comprises an exam, a presentation, a lab and field trip report, and a bonus for discussion. Practical activities account for 30% of the assessment method techniques to ensure the transformation of knowledge on the ground.

3.2 Addressing the “Why” question.

With the skill set requirements of the new age and the rapid development of technology, teachers and curriculum developers encounter criticism because the curriculum is outdated or can't meet industry requirements. Additionally, stakeholders involved in curriculum development hold diverse perspectives. Therefore, the challenges lie in teachers being able to impart the necessary skills and prepare students to be workforce-ready upon graduation while also being responsible citizens of the development process. A systematic investigation of the curriculum gap will highlight the shortcomings in the curriculum, which will help the faculty refine their subject to meet the expectations of stakeholders. (Vinish, Pinto, & D'Souza, 2022).

Through the syllabus deconstruction process, it was found that the course outline did not sufficiently address all six learning pillars, the 10Cs, and sustainability justice. Among the six learning pillars, the subject addresses learning to know, learning to be, and learning to do through its content and teaching methodology. The subject of the course is on

the environmental impact assessment process for the development projects, so the course outline focuses on providing technical knowledge about the assessment process, methods and tools used to assess different types of impacts of the proposed project. At the same time, the course also focuses on providing knowledge of the laws and policies related to environmental impact assessment required by local and national governments, as well as donors. Laboratory analysis skills are offered through 1 lab credit. Practical knowledge is further integrated through one field trip. At the end of the term, students are asked to complete a group project on the environmental impact assessment of a hypothetical development project relevant to the domestic context, thereby enhancing skills in 10Cs, including collaboration, communication, critical thinking, knowledge construction, creativity, and Critical reflection.

Assessment methods and the corresponding rubrics were constructed according to criteria related to technical knowledge and the six skills, utilizing group exercises and classroom discussions. Regarding sustainability justices, the subject has addressed all aspects, including environmental justice, social justice, and economic and cultural justice through assessing the project's impact and proposing solutions to minimize the impact of the project on economic, social, environmental, and cultural perspectives. However, three of the six learning pillars have not been addressed, including Learning to live together sustainably, Learning to transform oneself and society, and Learning to give and share.

In addition, four of the 10Cs were also not addressed in the pre-revision course outline, including Cross-cultural understanding, Connectivity, Critical consciousness, and Co-responsibility. In the course outline prior to revision, ICT tools were primarily used as calculation aids for technical problems within the subject content and to search for information online. Therefore, it is necessary to revise the course syllabus to meet the requirements of learners in the 21st century and to equip them with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to meet the country's high-quality human resource needs. and support the country's sustainable economic development.

3.3. Addressing the “Where” question

The issue of the skill set that students need to be equipped with upon graduation is a requirement from employers (Gammie, Gammie, & Cargill, 2002). Employers are no longer hiring based solely on qualifications, but also on skills, so that people can meet job requirements within their organizations (Harvey, Geall, & Moon, 1997). On that basis, all subjects in the training program need to focus on developing a comprehensive set of skills for students, enabling them to practice and develop their own skills during their studies. This course has been assessed for the gaps that still exist in the course outline, with a focus on equipping learners with 21st-century skills, including responsible learning and leveraging ICT tools.

Existing gaps in the course outline were identified and filled in the revised course outline, including gaps related to the 6 learning pillars, 10Cs, and SDGs.

The syllabus before revision had several questions that were not raised, such as:

- How can learners effectively work in a multicultural and global environment?
- How are different solutions applicable for different nations and cultures?
- How can we create a culture of sharing for students to have responsibility for environmental pollution problems?
- How can students use ICT tools and digital learning (online, Virtual techniques, etc) to mitigate the environmental impact of projects through effective and efficient project assessment methodology?

The other missing from the course content are:

- **Cross-cultural understanding:** The course discusses this area, as EIA standards should be globally searched and analyzed using modern ICT tools that facilitate interconnection across cultural differences.
- **Co-responsibility:** The course primarily discusses the EIA concept, which is considered a tool to serve as an indicator of a sustainable environment, reflecting co-responsibility towards environmental, economic, and social needs.
- **Learning to give and share:** ESD calls for dynamic participation to spread the knowledge considering the externalities, primarily when it is related to segments who do not have voices as a sort of ethical to activist the social justice
- Students should be engaged in the course through more profound, constructive, and appealing cognitive teaching methods to uplift the role of the students through deeper involvement and critical thinking and analysing techniques to generate the maximum benefit from the course's intended outcomes
- Nevertheless, the students should be aware of legalities and political policies in order to have a rounded view of the whole process

In terms of **social justice**:

- Social Impact should include societal measures as well, empowering the co-responsibility towards sustainable cities.

The syllabus prior to revision lacked detailed learning activities for each content. These questions should be taken into consideration in the revised syllabus. The revised syllabus provided a better connection between the course aim, objectives, and learning activities.

3.4. Addressing the “How” question

Methodologies: The How Question

In light of the above-discussed features, needs, and objectives, a six-stage capacity building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006) was used (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis ((2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on diagnosing the didactic profile of each trainee. Based on the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and is structured into thematic units, or modules that can be further enriched to meet the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The evaluation process is continued for the final recipients, the learners, by transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages, helping to sustain the proper functioning and facilitate possible upgrades to the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrakis (V. Makrakis, 2017b), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes (Figure 2):

31. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
32. **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
33. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
34. **Reconstructing:** Integration of newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
35. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
36. **Finalising:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (V. Makrakis, 2017a).

For the revised course evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) methodology, advanced by Makrakis (2023), has been employed. These processes encompass the entire course, covering what students bring to class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (reviewing, reflecting, and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but, more importantly, to make changes in order to improve it. Through the components of the DREAM Methodology (Figure 3), the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The instructor must analyse the students' DREAM portfolios, and a report must be prepared for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide crucial

information that the instructor and students can discuss and use to find ways to improve the course.

Figure 3. The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

The syllabus of this course was revised using DECORE and DREAM methodology. DECORE was applied to analyze and assess the course's syllabus, and reconstruct the syllabus according to the applied criteria, which includes 10Cs, 6 learning goals, Sustainability justice, ICT and EfS. DREAM methodology was applied in reconstruct of course syllabus.

4. Results- "Now What?"

The course outline has been revised. Learning outcomes were thereby clarified. Missing skills and learning requirements have been added. The assessment method has also been updated to reflect the revised learning outcomes. The course content was divided into seven modules. Learning activities were added to each module, detailing the missing skills and learning requirements through these activities. The connection between the course aim, objectives, and learning activities were strengthening. In connection with the criteria in the 10Cs and six learning goals (Makrakis, 2017), Sustainability justice was clarified. Additionally, the integration of ESD and ICT has also been taken into account. Course topics and learning activities related to real life via the practical topic for course project; related to environmental justice with the assessing the environmental impact of project/program and propose mitigation measure for protecting the environment. Social justice was addressed through the social impact assessment, which included societal measures, as well as empowering co-responsibility towards sustainable cities. Economic justice addresses cost structure as a key pillar to maintain the sense of 'doing more for less' and to establish a sustainable economic platform among developed projects. Cultural

justice addresses the elevation of environmental and societal consciousness among diverse cultures, focusing on intercultural integration towards environmental praxis. In addition, ICT tools have also been integrated to support sustainable justice by allowing students to learn about problems and find solutions to sustainability issues using websites and online resources.

The course's content was organized into modules with specific learning activities for each module, which was added into the revised syllabus. With the detailed learning activities, the connections between the learning activities and the 10Cs and the six pillars were specified. In the revised syllabus, the six pillars (learning to know, learning to be, learning to do, learning to live together sustainably, learning to transform oneself and society, and learning to give and share) were better addressed. All topics in the content encompass a range of learning experiences and prompt students to apply their knowledge in out-of-class practices that mirror in-class discussions. The learning activities are designed to encourage self-actualization, integrative thinking and practice, inclusiveness, motivation to make a positive difference, and engagement through class discussions, group work, and field trips. Students will conduct an Environmental Impact analysis of a practical project. Several activities will support them through lecture. In addition, students must develop tangible projects that transform academic knowledge into sustainable actions benefiting community welfare. Students learn to *actively collaborate with group members in lab work and on projects and interact with external surroundings, aiming for peaceful natural ventures through effective mitigation plans. By understanding the impact of the project or program on sustainability, learners will transform their understanding and capability to make the project or program more sustainable. Learners can relate to serving, especially marginalized segments, as they attempt to address their social needs through reflective projects and external activities.*

The linkage of the course content and learning activities with the 10Cs provided students with skills in collaboration, communication, creativity, connectivity, critical reflection, critical consciousness, and constructing knowledge, as well as co-responsibility. Students enhance their collaboration skills by working with other group members on course projects and lab assignments, as well as by collaborating with residents on field trips. Communication skills were enhanced through the assurance of transforming knowledge and ideas via both online and offline communication channels. Learners transition from being passive receivers to active change-makers. Critical thinking skills were developed through selecting a topic for the course project research, defining the problem, and finding a solution to the problem. Creativity and connectivity skills improve by developing new innovative project ideas conducting EIA. Students can connect the interaction between human activities and society settings and its impact on nature. Field trip connect theory with practice. Students improve co-

responsibility and enhancing the sense of social liability for the students towards assessing projects' effectiveness

The subject applying the new outline is taught at IU for 2 semesters (school years 2020-201 and 2021-2022). The DREAM methodology and e-concept mapping were applied to assess course performance three times per semester: at the beginning of the term (pre-assessment), at the midterm (review and reflection), and the end of the term (assessment). The results of the pre-assessment showed that the student has some preliminary knowledge related to the course's topic and has set expectations but is limited in their existing knowledge. In the review and reflection assessment at the midterm, most students stated that this course provides appropriate knowledge and skills, and the teaching methods are also suitable and understandable for students. However, the content of the law and policy is relatively short, but the relevant documents are many. End-of-term assessment results showed that students' understanding differed from that at the beginning of the semester. The student understood the application of this topic to their career, and their responsibility toward implementing the project's sound design will contribute to the sustainable development of the country and community. The role of subject knowledge in contributing to understanding, employability, and contribution to the SDGs is also more clearly understood by some students. The number of students has a more precise career orientation after completing the course. Subject assessment using DREAM methodology and E-concept mapping helps teachers understand how curriculum teaching and designed learning activities impact student performance, thereby enabling improvement in the teaching process for the next semester.

5. Discussion- "So What?"

Evaluating and adjusting course outlines requires an understanding of the educational requirements of the 21st century, which encompasses numerous new concepts, including critical reflection and critical consciousness. Through the knowledge and tools acquired from the ICTsEfs project, the lecturer was able to better understand these new concepts. Training by experts from Europe has provided a more comprehensive approach, making the course outline revision better oriented. The evaluation using the DREAM method needs to be conducted three times each semester, which also brings pressure in terms of time and workload for both teachers and students. However, the results of the assessment and the students' opinions provide valuable information for adjusting the curriculum and improving the teaching quality of the subject.

Through the course outline, which integrates 21st-century skills and training requirements, along with a focus on incorporating information and communication technology into learning activities, learners were equipped with a comprehensive understanding of integrated knowledge and skills. In addition to focusing on personal development, the course also develops skills to live responsibly as a member of the community and society.

The course revision process provided the lecturer with an opportunity to develop and refine course outlines, thereby strengthening their teaching skills and achieving the desired course learning outcomes. I have attended many training courses on pedagogy. However, the project's approach to revising the course outline, as described in the methods section, was new and effective for me in revising my course. Lessons I learned from participating in this project include how to generalize concepts and translate them into tools to apply at work. In addition, I find that the criteria in 21st-century education provide a good orientation to integrate into all subjects, not limited to the nature of the subject. When teachers focus on developing knowledge and skill sets for learners, learners will be more responsible for their own study and be more responsible to their country and community. In addition, focusing on sustainability through a specific subject will contribute to training a responsible workforce for the future, leading to a more sustainable community development.

What is left out and why, and what would be the following actions?

Education in the 21st century is transitioning from classroom instruction to a project-based model where teachers act as coaches and mentors. Digital technology plays a fundamental role in this educational process. Although the Internet and other digital technologies offer many benefits, they also expose students to some dangers. Teachers should have a good understanding of related issues, such as Cyberbullying, IT security, and identity theft, so that they can help students address these issues if they arise and encourage them to become more responsible Web users (ICS, 2022).

Recognizing the need for computer skills, I acknowledge that my current computer skills are still limited, despite increased attention to ICT integration. However, the subject has not yet fully explored the potential of ICT in both teaching and learning. My next actions will focus on developing additional skills in information technology to enhance the effectiveness of teaching and learning.

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Hydraulic Structures Course for Civil Engineering: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

This paper presents the process and results for revising the course entitled “Hydraulic Structures” of the Department of Civil Engineering at the International University through the lens of the SDGs. The main criteria used were the six learning pillars, the 10Cs, and sustainability justices. The DREAM methodology, with its six stages, was applied to the course revision. The results of the revision process are presented in this paper, addressing the six main questions: What, Why, Where, How, Now What, and So What. “What” question focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision. The “Why” justifies the reasons for revision, and the “Where” describes the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The “How” question describes the methodologies used for the revision. The “Now What” question shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course looks, highlighting how it has changed from what it was before. Lastly, the “So What?” question addressed the challenges encountered in navigating all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. By identifying the remaining gaps in the course syllabus using the DREAM methodology, the course syllabus was revised to clarify the learning outcomes. For instance, a new module, Environmental Impact Assessment, was added. Moreover, some ICT tools were introduced and practiced to increase the adaptive capacity of students to a changing society in the future (such as HEC-RAS and CMap). Furthermore, teaching methods shifted from lecturer-centered to student-centered, providing students with more opportunities to practice and develop their skills (10Cs).

Keywords: SDGs, DREAM methodology, six learning pillars, 10Cs, Hydraulic structures syllabus revision

1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, humanity has faced the impacts of unsustainable economic development driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014; Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2021), particularly water resources. Despite the current initiatives aimed at reversing this unsustainable development process, there is still much to be done. Education systems at all levels, and significantly higher education, bear a significant responsibility for the sustainability crisis we are facing globally. This is mainly because consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions who drive society and the economy, as well as shape an unsustainable consumer culture (Makrakis, 2011). Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that “[t]he scope and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented” (p. 3).

Education should play a critical role for a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is akin to Aristotle’s eudemonic well-being, as opposed to the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Kostoulas-Makrakis & Makrakis, 2020). The quest for “sustainability justice”, a concept developed by Makrakis (2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture, is of paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth noting that while considerable investment has been made in education for water resources engineering and civil engineering over the past few decades, it has more

reflected a shift toward fostering positive environmental attitudes rather than a more significant concern for protective actions. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into actions needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and actions does not only reflect education practices but can also be attributed to several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability show that lecturing (as expected) was the most prevalent teaching method, while role play, hands-on-sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, were rated much lower in use (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015; Makrakis, 2016; Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2021).

A project entitled Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2013; Makrakis, 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of, and capable of acting in transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts for teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are the agents for change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning and curriculum (Blake and Sterling 2011, Biasutti, De Baz et al. 2016, Biasutti, Makrakis et al. 2018) and for turning schools sustainable (Kadji-Beltran, Zachariou et al. 2013, Zachariou, Kadji-Beltran et al. 2013).

Research reported that Vietnam is a country at high risk from the effects of climate change, in addition to the consequences

of other environmental pollutions. Integrating sustainable development into education can support the country's sustainable development. Nguyen (2018) emphasized the application of the concept of Education for Sustainable Development, tailored to the specific situation of each developing country. Research conducted with geography teachers in Vietnam in January and February 2016 revealed that the teachers' perceptions regarding ESD in Vietnam differ from the ESD dimensions proposed by UNESCO, as these dimensions do not entirely encompass all the ideas of the teachers. The results also show that practical experiences of the teachers, training programs for student teachers, national curriculum and social perception shape the views on ESD (Nguyen 2018).

2. The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental degradation. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian policymakers must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby securing sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While Asian leaders have made a commitment to EfS, alongside their concern for implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS) and, on the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

- XLI. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning and research with the area of education for sustainability.
- XLII. Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to

the development, implementation, and evaluation of a broad ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.

- XLIII. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.
- XLIV. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
- XLV. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the following actions?

3. The What, Why, and Where Questions for Revising The Hydraulic Structures course

3.1 Addressing the "What" question

This course is a nominated elective one designed for fourth year students of Department of Civil engineering with 3 credits. Before taking this course, students are required to complete two foundational courses: Fluid Mechanics and Hydrology-Hydraulics. Typically, it is held once a year, with 15-20 students in attendance. This course aims to provide technical procedures and practices for designing hydraulic structures, with a focus on water resources engineering and structures for disaster prevention related to water. The key content themes of the old course are: (i) introduction and classification of hydraulic structures; (ii) detailed hydraulic design of structures in the storage water system, including reservoir, dam, spillways, and energy dissipater; (iii) Introduction to coastal engineering and management. Besides lectures, students are provided a field trip to visit real structures. Teaching methods include Classroom activities (Lectures, discussions, and presentations), self-learning (Reading materials and homework), Teamwork (Group assignments and a course project), and a field trip. The method of student assessment is a combination of examinations (mid-term and final), assignments, reports, presentations of course projects, field trip reports, students' attendance and contributions to class discussions, and quizzes.

3.2 Addressing the "Why" question.

It was recognized that although water resources projects have a strong impact on the natural and social environment,

the existing content of this course primarily focuses on knowledge related to designing or proposing solutions, with less emphasis on technical aspects. Therefore, it is necessary to revise the content so that the concepts of SDGs, the six pillars of learning, and the 10Cs of 21st-century education can be integrated. With the skill set requirements of the new age and the rapid development of technology, teachers and curriculum developers often face criticism because their curriculum is outdated or fails to meet industry standards. Additionally, stakeholders involved in curriculum development hold diverse perspectives. Therefore, the challenges lie in teachers being able to impart the necessary skills and prepare students to be workforce-ready upon graduation while also being responsible citizens of the development process. A systematic investigation of the curriculum gap will highlight the shortcomings in the curriculum, enabling faculty to tailor their subject to meet stakeholder expectations (Vinish, Pinto, & D'Souza, 2022). It was found that the main content of the course is needed to integrate environmental and socio-economical aspects into the design and planning process of water resources development projects. On the other hand, the concept of sustainability is integrated into the course content. Moreover, the old one included some traditional soft skills (4Cs), but it did not cover all 10 Cs of critical 21st-century skills, such as constructing knowledge, co-responsibility, cross-cultural competence, critical reflection, critical consciousness, connectivity, and networking. Furthermore, the syllabus prior to the revision lacked detailed learning activities to encourage students to participate in the lectures. Additionally, only AutoCAD software was requested for students to design their structures in the course project. This software is valuable and necessary for students in real-world professional activities; however, it is still insufficient for them to adapt to the dramatic development of the 4.0 industrial revolution after graduation. The current syllabus needs to be improved to meet the criteria in the 10Cs, the 6 learning goals, and sustainability and justice. As a result, the revised syllabus provided a more transparent connection between course objectives, learning outcomes, content, and activities.

3.4. Addressing the “Where” question

The issue of the skill set that students need to be equipped with upon graduation is a requirement from employers (Gammie, Gammie, & Cargill, 2002). Employers are no longer hiring based solely on qualifications, but also on skills, so that people can meet job requirements within their organizations (Harvey, Geall, & Moon, 1997). On that basis, all subjects in the training program need to focus on developing a comprehensive set of skills for students, enabling them to practice and develop their skills during their studies. This course has been assessed for the gaps that still exist in the course outline, with a focus on equipping learners with 21st-century skills, including responsible learning and leveraging ICT tools.

Based on the above analysis, the gaps in the existing syllabus were filled. Firstly, student learning outcomes were revised; which are to:

- (1) Recognize the different types of hydraulic structures and understand their purpose and function in the real world of water engineering.
- (2) Integrate the studied fundamental knowledge and skills (e.g., fluid mechanics, hydraulics and hydrology, drawing, and so on) to select and propose the structural measures for sustainable water resources development projects.
- (3) Design some common hydraulic structures in a sustainable approach, harmonizing technical, social, economic, and environmental criteria.
- (4) Broaden skills in teamwork, communication, and planning through a small project.

Secondly, the main content is restructured; the first three modules of the old syllabus were upgraded with the knowledge related to SDGs. The goals of this revision are to improve the understanding of student about the concept of SDGS and sustainable water resource development in particular; and to be practiced how to integrate sustainable approach into principal knowledge, and existing standards or codes for selecting, analyzing and designing of some common hydraulic structures (e.g., reservoirs, dams) and other water engineering projects (e.g., sustainable urban drainage system). Moreover, a new module, Introduction to EIA, was added to the revised syllabus. The key content of this module includes: (i) an introduction to existing national laws and regulations related to Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA); (ii) the process and methodologies for implementing EIA for infrastructure projects.

Furthermore, each module is described in detail, including key concepts, overview, aim, learning outcomes, units, readings, and activities. These activities are specifically designed to achieve the criteria of the 10Cs, six learning goals, and sustainability and justice. For example, students are taught to develop their professional skills as civil engineers, as well as their emotional and ethical relationships with the natural world and the water environment in particular. They are also *educated to apply various skills, such as living sustainably, sharing ideas, critical thinking, and resolving conflicts, through active collaboration with group members in homework and course projects.*

In addition, they can improve their communication skills by presenting the course project in class, discussing with other class members, and discussing with the company during field trips. Besides that, critical thinking and problem-solving skills will be developed through proposing a solution for the water storage system in the course project research, where students also learn about the connectivity between human activities, societal settings, and their impact on nature. The solution proposed in the course project to address the problem reflects learners' reality and personal values. Students will learn to advocate for and solve problems related to social, environmental, economic, and cultural justice, advancing quality of life and sustainability through solutions that mitigate environmental impact, as

assessed in the assigned project. Finally, some ICT tools (e.g., HEC-Ras, Cmap... software) have also been given during the course, which can support students to analyze and propose sustainable solutions in water engineering projects.

3.5. Addressing the “How” question

Methodologies: The How Question

In light of the above discussed features, needs and objectives, a six-stages capacity building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006) was used (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on the diagnosis of the didactic profile of every trainee. On the basis of the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and structured in thematic units, or modules that can be further enriched, considering the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The exact process of evaluation is continued for the final recipients, the learners, through transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages, helping to sustain the proper functioning and facilitate possible upgrades to the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrakis (Makrakis, 2017), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum

development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes (Figure 2):

37. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
38. **Deconstructing:** Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
39. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
40. **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
41. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
42. **Finalising:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. (Makrakis 2017).

For the revised courses evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by (Makrakis, 2023. Makrakis and Kostoulas-Makrakis 2021) has been applied. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but, more importantly, to make changes in order to improve it. Through the components of the DREAM Methodology (Figure 3), the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements (Makrakis, 2023). The instructor must analyse the students' DREAM portfolios, and a report must be prepared for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide crucial information that the instructor and students can discuss and use to find ways to improve the course.

Figure 3. The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

The syllabus of this course was revised using the DECORE and DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023). DECORE was applied to analyze and assess the course syllabus and then reconstruct it according to the applied criteria, which include 10Cs, 6 learning goals, Sustainability, justice, ICT, and EfS. DREAM methodology was applied in the reconstruction of the course syllabus.

4. Results- “Now What?”

In this revised version, the course learning outcomes have been clarified, and missing skills and learning requirements have been added. The course content was organized into four modules, with specific learning activities added to each. The connection between the learning activities and the 10Cs, as well as the six pillars, was explicitly implemented. In detail, these modules were: (i) General introduction on hydraulic structures; (ii) Principle design of a centralized water storage system; (iii) Introduction to coastal engineering and management; (iv) introduction to Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), a new module added. In addition, some ICT tools were introduced and practiced to increase the adaptive capacity of students to changing society in the future, such as Geoslope, HEC-RAS, and CMap. Moreover, teaching methods shifted from lecturer-centered to student-centered, providing students with more opportunities to practice and develop their skills (10Cs).

All topics in the content reflect all sorts of learning and trigger the student to construct out-of-class practices mirroring in-class discussions. The learning activities are designed to encourage self-actualization, integrative thinking and practice, inclusiveness, motivation to make a positive difference, and engagement through class discussions, group work, and field trips. Additionally,

students were asked to conduct an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) analysis of a real-world water engineering project as homework. This activity can enhance the capacities of students to work independently and solve real problems from sustainable perspectives in the field of water engineering. Moreover, in this course, a group project is assigned on the topic of designing a multi-purpose reservoir system. The project's outcomes are measured through reports, drawings, and oral presentations. As a result, students must work in teams to integrate academic knowledge, social demands, and sustainable actions into their project solutions. Obviously, through these activities, students are able to practice the six skills, six pillars, and 10Cs (Makrakis, 2017). For instance, students learn how to deliver water resource solutions that promote social welfare in a sustainable manner through a project. *By deeply understanding the interaction between the natural environment and dependent human communities, they can learn to be ethical and responsive civil engineers by conducting effective mitigation plans or EIA reports when developing a water engineering project.*

Besides, students learned to actively collaborate with group members and local residents during field trips and *project work*. Communication and sharing skills were enhanced by ensuring the transformation of knowledge and ideas through written reports, graphical drawings, and oral presentations. Learners also transitioned from being passive receivers to active change-makers. Critical thinking skills are developed through the implementation of course project research, individual homework that involves finding solutions to problems, and answering and questioning during class discussions and project presentations. Creativity and connectivity skills improve when proposing innovative ideas or solutions during EIA analysis and course projects. Specifically, after fulfilling these two activities, students can connect the interaction between civil engineering aspects, social-economic demands, and impacts to the nature of water development projects. Students improve their co-responsibility and enhance their sense of social liability towards assessing the effectiveness of water projects.

A new syllabus was introduced at IU in the 2nd semester of the 2020-2021 academic year and is being taught in the 2nd semester of the 2021-2022 academic year. Subject assessment using the DREAM methodology and e-concept mapping was performed three times per semester: at the beginning, midterm, and end of the term. The data from the first-semester assessment showed that students have preliminary knowledge related to the subject topic through related subjects in the previous semester; however, the expectations filled are limited by their existing knowledge, with less consideration given to SDGs or some new skills of the 10Cs. In the midterm assessment, some students stated that this subject covers a lot of new knowledge and has a wide scope of study; therefore, their absorption is also limited. Moreover, some students already presented that they have not spent enough time to study or review the knowledge. Learning in English also limits students' ability

to completely understand the lecture. Even so, around ten percentage of students thought that the content of the course is interesting and satisfying their expectation. Through e-concept mapping, the result of the end term assessment showed that, students' understanding has improved compared to the beginning of the semester. The role of subject knowledge in contributing to understanding, employability, and contribution to the SDGs is also more clearly understood by some students. The number of students has a clearer career orientation after completing the course. Subject assessment using DREAM methodology and mind mapping tools helps teachers understand how curriculum teaching and designed learning activities impact student performance, thereby enabling improvement. teaching process for the next semester.

5. Discussion- "So What?"

Assessing and revising course outlines requires the knowledge of the educational requirements for the 21st century with many new concepts, such as: critical reflection, critical consciousness. Through the knowledge and tools trained from the ICTsEfs project, it makes lectures better understand these concepts. Especially, with a lot of support and training by experts from Europe, the new course outline has been upgraded with a comprehensive approach, and better oriented to SDGs. The evaluation using DREAM method needs to be done 3 times in each semester, which also brings pressure in term of time and workforce for both teachers and students. However, the results of the assessment and the students' opinions provide useful information for the adjustment of the curriculum and the improvement of the teaching quality of the subject.

Through the course outline that integrates 21st century skills and training requirements, along with the focus on integrating information and communication technology into learning activities, learners were equipped with integrated knowledge and skills. In addition to focusing on personal development, the course also develops skills to live responsibly as a member of the community and society.

The course revision process provided an opportunity for lecturers to learn how to develop and revise course outlines, thereby strengthening their teaching skills to achieve course learning outcomes. Previously, we have attended some training courses on pedagogy. However, the project's approach to revising the course outline, as described in the methods section, was new and effective for us in revising the course.

Lessons that we learned from participating in this project are the ways to generalize the concepts and translate them into tools to apply at work. Additionally, it is found that the criteria in 21st-century education provide a good orientation for integrating into all subjects, not limited to the subject's nature. When teachers focus on developing knowledge and skill sets; learners will be more responsible for their own study, and be more responsible to their country and community. Moreover, the focus of Sustainability justices

through a specific subject will contribute to training people to be a responsible workforce in the future, making the community develop more sustainably.

Education in the 21st century is transitioning from classroom instruction to a project-based model where teachers act as coaches and mentors. Digital technology plays a fundamental role in this educational process. Although the Internet and other digital technologies offer many benefits, they also expose students to some dangers. Teachers should have a good knowledge of related issues such as Cyberbullying, IT security and identity theft so that they can help students deal with these issues if they arise - and encourage students to become more responsible Web user (ICS, 2022).

Moreover, it is realized that our computer skills are still limited in comparison with requirements. Although more attention has been paid to ICT integration, but the subject has not really explored the full power of ICT in both teaching and learning. In the future, our actions will be focus on developing more skills in information technology, to be able to make teaching and learning more effective.

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From a Perspective of Sustainable Development Goals: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing Technology-Enhanced Language Learning Course

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Abstract

The study aimed to revise the syllabus for the Technology-Enhanced Language Learning (TELL) course to address the needs of the Sustainable Development Goals and evaluate the modified syllabus after students' engagement in the course. This study adopted Makrakis's (2006) training model for teachers and Makrakis's (2017) DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach to transform curricula. Additionally, it utilized Makrakis's (2023, 2019, 2022) DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) methodology to evaluate the revised syllabus. Course learning outcomes, course content, module content, and course assessment in the TELL syllabus were modified to align with the 17 Sustainable Development Goals. In the evaluation stage, despite students facing a heavy workload, responses from 77 students at a university in Vietnam revealed positive perceptions toward the modified syllabus. More importantly, students could become engaged in the educational process and deepen their social and educational experiences. The findings revealed that the most fundamental change is associated with the shift in both the teacher and students' perceptions of learning for sustainability. It is hoped that the perceptual change will last and be applied in their lives and professions in the future. A limitation of the revised syllabus may lie in the reproduction of the dominant ideology and the economic model of non-sustainable economic growth. Future research into students' learning process during the course should be conducted.

Keywords: ICT; curriculum, sustainability development

1. Introduction

Technology-enhanced language learning is an elective course in an undergraduate program in English Linguistics and Literature. The course is designed to equip undergraduate students with a general theoretical foundation and practical experience in integrating technology into the teaching and learning of English. With all the knowledge and experience from the course, learners can apply the most relevant technology to each class' background, levels or purposes of teaching. As technology has been significantly advanced during the last decades, the advantages that technology has brought to education are huge; thus, language teachers need to understand about technology enhanced language learning (TELL) applications and employment to improve teaching and learning practices. Therefore, the course was selected for revision because the course is expected to equip students with technological skills which are deemed crucial for students' sustainable development to be ready in their future study and professional practices. The graduates with expertise in technology as well as their teaching skills could gain competitive advantage in the job market. This course aims to enable students to identify the benefits of relevant software applications and employ appropriate TELL teaching approaches in language class. Approximately 45-50 students enrol in the course every academic year. The course contents include the four main themes: (a) introduction to technology in learning, communication, and teaching young learners; (b) technological application in teaching language skills and language components; (c) computer-based assessment; and (d) computer-based

material design. The course aims to develop the following competences:

- Understand theories underpinning approaches to learning with technology,
- Understand how technology provides new environments for language use and how these changes both the ways in which we communicate with each other and the language that we use,
- Understand the role of technology in teaching and choosing materials for Listening and Speaking Skills and practice using technology in teaching Listening and Speaking Skills,
- Discuss and point out the effects of technology on reading skills; and analyze activities related to teaching Reading Skills and practice teaching Reading Skills with the support of technology;
- Understand how technology affects the processes and contexts of writing and tools that support writing; analyze some activities related to teaching Writing Skills then apply technology in teaching Writing Skills,
- Examine the role of technology in the lives and education of children and in the school curriculum, explore some ways that technology maybe used to engage and support young learners;
- Discuss and analyze activities related to teaching vocabulary and grammar then design a lesson teaching vocabulary and grammar using technology
- Understand the benefits of using PowerPoint in the classroom, review some basic standards for Power Point slides, learn some PowerPoint activities or games used in the

classroom then create the visual aids (PPT) for a particular lesson

- Understand different purposes of assessment, recognize both benefits and drawbacks of technology for assessment
- Explore the ways in which TELL may be incorporated into existing syllabus and how coursebook materials maybe enhanced by technology

Teaching methods include lecturing, discussion and demonstrations. Course assessment is based on the whole course on-going progress (30%) and written midterm and final exams (70%). As for on-going assessment (30%), students are expected to participate in in-class activities and write a reflective paper, and a group project or demonstration.

2. Addressing the Sustainable Development Goals in the course syllabus revision

We conducted the revision of the course syllabus by the use of DeCoRe (Makrakis, 2017) and CARE methodology (Kostoulas-Makrais and Makrakis, 2020). During the deconstruction process, we analyzed, and assessed the TELL syllabus based on 10Cs, six learning goals, Sustainability justice, ICT and EfS (Makrakis, 2017).

Before the revision, the connection of the course with different fields, either interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary) remained unclear. In other words, questions of what and how the course is connected with other subjects in the program should be specified. Another issue is associated with the syllabus lacking the reproduction of dominant ideology and the economic model of non-sustainable economic growth. It is partly because students at undergraduate level may focus on possible technological tools and their uses in teaching and learning language, rather than evaluating online teaching materials according to a range of standards or criteria. More importantly, course assessments which heavily focused on written exams could fail to measure students' ability to develop practical projects and initiatives to validate the academic side into deliverables. Further, the written examinations may limit student interests to actively engage in the learning process. Practical reflection should be emended to foster the sense of involvement and the knowledge construction, social empathy and modern community practice moves.

In the revised TELL syllabus, learning outcomes were explicated in addressing the six pillars for sustainable development. As for learning to know, students will able to know general theoretical knowledge and practice on integrating technology into the teaching and learning of English, historical models of computer assisted language learning and consider the various roles of technology in relation to theories of learning, and understand the notion of digital competence and its relationship with communicative competence. Students will be knowledgeable about the integration of technology and English language education (e.g., teaching language skills and language components); be

critical in evaluating and choosing instructional and learning oriented material to meet the audience preferences, and be self-aware of their readiness and expertise in using technology in language education. Regarding learning to do, students will be able to design teaching-learning activities and apply the most relevant technology to each class' background, levels and teaching purposes. As students learn to live together sustainably, students will plan to make use of technology-facilitated activities (such as online group discussion) to provide equal learning chances to students, plan to develop individualized materials for language learners to learn at their own pace, and plan to design group work activities to collaborate peers/ classmates and to enhance the co-existence spirit for sustainable lifelong mode. In order to transform oneself and society, students will be able to give recommendations or solutions to integrating technology into language classes, start to search for the surrounding challenges that could technology, and address for social modern life transformation reflecting technological power. As students learn to give and share, students will be able to share their knowledge about technology-based teaching to their colleagues, and administrators, and collaborate with colleagues to design technology-based materials or conduct related research. The course was divided into three modules, consisting of (a) Theoretical aspects behind technology-enhanced language learning (TELL), (b) TELL activities to enhance L2 language skills, and (c) TELL activities to teach language components. In each module, key concepts, module overview, aims, learning outcomes, related readings, an in-class activity were identified.

The goal of the course attempted to address all dimensions related to sustainability. However, there remains several aspects include environmental, economic and cultural justice that are not covered clearly due to the limited time of the course at undergraduate level. It can be important to address the technological use in language teaching and learning as a double-sided weapon. Regarding environmental issues, the course should have explicitly addressed eco-friendly technology to language and teaching English. Several issues relating to teachers and learners can be problematic such as decreasing students' writing ability, dehumanizing educational contexts, distorting social interactions between teachers and students and isolating individuals when implementing technology. Furthermore, teachers may focus on possible technological tools and their uses in language teaching, rather than evaluating online teaching materials according to a range of standards or criteria.

3. Methodologies

The aim of the study was to revise the syllabus for Technology-Enhanced Language Learning course (TELL) in addressing the 17 Sustainable Development Goals and evaluate the modified syllabus after students' engagement into the course. This study adopted Kostoulas-Makrakis and Makrakis (2006) and Makrakis's (2006) training models for

teachers to embed sustainability in their courses. The model includes six stages as follows.

In the first stage, training focuses on the diagnosis of the didactic profile of every trainee. On the basis of the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and structured in thematic units, or modules that can be further enriched, considering the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The same process of evaluation is continued for the final recipients, the learners through transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages that help to sustain the proper functioning and possible upgrading of the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and most specifically the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction advanced by Makrakis (2017) was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is an approach that views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes.

1. Diagnosing: Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
2. Deconstructing: Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
3. Constructing: Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
4. Reconstructing: Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
5. Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. Finalising: Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

For the revised courses evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2023, 2022) has been applied. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023) reflects a critical action research process which aims not only assess a course but more importantly to make whatever changes in order to improve it. Through the parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student guided by the course instructor creates a portfolio that he/she has to give back to the instructor at the end of the

course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students' DREAM portfolios must be analysed from the instructor and prepare a report for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide very important information that the instructor and the students could discuss and find ways for improving the course.

4. Results

This section presents the revision of the syllabus and the results of students' reports of the updated syllabus.

Table 1 Description of the revised syllabus

Category	Original syllabus	Revised syllabus
1. Course learning outcomes	Meticulously described in 10 categories based on Bloom's taxonomy	Systematically described to address the six pillars for sustainable development
2. Course contents	Structured by chapters of the main textbook and in-class activities	Properly grouped in modules (e.g., theoretical aspects behind technology-enhanced language learning (TELL), TELL activities to enhance L2 language skills; and TELL activities to teach language components)
3. Module contents	Failed to detail and explicate module contents	Clearly explicated with key concepts, overview, aims, learning outcomes, units, related readings, and activity description in each module.
4. Course assessment	Heavy focus on written exams	The practical projects and external social reflection help the students to get engaged into the educational process and to deepen their social educational privilege.

As shown in Table 1, there were several changes in the revised syllabus as compared to the original. The course learning outcomes in the original syllabus were meticulously described in ten categories according the Bloom's taxonomy while in the revised version they were systematically described to address the six pillars for sustainable development. The course contents originally were structured by chapters of the chosen main textbook and in-class activities. However, the contents were then revised by grouping into modules (e.g., theoretical aspects behind technology-enhanced language learning (TELL), TELL activities to enhance L2 language skills; and TELL activities to teach language components). Each module was clearly explicated with key concepts, overview, aims, learning outcomes, units, related readings, and activity description. Instead of heavy reliance on written examinations, course assessment was modified with practical projects and external social reflection help the students to get engaged into the

educational process and to deepen their social educational privilege

TELL students' responses and mind maps to the revised syllabus can be divided into three parts: pre-course, assess and review. The results of the pre-course questionnaire reveal that a majority (74%) of 77 students at a university in Vietnam never attended a course in technology before. Other students (26%) have attended some workshops or tutoring sessions. A few students have certain experiences with technology in teaching, such as creating a website or a short tutorial video. During COVID 19 pandemic, the students engaged in real time meetings over the Internet with their teachers. All of the students reported their familiarity in both synchronous and asynchronous communication with their teachers and peers. In answering the question about their expectations from this course, the students voiced their hope to learn more about theoretical and practical aspects of using technology effectively in language teaching and learning. More interestingly, one student expressed their interest in assessing language performance with the use of technology.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

There were some challenges the students faced during the semester. The first challenge relates to workload as the students were required to learn both the target knowledge and its application, as well as the connection with the SDGs. The students reportedly spent more time to work on their projects apart from in-class activities, which may result in their heavy workload. The finding was in line with several studies in the ICT project.

The revised course seemingly made a range of positive impact for various stakeholders. Regarding the impact of the revised course on learning, although the knowledge was taught during the limited time of the course, the students could conduct their own leaning in the future. More importantly, students could get engaged into the educational process and to deepen their social educational privilege. As for teaching, the teacher could make the connections between the target knowledge and the SDGs based on the six pillars.

The most fundamental change is associated with the shift in both the teacher and students' perceptions of learning for sustainability. It is hoped that the perceptual change would last and put into use in their life and professions in the future. The teacher and students would understand that the course is strongly related to the six pillars where it covers the Environmental pillar for delivering the significant importance of using the appropriate technological techniques that will facilitate the educational process than using the traditional ways consuming resources and material. Also, the Social pillar to empower people with knowledge and action centric skills. The Economic pillar is also related as integrating the relevant technology as a main factor in the education rationalize the cost structure of the process and enhance the effectiveness of the outcome. Finally, the cultural pillar has the highest weight as the technology opened the gates to the world and limited the boundaries between people, where students will experience

different technological educational techniques to feel, see and act among the cultural differences and to engage integration and interaction.

However, the course seemingly did not reproduce the dominant ideology and the economic model of non-sustainable economic growth. That is probably because students at undergraduate level may focus on possible technological tools and their uses in teaching and learning language, rather than evaluating online teaching materials according to a range of standards or criteria. Moreover, although the assessment tasks were designed to require students to use all cognitive and conceptual learning techniques, such as constructing, consolidating, testing and reflecting, it has remained unclear which techniques were effective and how the students used those techniques in their study during the course. It would be fruitful for students to keep their own journals during the course, rather than reflecting at the end of the course.

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The “Construction Materials” Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

Constructing structures using materials has a significant impact on the environment. Education systems, especially at the higher education level, strive for sustainability in using construction materials that are needed to address global crises. This paper presents a process for modifying the syllabus of the “Construction Materials” course to integrate ICT-enabled Education for sustainability. The syllabus has clarified the course objectives by utilizing construction materials that meet sustainable criteria, including environmental justice, social justice, and economic justice. The content of the course, especially the learning activities, is designed to connect with the six learning goals for sustainable development in the application of construction materials, including learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to transform oneself and society, and learning to give and share. The syllabus of the course is also designed to encourage students to develop the ten critical skills necessary for solving complex sustainability problems, including collaboration, communication, critical thinking, creativity, cross-cultural understanding, connectivity, critical reflection, critical consciousness, and knowledge construction. The course is also assessed using the DREAM method, which includes diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage. The content of the course is then divided into some modules with units, questions, activities, clips, examples, and so on to act in the class. The syllabus is revised for integrating ICTs tools in educating for sustainability goals in using construction materials.

Keywords: construction materials, six learning goals, ten critical skills, education for sustainability, ICTs

1. Introductions

Constructing structures using materials has a significant impact on the environment. Construction typically consumes approximately 30–50% of available raw materials and generates about 40% of waste to the environment. The production of cement, steel, and aluminum accounts for 6% of global electricity consumption and contributes to over 12% of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions worldwide. Therefore, humanity has been facing the impacts of unsustainable economic development growth driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014; 2021). Identifying what constitutes a sustainable material and utilizing materials sustainably remain significant challenges for civil engineers. Education systems at all levels, and especially at the higher education level, strive for sustainability in using construction materials that are needed to address global crises. This is due mainly to the fact that consumers, leaders, and decision-makers who drive society and the economy, as well as shape an unsustainable consumers’ culture, are the products of educational institutions. Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that “the scope and range of the negative impacts of university-educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented” (p. 3).

Education should play a critical role in a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is close to Aristotle’s eudaimonic well-being as contrasted to the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Kostoula-Makrakis & Makrakis, 2020). The quest for “sustainable justice”, a

concept developed by Makrakis (2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development —environment, society, economy, and culture —is of paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth pointing out that while much has been invested in environmental education over the last few decades, it has been more reflected in raising positive environmental attitudes, but less concern for environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability have shown that lecturing, as expected, was the most prevalent teaching method, while role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, were rated much lower in use (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2013, 2015, 2021).

A project entitled Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2014) has revealed that the great challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of and capable of acting in transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts for teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. The teaching staff serves as the agent for change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016, 2018; Blake et al., 2011), as well as in

transforming schools into sustainable institutions (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

In Vietnam, sustainable education has become an important strategy, encompassing inclusive and equitable quality education, as well as lifelong learning opportunities, for all. Strategy for development of Vietnam's building materials is also published with main points such as: To efficiently and sustainably develop the sector of building materials, meeting domestic demands, gradually increasing exports, thus contributing to promoting growth and socio-economic development; To efficiently use resources and thoroughly save energy, raw materials, and fuels; To minimize environmental impacts during the exploitation and processing of minerals into building materials and production of building materials. Therefore, revising the construction materials course for sustainable education in teaching, learning and curriculum is necessary.

2. The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible side-effects of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental damage. Recent climate-related disasters in the region show that Asian policymakers must act now to protect their citizens and mitigate and reverse the impacts of climate change to secure sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While there is the commitment of Asian leaders for EfS, along with their concern for the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching forces need training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS) and, on the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. However, the integration of ICT does not merely mean the addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

XLVI. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align

curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.

XLVII. Build the capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a broad ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.

XLVIII. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.

XLIX. Develop innovative teaching, learning and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning and curriculum.

L. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices, and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the International University – Vietnam National University Ho Chi Minh City entitled Construction materials considering six main questions: The first question is the “What” question that focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The second and third questions refer to “Why” (justifying the reasons for revision) and “Where” describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The fourth question is the “how” question, describing the methodologies used for revision and course assessment during the implementation process. The fifth question is the “Now What” question, which shows what the revised and/or updated version of the course looks like and how it has changed from what it was before. Lastly, the sixth question is the “So What?” question, which focuses on discussing the challenges encountered while navigating all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did the understanding of teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why and what would be the next actions?

2.1 The first question is the “What” question:

This is a 3-credit mandatory course of the Civil Engineering program which is taught to about 10 to 30 students every semester. The course provides students with basic definitions and properties of various construction

materials, including both conventional and modern materials commonly used in civil engineering construction, such as concrete, steel, asphalt concrete, and others. Furthermore, the student can appreciate the criteria for selecting the appropriate materials and various tests to ensure the quality of their use. Using materials to develop infrastructure causes environmental problems and also impacts the Sustainable Development Goals of local communities. The teaching method is a combination of classroom activities, including lectures, questions, and discussions, with self-learning components such as reading, writing, homework, and teamwork. The method of assessing students includes three parts: process evaluation (30%), midterm examination (30%), and final examination (40%). Process evaluation includes in-class quizzes, class participation, learning attitude and homework.

2.2 The second question is the “Why” question:

The content of this course has been revised and improved to achieve the competence requirements. Before being revised, the content of the course focused on knowledge about the properties of materials, and the topic is shared in each lecture. After revision, the course description is more detailed, taking into consideration the SDGs. The course description enhances students' knowledge not only of the properties of construction materials but also of their application, with a focus on harmonizing materials with environmental sustainability, resource durability, and the use of local materials to minimize costs and strengthen and retrofit buildings. The relationship between program objectives and the 10Cs is also enhanced by the use of local materials, which helps satisfy cultural, economic, and social justice. From the beginning of the course, students developed skills in areas such as collaboration, communication, critical thinking, and creativity. Critical consciousness can help individuals choose suitable materials for sustainability.

In the revised syllabus, problems and interests are also mentioned, of course. It is challenging to fully apply the theory of construction materials in real-life situations. Types of construction materials change based on numerous factors. It is expensive and time-consuming to modify the existing materials to meet the requirements. Constructors do not consider the durability of structures, projects and sustainability because of their benefits. The use of construction materials in civil life indeed harms the natural environment. Making cement destroys mountains and natural ecosystems, creating CO₂ emissions. Exploring concrete sand in rivers may cause erosion of riverbanks. Therefore, civil engineers can use different materials to achieve nearly the same product. Civil engineers can utilize industrial waste and recycled materials to address environmental pollution and develop new materials. If civil engineers are aware of the importance of protecting the environment and consider taking all necessary measures to conserve resources and materials, we can choose suitable materials to minimize their negative impact on the environment.

In the revised syllabus, the course modules are also added. Each module is a topic of the course. Key concepts and overview are keywords to show the content of the topic. Each module also points out the learning outcome of the course. In each model, the content could be shared in several units. The textbook and reference book are also guided so that students could be self-learning. In one module, activities are listed, accompanied by numerous questions and teaching methods for each unit.

2.3 The third question is the “Where” question:

The previous syllabus focuses on course description, learning outcomes, student responsibilities, textbooks and reference books, and the course content. It does not cover all aspects of sustainability. After revising, the syllabus now covers more information about sustainability, including environmental justice, social justice, and economic justice. The content of the course and especially the learning activities are designed to connect to the six learning pillars for sustainable development (learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to transform oneself and society, and learning to give and share), and ten critical skills (10Cs) (Collaboration, Communication, Critical thinking, Creativity, Cross-cultural understanding, Connectivity, Critical reflection, Critical consciousness, Constructing knowledge).

To develop the skill of “learning to know”, students are taught to understand the basic definitions and physical, chemical, and mechanical properties of various construction materials, including local materials, industrial waste, and recycled materials used in civil engineering. After completing the course, students will acquire a “Learning to be” skill that enables them to become construction materials engineers who can classify types of construction materials based on their advantages and disadvantages in terms of properties relevant to civil engineering. Meanwhile, the “Learning to do” skill requires that students learn to design a mix of proportions of composite construction materials, such as types of Portland concrete, types of asphalt concrete, mortar, grout, and composite materials with fibers, among others. Cast some types of civil engineering materials. To contribute to sustainability, the skill of “learning to live together sustainably” is required. Therefore, students should consider using construction materials that are both durable and environmentally harmonious. Students are also aware of selecting construction materials for suitable purposes, considering economics and the environmental impact in civil engineering. Based on the information in the syllabus, students gain a deeper understanding of the skills they have achieved after completing the course.

In the syllabus, ten critical skills (10Cs) are explained in more detail. Collaboration is trained by sharing class into several groups, teamwork to find what type of materials for each type of structure and project, what type of materials could be replaced, discussing recycled materials and types of industrial waste that can be used or replaced as construction materials), whereby, students will share ideas and thoughts along with virtual field trips. Communication

is enhanced through presentations on the results of teamwork in class, asking questions from other groups and receiving answers, and identifying types of construction materials from other projects, thereby allowing students to develop their communication skills. The critical thinking skill is developed by identifying and discussing the properties of new materials, industrial waste, and recycled materials used in civil engineering, as well as by applying these materials in civil engineering projects. Creativity is developed by creating and designing new mix proportions, utilizing local and recycled materials, and finding ways to test properties and evaluate their application. Cross-cultural understanding is enhanced by discussing some properties that may affect local culture or conditions to which it applies. Connectivity means some properties that affect the environment such as thermal isolation, proof, and being environmentally friendly. Critical reflection is expressed by the relationship among workability, price, and transportation ability of new materials. Critical consciousness is considered as being aware to choose materials. Meanwhile, constructing knowledge is expressed by informing new types or properties of the material for sustainability.

2.4 The fourth question is the “How” question:

In the first stage, training focuses on the diagnosis of the didactic profile of every trainee. For course revision to embed sustainability and most specifically the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction advanced by Makrakis (2017) was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes:

Diagnosing: Reflecting on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.

Deconstructing: Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.

Constructing: Gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meanings (perspectives).

Reconstructing: Integration of newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.

Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module, supplemented by service learning.

Finalizing: Reflecting and evaluating what has been learned and changed.

For the revised course evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology has been applied (Fig. 1). These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing),

during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but, more importantly, to make changes in order to improve it. Through the various parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students’ DREAM portfolios must be analyzed by the instructor and prepared into a report for the whole class (Makrakis, 2023). The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide crucial information that the instructor and the students could discuss and find ways for improving the course.

Figure 1: The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

2.5 The fifth question is the “Now What” question:

After the revised syllabus was introduced to students, they gained a deeper understanding of the objectives, learning outcomes, the six sustainable development pillars, and the ten critical skills. The course is divided into several modules, each containing specific content. In each module, contents are divided into units. In each unit, questions and activities are listed and then acted upon in class to provide content to students. After each module, quizzes and homework are given to students to assess their understanding of objectives and learning outcomes. After each module, students are given questionnaires to modify the teaching and assessment methods to ensure that they acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. Midterm and final examinations are also given for assessment. The quizzes, homework, midterm, and final examinations, as well as the presentation and discussion questions in class, are designed to assess comprehension of the properties of concrete and concrete, to design mix proportions, and to develop writing skills in reporting, including definitions, meanings, applications, and conclusions for each topic or property.

3. Conclusions

The training course is conducted to help lecturers to revise and modify the syllabus to tend to sustainable education. Construction materials significantly impact the environment. Therefore, the effect of construction materials on the environment could be considered by construction materials engineers. The course could help construction materials engineers to be aware to choose suitable materials in order to harmonize environmental sustainability and resource durability and satisfy culture, economic, and social justice.

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The “Solid Waste and Hazardous Waste Management” Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of Sustainable Development Goals

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Abstract

This paper presents the processes, practices, and outcomes of revising the course "Solid Waste and Hazardous Waste Management" at the International University – Vietnam National University, Ho Chi Minh City (IU-VNUHCMC), by applying the DeCoRe+, DREAM, and CARE methods. After revision, the content is explained in greater detail to highlight the underlying principles, such as environmental justice, social justice, and economic justice. Furthermore, the assessment is aligned with the learning outcomes outlined in the course assessment policy and the assessment activities outlined in the content table. The revised contents and assignments enable the lecturer to effectively manage student performance and ensure that students meet the expected learning outcomes upon completing the course. However, students will face a more significant workload, especially if the class size is smaller than 15 students. Moreover, the lecturer also has to spend more time designing the assignments, evaluating students' submissions, and providing feedback to students. The remaining concern for both the lecturer and the students is how students will continue to practice solid waste management at home and in the community and whether they will feel engaged with the community through the reflective activities addressing the social and societal issues.

Keywords: ICTeEfS; DeCoRe+; DREAM; CARE; Solid waste and hazardous waste management

1. Introduction to ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental degradation. Recent climate-related disasters in the region underscore the need for Asian policymakers to take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby ensuring sustainable growth for the future. One way to address these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS) (Biasutti et al., 2018; Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2017). While Asian leaders have committed EfS, alongside their concern for implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS), and on the other hand, they must capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing Education for Sustainability to all in-service subject teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project

aims at developing an ICT-enabled capacity-building program to in-service teachers and teacher educators and turn them able to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies orienting to education for sustainability. The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

1. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.
2. Build the capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education to enable them to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers' training program on education for sustainability.
3. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program, enabled by blended learning, that focuses on integrating education for sustainability across school curricula.
4. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
5. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

2. Introduction about SWM course at IU-VNUHCMC

2.1 What is it?

This is a 4-credits mandatory course of the Environmental Engineering program, which is taught in the fifth semester for around 5-10 third-year students. The content of theory part (3 credits) is organized in 3 themes. The first theme encompasses general concepts related to the classification, sources, components, quantity, and characteristics of urban solid waste, as well as the storage and collection systems for urban solid waste. Additionally, it covers the transfer and transport processes involved in solid waste and hazardous waste management.

After learning the first theme, students will understand the different stages in solid waste and hazardous waste management and realize the importance of classification at the source (the first stage) to the efficiency of the latter stages. The second theme outlines the methods of solid waste treatment, including waste composting, biogas production, incineration, waste-to-energy, landfill disposal, and modern technologies for solid waste and hazardous waste management.

After learning the second theme, students will be able to discuss the pros and cons of these methods. The last theme enables students to compare and select appropriate solid waste management methods based on the characteristics of solid waste and the context of national solid waste and hazardous waste management strategies. Additionally, the labwork part (1 credit) is designed for students to practice measuring the characteristics of organic solid waste and designing and operating solid waste treatment models (composting, biogas, black soldier flies).

Competences to be developed from the course include:

- Distinguish the classification, sources, components, quantity, and characteristics of urban solid waste; the storage and collection system of urban solid waste; the transfer and transport process in SWM;
- Demonstrate the waste composting, biogas, incineration and waste to energy, landfill and sludge treatment as well as modern technologies for SWM;
- Compare methods of solid waste treatment and management towards the development of national SWM strategies;
- Experiment to measure the characteristics of organic solid waste, design and operate solid waste treatment models;
- Identify the impacts of solid waste to the environment.

The teaching method combined classroom activities (lectures, discussions, presentations, and lab work) with self-learning (reading and homework) and teamwork (group assignments). Method of assessment of students is the combination of in-class presentation, homeworks, lab report, mid-term exam, and final exam.

2.2 Why is it chosen for syllabus improvement?

The content of this course has been revised and improved to achieve the competence requirements. Before being revised, the content of the course was not organized in detail, especially for each class. After revision, the module for each class is developed precisely to meet the expected outcomes, including more discussion questions for in-class activities and additional reading and homework. Now, the students are asked to read additional materials, summarize the main content related to the topic, and present it in the class. Students must also link the theoretical content with the actual situation of solid waste management in their homes and communities.

Besides environmental and social justice, economic and cultural justice are more clearly indicated through homework, where students can realize the economic value of waste and practice at home to reduce costs associated with collecting, storing, transporting, and treating solid waste, thereby increasing revenue and benefits. Moreover, students will also increase their awareness of environmental protection and practice a minimalist lifestyle.

Students do not only learn to know the knowledge about solid waste management but also learn to tackle the call and to be self-aware of the environmental protection, to think and act in an environmental-friendly manner; to apply knowledge in identifying the solid waste problem and propose the solution for the sustainable management and treatment of the solid waste. Moreover, students will also learn to delegate and involve family and neighbors/community in reducing the disposal of solid waste; to learn to balance personal demands with environmental protection from solid waste problems. Students will learn to understand the need for change towards low- and zero-waste lifestyles, as well as to actively share knowledge related to solid waste management and treatment, in order to motivate themselves and others to become sustainable citizens.

Students will learn to communicate and collaborate with groupmates in assignments and lab work. Students will learn to apply critical thinking and creative thinking skills in exploring and investigating essential problems related to solid waste management and find optimal problem-solving techniques. Students will understand the different cultural-related awareness of solid waste matters in various families through discussions with classmates and case study reviews of different countries and regions. Furthermore, students will be self-aware about the solid waste issues and will apply the knowledge obtained in this course to the solid waste management at their home/community. Students will learn to transition from a consumerist lifestyle to a more sustainable one and will feel a sense of engagement with the community through reflective activities that address social and societal issues related to solid waste and hazardous waste.

2.3 *Where are the parts to be improved?*

Although the course attempts to cover all aspects of sustainability, some dimensions are still being overlooked or underrepresented, including environmental justice, social justice, and economic justice. In terms of environmental justice, the environmental impacts of solid waste treatment methods are not thoroughly discussed. Even though this course provides knowledge for solid waste management and treatment, there will be environmental impacts associated with treating the solid waste, such as odour and leachate, during the storage, collection, transportation, and landfilling processes. These environmental impacts of solid waste management will lead to health effects to those people involved (waste collectors, transporters, engineers, etc.). This is the social justice dimension that is not discussed in detail of the previous curriculum. Moreover, the comparison of treatment costs among different solid waste treatment methods is not precisely calculated and analyzed. This is the limitation in terms of economic justice that the revised curriculum should cover.

Through this course, at least five SDG themes are infused, which are responsible consumption and production, life on land, life below water, climate action, and sustainable cities and communities. Firstly, the responsible consumption and production goal will be achieved through the practice of Reduce-Reuse-Recycle, or even more, such as Rethink, Refuse, Repair, Regift, Recover, etc. The practices of these companies help reduce the demand for raw materials in the production process and minimize waste generation from end-users. Secondly, the successful practices of these Rs will also reduce the amount of solid waste that needs to be buried in landfills or burned in incinerators. With less solid waste, there will be a reduced impact on land and aquatic species due to soil and water contamination from leachate. Moreover, there will be fewer greenhouse gases emitted into the atmosphere, and thus a lesser impact on the climate. Sustainable management of solid waste and hazardous waste will contribute to achieving Sustainable Development Goal 11, which aims to create sustainable cities and communities.

To evaluate students' performance based on the revised content discussed above, the competence level is raised from remembering and understanding to applying and analyzing. From understanding the concepts related to solid waste management, students must be able to apply these knowledge in distinguishing different stages of urban solid waste management, demonstrating the waste composting, biogas, incineration and waste to energy, landfill and sludge treatment as well as modern technologies in theory, and thus to design and operate some solid waste treatment models (composting/biogas) at home (small scale) and in the laboratory (pilot scale) and analyze the effectiveness of these models.

3. Methodology

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction- Construction-

Reconstruction) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2017) was applied. The DeCoRe+ is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes:

1. Diagnosing: Reflecting on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.
2. Deconstructing: Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
3. Constructing: Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
4. Reconstructing: Integration of newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
5. Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. Finalizing: Reflecting on and evaluating what has been learned and changed.

After the syllabus is revised to address the existing justice themes, sustainable development pillars, and the 10Cs as well as to point out the missing elements in the content, the new syllabus and course content are distributed to the new classes. The DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) methodology, advanced by Makrakis (2023), has been applied to course assessment based on feedback from students. The CARE methodology (Kostoulas-Makrakis & Makrakis, 2020) is employed for course improvement, encompassing lesson plans, teaching methods, student assessment, and other related aspects.

At the beginning of the course (the first class), the pre-course diagnose assessment is conducted, in which students will be asked to answer several questions related to solid waste issues and draw the mind-map to link their current understanding on solid waste and hazardous waste management as well as to know their expectation when learning this course. In general, students can list several types of solid and hazardous wastes from their homes and classify these wastes by their characteristics and sources. However, there is still some confusion in classifying non-recyclable wastes and hazardous wastes, as well as the environmental impacts of solid wastes, since students associate waste with dirt and are reluctant to even look at it at home. Therefore, a new assignment arises, where students must observe the waste in their homes and categorize it into three main groups (recyclable, non-recyclable, and hazardous), explaining the characteristics of each. Moreover, students are asked to conduct composting and biogas models from the organic waste in their houses and observe and record the changes within the models. Furthermore, some students do not really know about different stages in solid waste management, so more pictures

are added into the study materials to introduce to students (such as collection trucks, transfer stations, incinerators, landfill sites, etc.) advanced by Makrakis (2017).

In the middle of the course, before the midterm exam, a review and reflection assessment is conducted to evaluate students' understanding after learning half of the semester and to identify their difficulties as well as concerns regarding the lectures. The results show that students also want to learn intensively about hazardous waste treatment methods. However, due to the hazardous waste profession, I am unable to provide practical activities for students. Instead, I introduce students to information about some authorities and private companies that hold certificates for collecting and treating hazardous waste. We were unable to conduct the field trip due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

At the end of the course, before the final exam, students are asked to complete the final assessment. Responses indicate that students have a significantly better understanding of the elements of solid waste and hazardous waste management, encompassing not only the management stages but also the relevant stakeholders. Moreover, students can also apply certain equations to calculate the storage capacity, collection frequency, number of collection vehicles, amount of leachate and gases emitted from decomposition processes, etc. Last but not least, students practice composting and biogas at home and also on a pilot scale in the laboratory. Another group of students practiced feeding the black soldier flies as one of the other environmentally friendly methods for organic waste treatment. Overall, students are more aware of the solid waste problems within their communities and understand the theory, applying it to practice, not only during this course but also after completing it.

4. Results and discussion

After applying the DREAM and CARE methodologies, all diagnosed knowledge gaps in students, particularly their confusion before taking the course, are fulfilled and reflected through the lectures and assignments. The content is explained in more detail to highlight the hidden justices, as mentioned earlier (e.g., environmental justice, social justice, and economic justice). Moreover, the assignments are used to assess students' understanding of the provided lectures as well as their additional readings. Besides, the course structure is also redesigned to provide students one field trip (half a day) at the solid waste treatment company. The practical, actual projects (assignments, field trips) and external social reflections will encourage students to engage in the educational process and deepen their social and educational understanding in this course. Furthermore, the assessment is linked to the learning outcomes outlined in the course assessment policy and the assessment activities listed in the content table.

The revised contents and assignments help the lecturer to manage the performance of students and ensure that the students will meet the expected learning outcomes when they finish the course. However, there will be a greater

workload for students, especially if the class size is less than 15 students. Moreover, the lecturer also has to spend more time designing the assignments, evaluating students' submissions, and providing feedback to students.

After completing the course, students will be able to explain the key concepts of solid waste and hazardous waste management. They also can demonstrate the theoretical process of waste composting, biogas, incineration and waste to energy, landfill and sludge treatment as well as modern technologies for solid waste management. Students also conduct the composting model and raise black soldier flies as two practical activities. Moreover, through field trips and lab work, students have practical observations about the solid waste problems (especially when the waste amount becomes more extensive), and how treatment can help to reduce the pollution from solid waste and make money from waste.

The interesting point is that bonuses will encourage students to become more active in class and apply their critical thinking and creative problem-solving skills. They also collaborate, discuss with their groupmates, and share knowledge to complete assignments and write reports for lab work. Cross-cultural understanding and awareness also help students connect and collaborate effectively with one another. The remaining concern for both the lecturer and the students is how students will continue to practice solid waste management at home and in the community and whether they will feel engaged with the community through the reflective activities addressing the social and societal issues.

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Shifting Higher Education Curriculums toward Sustainable Education: the Case of Business Law Courses at International University

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Abstract

With the ambition to ensure peace and promote the well-being of people and the planet, in 2015, the United Nations called for global action to achieve its Sustainable Development Goals by 2030. To achieve these goals, education plays a crucial role in equipping citizens in each country with the necessary knowledge and skills to become effective global citizens and address global issues. Without global citizens, it will be challenging to bring the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals into reality by 2030. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure that education has shifted from traditional to sustainable teaching and learning. As a part of the funded ICTeEFS project (ICT-enabled In-service Training of Teachers to Address Education for Sustainability), this paper will explain how our business law courses at International University have changed toward sustainable education after applying DeCoRe Plus, DREAM, and CARE methodologies to enable ICTs into teaching and learning processes.

Keywords: DeCoRe Plus, DREAM, CARE, Sustainable education

Introduction

Business Law is a core course in the programme of the bachelor's degree in Business Administration provided by the International University – VNU, Vietnam. This course is designed for third-year students. To take the course, students were required to have previously completed the Introduction to Vietnamese Legal System course. As Business Law is a core course, it is expected that around 500 students will attend the course every term in an academic year. The Business Law course provides students with a fundamental understanding of legal concepts related to business entities, business activities, and dispute resolution methods. After completing the course, students will understand provisions (1) on forms and organisational structures of business entities in the law on enterprises, (2) on business-related contracts in the commercial law and the civil code, (3) on dispute settlement by arbitration and litigation in the law on commercial arbitration and the civil procedure code. Additionally, students will develop their critical thinking and problem-solving skills to resolve legal issues in practical cases effectively. Previously, lecturers delivering this course mainly adopted teacher-centred approaches. In particular, the course contents were mainly presented by lecturers. Sometimes, students were asked to work in groups to complete projects or assignments, prepare presentations, or prepare for moot court competitions. Students' learning outcomes were evaluated through midterm and final examinations and in-class activities such as quizzes, tests, presentations, projects, assignments, and moot court competitions.

As the improvement of sustainability in education is one of the urgent actions required to meet the UN Agenda for Sustainable Development by 2030,¹ it is necessary for the

world to develop sustainability-justice in education. The teaching methods, tools, and activities used in the Business

Law course provided students with legal knowledge and helped build their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. However, students' knowledge and skills were not strong enough to solve problems in their future careers. Furthermore, the majority of students were unable to serve as ambassadors for ensuring sustainability and justice in society. Students were facing these issues because the Business Law course faced the same problem as the current educational systems, which did not provide students with the knowledge, skills, and tools to understand what is happening in the world and how to transform oneself and society towards more sustainable, just futures.² As a result, it is necessary to revise the Business Law course toward sustainability. In the following sections, this paper will explain why the course needs to change, describe the changes made to the course, outline the modifications made, and present the current state of the course.

	Before the revision	After the revision
Course objectives	<p>The aim of this course is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">Familiarize the student with legal language; basic concepts, principles and general knowledge of business Law.Introduce to students about main business forms in Vietnam and regulations for	<p>The overarching aims of this course are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">Provide essential knowledge of business law through integrated technology and real cases for social and cultural sustainabilityRaise awareness of responsibility toward others in society and how to stand for ending all types of legal violations

	<p>each. Also, possibility of reorganization and Insolvency for enterprises, as main subject matter of this course.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the student's understanding of the Vietnamese regulations over business dispute resolution, • Expose the student to legal reasoning and develop his/her ability to apply legal concepts. • Introduce students to main trade international organizations and main international trade rules. • Develop problem solving and legal analyzing skills and apply it to day-to-day practical situations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntarily act as an ambassador to ensure social fairness and global equitable rights • Use integrated online legal resources and communication tools to help the community to identify issues and develop countermeasures. • Use the online forum and video conferences to collaborate with their peers and colleagues to conduct business activities legally
Course expected learning outcomes	<p>After completing the course, students should have:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic knowledge on Legal regulations on business activities and enterprises. Main concepts and principles. • Knowledge on specific issues for operation, 	<p>After completing the course, students should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand legal concepts in business law and start to develop base on how to communicate the legalities theoretically delivered through the course content into real social praxis for fair

	<p>reorganization and insolvency of enterprises</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to analyze and choose the best way to solve business disputes and apply best suitable regulations for enterprises. • Analyzing and problem-solving skills to be applied to practical cases 	<p>sustainable lifelong being.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand and take responsibilities to comply with the business law and to rise the self-motivational theme to reflect the academic knowledge through activities such as case studies from real life • Learn to how to apply the theoretical contents into practice; to move from awareness of business law to knowledge and action • Learn how to approach those who do not have voices and to raise their legal rights aiming for fair social/cultural moves. • Realize whether their prior thoughts/ behavior complies with law or not and change students' previous thoughts and to act as ambassadors for social fairness and global equitable rights. • Take responsibility to conduct business activities legally and learn the base for coexistence on the national and international scope of business. • Use online legal libraries and resources, video review for moot
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		courts for effective integration and interaction between knowledge and reality
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Why does the course need to change?

For the sustainability-justice in education, a course needs to help students achieve the 21st century learning pillars (learning to know, be, live, do, transform, and share) and 10Cs (critical thinking and problem solving, communication, collaboration, creativity and innovation, connectivity and networking, critical consciousness, critical reflection, cross/inter-cultural competence, co-responsibility, and constructing knowledge). For improvement, it is necessary to identify which pillars of 21st-century learning and skills in the 10Cs are missing in the Business Law course. After analysis, it is revealed that the teaching methods, tools, activities, and assessments used in the Business Law course helped to ensure not only social and cultural justice but also the achievement of the 21st-century learning pillars. However, the course did not build creativity and innovation, connectivity, knowledge construction, and cross-cultural competence skills for students. Regarding identifying areas for improvement, we first revised the course objectives and expected learning outcomes, which are at the heart of the course. Since Prof. Makrakis pointed out that the use of ICTs in education can enable students to achieve 10Cs, we ensured that the course objectives and expected learning outcomes express the adoption of ICTs in teaching and learning toward sustainability. In comparison with the syllabus prior to revision, the course objectives and expected learning outcomes now emphasize the achievement of 21st-century learning pillars and the 10Cs to enhance social and cultural justice. In particular, the following table demonstrates the differences in the course objectives and expected learning outcomes before and after the revision:

Based on the revised course objectives and expected learning outcomes, we attempted to incorporate ICTs into our lessons to help students achieve the expected learning outcomes. However, as we adopted lecture-centered approaches in our teaching, they did not significantly enhance students' 10Cs and change the way students learn towards the 21st-century learning pillars. As a result, we need to revise our lesson plans and teaching methods to transition student learning from a passive to an active approach through the use of ICTs.

Where did the courses change?

To help students to achieve the revised expected learning outcomes of the course, it is necessary for students to use web-enabled ICTs in learning for sustainability justice development. In other words, the course should encourage the use of the internet and online communication platforms (such as Blackboard, Facebook, MS Teams, Miro, and other

software for mind mapping) for group discussions, information searching, and enhancing critical thinking skills. The use of ICTs in discussions and communications will remove the

distance in geography and culture between students. Regardless of where, when, or with whom students are, they can communicate with each other to exchange ideas and advice. Besides, the course needs to help students develop and generate ideas related to social justice and expose them to real-life practice, allowing them to establish a strong sense of co-responsibility towards community liability. Therefore, during lessons, students need opportunities to expose themselves to real-life cases through newspapers. Students should be encouraged not only to express their ideas on cases and explore why their friends have different perspectives from them but also to help their teammates (who are shy about sharing their opinions) to share their thoughts on related topics in the course. Additionally, after discussions, students need to be able to reflect on why their beliefs are right or wrong. From that, students will know how to adapt their understanding and approach. Furthermore, by resolving legal issues from real-life cases, students will have opportunities to practice their problem-solving skills and learn how to prevent and address illegal acts and unfair treatment.

To encourage students to perform all of the above effectively, it is necessary to revise the current assessment methods used in the course. In addition to midterm and final examinations, as well as in-class quizzes, the course utilizes peer evaluation to assess students' capacity to work in groups and their sense of responsibility toward social and cultural justice. Moreover, information on marking criteria and how assessment methods help to evaluate the course's expected learning outcomes should be published and announced to students clearly to prevent unfair treatment in the course.

How did the course change?

After using the DREAM Methodology⁵ as a course assessment, we gained insight into what students thought about how we delivered lessons, what they expected from us, and which kinds of development they achieved through the course. In particular, the majority of students who enrolled in the course expected to acquire legal knowledge related to business activities. They were unaware of the importance of acquiring skills for sustainable development or their responsibility toward social and cultural justice. As we were aware of the problem, we revised the course's expected learning outcomes. We modified its learning activities to help students acquire the necessary skills for sustainable development while also raising their awareness of responsibility toward social and cultural justice. However, after the course, it seemed that students did not achieve what the course was expected to teach them. Since we acknowledged the gaps we needed to fill, we attempted to explore the reasons why they did not achieve certain types of development as outlined in the course's expected learning outcomes. With comments and suggested learning activities

raised during the peer review, we understood that the problems we were facing stemmed from the way we delivered our lessons and designed learning activities. To improve the situation, we needed to revise our lesson plans and teaching methods to encourage students' engagement and active learning. To do so, we have adopted the CARE methodology⁶ in revising our lesson plans. For each lesson, we have ensured that students will have opportunities to (1) involve themselves in creating learning activities, (2) activate their knowledge through ICTs, (3) reflect on their prior thoughts and habits of mind, and (4) involve themselves in activities. In particular, for each class, students are required (before class and in class) to use Google or the digital library to search for information related to the given topics. This activity helps students to gain 10Cs, and learn to know. During class, students are required to work in groups to discuss and share their knowledge with their friends. With this activity, we aim to encourage students not only to share their opinions on the given topics but also to explore why their teammates hold different opinions. We also encourage students to find ways to help their teammates who are shy to raise their voices during group discussions. The main idea of the group discussions is to enhance students' learn to share and learn to live together. Additionally, students can develop skills to serve as ambassadors for social and cultural justice throughout the course. After group discussions, students will share their opinions and discuss their group's opinions with other classmates and their lecturer. At this stage, students can reflect on what they learnt before class. They will understand the gaps in the knowledge they gained prior to class. From this understanding, they learn how to acquire the correct knowledge and apply it effectively in solving real-life problems. This stage helps students to learn to be, do, and transform, as well as act toward social and cultural justice.

What does the course look like now?

After going through the DeCoRe plus processes, we have made significant changes to our teaching, learning, and syllabus for the Business Law course. This section will present how the current course syllabus, teaching, and learning differ from those of the previous course.

Before joining the ICTeEfS project⁸, the course did not focus on the aim for sustainable education. Instead of providing sustainable education, the course aimed to equip students with the knowledge and skills required by industry stakeholders. As a result, the course objectives focused on helping students understand legal regulations on business activities, and apply the knowledge to solve cases from real life. Students were not aware of their role in ensuring justice in society. Although we required students to work in groups to address real-life cases, the course did not effectively enable students to study independently. Students still relied on what lecturers provided for them. The majority of students lacked the skills of intense self-study, critical thinking, analysis, and problem-solving. After the course, the majority of students could memorize the knowledge but not understand it deeply.

After analyzing and reviewing the course syllabus on sustainable education, I found that the course aims to raise students' awareness of social and cultural justice while also helping them become active citizens. Furthermore, the course will encourage students to utilize ICTs to access information, connect with classmates, and promote justice in society. To achieve these course objectives, lecturers have modified classroom activities, teaching methodologies, and assessment methods. In particular, lecturers no longer act as teachers who provide knowledge to students. Instead, lecturers now act as instructors to encourage students to engage in independent study. Before class, students are now required to use ICTs to discuss with each other and search for information as instructed by the lecturers. In class, students are required not only to share their opinions but also to build skills to help others raise their voices. Additionally, students are encouraged to explore why their classmates hold different opinions from their own. Additionally, through group discussions and in-class activities, students will have the opportunity to reflect on themselves and reconsider their previous thoughts on various issues. Lecturers only provide advice to help students find appropriate knowledge, reflect on themselves, and build problem-solving skills. In other words, lecturers have replaced their traditional teaching methodology, which involves lecturing, with a student-centered approach when delivering the course.

After a few semesters of implementing the new syllabus and teaching methodology, students still do not understand how the course helps them become active citizens and how it can ensure sustainable education. Therefore, lecturers now provide instructions explaining what the course can offer in terms of sustainable education, how it can promote social and cultural justice, how classroom activities contribute to students achieving the course's expected learning outcomes, and how lecturers will assess students. In the first class, students will be introduced to the concept of sustainable education, the course objectives, classroom activities, and assessments. In particular, students are now aware that for sustainable education, students need to gain 10 Cs and achieve the six 21st-century learning pillars (learn to know, be, do, share, live together, and transform). For each classroom activity, students are required to use Google to search for information and discuss it with their peers before class, either through Facebook or group discussions on Blackboard. By using Google, Facebook, Blackboard, mindmap tools, or other ICTs in study, students will have skills for critical thinking, problem solving, communication, collaboration, creativity, connectivity, critical consciousness, critical reflection, cross-cultural competence, coresponsibility, and knowledge construction. These skills will help students to become an active learner and achieve the six 21st century learning pillars. Besides, students understand that students can reflect themselves, construct knowledge, learn to live together, and ensure social and cultural justice during group discussions. In fact, when students encourage their teammates to share their opinions during group discussions or offer advice on how to prevent illegal acts, they promote social and cultural justice.

When students explore why their friends have different opinions from their own, they gain skills to live together effectively. Through group discussions, students will realize whether their previous thoughts on an issue are correct. After each lesson, students will reflect on the issues discussed using mind map tools.

In comparison with the previous course syllabus, teaching methodology and classroom activities, every current contents and activities arranged in each lessons of the course will ensure students (1) be aware of their responsibility toward social and cultural justice, (2) build 10 Cs, and (3) achieve the 21st century learning pillars. To assess whether students achieve the course's expected learning outcomes and encourage active in-class discussion, students are required to complete peer evaluations after each class. Additionally, students should evaluate themselves at least three times during the course. Lecturers will show students their results before their midterm and final examinations. Through the results, students will be able to identify which learning outcomes they have achieved and which ones they have not. Based on the results, students will have plans to improve themselves throughout the course. Lecturers also provide guidance to help students enhance their skills and study more effectively.

Understanding that social and cultural justice is ensured not only through course content but also through classroom activities and assessment methods, lecturers ensure that all students are treated equally throughout the course. As a result, lecturers publish marking criteria as well as explanations on how questions in exams assess students' learning outcomes. Students' results are communicated to students. Lecturers also listen to students' feedback and improve the course.

Students, who studied the course before the changes and now are teaching assistants for the course, commented that they saw the differences when they attended the course again. After completing the course before, they thought they understood all the contents. However, when they attended the course again, they found out that they had only memorized what they had learned. As a result, they sometimes struggle to address real-life issues because they lack effective solutions. For current students who have studied the course after the changes, they comment that their thoughts have undergone significant changes as a result of the course. They now think critically and solve issues logically. They also learn how to approach others, how to help others to raise their voices, and how to understand others and effectively change others' thoughts toward the right things.

Conclusion

Since joining the ICTeEfS project, our understanding on sustainable education and justice has significantly changed. At the beginning, when we heard about sustainable education, we thought that our courses need to be added more contents related to social, cultural, environmental and economic justice for sustainable education. Additionally, we were unsure how to achieve sustainable education. After the

training workshops, which the project arranged in Malaysia and Indonesia, we realized that to achieve sustainable education, students are not only provided with knowledge but also the 10Cs and skills to learn to know, be, do, live together, share, and transform. When students gain 10Cs and skills to achieve the 21st-century learning pillars, students can be active citizens who can stand to protect justice in society. Besides, the courses need to raise students' awareness of their responsibility toward social, cultural, environmental, and economic justice. It is not necessary to introduce students to content related to justice through the course to ensure justice in society. Skills to ensure justice in society can be built through group discussion activities. In other words, if it is impossible to add content related to environmental and economic justice, courses can at least raise awareness of social and cultural justice through in-class activities. When lecturers treat students equally or when students treat each other equally irrespective of nationality, skin color, gender, or social class, it means lecturers and students are ensuring cultural justice. When lecturers and students help shy students and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds to raise their voices, it means that lecturers and students are ensuring social justice.

Previously, we believed that after completing our courses, students could solve problems effectively because we designed classroom activities based on real-life cases. However, with the previous lesson plans, the majority of students did not know how to independently solve problems in real-life cases. For cases similar to cases introduced in class, students could solve the issue quickly because they memorized what the lecturers told them. For cases with new facts or more complicated, students seemed to struggle

. After understanding that students need to move from learning to know to learning to be, do, live together, share and transform. We now focus on building students' problem solving and critical thinking skills. Instead of telling students the results or providing a model answer to case studies, we now offer students guidance on how to identify issues, analyze the issues, locate relevant legal frameworks, and apply these frameworks to resolve the issues. When we changed our roles from lecturers to instructors, students did not adapt to the new methodology. Some of them did not want to join in class activities. They also complained that it was too stressful and that they had an overwhelming workload. In order to encourage students to join class activities, we introduced the course objectives and sustainable education in the first class. The introduction helped students understand the course objectives and how classroom activities are structured to support them in achieving the course's expected learning outcomes. We also request peer evaluations to encourage students' independent study. Through the peer evaluation results, students know how their peer thinks about their students and what their peer thinks they should improve. For the current semester, the majority of students in our classes now actively joins discussions and helps their friends to raise voice.

Since the course encourages students to use ICTs in their study, students discuss with each other before class through

Facebook or online chat box. They found that it is a lot easier for them to share opinions and join discussions wherever they are. For some shy students, they share more opinions because they feel more comfortable to share their opinions through machine rather than in person. Therefore, it can be concluded that ICTs help to enable sustainable education. Students have changed their thought and their learning way significantly after the course. Students also find they understand issues deeply and have more skills to live in society after the course. However, there are still some students do not get on well with the course, because they feel over workload. Students sometimes get bored with evaluations and discussions. As a result, it is necessary to find out a way to attract students' willingness in joining group discussions and classroom activities, and reduce workload for students.

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SESSION H

Multimedia Design and Human Computer Interaction Course: Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

This paper discusses the integration of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) throughout the deconstruction, construction, and reconstruction processes of multimedia design and human-computer interaction courses. The Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction (DeCoRe+) methodology was applied in this study. For the evaluation of revised courses during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess, and Manage) framework was used. Findings from the DREAM survey concluded that all 18 students had heard of the SDGs before. Most students had heard about the SDGs at the University, and a small number reported having learned about them in secondary school. During class discussion, it was discovered that all 31 students had been exposed to the concepts of the SDGs through various resources. The findings showed that these students had never attended a course on this topic and had never created a project or written work similar to this course. The findings showed that students never succeeded in a work dealing with issues such as the topic of the Multimedia Design and Human-Computer Interaction course. This course is entirely new to the students as their background is in sports science. Most of them stated that they hope to learn new things, particularly in designing multimedia applications for educational purposes.

Introduction

The repercussions of unsustainable economic development fueled by profit maximization have led to the excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources, affecting humanity over the past few decades (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite existing initiatives to halt this type of unsustainable development, more work remains to be done. All levels of the education system, but particularly higher education, are to blame for the global sustainability problem we are currently experiencing. This is mainly because the individuals who drive society and the economy, creating an unsustainable consumer culture, are often the products of educational institutions: consumers, leaders, and decision-makers (Makrakis, 2011). According to Corcoran and Wals (2004), the scope and variety of the adverse effects of persons with university educations on the natural systems that sustain our planet are unprecedented.

For a significant transition to occur through an alternative development model that gives proper weight to sustainable well-being, education should play a crucial role for disseminating and infusing sustainable development principles (Biasutti & Frate, 2017). Our understanding is that eudaimonic well-being, as opposed to the prevalent hedonic well-being caused by unsustainable behaviours and ways of production and consumption, is similar to Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The quest for "sustainable justice", a concept

Developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development —environment, society, economy, and culture —is of paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is important to note that, despite significant funding for environmental education over the past few decades, environmental action has received less attention than favourable views on the environment. A paradigm shift in curriculum, teaching, and learning is necessary to translate environmental awareness and understanding into environmental action. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being and living (Makrakis, 2012). The discrepancy between environmental attitudes and environmental activity is also due to several other factors, as well as ineffective educational techniques. Role-play, hands-on science, and problem-based learning, which are more effective approaches, were ranked significantly lower in use than lecturing, according to recent curriculum development studies that focused on sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

A recent research underlines how the use of Ecological Projects in Higher Education raises awareness in students about SDGs and how students become more active in the dissemination of the right action (Manolis, 2021)

According to a project titled "Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability" (Makrakis, 2013, 2014), the great challenge facing institutions of higher learning in the 21st century is training professionals who are critical of and capable of changing their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. One of the main obstacles is the problem of translating the theoretical concepts of sustainable development into practical actions (Reid & Petocz, 2006; Biasutti et al, 2018). Teachers in primary and secondary school classrooms, as well as teacher educators, face a similar set of challenges. Teaching staff are the change agents in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and

curriculum, as well as for making schools sustainable (Biasutti et al., 2016; Blake et al., 2013; Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

A teaching approach called Education for Sustainability (EfS) aims to instil in students, schools, and communities the values and motivation to act in the interests of the environment. Universiti Teknologi Malaysia and the Johor State Education Department (UTM-JPNJ) launched a collaboration programme in the state of Johor in 2019 to further the university's Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) objectives. 2019; Jabatan Pendidikan Negeri Johor. To promote the SDGs through education for sustainability, the Johor state government of Malaysia has formed a collaboration with organisations in both the education and non-education sectors. The plan outlines five measures to improve curriculum, co-curriculum, administration, management, and evaluation at various levels of education in the state of Johor based on the research findings. With the help of this Action Plan, several sustainability initiatives and projects in Johor can be coordinated to be more targeted and high-impact, based on three key pillars: 21st-century learning, STEM education, and sustainability education.

The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental degradation. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian policymakers must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby securing sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While Asian leaders have committed EfS, alongside their concern for implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS) and, on the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education. The use of effective teaching practices with ICT consent can transform educational practices into more collaborative, interactive, and motivating experiences for students (Alonso-Garcia et al., 2019).

Considering all the challenges and shortages outlined in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to utilize innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards

Education for Sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning and research with the area of education for sustainability.

Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation and evaluation of a broad ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.

Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.

Develop innovative teaching, learning and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning and curriculum.

Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the Universiti Teknologi Malaysia entitled Multimedia Design and Human Computer Interaction course: Deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing it through the lens of SDGs considering six main questions: The first question is the "What" question, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The second question and third questions refer to "Why" (justifying the reasons for revision) and "Where" describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The fourth question is the "How" question describing the methodologies used for the revision and the course assessment during the implementation process. The fifth question is the "Now What" question that shows how the revised and/or updated revision of the course looks like, how it has changed from "What" was before. Lastly, the sixth question is the "So What?" question that focuses on discussing the challenges met to go through all the preceding processes from the beginning up to now and how has been tackled. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience and how will it affect the beneficiaries such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why and what would be the next actions?

The What, Why and Where Questions for Revising Multimedia Design and Human Computer Interaction course: Deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing it through the lens of SDGs

This course introduces the concept of designing media for educational purposes, including the development of courseware and web pages for teaching and learning. In this course, students are exposed to the systematics models for instructional design, the implementation of learning theories in software design, components of the design (information, visual, and interaction design), and an integration of motivational models into the design and development of educational courseware. Students could also learn the appropriate guidelines of interface instruction, including menu design, screen design, and screen layout. Students are also exposed to the tools used in the design of software including a flowchart and a storyboard. Students who attend this course could produce the planning documents before the development of the actual software. Besides, in this course students learn about the concept of human - computer interaction (HCI) in relation to interaction design concept and the process of Interaction Design.

Through this course, students will develop their thinking skills to prepare technology-based teaching and learning activities by considering the characteristics of the target user. The knowledge of designing instruction using technology is a main part of this course. Moreover, students will recognize the need for balance between freedom and responsible behavior through the group activities in project-based learning. This course also intended to raise thinking and communication skills among students through project-based learning. Indeed, this soft skill is important for 21st century learners. Although this course is focusing on educational technology, the human factor is still the priority, which emphasized on the ethics of using the technology in teaching and learning only for the benefit of human being. In addition, students learn in the learning environment with equitable quality education and gender equality. Therefore, there is a need to revise this course by embedding SDGs to ensure issues related to SDG has explicitly been taught to the students.

The assessment of this course includes group work assignment particularly following the project-based learning approach. Students are required to design and develop a prototype of a multimedia application for teaching and learning by using Microsoft Power Point. They are also required to present their final product at the end of the semester. 60 students had attended this course. The followings are the course learning outcome.

Explain the concept and application of computer assisted learning (CAL), different types of instructional design models, the instructional design phases of ADDIE, and human computer interaction.

To apply learning theories and models to be used when designing educational software.

To describe information design, interaction design and visual design when designing educational software using a story board and a flowchart.

Present the planned documents needed while developing multimedia applications for teaching and learning.

Based on the preliminary review, the elements of sustainable justice are not being taught and are not explicitly mentioned in the learning outcome for this course. The elements have been silenced because they are not required by the Malaysian Qualifications Agency's programme learning outcomes, which are highlighted in the document. The elements identified below however are not being taught and mentioned explicitly in the learning outcome. For the four pillars of sustainable justice:

Environmental justice - paperless assignment submission as assignments are uploaded in e-learning.

Social Justice - fair distribution of the learning materials (i.e: lecture notes) and submission of learning activities through e-learning.

Economy justice - Students are equipped with stable Internet infrastructure (i.e: hotspot and wifi connection) which they can access learning content inside and outside of the classroom. Besides, providing online learning materials allowing students regardless of their economic status to have equal access to educational resources.

Cultural justice - Allows the students to voice out opinions and ideas that is relevant with their experiences and taking ownership with their knowledge development.

It is suggested that these four pillars of sustainable justice to be included in the learning outcome and explicitly mentioned in the assessment process. This resulted in the second revision, which focused on the delivery of structured and well-managed classroom activities that could be used to contribute to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), while also includes embedment of the following soft skills in the activities:

CS5: Ability to negotiate and reach agreement.

SC1: Ability to seek and manage relevant information from a variety of sources.

C3: Applying (Use a concept in a new situation or unprompted use of an abstraction.

Further, the course content, and particularly the learning activities, are already linked to the six learning pillars for sustainable development, according to the findings of the preliminary review (learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to transform oneself and society & learning to give and share). The remarks on the six pillars of sustainable development are as follows:

1. Learning to know

Understanding on the concepts of instructional design models and learning theories and how it can be applied in multimedia application for teaching and learning. This course also promotes equitable quality education and lifelong

learning opportunities for all. Through this course, students are treated equally without gender bias. Students will also be exposed with the knowledge of sustainability of education where it promotes paperless learning environment where technology promotes digital learning among students.

2. Learning to be

Students are fully immersed in learning activities since students are given problems that exist in real world context. This could lead to students' self-actualization, self-understanding, self-regulation and cultivating a sense of being versus having.

3. Learning to do

Students will prepare the technology-based teaching and learning activities that embed ded with sustainability messages on sustainability.

4. Learning to live together sustainably

Through this course, students are treated equally without gender bias and racist. This could lead to a peaceful and non-discriminatory society and human co-existence with the natural world.

5. Learning to transform oneself and society

Awareness on e-waste management, self-learning through the preparation of messages on sustainability, and paperless assignments and reports.

6. Learning to give and share

Learning activities are meant to be shared with other students through e-learning.

Additionally, the preliminary review also examines the course's content, particularly the learning activities associations with the 10Cs elements where the findings are such as follows:

Collaboration

Collaboration in groups to prepare technology-based teaching and learning activities.

Communication

Individual presentation, groups, explaining to others on the technology-based teaching and learning activities.

Critical thinking

Finding solution of issues that requires preparing the technology-based teaching and learning activities.

Creativity

Making the right way, effective and efficient in solving issues that requires preparing the technology-based teaching and learning activities.

Cross-cultural understanding

Solving issues that requires preparing the technology-based teaching and learning activities, while concerning on multi-racial society in Malaysia.

Connectivity

Involving interdisciplinary courses on the knowledge of e-waste management, and the principles and theories of teaching and learning in subject "Educational Psychology".

Critical reflection

The use of online assessment media makes it easy to evaluate and reflect on the success of learning, using quiz online, online reflection, and others.

Critical consciousness

Raising consciousness for being active in class and online discussion.

Constructing knowledge

Finding solution of issues that requires preparing the technology-based teaching and learning activities.

The preliminary review identified the need to integrate education for sustainable development (ESD) that addresses the four pillars of sustainable justice, the six learning pillars for sustainable development and the 10Cs elements. The existing course delivery and assessment focusses on the application of computer assisted learning (CAL). Initially, the course did not explicitly mention the elements of SDG. Therefore, there is a need to revise this course by embedding SDGs to ensure issues related to SDG has explicitly been taught to the students.

There are three SDGs themes to be infused in this course, which are SDG 4: Quality Education, SDG 5: Gender Equality and SDG 17: Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development

SDG 4: Quality Education

The notion that education is one of the most powerful and proven drivers for sustainable development is reaffirmed by achieving inclusive and high-quality education for all. By 2030, this objective will ensure that all girls and boys have received free elementary and secondary education. It also aspires to equalise access to inexpensive vocational training, erase gender and income gaps, and ensure universal access to a high-quality higher education.

SDG 5: Gender Equality

Ending all forms of discrimination against women and girls is not only a basic human right, but it is also essential for a long-term future; it has been demonstrated that empowering women and girls promotes economic growth and development. Gender equality is at the heart of UNDP's work, and we've made significant progress in the last 20 years. In comparison to 15 years ago, there are more girls in school currently, and gender parity in elementary education has been achieved in most regions.

SDG 17: Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development

The objectives are to improve North-South and South-South collaboration by assisting national programmes to meet all the objectives. Promoting international trade and assisting poor nations in increasing their exports are all important

aspects of building a global, rules-based, and equitable trading system that benefits everyone.

This paper will discuss the integration of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (SDG 4, SDG 5 and SDG 17) into Multimedia Development and Human Computer Interaction course. The new competences that the course developer wishes to develop including student’s knowledge, skills and attitudes about SDGs element and applied it in everyday lives.

Methodology

Figure 1 illustrates the six-stage capacity building approach proposed by Makrakis (2006) for training academic staff to include sustainability into their courses in light of the aforementioned characteristics, needs, and goals.

Figure 1: A Capacity Building Model (Makrakis, 2006)

Training in the initial stage is concentrated on identifying each trainee's didactic profile. An action plan for the particular training session is created based on the analysis of each trainee's profile (second stage). The training material, which combines theory and practise and is organised into theme units or modules that can be further developed while taking the trainee's needs into consideration, follows the action plan (third stage). The action plan's goals and objectives will be compared to the trainees' initial profiles as well as the evaluation of their learning results (fourth stage). By using their newly learned skills and information in the classroom, the end recipients, the learners, continue the evaluation process (fifth stage).

The DeCoRe+ methodology—an acronym for Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction introduced by Makrakis (2017)—was used for course revision in order to integrate sustainability and, in particular, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). By using a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development, the DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living texts. The following processes are among the six that make up DeCoRe+.

Diagnosing: Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.

Deconstructing: Analysing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.

Constructing: Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).

Reconstructing: Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.

Implementing: Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.

Finalising: Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction (Makrakis, 2017).

For the revised courses evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2019;2022) has been applied. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process which aims not only assess a course but more importantly to make whatever changes in order to improve it. Through the parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student guided by the course instructor creates a portfolio that he/she has to give back to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students’ DREAM portfolios must be analysed from the instructor and prepare a report for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide very

important information that the instructor and the students could discuss and find ways for improving the course.

Figure 3: The DREAM interaction (Makrakis, 2023)

Results

The course initially is pretty much “theoretical” and the assignment is in a “structured” format following the course syllabus without the content of SDGs element. The updated revision of the course implemented the real life, “authentic task” that integrated with some elements of SDG in the course curriculum structure. The authentic task, also known as an authentic assignment, is a task provided to students to evaluate their ability to apply standard-driven knowledge and abilities to real-world scenario. In other words, a task is regarded authentic when i) students are required to design their own replies rather than selecting from a list of options, and ii) the work reflects real-world issues.

The SDGs covered in this course include SDG 4, Quality Education which is ensuring the inclusivity and equitable quality of education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all, SDG 5, Gender Equality and SDG 17 which is strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development. The authentic tasks that integrated with SDGs element including provide reflections on the experiences that students face while developing instructional design. For SDG 5, students are encouraged to work in groups of 3 that consist of male and female students. In a group they need to discuss on how Behaviorism, Cognitivism and Constructivism emerged from our daily life routine.

Besides that, in this course, students are required to complete assignments on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) concept map. At first, they have to understand about the development of concept map. A concept map is a diagram or graphical tool that depicts the connections between concepts and ideas. In this case the concept is centred around the idea of SDG elements and how these elements can be linked to improve universal well-being.

In order to assess their understanding of the 17 concepts of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the students completed Assignment 1 (a) by creating a Group Work Concept Map as shown in Figure 4a and Figure 4b. In these Assignment 1 (a) and Assignment 1 (b), students are introduced to the familiarization and identifying connections between SDGs.

Figure 4a: Assignment 1 (a) - Group Work Concept Map

Figure 4b: Assignment 1 (b) - Individual Concept Map

Furthermore, the students completed Assignment 2 where they have to create a concept map for one selected SDG as depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Assignment 2 Creating a concept map for SDG 4: Quality Education

A total of 18 out of 31 students responded to the DREAM survey. These students are in their Second Semester. All 18 students had heard of the SDGs before. Most students had heard about the SDGs at the University, and a small number reported having learned about them in secondary school. During class discussion, it was discovered that all 31 students had been exposed to the concepts of the SDGs through various resources.

The findings showed that these students had never attended a course on this topic and had never created a project or written work similar to this course. The finding also showed that students had never worked on a project dealing with issues like the topic of this course. This course is relatively new to them as their background is in sports science. Most of them stated that they hope to learn new things, particularly in designing multimedia applications for educational purposes.

Discussion and conclusion

One of the issues students face after going through all these steps is that they are unaware of the Sustainable Development Goal. Students will gain a better understanding of the impact of environmental sustainability in daily life after being exposed to the SDG themes in this course in with other research (Manolis and Manoli 2021) This course's understanding of teaching, learning, and curriculum has not altered significantly; instead, the SDGs are linked in the teaching and assignments of students so that they are aware of their importance. The lesson learned from this experience is that incorporating SDG aspects into the teaching curriculum and achieving the objective of sustainable development is not impossible; however, all parties must work together to attain this goal. In this context, cooperation between teachers and students is essential in ensuring that the goals of the SDGs are achieved through this course.

The objective of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is to educate people about the importance of the global issues we face today, such as poverty, inequality, quality of life, and quality of education. The SDGs outline

three important components for a nation's well-being: economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental protection. The observed and expected impact of the revised course on teaching and learning is reflected in the learning activities provided by the course instructor and the awareness that was instilled in the students.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are important in today's classrooms. These objectives can help engage students in learning and serve as a guide for developing effective lesson plans. There are many reasons why educators should make use of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in their classrooms One of the substantial reasons is to make students appreciate their planet. Our planet faces numerous challenges today. Thus, it is important for the students to be educated with such issues. With the implementation of integrated SDGs element into the course, students can make an impact to the world they live in. The other substantial reason is the innovation of teaching method and pedagogical solutions such us interdisciplinary and student-centred approaches, which have an impact on students' self-regulated learning and the development of metacognitive strategies (Biasutti et al, 2016; Biasutti et al., 2018).

Additionally, the integrated SDGs in the course will provide students with a deeper understanding of the world they live in. Serious issues, such as poverty, inequality, economic growth, peace, and justice, that people might not be aware of should not be taken for granted. Students will gain a deeper understanding of the issues they face in their own lives, as well as those affecting people worldwide. These SDGs illustrate the economic, legal, and political foundations that underpin our society, as well as their intricacies. They bring to light issues that students may be unaware of or overlook.

Furthermore, learning about the SDGs has the effect of broadening students' horizons by exposing them to communities and experiences outside of their own. As a result, empathy is fostered in the classroom. Global leadership is based on empathy and inquiry. They help pupils become more aware of the larger world, as well as its values and identities. This helps develop children into more well-rounded global citizens and shows them how they can make a positive impact in the future.

Because the SDGs are so broad, they can be used to provide lesson ideas, new perspectives, and real-world context. For example, in this course, instructional design tasks can be enriched by allowing students to discuss the importance of providing quality education, including the causes and effects of developing a quality instructional design for effective education, whether in face-to-face or online learning formats. This issue is significant to address, especially as our world suddenly came into contact with the

COVID-19 pandemic. To comprehend traditional face-to-face learning, educators took on the challenge of providing education through online learning platforms. To ensure that online learning delivery is meaningful and resourceful, educators worldwide put extra effort into designing instructional learning materials suitable for online learners. Indirectly, students in this class also made an effort to provide a quality learning environment and education for all through instructional design tasks included in this course.

The SDGs are closely aligned with today's curriculum, which is worth noting. Rather than being something that requires work to integrate into the curriculum, educators can view the SDGs as an opportunity to add depth to their lesson plans. For example, the features of the SDGs were emphasized in this course to ensure that students were fully immersed in each target.

It's critical to spread the word about the SDGs once students have learned more about them. The more individuals actively think about and work on the Global Goals, the more likely it is that significant progress may be made. It is simple to get involved in this initiative, and you can quickly promote awareness through word of mouth or social media. The power of social media should not be underestimated; everyone has a social media platform where they can be a superhero. In this course, students are encouraged to share their final work through social media for a good cause, regardless of its nature. The use of social media as a tool facilitates the dissemination of knowledge about the SDGs. This finding aligns with research by Morsidi et al. (2021) and Jumaat et al. (2019), which suggest that social media can facilitate the effective sharing of knowledge and information. Furthermore, technology may aid in the development of pupils' socio-emotional skills (Ashari et al., 2018).

Global Goals provides a collection of eye-catching social media photographs that you may use for free. Make it a challenge to educate five friends, and then have each of them share the information with five others to start a chain reaction in your neighborhood. Post flyers in your office, gym, neighborhood, and other high-traffic places. Here are some SDG visual resources available for free use.

We emphasize the importance of cultivating global leadership in the classroom at Participate Learning, with the SDGs at the heart of this approach. We hope that this post has underlined the importance of these objectives and the role that they can – and should – play in enriching lesson planning, teaching the curriculum, and demonstrating to today's students that they have a place in the future world.

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The Educational Psychology Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

Humanity has been dealing with the effects of unsustainable economic development driven by profit maximization, which has led to excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources over the past few decades. Moreover, education should play a critical role in a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. Therefore, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards education for sustainability (EfS). The focus is to present the processes, practices, and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the Universiti Teknologi Malaysia entitled Multimedia Design and Human Computer Interaction course. The three models used in this study were 1) a capacity building model (Makrakis, 2006) for training academic staff to embed sustainability, 2) the DeCoRe plus interaction (Makrakis, 2017) for course revision to embed sustainability and 3) the DeCoRe plus interaction (Makrakis, 2017) for the revised courses evaluation during the implementation process. As a result, the revised course has been approved and used by all instructors of the course until last semester. Moreover, based on students' responses, the majority of them were excited to learn about the SDGs and volunteered to be involved in a project that incorporated all three.

Introduction

Over the last few decades, humanity has been facing the impacts of unsustainable economic development growth driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite the current initiatives aimed at reversing this unsustainable development process, there is still much to be done. Education systems at all levels, and higher education in particular, bear a significant responsibility for the sustainability crisis we are facing globally. This is mainly because consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions who drive society and the economy, as well as shape an unsustainable consumer culture (Makrakis, 2011). Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that "the scope and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented" (p. 3).

Education should play a critical role for a radical transformation through an alternative development model that places due emphasis on sustainable well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is closely aligned with Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being, as contrasted with the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The quest for "sustainable justice", a concept developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development—environment, society, economy, and culture—is of paramount importance in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth pointing out that while much has been invested in environmental education in the last decades, it has more

reflected in raising positive environmental attitudes (Biasutti & Frate, 2017), but less concern on environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum. However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not necessarily lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability have shown that lecturing, as expected, was the most prevalent teaching method, while role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, were rated much lower in use (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021). Teachers should revise their curricula and become more goal-oriented in curriculum planning, offering students some opportunity to develop some strategies, such as meta-cognitive strategies (Biasutti et al. 2018). Some recent research underlines how the use of different teaching methods in higher Education improves SDGs awareness and the active role of the students in the disseminating right actions (Ferguson & Rooft, 2020; Manolis et al. 2021).

A project entitled "Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability" (Makrakis, 2013, 2014) has revealed that one of the significant challenges of the 21st century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of and capable of transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. A similar challenge also accounts for teacher educators and classroom teachers at primary and secondary school levels. Teaching staff are key agents for change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to

teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016; Blake et al., 2013), as well as in transforming schools into sustainable institutions (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

The ICTeEfS project

One of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental degradation. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian policymakers must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby securing sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While there is the commitment from Asian leaders for EfS along with their concern for the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change makers are the teachers in the classroom (Biasutti et al., 2018).

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS) and, on the other hand, they have to capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. According to Woo, et. Al (2019), teachers not in the aligned thinking where ICT does better in class-based instruction for promoting cooperation and reflection in learning. Thus, implementation of ICT in education is still under-utilized as teachers are still incapable in ICT teaching. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

- LI. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.
- LII. Build the capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a broad ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.
- LIII. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.
- LIV. Develop innovative teaching, learning and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning and curriculum.
- LV. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, we focus on presenting the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the Universiti Teknologi Malaysia entitled Multimedia Design and Human Computer Interaction course. Deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing it through the lens of SDGs. The following six main questions will be considered: The **first question is the "What"**, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The **second and third questions refer to "Why"** (justifying the reasons for revision) and **"Where"** describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The **fourth question is the "How" question**, describing the methodologies used for the revision and the course assessment during the implementation process. The **fifth question is the "Now What"** that shows how the revised and/or updated revision of the course looks like, how it has changed from "What" was before. Lastly, the **sixth question is the "So What?"** question, which focuses on discussing the challenges encountered while navigating all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience and how will it affect the

beneficiaries such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the next actions?

The What, Why and Where Questions for Revising Multimedia Design and Human Computer Interaction course: Deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing it through the lens of SDGs

The purpose of this paper was to emphasize the importance of academic staff development and programs targeted at staff capacity building as a catalyst for curriculum transformation toward education for sustainable development (ESD). The incorporation of education for sustainable development (ESD) into university curricula presents a new challenge to the academic system. Many universities have undertaken activities to implement this in recent years, and numerous case studies of such processes have been documented. However, transforming university curricula in a way that makes them 'built-in' sustainability remains a significant challenge.

Educational Psychology is a compulsory course offered to first-year students at the School of Education, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. The Educational Psychology course has excellent relevance for teachers, as it helps them achieve their goals while teaching students in the classroom. Educational Psychology aims to assist teachers in organizing material to be taught to children while also studying heredity, growth, and maturation, as well as environmental influences, language development, thinking, and the process of socialization concerning their effects on the child as a learner.

For all prospective teachers currently studying in the School of Education, this course introduces students to the importance of educational psychology, providing the basics of various concepts related to learning, cognition, motivation, and classroom practice. This course is designed to facilitate students' understanding of differences among students, especially in terms of their cognitive, emotional, and social development during the schooling age, through active learning activities and discussions. In addition, the course is crafted to assist students in acquiring knowledge and understanding psychological concepts, principles and theories relating to teaching practice and learning strategies. The course involves assessments that evaluate students' understanding and ability to apply relevant principles and theories related to classroom teaching through various types of assessments.

This course is delivered through lecture, active learning and blended learning including using of e-Learning (LMS), group discussion, mini scale research and online quizzes that related with the concept and theories of Educational psychology. Besides, students are allowed to explore a phenomenon in a classroom setting after getting permission to access the class.

This course is significant in that it requires us to consider what it means to be an effective teacher, as well as how teachers are trained and developed in order to improve the quality of their professionalism and competence.

As part of this course, students will engage in activities that enable them to evaluate the practicality and applicability of various learning theories and their applications in teaching and learning practices. Therefore, students will have opportunities to acquire knowledge of developmental (human development) and learning theories, as well as their applications in teaching and learning practices, at all levels of Bloom's Taxonomy, ranging from the knowledge to the synthesis level. They also possess the competence to evaluate the practicability and applicability of various learning theories and their applications in teaching and learning practices. Additionally, students are capable of producing a report with references from various resources to effectively communicate the application of educational psychology concepts through the analysis of teaching practices in a classroom setting.

For this course, the students are assessed through group work and individual assignments. Assessment on coursework constitutes 60% and the final exam is 40%. There are four tasks to complete by every student in the coursework as follows:

1. Quizzes: It can be in paper-and-pencil or online format. There are two quizzes, each comprised of objective questions, to be completed at weeks 5 and 9.
2. Concept Map Weekly Notes: This is an individual assignment, and each student should provide a concept map for all topics.
3. Academic report: Students have two options to do their project: (1) classroom observation or (2) observation of behaviour based on real-life cases in a school setting. Focus on students' behaviors and explain their occurrences, consequences, etc., through educational psychology perspectives. The report would be based on a pseudo collaborative problem-based research that conduct as a group work.
4. Presentation of report: This is a group assignment. Each group is assigned to present their report verbally face-to-face.

A review was conducted to ascertain the components of sustainable development in this Educational Psychology course. It is discovered that the elements of sustainable justice are not being taught directly and are not explicitly mentioned in the learning objectives. The elements of sustainable justice

have not been mentioned because they are not required by the Malaysian Qualifications Framework (MQF). The Malaysian Qualifications Framework (MQF) is Malaysia's declaration regarding its qualifications and their quality with the country's education system. However, the sustainability aspects have been addressed through SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities) in the revised course. This course promotes equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all. Through this course, students are treated equally without gender bias among multi-racial students. This course also encouraged students to understand a variety of human performances and abilities to make sure SDG10 was implemented in class.

For the four pillars of sustainable justice:

- i. Environmental justice - paperless assignment submission as assignments are uploaded in e-learning.
- ii. Social justice - fair distribution of the learning materials (i.e: lecture notes) and submission of learning activities through e-learning. They can download learning materials from e-learning as well as upload their work via template provided
- iii. Economic justice - Students are equipped with stable Internet infrastructure (i.e., hotspot and Wi-Fi connection), which they can access to learn content inside and outside the classroom. Additionally, through the use of online learning materials, students, regardless of their socioeconomic status, are afforded equal access to educational resources.
- iv. Cultural justice - Allows students to voice their opinions and ideas that are relevant to their experiences and take ownership of their knowledge development. Sensitive issues are avoided.

It is suggested that these four pillars of sustainable justice be integrated into the course content, regardless of gender, race, or performance, to ensure fair opportunities throughout the course. During the course revision, the learning activities are aligned with the six learning pillars for sustainable development, including learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to transform oneself and society, and learning to give and share. The remarks on the six pillars of sustainable development are as follows:

Learning to know

Understanding on the concepts of developmental (human development) and learning theories and their applications in teaching and learning practices at all levels of Bloom's Taxonomy (from knowledge to synthesis level). This course also promotes equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all. Through this course, students are treated equally without gender, race and culture bias.

Learning to be

Students are fully immersed in learning activities since students are given problems that exist in real-world contexts through mini-scale research. This could lead to students' self-actualization, self-understanding, self-regulation and cultivating a sense of being versus having.

Learning to do

Students will experience conducting mini-scale research through exploring a phenomenon in a classroom setting. First, students will identify the area (in weekly topics) that they want to investigate (in-group). Then, they will conduct mini-research through observation or survey in an actual setting to gather the data and compare it to the theories they have learned before.

Learning to live together sustainably

Through this course, students are treated equally, without regard to gender bias or racism. This could lead to a peaceful and non-discriminatory society, as well as harmonious human coexistence with the natural world. Actively engage different groups in completing projects/assignments and class activities.

Learning to transform oneself and society

Awareness of children's verities and human development in a global world. Using paperless assignments and reports. From the findings, students will get the differences between the facts on learning theories and the actual setting.

Learning to give and share

Create opportunities for sharing ideas and experiences and finding the best solutions through individual presentations for academic reports.

Additionally, the preliminary review also examines the course's content, particularly the learning activities associated with the 10Cs elements, where the findings are as follows:

- **Collaboration**

Work with others in groups, resolving conflicts, making decisions, solving problems, negotiating, and fostering recognition and respect. Listen, clarify, organize, participate, and build positive relationships. In this class, the students collaborate with small group in order to carry out the best mini scale research.

- **Communication**
Interacting, communicating with a broader audience (school or tuition centre), justifying, discussing, and sharing different issues faced by members.
- **Critical thinking**
For example, finding solutions to identify problems in classroom settings through mini-scale research. A selection of method and sampling.
- **Creativity**
For instance, the creative elements include creating, designing, imagining, inventing, improving, and changing. The students draft and plan a mini-scale research project using effective and creative methods among group members.
- **Cross-cultural understanding**
Interpersonal competencies emphasized on communication and awareness on searching issues related to diversity - concern on multi racial society in Malaysia)
- **Connectivity**
This involved interdisciplinary courses on the knowledge of human development and teaching and learning theories and strategies.
- **Critical reflection**
Periodically reflections on teaching session in class and online
- **Critical consciousness**
This include raising consciousness for being active in class and online discussion.
- **Constructing knowledge**
Students find a solution in real setting problem through mini scale research using appropriate method and identify a better result.

The preliminary review identified areas that require additional emphasis in terms of course development for integrating education for sustainable development (ESD) which in specific addresses the four pillars of sustainable justice, the six learning pillars for sustainable development and the 10Cs elements. Initially, the course did not explicitly mention the elements of SDG. Therefore, there is a need to revise this course by embedding SDGs to ensure issues related to SDG has explicitly been taught to the students.

There are three SDGs themes to be infused in this course, which are SDG 4: Quality Education, SDG 5: Gender Equality and SDG 10: Reduced Inequality

- SDG 4: Quality Education

The 2030 SDGs agenda contains 17 goals including a new global education goal (SDG 4). SDG 4 is to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all and has seven targets and three means of implementation. The aim of SDG 4 to ensure equal access for all students regardless high or low status economy, typical or untypical students to affordable teaching and learning and to eliminate disparities in gender and wealth in order to achieve universal access to a high-quality higher education.

- SDG 5: Gender Equality

The aim of SDG 5 to value every gender equally to progress at the right place. A society attains better development in all aspects when both genders are entitled to similar opportunities. When a community reaches gender equality, everyone enjoys the same privileges and gets similar scopes in education and achieve good performances. This is an important area to be discuss in the course especially looking at the important girls and boys in receiving the best education.

- SDG 10: Reduced Inequality

SDG 10 at reducing inequality within and among countries. This SDG calls for reducing inequalities in income as well as those based on age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status within a country. The goal also addresses inequalities among countries, including those related to representation, migration and development assistance. Policies should be universal in principle, paying attention to the needs of disadvantaged and marginalized populations.

This paper will discuss the integration of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (SDG 4, SDG 5 and SDG 10) into Educational Psychology course.

Methodologies: The How Question

In light of the above discussed features, needs and objectives, a six-stages capacity building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006) was used in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The Capacity Building Model by Makrakis (2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on the diagnosis of the didactic profile of every trainee. Based on the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and structured in thematic units, or modules that can be further enriched, considering the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The same process of evaluation is continued for the final recipients, the learners through transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages that help to sustain the proper functioning and possible upgrading of the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and most specifically the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction advanced by Makrakis (2017) was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes.

43. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
44. **Deconstructing:** Analyzing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
45. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
46. **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.

47. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
48. **Finalizing:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction (Makrakis, 2017)

For the revised courses evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2023; 2022) has been applied. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process which aims not only assess a course but more importantly to make whatever changes in order to improve it. Through the parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student guided by the course instructor creates a portfolio that he/she has to give back to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students' DREAM portfolios must be analyzed from the instructor and prepare a report for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide very important information that the instructor and students can discuss and use to find ways to improve the course.

Figure 3: The DREAM interaction (Makrakis, 2023)

Results

The revised course has been approved and used by all instructors of the course until last semester. In every semester, there are minimum of two instructors teaching the course. Moreover, based on students' response, majority of them excited to know about SDG and volunteered to involve in project that embedded all three SDG's. The SDGs covered in this course include SDG 4, Quality Education that is ensuring the inclusivity and equitable quality of education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all, SDG 5, Gender Equality and SDG 10 which is to reduce inequalities in everything in the global situation for sustainable development. More than half of the class are able to show understanding of the 3 SDG's and able to relate with the topic in Educational Psychology. In this course, students are encouraged to work in group of 4 that consists of male and female students. They need to discuss on how to embed and relate SDG's in the topics that they have learned along the semester. In order to assess their understanding of the 17 concepts of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the students completed Assignment 1 (a) by creating a Group Work Concept Map as shown in Figure 1. In these Assignment 1 (a) and Assignment 1 (b), students are introduced to the familiarization and identifying connections between SDGs.

Figure 4: Assignment 1 (a) - Group Work Concept Map

Figure 5: Assignment 1 (b) - Individual Concept Map

Figure 6: Assignment 1 (b) - Individual Concept Map

The course was implemented 100% through online learning. Forty-four students completed both pre and post survey out of 85 students in the class. The remaining students completed

only one of the pre or post. The overall finding showed that all 44 students responded to NO when they were asked about the attending a course related to sustainable development goal in the past. Since the all students are in their first year, this is the first time they are exposed to the similar classes or courses.

At end of the course students' feedback on the impact of the course were collected and the results are as follow:

<p>Impact on academic development</p>	<p>The findings showed that the impact on their knowledge that contributes to their academic development as follow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theories learned in this course can be linked with other subjects where why sometimes we feel hard to accept changes with our own understanding as this were explained by schemas. • This subject also taught students on how to look at ample of knowledge with different views that helps to alter them accordingly.
<p>Impact on competency and professional development</p>	<p>The findings showed that the impact on their professional development that makes them more competent in terms of employment are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This course enhances my knowledge to understand more students' behaviour and the ways to create conducive class environment in order to achieve learning objective. • This course helps me to understand my task and responsibilities as a future teacher since this subject teach a lot on the do and the don'ts of a teacher. • This course provides lots of interesting information such as communication skills and technique to deliver knowledge. • This course assists me to enhance my creativity in delivering teaching process since this course shared some activities that could attract students' attention. • This subject definitely ignites my passion towards

	<p>understanding my students in future as it was delivered very smoothly.</p>
<p>Impact on the community and country</p>	<p>The findings showed that the impact on social that turn the community and country more sustainable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This course helps me to understand learners' diversity • This course teaches me how to interact with students with different abilities so that the students will be feel comfortable to communicate with the educators • This course helps me in my social development on how to communicate with community from different age group I learnt the significance of being friendly with students when teaching • I have learnt that teaching is only about giving knowledge but also taking knowledge back • I can understand why some people thinks that education is not important because of their mindset when I related them with what I have learnt in this course. • I feel very inspired to learn this subject and gave the community back what I have learnt.
<p>Impact on personality</p>	<p>The findings showed that impact on your personality are especially during the pandemic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This course open up my mind to identify my weaknesses and improve it such as applying effective learning technique and time management • After attending this course, I have become someone who taking care more on my environment • I have changed my view of looking at others opinion and not underestimating people. • This course helps me to accept all thing in a positive

	ways and become more open and not have a quick prejudgement.
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Discussion

One of the problems students face after going through all these steps is that they are unaware of their Sustainable Development Goals. After exploring the SDG theme in this course, students will gain a deeper understanding of the impact of environmental sustainability on their daily lives. This result is in line with the previous research about the importance of raising awareness about SDGs (Ferguson & Roofe, 2020; Manolis et Manoli 2021). The teaching, learning and curriculum understanding of this course has not changed significantly. Instead, the SDGs are integrated into student education and assignments, enabling students to recognize their importance. The lesson learned from this experience is that it is not impossible to incorporate aspects of the SDG into the educational curriculum and achieve the goals of sustainable development. Furthermore, the use of social media as a tool facilitates the spread of awareness about climate change and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This finding aligns with research by Morsidi et al. (2021) and Jumaat et al. (2019), which suggest that social media can facilitate the effective sharing of knowledge and information. In addition, technology could help in students' socio-emotions development (Ashari et al., 2018). However, all parties must work together to achieve this goal. The lesson learned from this experience is that it is not impossible to incorporate aspects of the SDG into the educational curriculum and achieve the goals of sustainable development. In this context, cooperation between teachers and students is very important in ensuring that the goals of the SDGs are achieved through this course.

Furthermore, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aim to bring individuals from all over the world together to improve people's lives. They are a set of common goals set by the United Nations to help us overcome global challenges such as poverty, inequality, climate change, and others. They are attempting to merge three crucial components for the future: economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental conservation. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) play an important role in today's schools. As a blueprint for making the world a better place, these goals can be used to engage students and inform lesson ideas. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were established with the aim of drawing attention to some of the world's most pressing environmental challenges. All of these challenges, including sanitation, sustainability, pollution, and climate change, are addressed. The SDGs, on the other hand, are about more than raising awareness. They also broke down each goal into a series of attainable sub-goals. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) point to minor steps that can be taken to help the world cope with climate change. The SDGs indicate smaller ways to contribute to climate action for the benefit of the planet. Tackling a subject like climate change is a great problem, but the SDGs show smaller ways to contribute to

climate action for the benefit of the globe. Educators can illustrate to their students how they can help to improve the world in which they live.

Based on these findings, it is clear that implementing the SDGs in education is a foundational step for all of the SDGs. The links between human development and SDGs are clear, and the importance of pursuing them as pillars of progress is firmly established. Making smart investments in education for the most vulnerable is important, and we need to do it based on sound evidence. This guide can be used to point practitioners toward the areas of most promise. In addition, education is essential to meeting the goals of the SDGs. In particular, primary education is recognized as a key factor in reducing poverty and increasing opportunities for all. As governments and the international community increasingly focus on meeting the needs of citizens of middle-income countries, it is critical to continue to focus on the needs of the most marginalized and vulnerable groups. It is equally important for educational planning to benefit from the most rigorous research available; this document can guide practitioners towards the most promising areas. Education plays a transformational role in addressing all development challenges in the post-2015 era.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are about more than just the environment. Poverty, injustice, economic growth, peace, and justice are just a few of the major, life-altering issues they address. Students will gain a deeper understanding of the difficulties they face in their own lives, as well as those that affect people worldwide. The economic, legal, and political foundations that underlie our society, as well as their complexities, are depicted in these SDGs. They bring concerns to light that students may be unaware of or dismiss. Learning about the SDGs also exposes students to a variety of groups and experiences outside of their own. Empathy is so fostered in the classroom as a result. Empathy and inquiry are the foundations of global leadership. They help pupils become more aware of the larger world, as well as its values and identities. This aids in the development of kids into more well-rounded global citizens and demonstrates to them how they can make a difference in the future.

Additionally, because the SDGs are so wide, they can be used to bring new views and real-world context to educational ideas. Climate change themes can be studied in geography and science schools, such as the causes and effects of the increase in average world temperature, or how climate change is creating natural disasters like tsunamis and tropical storms. For example in my course, classes might examine not only the Educational Psychology topic, but also the social factors that allow them to thrive, such as a lack of inequality development and so on. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a fantastic filter for broadening and improving educational plans. Educators can boost student engagement in the classroom by demonstrating how the subjects they teach have real-world applications.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are more than a collection of principles. Each SDG has particular time-bound

targets that are SMART. Many of these objectives will be achieved in the coming years, with some of the more challenging challenges being postponed until 2030. This allows educators to see not just which components of the goal are most important, but also what can be done in a short amount of time. As the SDGs show, even small adjustments may have a big impact on the world. Specific, measurable, realistic, practical, and timely goals can be utilised to focus classroom discussion.

The United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are more than a set of concepts. SMART time-bound targets are assigned to each SDG. Many of these goals will be met in the next few years, with some of the more difficult issues being deferred until 2030. This enables educators to identify not only which aspects of the objective are the most important, but also what can be accomplished in a short period of time. As the SDGs demonstrate, even minor changes can have a significant influence on the world. To drive classroom discussion, use specific, quantifiable, realistic, practical, and timely goals.

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Basic Food Preparation and Nutrition course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

Higher Education Institutions play a crucial role in the development of sustainability, and a rising number of stakeholders anticipate that they will be sustainable organizations. However, this can only be accomplished by overcoming obstacles and difficulties. The proposed ICTeEfs project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to utilize innovative teaching techniques and pedagogies that promote sustainable education. The project requires extensive and integrated planning of ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education, necessitating modifications to teaching and learning practices. This paper focuses on the procedures, techniques, and outcomes of redesigning an introductory-level course entitled Basic Food Preparation and Nutrition. The Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction (DeCoRe+) technique was employed to revise this course, incorporating sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The newly created module for this course incorporates three SDG topics: SDG 1: End Poverty, SDG 2: Zero Hunger, and SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth. The revised food-related education course is unquestionably in line with these educational practices, which places SDG's infusion at the proper place, resulting in holistic and highly skilled graduates. Community services aimed at achieving the SDGs will expand once it is fully implemented in higher education institutions.

Introduction

Humanity is confronted with two significant adaptation challenges: natural environmental challenges posed by climate change and global humanitarian challenges related to ensuring the well-being of all. In recent decades, humanity has faced the consequences of unsustainable economic development driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014, 2021; Kashima, 2020). Despite current initiatives to reverse such an unsustainable development process, much work remains to be done. Education systems at all levels, particularly higher education, bear responsibility for the global sustainability crisis. This is largely because the individuals who drive society and the economy, creating an unsustainable consumer culture, are the products of educational institutions: consumers, leaders, and decision-makers (Makrakis 2011). Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that “the scopes and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented” (p. 3). There is an urgent need to educate and motivate professionals, citizens, current and future leaders, and others to shift their focus to a more sustainable environment.

Developing cultures of sustainability that highlight and reward the ideas and practices that will facilitate the transition to a sustainable lifestyle is one way ahead. Education should play a critical role in achieving a radical transformation through an alternative development model that prioritizes long-term well-being. In our understanding, sustainable well-being is closely aligned with Aristotle's eudaimonic well-

being, as contrasted with the prevailing hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The pursuit of "sustainability justice," a concept coined by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development — environment, society, economy, and culture — is of the most importance in learning to improve oneself and society.

It is essential to note that although significant resources have been invested in environmental education over the past few decades, this investment has had a more significant impact on fostering favorable environmental attitudes than on promoting ecological action. Environmental action necessitates a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum to effectively translate environmental knowledge and consciousness into action. However, merely educating citizens to a higher degree does not inevitably result in more sustainable patterns of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The disparity between environmental beliefs and environmental behavior is not solely attributable to educational techniques but also several other factors. Recent studies on curriculum creation, focusing on sustainability, indicate that, as expected, lecturing is the most popular teaching approach. However, role play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more appropriate, were rated far lower in terms of frequency of usage (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021). Teachers should design their curricula and pay more attention to curriculum planning and meta-cognitive strategies (Biasutti et al. 2018). The literature highlights how the use of a variety of teaching methods enhances students' awareness of the

SDGs and their active role in disseminating the right actions (Ferguson and Roofe, 2020; Manolis et al., 2021).

The Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability project, conducted by Makrakis (2013) and Makrakis (2014), revealed that the greatest challenge of the 21st century for institutions of higher education is to train professionals capable of transforming their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. The same difficulty applies to teacher educators and classroom instructors at the elementary and secondary levels. Teaching staff are the change agents in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016;2018; Blake et al., 2013) and in making schools sustainable (Biasutti et al., 2016;2018; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013; Zachariou et al., 2013).

The ICTeEfS project

There is an urgent need for global sustainability, as "filling the needs of the present without sacrificing future generations' ability to fulfill their own needs" may become unattainable due to numerous challenges (Rockström, Bai, & DeVries, 2018). Environmental degradation has been one of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth. Recent climate-related disasters in the region underscore the need for Asian policymakers to take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the effects of climate change, thereby securing long-term economic growth. Education for sustainability (EfS) is one way to meet these challenges. While Asian leaders are committed to EfS and are concerned about the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the true change agents are teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS), and on the other hand, they must capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing Education for Sustainability to all in-service subject teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. Teaching practices with ICT enhance students to be more collaborative, interactive, and motivated (Alonso-Garcia et al., 2019). However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Considering all the challenges and shortages outlined in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to utilize innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards

education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

1. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.
2. Build the capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education to enable them to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers' training program on education for sustainability.
3. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program, enabled by blended learning, that focuses on integrating education for sustainability across school curricula.
4. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
5. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the undergraduate level entitled Basic Food Preparation and Nutrition considering six main questions: The **first question is the "What" question**, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The **second and third questions refer to "Why"** (justifying the reasons for revision) and **"Where"** describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The **fourth question is the "how" question, describing the methodologies used for revision and** course assessment during the implementation process. The **fifth question is the "Now What"** that shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course appears and how it has changed from its previous iteration. Lastly, the **sixth question is the "So What?"** that focuses on discussing the challenges encountered while going through all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for

not being done and why, and what would be the following actions?

The “What” Question

As an overview, this course provides students with theoretical knowledge in food nutrition and food preparation. For technical content, students are trained to acquire skills and gain experience in cooking activities that take place every week, following specific cooking themes. Each cooking theme encompasses food sanitation, food safety, time management, food cost, nutritious food ingredients, well-planned menu planning, proper etiquette, and attractive presentation and evaluation of the food product. Theoretically, students learn the fundamental concepts of nutritional intake, as well as the nutritional aspects of food preparation. The students will conduct a food demonstration as a group project with the selected community, demonstrating critical thinking skills in fulfilling the food innovation tasks for their practical cooking tests.

This course addresses both food education at higher educational institutions and the individual teacher trainee's ability to handle and react to the numerous scientific facts and paradigms commonly related to food, health, and a sustainable lifestyle. According to previous studies, food has the potential to play a significant role in everyday activities in classroom settings, both in planned educational activities and in meal situations. This implies that a holistic understanding of food in teaching and learning is required for long-term work with food as a natural part of everyday activities. The course should be revised to incorporate the SDGs into the curriculum, allowing students to explore issues related to food and the SDGs in greater depth. Since students come into contact with food daily, they possess contextual knowledge that can be applied to new observations. As a result, fundamental sustainable practices are more relevant to them than they were previously. This course is a prerequisite for SPPL2142 (Foodservice Operations), which is scheduled to be taken in the 5th Semester. Before enrolling in this advanced Foodservice Operations course, students must master all the essential skills related to basic cooking, food preparation, and nutrition.

The following are the objectives of the course before the course revision:

1. Possess basic knowledge of food nutrition and food preparation (PLO1-KW Knowledge)
2. Demonstrate skills in food preparation with good time management, modern kitchen utensil handling, food safety and sanitation application, and product evaluation (PLO2 –AP Application)
3. Practice the knowledge and skills in food preparation (PLO3 – Practical Skills)

4. Produce food products based on food recipe innovation by applying concepts in food nutrition and preparation (PLO5 – TH Thinking Skills)

For this course, the students are assessed through Group work assignments and individual assignments. Examples of assessment methods based on the Program Learning Outcomes (PLOs):

- i. Possess basic knowledge of food nutrition and food preparation (PLO1-KW Knowledge)

Students are assessed individually through quizzes, tests and final exams

- ii. Demonstrate skills in food preparation with good time management, modern kitchen utensil handling, food safety and sanitation application, and product evaluation (PLO2 –AP Application)

Students are assessed individually and in groups through the Weekly Practical of Food Preparation and Cooking Skills (Competency Assessment)

- iii. Practice the knowledge and skills in food preparation (PLO3 - Practical)

Students are assessed through short-term kitchen Wizard activities with the community. They are assessed through group assessment

- iv. Produce food products based on food recipe innovation by applying concepts in food nutrition and preparation (PLO5 – TH Thinking Skills)

Students are assessed in groups where they have to delegate tasks on doing the recipe conversion, menu development, preparing the costing, order for raw materials, and conducting the on-site food and cooking demo with the intended community.

This course includes learning activities related to cooking, where students learn how home and domestic cooking differ from commercial cooking, which adheres to industry-based standards. For example, they learn about food safety systems such as Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP). The students also learn about basic Vegetable Cutting in French, which is globally utilized as a culinary term (such as

- Chiffonade (shredded)
- Brunoise (fine dice)
- Macedoine (large dice)
- Julienne (match stick cuts)
- Batonnet (significant match stick cuts)

Essentially, the students will reevaluate how they prepare food at home based on their previous experience. Students who are not exposed to home cooking will have to rely on their classmates for support. The learning activities are connected to the course objectives. For example, in each practical cooking class, students will be provided with a recipe prepared by the instructor prior to the class. The students must prepare a visual recipe (e.g., a sketch, diagrams, graphics, images, etc.). They also have to re-write the recipe in a pocket-sized notebook. It can be observed that this kind of activity helps students memorize recipes by mastering the knowledge of ingredients and step-by-step food preparation methods.

The “Why” question

In Malaysia, for example, there is a deficiency in teaching authentic cuisine to multi-ethnic people due to the seasonal nature of the ingredients. Many books and instructional materials on culinary topics are available in both English and French. As a result, students must become fluent in the culinary jargon of these languages. A preliminary review was conducted to determine the components of sustainable development that would be covered in this Basic Food and Nutrition course. During the course of this investigation, it was discovered that the elements of sustainable justice were neither taught nor explicitly mentioned in the learning outcomes. Due to the fact that they are not required by the Malaysian Qualifications Agency's program learning outcomes, as highlighted in the paper, these elements have been omitted. It is important to note that none of the elements listed below are explicitly taught or acknowledged within the learning outcomes. For the four pillars of sustainable justice:

1. Environmental justice - paperless assignment submission, as assignments are uploaded to the e-learning platform. Students upload their pictures of Team Happy Hour! Session as an evidence of group meetings
2. Social justice - fair distribution of the learning materials (i.e, lecture notes) and submission of learning activities through e-learning. The class materials are also uploaded through a WhatsApp group that has been created specifically for the subject.
3. Economic justice - Students are equipped with stable Internet infrastructure (i.e., hotspot and Wifi connection), which they can access to learn content inside and outside the classroom. Additionally, through the use of online learning materials, students, regardless of their socioeconomic status, are afforded equal access to educational resources.

4. Cultural justice enables students to express their opinions and ideas that are relevant to their experiences, thereby taking ownership of their knowledge development.

These soft skills are embedded in the activities:

TH3 (ability to look for alternative ideas and creative solutions)

C4: Applying (application)

A3: Value (attach value and express personal opinions)

P5: Set (Readiness) - Bloom Taxonomy (Psychomotor)

These four pillars of sustainable justice could be integrated into the course content by incorporating digital literacy components into the assessment process, as it has become a significant part of the teaching and learning requirements. This resulted in the second revision, which focused on the delivery of structured and well-managed classroom activities that could be used to contribute to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), while also including embedment of the following soft skills in the activities:

- CS2: Ability to actively listen and respond to the ideas of other people
- CS3: Ability to make clear and confident presentations appropriate to the audience
- CS4: Ability to use technology in presentation
- ET1: Act ethically, with integrity and social responsibility
- ET2: Understand the economic, environmental, and sociocultural impacts of professional practice
- C2: Comprehension (understanding)
- A2: Respond (React and participate actively)
- A3: Value (attach value and express personal opinions)
- P2: Set (Readiness) - Bloom Taxonomy (Psychomotor)

Further, the course content, and particularly the learning activities, are already linked to the six learning pillars for sustainable development, according to the findings of the preliminary review (learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to transform oneself and society & learning to give and share). The remarks on the six pillars of sustainable development are as follows:

1. Learning to know

Various concepts and principles of cooking methods, culinary terms, and nutritive value of foods.

2. Learning to be

Developing individual capacity to be skilled culinary professionals. Students learn about future jobs and are exposed to industry skill requirements, which differ significantly from their academic context—a degree program in teacher education. From this, the students learn about the differences between being a teacher and being an industrial worker. Furthermore, involvement in the Free Meal Project fosters a spirit of volunteerism among students and staff, allowing them to channel their generosity and willingness in terms of time or energy.

3. Learning to do

Designing the lesson plan for the cooking demonstration session. The assignment is Short Term Food Course: Kitchen Wizard. They have to plan for the session, job delegation, and menu that are going to be shared with others.

5. Learning to live together sustainably

The students actively engage with various groups, including other UTM students, preschoolers, and community-based parent-led playgroups, in completing projects, assignments, and class activities.

5. Learning to transform oneself and society

Community engagement (short-term Food course –Kitchen Wizard)

6. Learning to give and share

(e.g. create opportunities for sharing ideas and experiences and finding the best solutions)

Online video-sharing on weekly practical cooking.
Exchanging the pictures of their food products and sharing the comments from the class instructor and lecturer)

Additionally, the preliminary review also examines the course's content, particularly the learning activities associated with the 10Cs elements, where the findings are as follows:

Collaboration

Work with others in groups, resolving conflicts, making decisions, solving problems, negotiating, and fostering recognition and respect. Listen, clarify, organize, participate, and build positive relationships. Conduct the Short-term Food

Course – Kitchen Wizards with the community (preschoolers / community-based parent-led playgroup)

Communication

Interacting, communicating with a broader audience (school communities), justifying, discussing, sharing, and articulating. Conduct the Short-term Food Course – Kitchen Wizards with the community, specifically preschoolers and community-based parent-led playgroups. Reviewing the YouTube or cooking show to learn how to conduct the cooking demonstration.

Critical thinking

Finding the best teaching methods to teach others through cooking demonstrations. Planning a creative menu for the Food Innovation task, where they must initiate the menu development process. This involves critical and creative thinking skills.

Creativity

Teaching plans with practical and creative teaching aids – an interesting menu, step-by-step cooking preparation

Cross-cultural understanding

(e.g., Interpersonal competencies: communication and awareness of different cuisines (local/ international/ fusion) related to diversity - concern on multi-racial society in Malaysia). They also learn how to prepare foods for individuals with special diets, including therapeutic diets such as hypertension menus and diabetic menus, as well as kids' menus and vegetarian menus.

Connectivity

- multidisciplinary (pre-requisite course for SPPL2142 Foodservice Operations – the technical content is more advanced where the students have to set up a mock restaurant)
- Basic exposure before they go for Industrial Training. Data on Industrial Training shows that some of the students chose the food industry as their internship placement.

Critical reflection

Periodically, reflections on the food products so that they learn what are the mistakes they did during weekly practical cooking activities in class and online. The students have to jot down every comment and remark related to their food products

Critical consciousness

Raising awareness of being active in class (dealing with food, avoiding food contamination, planning well, and managing time) and being more helpful to others as they work in groups.

Constructing knowledge

Develop digital artifacts for empowerment, advocacy, and capacity building. In this course, students will learn about developing compelling procedural text through the recipe recognition process.

Furthermore, these are the kinds of knowledge interest that are promoted in this course:

1. Technical/instrumental knowledge (transmit information-knowledge)
 - Knowledge on carry out food preparation tasks, cooking different types of food products
 2. practical knowledge (focus on deep understanding of the subject)
 - Knowledge of different cooking methods, ability to master culinary skills, ability to conduct sensory testing.
 3. - Emancipatory knowledge (creating conditions for empowerment and change towards a sustainable society)
 - Students learned how to produce a video that captures the teaching and learning sessions of the weekly practical cooking sessions.
- They learn the technological aspects independently – they must present a critical reflection based on their performance during the weekly practical cooking session.

The “Where” question

These are the questions that guide the review and provide the revision with guidance on how to incorporate ESD into the course:

1. *Can we give priorities on using local produce in our cooking ingredients?*

Due to limitations of costs provided by the university, we have limited choice in selecting the food ingredients to be included in the class.

We were not concerned about students’ background in food literacy; there is no preliminary assessment on students’ food literacy. The concept of knowledge

construction is not addressed during the development of learning outcomes due to the nature of the Outcome-Based Education System, where the learning process is characterized by specific mastery. ie, content or skills. Thereby,

2. *What are the mechanisms that need to be determined to allow the skills or content to be mastered?*
3. *How to implement sustainable practices in the teaching and learning of this subject?*
4. *In what way transformative learning can be identified from the critical reflections?*

The preliminary review identified areas that require additional emphasis in terms of course development for integrating education for sustainable development (ESD), which specifically addresses the four pillars of sustainable justice, the six learning pillars for sustainable development, and the 10Cs elements.

Why do we need to learn about food and cooking? How does food affect our life? In this course, students learn that not all foods are equal to good health. Non-communicable diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, and heart disease are all caused by unhealthy food intake. Thus, awareness related to the connection between food and well-being needs to be improved. Another critical point is that food is a tool for learning – this concept could be integrated into every aspect of life. In designing the course content after revision, it can be seen that the students will be engaged in various types of class activities that stimulates their interests in food studies. The course is designed to allows engagement with social theory in food studies.

There are three SDGs themes to be infused in this course through the newly-developed module, which are SDG 1: End Poverty, SDG 2: Zero Hunger and SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth

- SDG 1: End Poverty

The 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) agenda comprises 17 goals, including the goal of ending poverty (SDG 1). The eradication of poverty in all its forms remains one of the most challenging tasks facing humanity. Even though the number of people living in extreme poverty has decreased by more than half between 1990 and 2015, a disproportionate number of people are still struggling to meet

their most basic requirements. Why is nutrition essential for the success of sustainable development goals? Nutrition is both a maker and a marker of development. Improved nutrition serves as a foundation for progress in health, education, employment, women's empowerment, and the reduction of poverty and inequality. It can lay the foundation for peaceful, secure and stable societies.”

- SDG 2: Zero Hunger

Sustainable Development Goal 2 aims to achieve "zero hunger". It is one of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals established by the United Nations in 2015. The official wording is: "End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture

- SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth

The aim of Sustainable Development Goal 2 Sustainable Development Goal 2 is to promote sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all. SDG 8 recognizes the importance of sustained economic growth and high levels of economic productivity for creating well-paid, quality jobs, as well as promoting resource efficiency in consumption and production.

This paper will discuss the integration of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (SDG 1, SDG 2, and SDG 8) into the higher education curriculum through the Basic Food and Nutrition course. Given the diverse backgrounds of the students, the course developer makes every effort to address the following:

- philosophical positions
- educational psychological norms
- sociological insights

The value of food is not equal to health. However, food is equal to well-being. It is a fact that food is one of the leading causes of non-communicable diseases (NCD) such as obesity, diabetes, etc. Although many awareness campaign was done to improve the rate of mortality caused by food-related diseases, more efforts are needed to tackle this problem. As a result, many crucial preliminary review findings were taken into account when planning the course's implementation, which will be using the DREAM methodology.

Methodologies: The How Question

In light of the above discussed features, needs, and objectives, a six-stage capacity building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006) was used (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on diagnosing the didactic profile of each trainee. Based on the analysis of all trainees’ profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and is structured into thematic units or modules that can be further enriched to meet the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees’ learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The same process of evaluation is continued for the final recipients, the learners through transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages that help to sustain the proper functioning and possible upgrading of the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and most specifically the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction advanced by Makrakis (2017) was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ include the following processes.

- i. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
2. **Deconstructing:** Analyzing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.

- **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
 - **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
 - **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. **Finalising:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 1: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017)

For the revised courses evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2023;2022) has been applied. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process which aims not only assess a course but more importantly to make whatever changes in order to improve it (Makrakis, 2023). Through the parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student guided by the course instructor creates a portfolio that he/she has to give back to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students' DREAM portfolios must be analyzed from the instructor and prepare a report for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide very important information that the instructor and the students could discuss and find ways for improving the course.

Figure 3: The DREAM interaction (Makrakis, 2023)

The “What Now” question

The following section describes the methodology used for the second revision, which was informed by experiences gained during implementations and assessments using the DREAM methodology, as well as the new peer review. The methodology is guided by revised course content learning outcomes where, at the end of this course, students should be able to:

1. Identify the various positions and functions within kitchen production.
2. Identify and operate equipment and standard culinary hand tools effectively.
3. Productively apply appropriate cooking skills by identifying various cooking techniques.
4. Develop practical procedural text through recipe recognition process as guidance in presenting the food design (recipe and cooking process) before the practical cooking session
5. Demonstrate the ability to follow effective cooking principles by preparing various products, including preparing, clarifying, and utilizing basic stocks, sauces, soups, and thickeners, as well as egg dishes, salads, complete meals, and bakery products (bread, pastries, cake, and biscuits).
6. Utilize portion control, workflow, plating, and garnishing principles in the planning session for the food project by using the standard recipe provided in a practical cooking class
7. Comply with and practice safe work habits, identify safety hazards, employ preventative safety measures.
8. Demonstrate a positive attitude, conversation skills, & personal hygiene

9. Demonstrate capability to work in team by maintaining positive relations with others; cooperate through teamwork and group participation; exhibit appropriate work habits and attitudes; demonstrate willingness to compromise.
10. Identify behaviors for establishing successful working relationships through collaborative work with the identified community
11. Incorporate the use of technology in demonstrating accurate food preparation by producing 5-10 minutes reflective digital video addressing fundamental knowledge and skills in food preparation and nutrition
12. Reflect on present issues related to the current food preparation and nutrition practices among the society (such as waste management practices, genetically modified food (GMO), and the use of organic food ingredients)

Discussions

Every country in the globe is mandated under the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development to support sustainable development in an economically, socially, and environmentally balanced manner, leaving no one behind and focusing mainly on the poorest and most excluded people (Fonseca, Domingues & Dima, 2020; Sachs, Schmidt-Traub, Mazzucato, Messner, Nakicenovic & Rockström, 2019). In addressing Climate Change, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) call for profound transitions in every country, which will require complementing initiatives by governments, civil society, research, and business. However, stakeholders lack a consensus on how the 17 SDGs can be implemented. There is a need for strategic initiatives aimed at enhancing current teaching and learning in light of the problems that teachers have faced throughout these processes, from their inception to the present day, particularly in the execution of the task involving subjects from technical and vocational education and digital literacy. The anticipated impact of the updated course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society will be an increased student comprehension of incorporating the SDGs into classroom activities.

The understanding of teaching, learning, and curriculum has evolved in a way that requires us to undergo a process of teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, which has emphasized the utilization of technology in lesson delivery. For the pre-service teachers, many of whom are digital natives, this will be a familiar task, as they will be at ease in producing a 5-10 minute reflective digital video addressing fundamental knowledge and skills in food preparation and nutrition. Before the pandemic, most

undergraduates were familiar with ICT that supports learning, such as e-learning, spreadsheets, and social networking tools, as reflected in the works of Kashefi et al. (2012; 2013). When it comes to facilities, there may be hardware or internet line issues that disrupt or hinder learning. These are the lessons we learned from this experience, and they will have an impact on our students and society as we consider how to continue the learning process with the emergency remote teaching (ERT) concepts. Environmental, social, and governance (ESG) investing and calls for 'harmonization' of sustainability efforts in the wake of the COVID-19 epidemic. During these unprecedented times, the entire world is witnessing the transformative power of ICT in supporting nearly every aspect of life, including education (Adams & Abhayawansa, 2022). Because the course was taught during this period, the discussion of economic, environmental, and social justice is especially timely. Highlighting the local government's efforts to support the economy is another way to revitalize the classroom environment. Many laid-off individuals in the airline and tourism industries began to establish modest firms that do not require substantial capital. The community-based skills of preparing and delivering food create new opportunities for many.

In 2021, the Ministry of Higher Education launched the Competency-Based Education Landscape (Excel) framework, which would focus on competency-based education and experience learning methods through four cores. The four cores are Industry-Driven Experiential Learning (Ideal), Community Resilience Experiential Learning (Care), Research-Infused Experiential Learning (Real), and Personalized Experiential Learning (Poise). The creation of Excel aims to further strengthen the implementation of the Malaysian Education Development Plan (Higher Education) 2015-2025 while also striving to produce lifelong learners, innovative entrepreneurs, creative practitioners, and change-makers. The revised food-related education course is undoubtedly in line with this educational practice, which places SDG infusion in the proper place, leading to the production of holistic and highly skilled graduates. Once Excel is fully implemented in higher institutions, community services with the intention of attaining SDGs will grow.

The revised course is a contribution to the country, as prospective teachers learn that the SDGs are a vast topic encompassing multiple targets and indicators. Typically, Malaysian education is limited to environmental sustainability, leaving the other goals behind. Many scholars research on environmental education as provided in local works like Kavitha (2012) and Zaleha et al. (2014). Many efforts are made to prevent or reduce future ecological damage. One of these initiatives is environmental education for the next generation. Enhancing children's environmental knowledge, protection skills, and management, as well as fostering their caring and responsible nature, can be a long-term solution (Alba-Hidalgo, Benayas del Álamo & Gutiérrez-Pérez, 2018; Suryani et al., 2019). Reflecting on the

influence and efficacy of university sustainability initiatives is timely, as sustainability is becoming increasingly prevalent at universities (Biasutti et al., 2018). Several authors have identified mature environmental sustainability experiences in the various aspects of higher education, including teaching, research, operations, and outreach. Many people will see through the current ICTEFS project that we can incorporate different SDGs into the classrooms if we are creative about how to integrate them with the original course material. What we really need is for the work being done now to be expanded to more schools nationwide. Education has given people hope that they can change into sustainable citizens.

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The Teaching Method in Technical and Vocational Education Course: Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

A growing number of stakeholders believe that higher education institutions will become sustainable organisations due to the critical role they play in promoting sustainability. However, it is not an easy feat as it requires overcoming challenges and hurdles. The proposed ICTeEfs project aims to provide an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, preparing them to utilize cutting-edge pedagogies and teaching methods focused on education for sustainability. Planning for ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education will require extensive and integrated efforts, and teaching and learning procedures will need to adapt as a result of the project. This paper focuses on the methods, strategies, and results of rethinking Teaching Methods in Technical and Vocational Education, one of the introductory-level courses. This course was revised using the Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction (DeCoRe+) methodology to incorporate sustainability, with a focus on the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Two SDG topics are included in the newly designed module for this course: SDG 4, Quality Education, and SDG 16, Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions. Unquestionably, the updated food-related education course aligns with these educational approaches, positioning the SDGs infusion correctly and producing graduates who are holistic and highly trained. Once it is fully implemented in higher education institutions, community services aimed at achieving the SDGs will increase.

Introduction

The effects of unsustainable economic development fueled by profit maximization have led to the excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources, which have been felt by humanity over the past few decades (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). There is still considerable work to be done to reverse this unsustainable development process, despite current measures. All levels of the education system, but particularly higher education, are to blame for the global sustainability problem we are currently experiencing. This is mainly because the individuals who drive society and the economy, creating an unsustainable consumer culture, are often the products of educational institutions: consumers, leaders, and decision-makers (Makrakis 2011). The depth and breadth of the detrimental effects of university-educated individuals on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented, according to Corcoran and Wals (2004). (p. 3).

A fundamental change through an alternative development model that gives proper weight to sustainable well-being should depend heavily on education. In contrast to the prevalent hedonic well-being fueled by unsustainable behaviors and forms of production and consumption, sustainable well-being, in our understanding, is similar to Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). To learn how to improve oneself and society, it is crucial to pursue "sustainability justice," a concept coined by Makrakis (2006, 2017) that reflects the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economics, and culture.

It is essential to note that, despite significant funding for environmental education over the past few decades,

environmental action has received less attention than favorable views on the environment. A paradigm shift in curriculum, teaching, and learning is necessary to translate ecological awareness and understanding into environmental action. However, merely raising citizens' levels of education does not always translate into better levels of sustainable behavior (Makrakis, 2012). The discrepancy between environmental attitudes and environmental actions is due to several other factors, as well as ineffective educational techniques. Role-play, hands-on science, and problem-based learning, which are more effective approaches, were ranked significantly lower in use than lecturing, according to recent curriculum development studies that focused on sustainability (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

According to a project titled "Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability" (Makrakis, 2013, 2014), the great challenge facing institutions of higher learning in the 21st century is training professionals who are critical of and capable of changing their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. Teachers in primary and secondary school classrooms, as well as teacher educators, face a similar set of challenges. Teaching staff are the change agents in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum, as well as for making schools sustainable (Biasutti et al., 2016; 2018; Blake et al., 2013; Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

The ICTeEfs project

One of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental degradation. Recent climate-related disasters in the region demonstrate that Asian policymakers must take immediate action to protect their citizens and mitigate the impacts of climate change, thereby securing sustainable growth for the future. A way to rise to these challenges is through education for sustainability (EfS). While Asian leaders have committed to EfS, along with their concern for the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the real change-makers are the teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries whose teaching force needs training to address the challenges posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental threats. On the one hand, faculties of education need to reconstruct their study programs by integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS), and on the other hand, they must capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing Education for Sustainability to all in-service subject teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly growing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs make the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. The benefits of using ICT-consented teaching practices to transform educational practices into more collaborative, interactive, and motivating experiences for students (Alonso-Garcia et al., 2019). However, integration of ICT does not merely mean an addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Taking into consideration all the challenges and shortages described in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2023. The more specific objectives are to:

1. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.
2. Build the capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education to enable them to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers' training program on education for sustainability.
3. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program, enabled by blended learning, that focuses on integrating education for sustainability across school curricula.

4. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
5. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the undergraduate level entitled Teaching Method in Technical and Vocational Education considering six main questions: The **first question is the "What" question**, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The **second and third questions refer to "Why"** (justifying the reasons for revision) and **"Where"** describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The **fourth question is the "how" question, describing the methodologies used for revision and course assessment** during the implementation process. The **fifth question is the "Now What" question**, which shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course looks and how it has changed from what it was before. Lastly, the **sixth question is the "So What"** that focuses on discussing the challenges met to go through all the preceding processes from the beginning up to now and how has been tackled. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience and how will it affect the beneficiaries such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the following actions?

The "What" Question

TVET instruction takes place in a variety of settings, including schools, public and private specialised vocational education and training providers, workplaces, and other community-based settings. We will concentrate our attention in this paper on these more formalized and institutionalized approaches to vocational teaching and learning. However, we recognize the value and importance of informal learning on the job as it occurs in the real world. This course is designed to familiarize students with the teaching and learning methods used in Technical and Vocational Education (TVE), specifically in Civil, Electrical, and Mechanical Engineering, Living Skills, Home Economics, Agriculture, and Engineering Drawing Classes in schools and vocational training institutions. Discussions include the development of

lesson plans for Technical and Vocational Education subjects. Students will be able to articulate the pedagogical components of teaching in schools and the andragogical component of teaching in vocational training institutions.

As there are numerous issues concerning 21st-century learners (whether young or adult learners), as well as matters related to teacher professionalism, this course offers an opportunity for teacher trainees to become aware of the expectations of today's educational ecosystem. The question, "What are the qualities of a great teacher?" guides this course as students learn how to align teaching content and delivery methods in order to convey an impactful learning process. This course is significant in that it requires us to consider what it means to be a TVE teacher, as well as how teachers are trained and developed in order to improve the quality of their practise and vocational competence. Thus, there is a need to consider the essential differences between vocational and academic approaches to education and having a platform to discuss the diverse approaches to TVET teaching and the directions in which conceptions of it are moving.

As part of this course, students will engage in authentic activities that will allow them to both revoke prior learning while also acquiring new knowledge. Before enrolling in this course, students must first complete a Basic Pedagogy course, where they will learn about teaching theories and philosophy. Students will enrol in Microteaching the following semester as a preparation for Teaching Practice (internship at schools/vocational colleges) in their fifth semester after completing this Teaching and Methods in TVE course. Problem-based learning (PBL) strategies are also incorporated into the learning activities as we believe undergraduate students are mature enough to engage in this challenging approach. Moreover, school students could also be able to cope with the high cognitive demand in the problem-based learning environment (Najihah, et. Al 2014). The following types of knowledge interest are promoted in this teaching/learning unit/module:

6. Technical/instrumental knowledge (transmit information-knowledge) - knowledge on teaching style, delivery methods – ability to differentiate teaching
7. Practical knowledge (focus on deep understanding of the subject) - knowledge of different approaches that suit the specific content of the curriculum well
8. Emancipatory knowledge (creating conditions for empowerment and change toward a sustainable society) - Students learned how to produce a lesson plan that captures the teaching and learning sessions of the selected exemplar teacher. They understand the technological part independently.

The followings are the objectives of the course prior to the course revision:

1. Explain various concepts and principles of teaching theories, teaching lab / workshop subjects in TVE
2. Prepare lesson plan for theories, lab/workshop, and engineering drawing subjects.
3. Demonstrate competency in developing effective teaching simulation in TVE subjects

For this course, the students are assessed through group work assignments and individual assignments. Authentic assessment encompasses multiple modes of evaluation, including both quantitative and qualitative criteria, as well as assessment methods that are grounded in real-world contexts and situations. These assessments pique students' interest, allowing them to learn about a wide range of teaching methods. As a class, they studied the teaching styles of various teachers (including those from the video and from real-world schools) and then presented their findings to their peers. Additionally, they can gain insight into different teaching approaches by observing those employed by other students.

The “Why” question

A preliminary review was conducted to identify the components of sustainable development in this teaching method within the Technical and Vocational Education course. It has been discovered that the elements of sustainable justice are not being taught and are not explicitly mentioned in the learning outcomes for this course. The components have been omitted because they are not required by the Malaysian Qualifications Agency's programme learning outcomes, as highlighted in the document. The elements identified below, however, are not being taught and mentioned explicitly in the learning outcome. For the four pillars of sustainable justice:

- Environmental justice - paperless assignment submission as assignments is uploaded in e-learning
- Social Justice - fair distribution of the learning materials (i.e, lecture notes) and submission of learning activities through e-learning.
- Economic justice - Students are equipped with stable Internet infrastructure (i.e., hotspot and Wi-Fi connection), which they can access to learn content inside and outside the classroom. Additionally, through the use of online learning materials, students, regardless of their socioeconomic status, are afforded equal access to educational resources.
- Cultural justice - Enables students to express opinions and ideas relevant to their experiences, taking ownership of their knowledge development.

It is suggested that these four pillars of sustainable justice could be integrated into the course content by incorporating digital literacy components into the assessment process, as it has become a significant part of the teaching and learning requirements. This resulted in the second revision, which focused on the delivery of structured and well-managed classroom activities that could be used to contribute to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), while also including the embedment of the following soft skills in the activities:

- CS2: Ability to actively listen and respond to the ideas of other people
- CS3: Ability to make clear and confident presentations appropriate to the audience
- CS4: Ability to use technology in presentation
- ET1: Act ethically, with integrity and social responsibility
- ET2: Understand the economic, environmental, and sociocultural impacts of professional practice
- C2: Comprehension (understanding)
- A2: Respond (React and participate actively)
- A3: Value (attach value and express personal opinions)
- P2: Set (Readiness) - Bloom Taxonomy (Psychomotor)

Further, the course content, and particularly the learning activities, are already linked to the six learning pillars for sustainable development, according to the findings of the preliminary review (learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to transform oneself and society & learning to give and share). The remarks on the six pillars of sustainable development are as follows:

Learning to know

Numerous concepts and principles relating to teaching theories, as well as teaching laboratory/ workshop subjects in Vocational and Technical Education. Students gained knowledge of various theories, such as constructivism and behaviourism, and discussed how each theory relates to their teaching style.

Learning to be

Developing individual capacity to be an effective teacher, practicing teacher professionalism.

- value based
- view about something
- defined as a good teacher
- humanity thinking

A visit to a centre/ shelter for adolescents with social problems (i.e., a shelter home for childbearing/ pregnant teenage girls) is possible. As future teachers, the students in the class will gain a more nuanced understanding of the real social issues they will face once they begin their careers. They should keep in mind that teaching is about much more than the classroom setting. If properly managed, the teacher-student relationship can foster the development of a better person. Teachers can instill a positive attitude in students by sharing positive thoughts and advice.

Learning to do

Creating lesson plans for theoretical, laboratory/workshop, vocational, and technical subjects that focus on the various teaching epistemologies and their implications for curriculum development and pedagogy, along with appropriate teaching aids for use in teaching and learning.

Learning to live together sustainably

Actively engage different groups (teachers from vocational and technical education) in completing projects/assignments and class activities.

Learning to transform oneself and society

Involvement of community engagement (short courses).

Learning to give and share

Create opportunities for sharing ideas and experiences, and finding the best solutions through online video-sharing of different teaching styles. Prepare a compilation of videos that can be shared through social media.

Additionally, the preliminary review also examines the course's content, particularly the learning activities associated with the 10Cs elements, where the findings are as follows:

Collaboration

Work with others in groups, resolving conflicts, making decisions, solving problems, negotiating, and fostering recognition and respect. Listen, clarify, organize, participate, and build positive relationships. In this class, students collaborate with school authorities, teachers, and the

community to implement the most effective teacher-sharing projects.

Communication

Interacting, communicating with a broader audience (school communities), justifying, discuss, share, articulating different issues faced by the schools

Critical thinking

Finding the best teaching methods based on the teaching philosophy. Evaluate and suggest improvements for better teaching, which involves dimensions of Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving, as these have been key elements of 21st-century teaching and learning practices.

Creativity

For instance, the creative elements include creating, designing, imagining, inventing, improving, and changing. The students develop teaching plans that incorporate practical and innovative teaching aids for various types of schools and vocational colleges. Some vocational colleges offered courses for students with disabilities. Therefore, the students have prior preparation for what to expect once they go to school.

Cross-cultural understanding

Interpersonal competencies emphasized on communication and awareness on teaching issues related to diversity - concern on multi racial society in Malaysia)

Connectivity

This includes multidisciplinary (previous course- basic pedagogy, related to technical content) and integrating participatory video clip in lesson planning; Inter/cross-disciplinarity)

Critical reflection

Periodically, reflections on teaching sessions in class and online

Critical consciousness

This includes raising awareness about the importance of being active.

Constructing knowledge

Develop digital artifacts for empowerment, advocacy, and capacity building

The Where Question

The preliminary review identified areas that require additional emphasis in terms of course development for integrating education for sustainable development (ESD), which specifically addresses the four pillars of sustainable justice, the six learning pillars for sustainable development, and the 10Cs elements.

A better understanding of educational institutions, including schools and vocational training institutes, is one of the gaps that this course aims to fill, leading to more robust engagement and collaborative efforts among parties. For example, the class assignment established guidelines and procedures for students to contact Exemplary Teachers (a title and reward appointed by the Ministry of Education Malaysia, preferably those who have been in the system for more than ten years). Through project presentations to the entire class and video sharing of how these exemplary teachers teach in class, students can form their own opinions about the abilities and performances of each of these seasoned teachers. However, these perspectives on various teaching styles, including their critics and shortcomings, are not discussed in class. The emphasis has been shifted to emphasise the strength and opportunity of the teaching videos. Specifically, each student will be assigned to a different group and required to learn how to work cooperatively to complete the group project goals. However, several considerations must be taken into account, including the selection of institutions and the identification of exemplary teachers who will serve as their respondents. The difficulty lies in determining which schools will be included in the project at the start of the semester. Based on previous experience with course delivery, certain groups of students have difficulty scheduling appointments with the school administration. Several schools prohibited videotaping of their teachers' teaching practices, for example. In the worst-case scenario, the groups will need to contact and locate other schools willing to collaborate. As a result of these delays, the students did not have enough time to complete the task. This is one of the current difficulties encountered when implementing the course task. Additionally, this necessitates the school administration's awareness and willingness to collaborate to facilitate our students' learning processes.

There are two SDG themes to be infused in this course, which are SDG 4: Quality Education and SDG 16: Peace, Justice & Strong Institutions

- SDG 4: Quality Education

The 2030 SDGs agenda contains 17 goals, including a new global education goal (SDG 4). SDG 4 aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all, with seven targets and three means of implementation. The question now is how the Sustainable Development Goals will ensure a high standard of education. By 2030, this goal ensures that all girls and boys have access to free primary and secondary education. Additionally, it aims to ensure equal access to affordable vocational training and to eliminate disparities in gender and wealth in order to achieve universal access to a high-quality higher education.

- SDG 16: Peace, Justice & Strong Institutions

The aim of SDG 16 is to promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all, and build effective, accountable, and inclusive institutions at all levels. The SDG framework is a valuable and accessible starting point for developing a more sustainable approach and embedding a more global ethos into any school or organisation, according to SDG 16. The SDGs are an excellent tool for supplementing existing curricula, engaging the entire school community (including parents and governors), and collaborating with other groups and organisations to consider the relationship between the local and the global.

This paper will discuss the integration of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (SDG 4 and SDG 16) into higher education curricula through this Teaching Methods in TVE course. Given the diverse backgrounds of the students, the course developer makes every effort to address the following:

- philosophical positions
- educational psychological norms
- sociological insights

We are looking for teachers who are both qualified and skilled (enthusiasm, leadership, organisation, respect, multitasking, teamwork, communication, adaptability, interpersonal skills, creativity, patience, self-evaluation, emotional intelligence, empathy, critical thinking, confidence, commitment, a sense of humour, approachability, and, of course, the ability to teach). As a result, many crucial preliminary review findings were taken into account when planning the course's implementation which will be using the DREAM methodology.

Methodologies: The How Question

In light of the above-discussed features, needs, and objectives, a six-stage capacity-building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses, advanced by Makrakis (2006), was employed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

In the first stage, training focuses on diagnosing the didactic profile of each trainee. Based on the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and is structured into thematic units or modules that can be further enriched to meet the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The evaluation process is continued for the final recipients, the learners, by transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages, helping to sustain the proper functioning and facilitate possible upgrades to the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability and, more specifically, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction, advanced by Makrakis (2017), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ are as follows.

- Diagnosing:** Reflecting on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.

2. **Deconstructing:** Analyzing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
- **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
- **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
- **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. **Finalizing:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 3: The DREAM interaction (Makrakis, 2023)

Figure 1: The DeCoRe plus interaction by Makrakis (2017)

For the revised courses evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2023;2022) has been applied. These processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but, more importantly, to make changes in order to improve it. Through the various parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course (Makrakis, 2023). Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The instructor must analyze the students' DREAM portfolios, and a report must be prepared for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide crucial information that the instructor and students can discuss and use to find ways to improve the course.

The “Now What” Question

The following section describes the methodology used for the second revision, which was informed by experiences gained during implementations and assessments using the DREAM methodology, as well as the new peer review. The methodology is guided by a few questions.

What kind of teachers that we are going to produce?

What is the student's learning styles?

The concept of knowledge construction is not emphasized during the development of learning outcomes due to the nature of the Outcome-Based Education System, as encouraged by the university authority, where the process of learning is characterized by specific mastery. ie, content or skills. Thereby, *what are the mechanisms that need to be determined to allow the skills or content to be mastered?*

How to implement sustainable practices in teaching and learning? Teachers have to think of ways to instil good citizen values such as promoting the intention to recycle, reduce and reuse (3Rs), conduct class activities where the students could bring recycle material for classroom project

In what way transformative learning can be positioned within the norm of positivist? A teacher could address the concerns to address this issue. Teacher could develop their expertise by not only focusing on aspects of curriculum delivery but also

by addressing the different backgrounds of the students in the class.

The second revision phase commenced when the course instructors revised the course outline, and the reviewer provided the final evaluation based on the feedback and thematic areas for the module development of the course. The adjustment included changes to the course delivery while preserving the course outline to ensure that the course descriptions aligned with the course objectives. Students were introduced to the SDGs via a newly developed teaching module. Each module focuses on a specific objective, enhancing students' abilities to effect change in the world through digitally enhanced and collaborative activities related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that complement the underlying theory on technical and vocational education and training (TVET) teaching methods.

The updated revision of the course incorporates sustainability elements into the Civil/Electrical/Mechanical Engineering, Living Skills, Home Economics, Agriculture, and Engineering Drawing classes, all of which exemplify Technical and Vocational Education (TVE) in schools and vocational training institutions. The discussed topics include effective lesson plans for Technical and Vocational Education, with an emphasis on incorporating embedded Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) elements. Students will be able to explain the related ESD with pedagogical and andragogical aspects of teaching in schools and vocational training institutions.

In this course, students are required to complete assignments on the concept of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Initially, they must understand the development of a concept map. To assess their understanding of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) concepts, students completed Assignment 1 (a) by creating a Group Work Concept Map, as shown in Figure 1. In these, Assignment 1 (a) and Assignment 1 (b), students are introduced to the familiarization and identifying connections between SDGs.

Figure 1. Assignment 1(a) by Group A

The following Figure 2 and Figure 3 are the examples of Assignment 1 (b) completed by the students in order to evaluate their understanding of the 17 concepts of Sustainable

Development Goals (SDGs) through the development of Individual Concept Map.

Figure 2. Assignment 1 (b) by Student A

Figure 3. Assignment 1 (b) by Student B

Furthermore, the students completed Assignment 2, in which they were required to create a concept map for one selected Sustainable Development Goal (SDG), as depicted in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4. Assignment 2 Creating concept map for SDG 6: Clean and Water Sanitation

Figure 5. Assignment 2 Creating concept map for SDG 3: Good Health and Wellbeing

So What? Question

According to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, every country in the world is required to promote sustainable development in an economically, socially, and environmentally balanced manner, with no one left behind, and with a particular focus on the poorest and most excluded individuals. In terms of the challenges that the teacher has to go through all these processes from the beginning up to now and how we tackled them, strategic initiatives in improving current teaching and learning are needed (Biasutti et al 2018), especially in the implementation of the assignment, which involves the substances in technical and vocational education and digital literacy. Moreover, teachers should revise their curricula to provide participants with opportunities to discuss various principles, teaching methods, didactic processes, and practices related to SD. Similarly, academic staff should reconsider their teaching methods (Biasutti et al., 2018). In line with previous research (Biasutti and al. 2018) the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum and local/global society will touch on the better understanding of the students related to embedding the elements of SDGs in the classroom activities. The understanding about teaching, learning and curriculum has changed in a way that we have to go through the process of teaching and learning during pandemics COVID-19, which emphasized on the utilization of technology in the lesson delivery. These were the lessons we learned from this experience, and they will influence our students and society in shaping their approach to continuing the learning process with emergency remote teaching (ERT) concepts.

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The Telecommunications and Computer Network Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

Over the last few decades, humanity has been dealing with the consequences of unsustainable economic development growth driven by profit maximization, which has resulted in an excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources. Education should play a critical role in achieving a fundamental transformation through an alternative development model that prioritizes long-term well-being. As a result, the purpose of this paper is to present the processes, practices, and outcomes of revising one of the courses at the Universiti Teknologi Malaysia entitled Telecommunications and Computer Network. Previously, the course only reminded students to keep up with the latest computer technology by upgrading or purchasing their computer equipment on a regular basis, specifically a notebook and a battery. However, the updated revised version of the course teaches students not only to view technology as constantly advancing in today's world, but also to be concerned about the explosive growth and rapidly escalating issue of computer e-waste. The disposal of computer e-waste has gradually evolved into a developing global environmental issue. Not only that, but it has also resulted in a number of public health issues, particularly because of landfills or primitive recycling operations. Toxic materials from old computer e-waste can be released into the environment. Indeed, more questions about computer e-waste must be addressed. Finding efficient ways to dispose of computer e-waste in schools and tertiary institutions is therefore critical. Students understand that computer e-waste must be disposed of securely and safely at the end of the course. SDGs 12 and 13 have been addressed in the revised course.

Introduction

Over the last few decades, humanity has been confronted with the consequences of unsustainable economic development growth driven by profit maximization, resulting in excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014; 2021). Despite current initiatives to reverse such an unsustainable development process, much work remains to be done. Education systems at all levels, particularly higher education, bear responsibility for the global sustainability crisis. This is largely because consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions, which drive society and the economy while also shaping an unsustainable consumer culture (Makrakis, 2011). According to Corcoran and Wals (2004), "the scope and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented" (p. 3).

Education should play a critical role in achieving a radical transformation through an alternative development model that prioritizes long-term well-being (Sterling, 2001). Sustainable well-being, in our opinion, is similar to Aristotle's eudaimonic well-being, as opposed to the prevalent hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The pursuit of "sustainability justice," a concept developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that represents the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture, is critical in learning to transform oneself and society.

It is worth noting that, while much has been invested in environmental education in recent decades, the results have been more positive environmental attitudes and less concern for environmental action. Environmental knowledge and consciousness must be translated into environmental action through a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum (Jones, Selby, and Sterling, 2010). However, simply educating citizens to higher levels does not always result in more sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action is caused by a variety of factors, including educational practices. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability reveal that lecturing was the most prevalent teaching method (as expected), while role play, hands-on-sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more appropriate, were rated much lower in use (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021), although there are starting to be some few first examples where the sustainable paradigm involves both the contents and the educational strategies (Sterling, Dawson, Warwick, 2018)

According to the project Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013; 2014), the great challenge of the twenty-first century for institutions of higher learning is to train professionals who are critical of and capable of acting to transform their frames of reference in order to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives. Teacher educators and classroom teachers in

primary and secondary schools face a similar challenge. Teaching staff serve as change agents in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum, as well as in making schools sustainable (Biasutti et al., 2016; Blake et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013; Zachariou et al., 2013).

This is supported by the Johor Sustainability Education Action Plan 2019-2023. UTM-JPNJ was established in 2019 to support the University's SDG aspirations (Jabatan Pendidikan Negeri Johor, 2019). The plan is a partnership between the government of Malaysia's Johor state and education and non-education organizations to promote SDGs through education for sustainability. The plan comprises five strategies, based on research findings, to strengthen the areas of curriculum, co-curriculum, administration, management, and evaluation at various levels of education in the state of Johor. With this Action Plan, various sustainability programs and projects in Johor can be coordinated to be more focused and high-impact, based on three main elements: sustainability education, STEM education, and 21st-century learning.

The ICTeEfS project

Environmental degradation has been one of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth. Recent climate-related disasters in the region underscore the need for Asian policymakers to act now to protect their citizens and mitigate the effects of climate change, thereby securing long-term growth. Education for Sustainability (EfS) is one way to meet these challenges. While Asian leaders are committed to EfS and are concerned about the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the genuine change agents are teachers in the classroom.

Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam are among the Asian countries where teachers require training to address ICTs, climate change, and other environmental challenges. On the one hand, education faculties must reconstruct their study programs by incorporating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS). At the same time, on the other, they must capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapidly increasing availability of ICT infrastructure in PCs necessitate the incorporation of ICT into the curriculum of teacher education programs and in-service training. However, ICT integration does not simply imply the addition of ICT as a subject or tool. It necessitates changes in teaching and learning, as well as comprehensive and integrated planning of ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

Considering all the challenges and shortages outlined in the rationale, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service teachers and teacher educators, enabling them to adopt innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies focused on education for sustainability (EfS). The Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in Higher Education, funded by the European

Commission, has supported the ICTeEfS project for the period 2019-2023. The more specific goals are as follows:

- LVI. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research with the area of education for sustainability.
- LVII. Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a broad ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.
- LVIII. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier, and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.
- LIX. Develop innovative teaching, learning, and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning, and curriculum.
- LX. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and the replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

In this paper, the processes, practices, and outcomes of revising the courses at Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, entitled Telecommunications and Computer Network, are presented. The following six main questions are considered: **The first question is the “What” question**, and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for revision, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. **The second and third questions refer to “Why”** (justifying the reasons for revision) and **“Where”** describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. **The fourth question is the “how” question, describing the methodologies used for revision** and course assessment during the implementation process. **The fifth question is the “Now What” question**, which shows how the revised and/or updated version of the course looks and how it has changed from its previous iteration. Lastly, **the sixth question is the “So What?” question**, which focuses on discussing the challenges encountered while navigating all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did understanding about teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact beneficiaries, such as students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the subsequent actions?

The What, Why, and Where Questions for Revising the Telecommunications and Computer Network Course

The Telecommunications and Computer Networks course is an introductory course that covers telecommunications and computer networks. It provides the foundation for telecommunications technologies and Internet applications and infrastructures, focusing on data communications, networking, and computer hardware and software, as well as network topology, analysis, and design of networking applications in organizations, and basic management of telecommunications networks. Students will be introduced to the LANs, WANs, and social and ethical issues related to web resources. At the end of the course, students should be able to demonstrate their understanding by utilizing Internet applications for teaching and learning and by demonstrating awareness of the ethical and social issues related to web resources. In addition, students will gain practical experience by studying a physical network using various networking applications.

This course includes all three kinds of knowledge. The conceptual and technical knowledge is transferred to practical knowledge with the inclusion of emancipatory knowledge throughout the learning process. Students learned through assembling computer hardware and recognizing the function of each component (skill development and practical know-how), as well as organizing, explaining, and solving issues related to network infrastructure, failures, and interruptions (development of competence, life skills, personal qualities, aptitudes, and attitudes). Additionally, students will solve computer network problems encountered in real-life situations. To identify the cause of the problem and find a solution, students must understand the concepts of computer networks, communication systems, and data communication. Therefore, students will develop concentration, memory skills, and critical thinking throughout the course.

Furthermore, throughout this course, students have opportunities to develop their independence through individual assessments, including quizzes, tests, final examinations, and self-reflection reports. They also have opportunities to develop critical and creative thinking by solving problems related to telecommunications and computer networks, as well as enhance their communication skills by presenting knowledge and ideas on telecommunications and computer networks. Soft skills and learning taxonomies are embedded in the activities. These include:

- i. Communication skills (CS1): Ability to present ideas clearly, effectively, and confidently through written and oral modes.
- ii. Teamworking skills (TW1): Ability to establish good rapport, interact with others, and work effectively with them to meet shared objectives.
- iii. Cognitive (C3): Applying (Use a concept in a new situation or unprompted use of an abstraction.)
- iv. Affective (A4): Organization (Organizes values into priorities by contrasting different values, resolving conflicts between them, and creating a unique value system.)
- v. Psychomotor (P4): Mechanism (This is the intermediate stage in learning a complex skill.)

However, the elements of sustainable justice are not being directly taught or explicitly mentioned in the learning objectives. The elements are silenced because they are not required in the program learning outcomes outlined by the Malaysian Qualifications Agency. In addition, the concept of knowledge construction is not addressed during the development of learning outcomes due to the nature of the Outcome-Based Education System, where the process of learning is characterized by specific mastery, such as content or skills. Through this course, it is expected that students will be able to portray the image of the world where the advancement of technology and the borderless world are highly reinforced by the importance of telecommunications and computer networks in this digital era. Although this course focuses on telecommunications and computer networks, the human factor remains the priority, emphasizing the ethics of using telecommunications for the benefit of human beings.

Methodologies: The How Question

In light of the above-discussed features, needs, and objectives, a six-stage capacity-building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses, advanced by Makrakis (2006), was employed (Figure 1).

Figure 1: A Capacity Building Model (Makrakis, 2006).

In the first stage, training focuses on diagnosing the didactic profile of each trainee. Based on the analysis of all trainees' profiles, an action plan for the specific training session is formulated (second stage). Following the action plan is the training content, which merges theory and practice and is structured into thematic units or modules that can be further enriched to meet the requirements and needs of the trainee (third stage). The evaluation of trainees' learning outcomes will be compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan (fourth stage). The evaluation process is continued for the final recipients, the learners, by transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages, helping to sustain the proper functioning and facilitate possible upgrades to the training process (sixth stage).

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49. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.
50. **Deconstructing:** Analyzing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
51. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas, and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
52. **Reconstructing:** Integration of newly constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
53. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
54. **Finalizing:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction from Makrakis (2017, p. 112).

For the evaluation of revised courses during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) methodology, advanced by Makrakis (2023; 2022), has been employed. These processes encompass the entire course, covering what students bring to class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (reviewing, reflecting, and explaining), and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM

methodology (Makrakis, 2023) reflects a critical action research process that aims not only to assess a course but, more importantly, to make changes in order to improve it. Through the various parts of the DREAM Methodology, the student, guided by the course instructor, creates a portfolio that they must return to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The instructor must analyze the students' DREAM portfolios, and a report must be prepared for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide essential information that the instructor and students can discuss and use to find ways to improve the course.

Figure 3: The DREAM interaction (Makrakis, 2023).

Results- "Now What?"

Participants

The revised course involved the total of 619 students from four semesters. In the revised course, the sustainability aspects have been addressed through the awareness of e-waste management (SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production), an emphasis on gender equality (SDG 5: Gender Equality), and a promotion of awareness about climate change (SDG 13: Climate Action). This course promotes equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all. Through this course, students are treated equally without gender bias among multi-racial students. Additionally, students are introduced to the principles of e-waste management, including recycling, reduction, and reuse of computer components. In addition, students learn in a learning environment that offers equitable quality education and promotes gender equality.

The course

This course involves problem-based learning strategies. In these strategies, learning is driven by challenging, open-ended problems that are specific to telecommunications and computer networks. Students work as self-directed, active investigators and problem solvers in small collaborative groups, typically consisting of about four students. Through this strategy, the key problem is identified, a solution is agreed upon, and it is implemented. While the instructors adopt the role of facilitators of learning, guiding the learning process and promoting an environment of inquiry rather than providing facts, students are faced with contextualized, ill-structured problems and are asked to investigate and discover meaningful solutions.

Through this course, students recognized the need for balance between freedom and responsible behavior through the group activities in problem-based learning. Students have the freedom to plan their own activities and schedule and find facts and information throughout the problem-based learning. However, they have to balance the freedom and their responsibility as a group member, including respect others' opinions and decisions, and complete the assigned task.

This course covers the four pillars of sustainable justice, including environmental, social, economic, and cultural justice. In the aspect of environmental justice, students receive fair treatment and meaningful involvement, regardless of their gender, race, nationality, religion, or family income classification, in maintaining a clean and healthy environment throughout the course. For social justice, students have a fair distribution of opportunities and privileges throughout their academic journey. For economic justice, every student, regardless of gender, race, nationality, religion, and family income classification, has an opportunity to create a sufficient material foundation upon which to have a dignified, productive, and creative life. Lastly, in the aspect of cultural justice, students from every culture receive equal proportions of all learning materials and opportunities throughout the course.

The six pillars for sustainable development are covered in the revised course. For the first pillar (learning to know), this course requires students to solve computer network problems encountered in real-life situations. To identify the cause of the problem and find a solution, students must understand the concepts of computer networks, communication systems, and data communication. Therefore, students will develop concentration, memory skills, and critical thinking throughout the course. For the second pillar (learning to be), this course provide opportunities for students to develop their own independent through individual assessments such as quiz, test, final examination and self-reflection report, critical and creative thinking through solving problems related to telecommunications and computer network, and communication skills through presenting the knowledge and idea on telecommunications and computer network.

The third pillar of sustainable development is learning to do. Therefore, through this course, students will learn through

assembling computer hardware and recognizing the function of each hardware (skill development and practical know-how), and organizing, explaining, and solving issues on network infrastructure, failure, interruption (development of competence, life skills, personal qualities, aptitudes, and attitudes). Then, learning to live together sustainably is the fourth pillar of sustainable development. Through this course, students will work in groups. Therefore, it can help them develop their social skills, interpersonal skills, teamwork skills, and values through respect for and concern for team members, as well as an appreciation for the diversity of the world.

The fifth pillar is learning to transform oneself and society. Therefore, through awareness on e-waste management, paperless assignments and reports, and group work involving different genders, races, and nationalities, students will develop respect for the environment, for social solidarity, and for a non-discriminatory, gender-sensitive world. Lastly, the sixth pillar is learning to give and share. Thus, learning activities are meant to be shared with other students through e-learning and presentations. Additionally, students can offer the community basic knowledge of telecommunications and computer networks, enabling them to solve simple computer network problems that may arise in daily life.

All 10 Cs, including collaboration, communication, critical thinking, creativity, cross-cultural understanding, connectivity, critical reflection, critical consciousness, and constructing knowledge, are well-blended in this course. In terms of collaboration, students work in groups to assemble computer components and design network layouts. Practical communication skills are essential among students (Morsidi et al., 2021). The communication aspect is emphasized through individual presentations, group activities, and explaining to others how to design network layouts. In the process of finding solutions to assemble computer components and designing a network layout for improvement, elements of critical thinking, creativity, and knowledge construction are involved. The importance of cross-cultural understanding is emphasized through addressing issues related to telecommunication and computer networks while also considering the multi-racial and multicultural society in Malaysia, which resides in various areas, including urban, suburban, and rural settings. Additionally, the emphasis on connectivity is underscored by the inclusion of interdisciplinary courses that provide knowledge of e-waste management.

The use of online assessment media makes it easy to evaluate and reflect on the success of learning, utilizing online quizzes, reflections, and other tools that emphasize the aspect of critical reflection. Additionally, this course fosters awareness of being an active participant in group discussions and activities. Through discussions and group work that involve students from diverse genders, races, cultures, nationalities, and religions, students will learn to appreciate others' points of view. This could enhance critical consciousness and understanding of the world's diversity. Apart from that, multilingualism, literacy, cultural awareness and expression,

entrepreneurship, citizenship, personal, social, and learning skills, as well as digital, science, technology, engineering, and mathematics, are some of the core competencies addressed in this course to support lifelong learning.

This course is designed for undergraduate students who are not computer science majors and who have had minimal prior knowledge of computers. Therefore, the objectives of the revised course are:

- i. To introduce the foundation of telecommunication technologies, focusing on data communications, telecommunication media, and computer hardware and software, with an emphasis on gender equality. (SDG5)
- ii. To organize the concept of network architecture and internet infrastructure in fair treatment and meaningful involvement among students. (SDG 5)
- iii. To provide a critical approach to distinguish which computer component can be recycled and considered as e-waste (SDG12).
- iv. To use reflective video and social media as tools to help the community to identify risks of hazardous waste and propose climate change adaptation strategies (SDG13).

This course is revised with the aims that at the end of the course, students should be able to:

- i. Apply critical assumptions assessment through empirical analytical discovery on telecommunications technologies, computer hardware & software, Internet applications, and data communication.
- ii. Demonstrate the understanding of telecommunications technologies, computer hardware & software, Internet applications, and data communication.
- iii. Organize the concepts and issues of network architecture in a written report for a heterogeneous group of members.
- iv. Provide a critical approach to distinguish which computer component can be recycled and considered as e-waste.
- v. Promote a gender, religion, and ethnicity equality curriculum that reflects the life experiences of both males and females.
- vi. Assemble computer hardware for simple and standard computer setup by considering e-waste management.
- vii. Produce 5-10 minutes reflective digital video addressing the risks of hazardous waste towards climate change.
- viii. Use social media to raise awareness for action and advocacy from the bottom up.
- ix. Reflect on ethical issues related to telecommunication technologies that become part of the habitual practices in society.

All this time, the course has only made students aware of the importance of keeping up with the latest computer technology by consistently upgrading or purchasing their computer equipment, specifically notebooks and batteries. However, with the updated, revised version of the course, students are taught not only to view technology from the perspective of constantly advancing in today's world but also to be concerned about the explosive growth and the rapidly escalating issue of computer e-waste. The disposal of computer e-waste has gradually transformed the topic into a growing global environmental concern. Not only that, but it has also led to various public health issues, especially due to the landfills or primitive recycling operations. Toxic materials from old computer e-waste can be released into the environment. More questions regarding the issues of computer e-waste need to be addressed. Thus, finding efficient ways to dispose of the computer e-waste in schools and tertiary institutions is crucial. At the end of the course, students are aware that the computer e-waste must be disposed of securely and safely. In some ways, these have addressed SDG 12 and SDG 13.

Discussion- "So What?"

The revised course has primarily raised two interrelated issues of importance among students, as they discussed them through their assignments. The issues primarily concern the frequency of recycling activities, which often fail to keep pace with the amount of computer e-waste generated daily by companies and organizations. One of the suggested solutions is to advise the company or organization to make predictions on the amount of computer e-waste that will be generated within a suitable timeframe, based on the number of computers and their peripheral accessories purchased. The use of "Cloud" storage, for example, could reduce the number of storage peripherals. The revised course has trained students to be vigilant at all times about computer e-waste, to become aware of the issue, to raise concerns about the poor management of recycling activities in some countries, and to broaden their perspectives on health issues related to the above point. Upon graduation, the students will bring the computer e-waste alertness with them to the companies/organisations they will be attached to in the future. Furthermore, the use of social media as a tool facilitates the spread of awareness about climate change and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This finding aligns with research by Morsidi et al. (2021) and Jumaat et al. (2019), which suggest that social media can facilitate the effective sharing of knowledge and information. Additionally, technology can aid in students' socio-emotional development (Ashari et al., 2018).

One of the issues students face after completing all these steps is that they are unaware of the Sustainable Development Goals. Students will gain a deeper understanding of the impact of environmental sustainability in their daily lives after being exposed to the SDG themes in this course. The course's understanding of teaching, learning, and curriculum has not changed significantly; instead, the SDGs are integrated into the teaching and assignments of students,

making them aware of their importance. The lesson learned from this experience is that incorporating SDG aspects into the teaching curriculum and achieving the objective of sustainable development is not impossible; however, all parties must work together to attain this goal. The lesson learned from this experience is that incorporating SDG aspects into the teaching curriculum and achieving the objective of sustainable development is not impossible; however, all parties must work together to attain this goal. In this context, cooperation between teachers and students is very important in ensuring that the goals of the SDGs are achieved through this course.

Furthermore, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aim to unite people worldwide to improve the lives of all. They are a collection of common goals established by the United Nations to help us overcome global challenges such as poverty, inequality, climate change, and others. Economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental conservation are the three key components they attempt to integrate for the future. SDGs have a significant role in today's classrooms. These goals can be used to engage students and inform lesson ideas as a blueprint for making the world a better place.

The SDGs were designed to draw attention to some of the world's most pressing environmental issues. All of these issues are addressed, including sanitation, sustainability, pollution, and climate action. However, the SDGs are about more than raising awareness. They also split each goal down into a collection of manageable sub-goals. The SDGs indicate more minor ways to contribute to climate action for the good of the world. Tackling a subject like climate change is a tremendous challenge, but the SDGs show more minor ways to contribute to climate action for the benefit of the planet. Educators can demonstrate to their students how they can contribute to the betterment of the world in which they live.

The SDGs encompass more than just environmental concerns. Poverty, inequality, economic growth, peace, and justice are among the significant, life-altering human concerns they address. Students will gain a deeper understanding of the issues they face in their own lives, as well as those affecting people worldwide. These SDGs illustrate the economic, legal, and political foundations that underpin our society, as well as their intricacies. They bring to light issues that students may be unaware of or overlook. Learning about the SDGs has the added benefit of exposing pupils to diverse communities and experiences outside of their own. As a result, empathy is fostered in the classroom. Global leadership is based on empathy and inquiry that help pupils become more aware of the larger world, as well as its values and identities. This helps develop children into more well-rounded global citizens and shows them how they can make a positive impact in the future.

Furthermore, because the SDGs are so broad, they can be used to provide new perspectives and real-world context for lesson ideas. Climate change topics, such as the causes and consequences of the increase in average global temperature or how climate change contributes to natural disasters like flash

floods, can be discussed in all university and high school courses. The SDGs serve as an excellent filter for broadening and enhancing educational plans. Educators can increase student engagement by demonstrating how the subjects they teach have practical applications in the real world. Aside from that, the amount of research and material crammed into each of the SDGs should not be disregarded. The United Nations has compiled all the necessary information for each objective in one location. The SDGs are valuable classroom resources that provide depth and meaning to lesson ideas, ranging from lengthy facts and figures to the specific targets that comprise each goal. They also include connections to additional reading from organisations like the World Health Organization, UNICEF, and others.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are more than a set of abstract ideals. Many of these goals are expected to be met within the next few years, with some of the larger-scale challenges scheduled for 2030. This allows educators to understand not only which aspects of the objective are the most important but also what can be accomplished in a short amount of time. As the SDGs demonstrate, even small changes can have a significant impact on the world. Goals can be used to focus students' discussions by ensuring that they are specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, and time-bound. It is also worth noting that the SDGs are closely aligned with current curricula. They cover a wide range of traditional academic topics, such as the foundation of education, educational technology, sports science, and technical and vocational education and training (TVET). Rather than being something that must be worked into the curriculum, educators can view the SDGs as an opportunity to add more depth to their lesson plans.

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The Educational Technology Course: Deconstructing, Constructing, and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

Education plays a crucial role in transforming fundamental knowledge through an alternative development model that emphasizes sustainable well-being. This paper aims to present the processes, practices, and outcomes of revising one of the courses at Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, entitled Educational Technology, when the elements of sustainability are taught directly and explicitly mentioned in the learning objectives of this course. The aspects of sustainability have been integrated into this course through, firstly, focusing on a description of the system before revision. I will also include why it was chosen for modification, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competencies to be developed, teaching methods employed, and methods of assessing students—secondly, describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. Thirdly, the methodologies used for the revision and the course assessment during the implementation process. This paper presents the main results of the revised courses and updated revisions following the integration of sustainability elements into the course, as well as the changes made compared to the previous version. Lastly, it discusses the challenges met through all the preceding processes from the beginning and how they have been tackled.

Introduction

Over the last few decades, humanity has faced the consequences of unsustainable economic development driven by profit maximization, resulting in the exorbitant depletion and degradation of the natural resource base (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Despite the current initiatives aimed at reversing this unsustainable development process, there is still much to be done. Educational systems at every level, particularly Higher education, assume responsibility for the global sustainability crisis that humanity faces (Sterling, 2010, 2013). This is essential because consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions that drive society and the economy, shaping an unsustainable consumer culture (Makrakis, 2011; McGregor, 2005). Corcoran and Wals (2004) note that “the range and scope of the negative consequences of university-educated persons on the natural systems which sustain Earth are extraordinary” (p. 3).

Education must play a pivotal role in driving a radical transformation of human society, attitudes, and behaviors through an alternative development model that emphasizes sustainable well-being. To our knowledge, sustainable well-being is close to Aristotle’s eudaimonic well-being as compared to the total hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable modes and behaviors of consumption and production (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The quest for “sustainability justice,” a concept developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017) that reflects the sustainable development of the four pillars, namely, environment, society, economy, and culture, is crucial in learning how to transform individuals and society (Little & Green, 2009).

It is worth noting that, while significant investment has been made in environmental education over the past few decades, it has primarily reflected a shift towards fostering positive ecological attitudes rather than a greater emphasis on environmental action. Translating environmental knowledge and consciousness into environmental action needs a paradigm shift in teaching, learning, and curriculum (Sterling,

2001; 2010). However, teaching citizens at higher levels does not automatically lead to higher levels of sustainable ways of living, being, and thinking (Makrakis, 2012). The mismatch between environmental attitudes and environmental action reflects not only education practices but also several other factors. Recent curriculum development studies focusing on sustainability have shown that lecturing, as expected, was the most prevalent teaching method, while role-play, hands-on sciences, and problem-based learning, which are more suitable, were rated much lower in use (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021). There are now some initial examples where the sustainable paradigm encompasses both the content and educational strategies (Sterling, Dawson, Warwick, 2018), but it is urgent to develop innovative methodologies for integrating sustainability into higher education.

A project entitled “Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability” (Makrakis, 2013, 2014) has revealed that the biggest challenge of the 21st century for higher education institutions is to prepare professionals who are critical and able to act in renovating their reference settings to attain sustainable development objectives and goals. A similar challenge also applies to teachers at primary and secondary school levels. The teaching staff serves as the agent for change in promoting an Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning, and curriculum (Blake et al., 2013; Biasutti et al., 2016), as well as in transforming schools into sustainable institutions (Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013; Zachariou et al., 2013).

This is supported by the Johor Sustainability Education Action Plan 2019-2023. UTM-JPNJ was established in 2019 to support the University’s SDG aspirations (Jabatan Pendidikan Negeri Johor, 2019). The plan is a partnership between the government of Malaysia’s Johor state and education and non-education organizations to promote SDGs through education for sustainability. The program encompasses five strategies, grounded in research findings, to

enhance the areas of curriculum, co-curriculum, administration, management, and evaluation at various levels of education in the state of Johor. With this Action Plan, various sustainability programs and projects in Johor can be coordinated to be more focused and high-impact, based on three main elements: sustainability education, STEM education, and 21st-century learning.

The ICTeEfS project

One of Asia's most conspicuous side effects of the rapid growth has been environmental damage. The recent climate-related crises across the region suggest that Asian policymakers must act promptly to safeguard their nations and mitigate the effects of climate change, thereby helping to secure sustainable future growth. Education for Sustainability (EFS) is considered a way to rise above such challenges, as long as Asian leaders commit to implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through EFS, the true change-makers are educators in schools.

Asian countries where pedagogical forces need training to respond to challenges, such as Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam, are among those facing threats posed by ICTs, climate change, and other environmental issues. Meanwhile, educators must rebuild their study programs by incorporating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS). Moreover, they should leverage the possibilities of these technologies in promoting EFS to all subject in-service teachers. ICT literacy and the rapid expansion of ICT infrastructure accessibility on PCs make ICT integration in curricula and in-service training unavoidable. Nevertheless, ICT integration does not simply suggest adding ICT as a tool or a subject. It involves changes in educational programs and demands an integrative and comprehensive approach to scheduling the ICT-enabled EFS in teacher training.

Considering all the shortages and challenges outlined in the rationale, this project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for in-service educators and teacher instructors, enabling them to practice advanced pedagogies and teaching methodologies related to education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project was funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program through Higher Education for 2019-2023. The project objectives are as follows:

- LXI. Support faculties of education development among partner universities to align research, learning, teaching, and curriculums with the field of education for sustainability.
- LXII. Building the capacity of education faculties and academic staff, which will turn them to be able to contribute toward the implementation, development, and assessment of a comprehensive ICT-enabled in-service educators training program in education for sustainability.
- LXIII. Developing an effective, decentralized, cost-effective, innovative, and multiplier in-service educator professional development program,

enabled by blended learning, with an emphasis on integrating education for sustainability among school syllabuses.

- LXIV. Develop innovative curriculum, learning, and teaching materials in the shape of a multilingual e-Toolkit coping with the integration of education for sustainability in learning, teaching, and syllabus.
- LXV. Developing a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to enhance cooperation in the area of ICTeEfS and replicability of produced outcomes and outputs.

In this paper, we focus on presenting the processes, practices, and outcomes for revising one of the courses at the Universiti Teknologi Malaysia entitled Educational Technology considering six main questions: The **first question is the "What" question** and focuses on a description of the course before revision, including why it was chosen for modification, the number of students attending the course, key content themes, competences to be developed, teaching methods employed and methods of assessing students. The **second and third questions refer to "Why"** (justifying the reasons for revision) and **"Where"** describing the gaps to be filled in the course through the revision process. The **fourth question is the "how" question**, relating to the methodologies used for revision and course assessment during the implementation process. The **fifth question is the "Now What" question**, which shows what the course's revised and updated version looks like and how it has changed from what it was before. Lastly, the **sixth question is the "So What?" question**, which discusses the challenges encountered throughout all the preceding processes from the beginning to the present and how they have been addressed. In particular, the discussion section addresses the following sub-questions: What will be the expected impact of the revised course on teaching, learning, curriculum, and local/global society? How did the understanding of teaching, learning, and curriculum change? What lessons have been learned from this experience, and how will it impact the beneficiaries, including students and society? What is left for not being done and why, and what would be the following actions?

The What, why, and where Questions for Revising the Educational Technology Course

The educational technology course is an introductory course that introduces principles of educational technology in the context of the teaching and learning process. It explores the utilization and integration of technology in education to enhance learning outcomes. This includes discussions on applying the basic concept of communication and instructional design models to design learning materials that enhance and meet specific teaching and learning goals. As learning materials have greatly expanded today due to various technological advances, students will take a step back to learn conventional techniques, such as using blackboards, whiteboards, televisions, VCRs, and different types of projectors (overhead, slide, and opaque projectors). The students will also be allowed to explore the use of newer technology such as computers, various software applications,

LCD projectors, camcorders, digital cameras, scanners, the Internet, satellites, interactive TV, audio and video conferencing, and artificial intelligence in designing the most effective learning environment for students. With the knowledge of educational technology, future educators must be proficient in computer literacy. Thus, at the end of this course, students are taught to develop instructional materials for teaching and learning purposes through group work projects. They will later become educators to address the digital divide in society.

The key objectives of the educational technology course.

- To describe the concept of educational technology about effective teaching and learning process.
- To differentiate the effectiveness of learning instructions using conventional and newer technology.
- Develop computer-based instructional materials for teaching and learning purposes through group work projects, considering students with diverse abilities, including those with or without disabilities.

This course includes all three kinds of knowledge. The conceptual and technical knowledge is transferred to practical knowledge, including emancipatory knowledge, throughout the learning process. Students learn through practicing technology daily as future teachers through designing and developing their teaching aid using professionals, for instance, adobe photoshop, and nonprofessional software, for example, Canva app (skill development and practical know-how), and organizing, explaining, and solving issues on designing, film editing, developing multimedia kits (development of personal qualities, aptitudes, life skills, and attitudes). Moreover, learners will develop critical thinking and memory skills throughout the course.

Furthermore, throughout this course, students develop their independence through various assessments, including quizzes, tests, final examinations, and self-reflection reports. They also have opportunities to develop creative and critical thinking through solving problems in relation to technology in education by presenting the ideas and knowledge of technology in education. Soft skills and learning taxonomies are embedded in the activities. These include:

- Communication skills (KW): Ability to describe the concept of educational technology about effective teaching and learning process.
- Teamworking skills (CS): Develop computer-based instructional materials for teaching and learning purposes through group work projects (by considering students with different abilities / with or without disabilities)
- Cognitive (CG): Differentiate the effectiveness of learning instructions using conventional and newer technology.

However, the elements of sustainability are not being directly taught or explicitly mentioned in the learning objectives. The details are omitted because they are not required in the program learning outcomes outlined by the Malaysian Qualifications Agency. In addition, the concept of knowledge construction is not addressed during the development of learning outcomes due to the nature of the Outcome-Based Education System, where the learning process is characterized by specific mastery, such as content or skills. Through this course, it is expected that students will be able to portray an image of the world where the advancement of technology and the borderless world are highly reinforced by the importance of technology in education in this digital era. Although this course is on educational technology, the human factor is still the priority; it emphasizes the ethics of using technology only for the benefit of the human being.

Methodologies: The How Question

Considering the above-discussed features, needs, and objectives, a six-stage capacity-building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses, advanced by Makrakis (2006), was employed (Figure 1).

Figure 1: A Capacity Building Model (Makrakis, 2006).

In the first phase, guidance focuses on diagnosing the didactic profile of each trainee. Based on the analysis of the trainees' profiles, an action plan for a particular training session will be developed (second stage). After the action plan, the training content combines practice and theory and is divided into modules or thematic units that can be further enhanced to meet the trainee's needs and requirements (third stage). The trainees' learning outcomes assessment will be compared with their original profiles and the objectives and aims set in the action plan (fourth stage). The exact process of evaluation will be continued for the final learners, the recipients, through transferring their acquired knowledge and skills to the classroom (fifth stage). A scheme of upgrading and monitoring will be integrated across all locations, helping maintain proper functioning and possibly upgrade the training process (sixth stage).

For course revision to embed sustainability, specifically the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction advanced by Makrakis (2017), was applied. The DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) approach views curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six methods comprising DeCoRe+ include the following procedures.

55. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.
56. **Deconstructing:** Critically analyze the habits of mind, personal perspectives functions, and chosen curriculum units/modules.
57. **Constructing:** Constructing new meaning (perspectives), creating ideas, and gathering resources.
58. **Reconstructing:** To integrate newly built knowledge by a reconstructed frame of reference.
59. **Implementing:** Implementing a reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service education.
60. **Finalizing:** Evaluating and reflecting on what was learned and tracking all changes that occurred.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017)

Figure 3: The DREAM interaction (Makrakis, 2023)

Participants and data collection

Participants of this study were mainly educational technology students who registered for this course as a compulsory course in the school of education. The participant of this study consisted of 620 students. For the first intake during the first and second Semesters, 2021-2022, 408 students were involved. Moreover, for the first and second Semesters, 2020-2021, 212 students were involved. The students were asked to participate in the dream methodology survey. They were also asked to develop a mind map for a topic of their choice based on their understanding of the revised course and its integration with the sustainability items. Figure 4 illustrates an example of students' work on that.

For the revised course evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) methodology, advanced by Makrakis (2023; 2022), has been applied. These procedures encompass the entire course spectrum, including the aspects that students bring to the class prior to the implementation of the systems (Diagnosing), throughout the course (Explaining and reflecting/reviewing), and at the end of the course (Managing and Assessing). In a sense, the DREAM methodology mirrors a critical action research procedure that is designed to evaluate a course and, even more important, make the modifications to enhance it. Over parts of the DREAM Methodology, the learner is led by the course tutor by creating a portfolio they need to give back to the teacher at end of the course. Therefore, the DREAM Methodology is considered a requirement of the course (Makrakis, 2023). The students' DREAM portfolios will need to be analyzed by the teacher and prepared into a report for the entire class. Analyzing the DREAM portfolios will be providing critical information that the teacher and pupils could argue and find ways to help improve course.

Figure 4: Example of students' mind map illustrations

Results- “Now What?”

In the revised course, the sustainability aspects have been addressed through the awareness of e-waste management (SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production), emphasis on gender equality (SDG 5: Gender Equality), and promotion of awareness about climate change (SDG 13: Climate Action). This course supports equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all. Through this course, students are treated equally without gender bias among multi-racial students. Additionally, students are introduced to the principles of e-waste management, including recycling, reduction, and reuse of computer components. In addition, students learn in a learning environment that offers equitable quality education and promotes gender equality.

This course involves problem-based learning strategies. The strategies include challenging, open-ended problems that drive learning, and the issues are specific to technology in education. Students work as self-directed, active investigators and problem solvers in small, collaborative groups (typically consisting of about four students). This strategy identifies the fundamental problem, and a solution is agreed upon and implemented. While the instructors adopt the role of facilitators of learning, guiding the learning process and promoting an environment of inquiry rather than providing facts, students face contextualized, ill-structured problems. They are tasked with investigating and discovering meaningful solutions.

Through this course, students recognized the need to balance freedom and responsible behavior through group activities in problem-based learning. Students have the freedom to plan their activities, schedule, and find facts and information throughout the problem-based learning process. However, they must balance their freedom and responsibility as a group member, respecting others' opinions and decisions and completing the assigned task.

This course covers the four pillars of sustainable justice, including environmental, social, economic, and cultural justice. In environmental justice, learners receive fair treatment and meaningful involvement, regardless of their

religion, nationality, race, gender, or family income classification, in maintaining a healthy and clean environment throughout the course. For social justice, learners have a fair distribution of privileges and opportunities during the course. For economic justice, every learner, regardless of family income classification, religion, nationality, race, and gender, has the opportunity to create a sufficient material foundation upon which to have a creative, productive, and dignified life. Finally, in cultural justice, learners from every culture receive equal proportions of all opportunities and learning materials throughout the course.

The six pillars for sustainable development are covered in the revised course. For the first pillar (learning to know), this course requires students to develop media aids that they will use in their future teaching careers. To identify the purpose of the media aid and implement it in their class, students must understand the concepts of computer technology, technology in education, and factors of technology usage in teaching and learning. Furthermore, learners will develop critical thinking, memory skills, and concentration throughout the course. For the second pillar (learning to be), this course provides opportunities for students to develop their independence through individual assessments such as quizzes, tests, final examinations and self-reflection reports, and critical and creative thinking through solving problems related to telecommunications and computer network, and communication skills through presenting the knowledge and idea on technology in education.

The third pillar of sustainable development is learning to do. Therefore, through this course, students will learn by dealing with professional software, developing practical know-how and skills, and explaining, organizing, and solving issues by creating teaching aids, thereby fostering the development of attitudes, aptitudes, personal qualities, life skills, and competence. Then, learning to live together sustainably is the fourth pillar of sustainable development. Through this course, students will work in groups. Therefore, it could help them develop their social, interpersonal, teamwork, and value skills through respect, concern for team members, and appreciation of the world's diversity.

The fifth pillar is learning to transform oneself and society. Therefore, through awareness of e-waste management, paperless assignments and reports, and group work involving different genders, races, and nationalities, students will develop respect for the environment, social solidarity, and a non-discriminatory, gender-sensitive world. Lastly, the sixth pillar is learning to give and share. Thus, learning activities are meant to be shared with other students through e-learning and presentations. Additionally, students can offer the community basic knowledge of technology in education for daily life.

All 10Cs, including collaboration, communication, critical thinking, creativity, cross-cultural understanding, connectivity, critical reflection, critical consciousness, and constructing knowledge, are well integrated in this course. In terms of collaboration, students work in groups on designing

and developing their teaching aid projects. The communication aspect is emphasized through the individual presentations, group activities, and explanations to others on how to create teaching aid layouts. In designing media aids, the elements of critical thinking, creativity, and knowledge construction are involved. The importance of cross-cultural understanding is emphasized through addressing issues related to technology in education, particularly in a multi-racial and multicultural society in Malaysia, which is comprised of diverse areas such as urban, suburban, and rural settings. Additionally, the emphasis on connectivity is underscored by the inclusion of interdisciplinary courses that provide knowledge of e-waste management.

The use of online assessment media makes it easy to evaluate and reflect on the success of learning, utilizing quizzes, online reflections, and other tools and strategies that emphasize the aspect of critical thinking. Also, this course raises consciousness about being active in group discussions and activities. Through conversations and group work that involve students from diverse genders, races, cultures, nationalities, and religions, students will learn to appreciate others' points of view. This could enhance critical consciousness in understanding the world's diversity. Apart from that, this course addresses core competencies in multilingual literacy, cultural awareness and expression, entrepreneurship, citizenship, personal and social learning, digital literacy, science, technology, engineering, and mathematics to support lifelong learning. This course is designed for undergraduate students who are not computer science majors and have minimal prior knowledge of computers. Therefore, the objectives of the revised study are:

To design instructional strategies and methods by considering students with different abilities. (SDG 10) – Week 1, Week 2, Week 3, Week 4

To prepare learning activities using instructional technology and media by considering people with or without disabilities. (SDG 10) – Week 5, Week 6, Week 8, Week 9, Week 10

To produce a technology-based media in educating on good health and well-being. (SDG 3) – Week 11, Week 13

To promote affordable and clean energy by integrating interactive multimedia elements through social media. (SDG 7) – Week 12, Week 14, Week 15

This course is revised with the aims such that at the end of this course, students should be able to:

- Analyze critical methods and instructional strategies that are suitable for learners with diverse abilities.
- Design instructional methods and strategies that consider learners with diverse abilities.
- Develop multimedia for teaching and learning that considers learners with and without disabilities.
- Prepare learning activities for learners with different abilities using multimedia developed.
- Produce 5-10 minutes reflective digital video addressing the importance of good health in the community.

- Produce a 5-10 minute reflective digital video addressing the importance of good well-being within the community.
- Develop interactive multimedia elements to promote affordable and clean energy.
- Share multimedia elements through social media.

The course educated students about the role of computer technology in education. However, with the updated, revised version of the course, students are taught not only to view technology from the perspective of constantly advancing in today's world but also to be concerned about the explosive growth and the rapidly escalating issue of computer e-waste. The disposal of computer e-waste has gradually transformed the topic into a growing global environmental concern. It has also led to various public health issues, primarily due to landfills or primitive recycling operations. Toxic materials from old computer e-waste can be released into the environment. More questions regarding the problems of computer e-waste need to be addressed. Thus, finding efficient ways to dispose of computer e-waste in schools and tertiary institutions is crucial. Students understand that computer e-waste must be disposed of securely and safely at the end of the course. In some ways, these have addressed SDG 12 and SDG 13.

Discussion- “So What?”

The revised course has primarily raised two critical issues among students as they discussed them through their assignments. The problems primarily concern the frequency of recycling activities, which often fail to keep pace with the amount of computer e-waste generated daily by companies and organizations. One of the suggested solutions is to advise the company or organization to predict the amount of computer e-waste that will be generated within a suitable timeframe based on the number of computers and accessories purchased. For example, using “Cloud” storage could reduce the number of storage peripherals. The revised course has trained students to be aware of computer e-waste, raise concerns about poorly managed recycling activities in some countries, and broaden their perspectives on health issues related to the above point. Upon graduation, the students will bring awareness of computer e-waste to companies and organizations in the future.

One of the issues students face after completing all these steps is that they are unaware of the Sustainable Development Goals. Students will gain a deeper understanding of the impact of environmental sustainability in their daily lives after being exposed to the SDG themes in this course. The course's understanding of teaching, learning, and curriculum has not changed significantly; instead, the SDGs are integrated into the teaching and assignments of students, making them aware of their importance. The lesson learned from this experience is that incorporating SDG aspects into the teaching curriculum and achieving the objective of sustainable development is not impossible; however, all parties must work together to attain this goal. The lesson learned from this experience is that

incorporating SDG aspects into the teaching curriculum and achieving the objective of sustainable development is not impossible; however, all parties must work together to attain this goal. In this context, cooperation between teachers and students is essential in ensuring that the purposes of the SDGs are achieved through this course.

Furthermore, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aim to unite people worldwide to improve the lives of all. They are a collection of common goals established by the United Nations to help us overcome global challenges such as poverty, inequality, climate change, and others. Economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental conservation are the key components they attempt to integrate for the future. SDGs have a significant role in today's classrooms. These goals can be used to engage students and inform lesson ideas as a blueprint for making the world a better place.

The SDGs drew attention to some of the world's most pressing environmental issues. These issues are addressed, including sanitation, sustainability, pollution, and climate action. However, the SDGs are about more than raising awareness. They also split each goal down into a collection of manageable sub-goals. The SDGs outline more minor ways to contribute to climate action for the benefit of the world. Tackling a subject like climate change is a tremendous challenge, but the SDGs show more minor ways to contribute to climate action for the benefit of the planet. Educators can demonstrate to their students how they can contribute to the betterment of the world in which they live.

The SDGs encompass more than just environmental concerns. Poverty, inequality, economic growth, peace, and justice are the significant, life-altering human concerns they address. Students will gain a deeper understanding of the issues they face in their own lives and the lives of people worldwide. These SDGs illustrate the economic, legal, and political foundations underpinning our society and its intricacies. They highlight issues that students may be unaware of or overlook. Learning about the SDGs has the added benefit of exposing pupils to diverse communities and experiences outside of their own. As a result, empathy is fostered in the classroom. Global leadership is based on compassion and inquiry. They help pupils become more aware of the larger world and its values and identities. This helps develop children into more well-rounded global citizens and demonstrates how they can make a positive impact in the future.

Furthermore, because the SDGs are so broad, they can be used to provide new perspectives and real-world context for lesson ideas. All university and high school courses discuss climate change topics, such as the causes and consequences of the increase in average global temperature or how climate change contributes to natural disasters, including flash floods. The SDGs serve as an excellent filter for broadening and enhancing educational plans. Educators can increase student engagement by demonstrating how the subjects they teach have practical applications in the real world. Aside from that, the amount of research and material crammed into each SDG should not be disregarded. The United Nations has gathered

all of the necessary information for each objective in one place. The SDGs are valuable classroom resources that provide depth and meaning to lesson ideas, ranging from lengthy facts and figures to the specific targets that comprise each goal. They also include connections to additional resources from organizations such as the World Health Organization, UNICEF, and others.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are more than a set of abstract ideas. Many of these goals are expected to be met within the next few years, with some of the larger-scale challenges scheduled for 2030. This enables educators to identify the most important objective aspects and determine what can be accomplished efficiently. As the SDGs demonstrate, even minor changes can have a significant impact on the world. Goals can be used to focus students' discussions by ensuring that they are specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, and time-bound. It is also worth noting that the SDGs are closely aligned with current curricula. They cover a range of traditional academic topics, including the foundations of education, educational technology, sports science, and technical and vocational education and training (TVET). Rather than being something that must be worked into the curriculum, educators can view the SDGs as an opportunity to add more depth to their lesson plans.

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The Outdoor Education Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

The Asia-Pacific region has experienced some of the most devastating climate and environmental disasters of recent decades, with severe consequences for human well-being. Many scientists believe that there is a link between the increase in natural disasters in Asia and the Pacific and anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. Support from teachers at all levels is essential for taking action by integrating Education for Sustainability (EfS) into their teaching, with the hope of generating more sustainable citizens. Our current project aims to develop an ICT-based capacity-building program for employed teachers and teacher trainers, enabling them to utilize innovative teaching methods and pedagogies focused on sustainability education. In this paper, we report on the revision of an Outdoor Education course that employed frameworks, including DeCoRe+ and DREAM methodologies. The outcome of the revised curriculum suggested that the methodology for curriculum revision, which aims to generate sustainable citizens, has strong potential to support the SDGs. It is recommended that more undergraduate courses undergo curriculum revision to embed the SDGs with the support of ICTs.

Introduction

Over the past few decades, we have witnessed economic development that has led to the excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014, 2021). Poor management in the economy signals that our education systems are not successful in generating consumers, leaders, and decision-makers who can drive a sustainable society, environment, and economy (Makrakis, 2011). Therefore, much attention should be given to education at all levels, in particular tertiary education, as Corcoran and Wals (2004) observe that “the scope and range of the negative impacts of university educated people on the natural systems that sustain Earth are unprecedented” (p. 3).

Many advocates of sustainable development believe that education is a powerful tool to develop sustainable well-being; currently, in this context, more people refer to the role of sustainable citizens. Sustainable citizens are those who adopt Aristotle’s eudaimonic well-being, which contrasts with the hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The transformation of human behavior into sustainable citizens requires them to adopt the concept of sustainable justice, as developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017), which encompasses the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture. Education can play a major role in ensuring that students acquire this concept. Therefore, a well-designed curriculum is necessary to achieve this goal.

For several years, considerable efforts have been invested in environmental education; however, little progress has been made in environmental action. It is not sufficient for students to be aware and have positive attitude towards environmental issues, but it would be more impactful if they can demonstrate some positive actions (Sterling, 2001; 2010.; 2013) We need to educate citizens about sustainable ways of thinking, being and living (Makrakis, 2012). Educators should design quality curriculum that support SDGs which takes beyond lecturing

but explore the possibility of employing innovative pedagogies such as role play, hands-on-sciences, problem-based learning, (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015; 2016; Makrakis et al. 2021). Teaching staff who are the key players in promoting Education for Sustainability should seriously progress in this direction as they are recognized as agent of change for a society. A project entitled "Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability" (Makrakis, 2013, 2014) involved the training of teacher educators to transform their frames of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives, and has proven to be successful.

In 2021, the Ministry of Higher Education launched the Competency-Based Education Landscape (Excel) framework, which focuses on competency-based education and experiential learning methods through four core areas. The four cores are Industry-Driven Experiential Learning (Ideal), Community Resilience Experiential Learning (Care), Research-Infused Experiential Learning (Real), and Personalized Experiential Learning (Poise). The creation of Excel is to further strengthen the implementation of the Malaysian Education Development Plan (Higher Education) 2015-2025, besides aiming to produce lifelong learners, innovative entrepreneurs, creative practitioners and change-makers. Incorporating SDGs in undergraduate courses no doubt in line with these educational inspirations, which place SDGs infusion at the proper place leading to produce holistic and highly skilled graduates. Once Excel is fully implemented in higher institutions, community services with the intention of attaining SDGs will be growing.

The ICTeEfS project

The Asia-Pacific region has suffered some of the most damaging disasters of recent decades, with alarming consequences for human well-being. At the same time, the climate in the region is changing. Temperatures were on

average higher, as well as more variable and extreme. Precipitation was also more variable and extreme. Scientists claim that there is a link between the increase in natural disasters in Asia and the Pacific and anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. Asian policymakers should wait no longer to protect their citizens by making them aware of environmental threats caused by humans, and everyone is responsible for behaving more sustainably. The support of teachers at all levels is critically needed to effectively integrate EfS into their teaching. The teaching force in Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam needs to be trained professionally, starting with the reconstruction of teaching programs at the faculty of education. Programs driven by ICTs are the way forward, given the promising role of ICTs in education. Moreover, Malaysian institutions have sufficient infrastructure facilities to support activities driven by ICT. Careful planning should be devised to incorporate SDGs with the support of ICTs in the curriculum.

Malaysia's education system and its institutions at all levels play a pivotal role in instilling the spirit of Sustainable Development (SD) in its citizens to protect the earth and wellbeing of mankind from any destruction and disruption due to current global developments. Due to education's potential to drive individual and societal transformation, the Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is implemented in Malaysia's education system via its two blueprints – Malaysian Education Blueprint (Pre-School to Secondary) and Malaysian Higher Education Blueprint (Tertiary). The concept of SD has been misunderstood by many such that much focused to the environmental justice, with little attention has been given in the context of social and economic justice. Gender equality, sustainable economic actions, reducing poverty in society, and other critical areas of social and economic sustainability must be imprinted into students through viable ESD curriculum. Therefore, the curriculum for pre-serviced teachers should be designed to minimize this gap so that teachers are ready to implement ESD in a more holistic manner. Some early efforts to penetrate SDGs in schools locally are shared in the work of Kavitha (2012) and Zaleha et. al (2014).

Our current project aims at developing an ICT-enabled capacity-building program to in-service teachers and teacher educators and turn them able to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies orienting to education for sustainability (EfS). Also known in abbreviation as ICTeEfS, this project has been financed by European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education for the period 2019-2022. The more specific objectives are to:

1. Support the development of the faculties of education in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning and research with the area of education for sustainability.
2. Build capacity of academic staff at the faculties of education that will turn them able to contribute to the development, implementation and evaluation of a wide ICT-enabled in-service teachers training program on education for sustainability.

3. Develop an efficient, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplier and innovative in-service teacher professional development program enabled by blended learning, focusing on the integration of education for sustainability across school curricula.
4. Develop innovative teaching, learning and curriculum materials in the form of a multilingual e-Toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability in teaching, learning and curriculum.
5. Develop a Euro-Asian Network of ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability to strengthen cooperation in the field of ICTeEfS and replicability of produced outputs and outcomes.

Universiti Teknologi Malaysia along with eight other institutions from Malaysia, Vietnam, Indonesia, Greece and Cyprus is part of this project. The School of Education under Faculty of Social Science and Humanities engaged in this viable project as no present efforts to integrate SDGs with the support of ICTs in the department. Since our core business is producing future teachers, therefore this project is very relevant in upgrading the syllabus to meet the demand of global struggle.

The Outdoor Education Course

In this paper, the focus is to present the processes, practices and outcomes for revising one course at the undergraduate level offer in a public Malaysian institution entitled SPPR1832 Outdoor Education. Outdoor sports like camping is one activity which is loved by many Malaysian students. Being a tropical country with hot humid weather and dense forest, outdoor activities are challenging, dangerous and tiring. Not many students who have been living in the city can cope well during such harsh times. A good teacher who is confident and skillful to manage outdoor activities equipped with special skills are needed to supervise outdoor activities. The course entitled SPPR1832 Outdoor Education is offered to pre-service teachers who enrolled in sports science education program who are groomed to be a sports science teacher at secondary schools. The students enrolled in this 2-credit course will progress through an experientially-based program that emphasizes interpersonal relationships and individual growth. This course encourages students to develop greater self-confidence and, at the same time, acquire a sense of trust and commitment in their classmates. Outdoor education is designed to expose students to a variety of outdoor skills. Outdoor pursuit activities may include: camping, backpacking, survival skills, hiking, fishing, orienteering, first aid and kayaking.

In line with outcome based education, it is expected that students will attain the 4 Course learning outcomes stated as follows:

Demonstrate knowledge of general principles of outdoor education
Ability to apply knowledge and skill related outdoor education

Ability to look for alternative ideas and creative solutions

based on given task.

Ability to understand responsibility towards group decision on given task during practical activities and assignments

The course learning outcomes are paralleled to the four program learning outcomes which are listed as: a) Communication skills: Ability to present ideas clearly, effectively and confidently through written and oral modes; b) Team working skills: Ability to establish good relationships, interact with others and work effectively with them; c) Practical Skills: Demonstrating skills require for career development and d) Cognitive Skill: Applying and using concepts in a new situation. The last time the course was offered for 2017/2018-1 long before the Covid19 pandemic with 55 enrolments. The course was temporarily not offered during the first 2 years of pandemic as ordered by the Ministry of Higher Education. Unlike other courses which can be conducted fully online, this course requires outdoor physical setting. Now it resumes in the current semester, Semester 2, Session 2021/2022. The main assessment methods are group assignment (20%), group presentation (20%), camping project (30%) and final examination (30%).

The original curriculum is technically oriented as indicated in the content for Week 1 to Week 7 as shared in Table 1

Table 1: Topics for Outdoor Education Week 1 to 7

Week	Topics
1	1.0 Introduction to Outdoor Education 1.1 Outdoor Education in Malaysia 1.2 The need of Outdoor Education in Malaysian schools
2	2.0 Planning and management of Outdoor Education 2.1 Paperworks 2.2 Outdoor Education activities procedures
3	4.0 Camping 4.1 Selection of camping site 4.2 Rules 4.3 Safety
4	3.0 Initiatives games 3.1 Objectives and purposes 3.2 Initiatives games based on age & number of people
5	5.0 Camp craft, gadgets & knots 5.1 Knots 5.2 Gadgets 5.3 Campcraft
6	6.0 Kayak 6.1 Techniques 6.2 Safety

7	7.0 Compass and orienteering 7.1 Types of map and compass 7.2 Map reading 7.3 No map and compass
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The ICT elements in this curriculum is not explicitly mentioned as the course is outdoor oriented but some meetings are held indoors. The use of videos or other digital applications seems to be missing. However, the institution has made every course be equipped with e-learning platform including this course. Some studies provide evidence that blended learning supports the need of undergraduates by providing means to share resources, assignments, e-forum and online assessment (Kashefi et. al.,2012, 2013). Malaysian students are IT savvy such that typically they owned smart phones and laptops to support learning as expected by their instructors. Nowadays there are abundance of open resource videos in particular shared by Youtube that showcase critical problems that go on around communities local and abroad. Concern citizens can easily get first hand news associated with social, economic and environmental justice about what is going on locally and abroad. Besides ICT integration, the institution also give priorities to the use of effective pedagogies to enrich students problem solving skills by balancing independent learning with scaffolding as in advancing problem based learning which is has been our research focus (Najihah,2016).

Rationale for Revising Outdoor Education Curriculum

This course which exposes students to the real world and surroundings can be more useful if it is connected to societal issues encompassing social and environmental justice that are propagated in SDGs. Unfortunately, these elements are not clearly stated in the course learning outcomes. With a little revision, this course can become a powerful means to generate new teachers who can contribute to attain SDGs.

Methodologies For Revising Outdoor Education

A systematic process was carried out for revising the curriculum Outdoor Education. The revision process begin with training the academic staff who are the course owners. Figure 1 shares a six-stages capacity building model for training academic staff to embed sustainability in their courses advanced by Makrakis (2006)

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

Stage 1 involves gathering trainee didactic profiles to be used for the action plan in Stage 2, which formulates specific training sessions. The third stage involves implementing the training using content that merges theory and practice, structured into thematic units or modules. The trainees' learning outcomes will be compared with their didactic profiles obtained in Stage 1 for the evaluation phase in Stage 4. The same evaluation process is continued for the final recipients, who are the learners, by transferring their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom (fifth stage). A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages, helping to sustain the proper functioning and facilitate possible upgrades to the training process (sixth stage).

To embed the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the course, the DeCoRe+ methodology, an abbreviation of Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction developed by Makrakis (2017), was adopted. The framework, as depicted in Figure 2, is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ are as follows:

1. **Diagnosing:** Reflecting on: a) who we are; b) what we have (existing knowledge); c) where we want to go; and d) why we want to go there.
2. **Deconstructing:** Analyzing critically the functioning of personal perspectives and habits of mind and chosen curriculum units/modules.
3. **Constructing:** Gathering resources, creating ideas and constructing new meaning (perspectives).
4. **Reconstructing:** Integration of new constructed knowledge in line with the reconstructed frame of reference.
5. **Implementing:** Carrying out the reconstructed curriculum unit/module supplemented by service learning.
6. **Finalizing:** Reflecting and evaluating on what has been learned and changed.

Steps 1 and 2 require thoughtful consideration of fundamental questions, which ultimately lead to an understanding of our purpose in existence. In many situations, these steps are overlooked and left unattended as people are more concerned with the operational part. Once we are clear on Steps 1 and 2, the construction process becomes more purposeful, as we already understand the direction to take. Infusing the SDGs driven by ICT, the six pillars of learning, the ten sustainability competencies, and the sustainability pillars are integrated into the reconstruction process. For this course, Stage 5, involving service learning, is not something new. The final stage, involving reflection and evaluation, is an important step that requires careful planning with the necessary tools.

Figure 2: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017).

The DREAM (Diagnose, review, reflect, explain, assess, and manage) methodology, developed by Makrakis (2019, 2022), has been applied to evaluate the revised course during its implementation. For diagnosis, data was collected to determine what students brought to class before the implementation of the courses. Next, during the implementation of the course, the instructor reviews, reflects on, and explains how the course was conducted and how students responded to the materials and activities. Finally, at the end of the course, the instructor critically evaluated the course and made efforts to improve its management. The course instructor evaluates students' portfolios, which is useful in informing the instructors of the strengths and weaknesses of the course as well as what needs to be improved.

Figure 3 The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

Revising the Course

In 2019, the Outdoor Education course went through a revision. A deconstruction process was conducted to assess the quality of the original curriculum. The results of the process indicate that most components of the curriculum are favorable, particularly in terms of structure, content, student learning time, teaching methods, and assessment. Thus, a significant portion of the curriculum can be maintained, and considerable attention should be given to incorporating SDG dimensions, which are currently absent. Three SDG themes were explored to support learning activities, specifically SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being, SDG 6: Clean Water, and SDG 13: Climate Action. The CLOs need to be refined to explicitly highlight sustainability development goals and sustainable justice.

Although the course has considerable potential for integrating SDGs and sustainable justice, documents supporting their explicit or implicit teaching are not available. The Sustainable Development Goals are embedded in this course. The original course learning outcomes did not mention the SDGs. This is because Malaysian Quality Assurance does not require the sustainability elements. A close inspection of the DeCore process reveals that sustainability can be easily integrated into most topics throughout the course. Consequently, the revised curriculum has infused SDGs and sustainable justice in the course learning outcomes, as shared in Table 2.

Table 2: Course Learning Outcomes Before and After Revision

Course Learning Outcomes	
Before Revision	After Revision

Demonstrate knowledge of general principles of outdoor education	To emphasize the related general principles of outdoor education and environmental issues that are threatening humans in terms of pollutants and human threats.
Ability to apply knowledge and skill related outdoor education	To organize the presentations regarding outdoor education to diverse audience with confidence and to be able to distinguish between type of pollution, its causes and methods to reduce or eradicate the pollution.
Ability to look for alternative ideas and creative solutions based on given task.	To learn and reflect their own alternative ideas and creative solutions of the outdoor education based on the task given and differentiate the threats to children, youth, women and the aging group (drugs, trafficking and abuse, homelessness).
Ability to understand responsibility towards group decision on given task during practical activities and assignments	To apply the knowledge and skills related to outdoor education in real-life situations and organize programs alongside other government bodies and NGO to experience and learn what has been done and what needs to be done in the community.

The course prior to revision has not sufficiently addressed the four pillars of justice and the 6 learning pillars. Using DeCore Plus methodology, a new set of detailed descriptions was documented to embed the four pillars of sustainable justice and the six learning pillars.

The four pillars of sustainable justice documented in the revised curriculum are:

1. Environmental justice –The introductory topic on outdoor education in Malaysia discusses the importance of environmental education Outdoor education, principles and awareness in Malaysia education system. A strong emphasis is also given to students concerning not to dirty, polluting, and damaging the camping site/nature / lake and the outbound site throughout the semester.

2. Social Justice – this course provides equal opportunity to students to give ideas and opinion in performing tasks.

3. Eco-justice – For outdoor activities, learners are required to use as much natural, recyclable material as possible and avoid non-recyclable materials. Students are

encouraged to reuse materials and avoid spending money on new ones (such as plastic plates) during camping.

4. Cultural justice allows students to voice opinions and ideas that are relevant to their experiences and take ownership of their knowledge development. Since most of the students are Muslim, the concept of caring for the environment is also closely related to the practice of Islam. Students are encouraged to reflect on Islamic teachings and their connections to the environment. Non-Muslim students are also encouraged to share their perspective on the environment based on their religion.

The six pillars for sustainable development embedded in the revised course are:

1. Learning to know- Understanding the concepts of outdoor education, the principles and appropriate procedure in doing outdoor activities (camping, kayaking, abseiling, etc.) about environment education (environmental justice). The target outcomes of technical or interpersonal skills, connection to the environment, or personal development ring is directed at creating a more socially equitable and just world (social justice).

2. Learning to be During outdoor activities like kayaking, camping, and orienteering, students are trained as a classroom community. They also exposed to survival skills and safety technique while conducting outdoor activities. This could lead to students' self-actualization, self-understanding, self-regulation and cultivating a sense of being versus having.

3. Learning to do-- Students will become familiar with different outdoor activities including the safety technique, rules and procedures during experiential activities. The activities will require students to recognize the benefit of outdoor activities and the impact it creates to learners.

4. Learning to live together sustainably---Through this course, students are treated equally without gender bias and racist. This could lead to a peaceful and non-discriminatory society and human co-existence with the natural world. Experiential education may continue to utilize contrived challenges to promote value formation, as well as social and individual growth and development.

5. Learning to transform oneself and society--Throughout the activities, students are encouraged to maintain the cleanliness of the environment. Students are exposed to environmental issues, such as open burning, pollution, and waste management, during outdoor activities. These experiences are more appealing when safety and the meeting of physiological and emotional needs are taken for granted. Create a caring society. Since this course prepares future sports science teachers, it is hoped that

they can impact future students/generations on the importance of outdoor education.

6. Learning to give and share--Learning activities are meant to be shared with other students through e-learning. This course also promotes equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all. Students will be introduced with aid wilderness and survival skills. One of the topics, Kayaking, requires learners to organize kayaking sessions with primary/secondary school students. Many students also volunteer as facilitators for outdoor programs, team-building activities, and camping expeditions organized by schools and student organizations.

In Efs, ten sustainability competencies are recommended for integration into teaching. For outdoor education, we realized that some are highlighted during learning, such as these:

Cross-cultural understanding

For example, resolving issues that involve managing outdoor activities according to the correct procedures and principles in a multi-racial society like Malaysia.

Connectivity

For example, interdisciplinary courses on the knowledge of waste management and the principles and theories of teaching and learning in the subject "Teaching Methods in Sports Science Education"

Critical reflection

For example, students will provide reflections based on the experiences they gain from managing outdoor activities, such as the challenges faced by learners during the course tasks. The reflection is lacking on sustainability issues they encounter during outdoor activities and considers their role in addressing these issues. This deficiency should be given close attention in the future.

Once the course information has undergone the deconstruction process, the reconstruction process follows with the development of a set of modules to guide instructors on how to integrate the three selected SDG themes with ICT support. The themes from SDG 3 Good Health and Well-being, SDG 6 Clean Water, and SDG 13 Climate Action need to be carefully integrated with existing topics in the teaching and learning activities. One of the Course Learning objectives is to emphasize the related general principles of outdoor education and environmental situations that pose threats to humans in terms of pollutants and human hazards. For this objective, the dominant key concepts are Authentic experience in outdoor education and environmental awareness issues. An active learning activity was designed as follows:

1. Students are given the option to select several situations related to the topic they are studying.
2. Within 30 minutes, students must find information related to the activities assigned in pairs.
3. They are required to create a mind map using existing applications, such as mind mapping software. This mind map must be completed within 30 minutes.
4. Through the lucky draw method, the selected couple must present their task within 5 minutes. The question session is then open to all students via the hot seat method.

This particular activity adopts the CARE methodology to incorporate the six pillars of learning, 10 sustainable competencies, and pillars of sustainability. Although it was not fully tested on students, most phases of the DREAM methodology were carried out. Before intervention, students were required to provide their learning style and personality profile by responding to the pre DREAM survey. Once they had completed the learning activities, which were conducted both synchronously and asynchronously, they responded to the post-DREAM survey. In this survey, their perceptions about related SDG issues were collected.

Along with other assignments, the students were given three assignments whereby they have to develop 3 concept maps as follows:

Assignment 1 (Individual)

Create a concept map using Lucidchart or a similar application to relate a few selected Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Try to produce at least 25 concepts with the central concept as “The Relationship between SDGs”. Please submit in pdf format to: <https://bit.ly/35C8ARn>.

Assignment 2 (Group)

Share your Assignment 1 with your group members. Redesign the concept map to incorporate all the ideas shared. Submit the concept map to: <https://bit.ly/3DEUFH2>.

Assignment 3 (Group)

Create a concept map with at least 30 concepts using Lucidchart or similar applications to picture your knowledge and understanding on how to achieve one SDG that has been assigned to your group. Submit in pdf file to: <https://bit.ly/3K82BCY>.

A sample of concept maps created individually by Student A and B are depicted in Appendix C and Appendix D. Student A used 28 concepts with 36 links while student B used 26 concepts with 30 links. Both students collaborated to create another concept map illustrating the relationships between SDG concepts as outlined in Appendix E. For this map, they developed 36 concepts and 45 links. The same pair of students chose climate action, an SDG embedded in the revised course, as the topic for creating the figure in Appendix F, submitting it as part of Assignment 3. They successfully created a well-structured concept map on climate change utilizing concepts 31 and 30 links. All the links were not labeled. All links and concepts were appropriate, enabling them to acquire a good understanding of various SDGs and how these concepts should be connected with each other. Not only that, but they were also able to create all concepts using digital applications.

Overall, student participation in the concept map activity was poor. The 60 students were assigned to groups of three members to complete the group assignments. Only seven individual students submitted Assignment 1, 4 groups submitted Assignment 2, and only one group submitted Assignment 3.

Findings, Discussion, Reflection

To accomplish this project, the trainees underwent a training program that adopted the Capacity Building Model by Makrakis (2006). During the training, the Decore+ methodology and the Dream methodology, along with principles of the SDGs, EfS, and SD, were introduced. During the training, Decore+ was applied to revise the Outdoor Education course, facilitating the deconstruction and construction process. A well-structured set of four modules was developed, which maps the learning objectives, learning outcomes, and learning activities, supported by active learning and the application of ICT. For the learning activities, the elements of sustainable justice, learning pillars, and sustainable competencies are embedded. Both internal and external evaluators reviewed the revised syllabus; however, in the case of Outdoor Education, there is little to be refined. Thus, the revised curriculum can be adopted for implementation, which can subsequently be evaluated using the Dream methodology.

Our experience in completing all the tasks to fulfill the requirements of the ICTeEFs project has been challenging. The transformation from the original curriculum to the revised curriculum, its implementation, and its evaluation are a lengthy process with several challenges. Although the faculty management has been very supportive of this project from the outset to the present, not all academics involved were willing to cooperate. The course owner did a wonderful job deconstructing, reconstructing, and constructing the course. Due to the pandemic, the course has not been offered for 2 years. It is currently offered, but unfortunately, the panel of Sports Science is facing a shortage of qualified staff to teach this course, as the one who used to teach it has retired. The panel, through faculty management, was able to secure someone outside the faculty with a background in outdoor education to teach for the semester. From our lengthy discussion, he was not ready to implement the new revised curriculum. After discussing with the coordinator of the sports science program, the project manager at this institution was permitted to work with students to run 4.5 hours of the SDG program through 2 online meetings. Since this program is outside the requirements of their course, the 60 students were not sufficiently committed. More than 50% of the class attended the first meeting, while only 25% attended the second. Consequently, the data collected were not sufficient to support strong claims.

Although most activities in the module were not completed during the 4.5-hour program due to time constraints, the students also participated in two other courses that are part of this ICTeEFs program. After all, their exposure to SDGs is comprehensive throughout the three courses they enrolled in for the current semester. The 2 other courses are Adapted

Sports and Teaching Methods for Sports Science, which have been revised using DeCore+.

Sixty students who enrolled in the course were requested to join a 4.5-hour program conducted over two different days, designed to train them about SDGs related to their course. A couple of surveys were administered to the students. The results were shared in Appendices A and B. The purpose of the first survey was to determine the general learning style, as well as students' behavior in using ICTs, which was shared with the students prior to the program. The second survey was administered immediately after the program had been completed. Thirty students responded to the first survey, while only eight responded to the second survey.

After all, the effort in implementing the revised Outdoor Education syllabus has been well worth it. Some students made an effort to complete the given assignments, despite knowing that this was merely a program that would not affect their grades at all. The majority of students refused to get involved, as the program is optional, and feel unworthy to spend time on something that is not part of the requirement for their program. They might think the program is helpful, but they may also consider other priorities that need attention. Undergraduates are often overloaded with work, and it can be challenging to balance their studies and personal activities. Program managers should also take a look at this issue.

Both in the previous and revised courses, experiential learning is manifested in outdoor activities, where students learn to work together as a team while also meeting people with different personalities in the community. Furthermore, they will engage in community service, which requires interpersonal skills, leading them to learn about cultural, economic, social, and environmental justice. From the outdoor experiences, they build awareness of the problems the local community is facing. The development of participatory video among students and the community will be a valuable learning experience, as well as bringing local issues to greater visibility. In this perspective, they share their digital skills with the community while the community provides knowledge about their life concerns. Together, they can work out a solution to resolve problems. Additionally, if the program is successful, the networking opportunities can be extended beyond the program's completion.

Assessment is an important component of any curriculum. In this project, the quality of the curriculum and its implementation, among other factors, were assessed using a post-survey. The responses reflected on what respondents perceived about their feelings towards sustainability issues. Results show that their feelings are dominantly favorable. To achieve global goals, it is not merely having concerns and a positive attitude. It has to advance to a higher level, involving a change in lifestyle and behavior. A good education should reach to this point. From a spiritual perspective, only people who genuinely fear God and sincerely observe religious practices will manifest their support for the SDGs, regardless of their condition. After all, prospering the earth and being good to humankind are basic teachings of all religions. Preaching about global goals should be done all the time

anywhere like the way we talk aggressively to our children on having good manners. Realizing all these, education for sustainable development should reach all institutions at all levels. There are not many other means to fight the disease of human beings like greed, selfish, ego centered and stubborn since their existence until today. What a happy place our world would be if all these diseases are eradicated. The integration of SDGs with ICT support for Outdoor Education is very promising. The project also prepared for other courses to be revised in a very systematic manner through Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006) the DEcore+ methodology, the Dream methodology along with principles of SDGs, EfS and SD were introduced. The templates for deconstruction and reconstruction together with the instruments to evaluate learners before and after intervention are all useful tools that can be applied in other courses. Thus it is recommended that this project be extended to other faculties, institutions and schools to duplicate what has been accomplished with Outdoor Education Course. The advantage is that the original structure of the course can be maintained thus it is not necessary to request permission from stake holders to revise the accredited courses. In the Malaysian context, the requirement for adopting Excel that requires community service will be fulfilled.

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Appendix A Results of Survey 1

Part 1--Demography

1.1	Gender	%
	male	45.3
	female	54.7
1.2	Year of Study	
	Year 1	33.1
	Year 2	66.5
	Year 3	0.2
	Year 4	0.2
1.3	Age	
	21 years old	20.9
	22 years old	32.4
	23 years old	7.9
	Less than 21	10
	More than 23	28.8
1.4	Ethnic	
	Malay	87.6
	Chinese	2.9
	Indian	5.8
	Others	3.6
1.5	Residential location	
	Urban	52.5
	Rural	46
	Others	1.4

Part 2 Internet usage

		Frequent (%)	sometimes (%)	Not so frequent (%)	Never (%)
2.1	Getting information from the web	40.3	38.8	19.4	1.4
2.2	Using statistical tool	4.3	30.9	46	18.7
2.3	Using communication	29.5	52.5	15.8	2.2

	tools								
2.4	Using presentation tools	70.5	22.3	3.6	3.6		kepala saya	ideaden gan lantang atau senyap	
2.5	Using e-learning platform	65.5	23	7.2	4.3				
							44.1	22.4	33.6

Appendix B Results of Survey 2

Purpose of Survey: To determine the students' attitude towards SDGs after implementing the intervention

Part 3 Personal lifestyle

		Agree (%)	Moderately agree (%)	Disagree (%)
3.1	I enjoy doing new things	76.3	20.9	2.9
3.2	I love to do well when working	82.5	14.7	2.8
3.3	I will think carefully before making decisions	73.4	23.1	3.5
3.4	I make quick decisions	24.5	69.2	6.3
3.5	I love challenges	52.4	43.4	4.2
3.6	I love being outdoor and life	80.4	16.1	3.5
3.7	I do not take actions immediately	40.6	53.8	5.6

Part 1 Demography

	Item	%
1.1	Gender	
	male	80
	female	20
1.2	Have you heard before about SDGs?	
	yes	100
	no	
	If yes, tick the sources you have heard SDGs	
	At Secondary school	20
	At University	80
	On TV	
1.3	On radio	
	From friends	
	Via the internet	40
	In the newspapers	20

Part 4 Learning Style

	Agree (%)	Moderately agree (%)	Disagree (%)
I prefer to Read		Talk	Do physical activities
	20.3	20.3	59.4
In school I learn better by Reading		Listening	Doing hands-on activities
	16.8	23.1	60.1
I prefer to become a thinker		speaker	Person who acts
	30.1	11.9	58
During study for tests, it is most effective if Baca dan gambarkan maklumat		sayaMembaca dan menyebut	Serlahkan, tuliskan danmenyebut

Part 2 Feelings towards Sustainability Issues

Table: Part 2 Feelings towards Sustainability Issues

Assess the rate of your feelings on the following	Scale of Measurement (%)				
	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neither agree or disagree	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
1. Everyone ought to be educated in how to live sustainably.	20			40	40
2. Empathy for people who are discriminated and face unequal opportunities.	20			20	60
3. Access to ICTS can strengthen global partnerships for	20			20	60

The Adapted Sport Education Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing it Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

The Asia-Pacific region has experienced some of the most devastating climate disasters of recent decades, with severe consequences for human well-being. Many scientists believe that there is a link between the increase in natural disasters in Asia and the Pacific and anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. Support from teachers at all levels is essential for taking action by integrating Education for Sustainability (EfS) into their educational activities, with the hope of supporting the development of more sustainable citizens. Our current project aims to develop an ICT-based capacity-building program for employed teachers and teacher trainers, enabling them to utilize innovative teaching methods and pedagogies focused on sustainability education. In this paper, we will report on how an Adapted Sports course underwent revision by employing frameworks that include the Decore+ and DREAM methodology. According to the results of the updated curriculum, students demonstrated significant improvement in terms of awareness, attitude, and conduct, which enabled them to become more sustainable citizens. It is recommended that more undergraduate courses undergo curriculum changes to integrate the SDGs, leveraging the use of ICTs.

Introduction

In recent decades, we have witnessed economic development leading to the excessive depletion and degradation of natural resources (Makrakis, 2014; 2021). Poor management in economics suggests that our education systems are failing to produce consumers, leaders, and decision-makers who can foster a sustainable society, environment, and economy (Makrakis, 2011). Therefore, much attention should be paid to education at all levels, especially tertiary education, as Corcoran and Wals (2004) note that the magnitude and scope of the negative effects of university-educated people on the natural systems that support the Earth are unprecedented.

Many advocates of sustainable development believe that education is a crucial factor in promoting sustainable well-being, and increasingly, more people are referring to themselves as sustainable citizens. Sustainable citizens are those who adopt Aristotle's eudaemonic well-being, which contradicts hedonic well-being driven by unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). The transformation of human behavior towards a sustainable citizens' attitude requires that they embrace the concept of sustainable justice developed by Makrakis (2006; 2017), which forms the four pillars of sustainable development: environment, society, economy, and culture. Education can play a crucial role in ensuring that students acquire this concept, so an appropriate curriculum is necessary to achieve this goal.

For several years, many efforts around the world have been invested in environmental education, but unfortunately, little has been done in environmental action. It is not enough for students to be aware of and have a positive attitude towards environmental issues; it would have a more significant impact if they could demonstrate some positive actions. We need to educate citizens about sustainable ways of thinking, being, and living (Sterling, 2001; Makrakis, 2012; Malik, 2018). Educators need to design quality programs that support the

SDGs, going beyond lectures to explore innovative pedagogies such as role-playing, hands-on science, and problem-based learning (Tilbury, 2011; Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015, 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021). Educators, who are the key actors in promoting education for sustainability, should seriously engage in this direction as they are recognized as agents of change for society. A successful project, Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013, 2014), involves training teacher trainers to transform their frames of reference in order to achieve sustainability goals and targets.

In 2021, the Malaysian Ministry of Higher Education launched the Excel (Competency-Based Education Landscape) framework, which focuses on competence-based education and experiential learning methods through four core areas. The four cores are industry-driven experiential learning (ideal) and community resilience experiential learning (care), research-inspired experiential learning (actual), and personalized experiential learning (Poise). The establishment of Excel aims to further strengthen the implementation of Malaysia's Education Development Plan (Higher Education) 2015-2025 while nurturing lifelong learners, innovative entrepreneurs, creative practitioners, and agents of change. Embedding the SDGs in undergraduate courses is undoubtedly in line with the pedagogical inspirations that place the infusion of the SDGs in the right place, resulting in holistic and highly skilled graduates. Once Excel is fully implemented in higher education institutions, community services aimed at achieving the SDGs will increase.

The ICTeEfS project

The Asia-Pacific region has experienced some of the most devastating climate and environmental disasters of recent

decades, with significant consequences for human well-being. At the same time, the climate in the region is changing. Temperatures were, on average, higher but also more variable and extreme. Precipitation was also more variable and extreme. Scientists argue that there is a link between the increase in natural disasters in Asia and the Pacific and anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. Asian policymakers should no longer wait but protect their citizens by raising awareness of human-caused environmental threats, and everyone is responsible for behaving more sustainably. The support of teachers at all levels is essential to take action by integrating EfS into their teaching. Teachers in Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam should receive professional training, starting with the reconstruction of teaching programs at the faculty of education. ICT-based programs are the way forward, as the role of ICT in education is promising. Furthermore, Malaysian institutions have sufficient infrastructure to support ICT-based activities. Compared to many other nations, Malaysia has a stable Internet infrastructure that supports educational activities. Moreover, higher institutions have computer laboratories that are equipped with facilities for teaching. What is needed is careful planning of methods to integrate the SDGs with ICT support into the curriculum. The Malaysian education system and its institutions at all levels play a pivotal role in instilling the spirit of sustainable development (SD) in its citizens, protecting the earth and the well-being of humanity from destruction and disruption due to current global developments. Due to the potential of education to drive individual and societal change, Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is implemented in the Malaysian education system through its two plans – the Malaysian Education Plan (Preschool through Secondary) and the Malaysian Higher Education Plan (Tertiary). The concept of SD has been so misunderstood by many that it has focused primarily on environmental justice, with little attention given to social and economic justice. Gender equality, sustainable economic activity, poverty reduction in society, and other critical areas of social and economic sustainability must be instilled in students through a strong ESD curriculum. Therefore, the curriculum for future teachers should be designed in a way that minimizes this gap so that teachers are prepared to implement ESD more holistically. Some of the early efforts to push SDGs into schools locally are shared in the work of Kavitha (2012) and Zaleha et. al (2014).

Our current project aims to develop an ICT-based capacity-building program for employed teachers and teacher trainers, enabling them to utilize innovative teaching methods and pedagogies focused on sustainability education (EfS). This project, also known as ICTeEfS, is funded by the European Commission's Erasmus Capacity Building program in the field of higher education for the period 2019-2022. The more specific objectives are:

1. Support the development of teaching faculties in partner universities to align curriculum, teaching, learning, and research in the field of sustainability education.
2. Capacity building for academic staff in faculties of education, enabling them to contribute to the development, implementation, and evaluation of a comprehensive teacher-

- training program using ICT on education for sustainability.
3. Develop a practical, cost-effective, decentralized, multiplicative, and innovative in-service teacher training program, enabled through blended learning, that focuses on integrating education for sustainability into school curricula.
4. Development of innovative teaching, learning, and curricular materials in the form of a multilingual electronic toolkit addressing the integration of education for sustainability into teaching, learning, and the curriculum.
5. Develop an Eurasian ICT-supported sustainability education network to enhance ICTeEfS collaboration and the reproducibility of outputs and results produced.

This collaboration includes eight other institutions from Malaysia, Vietnam, Indonesia, Greece, and Cyprus in addition to Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. There were no ongoing initiatives to incorporate the SDGs, utilizing ICTs, in the School of Education under the Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities. Since producing future teachers is our primary business, this endeavor is crucial to modernizing the curriculum to meet the demands of the global war. The fifth objective is worth mentioning as networking between countries involving exchange and sharing of knowledge would be a means to resolve global complex issues in particular on how together we can effectively reach SDGs.

The Adapted Sports Course

When Malaysia as a whole adopted the SDGs, a plethora of new legislation began to emerge. To ensure students' health and wellbeing and to promote equity, it is essential to include all students in one sport and to encourage physical activity for all. As a result, kids with special needs are also required to participate in sports. Several adaptive sports are now being introduced. Adapted sports are very new in Malaysia. The Olympic medals of some accomplished athletes inspire more people to participate, and sports are becoming more well-liked than ever. Since then, as the development of young athletes has increased, so has the demand for skilled coaches and educators.

The course, entitled SPPR 2872 Adapted Sports Education, is offered to prospective teachers who have registered under Sport Science Education. The course aims to provide knowledge about the characteristics and needs of individuals with special needs, as well as to gain experience in organizing physical activity, exercise, and sports programs that are tailored to their needs. Students discuss the principles of conducting physical activity, exercise, and sports for individuals with special needs. The characteristics of individuals with special needs should be identified and understood in order to design programs that align with their existing capabilities. Individual needs and unique capabilities must be understood and assessed in developing individualized educational plans related to physical movement. Individuals with special needs should be encouraged to engage in physical activity and sport and achieve multiple goals that may be deemed impossible. Special programs according to the unique needs of individuals are essential to achieve the desired goals. Students are required to organize simulation games, physical activities, exercises, and sports for individuals with special needs. Students also discuss current issues related to

individuals with special needs and their participation in sports. At the end of the course, students should be able to apply the techniques of teaching, learning, coaching, and organizing simulation games for individuals with special needs.

The 3-credit course is designed for second-year prospective teachers. It is expected that by the end of the course, students will have attained the Course learning outcomes that align with the Program Learning Outcomes, topics, activities, and assessments, as depicted in Table 1. The first 7 weeks cover topics as listed in Table 2. For Semester 1, session 2018/2019, 55 students enrolled in the course. Since then, the course has not been offered due to the pandemic situation. The course is not suitable for full online delivery, as it is heavily reliant on outdoor physical activities. Now, it resumes in the current semester with 60 students enrolled. The main assessment methods are: mini-project: coaching sports for the blind (15%), simulation sports for a unique population (15%), Volunteer activity and assignment report, group assignment (30%), and final examination (40%). In addition, the teaching methods range from class lectures and discussions to practical activities, volunteerism, and cooperative learning. Like other courses in the institution, all lecture materials and activities are made available in e-learning in the form of online/synchroboze quizzes, surveys, e-forums, and assignment submissions. Besides that, other platforms for using ICT are also emphasized, whereby students have opportunities to use videos, digital games, and simulations in class that activate their interest in learning the course. UTM and other institutions in Malaysia are ICT-driven, as evidenced by many studies indicating that technology is the solution to various problems, with blended learning being emphasized (Kashefi et al., 2012, 2013).

Table 1 Alignment of Course Learning Outcomes, Program Learning Outcomes, Learning and Assessment Before Revision

Course Learning Outcomes	Program Learning Objectives	Teaching Methods	Assessment Methods
Discuss the principle of conducting games and related issues in adapted physical education and sport	Knowledge & Understanding	Lecture Cooperative learning	Final Exam
Discuss and analyze various types of physical activity/ex	Knowledge & Understanding	Lecture Discussion Practical activity	Final exam Mini project: Coaching sport for the blind

ercise/sports appropriate to the unique needs of each individual.	Practical Skills		
Plan appropriate educational activities, physical activity, exercise, and sports for individuals with special needs through simulation game activities.	Knowledge & Understanding Practical Skills Cognitive Skills Leadership, Autonomy & Responsibility	Lecture Practical activity	Game Simulation project
Engaging in volunteer activities to individuals with special needs	Knowledge & Understanding Cognitive Skills Interpersonal Skills	Lecture, Volunteerism	Assignment Report

Table 2 Topics for Adapted Sports Education Week 1 to 7

Week	Topic
1	1.0 Introduction 1.1 Adapted physical activity, adapted physical education 1.2 Motor development, perceptual-motor, and fitness for individuals with special needs 1.3 School Orientation Program
2	2.0 Adapted Physical Education in Malaysia 2.1 Related issues 2.2 Sports for special population in Malaysia
3	3.0 Sports for All 3.1 Paralympic 3.2 Special Olympic 3.3 Deaflympic

4	4.0 Sports Classification and Divisioning 4.1 Criteria for sports classification - Paralympic 4.2 Sports divisional structures – Special Olympics
5	5.0 Etiology of Impairment 5.1 Cognitive impairment 5.2 Sensory impairment 5.3 Physical impairment
6	6.0 Movement Measurement and Evaluation 6.1 MAND test 6.2 Movement ABC 6.3 Brockport Physical Fitness 6.4 Sport Education
7	7.0 Simulation games 1 7.1 Goalball 7.2 Rules and regulations 7.3 Game Competition

designed to minimize this gap, enabling them to implement ESD more holistically.

The Adapted Sports course has many strengths. This course aims to enhance critical thinking and communication skills among students through project-based learning. This is because these soft skills are important for 21st-century learners and pre-service teachers. In addition, issues on equality in sport (social justice), especially in Malaysia as a developing country, are raised throughout this course even though it is not explicitly stated in the list of content. Issues related to the lack of facilities and resources in providing equality to people with special needs are highlighted. Although the course has considerable potential for integrating SDGs and sustainable justice, documents supporting their explicit or implicit teaching are not available. The Sustainable Development Goals are embedded in this course. This is because the sustainability elements are not emphasized in the Malaysian educational context during the time the course was developed. SDG 10 focuses on reducing inequalities, which is a key objective of this course. Since it is not explicitly included, students are indirectly expected to grasp this idea through the projects they must engage in. However, throughout the course, the sustainability aspect can be discussed in the Volunteerism activity; yet, the element of sustainability does not appear in the course information. In this activity, students have the opportunity to assist someone who is physically impaired. To ensure that the prospective teachers are fully trained to implement education for sustainability, the revision of the course would need to focus on:

How to implement sustainable practices in adapted Sport Education?

How do you incorporate the human element and psychological aspects to ensure the Course is both physically and psychologically sound?

Bringing change to a curriculum is a complex activity that requires a sound framework. It is more challenging since bringing global sustainability to the current curriculum is something that the instructors have not been exposed. Many activities related to sustainability organized on campus are extracurricular, such as Recycle Day or Energy Saving Day. Attention is given to improving the environment, but little has been done to integrate the SDGs into classrooms that focus on the four pillars of sustainability.

Methodologies for Course Revision

A systematic process was carried out to revise the Adapted Sports curriculum. The review process begins with training the academic staff who own the course. Figure 1 shows a six-step capacity-building model for training academic staff to integrate sustainability into their courses, developed by Makrakis (2006).

The Rationale for Revision

Like other endeavors, Malaysia's education system and its institutions, from kindergarten to tertiary level, play a vital role in instilling the spirit of sustainable development (SD) among its citizens, protecting the biosphere and the well-being of humanity from destruction and disruption caused by current global developments. Due to the potential of education to drive individual and social transformation, Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is implemented in the Malaysian education system through its two projects: Malaysian Education Blueprint (Kindergarten to Secondary) and Malaysian Higher Education Blueprint (tertiary). In Malaysia, the concept of SD is primarily focused on environmental justice, with limited emphasis on social and economic justice. Much of the scientific research on sustainability conducted at the local level focuses on environmental issues, as exemplified by the studies of Kavitha (2012) and Zaleha et al. (2014). The social and economic components of sustainability have received little attention in Malaysian education due to a lack of understanding of the holistic meaning of sustainability. Sustainability has only been interpreted in a limited environmental context because educators and other stakeholders who designed the ESD curriculum have only limited exposure to the true meaning of sustainability and sustainable development. The mentality, according to which sustainability is limited to environmental factors, is also influenced by the cultural setting of Malaysians, who have prioritized environmental issues within the context of Sustainable Development (SD). Gender equality, sustainable economic practices, poverty reduction in society, and other critical areas of social and economic sustainability should be incorporated into students through a valid and assertive ESD curriculum to provide all Malaysian students with a comprehensive sustainability philosophy. Therefore, the curriculum for student teachers should be

Figure 1. A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

Step 1 involves collecting the didactic profiles of the trainees to be used in the action plan of Step 2, which will inform the formulation of specific training sessions. The third step involves implementing content-based training, which combines theory and practice in structured thematic units or modules. The learning achievements of the trainees are compared for the evaluation phase in level four with their didactic profiles acquired in level 1. The same evaluation process continues for the final recipients, who are the learners, by transferring their acquired skills and knowledge in the classroom (5th stage). A monitoring and improvement system is integrated at all levels, helping to maintain the proper functioning and facilitate possible improvements to the training process (sixth level).

To integrate the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into the course, we adopted the Decore+ method developed by Makrakis (2017), which comprises three processes: deconstruction, construction, and reconstruction. The framework illustrated in Figure 2 is an approach that considers living documents programs by accepting a process that focuses on the development of processing programs. The six processes in the Decore + are as follows:

1. **Diagnose:** Reflect on a) who we are, b) what we have (existing knowledge), c) where we want to go, and d) why we want to go there.
2. **Deconstruct:** Critically analyze the workings of personal perspectives and habits of mind, as well as the chosen program units/modules.
3. **Build:** gather resources, create ideas, and construct new meanings (perspectives).
4. **Rebuild:** Integration of newly constructed knowledge by the reconstructed frame of reference.
5. **Implementation:** Implementation of the reconstructed program unit/module complemented by service learning.
6. **Finalization:** Reflect and evaluate what has been learned and what has changed.

Steps 1 and 2 need thoughtful consideration of fundamental issues that help us comprehend our purpose for existing. These phases are frequently skipped and neglected since individuals are more focused on the operational aspect. Once Steps 1 and 2 are understood, the construction process becomes more meaningful since we know where to go next. The process of reconstruction involves incorporating ICT-driven SDGs, the six learning pillars, the ten sustainability competencies, and sustainability pillars. Stage 5, which involves service learning, is not novel for this course. The concluding part, which involves reflection and evaluation, is crucial and requires careful planning and the use of appropriate tools.

Figure 2: The Decore+ interaction. Makrakis (2017)

Next the DREAM (Diagnosis, Review/Reflect, Explain, Assess & Manage) methodology as shown in Figure 3 developed by Makrakis (2019;2022) was used to assess the revised course during implementation. For the diagnosis, data was collected to find out what the students bring to class before giving lessons. Then, while conducting the course, the instructor reviews, reflects and explains how the course went and how the students reacted to the materials and activities. Finally, at the end of the course, the instructor critically evaluated the course and worked to run the course more effectively. At this stage, the course instructor evaluates the students' portfolio, which is useful for informing the strength and weakness of the course as well as for thinking about what needs improvement.

Figure 3 The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

The Revision Process

In 2020, the Adapted Sports course went through a revision based on the DREAM methodology. A deconstruction process was conducted to assess the quality of the original curriculum. Analysis of the course involved answering a set of questions, and through this process, it was observed that most aspects of the curriculum are favourable. Thus, the majority of the curriculum can be maintained, and two concerns need to be addressed to ensure that EfS is effectively integrated into the classroom. First, not all elements of sustainable justice are stated explicitly in the learning outcomes. Social justice is dominant, but environmental and economic justice are not visible. In this course, social justice is manifested through the structure that promotes equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all (see some examples from the syllabus). Through this course, students are treated equally without gender bias among multi-racial students. Also, students will be exposed to the knowledge of planning and conducting games and related issues in adapted physical education and sport. They are also encouraged to engage in volunteer activities to individuals with special needs. The elements are silenced because it is not required in the program learning outcomes underlined by the Malaysian Qualifications Agency. If all these elements are explicitly documented, it will empower the curriculum.

The second concern is that sustainable development goals are hidden in this course. This is because the sustainability elements are not emphasized in the Malaysian educational context during the time this program was accredited. SDG 10 is about reducing inequalities which supposes to be transpire during this course. But, since it is not included explicitly, students are expected to be able to grasp this idea through the projects they need to engage. Throughout the

course sustainability aspect can be discussed in Volunteerism activity.

The course, prior to revision, has indirectly addressed the four pillars of justice —social, cultural, environmental, and economic justice —as well as the six learning pillars. The instructors were aware of this when the course was analysed using the Decore+ methodology. During the analysis, the course owner successfully mapped each pillar to appropriate learning activities. The unit/module topics and learning activities are closely related to real-life situations. However, the four pillars identified are not being taught or mentioned explicitly in the learning outcomes. It is true, based on the learning to know, that this course is capable of achieving all the four pillars of justice. The focus is about meeting the needs of individuals, which brings students to issues like equality, equity, and accessibility to sports among vulnerable groups. However, in the current structure of the course (since this is the deconstruction stage), the four pillars are limited to focusing on declarative knowledge rather than emancipatory knowledge, which requires students to understand the concept of adaptive sports. In this case, the environmental, economic, justice, and cultural aspects are not explicitly deliverable. It becomes the hidden curriculum for this course. The procedural knowledge focuses on different types of sports tailored to meet the diverse needs of people, considering their suitability and adaptability to their current conditions.

As the course was evaluated using Decore+, it was realized that the four pillars of sustainable justice are indirectly embedded in the course:

1. Environmental justice - paperless assignment submissions as assignments are uploaded in e-learning. In this course, students learnt how environmental factors are capable of modifying the structure of the games. For instance, for a person with limited mobility, environmental factors must be taken into account beforehand. This requires students' understanding about making the sport inclusive despite the barrier. However, the concept of inclusivity is not the core of this course. Focus is given more toward making the sport accessible from the perspective of cultural commentators rather than the vulnerable group themselves.

2. Social Justice - fair distribution of the learning materials (i.e, lecture notes) and submission of learning activities through e-learning. Adaptive sports enable students to understand that people with disabilities are given equal opportunities to participate in the same ecosystem, competing in similar sports. However, the discussion does not include the representation of sport as a social justice agency; instead, it only indirectly shows students how people with disabilities can compete in sports.

3. Economic justice - Students are equipped with stable internet infrastructure (i.e., hotspot and Wi-Fi connection), which they can access to learn content inside and outside the classroom. Additionally, through the use of online learning materials, students, regardless of their socioeconomic status, are afforded equal access to educational resources. Indirectly, students also learnt.

4. Cultural justice - Allow students to voice their opinions and ideas that are relevant to their experiences and take ownership of their knowledge development. Participation in recreation for vulnerable groups is the image portrayed by this course. The syllabus does not cover discussion on the right for disabled person to sport, the importance of being part of the sport or how the community is denying the rights of people with disabilities in sports

In addition, the six pillars of learning are embedded as follows:

1. Learning to Know – The course content, as listed in Table 1, outlines the knowledge and understanding students need to acquire in the first half of the course. Knowledge and understanding of various topics touch all four course learning outcomes. Since their knowledge will be assessed through examinations as well as other forms of assessment, coupled with diversified teaching methods, it is hoped that the knowledge related to adapted sports will have a long retention period, enabling its application in their teaching careers.

2. Learning to be students involves being fully immersed in learning activities, as students are given problems that exist in real-world contexts. This could lead to students' self-actualization, self-understanding, self-regulation, and the cultivation of a sense of being versus having. Students are assigned a task based on the outcome, which requires them to engage in volunteer activities. The activities take place at the disability centre where the students usually provide sports rehabilitation services. From the project, they learned the actual role sports are capable of playing in changing human motivation in life, including the quality of life. Example: Mini project: coaching sports for the blind

3. Learning to do: Students will manage outdoor activities that are suitable for individuals with special needs. This activity requires student to translate their knowledge about adaptive sports during their design stage. Students were asked to design activities that could meet the needs of various disability groups. Example: Coaching long jump for individuals with visual impairment

4. Learning to live together sustainably--Through this course, students are treated equally without gender bias, racism, and individual abilities. This could lead to a peaceful and non-discriminatory society and human coexistence with the natural world.

5. Learning to transform oneself and society — Awareness of sustaining a healthy lifestyle for a diverse community, including individuals with special needs. Perspective transformation - engage in critical reflection on learners' experiences throughout the project. Values clarification emphasizes universal values such as being helpful, working together productively, being honest, and caring.

6. Learning to give and share: Learning activities are designed to be shared with others regardless of their abilities. The activities involved in outdoor education should be fairly shared with others to encourage individuals with special needs to engage in physical activity and sports and achieve multiple goals that may be deemed impossible. Students can engage in volunteer activities with individuals who have special needs. This course also promotes equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all. Students will also be exposed to the knowledge of sustaining a healthy lifestyle in a diverse community, including individuals with special needs

Besides learning pillars and sustainability justice, EfS recommends the infusion of ten sustainability competencies. Examples of how these competencies are embedded for Adapted Sports are as follows:

Critical thinking

For example, finding solutions to issues that require organizing different types of simulation games, physical activity, exercise, and sports for individuals with special needs. Students also discuss current issues related to individuals with special needs and their participation in sports.

Creativity

For example, taking the right approach, proposing innovative ideas, and being effective and efficient in solving issues required for organizing various types of simulation games, physical activities, exercises, and sports for individuals with special needs.

Cross-cultural understanding

For example, solving issues that require organizing different types of simulation game/physical activity/exercise and sports to individuals with special needs, while concerning on multi-racial society in Malaysia.

In the reconstruction phase, a set of four modules were developed. Each module addresses the learning objectives, learning outcomes, learning pillars, ten competencies, and SDGs based on a well-structured template. Two SDG themes

were explored to support specific learning activities, specifically SDG 5: Gender Equality and SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities. In addition, the six pillars of learning and the ten competencies were also incorporated into the activities.

Consequently, the revised curriculum needs to explicitly address the SDGs and sustainability justice as part of the reconstruction process, resulting in four refined Course Learning Objectives, also known as Course Learning Outcomes in the original course information. Course Learning Objective 2 and 3 are stated respectively as follows:

To discuss and analyze various types of physical activity/exercise/sports appropriate to the unique needs of each individual in an inclusive or non-inclusive educational setting (SDG 10)

To ensure fair treatment and meaningful physical activity/sport involvement for individual special needs regardless of gender, race, nationality, religion, and family income classification in maintaining a healthy living (SDG5)

Course Learning Objective 2 and 3 are mapped into these specific Course Learning Outcomes:

1. Discuss the important considerations in conducting a training program for blind athletes in a long jump event.
2. Plan a specific, progressive activities and training program for a blind athlete in a long jump event.
3. Organize and participate in a long jump competition for visually impaired athletes.
4. Promote an injury-free competition and reduce inequality of using technology
5. Reflect on ethical issues related to custom-made technology used in the Paralympics.
6. Reflect on your individual experience of being a coach and blind-athlete.

Obviously, the new course learning outcomes encompass not only social justice but also cultural and economic justice, which involve selecting and designing types of training programs for individuals with disabilities, organizing, participating in, and assessing the programs, as well as reflecting on ethics and developing professionalism as coaches.

The reconstruction of the course learning outcomes is extended to designing lessons such as this one:

Activity: Mini-project: coaching a long jump blind athlete

1. In pairs, each student is assigned a role as either a coach or a long jump blind athlete. The coach and the blind athlete (who was blindfolded during the long jump practice and training simulation). Students are required to research information related to sports coaching for blind athletes and plan suitable physical

activities to train them. In this activity, participants are required to document their activities (both as coaches and as blind athletes) in a logbook. Students are required to submit their log book and physical activity reports after participating in the long-jump competition.

2. Students are required to participate in the long-jump competition for visual impairment (competition among students in the class)

In another activity designed for students, they were required to complete group tasks by organizing sports simulation activities for special needs groups with physical limitations and visual impairments. The organization of these simulation activities necessitates that students plan sports events by adjusting the participants' movement abilities in line with the rules of the sports simulation game.

Students are divided into two groups: one acts as an organizer, while the other behaves as an athlete participating in organized sports. This group of students has organized one visually impaired sport, goalball, and two types of physically disabled sports, boccia and seated volleyball. During the planning session of this sports simulation game, the students who play the role of organizers must establish competition regulations that are customized and adjusted based on the type of sport being played.

Participants in the physical disability group's sports simulation game were given conditions that restricted their ability to move by focusing on either the upper or lower body. Participants in the visually impaired group sports simulation game are obliged to wear a blindfold while playing goalball. Competitors, on the other hand, must follow the competition's regulations and then compete by devising methods that take into account their physical limitations or visual abilities in order to win. After completing the assignment of organizing a sports simulation game, each group must provide a report on how the sports simulation was organized.

The use of concept maps to communicate complex ideas to illustrate the various concepts and inter-relationships between them was introduced. They were encouraged to create their own concept maps that portrayed the relationships between the 17 global goals. They started this activity individually and later formed another concept map in a group of three. Specifically, the students were given three assignments whereby they have to develop 3 concept maps as stated in the instructions as follows:

Assignment 1 (Individual)

Create a concept map using Lucidchart or a similar application to relate a few selected Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Try to produce at least 25 concepts with the main concept being "The Relationship between SDGs". Please submit in PDF format to: <https://bit.ly/35C8ARn>.

Assignment 2 (Group)

Share your Assignment 1 with your group members. Redesign the concept map to incorporate all the ideas shared. Submit the concept map to: <https://bit.ly/3DEUFH2>.

Assignment 3 (Group)

Create a concept map with at least 30 concepts using Lucidchart or similar applications to picture your knowledge and understanding of how to achieve one SDG that has been assigned to your group. Submit in pdf file to: <https://bit.ly/3K82BCY>

A few students took this challenge to produce concept maps individually, in pairs, or in groups of 3. In the case of a pair of students, each formed two separate concept maps associated with the SDGs. One successfully created a digital map with 28 concepts and 36 relationships, while the partner created 26 concepts and 30 relationships. They then combined their two concept maps to form a larger one with 36 concepts and 45 relationships. The final concept map, which they collaboratively worked on, displays 31 concepts and 30 relationships related to climate action. Figure 3 illustrates a concept map shared by the instructor during class to introduce the fundamental concepts of concept maps. The map illustrates the interrelationships of several concepts in adapted sports. Adapted sports, as the central concept, were linked to good health and well-being, as well as reducing inequalities. A user-friendly online application for creating concept maps can be explored within minutes. Creating and changing concepts, as well as linking them together, can be done quickly with a digital tool like this, compared to the manual method.

Figure 3 A Concept Map on Adapted Sports Discussed with Students

Discussion

Initially, the course owner felt overwhelmed by the numerous theories and methodologies associated with EfS, which flooded her mind. Most of the ideas were new to her, particularly the sustainability pillars, the pillars of justice, the 10 sustainable competencies, the 6 learning pillars, and the DREAM and CARE framework. The Decore+ exercise gradually brought into focus the need to transform a curriculum after spending several hours trying to answer related questions, engaging in numerous discussions, and conducting brainstorming sessions. Presentations and sharing from other partners, as well as input from the trainer, were

beneficial. Preparing the reconstruction module was painful, too. It took several months to complete. Careful planning and development were fruitful, as not many comments from the reviewer validated this output. Due to the pandemic, the implementation of this course was delayed because it required physical activities that needed to be closely monitored. Instead of enrolling in the course during their second year of studies, they must sit for the course during their third year. It would have been much better for the course owner, who is also the instructor, to implement the revised course immediately after the materials were developed. Since the course revision and development of modules were completed a year ago, the instructor needs to familiarize herself with skills and knowledge that she developed many months ago. The students were also overloaded with many high-level courses during their current third year of study, as many sports science courses require physical meetings, which were offered once the movement control order was lifted during the current semester. Therefore, considering the workload and psychological status of the undergraduates, the instructor did not rush to implement everything outlined in the module. Slow integration, rather than drastic change, is the correct move to ensure the course runs smoothly.

Compared to the original course topics, this course encompasses a wide range of skills, theories, and concepts. Adding SDG elements will increase the structure of the course. The course owner expressed concern that there might not be sufficient time to cover all the topics. It is suggested that these third-year undergraduates have already been equipped with research skills, enabling them to effectively learn through researching materials of interest with the support of collaborative teamwork. In other words, more opportunities to learn independently on some important topics through independent exploration. Thus, problem-based learning can be practical, as our research provides evidence that even school students are mature enough to cope with this learning strategy (Najihah et al., 2014).

Embedding sustainability in the university curriculum is a process and not simply adding existing structures. It requires the instructors to engage in increasing their global competence and sustainable citizenship. As activists, they should undergo a sustainable change in their mindset, attitude, and practices. Recognizing that global sustainability is a critical target, individuals should always consider ways to connect instructional activities with sustainable justice. In this course, the instructor is making an effort to cultivate sustainable citizens who will themselves become teachers within a few months. Important principles of EfS, including learning pillars, sustainability pillars, and 10 sustainable competencies, are incorporated into the lessons for the Adapted Sports Course. This is made possible with the systematic templates provided by the DeCoRe+ methodology and the DREAM framework.

Once we have strong beliefs that, through our efforts as teacher educators, we can bring a significant impact to our students, both directly and indirectly, to the communities, we should apply the new skills acquired to other courses. As in the case of the Adapted Sports course, the integration would not much change the course structure and certainly does not interfere with accreditation. Embedding SDGs is an art form

that enriches the course by connecting the subject of interest with real people and their lives. Most importantly, through a new curriculum that integrates the SDGs with the support of ICTs, more sustainable citizens, as well as SDG ambassadors, can be developed to make our planet a better place. Imagine how many students an instructor can transform into promising, sustainable citizens during their teaching career, which can last as long as 40 years.

It is very encouraging to see the SDGs being integrated with ICT support for outdoor education. Through the Capacity Building Model developed by Makrakis (2006), the DeCoRe+ methodology, the Dream methodology, as well as the principles of SDGs, EfS, and SD were introduced. The project also prepared other courses for alteration in a highly systematic manner. The instruments for evaluating learners before and after intervention, along with the templates for deconstruction and reconstruction, are all valuable resources that can be utilized in various courses. It is suggested that this programme should thus be expanded to include other universities, institutions, and schools in order to replicate the success of the Adapted Sports Course. The advantage is that the original structure of the course can be maintained; thus, it is not necessary to request permission from stakeholders to revise the accredited courses. In the Malaysian context, the requirement for adopting Excel, which involves community service, will be fulfilled.

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The Teaching Methods in Physical Education and Sport Science Course: Deconstructing, Constructing and Reconstructing Through the Lens of SDGs

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Abstract

The course "Teaching Methods in Physical Education and Sport Science" is a compulsory course that pre-service teachers must take in their university training program. The course prepares students for authentic teaching and learning in school during their practical teaching. This course was selected for revision according to the DREAM methodology, which stands for Diagnose, Review, reflect, explain, and Access, and was developed by Makrakis. The primary objective of this revision is to integrate several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into the tertiary education program, enabling students not only to develop environmental awareness and attitudes but also to take environmental actions. For this course, two Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have been addressed: SDG 4, Quality Education, and SDG 3, Good Health and Well-being. However, both SDGs are addressed implicitly in the course through the integration of teaching and learning activities. The DREAM methodology has led to the course being redesigned into four modules: "Understanding the Framework of Teaching in Physical Education and Sports Science Lesson Plan," "Microteaching," and "Reflection." After implementing the course, several challenges were identified, including the implicit nature of the delivery, which could mean that students would take the course solely to complete it rather than to develop their SDG awareness as intended. Another challenge is that pre-service teachers' centered activities require the instructor to be hands-on in order to provide effective feedback and guidance to students.

Introduction

Over the last few decades, we have witnessed numerous natural disasters, including tsunamis, floods, and earthquakes, in various parts of the world. Crime rates have also seen an overall increase, including those involving violent crimes and cybercrimes. We also observe a slow destruction and brutal exploitation of our earth's resources. The causes of these issues can be traced back to humanity's irresponsibility and greed in treating the Earth, as well as other living beings.

This has led to a significant imbalance between emotional, physical, and cognitive health in various countries. In some regions of the world, lack of welfare, low income, and desperation may have led to violent crimes and online scamming. Climate change, driven by the irresponsible management of Earth's resources, such as deforestation, has led to an increase in the Earth's temperature and depletion of the ozone layer, contributing to natural disasters like landslides, earthquakes, and forest fires.

Education is crucial for instilling in the world's nations the importance of social responsibility, not only among humans but also in the management of the earth and its other inhabitants (Sterling, 2001, 2010, 2013). The word Khalifah in Islam means 'protector and leader of the world' and refers to every human who walks this earth. The 17 SDGs promoted by the United Nations outline the roles of each khalifah. Tertiary education is

a critical setting for formulating an alternative development model because, at this stage, youngsters are not only impressionable but also at an age when they are developing their passions and gaining a deep understanding of the world around them. Therefore, the university bears a considerable burden to shape the new generation who are passionate about sustainable well-being. However, according to Makrakis (2011), consumers, leaders, and decision-makers are the products of educational institutions, and their impact on the environment is unprecedented (Corcoran & Wals, 2004; Little & Green, 2009).

Sustainable well-being is defined as being close to the eudaimonic well-being of Aristotle and is in stark contrast to the prevailing hedonic well-being, which is a result of unsustainable behaviors and modes of production and consumption (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2020). Sustainable justice (Makrakis, 2006, 2007), reflecting the four pillars of sustainable development —environment, society, economy, and culture —is important in learning to transform oneself and society as a whole. The distance between environmental attitudes and environmental action can be attributed to current teaching methods. In today's current environment, lecturing is still the most prevalent and popular method of teaching, although it is well documented that role-play, hands-on, and problem-based learning approaches are

much more effective in raising awareness and causing behavioral change (Makrakis & Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2015; 2016; Makrakis et al., 2021).

One of the significant challenges in today's higher learning institutions is to train lecturers, instructors, and educators who are critical and capable of transforming their frame of reference to achieve sustainable development goals and objectives, as revealed by a project called Reorienting University Curricula to Address Sustainability (Makrakis, 2013, 2014). This challenge is also relevant for classroom teachers at primary and secondary levels. It is well known that teachers are change agents and they can be the link for Education for Sustainability (EfS) approach to teaching, learning and curriculum (Biasutti et al., 2016;2018; Blake et al., 2013) and for turning schools sustainable (Zachariou et al., 2013; Kadji-Beltran et al., 2013).

Malaysia is also one of the countries involved in SDGs. However, efforts to incorporate the SDGs into the curriculum have encountered some constraints. Iyengar et al. (2021) highlighted three variables that hinder the implementation of the SDGs in education: an exam-oriented education system, the hierarchical nature of the training framework, and students' outcomes in ESD. Lee (2006) agreed that education in Malaysia is heavily centralized, as instructors are dependent on the information disseminated by the Ministry of Education to the school system. Instructors are confined from leading ESD exercises in their study halls.

Universiti Teknologi Malaysia is one of the tertiary education institutions selected to develop and disseminate awareness about the SDGs, ultimately aiming to bring about behavioral and attitudinal changes among its undergraduate students. SDG 3: Good health and well-being was selected as the central theme addressed in the undergraduate course "Teaching Methods in Physical Education and Sports Science." However, the overarching theme that drove the reconstruction of this course was Sustainable Development Goal 4: Quality Education. The students who take this course will eventually become sport or physical education teachers and are in critical need to become aware of the SDGs, their messages, and how to impact students.

Climate-related disasters in Asia's region are increasing in frequency and severity. One of the most visible consequences of Asia's rapid growth has been environmental degradation. Therefore, Asian leaders are growing increasingly concerned about their choices and how they impact the environment through the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and education for sustainability (EfS) activities, with a focus on the actual change makers—the teachers in the classroom.

A way to rise to these challenges through education for sustainability (EFS) is being implemented in Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam, among other Asian countries, which are providing training to address the challenges posed by ICTs,

climate change, and other environmental threats. By integrating ICT-enabled Education for Sustainability (ICTeEfS), faculties of education must reconstruct their programs and capitalize on the potential of such technologies in advancing EfS to all in-service subject teachers. Additionally, the rapid growth of ICT literacy and ICT infrastructure in PCs makes the integration of ICT in teacher education programs' curricula and in-service training inevitable. Hence, the integration of ICT as a subject or tool implies changes in teaching and learning and requires comprehensive and integrative planning of the ICT-enabled EfS in teacher education.

In light of the challenges and deficiencies, the proposed project aims to develop an ICT-enabled capacity-building program for pre-service teachers, enabling them to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies oriented towards education for sustainability (EfS). The ICTeEfS project has been funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ Capacity Building Program in the Field of Higher Education.

Overview of the course

The Teaching Method course is designed for pre-service teachers, with a curriculum intended to guide students in planning, designing, and implementing curriculum materials according to specific contextual needs. Before revision, this course was designed using Biggs's constructive alignment structure, as instructed by the Curriculum and Innovation Unit (CIDU) at Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. The course owner is responsible for determining the curriculum design, with the ultimate goal of helping pre-service teachers develop the skills to analyze curriculum materials constructively. Initially, the key content themes focused on declarative and procedural knowledge, which are the theoretical basis, skill, and understanding of concepts, principles, and techniques of teaching. The course owner collaborates with the other instructors in the curriculum design process. Within each phase of developing the teaching material, activities, and assessments, instructors are permitted to make adjustments to the weekly lesson, activity sequences, and participant structures. In brief, this course is designed to facilitate the acculturation of teaching practices in Physical Education and Sport Science

The course explores various teaching approaches in Physical Education and Sport Science at the secondary school level. Students implement the teaching approach in both theoretical and practical teaching sessions, utilizing a guided lesson plan to acquire teaching skills and professional competencies in an applied setting. These experiences enable students to develop positive teacher-student interactions within the teaching context for practical teaching and learning activities. Students are

required to reflect on their micro-teaching experience. At the end of the course, students can conduct practical teaching and learning activities in a simulated environment, applying the knowledge gained from the course.

The key content themes focus for this course covered the following areas:

- a) Physical Education and Sport Science Curriculum in Malaysia
- b) Lesson Plan
- c) Issues related to teaching activities
- d) Levels of Bloom’s Taxonomy
- e) Instructional Model in PE & SS I
- f) Instructional Model in PE & SS II
- g) Lesson plan for teaching practice
- h) Practical teaching sessions
- i) Teaching reflections

The number of students enrolled in this course is listed in Table 1. As this is a compulsory course, all students are expected to participate in and fully experience its learning activities.

Table 1: Number of students enrolled in the course

Semester	Number of students
Semester 20212022-1	55
Semester 20202021-2	87
Semester 20202021-1	65

This course was chosen simply because it is offered to pre-service teachers and was recently updated during the latest curriculum revision at the faculty level. Upon discussion, emancipatory knowledge is considered to be hidden rather than missing. The course owner does consider the conditions that

permit revocation or the building of new knowledge. To prioritize what is hoped for from pre-service teachers once they have learned about teaching methods, the training must be able to equip students with the knowledge to support their actions in the teaching practice. Once the course owner engages with ICTeEfs members, particular consideration on emancipation surfaces during the discussion. This brings the discussion to rethinking pre-service teachers’ agency as they enact the activities designed for them. The course owner agreed to the opportunity to reform the implementation without requiring changes to the curriculum structure. At the centre of the highlighting agency is the aim to change the cultural practice of teaching methods among sports teachers, which led to the possible process of deconstructing, constructing, and reconstructing instructors’ practice in course design.

Revising the Teaching Methods in Physical Education and Sport Science course

One of the key aspects of learning to become a teacher is being able to write a well-structured lesson plan while also knowing and effectively applying teaching strategies. One of the important activities is microteaching, which is conducted both inside and outside the classroom. Although the chalk and talk approach is not necessarily a concern for such an active and hands-on course, managing pupils' engagement is also important. This course enables students to explore various 21st-century skills, develop a standard lesson plan, and engage in microteaching (Figures 1 and 2). Another interesting approach employed in this class is public speaking, which includes the evaluation and preparation of speeches to enhance students' confidence and communication skills.

Figure 1: Outdoor microteaching

Figure 2: Indoor team teaching

The competencies chosen for this course have a broad definition and require the course instructor's interpretation. It is known as Program Learning Outcomes (PLOs), which students are expected to acquire upon graduation. Knowledge, for instance, only reflects the declarative knowledge that pre-service teachers possess about teaching methods. Apart from this, since the competencies are primarily developed within a content-

driven structure, the revision allows for realigning the knowledge with the six learning pillars and the 10 Cs.

It was agreed that no significant changes were made on the course learning outcomes. The proposed learning outcomes are possible to be (re)contextualized based on ICTeFFs needs when applied to particular situations. Hence the revised version fine tunes the original version into Course Content Learning Outcomes. The following are the original course learning outcomes:

1. Discuss, compare and evaluate teaching approaches that are appropriate with Malaysian current education setting.
2. Plan, develop and evaluate individual lesson plans and units of instruction.
3. Apply appropriate teaching approaches and adapt teaching strategies to different skill development stages and individual learning characteristics.
4. Reflect critically and constructively on individual own teaching practices as basis for improving educational outcomes.

While the following are the new course learning outcomes. The new course learning outcomes highlight the SDGs which can be addressed implicitly. They are SDG3: Good Health and Well-being and SDG4: Quality Education.

- a) **To discuss and compare** teaching approaches that appropriate with Malaysian current education setting (SDG4) - Week 1, Week 2, Week 3, Week 4, Week 5,
- b) **To plan and develop** individual lesson plans and units of instruction. (SDG3) - Week 9, Week 10,
- c) **To apply** appropriate teaching approaches and adapt teaching strategies to different skill development stages and individual learning characteristics. (SDG3) - Week 11, Week 12, Week 13, Week 14
- d) **To evaluate and reflect** on individual own teaching practices as a basis for improving educational outcomes. (SDG4) - Week 6, Week 7, Week 15

The following are the soft skills embedded in the course:

CS4: Ability to use technology in presentation

A3: Value (attach value and express personal opinions)

LL3: Patience for knowledge

The learning content is related to the 6 pillars of learning for sustainable development which are learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do, learning to transform oneself, learning to give and share. The following are the 6 learning pillars as addressed in the course.

1. Learning to know

Various concepts and principles of teaching theories, teaching lab / workshop subjects in Sport Science Education.

2. Learning to be

Developing individual capacity to be a critical sport teacher and practicing teacher professionalism. With this course, students must be able to understand the role teaching approaches as the interplay between teacher and students. With this, they are required not only to learnt on the theoretical knowledge about the teaching approaches, but to understand the philosophical assumption for each teaching approaches. There are three domain that become part of the national curriculum which are cognitive, psychomotor and affective. Thereby, in sport science, self-concepts, character and ability become the main focus for learning to be. This is hope to shift their paradigm from ‘teaching to play’ toward ‘learning through playing’.

3. Learning to do

Designing the lesson plan for theories, lab/workshop, and sport science subjects.

- what are the different epistemological approaches of teaching and the implications of them in curriculum development and pedagogy

4. Learning to live together sustainably

Actively engage different groups (teachers from sport science education) in completing projects/assignments and class activities.

5. Learning to transform oneself and society

Community engagement (short courses)

6. Learning to give and share (e.g. Create opportunities for sharing ideas and experiences and finding the best solutions). Online video-sharing on different teaching styles.

The 10’c as addressed in the course are:

Table 2: 10c’s addressed in the course

10’Cs	Description
Collaboration	Work with others in groups to analyze the current curriculum, design a lesson plan based on sport science. The process will involve conflict resolution; decision making; problem solving; negotiation; recognition and respect; listen, clarify, organize, participate; build positive relationships. Group work is also conducted during class discussion.
Communication	Interacting; communicating with a broader audience in microteaching. They need to justify, discuss, share, articulate communication with students during the teaching task. Public speaking.
Critical thinking	Finding the best teaching methods based on the teaching philosophy. Evaluate and suggest improvement for better teaching which involve dimensions of Critical Thinking and Problem Solving
Creativity	Create, design, imagine, invent, improve teaching plans with effective and creative teaching aids
Cross-cultural understanding	Interpersonal competencies: communication and awareness on teaching issues related to diversity - concern on multi racial society in Malaysia
Connectivity	multidisciplinary (the previous course used only basic pedagogy, related to technical content. In this course, integrating participatory video clip in lesson planning; Inter/cross-disciplinarity)
Critical reflection	Periodically reflections on teaching session in class and online

Critical consciousness	Raising consciousness for being active in the class and being aware of other people's and students' needs.
Constructing knowledge	Develop digital artifacts for empowerment, advocacy and capacity building. In this class, students need to develop lesson plans which are submitted digitally and can be used by other physical education teachers.

2. Students typically just have to design the lesson plan based on the pre-existing structure of the lesson plan. The inclusion of SDG3 is relevant to sport education syllabus in Malaysia that focus on wellbeing and health. Here SDG3 is brought in as additional content to draw student attention on global issues related to SDG 3 and how this information must be translated as learning outcomes.

SDG's addresses in the course

Blending the 6 learning pillars and 10C's with pre-existing outcomes requires mapping between them. This is because at the end of this course, students will only be assessed for these five outcomes. Thereby, adding to this must consider the possibility of adding weight to students' learning times. To solve this scenario, there are activities designed for this course which can be enhanced to meet the expectation for the 10'C. Gaps identified for this transformation effort are:

1. Institution values and ICTeEfs values of education for sustainability do not rhyme thus creating a conflict of interpretation.
2. The cultural context of implementing this course became the difficult choice because instructors must revamp their existing teaching materials to accommodate with the new interpretation of ICTeEfs. For example, students' learning time will be a burden to expand the learning activities for inclusion of SDGs.

Initial planning to revamp the direction and purpose of this course proposed to include SDG3 (Good health and wellbeing) and SDG 4 (Quality education) mapped to the course learning objectives with the 10Cs' competence to be emphasized during class activities and assessments. Students are required to develop lesson plans and conduct micro teaching based on knowledge gained from the four modules. Although instructor try to maintain different interpretation when enacting the modules, students were introduced to SDG3 and SDG4 through:

1. Consciously and critically underlying structure that permits the existing social structure revolves around teaching practices at school level. The discussion gravitates to how their views can lead to implication to practices and modification for better practices. (SDG4)

Methodology

The method that we use to embed sustainability in this course has been explained in Figure 2. This six stages capacity building model is for training the academic staff to apply the strategies in teaching so that the pre-service teachers are able to use innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogies orienting to education for sustainability (Efs).

Figure 2: A Capacity Building Model Makrakis (2006)

From Figure 2, the six stages capacity building model for instructors to apply in teaching for pre-service teachers in the course as the following steps.

1. Stage 1: The training focuses on the diagnosis of the didactic profile of every pre-service teacher
2. Stage 2: After the analysis of pre-service teacher's profiles, formulate an action plan for the specific training session
3. Stage 3: Follow the training content (action plan), which merges theory and practice and is structured in thematic units, or modules and considering the requirements and needs

4. Stage 4: The evaluation of pre-service teachers' learning outcomes compared to their initial profiles and the aims and objectives set in the action plan
5. Stage 5: The same process of evaluation is continued for the final recipients. The outcome and the changes of learners will be transferring through their acquired skills and knowledge to the classroom
6. Stage 6: A system of monitoring and upgrading is integrated across all stages that help to sustain the proper functioning and possible upgrading of the training process

For course revision to embed sustainability, the DeCoRe+ (Deconstruction-Construction-Reconstruction) is an approach that sees curricula as living documents by adopting a design process that focuses on transformative curriculum development. The six processes comprising DeCoRe+ is shown in Figure 3..

Figure 3: The DeCoRe plus interaction. Makrakis (2017)

For the revised course evaluation during the implementation process, the DREAM (Diagnose, review/reflect, explain, assess, and manage) methodology advanced by Makrakis (2023;2022) has been applied (Figure 4). As we can see, the processes cover the whole spectrum of the course, that is, what students bring in class before the implementation of the courses (Diagnosing), during the course (Reviewing/reflecting and explaining) and at the end of the course (Assessing and managing). In a way, the DREAM methodology reflects a critical action research process which aims not only to assess a course but more importantly to make whatever changes in order to improve it. Through the parts of the DREAM Methodology, the pre-service teacher guided by the course instructor creates a portfolio that he/she has to give back to the instructor at the end of the course. Consequently, the DREAM Methodology is part of the course requirements. The students' DREAM portfolios must be analysed by the instructor, and a report must be prepared for the whole class. The analysis of the DREAM portfolios will provide very important information that the

instructor and the students could discuss and find ways for improving the course.

Figure 4: The DREAM methodology (Makrakis, 2023)

Implementing the revised course does not come easy; however, expanding the curriculum design to communicate the four pillars (social, economic, cultural, and environmental) can be confounding since there is no consensus on what the course needs to deliver. The ambiguity, however, helps the instructor to seek more information on how the infusion into the existing structure can be made seamless. Here, SDGs are presented to students as an ideology that they need to understand as pre-service teachers. Sustainability concepts are justified by changing their role as teachers from being solely 'just teaching' to being responsible to society with a focus on the impact of activities related to sports, wellbeing and health issues.

The methodology used for this course is project-based learning via an online platform due to the pandemic. Students are required to develop lesson plans and instructional videos. The most challenging part for this course is that due to online learning, students have to use all available resources in developing lesson plans. For instance, as below:

Activity: Task-based learning

1. Students are given various tasks related to classroom time and management, physical education, wellness, and sports science.
2. Students are required to plan a lesson that is

- appropriate and address the scenario given to them.
- Students also need to include reliable practices that can relate or enhance good health and well-being among society/community in their lesson plan. (SDG3)

Here, this student chooses to leverage ICT for her usage and at the same time make sure that ICT is used as one of the resourceful artefacts for knowledge development. The proposed lesson plan used television and YouTube to learn about handball (*bola baling*) rules and the nature of games. The initiative to inject ICT usage in their proposed homework (*tugas pelajar*) can be related to the initiative taken by the instructor to ensure accessibility to learning. This is showing a good sign of change in a way the homework (*tugas pelajar*) is crafted to students.

Results

The updated version of this course now consists of 4 modules. The first module is entitled understanding the framework of teaching in physical education and sports science. This is addressed in the first few weeks of the semester. The key principles of module 1 are understanding on concepts, principles and techniques of teaching, Teaching methods, Teaching approaches, Physical Education, Sports science. In this module, students will learn about:

Unit 1.1: Introduction of School curriculum teaching program

Unit 1.2: Concept of Physical Education and Sport Science curriculum program in Malaysia

Unit 1.3: Level of Bloom's Taxonomy

Unit 1.4: Instructional Model in Physical Education and Sport Science

Students will conduct several activities such as critical review, brainstorming, public speaking consisting of prepared speech and impromptu speech.

Module 2 is entitled Planning, Developing and Organizing Lesson Plan. Since this course is about teaching methods, the lesson plan aspect is a very important component of the course (Table 3). What's more, it is also a vital preparation for students to go for teaching practice in the coming semesters. The key concept of the module is to develop and produce lesson plans for physical education and sport science sufficient and appropriate for classroom learning time setting. In this module, students will learn about:

Unit 2.1: To plan and develop individual lesson plans and units of instruction.

Unit 2.2: Organize lesson plans and units of instruction that are well-planned and align with the needs of the education environment.

Module 3 is Microteaching. Microteaching is also an important component that prepares students for actual teaching in school, namely in practical teaching. It represents the key concept of the course. The overriding aim of this module is to execute a developed lesson plan, implement proposed activities, and learn assessment skills to improve teaching skills. Figure 5 shows an example of indoor microteaching. In this module, students will learn about

Unit 3.1 Apply appropriate teaching approach and strategies that suit with all skill development stages and individual learning characteristics

Module 4 is reflection. Reflecting is an important part of being a good teacher as it helps them to identify their weaknesses and strengths. The aim of this module is to evaluate and reflect on individual own teaching practices as a basis for improving educational outcomes. Figure 6 shows the reflection activity that has been conducted by the instructor. At the end of this module learners will be able:

- To evaluate and reflect** on individual own teaching practices as basis for improving educational outcomes.
- Reflect** on own teaching practices as basis for improving educational outcomes.

In this module, the students will conduct, think-pair-share and gallery tour.

Table 3: The example of lesson plan (module 2)

MING GU	16	S U B J E K	P E N D I K A	Tandakan (√) pada ruangan berkenaan .
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			N K E S I H A T A N	STRATEGI PdPc	UNGA N	prestasi atlet	Nilai Murni			
				Pembelajaran Masteri				Sains Teknologi dan		
				Pembelajaran Berasaskan Inkuiri	√			Patriotisme		
TARIKH & HARI	29.03.22 / Selasa	MASA		Pembelajaran Berasaskan Projek				Kreativiti dan Inovasi dan		
				Pendekatan Teaching Games for Understanding (TGfU)				Keusahawanan		
				Pendekatan Bersepadu				Teknologi Maklumat dan Komunikasi dan		√
TING KATA N	5	KEHADIRAN	Aplikasi Teori Kecerdasan Pelbagai(TKP)			Kelestarian Global				
			Pembelajaran Secara Kontekstual			Pendidikan Kewangan				
TEMA	5.0 Pemakanan sukan 5.1 Membezakan antara pemakanan dan pemakanan sukan		ELEMEN KURIKULUM (EMK)			PETA PEMERINTAHAN (I-THI)				
TAJUK	Pemakanan seimbang untuk kesihatan dan prestasi atlet		Bahasa			Peta Bulatan				
STANDAR KAND	Membincangkan kepentingan pemakanan seimbang untuk kesihatan dan		Kelestarian Alam Sekitar			Peta Buih				
						Peta Berganda				
						Peta Pokok				
						Peta Dakap				
						Peta Alir				

<p>STANDAR D PEMBELAJARAN</p>	<p>Pada akhir pelajaran , murid boleh :</p> <p>5.1 Pelajar dapat membezakan pemakanan yang sihat dan pemakanan sukan untuk atlet .</p> <p>5.1.1 Pelajar dapat menerangkan pemakanan yang seimbang untuk kesihatan dan prestasi atlet.</p>			
<p>KRITERIA KEJAYAAN</p>	<p>Murid berjaya sekiranya dapat</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Membezakan pemakanan dan pemakanan sukan. 2. Menjelaskan makanan yang seimbang untuk kesihatan dan prestasi atlet. 		<p>antara pemakanan dan pemakanan sukan mengikut kefahaman.</p> <p>Ø Guru menilai dan memberi maklum balas terhadap hasil kreativiti murid.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Murid dan guru bersoal jawab dan perbincangan tentang pemakanan seimbang untuk kesihatan dan prestasi atlet. 	
<p>RINGKASAN AKTIVITI</p>	<p>Set Induksi</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Murid disoal maksud tentang pemakanan dan pemakanan sukan. 2. Pembelajaran /Aktiviti: <p>Googlemeet: Murid diberi penerangan tentang pemakanan dan pemakanan sukan .</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Murid buat aktiviti: team projek(peta minda) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ø Setiap kumpulan membina peta minda mengenai perbezaan 		<p>Penutup/Rumusan:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Murid membuat rumusan/refleksi topik yang dipelajari. 	
			<p>REFLEKSI</p>	<p>Pada sesi pengajaran kali ini seramai 23 orang pelajar dapat menghadiri kelas dan dua pelajar tidak dapat menghadiri kelas disebabkan alasan tertentu. Saya berasa kurang gembira dengan keadaan ini. Pada akhir kelas mereka diberikan soalan kuiz online untuk dijawab. Akibat kekangan data internet yang mungkin dialami oleh segelintir murid maka saya</p>

	memberikan masa sehingga hari Jumaat ini untuk mereka menjawabnya.	
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Figure 5: The implementation of module in microteaching indoor (module 3)

Figure 6: Reflection activity (module 4)

Discussion

The challenge in conducting this course is to allow students to embrace the messages of the SDGs which are quality education and good health and well-being. Students may be motivated more towards completing the goals of the course and getting good grades rather than fully embracing the messages of the SDGs. This is because the delivery of the SDGs is implicit and not well elaborated as reported in the module developed.

The instructor also had to continuously interfere in the teaching process although the role is as facilitator. For example, in one of the microteaching sessions which involve team-teaching. The two pre-service teachers who presented, selected to teach about CPR specifically what, when and where CPR. Although much of the content was delivered, the instructor gave many comments on the pedagogical aspect of the delivery. In part, the art of questioning was not mastered yet by the pre-service teachers, controlling students during student-centred activities, and the set induction was not related specifically to the content. Therefore, SDG4: Quality Education is still in the process of being achieved by the student.

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